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Leonardo CALCAGNO

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**Argentina's social security system: a dynamic
microsimulation model for projecting its sustainability,
adequacy and redistributive impact**

Thèse dirigée par :

Alexis DIRER

Professeur, Université d'Orléans

Anne LAVIGNE

Professeur, Responsable des études au COR

RAPPORTEURS :

Hippolyte D'ALBIS

Directeur de recherche, CNRS

Didier BLANCHET

Expert de haut niveau, INSEE

JURY :

Vera CHIODI

Maître de Conférences, Université Paris 3

Gijs DEKKERS

Analyste de politiques senior au Directoire
Général; chercheur associé à l'Université de
Leuven, et Président de l'Association Inter-
nationale de Microsimulation

Muriel ROGER

Professeur, Université Paris 1

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General Introduction

Social security is a key component of the functioning of developed and various developing economies. Its goal is to protect against the vagaries of life, so as to "ensure the livelihood of all citizens, in all cases where they are incapable of earning it through their work", as put by the French National Resistance Council on March 1944 (Conseil National de la Résistance, 1944). There are four broad situations where individuals may find themselves excluded from the labour market, which represent four kinds of risks covered to various degrees by the welfare state. First, the retirement component of social security seeks to insure against the longevity risk, that is, of living up to an age where it becomes impossible to keep working. Then, the unemployment benefits system seeks to insure wage-earners against the risk of losing their job, and ensure their livelihood in that case. After that, the health insurance scheme covers the risk of illness, funds the cost of treatment and bridges the missing income of those who temporarily cannot work. A similar but usually separate branch of social security, labour hazards, seeks to compensate workers for accidents in the workplace. Finally, the family benefits branch of social security does not cover a risk *per se*. It subsidises families with children in order to ensure the latter's health, education and well-being, at an age where they are too young to work.

Social security institutions step in because the insurance market does not self-regulate to provide for the needs of those excluded from the labour market. As theorised by Polanyi (1944), the free market left to itself tends to reduce the labour force to a commodity, which can be freely bought and sold. Labour as a "fictitious commodity" is dangerous for society, "for the alleged commodity, 'labor power' cannot be shoved about, used indiscriminately, or even left unused, without affecting the human individual who happens to be the bearer of this peculiar commodity. In disposing of a man's labor power the system would, incidentally, dispose of the physical, psychological, and moral entity of 'man' attached to the tag." Thus, "to allow the market mechanism to be sole director of the fate of human beings (...) would result in the demolition of society" (Polanyi, 2001, p. 76). Nevertheless, there is no consensus on how these social security institutions should function, or to what extent they should replace market mechanisms. A liberal approach

to social security advocates for a limited welfare state on the grounds that it subsidises leisure and discourages labour supply. After all, the health and longevity risks can be insured through private schemes. Family and unemployment benefits, who do not cover insurable risks, are the result of political arrangements. The former are for instance low in the US (Ozawa, 2004), strongly means-tested and mostly limited to the Temporary Assistance for Needy Families (TANF). The latter have been *de facto* abolished in Argentina, as the maximum unemployment benefit has been barely adjusted with respect to inflation since 2002 and frozen in nominal terms between 2005 and 2016 despite double-digit yearly inflation figures.

Esping-Andersen tackles the debate on social security institutions by considering how they answer the fictitious commodity issue introduced by Polanyi. He indeed considers that the role of the welfare state, and thus of social security, is to "emancipate individuals from market dependence" (Esping-Andersen, 1990, p. 163) and "de-commodify" them. As such, he deems incorrect to take total social security expenditure as the standard for determining the size and depth of the welfare state. Instead, he maintains "the outstanding criterion for social rights must be the degree to which they permit people to make their living standards independent of pure market force. It is in this sense that social rights diminish citizens' status as 'commodities'." (Esping-Andersen, 2013). Grounded on this theoretical background, Esping-Andersen (1990) then establishes what has now become the standard classification typology of social security. He defines three worlds of welfare capitalism: the liberal, conservative and social-democratic worlds. This typology does not strictly refer to a concrete historical situation but can be used as a point of reference for the study of empirical cases. Each of these worlds mostly resort to a given set of methods. The liberal relies on market mechanisms; the conservative favours status-linked corporatist insurance; the social-democratic grounds social security on universalistic benefits funded but also earned by all residents. We will describe them more in depth below.

First of all, the liberal world tends to minimise the welfare state, limited to low means-tested benefits, and make social security mostly reliant on private welfare schemes. Esping-Andersen links this world to the residual welfare state as defined by Titmuss (1958), where "the state assumes responsibility only when the family or the market fails; it seeks to limit its commitments to marginal and deserving social groups" (Esping-Andersen, 1990, p. 162). A typical element of social security in the liberal welfare state are workfare programs, where benefits are means-tested, modest and conditional on work (Besley & Coate, 1992). As such, "entitlement rules are (...) strict and often associated with stigma; benefits are typically modest. In turn, the state encourages the market, either

passively - by guaranteeing only a minimum - or actively - by subsidizing private welfare schemes" (Esping-Andersen, 1990, p. 167). The liberal welfare world is therefore the one that "de-commodifies" workers the least, since social security benefits act as a last resort and modest safety net. Esping-Andersen puts forward Anglo-Saxon economies such as the United States, Canada or Australia as the clearest examples of liberal social security models.

In the case of retirement pensions, "the liberal model falls into an actuarial logic in which pensions are but the profitability of a free, enlightened and voluntary savings decision" (Lavigne, 2013, p. 7). This means liberal social security systems often favour Defined Contribution (DC) fully-funded pension schemes. In these, workers contribute a defined proportion of their income to private pension funds, who manage these funds. Upon retirement, they get a pension that depends on the market value of their accumulated financial assets. The future level of their pensions is thus not guaranteed, which means it is the pensioners that bear the financial risk. A good example of a liberal pension system is Chile. Since its 1981 full privatisation under Pinochet's military rule, there is a single compulsory fully-funded Defined Contributions pension system. The central government completes pensions that fall behind the minimum benefit (roughly equal to 175€ on August 2018¹ for pensioners under 70), thus subsidizing private pension funds who are not compelled to pay at least this minimum pension. It also provides a non-contributory means-tested "basic solidarity pension" (nearly 140€²) for people aged 75 or more with no pension. As a means of comparison, the legal minimum wage in Chile equals nearly 370€³. This shows the Chilean pension system offers a very modest and minimal protection for the elderly, who if they did not contribute to the private pension system when they were of working age do not get any benefit at all before age 75.

Secondly, the conservative world as defined by Esping-Andersen (1990) was founded by conservative reformers such as Bismarck, which is why it is usually called the "Bismarckian" social security regime in the literature. It follows a corporatist logic, where social security is strongly linked to the labour status and often managed separately by branch. It "[relies] on professional activity and [falls] within a contributory, egalitarian and insuring logic: social security coverage aims at compensating a loss of professional revenue following the realisation of a risk, proportionally to contributions taken off wages"

¹Art. 26 of Law 15.386 ensures a minimum pension of 134.784,86 Chilean pesos for pensioners under 70 since the 1st of December 2017. Source: Social Prevision Institute's (IPS) website, <http://www.ips.gob.cl/servlet/internet/content/1421810853538/montos-de-pensiones-minimas-y-basicas-solidarias>.

²Since the 1st of July 2018, this pension equals 107.304 Chilean pesos. Source: Ibid.

³It is exactly equal to 286.000 Chilean pesos since the 1st of August 2018.

(Lavigne, 2013, p. 7). In these schemes, the level of social security benefits thus depends on past contributions, which minimises the system's redistributive role. It however crowds out market mechanisms. On the one hand, the Bismarckian social security system uses today's contributions to pay for the current social security needs of other insured members, and in exchange grants social security rights. It therefore does not need to invest these contributions on financial markets to preserve their value over time. On the other hand, it is capable of providing the middle classes and wealthy workers benefits adequate enough that they do not need to subscribe to additional private social security schemes (Esping-Andersen, 1990, p. 168). Still, those excluded from the formal labour force are not covered by the conservative welfare state, or at least not directly. Indeed, the inactive spouse and children get social security rights derived from those accumulated by the working family head, be them family benefits, survivor's pensions or health coverage. As such, this Bismarckian social security system is tailored for the traditional male breadwinner family unit. In this welfare state, it is only when the traditional family fails to provide for the needs of its members that the state will interfere with social assistance, which can then be similar to the safety net of the liberal welfare state (Esping-Andersen, 1990, p. 168).

In the Bismarckian social security scheme, retirement benefits are usually "managed jointly by employers and employees inside autonomous pension plans organised by professional categories" (Lavigne, 2013, p. 7). They are most of the time Pay-As-You-Go (PAYG) pension schemes, which means current contributions pay for the benefits of today's pensioners. They are also Defined Benefits (DB) schemes: following an insurance logic, retirement benefits depend on the amount and length of past contributions and replace a proportion of the contributor's reference income, usually computed on the wages earned during the last years of the worker's career. The age at retirement and total contribution years determine the replacement ratio of the retirement benefit, or how much of the reference income it replaces. Thus, the level of retirement benefits is an acquired right that is in theory impervious to the economic or financial conjuncture, contrary to Defined Contributions schemes. Typical examples of the Bismarckian or conservative welfare state are countries in continental Europe such as France or Germany (Esping-Andersen, 1990, p. 168). The French pension system is a good example of a Bismarckian retirement scheme, with a multiplicity of status-linked basic and complementary pension schemes, most of the time PAYG and DB.

The third and final category is the social-democratic welfare state world. It is the one that de-commodifies the most workers according to Esping-Andersen's typology. They

are based on the "Beveridgean" doctrine introduced by Lord Beveridge, a Labour Party minister of UK's war cabinet during World War II. It follows three basic principles: "universality by which all workers must be covered against all social risks, whatever their professional status; uniformity through which citizens must receive identical benefits as a counterpart of equal contributions; unity by which benefits fall under a unique public service"(Lavigne, 2013, p. 7). The most common example of a Beveridgean institution is the British National Health System. Funded mostly through general taxation, it provides free and universal healthcare for residents of the UK. Still, Esping-Andersen considers that Beveridgean components of social security cannot be truly de-commodifying on their own unless they provide an actual alternative to not working. If the state limits social security to a Beveridgean system with low adequacy (with modest benefits, that cover only a small proportion of the dependent population, or both), the paradigm may gradually shift towards the liberal welfare state, where the upper and middle classes resort to private social security schemes to complement this basic benefit, as was the case in Canada or Great Britain in the 1980s (Esping-Andersen, 1990, p. 166). Esping-Andersen identifies as social-democratic systems those where "the state incorporates the new middle classes within a luxurious second-tier, universally inclusive, earnings-related insurance scheme on top of the flat-rate egalitarian one. Notable examples are Sweden and Norway. By guaranteeing benefits tailored to expectations, this solution reintroduces benefit inequalities, but effectively blocks off the market" (Esping-Andersen, 1990, p. 167).

This kind of universal social security coverage with high adequacy is however difficult to achieve. Due to its high cost, it relies on both universal employment and the acceptance of very high taxes to fund it. This welfare state is one in which "all benefit; all are dependent; and all will presumably feel obliged to pay"(Esping-Andersen, 1990, p. 169). As such, the social-democratic welfare state is currently limited to some Nordic countries, or agencies such as Britain's NHS. Beveridgean aspects of social security do however tend to spread, particularly among countries with a Bismarckian or corporatist social security scheme. For instance, the French social security system increasingly relies for its funding on universal taxes such as the Generalised Social Contribution (CSG), and provides a safety net with universal benefits such as the Active Solidarity Revenue (RSA), Universal Illness Coverage (CMU) or the minimum pension benefit. The latest example of this is the 2018 reduction of employee's unemployment and healthcare contributions, compensated by an increase of the CSG. As we will see more in depth below, Argentina's social security system has also recently incorporated various universalistic Beveridgean aspects.

Interestingly enough, countries such as Norway or Sweden put forward by Esping-

Andersen as the main examples of the social-democratic welfare world do not always have full employment. They still propose public, Pay-As-You-Go, universal and highly adequate coverage with little room for private welfare schemes, despite some reforms that increased the latter's importance in the case of Sweden. A reason why they still propose such a high level of public coverage may be that both their PAYG pension schemes are partially funded by national pension funds or sovereign wealth funds who represent a significant proportion of their domestic GDP. Sovereign wealth funds with a relevant impact on the pension system are an exception, the best example being Norway's Government Pension Fund Global (123% of GDP in 2010) (Severinson & Stewart, 2012, p. 12) mostly funded by oil revenues. National pension funds, which mostly manage past social security surpluses, sometimes invest them in the domestic economy and often use them as buffer funds for the temporary funding of social security, most notably in times of economic crisis. These are far more common than sovereign wealth funds that fund social security systems, and sometimes represent a significant proportion of the GDP. Examples, with 2010 figures taken from Severinson & Stewart (2012), include Government Pension Fund Norway (GPFN, 5.6% of domestic GDP), Sweden's National Pension Fund (27% of GDP), the United States Social Security Trust Fund (18% of GDP), South Korea's National Pension Fund (28% of GDP), Japan's Government Pension Investment Fund (GPIF, 26% of GDP) or Canada's Pension Plan Investment Board (CPPIB, 8.6% of GDP). These funds strengthen the economic sustainability of the domestic Pay-As-You-Go pension fund. Funded PAYG systems can limit themselves to providing a basic safety net in countries such as the US, Canada or Japan. Adding a national pension fund to the PAYG system can also serve as a way to provide higher adequacy inside the social-democratic welfare state, such as in Sweden or Norway.

Among developing⁴ countries, the only case where a public Pay-As-You-Go pension system is complemented by a significant pension fund is Argentina. The country's Sustainability Guarantee Fund (FGS), established in 2007, represented 11% of the GDP in December 2017. The origin of these funds is tied to Argentina's turbulent social security history. The country has indeed witnessed various contradictory reforms that have made it swing between the Liberal, Bismarckian and Social-Democratic worlds in the last 25 years. The latest of such swings happened in 2008, when Argentina nationalised private pension funds and shifted to a single-pillar PAYG pension system, moving away from the liberal welfare state. These funds were transferred to the public pension system, who invests them through the FGS national pension fund. This is why Argentina is the only

⁴We do not take into account the pension fund managed by Saudi Arabia's General Organisation for Social Insurance, equal to approximately 106% of domestic GDP (Severinson & Stewart, 2012, p. 12), or the use by other oil-rich countries of oil revenue for the funding of social security.

developing country that has a funded PAYG pension system. This puts Argentina in a peculiar position in the global landscape of social security, as it has experienced various elements of the liberal, conservative and social-democratic welfare state in a short period of time. Argentina is thus an interesting subject for the study of the welfare state, as the evaluation of the various reforms undertaken by the country can shed light on the impact of these institutional arrangements on social security accounts, adequacy and redistributive impact. To this end, let us summarise the main changes the country's social security system witnessed in recent years, and focus on the successive reforms undertaken by the incumbent administration in office since December 2015.

First, from a conservative welfare state following Esping-Andersen's classification, Argentina shifted to the liberal world with the introduction in 1993 of a two-pillar pension system, where cohabited a unified public Defined Benefits PAYG pillar and a private fully-funded Defined Contributions scheme. The public scheme was managed by the newly created National Social Security Administration (ANSES) that functioned under the Ministry of Labour. It unified most of the pre-existing sectoral family, unemployment and retirement benefits systems. The fully-funded scheme was run by private pension funds managers, known as AFJPs⁵. All workers were affiliated to an AFJP unless they expressly opted for the Pay-As-You-Go pension pillar, and they could not later decide to shift back to the public system.

This particular social security setting was however neither economically nor politically sustainable. On the one hand, the cost of the transition to this two-pillar system was supported by the public pillar, who paid for all the retirement rights acquired before 1993 but received only a minority of contributions. Additional funds were allocated to ANSES to fund these transition costs, most notably 15% of all taxes normally shared between the federal government and the provinces (called *coparticipable* taxes). These costs were however underestimated, so this reform resulted in a structural social security deficit that played its part on Argentina's 2001 default. Moreover, when the country was cut off from international financial markets in 2002, this deficit was curbed by illegally lowering real retirement benefits other than the minimum pension in the 2002-2006 period. This measure was condemned by various Supreme Court rulings and led to high pension litigation. This setting was thus not politically sustainable as far as the public pillar was concerned. The private pillar was not politically sustainable either, as private funds were incapable of providing a pension equal to at least the legal minimum to all their affiliates, due in no

⁵This acronym stands for *Administradoras de Fondos de Jubilaciones y Pensiones*, or Retirement and Pension Funds Managers.

small part to operating costs fluctuating between 15.6% and 37.8% of all private pension funds revenues (Arza, 2008). This led the government in 2007⁶ to guarantee the legal minimum benefit to private pensioners and thus subsidise the benefits below it. Finally, the major problem with this setting was that not only there was no universal family or pension benefit for people excluded from the formal labour market, but also access to a retirement pension was made more difficult. Thus, pension and family benefits coverage plummeted after the 1993 reform.

Social and political support to this two-pillar system was thus already low when the 2008 international financial crisis broke out and jeopardised individual pension accounts and the future payment of private retirement benefits. The federal government recognised past contributions to the private scheme as if they had been made in the public pillar. In exchange, the funds accumulated on individual accounts were nationalised and transferred to the Sustainability Guarantee Fund (FGS). This gave birth to a single Pay-As-You-Go Defined Benefits pension system run by ANSES and funded by the FGS, a national fund equal to 8.5% of GDP by the end of 2008. This gave way to a new institutional arrangement, consisting on a Bismarckian social security system with Beveridgean components. On the one hand, contributive retirement rules were left unchanged, which meant these were reserved to people with long formal careers and their levels depended on the last wages before retirement. On the other hand, a variety of measures sought to increase social security transfers adequacy and redistributive impact based on strong economic growth (2003-2007) and the nationalisation of private pension funds. These include the indexation of pensions (mostly) on formal wages implemented on March 2009, the 2009 Universal Child Benefit AUH for the children of informal workers and of the unemployed, the temporary retirement pension moratoriums for people of retirement age with no benefits of 2006 and 2014, the 2016 historical reparation program for pensioners wronged by the real decrease of pensions after the 2001 default, and the 2016 permanent Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult (PUAM) aged 65 or more.

Finally, a last set of measures taken since 2016 by the incumbent administration decreased social security funding, despite the aforementioned increase in expenditure. First, the 2016 historical reparation Law 27260 gradually stops the detraction of 15% of *co-participable* taxes in favour of ANSES, which was established as part of a fiscal pact between the federal and provincial governments in 1993. Since this pact had expired in 2006, some provinces litigated against the federal government to stop this detraction and increase their revenue. The Supreme Court of Justice eventually ruled in their favour in

⁶Through Art. 11 of Law 26222, issued the 8th of March 2007.

November 2015. The problem is that these taxes represented a little less than 20% of all ANSES funding in the 2008-2017 period, and no sustainable measure has been taken to make up for these missing funds: these have been so far compensated by the federal budget. Then, a series of late 2017 fiscal and social security reforms reduced employers contributions (Law 27430⁷) and stopped funding ANSES with 20% of the Income Tax. As a counterpart, ANSES gets 100% of the Tax on Credits and Debits on banks' Current Accounts⁸ (commonly known as "Check" tax), which is slightly higher than 20% of the Income Tax. The same reform however allows for the gradual elimination of this tax by 2022 (Laws 27430 and 27432⁹), that was reduced by 33% on May 2018¹⁰. Finally, the late 2017 reforms also replace the indexation of benefits (mostly) on formal wages by a less generous indexation formula for social security benefits (70% on the Consumer Price Index and 30% on formal wages).

In the end, this set of reforms gave Argentina a public national social security system that covers the vast majority of workers and even reaches out to those excluded from the formal labour market through the universal child benefit, moratorium pensions and the PUAM. Following Esping-Andersen (1990), this puts Argentina in the conservative-Bismarckian welfare world but with Beveridgean elements, comprising both a unified non-corporatist public social security system and universalistic non-contributive benefits. The current social security setting is however temporary, as the historical reparation Law 27260 issued in 2016 schedules an additional, systemic reform of social security due by 2019. Further reforms are currently being discussed as part of the 2019 national budget, which include barring access to the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult (PUAM) to formal workers and opting not to further reduce the "Check" tax on 2019.

The problem is that despite the successive measures taken for the past 25 years and the incoming structural reform, there has so far not been any simulation of Argentina's social security scheme nor any serious projection of its funding needs. Public bodies refuse to carry out actuarial projections on future social security revenues or spending due to the politically explosive characteristic of such an exercise. Thus, none of the social security reforms have been thoroughly evaluated *ex ante* in what regards their expected impact on social security accounts or on its beneficiaries. In particular, there has been no official projection on the cost of the various reforms that increased pension and family benefits expenditure and reduced social security funding. There has not been a rigorous

⁷Issued the 29th of December 2017.

⁸This tax was instituted through Law 25413, issued the 26th of March 2001.

⁹Issued the 29th of December 2017.

¹⁰Following Decree 409/2018, published the 7th of May 2018.

ex post analysis of these reforms either, where their consequences would be compared to a counter-factual scenario with no reforms. Looking at the succession of contradictory parametric and even systemic social security reforms in the past 25 years, it becomes clear that not only there is no basic consensus on social security among Argentina’s political parties. The reforms taken by the successive governments also seem improvised and short-sighted. There is thus a lack of a consistent and sustainable long-term plan for social security, which is linked to the absence of publicly available long-term projections. A public body equivalent to France’s Pensions Advisory Council (COR), which would provide neutral projections on social security funding needs, would greatly help guide the debates on long-term welfare policies. The current lack of any actuarial projection of social security funding needs is not only a gap in the literature, but a serious issue for the functioning of Argentina’s social security system itself.

This thesis aims at contributing to bridge this gap in the literature and to improve the management of Argentina’s social security system. In particular, we have modelled the future funding needs of the social security’s system and evaluated the impact of the most recent reforms undertaken by the incumbent administration since 2016 on its economic sustainability, adequacy and redistributive impact. To do so, we needed a methodology that would be able to both project the aggregate economic sustainability of social security and simulate the impact of benefits down to the individual level across various counter-factual legislation scenarios. We decided to adopt a dynamic microsimulation methodology, coded on the free open-source LIAM2 toolbox developed by the Belgian Federal Planning Bureau (Bryon *et al.* , 2015). As we explain in detail in our literature review of section 2.1, dynamic microsimulation is the standard methodology used by public social security bodies when projecting their accounts or evaluating the *ex ante* impact of reforms (Li & O’Donoghue, 2013). Starting with a micro-level dataset, it consists in simulating the behaviour of each surveyed individual over time. From a cross-section, it thus becomes possible to create a synthetic panel, where the initial population ages and evolves endogenously. Since it simulates heterogeneous individuals, it becomes possible to model the different social security rights and contributions of each member of the population. Social security’s economic sustainability is deduced from this aggregation of individual elements. Since this is a micro-level method, it becomes also possible to study the adequacy of benefits and their distribution among the population, which allows for the analysis of its redistributive impact on household income inequality. Finally, since benefits are simulated separately in all their details, this methodology allows for an *ex ante* policy impact evaluation of reforms, but also to design counter-factual legislative scenarios. By changing the legislative calibration of the model, it becomes possible to compare

what would have happened with social security's economic sustainability, adequacy and redistributive impact with two distinct legislations all other things being equal.

The core of this thesis is thus the building of the first dynamic microsimulation model of Argentina's social security system, run by the National Social Security Administration (ANSES). This is the second social security microsimulation model developed in all Latin America after Brazil's BRALAMMO (Zylberstajn *et al.* , 2011) and, as far as we know, among all developing countries (Li & O'Donoghue, 2013). It is also one of the first such models developed outside of a public body and using only publicly accessible data. All the steps behind the development of this model are laid out in full in this thesis, and the whole code is accessible on-line¹¹. We thus also aim to crack open the black box of dynamic microsimulation models, developed with non-public data and whose code is not made public, and help other researchers or agencies develop their own models in the future. Finally, this thesis has an immediate utility since we provide the first simulation of Argentina's social security system and are the first to project the system's long-term economic sustainability.

Moreover, we do not limit ourselves to an actuarial analysis that could have been approximated with an aggregate model. We study the impact of social security on surveyed individuals and provide the first analysis of Argentina's social security scheme's adequacy and redistributive impact on household income. Adequacy, the combination of the real level of benefits and what share of the dependent population they reach, is the measure through which we can gauge the "de-commodification" power of the welfare state (Esping-Andersen, 1990). The redistributive impact of social security is also crucial in a country like Argentina with high income inequality. Finally, we develop counter-factual legislative scenarios, which allow for an evaluation of the public policies carried out by the incumbent administration since 2016. These included important measures such as the decrease of ANSES fiscal funding (cuts in employers contributions, the fact 20% of the Income Tax and 15% of all *coparticipable* taxes no longer fund ANSES), a less generous pension mobility index and the introduction of the Universal Pension for the Elderly (65+) with incomplete careers (PUAM). We thus estimate the impact of the 2016 and 2017 pension and fiscal reforms on social security's economic sustainability, adequacy and redistributive impact. Our model is however also capable of carrying out *ex ante* evaluations of a wide range of policies. It can thus test the impact of various possible measures on Argentina's social security accounts and populations before they are adopted. We thus believe we have developed a useful tool for policy makers to help them design the future

¹¹We use the Zenodo digital repository service for long-term preservation of our code. The DOI link is: [10.5281/zenodo.1420273](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1420273)

social security reforms they are *de jure* obliged to present by 2019, as established by the 2016 "historical reparation" Law 27260.

Our work is structured around this dynamic microsimulation model of Argentina's social security system, as we will broadly lay out below. In our first Chapter, we prepare the ground for the development of this model. First, section 1.1 provides a detailed review of Argentina's social security system, history, accounts, legislation and reforms. Although this study is interesting on its own right, it is an indispensable step for designing our model, calibrating it to Argentina's current legislation and eventually evaluating the impact of the policies carried out by the incumbent administration. Then, section 1.2 introduces Argentina's Permanent Household Survey (EPH), and shows how we formatted this data-set to make it suitable for both calibrating various aspects of our model and being the starting dataset of our microsimulations. We harmonise the various versions of the survey in the 1974-2017, lay out our strategy to tell apart formal from informal labour and propose an algorithm for identifying basic family links within complex households. This lets us use this survey to simulate both labour-market and socio-demographic transitions in our microsimulation model. Finally, section 1.3 presents various relevant data-sets for the calibration of our labour-market module, and mostly for the simulation of plausible past individual careers. It also proposes a macro-level overview of Argentina's labour-market history since the 1970s, which is telling of the country's secular stagnation since the last military dictatorship (1976-1983).

In our second Chapter, we lay out our dynamic microsimulation of Argentina's social security system, run by the National Social Security Administration (ANSES). We first carry out a review of the dynamic microsimulation literature in section 2.1 and further justify our adoption of this technique for our projections. Then, we present in section 2.2 the general architecture of our microsimulation model. Starting from one wave of the EPH household survey, we first back-cast careers in our retrospective module that are consistent with current individual characteristics and with the history of Argentina's labour market reviewed in section 1.3. This augmented dataset is then projected up to 2040 with varying economic and legislative scenarios in our prospective module. Individuals age, enter or leave the dataset as they get born or die, and witness various socio-demographic and labour-market transitions that aim to be realistic at the individual level while still respecting the input macroeconomic and demographic scenarios. As simulated individuals develop in the labour and family spheres, the model simulates their social security rights, benefits and contributions, which are ANSES main sources of income and expenses. The prospective model is re-run several times by combining economic (pessimistic, central and

optimistic) and counter-factual legislative scenarios. This will allow in our third chapter to carry out actuarial projections of Argentina’s social security that cover various possible economic evolutions, and carry out a policy impact evaluation of the reforms undertaken by the incumbent government up to May 2018.

The remainder of the second chapter is devoted to the simulation of individual behaviour by thematic modules. We first explain in section 2.3 how we model both labour supply and income, which are necessary for determining individual social security rights and contributions. We estimate on the EPH household survey (2003-2015) logistic behavioural equations for labour-market state and Mincer wage equations for income. This adds to the plausibility of simulated behaviour, but also contributes to the labour market literature, in particular on the determinants and consequences of labour informality in developing countries. Next, we lay out in section 2.4 our simulation of marriage market and civil status in general, which aims to model plausible family units and households. This is necessary for the computation of survivor’s and family benefits, although it also influences labour supply and our projection of household income inequality. Finally, we detail in section 2.5 our modelling of education levels and the end of studies age, which affects both labour productivity and the start of individual careers.

All in all, this methodological chapter is a key element of this thesis: by laying out the model behind our social security projections, it helps making these as transparent as possible. Together with the code and instructions available on-line¹², it not only makes our social security projections reproducible, it also helps understand our model with its limitations. It finally constitutes a starting point for expanding and improving Argentina’s social security modelling in the future. This chapter is also of interest for the microsimulation literature in general, as some of the modelling choices adopted for Argentina can be useful for other microsimulation models. It can also help researchers not acquainted with this particular methodology understand it better and contribute to reducing the microsimulation field’s entry costs.

The third and final chapter of this thesis presents our model’s projections of Argentina’s social security system’s economic sustainability, adequacy and redistributive impact up to the 2040 horizon. Section 3.1 tackles the issue of getting aggregate economic results that are representative of Argentina’s economy out of a simulation which uses one wave of the EPH household survey as its starting dataset. We thus explain how we extrapolate

¹²We use the Zenodo digital repository service for long-term preservation of our code. The DOI link is: [10.5281/zenodo.1420273](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1420273)

our simulated social security contributions, family benefits and gross¹³ retirement and survivor's pensions for the elderly paid by ANSES to match actual administrative values. Social security contributions minus these simulated expenses result in our simulated ANSES "Bismarckian" result, which shows to what extent social security contributions alone are enough to pay for (most of) ANSES social security and family benefits. Still, to see the actual weight of this balance on the economy, we need to project future output so as to express ANSES "Bismarckian" result in GDP points. We therefore adopt a simplified growth model that makes output depend on aggregate variables simulated by our model: the evolution of the working population and of their labour income, which we assume reflects the workers' productivity. This lets us compute ANSES Bismarckian deficit as a percentage of GDP, with the current May 2018 legislation and varying economic scenarios. We find ANSES Bismarckian deficit is set to sharply increase in our central economic scenario, from the -2.1% of GDP it represented in 2014 to -4.8% in 2022 when we factor in the cost of the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult (PUAM). From there, the situation slowly worsens until reaching -5.3% of GDP in 2040. This deficit is first caused by the 2014 pension moratorium, fully taken into account in ANSES accounts on 2015 and responsible for making the Bismarckian deficit reach -3.2% in 2015. The further increase of the deficit is however caused by the reforms undertaken in 2016 and 2017, as we show in section 3.2.

Lastly, section 3.2 presents this thesis' main results, which are the simulated evolution of Argentina's social security economic sustainability, adequacy and redistributive impact and the evaluation on these grounds of the 2016 and 2017 reforms. First, we finish the legislative calibration of our model. On the one hand, we take into account non-simulated ANSES revenues (46% of all ANSES income in the 2009-2017 period) and expenses (16% of the total). These are mostly taxes that fund ANSES (see Table 3.7), the payment of court rulings and expenses not *de jure* endorsed by ANSES, but that the body funds in practice (see Table T.2). When combined to the aforementioned ANSES Bismarckian balance, we get the agency's economic result, which determines its actual economic sustainability. On the other hand, we summarise the impact of the 2016 and 2017 reforms on ANSES simulated and non-simulated income and expenses. This lets us precisely define four legislative scenarios. Our baseline scenario uses May 2018 legislation, and takes into account all the rules laid out in section 1.1. Then, our first 2017 counter-

¹³All retirement and survivor's pensioners are by default covered by the National Institute of Social Services for Pensioners INSSJP, also commonly known as PAMI. These pensioners thus receive a pension net of compulsory contributions to the PAMI. These contributions are however paid for by ANSES: the relevant variable for studying ANSES economic sustainability is thus gross pensions. We however take into account net pensions in our analysis of ANSES benefits adequacy and redistributive impact.

factual legislative scenario goes back to November 2017 and assumes the December 2017 social security and fiscal reforms never took place. Finally, our last two scenarios take November 2015 legislation and thus also ignore the 2016 historical reparation Law 27260. The first one assumes the 2014 pension moratorium becomes permanent, while the second one keeps the strict November 2015 legislation, considers the 2014 pension moratorium ends on September 2016 as originally scheduled, and that the elderly with incomplete careers do not get a non-contributive benefit. With these four counter-factual scenarios, it becomes possible to evaluate the economic sustainability, adequacy and redistributive impact of social security in Argentina with May 2018 legislation and gauge the impact of the 2016 and 2017 reforms on these variables.

We find the current legislation leads to a serious social security accounts crisis in all our economic scenarios. If we stick to our central scenario, we find ANSES economic result¹⁴ sharply falls from a balanced budget in 2014 to a measured -1.6% of GDP in 2016 as a result of the 2014 pension moratorium, and a simulated -5.5% of GDP in 2022. The situation then slowly deteriorates, until the deficit reaches -5.8% of GDP in 2040. These are by far the worst social security deficits witnessed by Argentina since the 1993 systemic reform and the creation of ANSES, where the social security deficit had never been durably higher than -1% of GDP. This is first caused by the fact that the Income Tax no longer funds ANSES, and is replaced by a Tax on Credits and Debits on banks' Current Accounts¹⁵ (commonly known as "Check" tax), due to be eliminated by 2022. When we instead consider the "Check" tax is maintained at its current level, including the 33% discount introduced on May 2018, this represents 1.4 GDP points of additional ANSES revenues. The deficit would thus only reach -4.2% by 2022 of GDP and -4.6% of GDP by 2040. So it is possible to alleviate the coming social security accounts crisis by simply refraining from eliminating the "Check" tax¹⁶. However, once we run our counter-factual legislative scenarios it becomes clear the 2016 and 2017 reforms were not taken with the economic sustainability of social security accounts in mind, as all the other scenarios have a better economic sustainability in the 2014-2040 period all other things being equal. With November 2017 legislation, the deficit would have reached -3.1% and -4.3% of GDP in 2022 and 2040. With 2015 legislation without permanent pension moratoriums,

¹⁴We take ANSES economic result including the cost of all the measures introduced by the 2016 historical reparation Law 27260, which are *de jure* assumed by the federal budget. These are the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult (PUAM) and the fact that 15% of all taxes shared between the provinces and the federal government (*coparticipable* taxes) stop funding ANSES. We however exclude both the cost of the historical reparation program, funded with FGS assets, and the returns of FGS investments.

¹⁵This tax was instituted through Law 25413, issued the 26th of March 2001.

¹⁶This should for instance be the case for 2019, as is scheduled by the first draft of the 2019 national budget presented the 17th of September 2019. It is still *de jure* possible to decrease this tax after 2019, and eliminate it by 2023.

the economic sustainability is logically far better, the balance being equal to -0.8% and -0.1% of GDP in 2022 and 2040. Finally, the scenario with 2015 legislation and permanent 2014 moratorium pensions results in deficits of -1.6% and -3.8% of GDP in 2022 and 2040.

We thus find the most generous legislative scenario, which discounts benefits mostly on formal wages and makes available to all people of retiring age moratorium pensions, has a better economic result in the 2014-2040 period than the situation stemming from the 2016 and 2017 reforms. It could make sense to take unpopular measures such as indexing pensions mostly on the consumer's price index (as established in December 2017) and replacing moratorium pensions by a less generous PUAM universal pension if it strengthened social security accounts. The opposite is however happening, which shows the three main motivations of the current government behind these reforms.

The first one is to increase the federal and provincial governments fiscal revenues at the expense of social security funding by ending the detraction of various *coparticipable* taxes (both 15% of all *coparticipable* taxes, worth 1.5%¹⁷ of GDP, and 20% of the Income tax, equal to 1.1%¹⁸ of GDP) in favour of ANSES. The second one is to use social security resources as a way to boost the domestic economy. First, the government chose in 2016 to gradually deplete the FGS to fund an increase in some pensions through the historical reparation program. Then, it may gradually eliminate by 2022 the late 2017 reforms the "Check" tax, worth on average 1.7% of GDP¹⁹. Finally, employer's contributions will be gradually reduced until decreasing social security funding by roughly 1.5% of GDP from 2022 onwards as deduced from our simulations. All these measures are funded with social security resources, and no durable source of income has been chosen to step in for this missing income. All this leads us to what we see as the third objective: the government might be willingly causing an alarming social security deficit to push through unpopular reforms in the near future. This point will be further debated in our general conclusion.

Our model's results do not however stop at the economic sustainability of social security. This cannot be the only variable of interest for policy makers, since social security must also provide for the needs of vulnerable populations (the young and the elderly) and contribute to a less unequal society by redistributing income between workers and non-workers. We thus also project the future evolution of social security benefits adequacy

¹⁷This is the average value in GDP points of the 15% of *coparticipable* taxes transferred to ANSES between 2009 and 2017. Source: own computation using data from the Federal Tax Commission.

¹⁸Source: Ibid.

¹⁹This is an average value computed over the 2009-2017 period. Source: own computation based on AFIP tax collection data.

and redistributive impact, with the political sustainability of Argentina's social security system in mind.

First, we carry out an exploratory analysis of the evolution of ANSES benefits redistributive impact, and how it is affected by the 2016 and 2017 reforms. These are preliminary results that need to be confirmed by further analysis, with in particular more realistic simulations of household composition and an estimation of labour revenues that better re-creates the observed income dispersion. Still, we find the redistributive impact of social security benefits lowers over time with 2018 legislation. Also, we show that the 2015 legislation counter-factual scenario with permanent 2014 pension moratoriums would have resulted in a more equal income distribution among households than the current May 2018 legislation. Finally, we carry out an analysis of income distribution among elderly individuals, unaffected by the limited realism of our simulation of household composition. We find the current legislation will increase the Gini index computed on all income among all people of retirement age from a simulated 0.3 in 2015 to 0.44 in 2040, instead of a slightly higher 0.33 by 2040 with 2015 legislation including permanent pension moratoriums.

We show that the two main elements that decrease the redistributive impact of social security are the 2016 replacement of pension moratoriums by the universal pension PUAM and the indexation of social security benefits mostly on inflation decided in 2017. The PUAM is only available since age 65, which pushes back the retirement age of women with incomplete careers from 60 to 65. This population thus stops receiving social security benefits. Since senior women are often excluded from the labour market and earn lower revenues (see section 2.3), this policy increases income inequality. Then, the change in the pension mobility index mostly freezes in real terms all benefits except contributory retirement pensions for wage earners, which follow real wage evolutions because they are computed on the last ten years of wages before retirement. This both increases inequalities among pensioners and decreases the redistributive impact of social security benefits in general since they represent a lower proportion of households revenue. In the end, we find the 2016 and 2017 reforms not only increased income inequality among the elderly, but also among all households. Argentina had a Gini index of 0.41 in 2014 according to the World Bank data bank, significantly higher than the 0.318 OECD average²⁰ for that year. Adopting policies that further increase already high income inequality levels is a regression, and reduces the political sustainability of the social security scheme.

²⁰Source: OECD income distribution database. Link: <http://www.oecd.org/social/income-distribution-database.htm>.

Finally, we project the evolution of social security benefits adequacy. Benefits are adequate when they are enough to provide for the needs of their beneficiaries and when they cover most of the dependent population. In a Bismarckian approach, they are also adequate when they replace a high proportion of the last earned wages. It is a vague concept, whose direct study is made even more difficult in the case of Argentina due to the controversy surrounding official inflation figures in the 2007-2015 period, which lead to conflicting measures of the poverty line. We can however study the benefits level and coverage of our simulations, and then compare them among legislative scenarios to ascertain the impact of the 2016 and 2017 reforms on social security adequacy. First of all, we show May 2018 legislation is capable of a high universal retirement and child benefits coverage, with only women aged 60 to 64 mostly barred from getting a retirement benefit. However, the real levels of child benefits and all pensions computed as a proportion of the minimum benefit (the universal pension PUAM, pension moratoriums and contributive pensioners that earn the minimum) stagnate in the long run due to their indexation mostly on inflation. Contributory retirement benefits do mostly follow real wages because they are computed on the last ten years of wages before retirement. Despite this, the median retirement benefit falls from representing on average a simulated 58% of the median labour revenue between 2015 and 2017 to reaching 46% in 2040. Thus, as real benefits stagnate and their coverage slightly decreases, they replace a decreasing proportion of labour income earned in the past. Our evaluation of the 2016 and 2017 policies show the best legislative scenario as far as adequacy is concerned is the 2015 legislation with permanent 2014 pension moratoriums. This allows for a universal access to a pension for all people of retirement age, the highest social security benefits thanks to the 2008 pension mobility formula that mostly follows formal wages, and thus a high replacement level of retirement benefits. This is a logical result, but we rigorously quantify this with our microsimulations and show by contrast the impact of the 2016 and 2017 reforms on Argentina's vulnerable population.

All in all, this thesis projects Argentina's social security system's economic sustainability, adequacy and redistributive impact across economic and legislative scenarios. First, we find social security accounts are heading towards an acute crisis in the very short term. Second, we assess the impact of the 2016 and 2017 reforms both in short and long term economic sustainability and show these are the direct causes of the incoming crisis. Finally, we estimate that maintaining 2015 legislation with permanent pension moratoriums not only would have resulted in lower income inequality and higher adequacy of social security benefits. Social security's deficit would have also been lower throughout the 2014-

2040 period had none of the major reforms adopted by the current administration never taken place.

Our results are a contribution to the ongoing social security debate in Argentina, and underscore the importance of carrying out rigorous *ex ante* policy impact evaluations before adopting social security reforms. The extremely high deficit of almost 6 GDP points we project by 2022 is most likely an intentional consequence of the 2016 and 2017 reforms. By making social security strongly unsustainable in the very short term, the incumbent administration is more likely to push through congress a drastic and overarching social security reform by 2019, as *de jure* specified in the 2016 historical reparation Law 27260. These reforms would have been harder to defend had they been evaluated *ex ante* through rigorous and publicly available actuarial social security accounts projections, as done in France by the Pensions Advisory Council (COR). The budgetary leeway to correct these reforms is however dramatically short now that the country has been cut off from international financial markets and that the renegotiation of the June 2018 stand-by agreement signed with the IMF is conditioned on a null primary public deficit by 2019. We hope this model will help policy-makers and the society alike take an informed decision on the matter, and decide whether to curb social security's deficit tax cuts should be reversed, additional sources of funding found, or social security benefits and coverage slashed.

Chapter 1

Social security and the labour market in Argentina: a historical analysis

Argentina has a rich, varied and troubled history in what regards the labour market, social security and retirement policy. It has witnessed multiple cycles, alternating periods of economic growth with crises, sometimes even deep recessions, since the 1970s. Real wages have been fluctuating following successive devaluations and sometimes hyperinflation outbursts. Unregistered labour as well as unemployment have also varied significantly over time. Finally, social security and retirement legislation has seen various comprehensive reforms of varying orientations, such as the introduction (1993) and dissolution (2008) of a fully-funded pension pillar, or the family and retirement benefits access' restriction (1991-1994 social security reforms) and universalisation (2006 and 2014 pension moratoriums, 2009 universal child benefit). All these elements are not only of high academic interest, since having such important economic and regulatory fluctuations in the same country is uncommon in peace time (excluding the 1982 Malvinas war). Their study is also necessary for this thesis, since it is with this data and legislative evolution that our dynamic microsimulation model is designed, calibrated and tested on. This work is also essential in reconstituting individual careers up to 1974, a prerequisite for studying retirement benefits in the long term.

This chapter does not however constitute a comprehensive study of Argentina's social security. Indeed, this thesis' objective is to study the long-term sustainability of the National Social Security Administration (ANSES), Argentina's main social security body, and the expected adequacy and redistributive impact of its benefits. Hence, the branches of social security which are not managed by ANSES are left out of this study, such as health insurance, compensation for labour hazards and accidents, special retirement regimes and benefits awarded by the Ministry of Social Development. Furthermore, for the

sake of simplicity, benefits representing a small portion of ANSES expenses will not be studied either. This includes disability pensions but also unemployment benefits, since the latter do not represent as of today nor in a foreseeable future a significant share of ANSES expenses due to their lack of inflation indexation. This work will hence focus on retirement benefits, pensions derived from retirement benefits and family benefits, which are the necessary elements for building the dynamic microsimulation model that will be described in this thesis' Chapter 2.

First of all, section 1.1 reviews Argentina's social security system's history through its various reforms, and shows ANSES economic result since its inception in 1993. It ends by reviewing the current legislation and the latest reforms to show how these changed the computation rules of contributory and non-contributory retirement benefits, survivor's pensions, family benefits, pension indexation and social security contributions. Then, section 1.2 studies our most important micro datasets, the Permanent Household Survey or EPH, in their punctual (1974-2003) and continuous (2003-2017) versions, which will serve as our starting micro-level dataset for our dynamic microsimulation model. We also show how we identify family links and informal labour in the EPH, which are important variables when modelling social security but are not always directly available in our datasets. Finally, in section 1.3 we carry out a historical analysis of three elements necessary for reproducing past careers and computing retirement rights. First, we measure labour-market participation rates following various iterations of the EPH household survey over the 1974-2017 period. Second, we combine various sources to compute quarterly real wages evolutions over the 1970-2018 period that are consistent with the Mean Taxable Income of Stable Workers (RIPTE) wage index, available since 1994. And third, we address the judicial controversy on which discounting index should be employed for computing the reference income.

To summarise, by studying Argentina's social security legislation, introducing our main individual-level data source and collecting relevant historical data, this chapter carries out all the preparatory work that is needed for building a dynamic microsimulation model for Argentina. It also constitutes a summary of the main aspects and reforms of social security in Argentina and an analysis of this country's labour market history, so it is also interesting in its own right.

1.1 Social security in Argentina: history, recent developments and current characteristics

1.1.1 Argentina's social security system: a history through its reforms

Argentina saw the development and extension of social security throughout the 20th century, until by the beginning of the 1990's it covered most of the population. This development came in phases: in the first half of the 20th century, there was first the emergence of sectoral, independent funds awarding retirement benefits and funding family benefits. Then since the 1950's, a series of reforms first harmonised their functioning, merged the different existing funds and extended coverage to all labour sectors, including in some cases informal employment. The generosity of the retirement system both in coverage and in promised benefits together with a deteriorating economic and demographic situation however lead to persistent social security deficit and to the partial payment of benefits in the late 1980's. The early 1990's saw structural reforms that sought to mend these issues and introduced a fully-funded pension pillar, but also gave way to various disequilibriums, manifested in growing social security deficits, a drop in pension coverage and, when access to the financial markets was cut in late 2001, a sharp drop in the real value of pensions. These issues lead to various additional reforms in the 2000's, which included private pension funds nationalisation in 2008 to strengthen social security financing and various efforts to increase the system's adequacy, including the reintroduction of pension mobility¹ in 2009 and a shift towards a universalistic social security paradigm, with measures such as pension moratoriums (2006 and 2014) and the creation of a Universal Child Benefit (AUH)² in 2009. Finally, a series of issues left unanswered together with the election of a right-wing coalition in 2015 lead to the 2016 pension reform³, which may herald a shift back from universalistic social security to a more Bismarckian scheme, where pensions are more tightly linked to past contributions.

¹Through the Pension Mobility Law 26417, published the 16th of October 2008 and first applied in March 2009

²(The *Asignación Universal por Hijo* (AUH) was created by Decree-Law 1602/09, issued the 29th of October 2009.

³This is Law 27260. the "National Program of Historic Reparation for Retirees and Pensioners", issued the 22d of July 2016.

History of social security in Argentina: from inception to the early 1990's

It is possible to locate the inception of Argentina's social security system with its first retirement fund, the National Civil Pension Fund created in 1904 through Law 4349. It covered federal civil servants as well as national railways and public banks employees. Other sectoral funds were progressively established, mostly in a fully-funded and Defined Contribution scheme, and particularly during the Perón vice-presidency (1944-1946) and then presidency (1946-1955). Law 14370 issued in 1954 introduced substantial changes. Indeed, "it fostered the unification of the [sectoral systems] and, on the other hand, the pension scheme started moving away from a fully-funded to a Pay-As-You-Go system" (Schulthess & Demarco, 1993, p. 24). Thirteen sectoral systems however still existed by 1967, when the *de facto* government created the Pay-As-You-Go (PAYG) "National regime of social security"⁴, which depended on the Social Security Secretariat (SSS) of the Ministry of Labour and Social Security. These started being managed by three different Funds, one for dependent private sector workers, another for independent private sector workers and a third one for civil servants and workers of national companies. Shortly after, Laws 18037 and 18038⁵ effectively dissolved the different private sector regimes, creating a unified regime for private sector dependent (Law 18037) workers, and for independent (Law 18038) workers. They were run by the aforementioned Funds and managed by the newly created "National System of Social Prevision" (SNPS), still dependent on the Social Security Secretariat. It was a Defined Benefit PAYG pension system that covered around 90% of working-age population and was relatively generous in its benefits. Indeed, for dependent private workers the reference wage was computed on the last three years before retirement and the pension represented 70% to 82% of it (SSS, 2003, p. 15). The retirement age was 55 for women and 60 for men. However, other pension plans remained, mainly for each Province's civil servants, the Police and the Military, and "Complementary plans" for such professions as lawyers or doctors still existed separately.

The retirement system entered a crisis in the mid-1980's. This was due on the one hand to a deteriorating economic situation, with rising unemployment and unregistered employment, as well as increasing evasion to social security contributions by registered workers (SSS, 2003). On the other hand, "employer's contributions (...) were used as a fiscal policy and private employment promotion tool" (Lo Vuolo & Goldberg, 2002, p. 6.), with for instance the elimination of employers' contribution between 1980 and 1983 by the *de facto* regime. Additionally, the population was ageing: "people aged 60 or more represented 5% of Argentina's population in 1950, rising to 10% in 1980; at the same time,

⁴Instituted by Law 17575, issued the 21th of December 1967

⁵Regulated by Decree 8525/68 and in force since the 1st of January 1969

individuals aged 25 to 60 remained in a percentage averaged 44% of total population in both dates" (SSS, 2003, p. 15). All this made that in the end, "the expenses in benefits had no relation whatsoever with the genuine revenues of the system"(Lo Vuolo & Goldberg, 2002, p. 6.). This forced the declaration by President Alfonsín's government of a social security emergency in 1986, suspending the payment of benefits according to the legal indexation formula, until 1988, without being able to recover a financial equilibrium. By 1989, this meant pensions only represented 40% of wages (SSS, 2003), nearly half of the *de jure* formula, which gave way to increased litigation against the social security system. In the end, despite high social security coverage of the elderly, with 80.9% of individuals aged 65 or more getting a pension in 1993 (Rofman & Oliveri, 2011), the retirement system had serious sustainability and adequacy issues at the eve of the 1993 reform.

Before studying the 1993 social security reform, let us make a quick review of the other branch of social security considered in this work, family benefits. Although their origin traces back to 1940 in some sectors such as banking, railways or public servants, they gained in width and organisation in 1957. That year saw the creation of compulsory sectoral compensatory funds established through collective bargaining agreements, for trading and industrial sector dependent workers⁶. These funds were funded by contributions from employers of said sectors and compensated the payment of child benefits to the wage-earners by their direct employers. Sectoral family allowances schemes were gradually available for all private sector employees, for public servants in 1968 and for retirees and state-owned companies' workers in 1973. All Provinces also had their family allowances system for provincial public servants. In the end, these sectoral funds collectively covered all registered wage-earners and pensioners (Rofman *et al.* , 2001) (Hintze & Costa, 2011, p. 155-156). These sectoral family allowances funds were dissolved under Chapter IV of Decree 2284/91⁷, and family allowances' contributions and benefits were transferred to the Unified Social Security System SUSS⁸. Provincial family allowances systems were not however transferred to this unified system, and still exist today.

Structural reforms, and crisis of the reform: from the creation of ANSES to the 2001-2002 crisis.

In this context, partly inspired by the full privatisation of the Chilean pension system in 1981, the 1993 law 24.241 instituting the "Integrated Retirement and Survivors' Pension

⁶As established by Decree/Laws 7913 and 7914/57

⁷Issued the 31st of October 1991

⁸*Sistema Único de la Seguridad Social*

System (SIJP)” unified the three pre-existing retirement Funds and implemented a mixed system by introducing an optional fully funded pillar. The proponents of this reform, close to the World Bank’s recommendation of instituting a three-pillar system (Pordes, 1994), argued this would guarantee the sustainability and equilibrium of the pension system. First of all, the private pension system was expected to increase workers’ contributions. In a country with high tax evasion and unregistered employment, a fully-funded system was seen as a good incentive for formalisation, with some authors even considering it would suffice to prevent individuals from evading social security compulsory contributions⁹. Furthermore, the establishment of a fully-funded pillar was expected to increase total savings, which would foster development. Indeed, by creating pension funds and making future benefits rely on individual savings, total savings would increase, which would result in a higher economic growth following standard capital accumulation theories. As Lavigne (Lavigne, 2013, p. 48) puts it, “with a scarce capital, capital’s yield becomes bigger than economic growth and hence fully-funded systems become more attractive than PAYG pension systems”. Furthermore, this system was presumably safe from political and demographic risks. Moreover, the worker was expected to choose whichever system suited him best, since both pillars were available. And within the fully-funded pillar, competition between private pension funds would induce efficient management and minimal operative costs. At the same time, in the original reform “the State guarantees (...) a minimum pension calculated on the system’s tax collection”(Lo Vuolo & Goldberg, 2002, p. 22). Since the Convertibility Plan of 1991 abolished pensions’ indexation that existed under the SNPS pension system, this became SIJP’s pension indexation’s mechanism, which was expected to compensate for inflation while at the same time limiting the expected burden on the State’s finances. This did not prove to be the case since starting from the 31st of March 1995, Law 24463’s Art. 7 incise 2 established that pension mobility was set yearly by the federal budgetary Law. Finally, the cost derived from transitioning to a two-pillar system was to be shouldered both by increased contributions to the system and by a temporary transfer of 15% of "coparticipable"¹⁰ taxes from Provinces to ANSES, as part of a broader agreement including the financing or absorption of provincial civil servants’ pension plans (Bertranou *et al.* , 2011, p. 63)¹¹.

⁹For instance, speaking about Argentina’s case, Schulthess & Demarco (1993) stated that "in a [fully-funded] scheme, (...) contributors have strong incentives to fulfil their obligations, since that will determine the amount of their future benefits, which eliminates the evasion problem which is characteristic of Pay-As-You-Go schemes" (p. 26).

¹⁰Some provincial taxes are collected by the federal government on behalf of the provinces (such as a percentage of the VAT or of the income tax) and redistributed to them afterwards. These are called "coparticipable" taxes, or "coparticipation"

¹¹The transfer of coparticipable was established by a pact signed between the federal government and the Provinces, enforced by Law 24130. published the 22d of September 1992.

However, “as contributions were diverted to individual accounts, social security revenues plummeted and more public transfers were needed to cover the gap”(Arza, 2009, p. 2). Indeed, workers were assigned by default to the private pension system and could not, until 2007, decide to opt out of it and contribute to the PAYG pension system. In addition, "the provincial pension plans' deficit amounted to around 0.45% of GDP between 1996 and 2002" (Bertranou *et al.* , 2011, p. 64), which further strained ANSES current accounts. This resulted in significant ANSES deficits that represented an average of 1% of GDP during the 1993-2002 period, as can be seen in Figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1: ANSES Economic result, 1993-2017 (% of GDP)

Sources: Nation’s General Accounts agency (CGN, 1993-2017); ONP (2018); ministry of Economy. To get ANSES economic result, we add to the current-account balance figurative contributions to ANSES originating from the Fiscal Pact Law 24130 (02/09/1994) and from other expenses funded by the Treasury since 2013 (PROGRESAR, Conectar Igualdad and national civil servants family benefits). We then subtract ANSES figurative expenses (excluding figurative contributions made by ANSES to the PAMI for years 1995 to 1997) and since 2008 the payment by ANSES of social security settlements. Finally, for years 2016 and 2017, we take out of the analysis both income and expenses linked to the Law 27260 historical reparation program, which are mixed with regular ANSES income and expenses. These are penalties linked to the fiscal amnesty (studied in section 1.1.2) and the additional expenses on pensions estimated in Appendix A. The FGS, or Sustainability Guarantee Fund, is a buffer fund managed by the ANSES that originated from the private pension funds nationalisation in 2008. It will be studied more in detail later in this section.

On top of that, coverage did not increase as was expected with the implementation of a more direct link between pension contributions and pension benefits in the fully-funded system. As explained by Arza, “under the rules established in 1993, workers needed to accumulate 30 years of contributions to claim for benefits. This was only feasible for long-term formal workers. As a result, coverage remained low and even fell after the reform”(Arza, 2009, p. 7). This, together with a worsening socio-economic situation leading up to the 2001-2002 crisis, effectively produced a significant drop in coverage, reaching

66.75% of individuals aged 65 or more in 2003 (Rofman & Oliveri, 2011). Furthermore, switching between private pension funds managers was also costly, difficult and thus seldom undertaken, which effectively reduced the reality of competition between private funds. This led to very high operating costs for the fully-funded pillar, representing 3.5% of contributors' gross income between 1995 and 2001 and, after a 2002 reform limiting these costs, around 2.4% of earnings between 2002 and 2008¹². This meant that operative costs represented on average 21.6 % of contributions to pension funds for the 1995-2007 period, greatly diminishing the pensions these funds could pay to their affiliates. During this same period, administrative costs only represented 1.7% of the Pay-As-You-Go pension system managed by ANSES (Arza, 2008). Finally, the fully-funded pillar was subjected to various political risks, the most obvious one having been the Decree n^o 1387-01 of November the 1st of 2001. This decree reduced to 5% of the wage employee's contributions to the fully funded system for one year and "forced private pension funds to invest almost entirely on public bonds"(Lo Vuolo & Goldberg, 2002, p. 27) just months before Argentina's default. In the end, the private pension system did not increase the pension system's sustainability, failing to promote individual contributions. It was also subjected to financial risks, huge operation costs and political risks of its own.

This dual system also left a very weakened public pension system that relied on government transfers to stay afloat until 2004 (see Figure 1.1 p. 48), once the economy had recovered from the collapse of convertibility in 2001-2002, despite a favourable demographic situation. This pillar was also gradually emptied out, as pensions stopped being indexed on the pension system's revenues and started being arbitrarily set by the authorities with the creation of the MOPRE¹³, a reference unit set by the government. This effectively led for instance the minimum pension to be frozen at 150 pesos (150 US\$) a month from September 1995¹⁴ to July 2002¹⁵. Also, the real value of pensions above the minimum pension decreased substantially in the 2002-2006 period, a period with an inflation of two digits: the mean retirement benefit decreased by 22% in real terms between December 2001 and December 2005¹⁶, as can be seen in Figure 2.

¹²Source: (Arza, 2009), table 3.

¹³Instituted by Decree 833/1997, issued the 29th of August 1997.

¹⁴As established by Decree 525/1995 issued the 22d of September 1995.

¹⁵The Decree 1275/2002, issued the 17th of July 2002, set the minimum pension to 200 pesos.

¹⁶Source: own calculations using (DNPE, 2012) and the consumer price index. We stop in 2005 in order to avoid moratorium pensions lowering the mean pension's level.

Figure 1.2: Real wage and retirement pensions evolution, 1994-2016

Note: the INDEC, Argentina's national agency of statistics and census, advises to take with caution Consumer Price Indexes issued between 2007 and 2015. We thus use an average of the CPIs from the city of Buenos Aires and the province of San Luis since 2007 for computing real wages and pensions. After this date, real wages and pensions computed using the period's official CPI are represented with dotted lines. December values, except for 2016 (September). The RIPTE, computed monthly by the ministry of Labour, is equal to the mean gross wage of stable formal wage-earners. Sources: (DNPE, 2016); INDEC; ministry of Labour; provincial statistics agencies from the provinces of San Luis and Buenos Aires Autonomous City.

Since "mobile retirement benefits and pensions" are guaranteed by the Constitution's Art. 14 bis, pensioners sued ANSES to force it to retroactively increase their benefits in line with a variety of wage indexes. The Supreme Court of Justice issued several rulings in favour of pensioners (see Box 1), and since ANSES did not generalise these rulings to all those eligible individuals, pensioners had to sue ANSES to benefit from those rulings.

Given the limited budget that has been set aside since 2007 for paying these sentences, an average of 20.000 to 40.000 pensioners have seen their sentences paid by ANSES each year, which made most plaintiffs wait 8 to 10 years (Bermúdez, 2016) to benefit from those rulings. By June 2016 several hundreds of thousands (between 300,000 (Bermúdez, 2016) and 700,000 (Verbitsky, 2016)) of pensioners had ongoing trials against ANSES or had won their lawsuits but were waiting for ANSES to compensate them.

Box 1: Supreme Court of Justice rulings against ANSES

- **Sánchez (2005)**: retroactively extends the indexation formula in place until the 31st of March 1991 (the general income index set by the INDEC) until the 31st of March 1995 for pensioners that retired before Law 24241 was in place (so before 1993). Since the 1st of April 1995, it is *de jure* set in the budget law^a.
- **Badaro (2006)**: retroactively indexes pensions received between the 1st of January 2002 and the 31st of December 2006 on INDEC's general wage index. This ruling is valid only for people who retired before Law 24241 was in place.
- **Eliff (2009)**: extends the Badaro ruling to people who retired with Law 24241 (hence since 1993). It also rules that, in order to compute the reference income from which is derived the first retirement pension past income must be discounted using the ISBIC of unqualified personnel. Computed by the Ministry of Labour, the ISBIC is an index that transcribes the mean base salary of collective bargaining agreements of industry and construction branches. It has risen faster than mean wages in the 2002-2006 period (see section 1.3.3.). Jurisprudence derived from the Eliff ruling has nevertheless considered that income received starting from the 1st of March 2008 must be discounted using ANSES' pension mobility index^b

^aAs set by Law 24463's Art. 7 incise 2.

^bSeveral Supreme Court rulings were held against pensioners that retired after the 1st of March 2009 and sued ANSES to get their initial retirement pension increased: Valtuille (19th of December 2013), Ackermann (23d of May 2014) and Golovca (11th of July 2014).

The reform of the reform: pension moratoriums, private pension funds nationalisation and new benefits (2003-2015)

Starting from the mid 2000's, a series of reforms were carried out in order to address the issues raised by the 1993 reform. The low coverage of the system led to the adoption of successive pension moratoriums (2005, 2006 and 2014), which will be described in the next section. These moratoriums not only helped increase coverage, but also represented a powerful tool for palliating gender inequality. Indeed, as stated by (D'Elia *et al.* , 2011, p. 14), "in May 2010. 78% of total awarded benefits through the Moratorium went to women and the remaining 22% to men". As they explain, "it is a stylised fact that most contributory pension regimes do not bring coverage against specific risks associated to motherhood and familial responsibilities that have historically been assigned to women, such as looking after children, the elderly, and the sick. Also, due to interrupted em-

ployment trajectories and generally lower wages, fewer and fewer women participate in a contributory pension regime during their working trajectory and receive benefits while of retirement age AISS (2002)." Hence, the decision of attaining universal pension coverage for people of retiring age, along with the earlier retirement age for women, "has had an active role in promoting gender equality in pension systems"(D'Elia *et al.* , 2011).

Furthermore, a series of reforms in 2007 and early 2008 sought to compensate the low level of pensions derived from the 1993 reform and the insufficient adjustment of pensions in the wake of the 2001-2002 crisis. First of all, the minimum pension was increased by 64% in real terms between December of 2001 and December of 2006¹⁷ as can be seen in Figure 1.2 (p. 50). Moreover, the low benefits some workers were entitled to in the fully-funded pension system because of low wages, extended periods of unemployment or of unregistered labour led to an early 2007 pension reform "encouraging worker affiliation to the public pay-as-you-go system" (Arza, 2009, p. 2). On the one hand, it allowed switching from the fully-funded to the PAYG pillar, which was impossible before, and on the other it automatically transferred to the public system contributors and retirees that may have had a pension benefit lower than the minimum pension in the fully-funded pillar¹⁸. Following this transfer of individual accounts, the FGS , "Sustainability Guaranteeing Fund", was created by Decree 897/2007¹⁹. It was constituted by the transferred individual accounts and current surpluses of ANSES. Its mission was guaranteeing defined benefits in the case of a temporary deficit caused by an economic crisis. Finally, the 2008 Pension Mobility Law 26417 indexed pension benefits to formal wages and ANSES revenue, through a formula we will analyse later on, and helped defuse further litigation against ANSES by fulfilling the constitutional requirement of mobile retirement pensions from March 2009 onwards.

The most crucial reform was the pension nationalisation Law 26425²⁰ that replaced the SIJP with the current Integrated Argentinian Pension System (SIPA). Both the various inefficiencies of the fully-funded pillar, its important cost and the mass of contributions it captured at the expense of the PAYG pillar were reasons enough for dissolving this pillar in the eyes of the government of the time. This administration had in fact already attempted to decrease its size with the 2007 reforms that incited affiliation to the public pillar. It was however with the 2008 international financial crisis that the political decision to dissolve the fully-funded pillar was taken. This is because the value of the pension funds'

¹⁷Source: own calculations based on nominal minimum pensions and consumer price index.

¹⁸Through Law 26222, implemented the 7th of March 2007.

¹⁹Issued the 12th of July 2007

²⁰Issued the 4th of December 2008.

assets was shrinking and with them the benefits these funds would pay in the future. Not only would have this been detrimental to these funds' affiliates, it also would have proven costly for the federal government because pensioners of the fully-funded pillar were guaranteed a retirement pension equal to at least the minimum pension²¹. The 2008 financial crisis thus proved to be the perfect window of opportunity to nationalise private pension funds without facing a significant political opposition.

This law is basically summarised in its first article, that states: “the current fully-funded regime is to be eliminated, absorbed and substituted by the PAYG regime”. The periods where contributions were made under the fully funded system give way to the same benefits as if those contributions had been made under the PAYG system. All individual accounts of the former fully funded pillar are transferred to the FGS and the PAYG pension system is required to pay the pensions of people retired under the former fully-funded system. The end of the fully-funded pension regime meant all formal workers started contributing to the same PAYG system. This measure, effective since the fourth of December 2008, increased the number of contributors per retiree in the PAYG system from slightly less than 1 in September 2008 to a little over 2 in December 2008, as can be seen in Figure 1.3. This strengthened the system's sustainability even amid the economic depression of 2009 and economic slowdown after 2012 as can be seen in Figure 1.1 (p. 48). It furthermore became a provisioned PAYG scheme, with the FGS acting as a buffer fund for future economic difficulties. This paved the way to the deepening of social security in Argentina. The clearest example of this is the creation of the Universal Child Benefit (*Asignación Universal por Hijo, AUH*)²², instituting a new regime of non-contributory family benefits which will be further described in the following section. It is interesting to note that this was the only benefit that could be paid for with “the annual performance of the FGS” in addition to the usual sources of funding of ANSES²³ until the 2016 reform, as we will see further below.

²¹As established by Art. 11 of Law 26222, issued the 7th of March 2007.

²²By Decree-Law 1602/09, issued the 29th of October 2009.

²³See Decree 1602/09's third article

Figure 1.3: Contributors per retiree, proportion of working-age people contributing to social security and elderly access to a retirement pension, 1994-2016.

Note : people aged 20 to 59 for women and 64 for men are considered of working age. Values correspond to December. Exceptions are for year 2016 (September) and, for the contributors per retiree variable, the 2008 value before nationalisation corresponds to the month of September. Sources: extrapolation of 1991, 2001 and 2010 census data, INDEC demographic projections; (DNPE, 2016) ; CGN (1993-2016) and (Arza, 2009).

All in all, Argentina had, by the end of 2015, witnessed a series of contradictory reforms. Its retirement system generosity decreased following the comprehensive 1993 reform, which also split it in two pillars, one fully-funded, one PAYG. The high cost linked to introducing a fully-funded pillar, its failure to bolster contributions to the system or to become a meaningful source of savings for financing the Argentinian economy and its very high operating costs resulted in it being dissolved at the outburst of the 2008 international financial crisis. This left a unified PAYG pension system that covered most of Argentina’s population and was furthermore provisioned with a significant buffer fund,

the FGS (whose value increased from 8.5% of GDP when it started operating in 2008 to 11.4% of GDP in December 2017). A number of issues were however left unsolved, and after the rise in power of a right-wing coalition in 2015 a new reform, which we will present in the following section, was quickly passed to answer some of these problems.

1.1.2 The 2016 reform: a transitory measure?

The reasons of the reform

At the eve of the 2016 reform, Argentina had a universalistic social security system, with a nearly universal access to a retirement pension. By September 2016 not only direct retirement pensions granted by ANSES represented 90% of the population of retirement age²⁴, there also was a wide array of benefits that covered a significant portion of the population, ranging from means-tested child benefits (the AUH and contributory child benefits) to the PROGRESAR²⁵ allowance (a scholarship to incite people aged 18 to 25 to carry on their education). This new universalistic social security system was however hindered by a series of limitations. On the one hand, it had accomplished a *de facto* shift from a Bismarckian to a more Beveridgean system. The insufficient adjustment of pensions with respect to inflation in the 2002-2006 period we mentioned earlier combined with a significant increase of the minimum pension in real terms in that same period (see Figure 1.2 p. 50) and the wide scope of pension moratoriums, that represented 65% of direct retirement pensions by September 2016 (DNPE, 2016), resulted in most retirees receiving almost the same benefit regardless of their working history. By September 2016, 71% of retirement pensions were at most equal to the legal minimum of 5661 pesos and 87% of retirement pensions were at most equal to 12000 pesos, a little more than two times the minimum (DNPE, 2016). On the other hand, the combination of renewed pension moratoriums and a stagnation of formal labour rates since the 2008 crisis resulted in a decrease of the ratio of contributors to retirees, as can be seen in Figure 1.3 p. 55, further straining ANSES accounts (see Figure 1.1 p. 48). In particular, ANSES accounts have been in a deficit since 2013 once we take out FGS returns, which have so far been wholly reinvested in the Fund.

Two elements were however decisive in carrying out the 2016 reform. The first was the huge stock of trials against ANSES we mentioned earlier that represented a potentially important risk on social security accounts were they to be all honoured. Indeed, every year

²⁴Source: own computation using INDEC population projections and (DNPE, 2016)

²⁵Instituted by Decree 84/2014 issued the 17th of March 2014.

since 2008 ANSES has been paying one-time compensations to individuals that won their trials against ANSES that represent between 0.1% and 0.2% of the GDP²⁶. This figure does not include the increased levels of pensions of those who won those trials and see their future payments increased. The second came from a dispute between some Provinces and the Federal government regarding the 15% of "coparticipation" that financed ANSES. The original pact was indeed instituted in 1992²⁷ and periodically renewed. However, three provinces (Córdoba, San Luis and Santa Fe) refused its renewal past the 1st of January 2006. The federal government disregarded these provinces' refusal and continued assigning 15% of "coparticipable" taxes to ANSES, leading these three provinces to sue the federal government in order to retrieve these taxes. The Supreme Court of Justice eventually ruled in favour of these provinces the 24th of November 2015 and ordered the government to find a settlement with them to compensate them and to refrain from deducting these amounts in the future. This represented a major loss for ANSES finances: between 2007 and 2017, these represented on average 1.5% of GDP and 16%²⁸ of ANSES current revenue (excluding figurative contributions that did not originate from this Fiscal pact). These two elements, together with the will to reinforce the link between past contributions and the received pension, prompted the right-wing coalition elected in 2015 to carry out an important social security reform, which we will describe in the following section.

A deal with the provinces and a universal pension for the elderly: a precarious funding

The pension reform instituted by Law 27260²⁹ tries to answer a number of the aforementioned issues the social security system was facing. First of all, this law ratifies the deal signed between the federal government and the provinces that gives back to the former the "coparticipable" taxes that funded ANSES. To begin with, starting the 1st of January 2016 the central government only holds 12% of the "coparticipation" in order to fund social security. This proportion will be reduced by 3 percentage points each year until reaching 0% in 2020. This reduction in ANSES income is compensated by the federal budget and will not be taken into account for the pension mobility formula. Moreover, as part of the deal the FGS makes four-year maturity loans to the provincial governments equalling to 6% of the "coparticipation" they are entitled to in 2016 and then 3% of said "coparticipation" between 2017 and 2019. The annual interest rate is the short-term

²⁶Source: Rosconi *et al.* (2017) (2010-2016) and CGN's Investment Account (2008, 2009 and 2017).

²⁷As formalised by Law 24130 issued the 17th of September 1992

²⁸Source: Federal Taxes Commission, *Comisión Federal de Impuestos*. URL: <http://www.cfi.gov.ar/>

²⁹Issued the 22d of July 2016.

market's (30 days BADLAR) but is subsidised by the Treasury so that the provinces do not pay more than 15% of interest rates for loans made in 2016 and 2017 then 12% for those made in 2018 and 2019. Since inflation for 2016 averaged 40%³⁰ these are negative real interest rates. This deal effectively ends the conflict with the provinces but it comes at a significant cost for the federal budget, while also forcing the FGS to make four-year maturity loans with short-term interest rates. By December 2016, these loans already represented 3.1% of FGS assets (FGS, 2016, p. 10), a share that should rapidly grow in the coming years.

Secondly, the reform creates a "universal pension for the elderly" equal to 80% of the minimum pension and accessible at age 65 (for further details, see section 1.1.3.). This benefit replaces future pension moratoriums and will be funded by the federal budget. It is on the paper positive for ANSES, since moratorium pensions represented 30% of ANSES current expenses, or 2.8% of GDP, in 2015³¹. This however puts under further pressure the federal budget, since it will have to fund an expense worth several GDP points. If we include the fact it will also have to shoulder the return of "coparticipation" to the provinces and subsidise the loans made to them by the FGS, this means several measures of Law 27260 will be funded by the federal budget. It is thus highly unlikely successive governments will accept to see the federal budget shoulder several GDP points worth of expenses for social security in the long run. The financing of both these measures is thus a temporary arrangement even though this reduction in social security funding and this new universal retirement pension are permanent. The more overarching social security reform scheduled for 2019 by Law 27260's Art. 12 is likely to either assign long-term resources to fund them or make the social security system shoulder them through either a decrease in benefits, pushing back the minimum retirement age, increasing the required number of validated years to retire or all of the above.

³⁰There are no nationwide official inflation figures for year 2016 due to the INDEC not reporting inflation values between November 2015 and March 2016. For the year 2016, marked by significant price hikes in public services in the Buenos Aires urban centre, annual inflation rates equal 31.5% in the Province of San Luis, 40.8% for the Autonomous City of Buenos Aires (CABA) and 40.3% as evaluated by an average of the two former indexes and seven other private indexes issued by some opposition congressmen ("Congress IPC")

³¹Source: own calculus using the 2015 Investment Account ("Cuenta de Inversión"). Spending on pension moratoriums is taken from total spending on pension moratoriums in 2015 is taken from Appendix ii.3, ANSES current account spending from Appendix 19 except for operating costs, which are taken from Appendix 3.10.

The "National Program of Historic Reparation for Retirees and Pensioners": a first step towards a Bismarckian revival?

Law 27260's core measure is however the "National Program of Historic Reparation for Retirees and Pensioners" that offers a compensation for retirees affected by insufficient pension indexation on inflation mainly in the 2002-2006 period. In an effort to end litigation against ANSES (see Box 1), this law creates a voluntary settlement plan for individuals who have sued or could sue ANSES following decisions Sánchez, Badaro or Eliff but did not yet receive a compensation through litigation. The plan first retroactively computes the level of past pensions as they should have been paid following the Supreme Court of Justice's rulings. To do so, it modifies the coefficients³² used to discount past income for computing the initial retirement pension (Art. 5). Income earned between the 1st of April 1991 and the 31st of March 1995 is discounted using INDEC's general wage index, while income earned between the 1st of April 1995 and the 30th of June 2008 is discounted using the RIPTE index, or Mean Taxable Income of Stable Workers (computed by the Ministry of Labour since 1994) whose evolution is close to that of INDEC's general wage index. It also retroactively adjusts pensions received between 1991 and 2008 following the Sánchez, Badaro and Eliff rulings³³. This pension readjustment does not however retroactively modify past minimum and maximum pensions, barring corrected pensions from exceeding the maximum pension values prevailing at the time. ANSES then takes away from these augmented pensions the pensions that were effectively paid as well as the income tax these increased pensions would have paid were they correctly given in the past. What remains, once discounted using the mean bank deposits rate as established by the Central Bank, is the debt acknowledged by ANSES to each of these pensioners. Finally, future pensions are increased in line with the retroactive increases in pensions and the initial retirement pension.

However, in order to benefit from these measures the pensioner must subscribe to a payment plan³⁴ with ANSES. By subscribing, lawsuits against ANSES on the incriminated periods are considered *res judicata* (Art. 6), so the pensioner has to drop any pending lawsuits against ANSES and should not be able to sue ANSES for the periods included in the agreement again. All subscribers see their future pensions automatically increased,

³²The new coefficients are set by Resolution 6 / 2016 of the Social Security Secretary issued the 3d of August 2016.

³³For the 2002-2006 period, the RIPTE is however used instead of INDEC's general wage index, although their evolution was similar in that period.

³⁴This payment plan is made in the context of the state of emergency in litigiousness on retirement matters established by Law 27260's Art. 2. This emergency ends in 2019 (three years after Law 27260's implementation), so subscription to this payment plan is limited in time.

but they are not all repaid their debt in the same way. First, the deal states that only half of the recognised debt will be paid up front, the remaining half being reimbursed in 12 monthly instalments indexed on the pension mobility index. Secondly, how much of the debt is reimbursed depends on whether the subscriber had sued ANSES in the past. Subscribers who had done so and obtained a definitive ruling in their favour before the 30th of May 2016 will be reimbursed for pensions incorrectly paid up to two years before they filed the lawsuit. Those who had litigated against ANSES before the 30th of May 2016 but had not yet obtained a firm ruling in their favour will be also reimbursed starting two years before the beginning of their lawsuit but within the limit of two years before subscribing to the payment plan. Finally, pensioners who had never sued ANSES before the 30th of May 2016 are only reimbursed for pensions incorrectly paid between the moment they sign the agreement with ANSES and the one where their pension is effectively corrected, leaving most of their debt unpaid.

We can thus see that the logic of this "Historic Reparation" is Bismarckian in nature: the objective is to increase inequalities between pensioners so that the level of pensions is more closely linked to the individual's contributing history. Indeed, the reparation is proportional to past levels of pensions and to the income taken for computing the first retirement pension, so those with higher pension rights get a higher correction. What is more problematic is the fact pensioners are rewarded for having sued ANSES, and thus a federal agency, in the past. This unequal treatment of pensioners is justified by the objective of curtailing litigation against ANSES and encouraging pensioners to drop their lawsuits, accepting to receive a smaller reparation than what they would have obtained through the judiciary path in exchange of a speedy payment. This measure however introduces unjustified inequalities between pensioners (why would two individuals with the same contributions get different pensions just because one of them sued ANSES and the other did not?) and encourages Argentinian citizens to sue the State in the future. This last point goes against the reform's objective of ending litigation against the State for social security matters.

A one-time funding for a one-time expense?

The funds for the historical reparation program come from two stocks: fines linked to a fiscal amnesty and the FGS. Indeed, Law 27260 also institutes a "Fiscal self-disclosure regime" accessible until the 31st of March 2017. Assets declared in this amnesty were fined between 5% and 15% of their value depending on the type of asset and the time of enrolment in the amnesty. Surprisingly enough, not only did this amnesty run very well,

it even set a world record in fiscal amnesty enrolment as a percent of GDP (around 25% of GDP). The first figures that were made public at the end of the fiscal amnesty stated that a total of 116.8 billion dollars worth of assets were declared to tax authorities (Franco, 2017), and 9.522 billions of dollars in fines, or 148.6 billions of pesos (1.8% of fourth quarter of 2016's GDP), were collected to pay for the increased retirement pensions. This first estimation is slightly above the 142,501.75 million pesos that ANSES actually ended up receiving due to the fiscal amnesty, of which 103,530.790 and 38,970.960 were respectively transferred in 2016 and 2017³⁵. In any case, these figures are far above the most optimistic *ex ante* previsions made by the government, who expected to collect funds for the reparation program ranging between 30 billions (Franco, 2016) and 60 billions (Burgueño, 2016) of pesos when the amnesty was being discussed and implemented. We have moreover found that penalties collected in 2016 were largely invested in financial products³⁶ and produced returns of 26,370.9 million pesos in 2017, as can be deduced from that year's Savings-Investment-Funding account. As such, the actual funds derived from the fiscal amnesty penalties were equal to 168,872.65 million pesos by the end of 2017. Since we estimate total expenses on the historical reparation program for years 2016 and 2017 to reach 72,883.834 million pesos (see Appendix A), there were still by the end of 2017 95,988.816 million pesos left to pay for this benefit, or 0.8% of the fourth quarter of 2017 GDP.

Despite this amnesty's significant success, funds allocated to ANSES will be fully spent by 2019, according to our simulations laid out in section 3.2 and Appendix U of Chapter 3. Therefore, in the short run it will be the FGS that will fully fund this benefit. At first glance, this makes it seem that the program's funding is unsustainable, since a Fund worth 10.4%³⁷ of GDP in December 2017 will have to shoulder a yearly additional expense that was equal to 0.62% of GDP in 2017, as shown in Appendix A. However, the cost of the historical reparation program is bounded in time: since the period under litigation is essentially comprised between 2002 and 2006 and does not go beyond 2012 (see Box 1), a limited number of cohorts are concerned by this pension re-evaluation. As these age and

³⁵Source: own computation using the 2016 Investment Account, the 2017 Savings-Investment-Funding account of the public sector, 2017 data from the Federal Taxes Commission and from AFIP tax recovery.

³⁶The 2016 Investment Account's Appendix 3.15. portrays the financial application of funds by social security institutions, including ANSES and the FGS. It shows the final investment in bonds or securities of 147.3 billion pesos was significantly higher than the initial credit of 55.2 billion pesos foreseen in the 2016 budget. The difference between these two values (92.1 billion pesos) is very close to the difference between fiscal amnesty funds received by ANSES in 2016 (103.5 billion pesos) and historical reparation payments made by ANSES in 2016 (7.1 billion pesos, as computed in Appendix A), which are equal to 96.5 billion pesos. This means this increased investment in bonds and securities by social security institutions (most likely ANSES) is directly linked to the leftover fiscal amnesty penalties.

³⁷Source: own calculus using (ANSES, 2018) and market price GDP of the fourth quarter of 2017.

eventually die, the program's cost will also progressively decline. The fact this program is only funded through stocks of revenue (the fiscal amnesty and the FGS) will thus not necessarily mean it will spill over current expenses and weigh on the federal budget. We simulate the impact of this program on the FGS through the microsimulation model we develop in this thesis, and the detailed results of these specific simulations can be found in section 3.2 and Appendix U of Chapter 3. Our simulations show the FGS should go from 10.1% of the fourth quarter of 2017 GDP in December 2017 (a proportion we assume it retains by the end of 2018) to 4.4% of GDP in our central³⁸ economic scenario as a result of these payments. In real terms, it should decrease by 41%³⁹ between 2017 and 2040. These figures are significantly higher than other more pessimistic *ex ante* projections that expected the Fund to be mostly depleted by the plan, reaching 1.4% of GDP by 2027 (ITEGA, 2016). In any case, it is not clear that the FGS will actually be used to fund the historical reparation program once the funds from the fiscal amnesty penalties run out. The comprehensive reform of the retirement system that is scheduled by 2019 may indeed contemplate alternative sources of funding that reduce this loss in the Fund's value. This hypothesis is likely since 57% (ANSES, 2018, p. 10) of this Fund's assets were invested in Argentinian federal debt bonds during the fourth quarter of 2017. The Argentinian government will probably be tempted to keep such an important (and indulgent) creditor. Also, making the FGS refrain from buying new debt bonds or even liquidate some of its capital would put a strain in Argentina's sovereign debt bonds' roll-over in a moment where the government is cut off from international markets funding and in the midst of a stand-by agreement with the IMF. This last point has been in particular made clear by the currency crisis that started in May 2018, which made it sign a stand-by arrangement with the IMF in June 2018.

Overall, the 2016 pension reform gave an answer to three issues that had been left unanswered. The introduction of a universal pension for the elderly guarantees a universal access to a pension for those aged 65 or more without needing to periodically renew pension moratoriums. The deal reached with the provinces gives them back all the "co-participable" funds that in the spirit of the 1994 Constitution they were entitled to. And the historical reparation program implies a sizeable increase in pension spending in order to abide by the Supreme Court of Justice's rulings against ANSES and curtail further litigation against this agency (see Box 1). We have shown all these measures are a heavy burden on the federal budget and on the FGS, although the fiscal amnesty and the design

³⁸In our low and high economic scenarios, the FGS should respectively reach 3.8% and 4.9% of GDP by 2040.

³⁹In our low and high economic scenarios, the real value of its assets should decrease by respectively 63% and 13% between those dates.

of the two former reforms delay the full impact of these measures on federal finances and the FGS until 2018 or 2019. The reform scheduled by 2019 is thus crucial: were it to fail to find durable sources of funding for all these three measures, a heavy strain will be put on both the federal budget and the FGS. Since Argentina already has troubles funding itself in international financial markets (as evidenced by the May 2018 currency crisis) and is even negotiating a stand-by arrangement with the IMF, it is very unlikely the federal budget will be able to shoulder this deficit. We will study these elements more in detail when we estimate the effect of these reforms on ANSES long-term sustainability in Chapter 3. We will for the time being resume our presentation of Argentina's social security system through a review of its most important benefits: retirement pensions, child benefits and the pension mobility index.

1.1.3 Computing social security and family benefits

As we have seen before, most of Argentina's federal-level social security system is run by a single agency, ANSES. Although it originally only managed contributory benefits, such as retirement pensions, derived pension rights, unemployment benefits and contributory child benefits, today most of the benefits it gives are of a non-contributory nature, be it the different retirement benefits obtained through pension moratoriums, the universal pension for the elderly adult or the Universal Child Benefits (AUH). In this section we will describe in detail the computation rules of ANSES main benefits: contributory retirement pensions, 26970 Moratorium Law pensions, derived pensions and child benefits. Finally, we will study the pensions' indexation rule as established by Law 26417, which was further extended to family benefits by Law 27160 starting from March 2016, and modified by Law 27426 since March 2018.

Contributory retirement pensions

Since the comprehensive social security reform of 1994, the conditions to obtain a contributory retirement pension have been particularly stringent for a developing country. As detailed in Law 24241 Art. 19, to retire a worker needs to have contributed at least 30 years and reached retirement age (60 for women, 65 for men). However, for every two years exceeding retirement age, this required number of years decreases by one year. So, for instance, a woman aged 62 is only required to contribute 29 years in order to retire. Every individual that meets these conditions gets access to the *PBU* (*Prestación Básica*

Universal), a fixed amount benefit determined by ANSES⁴⁰, and may claim a retirement pension $P = PBU + PC + PAP$.

Variables *PC* (*Prestación Compensatoria*) and *PAP* (*Prestación Adicional por Permanencia*) are only available for individuals that have access to the *PBU* (and can thus retire). The *PC* and the *PAP* are most of the time functionally equivalent. Following Article 24 of Law 24241, a simplified (the full formula is available in Appendix B) version of their computation rule is: $PC = 0.015 \times N \times I$. *N* is the number of contributed years and *I* the reference income when the individual liquidates his retirement pension. While the reference income *I* is the same for both *PC* and *PAP*, they are respectively computed on years validated before and after July 1994. The only other difference between the *PC* and the *PAP* is that for the *PC*, Article 24 of Law 24241 states that the replacement ratio cannot be computed with more than 35 years of contributions. However, Decree 679/1995 regulating Article 24 of Law 24241 specifies that "in order to cast away all doubt, the implementation of Article 30 of Law 24241 establishes that the computation of the [PAP] will be carried out by considering the total of months with contributions, that is, with no limitation regarding the time to take into account". Hence, this cap would only apply to generations having started work more than 35 years before 1994, that is since 1959, and has thus not concerned generations retiring since at least the mid 2000's.

Regarding the reference income, although it is calculated identically for the *PC* and for the *PAP*, according to Article 24 of Law 24241, it is computed differently for periods of dependent and independent work. For the former, it is equal to the mean wages earned during the ten years preceding retirement; and for the latter, it is the average of last 35 years' reference income of the independent worker categories they were enlisted in. If an individual has had both dependent and independent labour spells, then its reference income is an average of both formulas, weighted each by the duration spent in each labour state. It should, finally, be noted that all these yearly values have been mensualised in Decree 679/1995. So, for instance, it is necessary to contribute 360 months in order to retire, the reference income for dependent labour is computed based on the 120 months preceding retirement and for each two months past the retirement age, one fewer month is required to retire. The explicit formula along with some computation examples is laid out in Appendix 1 of Decree 679/1995, which we reproduce in Appendix B.

All in all, with Law 24241, it is otherwise impossible to earn a retirement pension if

⁴⁰ANSES Resolution 28 /2018 Art. 4 sets the PBU at 3,619.07 pesos between April 2018 and June 2018.

contribution years are missing. There was nevertheless some flexibility at the onset of the reform, since Article 38 of Law 24241 allowed to validate seven contribution years through sworn declarations for people retiring in 1994 or 1995. This was however a temporary measure, since the number of years which it was possible to validate this way gradually decreased until it reached zero for people retiring after 2007. The only retirement option that was left for people that could not reach the required number of contribution years was hence applying for an old-age pension at age 70, managed first by ANSES and then by the Ministry of Social Development since 1996. As we have seen in the previous section, this flaw in the 1994 social security reform led to a significant decrease in pension coverage. Nevertheless, successive moratoriums were adopted in order to placate this issue, though they were limited in time or in scope. We describe their functioning in the following section.

Moratorium pensions

Pension moratoriums have become a central part of Argentina's social security system. These permitted to reach a nearly universal access to a pension for the elderly (see Figure 1.3 p. 55) and by September 2016 65% of direct retirement benefits recipients received a moratorium pension (DNPE, 2016, p. 25). In Argentina, a pension moratorium can be defined as a payment plan that allows individuals who reached retirement age to buy back contribution years until reaching the mandatory 30 years for retiring. This condition is particularly hard to reach in a country who has had a high proportion of its working age population in the informal sector or unemployed since the 1990s (see Figure 4). The years that are bought back are done so in the independent workers regime and usually in the cheapest categories, those with the lowest contributions to social security. As such, the vast majority of moratorium benefits are equal to the minimum retirement pension. The individual starts receiving a pension as soon as he paid the moratorium's first instalment, the following being discounted from future benefits. The social security debt is furthermore only partially repaid, since a significant part of the principal is condoned by ANSES and instalments are capped to 20% of the pension's value (see Appendix B) ⁴¹. These moratoriums were however typically available for a limited amount of time and only allowed buying back non contributed years before a given date, as can be seen in Table 1.1.3. Both these elements meant only some elderly cohorts had access to each pension moratorium and that their efficiency decreased in time, necessitating their continued renewal in order to keep a universal access to retirement benefits. This is why there were two

⁴¹This limit is established by Article 14, clause d) of the Law N^o 24.241 that states that deductions from social security benefits "may not exceed (...) 20% of the amount of the monthly benefit".

main waves (2006 and 2014) of pension moratoriums, each of these significantly increasing access to a pension for the elderly (see Figure 1.3 p. 55). These pension moratoriums are described more in depth in Appendix B, but Table 1.1.3 is enough to understand what these moratoriums were and how they functioned.

Table 1.1: Pension moratoriums

Moratorium	Law 24476	Law 25865/24476	Law 25994	Law 26970
Begins - ends	25/11/93-27/12/93	25/11/05 - ongoing	06/07/06 - 30/04/07	19/09/14 - 18/09/16 for men and 23/07/2019 for women
Implemented by	Decree 493/1995	Decree 1454/2005	Joint Gen. Res. 2091 and 579/2006	Decree 1556/2014
Conditions for entry	Buying back all missing years	Paying first instalment + being of retirement age. Same as Law 26970 since 18/09/2016		Same as Law 24476's + means-tested
May buy back years before:	30/09/1993		31/12/2004	31/12/2003
Indexation of instalments?	On contributions by independent workers	None. Same as Law 26970 since 18/09/2016		Pension mobility index
Can be cumulated with other pensions?	Yes	Yes, but must buy back all missing years in one instalment (ANSES Res. 884/2006, Art. 4)	No (Art. 5)	No (Art. 9)
Coverage	None	2509727 direct and 177835 survivor's benefits by September 2016 (DNPE, 2016)		821441 retirement and 8822 survivor's benefits by September 2016 (DNPE, 2016)
According to Art. 22 of Law 27260. Law 25994 moratorium should have been reinstated for one year between 18/09/16 and 18/09/17 for men turning 65 in that period. This disposition has however never been implemented, as the ANSES circular 49/16 that extends in time access to the 2014 moratorium only does it for women, so the pension moratorium ended for men on September 2016. Also, as established by Law 27260 Art. 20, Law 24476 pension moratoriums granted since 18/09/16 are means-tested and indexed following Law 26970's Art.3.				

First of all, we can see that apart from the first version of Law 24476 moratorium,

conditions for entry to these moratoriums were particularly lax. Both the permanent Law 24476 moratorium modified by Law 25865 and the temporary Law 25994 moratorium only required a first instalment to be paid out of pocket by the subscriber in order to earn a retirement benefit. Law 26970 moratorium is slightly less generous: not only is it means-tested⁴², it also indexed its instalments on pension mobility, meaning the real value of the retirement pension is significantly lowered during the five years where the subscriber pays instalments (see Appendix B). Finally, it can be seen that the only permanent moratorium, Law 25865 / 24476, can only be used to buy back non contributed years before 1993, so it allows to buy back fewer and fewer years as time goes by. The limited extension in time of Law 26970 thus means that cohorts retiring in the coming years will barely have access to pension moratoriums. Individuals of these cohorts that fail to reach the mandatory 30 years of contributions will have to resort to the less generous "Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult" that we will describe more in depth below.

The universal pension for the elderly adult

The 2016 reform Law 27260⁴³, has introduced, as we have explained earlier in this thesis, a non-contributory pension that will replace by 2019 all temporary pension moratoriums called "Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult" (Art. 13). This same Article states this benefit is available for Argentinian residents aged 65 that do not receive any retirement pension (including survivor's benefits). Naturalised Argentinian citizens must also have ten years of residence, while foreigners must have lived twenty years in the country, including the immediate ten years prior to applying for this pension. The universal pension is permanently equal to 80% of the minimum retirement pension and gives access to pensioners' health insurance⁴⁴.

This non-contributory and unconditional pension is however less generous than the previous pension moratoriums. Its amount is lower, since we have seen that Law 26970 pensioners get 100% of the minimum pension five years after subscribing to the moratorium. Also, no derived pensions are generated upon the recipient's death. Most importantly, it *de facto* pushes back the retirement age to 65 for any woman with less than 30 years of contribution. Since nearly 80% of women aged 60 did not receive any retirement

⁴²These include income, wealth and expenditures conditions as detailed in Joint General Resolutions 533 and 3673/2014's Article 8. The income conditions are similar to those for having access to contributory child benefits.

⁴³Issued the 22d of July 2016

⁴⁴More specifically, the pensioner is affiliated to the PAMI ("Thorough Medical Attention Program") run by the INSSJP ("National Social Services Institute for the Retired and Pensioners").

benefit (be it a direct pension or a survivor's benefit) before the 2006 moratoriums⁴⁵ this means a vast majority of women will not be able to retire at the minimum age, lacking the required 30 years of contributions. This reform thus follows the reform proposal issued by the IMF a few months later of setting the minimum retirement age for women to 65 years (Canales-Kriljenko *et al.* , 2016, p. 68). In order to delay the political cost this unpopular measure would have entailed, Law 26970 pension moratorium's validity was extended for women aged between 60 and 65 until the 23d of July 2019 (Art. 22), an electoral year but also when a wider structural reform of the retirement system is scheduled to take place (Art. 12).

Derived pensions: survivor's benefits

Benefits derived from retirement contributions represent a sizeable portion of pensions given by ANSES. Although we lack detailed data on their overall cost, we know for instance that in September 2016 there were 1.5 million survivor's benefits, while there were 5.1 million direct retirement benefits (DNPE, 2016, p. 21). This means that derived pensions represent 23% of total retirement pensions, a proportion consecutive to the full implementation of Law 26970 moratorium in 2014. Before that, this proportion had remained stable around 25.5% since 2008 and the full implementation of the Law 25994 moratorium (DNPE, 2016, p. 21). This is a ratio that is on par with other PAYG retirement systems. For instance, in 2013 survivor's benefits represented 22% of total retirement pensions in France (Solard *et al.* , 2015). However, for Argentina's standards, this proportion is particularly low because of the moratoriums' implementation we studied earlier. In September 2016, 3.3 million moratorium direct benefits were given while only 186,657 survivor's pensions were derived from direct moratorium benefits (DNPE, 2016, p. 25). This proportion was considerably higher before the pension moratoriums, as it reached 40% of total retirement benefits in December 2001 (DNPE, 2016, p. 21). Survivor's benefits served hence as a *de facto* minimum pension for many women who could not get a direct retirement benefit and depended on the pension derived from their late spouse's contributory benefit. So although the proportion of survivor's benefits as a percentage of total pensions should rise as pension moratoriums retirees die, its rise will be limited by the fact a vast majority of moratorium pensioners are women, as seen earlier in D'Elia *et al.* (2011). This, combined with the replacement of pension moratoriums with a universal pension that does not generate survivor's benefits upon the recipient's death, will decrease the relative weight of derived pensions in social security spending. Nevertheless, the extended access to survivor's benefits and the fact they must be at least

⁴⁵Source: own calculus using the EPHc, third quarter of 2003 - second quarter of 2006.

equal to the minimum pension as per Law 24241's Art. 125 make them essential for studying Argentina's social security system's sustainability, adequacy and redistributive power.

These derived benefits trigger either when the insured individual dies or when he is awarded an invalidity pension in the case of non-retired individuals. The latter situation is not simulated in our model, so we will focus on survivor's pensions. First of all, Art. 53 of Law 24241 establishes that the survivor's pension beneficiaries are the widow, the spouse living in a common-law union with the departed and the latter's minor children as long as they are single, and until they come of age⁴⁶. Some conditions do however exist for the deceased's concubine to receive the survivor's benefit (see Appendix D). After that, the given survivor's benefits depend on the situation of the deceased. If the departed was receiving a retirement benefit given by the SIPA (including moratorium pensions but excluding the universal pension for the elderly) survivors get what is called a "derived pension". Its amount is a fraction of the deceased's retirement pension (see Appendix D) but must be at least equal to the minimum pension. If the individual was not receiving a retirement benefit at the time of death or disability, the rightful claimants may get a survivor's benefit called "direct pension" provided the deceased had contributed a minimum number of years. The pension's amount and eligibility conditions are detailed in Appendix D, but they are more restrictive than access to the "derived pension".

All in all, survivor's pensions are quite liberally attributed to retirees' spouses and partners in a (lengthy) common-law union, which explains the high number of survivor's benefits in Argentina. There are neither income conditions for a retiree's spouse to get a survivor's benefit, nor having been married (or in an union) for a minimum number of years in order to get the benefit, nor are the pensions limited in time either. It is however more difficult for the children and spouse of the departed to get a survivor's benefit when the deceased was not receiving a retirement benefit (see Appendix D), and as such only 1% of all survivor's benefits recipients are children (DNPE, 2016, p. 22). All these elements explain why derived pensions are such a central component of Argentina's social security system, and thus why they were included in this analysis. The following section, on child benefits, will complete our overview of the SIPA benefits studied by this thesis.

⁴⁶Handicapped children benefit from the survivor's pension with no age limit, but this case is not simulated in our model.

Child benefits: contributory, non-contributory and universal

As we have seen earlier, a specificity of Argentina's social security system is that child benefits and family allowances are managed with the same funds and by the same agency that grants social security benefits. Since they represent a sizeable portion of ANSES expenditures⁴⁷, it is necessary to include them in any analysis pertaining to ANSES sustainability. Moreover, family benefits are means-tested, represent a sizeable portion of the poorer families' income and thus have an important role both in income redistribution and in fighting poverty. There are a multitude of family allowances given by ANSES, including pregnancy benefits, birth pensions or a back-to-school allowance. We will however focus here on contributory and non-contributory child benefits, which are the most important in amount (77,2% in 2010 according to Basualdo *et al.* (2012)) and number⁴⁸.

The current contributive family benefits system was formalised shortly after the retirement system's reform through Law 24714⁴⁹. This Law formalised the unification and transfer of family benefits to the SUSS, run by ANSES. It also defines the different family benefits given by ANSES and, with successive modifications that will be detailed below, is still in force today. In its first Article, it establishes a contributive subsystem for registered private sector employees and people receiving an unemployment or occupational hazards pension⁵⁰. It also institutes a non-contributive subsystem for people receiving a retirement benefit or a survivors pension. "Even though it is not explicit in Law N°24.714's text, [the latter] encompasses national public servants. In this case, the benefit's funding is made by the National Treasury through the federal budget" as specified by Hintze & Costa (2011) (p. 157). Its Article 6 defines the awarded family benefits, which are mostly means-tested and decrease with gross income. The income conditions and benefits amounts were set by the government and have only recently been indexed⁵¹ to the Retirement Mobility Index established by the Pension Mobility Law. Their current value, ranges and eligibility conditions are detailed in Appendix E. All in all, these family allowances covered a significant proportion of children, reaching 31% of people under the age of 18 in 2009 (Hintze & Costa, 2011) (Lozano *et al.*, 2009), but left out children whose both parents were unregistered workers, inactive or unemployed without an unemployment benefit.

⁴⁷For instance, they were 13,4% of total ANSES expenditures as of 2014 excluding administrative expenses. Source: own calculations with data from the 2014 *Cuenta de Inversión*, Tomo II Anexo II.3

⁴⁸Child benefits represented 80% of total family allowances in 2014, excluding the back-to-school allowance which is paid only once a year. Source: own calculations with data from the 2014 *Cuenta de Inversión*, Tomo II Anexo II.3

⁴⁹Partially issued the 6th of October 1996

⁵⁰Decree 593/2016 has extended contributory child benefits to the children of small independent registered workers, or *Monotributistas*, starting from May 2016

⁵¹This has been the case only since March 2016, following Law 27160 passed the 16th of July 2016

The AUH⁵² was implemented in this context with the rationale of granting child benefits to children of low-income households that were left out of the aforementioned family allowances system⁵³. The AUH hence modifies the first Article of Law 24714 by instituting a non-contributory subsystem for the children "belonging to family groups currently unemployed or employed in the informal economy". The benefit is equal to the highest child allowance that existed previously, that is, the one that goes to the poorest registered workers. This allowance is paid for by ANSES, which gets in return the possibility of funding family allowances with the annual returns of the FGS. Although the AUH is *de jure* restricted to individuals earning less than the minimum wage, "this condition is difficult to monitor, and hence in practice the limitation is inconsequential" (Garganta & Gasparini, 2015, p. 100). This constitutes a significant difference as compared to the aforementioned means-tested child benefits. On the other hand, receiving the AUH is conditional to medical controls, following a compulsory vaccination schedule and attending a state school. This allowance increased coverage sharply, with in 2014 55% of individuals aged 19 or less receiving a child benefit from ANSES⁵⁴. It also significantly increased available income of the poorest households with children, as explained by Garganta & Gasparini (2015), and played an important part in redistribution and tackling poverty⁵⁵. If we consider furthermore that there is a deduction in the income tax for workers with children⁵⁶ a considerable proportion of families receive a benefit for having children⁵⁷. Family allowances hence are an important component of Argentina's social security system, both in the study of its sustainability and of its adequacy and redistributive impact.

The benefits indexation rule and its replacement (2008-2017)

In a country with a structurally high inflation, the aforementioned benefits can be brought to naught if they are neither indexed nor periodically raised by the government to account for this inflation. This is what happened with the unemployment benefit, whose

⁵² *Asignación Universal por Hijo*, established by Decree 1602/2009, starting the 1st of November 2009

⁵³ A pregnancy benefit was likewise implemented. It is described in Appendix E.

⁵⁴ Source: own calculation with demographic projections from INDEC and data from 2014 *Cuenta de Inversión*, Tomo II Anexo II.3 Using this method, 22% of individuals aged 19 or less received a child benefit in 2009.

⁵⁵ See for instance (Garganta & Gasparini, 2015), (Basualdo *et al.*, 2012), (Bustos & Villafañe, 2011), (Agis *et al.*, 2010)

⁵⁶ An individual who earns enough to pay the income tax, or *Impuesto a las Ganancias*, earns too much to be eligible for family benefits.

⁵⁷ For more information, see Basualdo *et al.* (2012)

maximum value stayed constant for more than ten years until it became negligible⁵⁸. In recent years, Argentina witnessed two consecutive changes in the benefit indexation rule which both had a major and immediate impact on social security benefits' real values, due to Argentina's high inflation figures. First, the 2008 Pension Mobility Law 26417⁵⁹ introduced an automatic rule to adjust retirement pensions and survivors benefits, as well as family benefits since 2016 through Law 27160⁶⁰. Then, starting from March 2018 the Pension Reform Law 27426⁶¹ adopted a less generous indexation formula, heeding previous IMF policy recommendations (Canales-Kriljenko *et al.* , 2016).

First of all, the Pension Mobility Law introduced a bi-annual adjustment of social security benefits (on March and September). As explained in Appendix E, 50% of the benefits' increase depends on the variation of ANSES fiscal revenues (excluding in particular social security contributions), the other 50% being dependent on nominal wage increases. The benefits increase was furthermore limited to 1.03 times the increase in ANSES total revenues⁶². Finally, pensions could not under any circumstance decrease in nominal terms. This indexation rule hence tried to balance two opposing imperatives: guaranteeing the value of pensions and thus their adequacy and the financial equilibrium of the pension system. Indeed, indexing benefits on wages is on average more generous than indexing them on inflation (Blanchet *et al.* , 2016b)⁶³. As long as labour productivity increases in the long term, real wages should increase and thus social security benefits should rise faster than inflation. On the other hand, making half of the mobility depend on the evolution of ANSES fiscal revenues and introducing a cap depending on ANSES total revenues evolution introduced an in-built automatic adjustment mechanism, ensuring that benefits follow in real terms the evolution of ANSES revenues.

This indexation rule had however the inconvenient of being pro-cyclical. On the one hand, real wages are pro-cyclical, as they usually increase faster when the economy ex-

⁵⁸In 2006, its maximum amount was equal to 400 pesos a month, or 130 US\$ with 2006's exchange rate. The amount was left unchanged until Res. 2/2016 issued the 19th of May 2016 by the National Council of Labour, Productivity and the Minimum Wage raised it to 3000 pesos a month. This meant that by May 2016, the maximum unemployment pension was raised from 28 US\$ a month to 214 US\$ a month. However, by May 2017 this amount was left unchanged in nominal terms, which meant that in a year it decreased in real terms by approximately 20%.

⁵⁹Sanctioned the 15th of October 2008, the first readjustment following this rule took place the 1st of March 2009.

⁶⁰Sanctioned the 16th of July 2015, the first family benefits readjustment following this rule took place in March 2016.

⁶¹Published the 28th of December 2017.

⁶²The cap could only be applied on September's increase.

⁶³Blanchet *et al.* (2016b) study the case of France's pension system. After a series of reforms in the late 1980's, France shifted from wage to price indexation of retirement benefits, which resulted in significant reductions on retirement spending.

pands and stagnate or decrease in real terms during a recession. On the other hand, ANSES revenues are mostly comprised of social security contributions and other taxes such as the income tax or Value-Added Tax, which are also pro-cyclical. These taxes depend on real wages, formal employment and consumption which all increase when the economy expands and decrease during economic recessions. This resulted in pension mobility losing to inflation between the last quarter of 2015 and the first quarter of 2017: as wages and tax collection decreased in real terms, so did the benefits indexed on the pension mobility law, reducing them just as the economy entered in recession. Thus, pensions increased in nominal terms between September 2015 and March 2017 by 48.75%, while in that same period inflation figures⁶⁴ reached 58.9%. This means that in a year and a half pensions decreased by $\frac{1+0.4875}{1+0.589} - 1 = 6.4\%$ in real terms.

With the joint argument of decoupling social security benefits from the economic cycle and curbing social security expenditure, the pension mobility law was replaced by a less generous index instituted by the Pension Reform Law 27426. Its first Article makes pension mobility depend 30% on the evolution of the RIPTTE wage index and 70% on the National Consumer Price Index (IPCN). It nevertheless increases the frequency of nominal adjustments, as these intervene every three months instead of the previous six months. This measure follows the policy reform proposed by the IMF of "indexing benefits (and actualizing past wages) only to realized inflation [which] would still allow retirees to preserve the real value of their benefit, but (...) would reduce the increase in pension spending" (Canales-Kriljenko *et al.*, 2016, p. 67). It is true this formula would have mitigated the real decrease in pensions we described in the previous paragraph, but it will decrease social security benefits both in the short and in the long term, as explained in Appendix E. Law 27426 partially compensates this decrease in pensions by guaranteeing to all pensioners who had contributed the required 30 years before retiring a pension at least equal to 82% of the minimum wage (Art. 5). As we explain in Appendix E, this measure does not compensate in the short-term the loss of revenue derived from this reform for retirees with 30 years of contributions, but the relevance of this guarantee will increase in the long run as the minimum pension decreases as a percentage of the minimum wage. We will explain this last point in detail in our Chapter 3.

⁶⁴Due to the controversy on official inflation figures up to October 2015 and the absence of nationwide monthly inflation figures between November 2015 and April 2016 (see Figure 1.2) we use an average of the Consumer Prices Index issued by the province of San Luis and the Autonomous City of Buenos Aires (CABA).

1.1.4 Social security contributions

The last characteristic of Argentina's social security system is compulsory contributions to ANSES. Bismarckian in its design, as we explained in section 1.1.1, the social security system is mainly financed by contributions paid by formal workers and their employers. In 2015, these sources of income represented 63% of ANSES current revenues (excluding figurative revenues), or 5.8% of GDP⁶⁵. We will thus review here the current legislative framework regarding social security contributions, with the goal to later apply it in our prospective study of ANSES accounts.

Employer and employee's contributions

First of all, employees contributions to social security reach 17% of their gross wage. Of these, 11 points go to ANSES to pay for retirement benefits (Art. 11 of Law 24241), 3 points go to fund the health coverage of the elderly (PAMI) run by the National Institute of Social Service for Retirees and Pensioners (INSSJP) (Art. 8 of Law 19032) and 3 points are assigned to their own compulsory healthcare. Of these, 90% go to their *Obra social*⁶⁶ (Art. 16 of Law 23660) and 10% (so 0.3 points) go to fund the Solidarity Redistribution Fund (previously called ANSSAL) (Art. 22 of Law 23661) that helps even out resources between sectoral *Obras sociales*.

Employers contributions to social security are more complicated to determine. At the eve of the fiscal reform Law 27430, these depended on the firm's characteristics and economic sector. Decree 814/2001⁶⁷'s second Article, modified by the "zero deficit" Law 25453⁶⁸ and by the 2002 national budget Law 25565⁶⁹ specified that firms of the service and trade sectors would pay contributions equal to 21% of the gross wage (Art. 2 section a) of Decree 814/2001), while other employers (including the public sector) would only pay contributions equal to 17% of the gross wage (Art. 2 section b) of Decree 814/2001). In theory, SMEs also pay 17% in contributions (following Law 24467). As shown by Lovero (2017) however, a maximum turnover limitation established by Decree 1009 of year 2001⁷⁰ and left unchanged since, despite high inflation figures, meant many SMEs from

⁶⁵Source: own computation based on the 2015 Investment Account, Appendix 3.14, by the Nation's General Accounts agency (CGN, 2015); ministry of Economy

⁶⁶In Argentina, compulsory healthcare for formal wage-earners is given by non-profit organisations called *Obras sociales*. These are usually linked to labour unions or to the public sector. They operate under Law 23660, issued the 5th of January 1989.

⁶⁷Issued the 20th of June 2001.

⁶⁸Issued the 31st of July 2001

⁶⁹Issued the 21st of March 2002

⁷⁰Issued the 13th of August 2001

the services sector paid 21% of contributions, although the exact proportion is unavailable. If we ignore the size of the firm, 49.7% of formal wage-earners work in firms subject to Art. 2 section a) of Decree 814/2001, while the remaining 50.3% work in the public sector or in firms subject to Art. 2 section b) of Decree 814/2001⁷¹. The following table, taken from (Lovero, 2017, p. 10) and complemented with contributions to employee’s healthcare (*Obra social*) established by Art. 16 of Law 23660, describes the destination of these contributions by employer.

Table 1.2: Contributions to social security by employer type and destination.

Subsystem	Legislation	Contributions: Decree 814/01	
		Art. 2 section b)	Art. 2 section a)
SIPA (see Section 1.1.1)	Law 24241	10.17%	12.71%
INSSJP - PAMI	Law 24241	1.5%	1.62%
Family Benefits Regime (AAFF)	Law 24714	4.44%	5.56%
National Employment Fund (FNE)	Law 24013	0.89%	1.11%
Subtotal		17%	21%
<i>Obras sociales</i> (health insurance)	Law 23660	5.4%	5.4%
Solidarity Redistribution Fund (ex ANSSAL)	Law 23661	0.6%	0.6%
Total		23%	27%

Source: (Lovero, 2017, p. 10) and Law 23660 Art. 16. The PAMI is the compulsory health insurance of the elderly, open in particular to all recipients of a SIPA retirement pension (those given by ANSES).

As we explained earlier in this section, ANSES manages retirement, family and unemployment benefits. As such, employers contributions to ANSES reach 15.5% of the gross wage for employers under Art.2 section b) (out of the tertiary sector, SMEs or governmental bodies) and 19.38% for employers under Art. 2 section a). Finally, Art. 9 of Law 24241 establishes both a minimum and a maximum taxable income for the computation of social security contributions, which are adjusted following the pension mobility formula ⁷².

However, a recent reform has changed both the level of employers contributions and their destination. First of all, the fiscal reform Law 27430⁷³ Art. 166 lets the federal

⁷¹Source: own computation on EPHc data (2003-2015).

⁷²ANSES Resolution 176-E /2017 Art. 7 sets the minimum and maximum taxable income for the period spanning September 2017 and March 2018 at respectively 2,520.60 and 81,918.55 pesos

⁷³Issued the 29th of December 2017.

government decide of the repartition of employer's contributions between ANSES and the INSSJP-PAMI (leaving aside the 6% that go to healthcare). It also gradually unifies employers contributions across economic sectors, so that they are set at 19.5% by 2022⁷⁴. Civil servants are however excluded from this measure, so the employer's social security contributions public administrations will pay for their workers will stay unchanged at 17%. This reform moreover gradually introduces a threshold under which the employer does not pay social security contributions⁷⁵. By 2022, all income under 12,000 pesos⁷⁶ at constant January 2018 prices will be taken out of the computation of employers contributions. That is, if by 2022 a worker earns 20,000 constant January 2018 pesos, he will pay employee's contributions on his 20,000 pesos while his employer will pay employer's contributions on 8,000 pesos only. This measure is an incentive for the recruitment of low-income workers, seeking to tackle informal labour. It however represents a loss in revenue for social security that is not compensated in any way and may introduce undesired threshold effects, discouraging the payment of wages above 12,000 (January 2018) pesos. The long-term impact of this measure on ANSES accounts will be studied in Chapter 3 of this thesis.

Independent workers contributions

Formal independent workers also contribute to ANSES, but how much so depends on their category. Independent workers in Argentina can enlist in two different social security regimes. First, the Autonomous Workers regime has the highest social security contributions and is compulsory for the wealthiest or those managing bigger firms. According to Art. 11 of Law 24241, they are meant to contribute 27% of their reference income to ANSES (which is equal to the sum of employer and employee's contributions to ANSES as established by that Article) and 5% to the PAMI (following Art. 8 of Law 19032). Their reference income is determined by their belonging to different subcategories of autonomous workers. As of today, only Categories II and V are *de facto* accessible for respectively own-account workers and entrepreneurs⁷⁷. All Autonomous workers categories and their characteristics can be found in Appendix F.

⁷⁴See Art. 173 of Law 27430 for the transition up to 19.5% of contributions for employers included respectively in section a) and b) of Decree 814/2001, Art. 2.

⁷⁵This threshold is introduced by Art. 167 of Law 27430, and the implementation schedule is laid out in this law's Art. 173.

⁷⁶This represented 640 US dollars with the exchange rate of the 12th of January 2018.

⁷⁷Categories I, III and IV are means-tested. However, these income limitations have never been changed since their implementation in 2007. For instance, as of January 2018 Category IV is reserved to entrepreneurs that earn less than 110 US dollars a month. As such, it is in today impossible as of today to subscribe to these Categories.

Secondly, there is a simplified regime for small contributors, commonly called *Monotributo*, established in 1998 by Law 24977⁷⁸. Created in order to foster the formalisation of small independent workers, it drastically reduces the taxes and contributions they pay. Instead of having them pay VAT, corporate tax or social security and health insurance contributions as a percentage of sales or income, the amount they pay is fixed and depends on their *Monotributo* category. Adherence to this simplified fiscal regime and to a particular *Monotributo* category depends on the independent worker's income and his firm's characteristics, which are described in Appendix F.

However, as we show in Appendix F, social security contributions of both Autonomous workers and *Monotributistas* are low when compared to those made by wage-earners. The consequence of this is that independent workers retirement rights are low, and seldom give access to a pension higher than the legal minimum. In practice, only Category V Autonomous workers may expect to get a retirement pension higher than the minimum. Autonomous workers in Category II do not contribute enough, and *Monotributistas* are even *de jure* barred from getting retirement benefits higher than the minimum pension⁷⁹. We nevertheless take into account independent workers social security contributions and retirement rights in both our prospective and retrospective microsimulation models, following the rules laid out in Appendix F.

With this, we have finished our review of the Argentinian social security legislation that is relevant for our model. We have reviewed its history and the sometimes gradual, sometimes systemic, changes it has experienced. We have laid out in detail the computation of the most important social security benefits and their accessibility conditions, which we reproduce in our simulations. We also give a thorough description of compulsory contributions to social security and even take into account the latest reforms on the matter, including the Law 27430 fiscal reform of December 2017. In addition to the necessary presence of this legislative section in our thesis, we believe in the academic value of this summary of Argentinian legislation in the matter since to the best of our knowledge there is no work written in English that describes it in such detail. The various reforms it has witnessed, the wide pension moratoriums progressively replaced by a universal pension benefit and the quite unique pension mobility index Argentina has adopted ought to be of interest in the field of social security, to which we contribute in this section. Before

⁷⁸Published the 6th of July 1998.

⁷⁹As established by Law 24977's Art. 42., *Monotributistas* do not contribute in order to get the PAP (presented in section 1.1.3), which is what makes getting a retirement benefit higher than the legal minimum possible. The exact formula is laid out in Appendix B.

presenting our dynamic microsimulation model in Chapter 2, we must nevertheless present how we studied, treated and harmonised two important data sources our model has been calibrated and estimated on: the EPH survey (1974-2017) and other sources for real wages (1970-2017).

1.2 Study and treatment of our data sources: the EPH surveys (1974 – 2017)

This work relies mostly on one publicly available individual-level dataset: the EPH, *Encuesta Permanente de Hogares*, or Permanent Household Survey. It started in 1974 and witnessed gradual improvements both in pace, number of cities surveyed and questionnaire content. Since 2003, under the name of EPHc (or continuous EPH), it has had a quarterly pace and is representative of most of the country’s urban population. This section will start with a review of this survey’s history and characteristics. Although it will be shown to be an extremely rich dataset in what regards labour-market, income, education and family variables, some information that is important for the development of a dynamic microsimulation model for Argentina’s social security is not directly available in this dataset. The second section will hence describe the identification strategy of formal independent work in the 1974-2015 period and of both dependent and independent formal work before 2003, because it is only in the EPHc that wage-earners answer directly whether they make social security contributions. Finally, the third section studies the identification of family links in the surveyed households, which is not straightforward for extended families.

1.2.1 Presentation of the EPH: its history, evolution and characteristics

The EPH survey covers a large time period, stretching as far back as October 1974. It has from its inception contained individual-level data, and a significant portion of the questionnaire has remained relatively stable, allowing for a comparability of different waves over more than 40 years. Fields covered include labour-market state, income and its sources, housing characteristics, the employing firm’s information, family links, migration and education. It is unusual for a developing country to count on such long-term micro datasets, a similar example being Brazil’s National Household Sample Survey (PNAD), which has been carried out annually since September 1976. This makes it a valuable historical source when studying the living conditions of Argentina’s urban population over

time. However, while the PNAD kept an annual pace and did not suffer from major interruptions since its inception, Argentina's EPH was not issued at a regular pace until the mid 1980s, had to wait until 1990 to have the same questionnaire for most cities and 1995 to see all the cities interviewed with the same questionnaire. Hence, although since as early as 1983 most of the major cities at the time were interviewed, the current coverage of 31 cities and agglomerations was only reached in October 2002 (the third quarter of 2006 for the EPHc).

When the EPH had different questionnaires for different cities, their quality was uneven. Early on, the Work (BT) and User (BU) bases had a similar questionnaire that was quite thorough in what regards labour-market information. However, the BU, intended to be more user friendly, is less complete than the BT. For instance, the latter has information on individual total monthly income (variable p21), while the BU only has hourly income information (variable P47hor) and total hours worked in the reference week (variable Horastot). The information regarding benefits linked to the occupation, such as retirement contributions, healthcare or paid holidays is also of poorer quality than in the BT, which forces us to adopt an identification strategy we will discuss further down. Finally, the R2 questionnaire, originally intended to be temporary while waiting for the extension of the other questionnaires to cities outside the capital, is the less complete of all. It for instance lacks information on the labour position's level of qualification as well as any information on the firm the respondent works in. First introduced in 1983, its use only stopped in 1995 when the extended user base (BUA) was implemented in all cities. As such, we do not use the R2 in this study. The BUA is very similar to the BT, despite some modifications. With the introduction of the EPHc in the third quarter of 2003, the questionnaire slightly changed once more. The most significant change for this study has however been the introduction of two questions for wage-earners, pp07h and pp07j, where they answer whether they contribute, by themselves or in the context of their job, to a retirement system. Additionally, the annual urban households survey (EAHU) has been carried out since the third quarter of 2011, with an annual pace. It surveys all towns of at least 2000 inhabitants with the same questionnaire than the EPH. It will not however be studied in this work, since for this thesis' dynamic microsimulation model a quarterly pace is preferable, as social security contributions are computed at the monthly level when determining pension rights. Finally, in the wake of the change in government in December 2015 the EPHc was temporarily discontinued following allegations of fraudulent management and tampering with the EPHc data since the INDEC's loss of autonomy with regard to the federal government in 2007 (INDEC, 2016). As a result, a new version of the EPH is being issued since the second quarter of 2016. We will further

discuss this issue below.

Before the introduction of the continuous EPH in May 2003, the punctual EPH varied slowly developed and varied over time regarding its characteristics and the population it covered. Between October 1974 and May 2003 punctual EPH surveys were carried out on March and October (1986-2003) and on October (1974, 1980, 1981, 1982 and 1985). Up until 1989, only Buenos Aires' city and metropolitan area were surveyed with the BT or the BU, while the R2 was used in provincial urban centres, a questionnaire we do not use in our work for reasons stated above. Starting from May 1990, other cities from across the country were progressively added to the punctual EPH until the last three were incorporated in 2006, although most of Argentina's medium to large cities had already been added to the EPH sample by October 1995. Similar, but evolving questionnaires were used over time: between 1974 and 1994, the User and Working bases (BU and BT); then between 1995 and March 2003 the Expanded User Base (BUA) was established and used in all surveyed cities. Finally, the EPHc introduced a new questionnaire, with slight but important upgrades, as we will see below.

As of today, the EPHc covers the 2003-2017 period. This survey studies a randomised sample of the population of 31 Argentinian cities and metropolitan areas. These represent most of Argentina's urban population, and hence most of its inhabitants, since about 91% of Argentinians live in towns of 2000 and more inhabitants⁸⁰. Each household is surveyed four times all in all: two consecutive quarters first, then after a break of six months two other consecutive quarters. This allows for a rotation in the studied population while still making it possible to study quarterly as well as yearly transitions. An average of around 50000 individuals are interviewed each quarter. There are however two main issues that the EPHc has recently faced and that hinder its trustworthiness. First of all, the second quarter of 2014 presents some unexplained inconsistencies in household identification variables that make studying individual transitions involving that quarter impossible. For instance, a household id that was used during the first quarter of 2014 for a household located in a given Province is used the second quarter for a household located in another Province, even though household ids are supposed to be unique across EPHc waves. Secondly, following a replacement of INDEC's directors consecutive to the change in government in December 2015, the EPHc's diffusion was cancelled for the second half of 2015 and the first quarter of 2016 on the grounds of alleged irregularities while carrying out the Survey during the 2007-2015 period (INDEC, 2016). The EPHc's micro-level

⁸⁰Source: own calculus based on 2010 Argentinian Census data (Censo Nacional de Población, Hogares y Viviendas, 2010), INDEC.

dataset has since resumed publication, but the available waves (second and third quarters of 2016) are incompatible with earlier waves. More specifically, individual household id variables from the second quarter of 2015 do not match those of the second quarter of 2016. We cannot hence use 2016 datasets for studying yearly transitions, and since we do not know to what extent they differ from surveys carried out in the 2003-2015 period, we prefer to refrain from estimating any of the equations simulating individual behaviour or income with these datasets. The questionnaire itself barely changed with respect of the older version of the EPHc (for instance, variable CH05 recording the respondent's date of birth has been introduced). This means that a couple of years from now, when additional waves of this new version of the EPHc will have been released, it should be possible to re-calibrate the model by using only the new version of the EPHc. Despite this, we use both of these waves as starting points of our prospective and retrospective simulations. We also compute the new EPHc's waves labour-market participation rates for aligning our dynamic microsimulation estimations, as will be further explained in Chapter 2.

Despite the recent limitations in what regards the EPHc and their recently denounced irregularities for the 2007-2015 periods, this survey still portrays accurately the current labour-market situation of the surveyed households. We get individual income by source, hours worked, labour-market state, length of employment or unemployment, characteristics of the employing firm and benefits included in the contract for wage-earners, including social security contributions. There is also information regarding the level of education, family links and living conditions. As such, this survey is the main source of information for unemployment, underemployment, informality and poverty levels in Argentina. This dataset, as it usually is the case with household surveys, lacks however information on individual careers, and as such is insufficient for computing retirement pension rights. These will be estimated in this work through dynamic microsimulation. Nevertheless, the identification of all pertinent labour-market states, as well as of family links, requires additional work on the 1974-2015 period, and will be described in the sections below.

1.2.2 Identifying formal workers in the EPH (1974 – 2017)

There are five labour-market states relevant for social security in Argentina. First, inactivity includes all individuals out of the labour force. Then, unemployment concerns people that are actively looking for a job, which following some conditions makes them eligible *de jure* to unemployment benefits given by ANSES, although their relevancy has been brought to naught as explained in section 1.1.2. The universe of non-contributors is completed by unregistered workers, who are working without making the compulsory

social security contributions, and as such are not accumulating pension rights. Finally, we have decided to distinguish formal wage-earners from formal independent workers among social security contributors due to the different regulations and contributions they are subjected to, which we surveyed in sections 1.1.3 and 1.1.4. Identifying inactive and unemployed people is straightforward in all EPH surveys, as is telling apart dependent labour from independent work. However, distinguishing formal from informal employment, and particularly registered from unregistered independent work, is more complicated, and will be described in the following section.

The definitions of labour formality: a review of the literature

Informal economy is a relatively new field of study in economics, and has but until recently received little attention, maybe because of it being most prevalent in developing countries. Indeed, estimations of the informal economy's size for the 1989-1993 period range between 12% of GNP for OECD countries, 25% for the former Soviet Union, 39% for Latin America or 44% of GNP for Africa (Gerxhani, 2004, p. 208), (Schneider & Enste, 2003). Originated in the fields of anthropology and sociology, the informal sector was first formalised in economics by the ILO (ILO, 1972) when studying employment in Kenya. This report states that "a significant proportion of adults not in enumerated employment are engaged in other activities providing economic goods and services to the urban population: they are members of the informal sector (...), frequently living in squatter settlements devoid of most essential services (...). Informal economic activity (...) is often economically efficient, productive and creative. In such activity people practise a variety of modern trades and crafts, just as in the formal sector, but without the formal sector's protection from competition or its favoured access to credit and sophisticated technology." (ILO, 1972, p. 51). The informal sector is thus defined as urban employment out of the registered sector, the latter comprised of the public sector and large private companies. It includes self-employment as well as dependent employment and is linked to the problem of the working poor in Kenya, since their income is seldom enough to breach the poverty line.

Technically speaking, that seminal paper by the ILO (1972) adopts a sectoral definition of urban informal labour by defining it as all employment out of the formal sectors of the urban economy. From a methodological point of view however, this approach is close to a legalistic definition of informality. It considers that workers whose activities are not registered and that do not fulfil their tributary, regulatory and social security obligations are informal. Later work, notably by de Soto (1990), developed the sectoral definition of informal labour. It distinguishes informal from formal activities through

the legal status of firms. In this approach, informality is a choice undertaken by the self-employed and owners of small firms, typically in low-productivity sectors, who decide not to abide by the current regulatory framework (Gerxhani, 2004). Methodologically speaking, this approach, focusing on the firms' characteristics, gave way to the sectoral definition of informality, where it is the self-employed and small firms in low productivity sectors, typically in services, that represent the informal sector. This methodology can also be extended to the grey economy, where an individual or firm under-declares to the fiscal authorities its labour income or profits, or to the economy derived from illegal activities such as drug trafficking, which is *per se* undeclared to the authorities.

Both approaches are nowadays used by the literature for studying informality. The legalistic definition is mostly mobilised for studying dependent informal work, since the necessary information is often included in household surveys in emerging and developing countries (see for Argentina Garganta & Gasparini (2015), Bosch & Maloney (2010) or Bertranou *et al.* (2013)). Due to scarce availability of the data, this definition is rarely used for independent workers, although exceptions do exist (De Paula & Scheinkman (2011) use Brazil's ECINF survey which asks the self-employed and owners of small firms whether their business is registered). It is most useful in emerging countries, where both formal and informal work represent a sizeable share of the labour force. The sectoral approach on the other hand is often mobilised to study informal independent employment (Maurizio, 2012) and sometimes all informal employment in countries where social security is not very developed (Günther & Launov, 2012). It is also useful for international comparisons, since the same definition of informality can be applied to a variety of countries regardless of their levels of development and social security systems (see Mesa-Lago (2008) or Gasparini & Tornarolli (2009) for Latin America). In some papers it is also pushed to the point where the informal sector consists exclusively of the self-employed and owners of small firms, while the formal sector is made of larger firms' employees (Fiess *et al.* , 2010).

It should however be noted that the two definitions are not equivalent. As Henley *et al.* (2009) point out for the case of Brazil, "the measures of informality based on contract and social security status (measures A and B) may distinguish very different groups of workers compared to the measure based on activity (measure C) "(Henley *et al.* , 2009, p. 998). This study shows that in 2004 although 40% of the workforce was classified as informal following measures A B and C, and 37% as belonging to the formal sector for each of the three retained measures, 23% of the workforce was classified as informal by one of these measures and as formal by another. For instance, 9% of the workforce was classified as informal following the legalistic definition (A and B) but as formal following the sec-

toral definition (C) and 6% of the workforce was informal following measure C but formal according to measures A and B. Thus, the informal sector also has workers contributing to social security, and there are unregistered workers within the formal sector. As such, the retained definition of informality is not trivial, even though it is often conditioned by the data at hand. In the rest of this section we will hence describe the definition we adopted for measuring informality throughout the different waves of our dataset. First for measuring informal dependent labour, then for identifying formal independent workers.

Our definitions for formal salaried and independent work in the EPH (1974-2017)

The main objective of this work is to estimate both contributions to social security and accumulated pension rights. As such, the relevant definition of informality for this thesis is legalistic: workers not contributing to social security, thus both not funding it but also getting lower pensions at retirement, are informal. It could be argued workers who benefit from at least some of the benefits usually linked to formal dependent work (paid holidays, 13th month, paid sick leave, healthcare insurance) should count as formal whereas only workers without any benefits are truly informal. Nevertheless, only a minority of wage-earners do not contribute to social security while also having other benefits (11% of wage-earners⁸¹) or contributed to social security without having any of the aforementioned benefits (3%⁸²). The remaining 87% either contributed to social security and had at least one of these benefits (57%⁸³ of wage-earners) or did not contribute to social security and did not have any of the aforementioned benefits (28%⁸⁴ of wage-earners). Thus, contributing to social security is a reasonable indicator of being in the formal sector and having access to social rights. Luckily, the EPHc allows for a precise measurement of formal salaried work in the 2003-2015 period. Surveyed wage-earners are asked questions pp07H ("Do you have in this work retirement deductions?") and pp07I ("Do you, on your own, contribute to any retirement system?") which are rarely left unanswered, and that measure directly contributions to the pension system. As such, we have considered as formal wage-earners individuals answering positively to any of these questions.

As is explained in Appendix G.2, we are able to define formal dependent labour as contributing to a retirement system even in older EPH datasets (1974-2003). This gives us a coherent legalistic definition of registered wage-earners across the varying questionnaires

⁸¹Source: own computation using the EPHc, 2003-2015.

⁸²Source: Ibid.

⁸³Source: Ibid

⁸⁴Source: Ibid.

adopted by the EPH (described in section 1.2.1). As a result, there are no jumps in the proportion of formal wage-earners when the questionnaire adopted by the EPH changes across the 1974-2017 period, as will be seen in Figures 1.7 to 1.9 analysed in pages 97 to 99. This makes a long-term measurement of formal dependent employment possible, which will be essential for reconstituting past plausible labour careers in Chapter 2.

However, no similar questions are made to independent workers. Since these are not asked either whether their business or self-employed activity is registered nor if they contribute to a social security system, it is not possible to use a similar legalistic definition of labour formality for independent workers. We are thus compelled to employ a sectoral definition of formal independent labour. The literature tends to classify as informal the self-employed or owners of small firms of low-productivity sectors. As Henley *et al.* (2009) explain, "household or individual surveys typically used may not provide information on the social security status of the self-employed or small employer. So studies often rely on a "hybrid" definition of informality in which employees are classified according to social security status. Own-account workers are classified as entirely informal and employers classified according to either or both the size of their business (number of employees) or the activity of the business."(Henley *et al.* , 2009, p. 994).

Nevertheless, it would be incorrect for our study of Argentina's social security system to follow the literature mentioned by Henley *et al.* (2009) and leave almost all independent workers out of the formal workforce. First, because the labour-market states we take on for our simulations are a crucial explanatory variable in our estimation of Mincer wage equations, as will be seen in section 2.3. It is to be expected that skilled own-account workers and business owners earn significantly more than informal wage-earners or independent workers with low qualification. Mixing them together would thus strongly bias our simulation of labour income. On the other hand, putting all independent workers in the informal sector could make sense as far as social security rights and contributions are concerned. This is because independent workers in Argentina have low social security contributions (and thus modest pension rights), specifically when they choose to be registered under the small contributors program (the *Monotributo*). Still, as has been studied in section 1.1.3., independent labour contributions are taken into account for reaching the minimum 30 years of contributions to earn a contributory retirement pension just as formal dependent labour spells. Also, contributions made by independent workers under the Autonomous workers regime represent 27% of each category's reference income (see Appendix F). Although the latter are today below the mean wage of formal wage-earners (RIPTE), before the return of high inflation figures in 2002 these were high

contributions that resulted in appreciable pension rights. Finally, formal independent workers have access to family benefits that are different from those of informal workers, as seen in section 1.1.3.

For all these reasons, we have adopted a sectoral definition of formal independent labour in the EPH (1974-2017) that allows both employers and some own-account workers to be considered as formal. Following Maurizio (2012), we not only take into account the size of the independent worker's firm. We also use his working's position level of qualification. Indeed, "given that household surveys do not inquire in depth into the characteristics of the firms, the ILO suggests adopting a measurement criterion based on the combination of occupational categories, occupation groups defined according to job qualifications, and the size of the firm.(...) In the case of independent workers, only those with no professional skills are considered as part of the [Informal Sector], as an operational way to leave only independent workers with low productivity in this sector. Finally, the public sector is excluded from the IS." (Maurizio, 2012, p. 6). This approach is consistent with the results of De Paula & Scheinkman (2011). Studying formality among independent workers in Brazil, they find "higher ability⁸⁵ entrepreneurs do tend to be formal"(De Paula & Scheinkman, 2011, p. 18). A detailed explanation of how we identified independent workers of the formal sector across all versions of the EPH dataset (1974-2017) can be found in our Appendix G.2. As will be evidenced in Figures 1.7 to 1.9, this strategy gives us a stable proportion of independent workers of the formal sector despite both the evolution of the EPH survey and a wildly varying economic conjuncture in the 1974-2017 period.

Independent contributors to social security

The main problem with this sectoral definition of independent labour is that it is an imperfect tool for identifying independent contributors to social security. Indeed, the number of registered independent workers varied significantly in the 1998-2017 period because of economic factors but also changes in legislation and real contributions paid by independent workers (see Appendix F). As the real cost of social security contributions (and taxes, in the case of *Monotributistas*) paid by independent workers fell due both to the introduction of the *Monotributo* regime in October 1998 and the insufficient re-evaluation of taxes and contributions with respect to inflation since 2002, an increasing proportion of independent workers started contributing to social security even though they were in the informal sector (following the sectoral definition of informality). This is

⁸⁵De Paula & Scheinkman (2011) proxy the ability of entrepreneurs with their education level.

evidenced by Figure 1.4 below, where we can see the proportion of independent contributors only matches that of formal sector independent workers between years 2004 and 2008 and has been higher since 2009. Therefore, during this period the sectoral definition of independent workers formality proposed by Maurizio (2012) matched in aggregate terms the legalistic definition of non wage-earners formality, which is being enrolled either in the Autonomous workers or the *Monotributo* regime. This is however no longer the case since 2009, and was not the case either before 2004.

Figure 1.4: Quarterly proportion of independent workers by formality definition as a percentage of the population aged 16 to 69 (1998-2017)

Sources: AFIP monthly social security bulletins, EPH survey (1998-2017).

It is thus necessary to complement this sectoral definition of informality with a legalistic approach, where we consider independent contributors to social security. To do so, we

take aggregate figures of independent contributors enrolled respectively in the Autonomous workers and the *Monotributo* regime between the fourth quarter of 1998 and the first quarter of 2017. Our sources are Argentina’s federal tax body AFIP’s monthly social security bulletins (2003-2017), yearly tax statistics (1999-2003) and (Salim & D’Angela, 2006, p. 12). Earlier figures are unavailable and not as relevant, since before October 1998 all independent workers contributed to the Autonomous workers regime, so the sectoral definition of formal labour gives an adequate approximation of independent contributors and their contributions. From these, we deduce proportions of *Monotributistas* and people in the Autonomous workers regime by age and gender as follows⁸⁶. We first assume two thirds of independent contributors are men in order to replicate the proportion of independent workers that are male in the EPHc (2003-2015) (67%). After that, we express these aggregate quantities of either Autonomous workers or *Monotributistas* as a percentage of the population aged 16 to 70, following population estimations made by the DEIS (2001-2010) for years 2000 to 2009⁸⁷ and the population projections made by the INDEC (2010-2040). We then compute the proportions of independent workers as a percentage of the population of a given gender and age group (between ages 16 and 69) in the EPH (1998-2017) and assume independent contributors follow this gender-specific age group repartition. We finally adapt these gender and age-group specific percentages so as to result in aggregate values of Autonomous workers and *Monotributistas* by gender that correspond to those of our aforementioned sources once applied to the EPH dataset.

The last step is assigning specific independent workers in the EPH (or in our microsimulations, as will be explained in Chapter 2) to the Autonomous workers or the *Monotributo* regime. We adopt an alignment by sorting procedure (see Section 2.1.1), where independent individuals are ranked by income separately by age group, gender and sector (formal or informal). We then align these ranked individuals to the proportions of people in the Autonomous workers regime first, *Monotributo* second, for their given age group and gender. This ensures first that for the 1998-2017 period, every independent worker is considered to be either in the Autonomous workers regime, a *Monotributista* or not contributing to social security. Then, that the repartition of independent workers between these three contribution states are consistent both with the aggregate values of contributors taken from AFIP and their age and gender. We finally assign individuals within each regime to a specific category as described in Appendix F.

⁸⁶These proportions are uploaded in this thesis’ digital repository. The code is available on Zenodo, under the DOI link: [10.5281/zenodo.1420273](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1420273)

⁸⁷We could not find population projections by age and gender for years 1998 and 1999 that are consistent with those made by the DEIS (2001-2010) for the year 2000. As such, we decided to use the estimated population in 2000 for years 1998 and 1999.

All in all, we have adopted a legalistic definition of social security for dependent labour that is consistent throughout the 1974-2017 period and fit to simulate individual social security contributions and rights. We have furthermore been able to identify from among independent workers those who are most likely to belong to the formal sector through a methodology consistent with ILO's recommendations and the practices of a part of the literature on informal labour. We also reproduce aggregate values of independent contributors to social security (1998-2017). We finally obtain shares of independent registered labour that are consistent with external data and previous literature on Argentina's labour market (Maurizio, 2012). The last important information needed for computing social security benefits that is not readily available in the EPHc is family links between individuals within a household. The methodology adopted for deducing these links from the EPH is presented in the following section.

1.2.3 Determining family links in the EPH

The EPH: an incomplete source on family links

In this work, family links act both as an explanatory variable in behavioural equations and, in our dynamic microsimulations, as an element that triggers certain social security benefits, most notably child allowances and pensions derived from retirement rights and family benefits. Indeed, child benefits are conditional on the parents' labour-market situation and revenues. This means it is the latter's characteristics that determine whether a given child is entitled to a family benefit. Also, survivor's benefits are granted to the spouse and dependent children. We hence need, for each individual in our dataset, to ascertain the identity of their partner, parents and children whenever possible, that is, when they live in the same household. Unfortunately, the EPHc does not have a variable that directly gives family links between household members, and the building of such variable has not, to the best of our knowledge, been undertaken in the literature. Although variable CH03 gives the family relationship with respect to the household head⁸⁸, "the information obtained through this [variable] only permits the identification of primary conjugal units, that is, those that include the household head. Consequently, some families remain invisible [in the EPH]" (Street, 2007, p. 142). As such, we need to identify these invisible families to determine what child allowances or survivor's benefits they will be entitled to in our prospective simulations.

⁸⁸By construction, each household has a head, designated by the surveyed household's members.

Figure 1.5: Primary and secondary conjugal nuclei (Street, 2007)

Street (2007) gives an example to illustrate his point, which we reproduce in Figure 1.5 and expand by adding the head's mother H and brother I. He considers a household

made of a complete primary conjugal nucleus with children⁸⁹ (the household head A, the head's spouse B and their single male child C), a secondary complete conjugal nucleus with children (made of A and B's single male child D, D's single concubine E and D and E's single child F) and a non-nuclear relative G (A's father). Despite this household having two conjugal nuclei, "[the EPH] does not capture the conjugal nucleus formed by members D, E and F. By reconstituting the household's composition exclusively through the family relationship with the household head, member D is assigned (due to being a single child) to the conjugal nucleus made up of A, B and C, while only the presence of three non-nuclear relatives is captured in the survey (daughter-in-law, grandchild and father). In order to establish that members D and E are spouses and that the member F is their child, it would be necessary to capture the family relationship of members between themselves. Otherwise, it can be noted that the head's daughter-in-law (member E) could be the partner of any of the two children (C or D) or of an absent child, and the grandchild (member F) could be the child of one of the present children or of an absent child." (Street, 2007, p. 143). The lack of a variable providing direct family links between members of a household is indeed a problem, and complicates for a significant number of individuals the task of identifying their parents and partner. We however have been able to identify these links for most respondents. When these pertain to the primary conjugal nucleus or can be deduced solely from the respondent's kinship with the household head, we have been able to identify them directly. When these pertain to secondary conjugal nuclei within the household, we have been able to infer them through the combination of kinship relative to the household head and individual civil status. The two following sections give these methods' general outlines and Appendix H.2 gives a verbal description and examples on how these methods work for different types of families. The full SAS code is available on-line⁹⁰.

Readily available family links: the head's partner, parents and children

In the EPHc, the only variable that gives an indisputable family link is CH03, kinship with respect to the household head. Possible values are: household head, spouse or partner, child or stepchild, son or daughter-in-law, grandchild, parent, father or mother-in-law, sibling, other relatives or not a relative. With this variable alone we directly get the

⁸⁹We follow the classification of conjugal nuclei established by Torrado (1998). A nucleus is classified as primary when it includes the household head, and as secondary when it doesn't. It is complete when both spouses are present in the household and single-parent when one of the spouses is missing. And it is considered with children when there is at least one single child living with their parents and childless when there is no single children cohabiting with their parents (Street, 2007, p. 140).

⁹⁰We use the Zenodo archiving service for long-term preservation of our code. The DOI link is: [10.5281/zenodo.1420273](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1420273)

partner's id for the head and his or her partner. For all respondents in the household that declare being the head's children, we also get their father's id (the head's if he is a male and the head's partner's if he isn't⁹¹) and their mother's id (the head's partner's if the head is a male, the head's if he isn't). Moreover, the head's father's (resp. mother's) id will be the one of a male (resp. female) household dweller that declares being the head's parent. If the head's sibling is present, he or she gets the same father and mother's ids. If both of the head's parents are present, they are assigned each other's id as partner's id. For instance, in 1.5, we can directly link the head's father G and the head's mother H together and assign them as both the head A and the brother's head I parents. Also, if the head's father-in-law (resp. mother-in-law) is present in the household, then the head's spouse's father's (resp. mother's) id is obtained. And again, if the head's father-in-law and mother-in-law are both present in the household, they get each other's id as partner's id. These are all mother, father, partner and children ids that are directly obtainable through the variable CH03. Not only do these cover all family links within households restricted to a simple nuclear family, which are the most common in our dataset⁹². Some family links within extended families living in the same household are covered as well. However, variable CH03 is unable to precisely determine secondary conjugal nuclei constituted by the head's children, as in the example given by Street (2007). In 1.5, this corresponds to the secondary conjugal nucleus constituted by D, E and F. We cannot know for sure with CH03 who the grandchildren's parents are, nor which child is the son or daughter-in-law's partner. It is nevertheless possible to establish these with reasonable certainty in most households, as we will explain in the next section.

Inferable family links: secondary conjugal nuclei involving the head's children

As we have seen above, we have established mother, father and partner's ids for members of the primary conjugal nucleus and for secondary conjugal nuclei involving the household head's parents or parents-in-law. The last family configuration we have yet to determine these ids for is one where in addition to the primary conjugal nucleus there exists a secondary conjugal nucleus consisting on the head's children, his or her partner and their children, which are the head's grandchildren. Although only 12.87% of minor children are the head's grandchildren, with 84.55% being the head's children⁹³, this proportion is still

⁹¹For the sake of simplicity, and because the low prevalence of same-sex couples in the base may bar estimating matching models specific to this kind of couples, we only consider different-sex couples.

⁹²73.69% of respondents live in households strictly comprised of individuals pertaining to a primary conjugal nucleus or of respondents living alone. Source: EPHc (third quarter of 2003 - second quarter of 2015).

⁹³Source: own calculus based on the EPHc (third quarter of 2003 - second quarter of 2015).

significant, and it is interesting for our work to identify their parents. Street (2007) makes a good point on why variable CH03 is insufficient to establish who is the son or daughter-in-law's spouse and who the grandchildren's parents are. We should however not forget that Torrado (1998) defines conjugal nuclei as being comprised of the two partners and all their single children living with them⁹⁴. A non-single child⁹⁵ living in their household by definition belongs to a secondary conjugal nucleus. Hence, any son or daughter-in-law with the same civil status as this non-single child and of opposite gender⁹⁶ is very likely to be his/her partner or spouse. It is moreover highly uncommon in the EPHc, when a son or daughter-in-law is present, that both him/her and all of the head's children declare being single⁹⁷. Most of the time a secondary complete conjugal nucleus is present, there is only one married (or in a free union) head's child and only one son-in-law or daughter-in-law with the same civil status (married or in a free union) and of the opposite gender present in the household⁹⁸. If we take the example of Street (2007) and suppose both D and E report being in a free union through variable CH07, instead of being single as in her example, it becomes highly likely that D is E's partner and that F is their child, and we can reasonably assume it is indeed the case. It is true that F may be C's child or the offspring of a sibling that was absent or does not live in that household, and it is impossible to know for sure, but this scenario is highly unlikely. Nevertheless, if both C and D are not single, it becomes impossible to know which one is F's parent. Figure 1.6 describes our take on identifying grandchildren's parents and the partners of children that are married or in a common-law.

We first count in each household how many non-single children the household head lives with. If there is exactly one non-single child, we consider that all grandchildren in the household are his or her children. If there are either no non-single children or two or more of these, we do not assign father and mother's ids to the grandchildren. We also count the amount of head's children and son or daughter-in-laws in the household by gender and civil status. Then if there is for instance exactly one married son and one married daughter-in-law, we assume they form a couple and assign them each other's id

⁹⁴Since the EPHc does not distinguish between children and stepchildren, we include in that conjugal nucleus children which may have been borne from a previous union.

⁹⁵Given the possible values for variable CH07, individuals who declared being in a common-law union, married, divorced or separated or widowed are considered as not being single.

⁹⁶Since we are restricting our analysis to different-sex couples.

⁹⁷In fact, 61.96% of the head's son or daughter-in-laws report being in a common-law union, 34.09% married and only 2.63% declare being single. Source: own calculus on the EPHc, third quarter 2003 - second quarter 2015.

⁹⁸Out of all households with a married son-in-law, 97.64% have exactly one married head's daughter and, conversely, out of all households with a married daughter-in-law, 96.41% have exactly one married head's son. These figures respectively reach 96.65% and 95.86% for households respectively with a common-law daughter-in-law and a common-law son-in-law. Source: Ibid.

Figure 1.6: Identifying conjugal nuclei comprising any of household head's children

as their partner's id. Then any grandchildren are considered as the couple's offspring, and thus the daughter-in-law is viewed as their mother. Even if there are for instance two daughter-in-laws, if one declares being married and the other one being in a common-law union, as long as there is exactly one married child and one child in a common-law union in the household, it is safe to assume the former is the married daughter-in-law's husband and the latter is the common-law daughter-in-law's partner. Else, if there is for instance two married sons but only one married daughter-in-law present in the household, we do not assign a spouse to any of the three. Through this method we are able to assign with a reasonably high level of certainty partners to children and son or daughter-in-laws that are married or in a common-law union, and parents to the grandchildren surveyed in the EPHc. For the period surveyed between the third quarter of 2003 and the second quarter of 2015, we have managed to assign a partner to 82.79% of the surveyed household head's children that are married or in a common-law union, and a partner to 92.60% of the surveyed household head's son or daughter-in-laws that are married or in a common-law union. In that same period, we have been able to assign at least one father or mother to 48.75% of the grandchildren. In the end, we are left with only 9.06% of minors for which we are unable to identify at least one parent, and 4.21% of individuals married or

in a common-law union for which we could not assign a partner. These proportions are far from being insignificant, but they are the best we could do given the EPHc's lack of information on direct family links between all household members. From there, we can count for each individual the number of children under a given age he lives with, with a small error margin. The computation of this and the other family links can be found in detail in Appendix H.2, and the SAS code is available on-line⁹⁹.

In the end, in section 1.2 we have introduced our main dataset, the EPH, through its characteristics and evolution. After that, we have defined a number of labour-market states we found relevant for studying Argentina's social security system. In particular, we laid out the methodology we used for identifying formal dependent and independent workers throughout the 1974-2015 period. Finally, after pointing out that the EPHc has incomplete information on family links between individuals within a household, we have shown how we have determined for most individuals in the EPHc their partner, mother and father's ids as well as the number of children under their care. Now that our main micro-level dataset is properly treated, we can study the labour-market related input we feed our microsimulation model with, in order to both simulate individual behaviour and reproduce historically accurate labour-market averages when simulating careers. In the last section 1.3 of our Chapter 1 we describe the historical evolution of Argentina's labour market and real wages from the 1970s to this day at a macro level, while we review the ongoing judicial controversy on the discounting index for computing the reference income.

1.3 General characteristics of Argentina's labour market: a historical perspective

Individual pension rights depend on past careers. However, our micro-level dataset, the EPH, does not include information on accumulated pension rights nor on past careers, apart from some seniority variables. The microsimulation model built in this thesis needs thus to simulate plausible careers in order to estimate future pension benefits. Individual consistency of estimated careers, achieved through the estimation of behavioural and wage equations that are studied in section 4, is however not enough. The careers we reconstitute must also be coherent at the macro level with past evolutions of aggregate variables, most importantly labour-market status and wages. The goal is, for each quarter we retrospectively simulate when reconstituting careers, that the estimated labour-force participation

⁹⁹We use the Zenodo archiving service for long-term preservation of our code. The DOI link is: [10.5281/zenodo.1420273](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1420273)

and wages follow historically observed averages. In this section, we reconstitute these two exogenous datasets: aggregate labour-market states up to 1974 (using the EPH) and mean real wages up to 1970. both at the quarterly level. Although necessary for the development of our dynamic microsimulation model, this reconstitution also gives an insight on Argentina’s social and economic history. Additionally, our work on quarterly mean real wages addresses three distinct, yet interesting, issues. First, there is the challenge of building a consistent quarterly real wage index through the 1970-2015 period, which must cover comparable worker’s earnings through time and data sets. The second issue stems from the controversy with official inflation figures starting from January 2007. Computed real wages drastically differ depending on the inflation index used for actualising past nominal wages. The third issue finally regards the choice of the index used for actualising nominal income before retirement and computing the reference income, from which stems the value of the first retirement pension. There is a judiciary controversy in Argentina on this matter for the period ranging from the 1st of April 1991 to the 1st of March 2009, where the index was set by ANSES in a discretionary fashion (see Box 1). We will thus study the evolution of real wages when obtained through discounting with the index ANSES used up to August 2016, then with the corrected index used after August 2016¹⁰⁰ and finally through the index established by the Supreme Court of Justice in the 2009 Eliff ruling.

1.3.1 The evolution of Argentina’s labour market: a troubled history (1974 – 2017)

The period retrospectively covered in this work covers a range of historical situations, whose effects can be seen both in the labour-market state and in the real wage series. In what regards the labour-market evolutions, we use the EPH dataset in the 1974-2015 period and abide by the methodology we exposed in section 2.2 of our work, particularly in what regards telling apart informal from formal labour. We also keep the five labour-market states we identified as relevant for our study in section 2: formal salaried labour, formal independent labour, informal labour, unemployment and inactivity. The three following figures depict labour force participation by gender for individuals aged 16 up to the period’s retirement age for dependent workers. We remind the reader that this age was of 55 for women and 60 for men until the 1993 reform, and that it was gradually pushed until reaching 60 for women and 65 for men in 2001. The three vertical lines

¹⁰⁰As established by Decree 807/2016 and by Res. 6 / 2016 of the Social Security Office published the 3rd of August 2016.

depict the major changes in the EPH we reviewed in section 1.2.1. The first one marks the inclusion of cities other than Buenos Aires and its suburbs in the EPH. The second one, located in May 1995, both shows when the BUA was extended to all surveyed cities and when all of Argentina’s main urban centres were included in the EPH. Finally, the third one, located in the third quarter of 2003 depicts the introduction of the continuous EPH.

Figure 1.7: Labour-market participation in Argentina for people of working age. Source: EPH.

Note: we define unregistered (or informal) workers as wage-earners that do not contribute to social security and independent workers that own very small businesses and have positions with little to no qualification. For more details, see section 1.2.2.

Figures 1.7 to 1.9 accurately summarise Argentina’s long-term labour market evolutions. Formal salaried employment in Argentina follows a U curve, while unemployment and informal labour both follow a bell curve. Starting at around 35% of working-age population in 1974, formal salaried labour slowly deteriorates during military rule (1976-1983), Alfonsín’s presidency (1983-1989) and Menem’s first term (1989-1994). This fall

was nevertheless compensated by an equivalent increase in formal independent employment. However, the Tequila crisis in 1994 marks a drop in formal employment correlative to a surge in unemployment. The collapse of the currency board (1998-2002) results in formal dependent employment plummeting to 23% of active age population, and both unemployment (14.5% for May 2002) and informal employment (32% for the second half of 2003) reaching record levels¹⁰¹. After that, formal salaried employment increased steeply following the 2003-2008 economic recovery. High growth rates (between 8% and 10%, depending on the base year) resulting from favourable international conditions (increases in commodity prices, sustained economic growth of Argentina's main commercial partners Brazil and China), an under-valued currency that promoted exports together with an expansive fiscal and monetary policy that promoted the countries' re-industrialisation lead to a sharp increase in formal dependent employment, and a subsequent decrease in unemployment and informal labour rates. However, the 2008 economic crisis stopped this economic recovery, and the combination of stagnant growth with increasing inflation ("stagflation") since 2012 resulted in a stagnation of formal employment around 35% since the end of 2010. reaching levels close to those of 1974. In parallel, both informal employment and unemployment fell and stagnated respectively around 25% and 5% of working-age population. Formal independent labour rates remained stable since 1990. Finally, inactivity rates are hard to analyse, since the fall recorded in 2003 is likely due to the introduction of the EPHc, which started surveying unpaid family workers. Following our labour formality methodology reviewed in section 1.2.2, these are informal workers. Before the third quarter of 2003 however, they were not considered as workers in the survey and were thus classified as inactive.

¹⁰¹The jump in informal labour and fall of inactivity between May 2003 and the third quarter of 2003 however also comes from the introduction of the continuous EPHc survey. This is because until May 2003 unpaid family workers were classified as inactive, while in the EPHc they are considered informal workers.

Figure 1.8: Labour-market participation in Argentina for men of working age. Source: EPH.

Figure 1.9: Labour-market participation in Argentina for women of working age. Source: EPH.

All in all, these huge swings in formal employment, informal employment and unemployment in the last 40 years resulted in most workers going through long unemployment or unregistered employment spells. This is why by September 2016 almost two thirds

(65 %) (DNPE, 2016) of direct retirement benefits were moratorium pensions, granted hence to individuals who could not contribute the mandatory 30 years for being eligible to a pension (see Table 1.1.3 p. 66). In what regards gender differences, we can see that gender inequality is reflected in Argentina's labour market. Throughout the period, formal labour is significantly higher for men than for women, and the former are less often inactive, unemployed or in unregistered labour than the latter. Despite an increase in female labour force participation in Figure 1.9, with inactivity rates dropping from 58% in 1974 to 44% in May 2003¹⁰², 40% of women of working age were inactive in 2015, while only 20% of men of active age were inactive. Finally, we stress that the above figures do not represent the actual proportions we used for the macro-alignment of our simulations. The actual proportions are computed, for each available quarter, separately by gender and five-years groups. Missing quarters are extrapolated from the nearest available EPH waves, so for instance the alignment values for the third quarter of 2007 (when the EPH was not carried out due to a strike among INDEC workers) are the average of the corresponding values for the second and fourth quarters of 2007. The complete alignment tables are available on-line¹⁰³.

1.3.2 A reconstitution of Argentina's real wages at a quarterly step (1970-2015)

The initial retirement pension is determined both by the number of validated years and the reference income, which depends on past wages or income, as has been shown in section 1.1. We cannot however estimate past real wages with the EPH, as we did with past labour-market states, for a number of reasons. First, income is self-declared and individuals with multiple occupations are not asked how much they earn for each of their occupations. The main problem however are the gaps between each EPH wave, which were considerable between 1974 and 1987. With quarterly inflation figures well over two digits during the whole 1970-1991 period and two hyperinflation outbursts in 1989 and 1990. considerable fluctuations of real wages happened at the quarterly level. Extrapolating quarterly real wages from annual or bi-annual readings would have thus

¹⁰²The EPHc stopped considering unpaid family workers as inactive and introduced them in the labour force, causing a drop in inactivity rates that is a statistical artefact. We thus use here May 2003's inactivity rates for the sake of comparing two periods with identical inactivity definitions. In our work, we have coded unpaid family workers as being informal workers. This is a debatable choice, but it is of little relevance when studying pension rights since neither the inactive nor informal workers contribute to social security.

¹⁰³We use the Zenodo archiving service for long-term preservation of our code. The DOI link is: [10.5281/zenodo.1420273](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1420273)

flawed our results, and even more so for longer gaps before 1987. We thus resort to nominal and real wages gathered from a range of external sources, which we will describe below.

Gathering quarterly wages data (1970-2015)

First of all, for the most recent periods we use the RIPTE¹⁰⁴ index provided by the Ministry of Labour. Available since July 1994, the RIPTE is the mean gross average taxable income of stable wage-earners affiliated to the SIPA. It excludes family benefits and the thirteenth month or *aguinaldo*. Therefore, this index measures directly the average income contributed to ANSES. It is thus a better option for estimating pension rights than the EPH, where it is not possible to distinguish between contributors to the SIPA and to special regimes (such as Provincial civil servants' pension plans). Since the reference income of wage-earners is computed for the last ten years before retirement, this wage series is enough for computing the initial retirement pension of most individuals retiring after 2004. However, the reference income of independent workers is computed over the 35 previous years before retiring, so it is necessary to extend the real wage series further backwards.

There is unfortunately not a readily available quarterly-level index on real wages that covers the 1974-1994 period. Some works estimate annual real wages on this period (see for instance González (2004) or Graña & Kennedy (2008)), deriving them from mean industrial worker's salaries or baseline manufacturing wages resulting from collective bargaining agreements. Mean industrial wages are obtained through surveys to medium and large factories, from across the country (in INDEC's Survey on production, labour and wages (1970-1990), and Monthly industrial survey (1990 onwards)) or Buenos Aires' urban area (in FIEL's industrial wages survey (1980 - 1995)) (González, 2004). The INDEC in particular computed a series of total (including family, illness, accident and other benefits paid by the employer) and normal (excluding these benefits) wages of industrial workers between 1970 and 1990. After 1990, it determined a mean industrial worker wage (excluding family benefits but including illness, labour hazards and other benefits). Available at a quarterly level since 1970 and at the monthly level since 1987, these constitute the main official source on quarterly and monthly wage evolutions. These series are however not publicly available for periods prior to 1997, and as thus we have used an array of sources to reconstitute the evolution of total mean industrial wages for the 1974-1994 period.

First of all, we get detailed quarterly-level information on nominal industrial wages

¹⁰⁴*Remuneración Imponible Promedio de los Trabajadores Estables.*

for the 1970-1984 period through CEPAL (1984). These are drawn from the Survey on production, labour and wages, which covers only a selection of the biggest manufacturing firms. 1328 industrial firms were selected in 1970. averaging 200 employees each. By way of comparison, the 1974 industrial census averaged 12 employees by factory (CEPAL, 1984, p. 82). For the period ranging from 1975 to the second quarter of 1982, we use the total monthly wage by industrial worker developed by the INDEC. For the same period there is also the decomposition of said wage by origin: normal hours, extra hours, family benefits, bonuses, illness, accidents and holiday benefits, thirteenth month and other benefits (CEPAL, 1984, p 340- 342). We noticed that contrary to what is stated in the methodology section, total industrial wages do include the thirteenth month, so we subtracted it from the former. CEPAL develops in this document a normal wage by industrial worker, which includes only wages from normal hours, extra hours and bonuses, and is even available at a monthly rate since April 1979. However, the other sources on real wages we found for the 1984-1994 decade are variations on INDEC's total monthly wage, so we have chosen to stick with this measure for the 1975-1984 period. For the 1970-1974 period, the only available information are nominal evolutions of normal hourly wages and of hours worked by worker in the industrial sector. We have thus multiplied these two terms to obtain a variation in nominal terms of normal wages for this period and expressed them as a percentage of the nominal total monthly wage of the first quarter of 1975. Finally, we discounted these nominal values with the consumer price index to get quarterly real wages for the 1970- second quarter of 1984 period.

The next sources we use, Frenkel & Damill (1988) and Szretter (1997), give a quarterly evolution of INDEC's total monthly wage. The former covers the 1979 - second quarter of 1987 period, and the latter the 1985- mid 1995 period. Frenkel & Damill (1988) express these with 1983 total monthly wages as their benchmark, which are given in detail by CEPAL (1984) so we complete our series up until the second quarter of 1987 with this source instead of using Szretter (1997) whenever possible. Szretter (1997), on the other hand, computes real wages using the survey on production, labour and wages (1970-1990) and the monthly industrial survey (1990-). He decides not to combine these two surveys even though there were some overlapping years(Szretter, 1997, p. 81). He depicts the evolution of INDEC's total monthly wage up until 1990. and starting from 1990 adopts the new measure by INDEC, the mean industrial worker wage we mentioned earlier. We chain these real quarterly evolutions with the real wages we previously estimated up until the second quarter of 1987 and thus complete our quarterly series until the second quarter of 1994, after which we switch to the RIPTE. Despite the succession of different sources and series, we managed to get a quarterly real wage series consistent with previous liter-

ature and with only a 10% gap between the second and third quarters of 1994. This is shown in the following section.

Real wages evolution: a traumatic history (1970-2017)

Figure 1.10 shows real mean wage evolutions of the sources listed above for the 1970-2017 period at a quarterly pace. We compute real wages until 2006 using the Consumer Price Index (CPI). However, the official CPI for the 2007-2015 is notoriously undervalued. This is evidenced by the aberrant values taken by the real wage when using the official CPI after 2006 that can be seen in Figure 1.10. At the moment no alternative CPI has been made available for the 2006-2015 period. As such, we chose to discount nominal wages with an average of the CPIs of the Provinces of San Luis and the City of Buenos Aires (CABA). Figure 1.11 depicts the evolution of annual real wages following Graña & Kennedy (2008), and shows our quarterly estimation of real wages is akin to what has been established by previous literature for the 1970-2006 period. In particular, it reproduces the same real wage falls of 1976, 1982, 1989 and 2002, that we will analyse more in depth below.

Figure 1.10: Quarterly real wages, deflated by consumer prices index, 1970-2018 (Base: Fourth quarter of 2006=100)

Real wages for the second quarter of 2018 are those of April.

Figure 1.11: Real wage series, Graña & Kennedy (2008) (Base: 1970=100)

First of all, for the 1970-2003 period, it can be said that real wages had a downward trend, with 2003 wages being lower than those paid in 1970. This long-term trend of decreasing real wages can be attributed to a series of shocks followed by stagnation at lower levels throughout the period. First, there was a surge in real wages in the 1973-1974 period following the end of military rule and the return of democracy under the government lead by Perón and his peronist party. The 1973 petrol shock however reached Argentina, deteriorating its trade deficit, and a set of austerity measures (most notably cutting public services' and petrol's subsidies) and devaluations were undertaken after Perón's death in July 1974. This resulted in high inflation, that during civil rule was mitigated by collective bargaining lead by the peronist trade union CGT. Real wages decreased by 3.5% between the first quarters of 1975 and 1976, following figures provided by CEPAL (1984). The first considerable fall however happened following the 24th of March 1976 coup that deposed Perón's widow. With a military dictatorship that far exceeded in brutality those the country had witnessed throughout the 20th century, trade unions were abolished as well as collective bargaining. Real wages thus fell abruptly in a context of high inflation (-31.6% between the first and the second quarters of 1976), and stabilised at considerably lower levels until late 1979. A significant but short-lived increase in real wages happened between 1979 and 1981 with the introduction of a crawling peg (Martínez de Hoz's "Tablita") that lowered inflation figures at the expense of an appreciation of the peso relatively to the dollar and of an increasing external debt. The strong devaluation following the end of the crawling peg in March 1981 and the 1982 Malvinas war fuelled inflation and decreased real wages.

The military dictatorship's loss of power following the defeat at the Malvinas war and the return of democracy in December 1983 with the election of Alfonsín reduced wage repression. This gave way to a second spike in real wages, which increased 54% between the first quarter of 1983 and the fourth quarter of 1984. High inflation in these periods meant high volatility of real wages, which decreased 21.6% in a year between the fourth quarters of 1984 and 1985. The Plan Austral introduced in June 1985 stabilised inflation figures and thus wages, but its gradual collapse in 1988 led to two hyperinflation outbursts in 1989 and 1990 that significantly lowered real wages: they decreased by 27.5% between the first quarters of 1989 and 1991. Real wages stabilised at these low levels from 1991 onwards¹⁰⁵ through the adoption of a currency board, also known as Convertibility plan, that drastically reduced inflation. The plan's collapse followed by Argentina's default and significant devaluation by late 2001 - early 2002 gave way to a major economic crisis with high inflation, which led to a drop in real wages (-19.7% between the fourth quarters of 2001 and 2003). In the first quarter of 2003, Argentina's real wages reached their lowest value since 1970, decreasing in 33 years by 35%. This long-term decrease of real wages is quite unprecedented in the history of economic development. It reflects the fact the participation of labour on national output had a downward trend, decreasing from levels akin to those of the USA in the 1970s to those of other countries of the region like Brazil (Lindenboim *et al.*, 2010). This element is however left out of the scope of this thesis.

Real wages recovered at a high pace since 2003, following Argentina's economic recovery. By the fourth quarter of 2006 real wages had regained the level they had throughout the 1990's when the Convertibility Plan was in force. After 2006, computing real wages is hampered by the fact official inflation figures were false. What we can see by using provincial Consumer Price Indexes is that real wages stagnated between 2007 and 2010. Since Argentina faced in 2008 both the conflict with rural producers due to export tariffs on agricultural products and the 2008 international crisis, it is notable real wages did not decrease as a consequence of these adverse shocks. Then, the 2011-2012 strong economic growth greatly increased real wages so that by 2013 these represented 125% of their fourth quarter of 2006 value, a level that had not been attained since the collapse of the Plan Austral in the mid 1980s. Since then, real wages fluctuated around this level subject to a *stop and go* economic policy dictated by political concerns. During electoral years (2013, 2015 and 2017) public spending increased and the peso's value was maintained with respect to the dollar. This resulted in higher economic growth and lower inflation figures,

¹⁰⁵The 1994 rise observed in Figure 1.10 is solely due to the change of base, and is not verified in the literature. See Figure 1.11 for Graña & Kennedy (2008), or (González, 2004).

thus increasing real wages. During non-electoral years (2014 and 2016), significant devaluations of the peso with respect to the dollar triggered high inflation figures (rounding 40% of annual inflation), while public expenditure stagnated or even decreased (2016). These measures took their toll both on economic growth and on real wages.

Thankfully enough, we are not directly concerned by the controversy on official inflation figures since 2007. This is because pensions are neither computed nor adjusted with the CPI. We already saw that pensions are adjusted following a mobility index that depends on the evolution of both wages and ANSES revenue. Also, when computing the first retirement pension, past income is not deflated by inflation, but following an index devised by ANSES. In turn, this index is subject to a judiciary controversy and has been recently reformed. The following section will lay out the controversy on this discounting index and its impact on retirement pension rights.

1.3.3 Computing the reference income: the impact of different discounting rules

At this point in our work, we have most of the elements needed for computing retirement pension rights. We adapted our main dataset, the EPHc, to our needs in section 1.2. We also obtained the information we need on Argentina's labour-market and wages history for simulating historically plausible individual careers in section 1.3. Finally, we also reviewed Argentina's social security system, its benefits and computation rules in section 1.1. A last element is needed for calculating pension rights: the index that is used to discount past income in the computation of the reference income.

As we explained in section 1.1, the contributory retirement pension is composed of different elements. A fixed amount, the PBU, is complemented by two different benefits, the PC and the PAP, that are proportional to total contributed years and to the individual's reference income. The latter is the average of discounted earnings received in the last ten years before retirement for dependent workers, and in the last 35 years for independent workers, as stated in Art. 24 incise a) of Law 24241. These earnings are however deflated using an index which is left to the Ministry of Labour's Social Security Secretariat's (SSS) discretion ¹⁰⁶. Until June 2016, this discounting index, provided by ANSES¹⁰⁷, followed

¹⁰⁶This element was established by Law 26417's Art. 12, issued the 15th of October 2008, that introduced pensions mobility. Before that, the rules that dictated the computation of the reference income were directly dictated by ANSES.

¹⁰⁷The last available version of the discounting index is found in the Appendix of Res. 28/2016 issued

past general nominal increases in retirement pensions. Thus, when computing the reference income, earnings received during periods where retirement benefits increased on par with inflation were correctly adjusted with respect to inflation. However, earnings received during periods where real retirement pensions decreased were badly deflated with respect to inflation, resulting in reference incomes that were by far lower than the average of the last ten years of real wages (35 years of income for independent workers) earned before retirement.

This problem affected to varying degrees most individuals retiring under Law 24241, so after 1993. This is because starting from the 1st of April 1991, the Austral Convertibility Law 23928's Art. 10 abolished all forms of indexation, including retirement pensions'. Before that date, pensions were indexed on wages. This meant they were most of the time adequately adjusted to inflation. On top of that, there were no nominal pension increases until September 2004 (except for the minimum pension, which was frozen until July 2002). Thus the discounting index was frozen between March 1991 and September 2004, meaning income earned in this period was not discounted when computing the reference income. It was not until 2007 that nominal pension increases resulted in increasing real pensions. This means income earned between 2002 and 2006, a period where real pensions decreased, was insufficiently discounted with respect to inflation. The reference income of many individuals retiring after those dates were thus far lower than what they should have been following Law 24241. The resulting retirement pensions were thus lower than what these pensioners were entitled to, leading to increased litigation against ANSES.

Consequently, the Supreme Court of Justice issued the Eliff ruling, ordering to change the discounting coefficient for periods ranging between the 1st of April 1991 and the 28th of February 2009 for people retiring following Law 24241. The Supreme Court ordered using the ISBIC coefficient for unqualified personnel¹⁰⁸. Jurisprudence later determined that starting from the 1st of March 2009, past income had to be discounted following the pension mobility index established by Law 26417¹⁰⁹. Consequently, the right-wing government of President Macri decided to partially heed the Supreme Court's ruling through Decree 807/2016¹¹⁰ of the Social Security Secretariat. It establishes a discounting coef-

the 18th of February 2016.

¹⁰⁸The ISBIC, or Base Salary Index for Industry and Construction, is an index computed by the Argentinian Ministry of Labour. It gives the mean nominal base wage resulting from collective-bargaining agreements for manufacturing and construction workers. Available since 1988, it has increased significantly faster than the RIPTE between 2002 and 2008.

¹⁰⁹This has been established by the following rulings in lawsuits against ANSES opened by the following claimants: Valtuille (19 December 2013), Ackermann (23 May 2014) and Golovca (11 July 2014). These all retired after March the 1st 2009.

¹¹⁰Issued the 24th of June 2016.

ficient that follows INDEC's general wage index up until the 31th of March 1995, then the RIPTE until the 30th of June 2008 and finally pension indexation established by the pension mobility Law 26417 afterwards (Art. 2) for all future pensions. This discounting index is also applied retrospectively when recomputing past pensions for individuals striking an amicable agreement with ANSES following Law 27260's Art. 5¹¹¹.

Figure 1.12 depicts the impact of each of these indexes on the level of the reference income, from which is computed the first retirement pension. We compute the reference income of an individual who has 30 years worth of contributions, only worked in salaried formal work and earned the RIPTE in the last 10 years before retiring. We then divide this reference income by the last wage earned before retirement (in this case, the period's RIPTE). However, the reference income is highly dependent on the index that is used to deflate past nominal labour income, as depicted in Figure 1.12. First of all is the discounting index established by the Resolution 28/2016 issued by ANSES that follows nominal pension increases. Then we use the discounting index currently in force as established by the Resolution 6 /2016 issued by the SSS in application of Decree 807/2016. After that, we show the reference income that would result from applying the Eliff ruling to these cases. Finally, we show what would have happened with initial pensions had they computed the reference income by discounting the last ten year's nominal wages with the official Consumer Price Index.

From Figure 1.12, we can see several things. First, that the discounting derived from the Eliff ruling is the most beneficial for individuals having retired between 2003 and 2014, this income being 40% higher than the last wage between 2003 and 2009. After this date, the gap with reference incomes computed following Res. 28/2016 of ANSES and Decree 807/2016 of the SSS is gradually reduced and practically disappears since 2014, due to all three coefficients following the pension mobility index applied since March 2009. We can also see that the discounting coefficient established by Decree 807/2016 is the most consistent for people retiring with Law 24241. It always computes a reference income close to the last wage's value, and would have prevented inequalities between different generations of retirees had it been used throughout the period. Moreover, the discounting coefficient that had effectively been used by ANSES up until June 2016 was detrimental to people retiring between 2003 and 2014, specially so for those retiring between 2003 and 2010: the reference income was 20% lower than the last wage. The situation would have nevertheless been far worse had past wages been discounted with the official Consumer Price Index: from 2006 onwards, it would have significantly reduced the reference income,

¹¹¹Issued the 22th of July 2016.

Figure 1.12: Reference income as a percentage of the last wage before retirement, by discounting coefficient

bringing it at 50% of the last wage by 2013. This is again due to the significant underestimation by official figures of inflation indexes between 2007 and 2015, significantly overestimating real wage increases in that period. Between 2001 and 2006 however, the reference income would have been above the last wage, due to the significant fall in real wages experienced in 2002 which we reviewed in Figure 1.10. We can thus see the choice of the discounting index used for computing the reference income is crucial in determining the level of retirement benefits. This point is also crucial when correcting past initial retirement benefits, which play a significant role in the settlements included in the historical reparation introduced by Law 27260’s pension reforms. This element is however left for future work, as we do not simulate the historical reparation program in our model, and prefer to work with *ex post* estimations of its cost.

All in all, this section provides a range of historical information useful for describing

Argentina's social and economic history, its labour-market and wages evolution and the impact of seemingly technical details on the computation of the first retirement benefit. All these elements are interesting in their own right as they provide an overview of Argentina's social and economic history. But most of all, these informations are necessary for building our dynamic microsimulation model, in order to reconstitute individual careers that, when aggregated, are plausible at the macro level.

Chapter 1 conclusion: laying the foundations of a microsimulation model of Argentina's social security system

To summarise, this first Chapter contains the preparatory work for our dynamic microsimulation model on Argentina's main social security body, the ANSES. It however takes this study as an opportunity to give the reader a detailed account of the history and current characteristics of Argentina's welfare state and labour market. We begin with a detailed review of Argentina's social security history, accounts, reforms and features. This is not only essential to compute all social security benefits relevant for ANSES accounts in the future. It also helps the reader understand the current situation of Argentina's social security by putting it into its historical context. We then introduce Argentina's most thorough publicly available individual-level dataset, the EPH, from which we develop our dynamic microsimulation model. We also show how we extract from this dataset information on labour-market formality and family links that are not directly available but are essential for our model. Finally, we lay out the historical information necessary for reproducing individual careers and computing retirement pension rights that are coherent at an aggregate level with Argentina's history. At the same time, we give the reader an account of Argentina's recent history through its labour market. At the end of this thesis' Chapter 1, we have thus most of the data that is needed for developing our dynamic microsimulation model. These are social security legislation, a micro-level dataset from which are extracted all the variables we need to make our model work and the historical values of past labour market participation and wages that our model will have to reproduce when studying individual careers. The following Chapter 2 will present the building of our thesis main contribution to the economic literature, the first dynamic microsimulation model for a social security system developed for Latin America.

Appendices

Appendix A

Estimating the cost of the historical reparation program (2016-2017)

Official information on the historical reparation program's cost is scarce. Although the first recipients started receiving increased pensions in September 2016, the cost of this program is not recorded separately in the physical-financial monitoring of ANSES expenses. The only pieces of official information on the program's estimated cost can be found in the 2017 and 2018 budget laws, in the "distribution by jurisdiction - entity" appendix devoted to ANSES¹. In these, the allocated funding for the historical reparation program for years 2017 and 2018 reach respectively 59,656,979 and 69,865,586 thousand pesos, or respectively 7.5% and 7% of the total ANSES budget for retirement pensions. It is not however confirmed in the various documents evaluating the execution of the 2016 and 2017 budgets how much was spent in the historical reparation program. These Appendices to the budget law however confirm that the additional spending induced by the historical reparation program is entered into the budget sub-program "Provisional Benefits of the Pay-As-You-Go Pension Scheme". This means the cost of the Historical Reparation program is mixed with normal ANSES spending on contributory retirement benefits.

Knowing this, we are able to approximate the surplus in pension spending derived from this program. We take the quarterly physical-financial monitoring of ANSES spending for years 2016 and 2017 and measure the mean retirement benefit (both normal and survivor's pensions) paid by ANSES following Law 24241. This excludes both moratorium

¹The detailed figures of budgeted ANSES expenditure are established by the Administrative Decisions 12/2017 and 6/2018 taken by the Executive Office of the Cabinet of the Ministers on the distribution of the budget among different entities. The exact figures can be found in both of these decisions' appendices on spending allocated to ANSES. These can be downloaded in the National Budget Office's website. For 2018, the link is <https://www.minhacienda.gob.ar/onp/presupuestos/2018> (accessed 22 May 2018).

pensions and the benefits paid to people that retired with the former provincial pension schemes that were absorbed by ANSES in the 1990s. We then take the mean Law 24241 contributory benefit paid by ANSES in the second quarter of 2016 (so before the historical reparation program was in force) and actualise it following the pension mobility indexes that were given between September 2016 and September 2017. This gives us an approximation of the mean Law 24241 benefit that would have been paid by ANSES had the historical reparation program never been implemented. This approximation is valid as long as we assume new retirement and survivor’s pensions given between the third quarter of 2016 and the fourth quarter of 2017 are similar to those of retirees or pensioners that died during that period. Alternatively, as long as the difference between these two terms does not impact the mean pension much, we can attribute all changes on the mean retirement or survivor’s pension to the mobility formula. This is likely to be true because we make this hypothesis over a short period of time (18 months) and no further legislative changes were in force during that period. Finally, we take the difference between the measured benefits and this (lower) estimated benefit, multiply it by the number of Law 24241 retirement and survivor’s benefits pensioners and get an estimation of additional expenses due to the historical reparation plan. The detail of all these computations is given by Table A.1 below.

Table A.1: Historical reparation program cost (2016-2017)

Quarter	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	
2016	2	86,906.152	3,108,084	7,988.95	-	-	0
	3	80,007.657	3,111,882	8,570.13	8,366.03	204.10	1,905.372
	4	104,425.922	3,109,413	9,595.37	9,120.19	475.19	5,171.436
2017	1	99,018.619	3,069,791	10,751.94	9,514.18	1,237.76	11,399.006
	2	126,739.061	3,075,900	11,772.54	10,302.16	1,470.38	15,829.591
	3	116,145.402	3,081,544	12,563.55	10,759.58	1,803.97	16,677.063
	4	147,933.499	3,084,454	13,703.14	11,674.41	2,028.73	21,901.367
<p>(1): Quarterly ANSES spending on Law 24241 pension benefits (millions of current pesos). (2): Beneficiaries of a Law 24241 retirement benefit or survivor’s pension. (3): Mean pension, paid (pesos). (4): Mean pension, deduced from pension mobility (pesos). (5) Mean surplus following the historical reparation (3)-(4). (6): Total additional spending (millions of pesos). We take into account that a thirteenth retirement pension is given to pensioners each year, the <i>aguinaldo</i>. Half of it is given in June, while the other half is paid in December. Each half is computed on the semester’s highest nominal pension. With Law 26417 pension mobility, this meant the June and December payment were respectively computed on the pension earned after the March and September re-adjustments.</p>							
Source: quarterly physical-financial monitoring of ANSES accounts (2016-2017).							

In the end, we find the historical reparation program costed nearly 7,076.808 million pesos in 2016 and 65,807.027 million pesos in 2017. This last figure is close to the 59.66 billion pesos budgeted in the 2017 budget we mentioned earlier. Also, additional spending due to the historical reparation program represented 0.62% of 2017 GDP and 7.9% of all retirement pension spending made by ANSES that year. Our estimation of the program's cost for 2017 is thus accurate. It is more complicated to gauge our estimations' performance for 2016 since we lack official data on that year's expenses. We simply wager that since the proposed methodology applied in Table A.1 worked properly for 2017, our estimation for 2016 must not stray too far away from the actual figures. In any case, this methodology captures the increase in non-moratorium pensions that was faster than the pension mobility applied since September 2016. In the wait of official figures on the cost of the historical reparation program, this estimation is the best available.

Appendix B

Formula for the computation of contributory retirement pensions, Decree 679/1995, Appendix 1.

Following Article 24 of Law 24241, the computation rules of the *Prestación Compensatoria* (PC) and the *Prestación Adicional por Permanencia* (PAP) are the same. The only real differences are that the PC can be computed on a maximum of 35 years (as per Art. 24 of Law 24241), while no cap is applied to the PAP (following Decree 679/1995). Apart from that, the PC and the PAP are computed on periods computed respectively before and after July 1994. The formula for computing the PC, as laid out in Appendix I of Decree 679/1995, is the following:

$$PC = 0.015 \times N \times \frac{(n + p) \times W + (m + p) \times R}{n + m + p}$$

being

$$n + m + p \leq 420$$

$$N \leq 35$$

$$N^* = \left\lfloor \frac{n + m + p}{12} \right\rfloor$$

$$N' = \frac{n + m + p}{12}$$

$$N = N^* + 1 \text{ si } (N' - N^*) > 0.5$$

$$N = N^* \text{ if } (N' - N^*) \leq 0.5$$

and:

- PC: the *Prestación Compensatoria*, or Compensatory Benefit
- N: number of years with contributions previous to the First of July 1994
- n: number of months with contributions made exclusively in dependent work, corresponding to periods preceding the First of July 1994
- W: mean pay for activities in dependent labour
- m: number of months with contributions made exclusively in independent work, corresponding to periods preceding the First of July 1994
- R: mean reference income for activities as an independent worker
- p: number of months with simultaneous dependent and independent labour, corresponding to periods preceding the First of July 1994

Let's say for instance a man retires on April 2018 at 67 with 29 years of contributions, all made as a wage-earner. The last required year of contributions is compensated by the fact the pension is liquidated two years above the minimum age. Let us also assume his reference income is equal to 20,000 April 2018 pesos as discounted by ANSES, with 10 years contributed before and 19 after July 1994. His pension would thus be:

$$PC = 0.015 \times 10 \times 20000 = 3000$$

$$PAP = 0.015 \times 19 \times 20000 = 5700$$

$$PBU = 3619.07$$

$$P = PC + PAP + PBU = 3000 + 6000 + 3619.07 = 12319.07$$

Let us now this same man retired with a total of 29 years of contributions (still, 10 before and 19 after July 1994) but that 19 of these were made as a wage-earner (including the last ten years before retirement), the remaining 10 being contributed in the Autonomous workers regime. Let us also assume the discounted mean of the last 10 wages was equal to 20,000 April 2018 pesos, while his reference income as an independent worker reached

10,000 April 2018 pesos. His pension is thus computed by:

$$I = 20000 \times \frac{19}{29} + 10000 \times \frac{10}{29} = 16,551.72$$

$$PC = 0.015 \times 10 \times I = 2482.75$$

$$PAP = 0.015 \times 19 \times I = 4717.24$$

$$PBU = 3619.07$$

$$P = 2482.75 + 4717.24 + 3619.07 = 10819.07$$

It is worth noting that had his last ten years of contributions been done in the Autonomous workers regime, his past wages would have not been taken into account in the computation of his pension, and his reference income would have been equal to 10,000. In this case, his retirement pension would have reached $10000 \times 0.015 \times 29 = 4350$, which is below the legal minimum for April 2018 of 7660.61 pesos. He would thus had gotten the legal minimum.

Appendix C

Argentina's pension moratoriums

There are two conditions in Argentina to benefit from a public pension: reaching retirement age (60 for women and 65 for men) and contributing 30 years. The latter condition is difficult to achieve in a developing country that has faced high levels of labour informality and unemployment at least since the 1990s (see Figure 1.7 p. 97). As such, a series of pension moratoriums were taken to grant access to a retirement benefit to the elderly. In this appendix, we give a detailed account of the characteristics of these pension moratoriums, and more particularly of the computation of moratorium pensions.

C.1 Law 24476 moratorium's first version: a *pro forma* measure

Law 24241 came into effect the 13th of October 1993 and was gradually implemented throughout 1994. In the wake of its implementation, Law 24476 was passed the 29th of March 1995 and came into effect the 25th of November 1995. This was the first law to make it possible for individuals to buy back missing contributed years and retire. This was made through enrolment on a payment plan that allowed to reimburse the debt in monthly instalments. This moratorium allowed buying back missing contribution years up until the 30th of September 1993. Since it gave access to a retirement pension for independent workers it was however not possible to buy back missing contribution years before January 1955, when the first own-account workers pension system was created. However, this moratorium had quite stringent conditions for adhesion and was not particularly generous, excepting forgiveness of compensatory and punitive interests derived from independent workers' social security debt¹. On the one hand, as stated in its Article

¹Art.1 of Decree 493 / 1995, issued the 22th of September 1995

5, each reimbursed year increased the replacement ratio of the *Prestación Compensatoria* of "0.85 percentage points" instead of the usual 1.5%. On the other hand, its Article 9 stated that "in order to gain access to SIJP's benefit, the totality of declared debt shall be included in the present [payment plan]", so there was no discount on the indebted capital. Finally, adhesion to this moratorium was possible for only a very short time. Indeed, General Resolution 4084/1995 issued the 17th of November 1995 established in its Art. 5 that participating in this Moratorium was only possible until the 27th of December 1995. All in all, this moratorium seems to have been essentially a rhetorical measure as subscribing to it was *de facto* almost impossible.

C.2 Modifying Law 24476 into a permanent pension moratorium

However, the significance of Law 24476 gradually returned when arose the political will of increasing retirement pension coverage. On the one hand, after various modifications, it stands today as the only permanent way, for people of retiring age missing contribution years, to retire. And on the other hand, it served as a reference for calculating and repaying social security debt in future moratoriums. First, Law 25865, which was partially into effect the 15th of January 2004, reopened the possibility to adhere to Law 24476 Moratorium for a period of one year. Furthermore, compensatory interests for past unpaid contributions were reintroduced, even though these were halved and capped at 30% of the debts' principal by Art. 8. However, Decree 164/2004² in its Article 1 reopened permanently the possibility to join the pension moratorium Law 24476, although it specified the implementation of this Law still had to be issued. This was done by Decree 1454/2005³, which introduced various changes to Law 24476. It made it more generous, since the replacement ratio penalty introduced in Art. 5 of Law 24476 was removed. It also abrogated Art. 7 of Law 24241, which stated that "[the moratorium] debt will be indexed with the same periodicity and in equal percentage to the variations of the contributions [of the independent worker category the worker was affiliated to in June 1994]"; since no other indexation of the debt under moratorium was introduced, it effectively meant that, once having subscribed to the payment plan, the real value of instalments was depreciated by inflation. But most importantly, the original Art. 9 of Law 24476 that barred access to retirement pension until the social security debt was repaid in full was replaced. In its stead, the current Art. 9 of Law 24476 states that "once granted the

²Issued the 5th of February 2004

³Issued the 25th of November 2005

respective benefit, the recipient will be able to request the discount of the payment plan's instalments (...) up to the limit established by the article 14, clause d) of the Law N^o 24241.⁴. This made it possible to only pay out-of-pocket the first instalment in order to enrol into the pension moratorium, while the remaining instalments could be paid with the obtained retirement pension.

C.3 Making retirement pensions accessible to everyone: 2006's Law 25994 moratorium

The most important was however the Law 25994 moratorium, partially issued the 29th of December 2004, even though it was limited in time⁵ and was implemented slowly. Indeed, not only did this law introduce an anticipated retirement feature for unemployed⁶ individuals five years short of retirement age that had at least 30 years of contributions. It also made it possible in its Article 6 for individuals having reached retirement age by the 31th of December 2004 to adhere to Law 25865 Moratorium, that is, following the conditions of Law 24776 but being able to buy back missing contributions after the 30th of September 1993 until the 31th of December 2004. So, once Decree 1454/2005 implementing Law 24476 came into effect and once Joint General Resolutions 2091 and 579/2006⁷ defined the last elements of the Moratorium, it became effectively possible to join a Moratorium for the first time since the 1993 social security reform.

The enrolment was massive; despite the short time the Moratorium was effectively accessible, in 2007 there were 1,369,110 Law 24476 or 25994 Moratorium retirement pensioners, that is 44% of total retirees⁸ and by June 2012, this figure had reached 2,465,855 pensioners, that is, more than 60% of the total.⁹ Since the Moratorium was no longer available after 2007, the amount of Laws 24476 and 25994 retirees however declined until reaching 2,409,434 in 2014¹⁰. In order to prevent coverage from dropping as younger generations retired, with only the Law 24476 moratorium available to buy back missing

⁴This clause states that deductions from social security benefits "may not exceed (...) 20% of the amount of the monthly benefit"

⁵Originally, its fourth Article gave two years since implementation to enrol, although Decree 1451/2006, issued the 23th of October 2006, extended the deadline until the 30th of April 2007

⁶Originally, for individuals unemployed by the 30th of November 2004, according to Art. 2. Res. 1054/2006, in effect since the fifth of February 2007, pushed it to the 31th of December 2005

⁷Issued The 6th of July 2006

⁸Source: own calculus from Cuenta de Inversión 2007, tomo II Anexo 3

⁹Source: own calculus from (DNPE, 2012)

¹⁰Source: own calculus from *Cuenta de Inversión* 2014, tomo II Anexo 3

contribution years until September 1993, a new moratorium was needed in the absence of a comprehensive retirement reform.

C.4 2014's Law 26970: a revised moratorium for guaranteeing universal access to retirement

With this in mind, the Argentinian government passed Law 26970 the 27th of August 2014¹¹, which introduces a pension moratorium open from the 19th of September 2014¹² to the 18th of September 2016¹³ for individuals "having reached, at the date of adhesion, the age required for accessing the retirement benefit he applies to"¹⁴. This moratorium has the same rules for computing social security debt and payment plan instalments than the previous ones, and is even compatible with them¹⁵.

This moratorium introduces however three major changes. The first one is that, as stated in its Art. 5, "[the value of] instalments will be bi-annually adjusted following the mobility index established by Art. 32 of Law 24.241 and its modifications. The financing interest rate will be [a monthly 1.35%]". Hence, instalments in this moratorium follow an indexation rule and their value is hence no longer necessarily depreciated by inflation. Secondly, its tenth Article makes it possible to buy back missing contribution months up until December 2003. Finally, adhesion to this Moratorium is subject to a set of income, wealth and consumption conditions detailed in Joint General Resolutions 533 and 3673/2014's Article 8. Most notably, the average gross income earned in the twelve months prior to applying to the moratorium, taking only contributed months, must not exceed the maximum individual income for earning child benefits. Even though this Moratorium is less generous in its payment plan than Law 24476's, adhesion was significant among people of retiring age. For instance, the 450.000th Law 26970 Moratorium retirement benefit was given the 7th of April 2015¹⁶, 7 months after the moratorium's beginning, and by September 2016 821,441 direct and 8,822 derived retirement pensions were granted in virtue of Law 26970 moratorium (DNPE, 2016).

¹¹Implementation Decree 1556/2014, issued the 9th of September 2014

¹²Date of issuance of Res. 540/2014 fully implementing the moratorium

¹³As established by Art. 2 of Joint General Resolution 3673 and 533 / 2014

¹⁴Source: Law 26970. Art. 4 clause a)

¹⁵This is guaranteed by Art. 2 of Joint General Resolution 3673 and 533/2014, which allows individuals to include debt regularised with other payment plans to Law 26970's payment plan. It is hence possible to buy back some of the required contribution months with Moratorium 26970 and the remaining with Moratorium 24476.

¹⁶Source: ANSES (2014)

Appendix D

Survivor's benefits: who can receive them and how they are computed

In Argentina's social security system, there are two kinds of survivor's benefits, both established by Law 24241: "derived pensions" that originate upon the death of a retirement pensioner and "direct pensions" that originate upon the death or disability of a non-pensioner. There are however some elements to be taken into account when computing these pensions. First, who are the rightful claimants and how do they share the survivor's benefit? Then, what are the conditions the deceased (or disabled) must have been fulfilling for these survivor's benefits to be given to the rightful claimants? Once we know the answers to these two questions we may compute the survivor's benefit level.

D.1 Survivor's benefits: who are the rightful claimants?

Law 24241 establishes who the rightful claimants for getting a survivor's benefit are. As stated in its Article 53, the rightful claimants are the deceased or disabled's single children under the age of 18, his or her widow and/or concubine. The former cannot however cumulate this survivor's benefit with other pensions (Art. 53), although it is unclear whether they can cumulate it with a child benefit. Unmarried concubines, on the other hand, are indeed eligible to a survivor's benefit even if he was not married to the deceased under the condition of having cohabited with the deceased at least in the five immediate years prior to his death, or two if they had children. If there is both an ex-spouse (separated *de jure* or *de facto*) and a cohabiting partner, the latter is usually awarded the pension, particularly when the ex-spouse is the person deemed responsible for the separation. But if it was the departed who was responsible for the separation or if the ex-spouse was financially dependent on the deceased, for instance if he was paying

child support, their share of the survivor's benefit is split between them.

D.2 Survivor's benefits: when do they trigger?

There are some conditions the deceased must have fulfilled at death in order for the pension to trigger. If the deceased was receiving a retirement pension (be it a contributory benefit or a moratorium pension, but excluding the universal pension for the elderly) the rightful claimants get a "derived pension". If at the time of death (or in this case disability) he was not receiving a retirement pension then the rightful claimants get a "direct pension". Conditions for "direct pensions" to be granted are however restrictive. If the worker had not been contributing steadily enough near death, then no derived pensions are triggered. The implementation of Art. 95 of Law 24241 through Decree 1120/1994¹ established that "1. An affiliate will be considered a regular contributor (...) if he (...) had made the corresponding social security contributions during at least ten of the last twelve months preceding (...) the date of death. 2. An affiliate will be considered an irregular contributor (...) if he (...) had made the corresponding contributions during at least six of the last twelve months preceding (...) the date of death. 3. Affiliates who would not fulfil the requisites indicated in points 1 or 2 (...) will not be entitled to earn [the survivor's pension]". These conditions were modified by Decree 460/1999², which established in its first Article that the affiliate had to contribute 30 of the last 36 months before death or invalidity to be considered a regular contributor, and 18 of these last 36 months to be considered an irregular contributor, determining hence the regular or irregular status of the contributor over a longer period.

However, section 1 of this first Article established that "when the affiliates prove to have contributed the minimum mandatory years (...) for ordinary retirement, they will be in all cases considered as regular contributors". And Art.1 section 5 of this Decree said that " the [aforementioned] demanded periods will be reduced to twelve months within the sixty months preceding the date of request of the retirement for invalidity or the date of death of the affiliate in activity, when said (...) worker would not reach the minimum years of service (...) required for accessing ordinary retirement, providing that fifty percent of said minimum and payment of the corresponding contributions are proven", that is, if he had contributed at least 15 years. These conditions broadened access to survivor's benefits.

¹Issued on 13th of July 1994

²Issued on the 5th of May 1999

Finally, pension moratoriums also made access to survivor's benefits easier. Not only because they greatly increased access to a pension, but also because they permitted to buy back some of the deceased's missing years of contributions in order to trigger survivor's benefits for the rightful claimants. Indeed, Instruction 9/2006³ made it possible for potential survivor's benefit's beneficiaries to claim it even if the worker was neither a regular nor an irregular contributor as defined by Art. 95 of Law 24241. Its Article 2 made it possible either to complete the 15 years of contributions if the deceased had contributed twelve of the last sixty years before death or to otherwise complete the 30 years of contributions through adhesion to the Law 24476 Moratorium. Similarly, Law 26970 moratorium, through its Art. 10. made it possible to adhere to the second moratorium to complete these required contribution years when the deceased or invalidated worker was neither a regular nor an irregular contributor. This possibility is however slowly disappearing: Law 26970 moratorium expired for men in September 2016 and will expire for women in July 2019. This will only leave the permanent Law 24476 moratorium accessible for rightful claimants to get "direct pensions", but since this moratorium only allows to buy back years until 1993, its relevance will quickly fade away.

D.3 Survivor's benefits: what is their level?

The survivor's benefit's amount depends on the deceased's reference income, his or her status at death and on the nature and number of beneficiaries. Decree 1120/1994 regulates Art. 97 of Law 24241, and establishes that, when calculating pensions derived from a workers' death or disability ("direct pension"), the reference income is the mean labour income received in the last 60 months before death or invalidity, excluding months where the worker had not contributed.⁴ Art. 97 of Law 24241 establishes that the pension of reference derived from the death or invalidity of a worker is equal to 70% of the reference income when he was a regular contributor, and to 50% when he was an irregular contributor. The pension of reference for retirement pension beneficiaries ("derived pensions") is the benefit they were receiving at the time of death as established by Art. 98 of Law 24241.

³Issued the 21th of December 2006

⁴The Supreme Court of Justice has however issued the Vergara vs. ANSES ruling the 3d of March 2015 that establishes this reference income must be computed on the last 10 years before the insured's death or disability, as is already done when computing the initial retirement benefit. This disposition has not yet been extended to all pensioners and has not been included in Law 27260 retirement pensions reform.

Finally, the survivor's benefits are a percentage of this pension of reference. Incises a) to c) of Article 98 define the benefit awarded to each survivor's as a percentage of the pension of reference. These will be: "a) [70%] for the widow or cohabitant, were there no children entitled to a [survivor's] pension. b) [50%] for the widow or cohabitant, when there are children entitled to a [survivor's] pension. c) [20%] for each [entitled] child." Sections I to III of Article 98 also state that "I. Were there not a widow or cohabitant entitled to a [survivor's] pension, the children benefits' percentage established in incise c) will be raised and shared equally between eligible children up to the percentage established in incise b). II. The sum of the pensions of all the beneficiaries shall not exceed [100%] of the [pension of reference] of the [deceased]. Were it to happen, each of the beneficiaries' pensions will be recalculated, keeping the proportions resulting from the [aforementioned] percentages (...). III. If any of the beneficiaries were to be no longer entitled to [a survivor's] benefit, the pension of the remaining beneficiaries shall be computed again, excluding the former beneficiary". A last element to take into account when computing each of these survivor's benefits levels is that they cannot be lower than the minimum retirement pension (Art. 125). Section II. of Article 98 however ensures the total sum of these pensions do not exceed the pension of reference. Hence, when for instance a pensioner receiving the minimum pension dies (this was the case of 71% of beneficiaries of a retirement pension in September 2016 (DNPE, 2016, p. 24)) the rightful claimants get survivor's pension whose sum is equal to the minimum pension. If there is only one rightful claimant (typically the widow) then he receives a survivor's benefit equal to the minimum pension.

It is worth mentioning here that if an individual is eligible to multiple survivor's benefits, each of these benefits can be received at the same time and stacked with other benefits. The only limitation on their amount is that the sum of all retirement pensions and survivor's benefits an individual gets cannot be greater than the period's maximum retirement pension. This element was introduced by the Art. 6 of Decree 764/2006, published the 15th of June 2006. This decision followed a Supreme Court of Justice ruling⁵ that condemned previous limitations on survivor's benefits for people that earned more than one of these pensions.

⁵Source: Hernández, Adelaida Susana c/ANSES s/ pensiones, Fallos:325:1294 (2002). 28/05/2002

Appendix E

Family benefits amount and income ranges, March 2016

Family benefits given by ANSES vary depending on individuals' labour-market state. Means conditions depend on the Family Group's Income (IGF¹). It equals the sum of income of all members of a given household. More specifically, it adds registered wage-earner's gross income and the maternity benefit, excluding additional hours, the bonus for unfavourable region (usually valid for Patagonian provinces, with higher cost of living) and the thirteenth month. It also adds the reference income of registered independent workers, be them autonomous or *Monotributistas*, and domestic service workers, plus pension and unemployment benefits, social plans and other non-family benefits. For *Monotributistas*, the means condition depends on the worker's categorisation as an independent worker.

In what regards family benefits, these are the following categories an individual may fall into:

- 1 Registered wage-earners, recipients of labour hazard benefits and veterans of the 1982 Malvinas war.
- 2 Recipients of an unemployment benefit.
- 3 Recipients of a retirement benefit from the SIPA or federal civil servants (Hintze & Costa, 2011).
- 4 Unemployed without an unemployment benefit, unregistered workers or inactive individuals.
- 5 *Monotributistas* since May 2016, by Decree 593/2016.

¹*Ingreso del Grupo Familiar*

The family benefits given by ANSES are the following:

- a) The maternity benefit "will consist in the payment of a sum equal to the pay the worker should have received during her corresponding legal maternity leave. A continuous seniority of at least three months will be required for perceiving this benefit". It is only given to registered wage-earners, and is not means-tested. Established by Law 24714, Art. 11.
- b) The birth and adoption benefits are given at birth or adoption. They are available for wage-earners having at least 6 months of seniority (excluding civil servants) and unemployment benefits recipients (categories 1 and 2). Established by Law 24714, Art. 12 and 13.
- c) The marriage benefit is given at the month of marriage to eligible spouses, being possible for both to receive it. It requires a seniority of at least 6 months, and is also reserved to registered wage-earners and unemployment benefits recipients (categories 1 and 2). Established by Law 24714, Art. 14.
- d) The child benefit is a monthly sum paid for each minor (17 or less) child at the charge of the individual. It is available for registered wage-earners, unemployment benefits recipients and *Monotributistas* (categories 1, 2 and 5). Established by Law 24714, Art. 7.
- e) The prenatal benefit "[consists] on the payment of a sum equal to the child benefits', that will be given since conception until the birth of the child. (...) A seniority of at least three months will be needed to benefit from this allowance". It is available for registered wage-earners (except civil-servants), unemployment benefits recipients and *Monotributistas* (categories 1, 2 and 5). Established by Law 24714, Art. 9.
- f) The handicapped child benefit is available for each handicapped child in the individual's care. This benefit has no age limit and is available since the beginning of the child's disability. It is available for registered wage-earners, unemployment benefits recipients and *Monotributistas* (categories 1, 2 and 5). Established by Law 24714, Art. 8.
- g) The yearly school aid is given for each child that attends a primary or secondary school, and is paid in March. In the case of disabled children, there is no age limit and it is given when they attend special-education establishments. It is available for registered wage-earners, unemployment and retirement benefits recipients and *Monotributistas* (categories 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5). Established by Law 24714, Art. 10 and Art. 14 sexies.

- h) The spouse benefit is given to the individual for his spouse. It is reserved to retirement benefits recipients (and hence also federal civil servants) (category 4). Established by Law 24714, Art. 16.
- i) The Universal Child Benefit for Social Protection (AUH) is a monthly benefit given for each minor children at the parent's charge. The minor must neither be working, emancipated nor receiving any of the aforementioned family benefits (excluding the yearly school aid). It is not possible to receive more of five of these benefits in a given household. In the case of disabled children, there is no age limit for the perception of this benefit, and the amount is higher. Additional conditions (Art. 14 ter) are: the parent and child both being Argentinian or residing in Argentina for at least 3 years. Also, "until the age of four -included-, the compliance of sanitary controls and of the compulsory vaccination plan must be accredited. From the age of five up to the age of eighteen, attendance to a public school must also be accredited." Its access is reserved to the children of informal workers earning less than the minimum wage, of the unemployed not receiving an unemployment benefit and of inactive individuals (category 4). Established by Law 24714, Art. 14 bis.
- j) The Pregnancy Benefit for Social Protection "is a monthly (...) benefit given to the pregnant woman from its twelfth week of pregnancy until birth or termination of the pregnancy." It is compatible with the perception of the AUH. It is available for informal workers earning less than the minimum wage, unemployed women not receiving an unemployment benefit and for inactive women (category 4). It is not available for foreigners with less than three years of residence or if the spouse is a registered worker. Established by Law 24714, Art. 14 quater.

The following are these benefits' values for each category (1 to 5) in May 2016, when the *Monotributistas* started receiving family benefits. These are given in current pesos. It should be noted though that due to the recent devaluation (December 2015) of the peso, high inflation (around 7% for the month of April 2016) and the temporary lack of official inflation numbers covering all provinces, it is for the moment hazardous to give a value in constant pesos or in dollars of these benefits. It is even more the case for dollars since while the purchasing power of these benefits decreased since the readjustment of March 2016 due to high inflation, the dollar has depreciated relatively to the peso between March and May 2016, giving higher values in dollars than at the moment of these benefits readjustment in March 2016, where their purchasing power was the highest.

Family benefits for registered wage-earners and unemployment benefits recipients (categories 1 and 2), May 2016 (Current pesos)			
Benefit	From	To	Amount
Birth	231	34605	1125
Adoption	231	34605	6748
Marriage	231	34605	1687
Prenatal and Child	231	8652	966
	8652	11305	649
	11305	14650	390
	14650	34605	199
Disabled child	0	8652	3150
	8652	11305	2227
	11305	No limit	1404
Yearly school aid	231	34605	808
Yearly school aid for a disabled child	-	-	808
Family benefits for recipients of SIPA retirement benefits and federal civil servants (category 3), May 2016 (Current pesos)			
Benefit	From	To	Amount
Child	231	8652	966
	8652	11305	649
	11305	14650	390
	14650	34605	199
Disabled child	0	8652	3150
	8652	11305	2227
	11305	No limit	1404
Yearly school aid	231	34605	808
Yearly school aid for a disabled child	-	-	808
Spouse	231	34605	231
Family benefits for unregistered workers, the unemployed without unemployment benefits and inactives (category 4), May 2016 (Current pesos)			
Benefit	Amount		
AUH	966		
AUH Handicap	3150		
Pregnancy	966		
Yearly school aid	808		
Yearly school aid for a disabled child	808		
Family benefits for adherents to the simplified regime for small tax-payers, or <i>Monotributistas</i> , May 2016 (Current pesos)			
Benefit	<i>Monotributo</i> categories	Amount	
Prenatal and child	B to F	966	
	G	649	
	H	390	
	I	199	
Disabled child	B to F	3150	
	G	2227	
	H to L	1404	
Yearly school aid	B to I	808	
Yearly school aid for a disabled child	B to L	808	

Appendix F

Comparing the Law 26417 (2009) and Law 27426 (2018) pension mobility indexes

Between March 2009 and September 2017, pensions and (most) social security benefits were increased every six months. The pension mobility formula is laid out in Law 26417's Appendix and is as follows:

$$m = \min [a; b] \text{ with } a = 0.5 \times RT + 0.5 \times w ; b = 1.03 \times r$$

- m is the mobility in the studied period.
- RT is the variation of ANSES fiscal resources. As established by Resolution 9/2009's Art. 14, these are ANSES revenues excluding social security contributions to ANSES, the 15% of *coparticipable* tax income that was transferred from the Provinces to ANSES following Law 24130's Appendix, Clause I, incise a, and transfers from the National Treasury to cover ANSES deficits.
- w is the general wage index RIPTE's¹ or the general wage index's² variation, whichever is higher.
- r is the variation of total ANSES resources. As established by Resolution 9/2009's Art. 14, these are ANSES revenues excluding transfers from the National Treasury to cover ANSES deficits. This implies that the mobility index cannot grow faster than 1.03 times the increase in total ANSES resources.

¹*Remuneraciones Imponibles Promedio de los Trabajadores Estables*, or mean taxable income of stable workers. It comprises all gross labour revenues of registered wage-earners. It is published monthly by the Ministry of Labour and Social security since July 1994.

²Published by INDEC

The pension mobility index made thus the real adjustment of pensions pro-cyclical, as both real wages and ANSES revenues are positively correlated with the economic cycle. This pro-cyclical element is partially mitigated during an expansive cycle by factor b , which caps pensions increase to 1.03 times the nominal evolution of ANSES total resources. The pension mobility index was thus built as an automatic adjustment mechanism that decreases real pensions expenditure during the downwards cycle and limits their increase when the economy expands.

The regulation of Law 26417's Appendix described in detail how the different elements of the pension mobility index are computed. This is done in ANSES Resolution 9/2009, Art. 14 as cited below:

- "4. RT 's value will result from comparing identical semesters of consecutive years. For the month of March will be considered the existing variation between the periods July-December of the two immediately previous consecutive years. For the computation corresponding to September will be considered the existing variation between the periods January - June of the current year with respect to the immediate previous year. Said variations will be adjusted to the corresponding semester (...) by halving the obtained result. "
- "5. w 's value will result from comparing consecutive semesters. This implies that for March, each year will be taken into account the variation of the index to be taken into account (...) between the months of June and December of the previous year. (...) For computing the amount corresponding to September will be taken into account the variation between December of the previous year and June of the current year of the aforementioned [index]."
- "6. r 's value will result from comparing periods of twelve consecutive months. To these effects will be taken the variation between the January - December periods of the two consecutive immediately previous calendar years."
- "7. The mobility corresponding to each year's month of March will equal " a " of said period's mobility function. The computation of the mobility corresponding to each year's month of September will be considered the accumulated value of " a " for March and September and it will be compared to the value of " b ". If the accumulated value of " a " were to be lower than the limit " b ", then September's mobility will be equal to the " a " computed for said month, were the opposite to happen then the awarded mobility will be the difference between " b "'s value and " a "'s corresponding to March."

- Finally, the minimal possible value of m is 0, so this mobility index may not result in a nominal reduction of social security benefits.

Following IMF policy recommendations (Canales-Kriljenko *et al.*, 2016), and in order to both de-couple social security benefits from the economic cycle and reduce public spending, a new pension mobility index has been established by Appendix I of Law 27426. The exact formula is laid out below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Mov_{mar_t} &= 0.7 \times \left[\left(\frac{IPCN_{sept_{t-1}}}{IPCN_{jun_{t-1}}} \right) - 1 \right] + 0.3 \times \left[\left(\frac{RIPT E_{sept_{t-1}}}{RIPT E_{jun_{t-1}}} \right) - 1 \right] \\
 Mov_{jun_t} &= 0.7 \times \left[\left(\frac{IPCN_{dect_{t-1}}}{IPCN_{sept_{t-1}}} \right) - 1 \right] + 0.3 \times \left[\left(\frac{RIPT E_{dect_{t-1}}}{RIPT E_{sept_{t-1}}} \right) - 1 \right] \\
 Mov_{sept} &= 0.7 \times \left[\left(\frac{IPCN_{mar_t}}{IPCN_{dect_{t-1}}} \right) - 1 \right] + 0.3 \times \left[\left(\frac{RIPT E_{mar_t}}{RIPT E_{dect_{t-1}}} \right) - 1 \right] \\
 Mov_{dect} &= 0.7 \times \left[\left(\frac{IPCN_{jun_t}}{IPCN_{mar_t}} \right) - 1 \right] + 0.3 \times \left[\left(\frac{RIPT E_{jun_t}}{RIPT E_{mar_t}} \right) - 1 \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

- Mov_{m_t} is the mobility that will be implemented during month " m " of year " t ".
- $IPCN_{m_t}$ is the National Consumer Price Index level for month " m " of year " t " as published by the INDEC.
- $RIPT E_{m_t}$ is the Mean Taxable Income of Stable Workers (RIPT E) for month " m " of year " t " as established by the Ministry of Labour's Social Security Secretariat.

By Art. 2 of Law 27426, this new index is applied since the 1st of March 2018. As such, there is an immediate reduction in real terms of all social security benefits that are adjusted following this pension mobility index. Indeed, by March 2018 social security benefits will increase by 5.7% and by another 5.8% in June 2018 following the Law 27426 formula, instead of an estimated 12% in March 2018 with the previous Law 26417 formula (Bermúdez, 2017). Finally, if we assume the retiree had at least 30 years of contributions before retiring and was receiving the minimum benefit in February 2018, he is guaranteed to get a pension at least equal to 82% of the minimum wage, as per Art. 5 of Law 27426. The Resolution 3-E/ 2017 issued by the National Council of Employment, Productivity and Minimum, Vital and Mobile Wage, has set a minimum wage of 9500 pesos starting from the 1st of January 2018 and of 10,000 pesos starting from the 1st of July 2018 (Art. 1). This means the minimum pension for people who contributed 30 years reaches $9500 \times 0.82 = 7790$ pesos since January 2018 (instead of a minimum pension of 7246.64

pesos) and 8200 pesos (instead of an estimated minimum pension of 8103.14 pesos) since July 2018.

As will be shown in the numeric example below, this reform significantly decreases pension income received between the 1st of January and the 31st of August 2018. This is mainly because using this new index on March 2018 deflates social security benefits over a period of three months (from June to September 2017) even though benefits had remained unchanged for six months (since September 2017). Although this was partially corrected in June 2018, where benefits were adjusted following the evolution of the RIPTE and Consumer Price Index (CPI) between September and December 2018, this transition to the Law 27426 index is mired on controversy and under litigation³, as pundits maintain the old Law 26417 pension mobility law should have been applied on March 2018. To partially compensate this decrease in purchasing power, the federal government granted a one-time payment on March 2018 for retirees earning less than 10,000 pesos after the March actualisation, as per Decree 1058/2017⁴. Its amount however depends on the type of pension received. For instance, if the retiree earns a contributory retirement pension, the compensation reaches 750 pesos. If not, it will only reach 375 pesos (Art. 1 and 3). In any case, this payment only partially compensates the loss in income derived from this reform, and will not be renewed in the future. As such, this reform effectively decreases the available income of all social security pensioners, even in the short run.

A last negative element is that pensions are adjusted following the inflation (and nominal wage appreciation) with a greater lag. The current formula adjusts social security benefits on the inflation and nominal wage evolution that happened between 9 and 6 months ago, while the previous formula did so with the evolution of wages and ANSES fiscal income between the last 9 to 3 months. For an adjustment in March, the Law 26417 index adjusted social security benefits following the nominal evolution of variables

³The 5th of June 2018, Room 3 of the Federal Chamber of Social Security determined that using the Law 27426 index for adjusting pensions on March 2018 was retroactive. This is because the latter law was in force since the 29th of December 2017, but March 2018 pension mobility would have been computed on wage and ANSES fiscal resources evolutions between June and December 2017 with Law 26417. The court thus concluded the right to a pension mobility computed between these six months with the previous Law 26417 was already acquired when Law 27426 was passed. Therefore, ignoring these acquired rights makes Law 27426 retroactive, which is unconstitutional. Thus, the court ruling orders pensions paid since March 2018 to be increased accordingly. This court ruling was appealed by the ANSES and it will likely be the Nation's Supreme Court of Justice that ultimately settles this case.

⁴This Decree was issued the 19th of December 2017. It was announced only after the federal government could not reach the quorum to vote the pension reform the 14th of December 2017 in the *Cámara de Diputados* (Argentina's House of Representatives). In exchange, a portion of the parliamentary opposition block "Federal Argentina" aligned with a group of Peronist governors gave the quorum to vote the reform the 19th of December 2017.

between the months of July and December, while the newest Law 27426 index does so for nominal evolutions of wages and inflation between July and September of the previous year. This means the formula shields poorly social security payments from an inflation outburst in the short term. Also, were inflation to decelerate, social security benefits would strongly increase in real terms in the following semester, which would put a strain on future social security expenditure and possibly fuel a renewed inflation outburst.

Let's take for example an individual receiving the minimum pension in January 2018, that is, 7246.64 pesos. With the old pension mobility formula, his nominal retirement income would increase to $7246.64 \times (1 + 0.12) \approx 8116.24$ pesos on March 2018 and would stay at that level until August 2018. He would thus receive $8116.24 \times 6.5 + 7246.64 \times 2 \approx 67,248.86$ pesos in retirement benefits between the months of January and August 2018 (including the "aguinaldo" paid in June). This level would have been the same had he retired normally or through a pension moratorium.

Things get a little more complicated with the new pension mobility formula. Let us first assume he is a moratorium pensioner. Law 27426 will make him get $7246.64 \times (1 + 0.0571) \approx 7660.60$ pesos for the months of March, April and May and $7660.60 \times (1 + 0.0578) \approx 8103.14$ pesos for the months of June, July and August. He would thus receive a total of $3 \times 7660.60 + 3.5 \times 8103.14 + 2 \times 7246.64 \approx 65,836.11$ pesos throughout the period, that is 1412.75 fewer pesos, a nominal reduction of 2.1%. If we factor in the fact this nominal reduction is concentrated in the first months of March, April and May, the real loss in income is higher. After we add the one-time compensation of 375 pesos paid in March 2018 as per Decree 1058/2017, the loss in income decreases to 1037.75 pesos, a nominal reduction of 1.5%.

If we now assume this pensioner had contributed at least 30 years, he gets at least 82% of the minimum wage starting from January 2018. He thus gets $7790 \times 6.5 + 8200 \times 2 = 67,035$ pesos between the months of January and August 2018, that is, 213.86 fewer pesos than with the previous formula or a nominal reduction of 0.3%. After taking into account the one-time bonus of 750 pesos paid on March, his retirement income will see a one-time increase of 536,14 pesos, or 0.8%. This increase is however only relevant for pensioners with 30 years of contributions that earned the minimum pension in January 2018. Those earning higher pensions, *a fortiori* those with earnings above 10,000 pesos that are not eligible to the 750 pesos payment, will see their real income decrease as compared to what they would have been entitled to following the previous pension mobility formula.

In the end, the previous pension mobility Law 26417 ensured that social security benefits were adjusted every semester following a mixture of nominal wage evolutions and ANSES fiscal sources of revenue (mainly part of the VAT and Income taxes), which themselves are closely related to real wage evolutions. This formula was however pro-cyclical, especially during the downward economic cycle. As tax collection, social security contributions and real wages all tend to decrease during a recession, so did pension benefits (although with a slight six months lag). In the upward cycle, social security benefits increase was however capped by 1.03 times the nominal rise of ANSES revenue (excluding figurative contributions from the Treasury made to cover ANSES deficits), which meant an automatic stabilisation mechanism was present in that case. The current Law 27426 indexes social security benefits by 70% on the consumer's price index and by 30% on the RIPTE, and adjusts pensions every three months. This index is less pro-cyclical, but results in lower pensions in the long term assuming real wages increase. Also, the new index shields social security benefits from the inflation that happened three quarters ago. This protects poorly social security benefits from inflation outbursts, and increases the real cost of pensions for social security in the short term were inflation figures to decelerate.

Appendix G

Formal independent workers categories

It is compulsory for independent workers to contribute to social security, as established by Art. 2 of the Integrated System of Retirement benefits and Pensions (which is now called SIPA) Law 24241. The Law 24241¹ pension reform, among other things, merged the independent (following Law 18038²) and dependent (Law 18039³) workers retirement system into the SIJP, which was later renamed SIPA (see Section 1.1.1). Contribution rules however differ between dependent and independent workers. Also, since the creation in 1998 of the Law 24977⁴ Simplified Regime for Small Tax-payers (or *Monotributo*), the latter are subject to two distinct contribution systems: the aforementioned *Monotributo* regime and the more classical Autonomous workers regime, intended for independent workers of higher earnings. We studied in section 1.2.3 how we assigned individuals to either of these two regimes. We will thus study in this Appendix the characteristics of the Autonomous workers and *Monotributo* regimes, their categories and how we determine a contributor belongs to a specific category.

G.1 The Autonomous workers regime: legislation review and current characteristics

First, contributors to the Autonomous workers regime are assigned to a specific category that depends on the nature of their activity, their business's characteristics and, for the most recent classification, their labour income. Then, each category has a taxable income of reference, which enters in the computation of the retirement pension's PAP (as shown

¹Partially issued the 13th of October 1993

²Issued the 10th of January 1969.

³Issued the 16th of January 1969.

⁴Issued the 6th of July 1998

in Appendix B). Finally, from this reference income are computed contributions to the social security system (which is currently called SIPA) and to the PAMI-INSSJP health-care system for the retired. As seen in section 1.1.4, since the Law 24241 reform SIPA and INSSJP contributions respectively amount to 27% and 5% of the reference income.

This organisation of the Autonomous workers regime by contributing categories exists since the Law 18038⁵ pension reform of 1969, and was laid out in its 10th Article. However, the characteristics of these autonomous workers categories have been modified multiple times between the 1970s and the early 1990s, to the point where it is unclear what particular contribution rule was in force at a given period in time. This is made worse by the very high inflation figures between the 1970s and the early 1990s (including two hyperinflation outbursts in 1989 and 1990), which makes complicated to figure out what the reference income or the contributions to the social security system of independent workers in a given category were in real terms. Ultimately, we decided to treat independent workers' revenues prior to the 1st of July 1994, when the Autonomous workers regime established by the Law 24241 retirement system began to function, as though they had been made in dependent labour.

Since the 1st of July 1994 however, the characteristics of each category of autonomous workers are clear. For the period spanning 1994 to 2006, there are 10 autonomous workers categories⁶) that we present in Table G.1 below. Their reference income was first established by Art. 4 of Law 23568⁷ as a multiple of the minimum pension. Unfortunately, the criteria to belong to one of these categories between 1994 and 2006 did not depend on labour income (which we simulate) but on other factors such as the characteristics of the firm they own, the nature of their work, the number of people they employ or their seniority in the position⁸. We do not simulate any of these elements in our backwards microsimulation model. As such, we use the gross reference income as an *ad hoc* criterium for assigning autonomous workers to a given category between 1994 and 2006. If for instance the reference income of categories $n, n \in [B; J]$ and $n - 1, n - 1 \in [A; K]$ are respectively equal to k and j pesos, we assume all individuals in the Autonomous workers regime with an income $i \in]j; k]$ are in category n .

⁵Issued the 10th of January 1969.

⁶These are actually 15 once we add 5 categories with increased contributions stemming from difficult work conditions. These categories only increase social security contributions without changing the reference income, so they do not change pension rights. We thus ignore them when simulating past contributions to social security.

⁷Issued the 21st of June 1988.

⁸The composition of each of these categories is described by Appendix I of Decree 433/94, issued the 24th of March 1994.

Table G.1: Autonomous workers categories in current pesos, 1994-2006

	Legislation	Res. SSS 41/94	Res. SSS 132/95	Res. SSS 46/95	Res. SH 32/96	Decree 978/96	Res. SSS 29/97
	Period	01/07/94→ 31/03/95	01/04/95→ 30/09/95	01/10/95→ 31/03/96	01/04/96→ 31/08/96	01/09/96→ 31/03/97	01/04/97→ 28/02/07
A	Taxable rent	189	216	225	228	296	312
A	Contributions	60.48	69.12	72	72.96	94.72	99.84
B	Taxable rent	232	265	276	280	364	383
B	Contributions	74.24	84.80	88.32	89.60	116.48	122.56
C	Taxable rent	310	354	369	374	486	512
C	Contributions	99.20	113.28	118.08	119.68	155.52	163.84
D	Taxable rent	465	531	553	560	728	766
D	Contributions	148.80	169.92	176.96	179.20	232.96	245.12
E	Taxable rent	775	886	923	935	1215	1279
E	Contributions	248	283.52	295.36	299.20	388.80	409.28
F	Taxable rent	1084	1239	1291	1308	1700	1789
F	Contributions	346.88	396.48	413.12	418.56	544	572.48
G	Taxable rent	1549	1770	1844	1869	2429	2557
G	Contributions	495.68	566.40	590.08	598.08	777.28	818.24
H	Taxable rent	2324	2656	2767	2804	3645	3837
H	Contributions	743.68	849.92	885.44	897.28	1166.40	1227.84
I	Taxable rent	3098	3541	3689	3738	4560	4800
I	Contributions	991.36	1133.12	1180.48	1196.16	1459.20	1536
J	Taxable rent	3780	4320	4500	4560	4560	4800
J	Contributions	1209.60	1382.40	1440	1459.20	1459.20	1536
Contributions are equal to 32% of the reference income. 27% of the reference income goes to the social security system SIJP and 5% to the healthcare for the retired system INSSJP-PAMI.							

One thing to note here is that the last readjustment of this old autonomous workers regime happened the 1st of April 1997. Before that date, autonomous workers categories were periodically readjusted following the changes in the AMPO index. Established by Law 24347⁹ and used in particular for determining the pension of people that retired with the Law 24241 regime, the AMPO index was linked to annual contributions to social security, and thus tended to increase in real terms in the 1994-1997 period. Even though most retirement pensions were not indexed to the AMPO (those of people that had retired before the 1st of July 1994 were frozen, while the 1995 Pension Solidarity Law 24463¹⁰ restricted the application of the AMPO to the computation of the first retirement pension only), the rise of the AMPO considerably increased the real value of autonomous workers' contributions. As such, Decree 833/1997¹¹ replaced the AMPO index with the MOPRE, a new index that was determined by the government and frozen until its elimination by the 2008 Pension Mobility Law 26417¹². As such, the real value of autonomous workers

⁹Issued the 27th of June 1994.

¹⁰Issued the 28th of March 1995

¹¹Issued the 29th of August 1997.

¹²Issued the 15th of October 2008

contributions to social security, and thus of their reference income, decreased significantly between 2002 and 2006, with double-digit yearly inflation rates.

Decree 1866/06¹³ reformed this autonomous worker contribution system. Since the 1st of March 2007, there are only 5 contribution categories¹⁴. To subscribe to one specific category, there are conditions regarding the nature of the position held by the independent worker, characteristics of the firm and annual gross income limitations. All these conditions have been left unchanged, including the yearly gross revenues conditions. On the other hand, the reference income of each category (and thus the related contributions to social security and the PAMI) has been periodically adjusted following the pension mobility index established by Law 26417 since the 1st of March 2009. Table G.2 below describes conditions to adhere to a given category (left unchanged since 2007), while Table G.3 gives the categories' reference income and contributions at inception, after the first March 2009 readjustment and for the September 2017 - February 2018 period.

Table G.2: Decree 1866/06: conditions to adhere to a given autonomous workers category (2007-2018)

Table	Category	Activity	Gross yearly income	
			Minimum	Maximum
I	III	Directors, managers or administrators of civil or commercial companies, or associates of any company(Law 24241, Art. 2, sections b), subsection 1 and d))		15,000
	IV		15,001	30,000
	V		30,001	
II	I	Own-account workers excluded from Table I, included in Law 24241 Art. 2, section b) , that deliver or rent services		20,000
	II		20,001	
III	I	Other own-account workers, included in Law 24241 Art. 2, section b), not in Tables I or II		25,000
	II		25,001	

The gross yearly income restrictions are in current pesos and have not been changed since implementation the 1st of March 2007. This blanks the importance of yearly income in the categorisation of autonomous workers and essentially divides them in two categories: own-account workers, that are enlisted in Category II, and entrepreneurs, enlisted in Category V. This loss of relevance of the gross income thresholds was even present since inception, as can be seen if we compare these thresholds to the sum of the mean gross wage of stable registered employees (RIPTE) for years 2007 to 2010. It equalled for each of these years 22,536.37, 28,939.35, 33,050.21 and 41,699.58 current pesos. This means even the highest threshold of 30,000 pesos that allowed entrepreneurs to register in Category IV was lower than the yearly gross income of registered wage-earners in 2009, two years

¹³Issued the 12th of December 2006.

¹⁴There are 5 additional categories for independent workers with difficult working conditions. They only differ from the normal categories by their increased contributions to social security. We do not simulate working conditions in our microsimulation model, so we ignore these additional categories.

after the reform. In 2016, the sum of each month’s RIPTE was equal to 222,385.98 pesos, showing all these income thresholds were effectively void by then. Table G.3 below shows us how the reference income and contributions of Categories I to V changed between 2007 and 2018.

Table G.3: Autonomous workers categories in current pesos, 2007-2018

	Legislation	Decree 1866/2006	Law 26417 and General Res. 2585/2009	Law 26417 and Res. 176-E/2017
	Period	01/03/07→ 28/02/09	01/03/09→ 31/08/09	01/09/17→ 28/02/18
I	Taxable rent	400	446.76	4200.95
I	Contributions	128	142.96	1344.30
II	Taxable rent	560	625.46	5881.30
II	Contributions	179.20	200.14	1882.01
III	Taxable rent	800	893.52	8401.90
III	Contributions	256	285.93	2688.60
IV	Taxable rent	1280	1429.63	13443.02
IV	Contributions	409.60	457.48	4301.76
V	Taxable rent	1760	1965.74	18484.15
V	Contributions	563.20	629.04	5914.93

Contributions are equal to 32% of the reference income. 27% of the reference income goes to the social security system SIJP-SIPA and 5% to the healthcare for the retired system INSSJP-PAMI.

Each category’s reference income was first determined by Decree 1866/2006 and was indexed following the pension mobility formula starting from the 1st of March 2009. As such, we refrained from putting in Table G.3 all the values of reference incomes and contributions until February 2018, and simply put the last available values. Despite following the pension mobility index between 2009 and 2018, the reference income of autonomous workers is low as of today. For instance, the RIPTE for September 2017 was of 25,136.35 pesos, which is almost five times higher than the reference income of Category II autonomous workers and 35% higher than the reference income of Category V autonomous workers. Autonomous workers contributions are equal to 27% of this reference income, so they are lower than that of most formal wage-earners. Therefore, the resulting rights to a pension of independent workers in the Autonomous workers regime are low.

As a thought experiment, let’s assume three individuals A, B and C contribute 30 years and retire exactly at retirement age. A and B are respectively in Categories II and V and have the reference income of September 2017, while C is a wage-earner earning the RIPTE of September 2017 (25,136.35 pesos). A gets a PAP pension of $5881.30 \times (30 \times 0.015) = 2646.59$ pesos, to which is added a PBU which in September 2017 is set at 3423.58 pesos, for a total of 6070.16 pesos (following the formula laid out in Ap-

pendix B). This is below the minimum pension of 7246.64 pesos, so A gets the minimum pension at retirement. B gets a retirement pension of $18484.15 \times 0.45 + 3423.58 = 11741.45$ pesos, so 62% higher than the minimum pension. Finally, C gets a retirement pension of $25136.35 \times 0.45 + 3423.58 = 14734.94$ pesos, slightly more than twice the minimum pension. Therefore, only the highest autonomous workers category gives access to a pension higher than the legal minimum, and even then the mean pension of a formal wage earner is still 25% higher than the one of the highest category of Autonomous workers.

In the end, we can see the Autonomous workers regime essentially distinguishes own-account workers, who make reduced contributions to social security and have few retirement pension rights, from entrepreneurs, who pay higher contributions. In any case, both these workers accumulate modest pension rights that need to be complemented with periods of dependent work to get more important benefits. Their social security rights are however significantly higher than those of independent workers registered in the *Monotributo* regime, or *Monotributistas*, as will be shown in the Section below.

G.2 The Simplified Regime for Small Tax-payers (or *Monotributo*): legislative background and current characteristics

Since 1998, there exists alongside the Autonomous workers regime a simplified regime for small independent workers, the *Monotributo*. Instituted by Law 24977 and enforced by Decree 885/1998¹⁵ and the General Resolution 198/1998¹⁶, the *Monotributo* started functioning the 15th of October 1998. This regime started with eight different categories. Access to a given category was determined by elements such as gross income, electric consumption or size (in square meters) of the business. Contributions to social security and retirement rights derived from these were the same for all *Monotributo* categories until the 1st of January 2017, as Art. 2 of Law 27346¹⁷ introduced varying social security contributions per *Monotributo* category.

However, *Monotributo* workers are only entitled to the minimum pension. Between its implementation in October 1998 and March 2000, as per Law 24977's Art. 32., all

¹⁵Published the 31st of July 1998.

¹⁶Published the 14th of September 1998.

¹⁷Published the 27th of December 2017.

Monotributistas had access to all benefits included in Law 24241. Decree 885/1998's Art. 50 established a reference income for *Monotributistas* of 300 pesos, derived from their 33 pesos monthly contribution to the SIJP (to which were added 15 pesos of contributions to the INSSJP). The worker could then choose to contribute to the public or private retirement system and get from this reference income either the PAP (see Section 1.1.3) or an additional payment from his private pension fund to complement the PBU.

This was changed by Law 25239¹⁸ that made the personal contributions of *Monotributistas* to the pension system optional (through section n) of its Art. 20). It also made additional retirement pensions beyond the PBU (the PAP or, before their nationalisation in 2008, payments by private pension funds) depend on these optional contributions. Compulsory contributions to the *Monotributo* still grant access to the PBU (and hence to the minimum retirement pension), survivors' benefits derived from the death or disability of the contributor and healthcare (through section o) of Law 25239's Art. 20). These optional contributions were implemented through AFIP's General Resolution 749/2000¹⁹ and were in force since April 2000. Finally, Law 26565²⁰, through its Appendix's Art. 39, eliminated the possibility of making these additional voluntary contributions to social security in December 2009. This means it is *de jure* impossible since then for *Monotributistas* to contribute extra to the pension system in order to get access to the PAP, although it is likely the vast majority of them did not make additional contributions to social security when it was possible between 2000 and 2009.

Recently, two reforms introduced first varying social security contributions by Category (Law 27346, Art. 2, implemented since the 1st of January 2017), then an indexation of all *Monotributo* categories, contributions and taxes on the past year's pension mobility (Law 27430's Art. 161²¹, implemented since the 1st of January 2018). When first applied, Law 27430 resulted in an increase of all nominal values in the *Monotributo* categories of 28%, as can be verified in Table G.4. This value is obtained by multiplying the two pension mobility coefficients of 2017: $(1 + 0.1296) \times (1 + 0.1332) \approx 1.2800$. This means there should be no medium term impact of inflation figures neither on the criteria of entry to a given *Monotributo* category nor on real taxes and contributions paid by *Monotributistas*.

Conditions of entry in the *Monotributo* are varied and combine characteristics of the business, annual labour income and other variables such as annual rent paid or electric

¹⁸Issued the 30th of December 1999.

¹⁹Published the 8th of March 2000.

²⁰Published the 21st of December 2009.

²¹This article replaces Law 24730's Art. 161.

consumption. Out of all these variables, only labour income is measured by the EPH and simulated by our microsimulation model. The problem is the maximum values of these thresholds are very high to the point virtually all independent workers can be *Monotributistas*. For instance, only 2% of independent workers in the EPHc interviewed during the fourth quarter of 2016 had earnings above the 400,000 pesos gross annual income limit valid at the time. This percentage even drops to 0.5% of independent workers the next quarter, when the threshold was raised to 700,000 pesos²². As such, we ignore conditions to enter the *Monotributo* in our model and are only interested in assigning individuals to a specific *Monotributo* category.

From a social security point of view though, this is only relevant for determining social security income as all *Monotributistas* get the same retirement rights (the minimum pension). We will thus only study the *Monotributo* categories relevant for our prospective microsimulations, that is, since 2014. The *Monotributo* acts as a source of income for ANSES through two channels. The first is social security contributions to the SIPA, currently established by Law 24977's Art. 39, which until the 1st of July 2018 will be the same for all categories. The second is the "integrated tax" determined by Art. 11 of Law 24977, which combines both the income tax and the VAT in one fixed payment. 70% of this integrated tax goes to the SIPA as per Art. 53 of Law 24977. This effectively means that in what regards ANSES income derived from the *Monotributo* regime, it is important to distribute the *Monotributistas* by category, particularly since 2017 where social security contributions started to differ by *Monotributo* category. For the sake of simplicity, belonging to a *Monotributo* category will only be decided by the simulated income. We thus ignore categories reserved to independent workers that exclusively sell personal property. Finally, the integrated tax differs for some categories depending on the independent worker's activity (selling personal property on the one hand, renting or providing services on the other hand). In those cases, we took the mean of both values and considered all *Monotributistas* of a given category paid the same integrated tax. Table G.4 below describes the *Monotributo* categories that exist since 2014.

²²This was done by Law 27346, Art. 2, and effective between the first of January 2017 and the 31st of December 2017.

Table G.4: *Monotributo* taxes, contributions and yearly gross income conditions by category, 2014-2018

	Yearly gross income	Integrated tax	SIPA contributions	Healthcare contributions
	01/01/2014 → 31/12/2016			
B	48,000	39	157	146 ^a 233 ^b 323 ^c 419 ^d
C	72,000	75	157	146 ^a 233 ^b 323 ^c 419 ^d
D	96,000	123	157	146 ^a 233 ^b 323 ^c 419 ^d
E	144,000	202	157	146 ^a 233 ^b 323 ^c 419 ^d
F	192,000	355	157	146 ^a 233 ^b 323 ^c 419 ^d
G	240,000	477.50	157	146 ^a 233 ^b 323 ^c 419 ^d
H	288,000	602.50	157	146 ^a 233 ^b 323 ^c 419 ^d
I	400,000	1420	157	146 ^a 233 ^b 323 ^c 419 ^d
	01/01/2017 → 31/12/2017			
A	84,000	68	300	419
B	126,000	131	330	419
C	168,000	215.50	363	419
D	252,000	354	399.30	419
E	336,000	621.50	439.23	419
F	420,000	836	483.15	419
G	504,000	1054.50	531.47	419
H	700,000	2485	584.61	419
	01/01/2018 → 31/12/2018			
A	107,525.27	87.04	384.02	536.35
B	161,287.90	167.69	422.42	536.35
C	215,050.54	275.85	464.66	536.35
D	322,575.81	453.14	511.13	536.35
E	430,101.07	795.56	562.24	536.35
Healthcare contributions were periodically modified between 2014 and 2016. a: valid until 31/08/14. b: 01/09/14 - 31/06/15. c: 01/07/15 - 31/05/16. d: 01/06/16 - 31/12/17.				
Source: AFIP's website, accessed the 18th of January 2018 : http://www.afip.gob.ar/monotributo/categorias.asp#ver				

	Yearly gross income	Integrated tax	SIPA contributions	Healthcare contributions
F	537,626.34	1070.13	618.46	536.35
G	645,151.61	1349.83	680.31	536.35
H	896,043.90	3180.96	748.34	536.35

Healthcare contributions were periodically modified between 2014 and 2016. a: valid until 31/08/14. b: 01/09/14 - 31/06/15. c: 01/07/15 - 31/05/16. d: 01/06/16 - 31/12/17.

Source: AFIP's website, accessed the 18th of January 2018 : <http://www.afip.gob.ar/monotributo/categorias.asp#ver>

We can see despite the significant increase of social security contributions starting from 2017, these remain low in real terms. If we take the exchange rate of the 18th of January 2018, *Monotributistas* in Category H contribute to social security 42 US dollars a month, while those in Category A only contribute 20 US dollars a month. These amounts respectively increase up to 160 and 24 US dollars once we take into account the fact 70% of the integrated tax goes to ANSES. We can also see these payments to ANSES by Category A and H *Monotributistas* respectively represent 5% and 4% of the monthly gross income derived from their categories' yearly income threshold. As a way of comparison, people in the Autonomous workers regime pay contributions to the SIPA equal to 27% of their Category's reference income. As such, we see *Monotributistas* contributions to ANSES remain very low compared to other workers, which explains why they get only access to the minimum retirement pension. In 2017, all *Monotributo* sources of income assigned to social security (included health-care contributions) represented only 3% of contributions to social security²³.

²³Source: own calculus based on AFIP's compared tax income for years 2017 and 2016.

Appendix H

Identifying formal dependent and independent workers in the EPH (1974-2017)

In this Appendix, we give an in-depth description of the strategies we adopted for identifying labour formality in Argentina's EPH household survey throughout the 1974-2017 period. First, we present the methodology we used for identifying formal wage-earners. Then, we will analyse how we determined what independent workers belonged to the formal sector.

H.1 Identifying formal wage-earners in earlier waves of the EPH (1974-2003)

We have described in section 1.2.2 how we identified formal wage earners in the continuous EPHc survey (2003-2017). In that case, wage-earners are directly asked whether they contribute to a pension scheme through questions pp07H and pp07I¹. Those that answer positively to either of these questions are considered as formal wage-earners. When we work with EPH surveys carried out before 2003, things get a little more complicated. As stated in section 1.2.1., in that period there are three available datasets: the BUA (1995-2003), the BT and the BU (1974-1994). For the BUA and the BT, the variable P23 ("Benefits of the wage-earners") gives a measure of social security equivalent to variable pp07H in the EPHc. Indeed, it includes the following list of benefits associated with the

¹Questions pp07H and pp07I of the EPHc ask wage-earners whether they contribute to a pension scheme. The former asks them whether their employer makes retirement contributions on their behalf, and the latter whether they make retirement contributions on their own.

occupation: severance pay, holidays, 13th month, retirement, labour risks insurance and other benefits. However, P23 is the sum of all the codes of the aforementioned benefits. For correctly reading this variable one needs to refer to (Clyde *et al.* , 2003, p. 40). In this document, we get a list of all values of P23 corresponding to wage-earners who benefit from a retirement pension insurance. We can thus, in a similar way than with the EPHc, consider these workers are formal, since it is the definition that more closely matches our needs. This methodological choice is validated by the fact we barely see any significant change in the share of informal workers between the last period of the BUA (May 2003) and the first period of the EPHc (third quarter of 2003) as evidenced by Figure 1.7.

Still, the dataset that poses the biggest problem for identifying formal wage-earners is the BU. Indeed, the only variable allowing for a legalistic definition of informality is BENEf, which inquires on the benefits associated with the dependent worker's job. Possible answers registered by the BENEf variable are "1- Only one benefit and 13th month and holidays" "2- Combinations with severance pay" "3- Combinations without severance pay" "4- All benefits" and "5- No benefits". Although answer 5 clearly corresponds to informal workers and answer 4 to formal workers according to a legalistic definition of formality, there is a problem with individuals having only some benefits (answers 1 to 3), since we cannot know from this survey whether retirement benefits are one of these. We cannot however only consider as formal workers having all benefits: although these represented 44% of people of working age in the BU of October 1980 and October 1982, in October 1981 this figure dropped to 20%, with the proportion of individuals who responded with answer 3 increasing by the same amount. We have hence adopted an intermediate solution, where individuals with answers 2, 3 and 4 are considered as formal, whereas people answering 1 or 5 count as informal wage-earners. This way we get a figure for formal dependent employment reaching around 55% of the labour force in the first half of the 1980s, which is only slightly higher than figures we get with the BT in that same time period (around 50%). We also avoid a sudden surge in informal employment in 1981 that did not correspond to any particular sudden and short-lived economic crisis at the time.

H.2 Identifying independent workers of the formal sector in the EPH (1974-2017)

Secondly, we adopt a sectoral definition of formal independent labour as explained in section 1.2.2. More specifically, we mimic Maurizio (2012), who also works with the EPHc, in identifying formal independent workers. For any given independent worker, if he is the owner of a firm with 6 employees or more working under him or if the firm belongs to the public sector, then he is considered as a formal independent worker. If the independent worker owns a firm with 5 or less workers (including himself), or if he is self-employed, the most qualified independent workers are considered formal. We do this across all samples in the EPH, but adapting to the variables at hand. For periods covered by the EPHc, we use the variable PP04D_COD that describes the respondent's occupation, including the position's degree of qualification. We consider all positions requiring at least a technical qualification (ending with digits 1 or 2) as formal. This allows us to have a percentage of formal non-wage earners for the third and fourth quarters of 2006 of 5.10% of working age individuals, which is close to Maurizio's 4.4% of formal non-wage earners estimated for the same period (Maurizio, 2012, p. 11). Knowing that on the second semester of 2006 5.4% of the working age population was either contributing as a *Monotributista* (3.65%) or as an autonomous independent worker (1.74%), our estimation of formal independent work is closer to the actual figures than Maurizio (2012)'s². Before 2003, we make do with the variables at hand. For the BUA and the BT we use variable P20, and for the BU variable "TAREA". Similarly to PP04D_COD, both variables depict the position occupied in the job, and their last digit corresponds to the position's required qualification. For periods not covered by the EPHc, we still combine sectoral and qualification aspects to identify formal non-wage earners. We consider that all independent workers working in the public sector or employing five individuals are formal. For small independent workers working in the private sector, only those occupying qualified positions are considered as formal.

However, the coding of variable P20³ gradually changed between October 1992 and October 1997, when the chosen occupation classifier gradually shifted from the CO-EPH⁴ to the CNO⁵ (INDEC, 2000, p. 4). For both the CNO and the CO-EPH, a last digit of 1 or 4 means the position needs respectively a professional qualification or no qualification

²Source: own calculations on contributors data from AFIP's Monthly Social Security Bulletins and using DEIS (2007)'s demographic estimations for 2006.

³Variable TAREA only appears in the BU, which was last used in 1990. It was thus always coded following the CO-EPH classifier.

⁴*Clasificador de EPH de Ocupaciones*

⁵*Clasificador Nacional de Ocupaciones*, developed for the 1991 Census.

at all. However, the meaning of a last digit of 2 or 3 changed. In the CNO, the former stands for technical qualification and the latter for operative qualification. In accordance with the discrimination strategy we adopted for the EPHc, we thus deem qualified small independent workers occupying positions requiring a professional or technical qualification (P20 ending with digits 1 or 2). However, with the CO-EPH, digits 2 and 3 respectively correspond to qualified and semi-qualified positions. Although semi qualified positions in the CO-EPH would be classified as requiring an operative qualification in the CNO, qualified positions in the CO-EPH can correspond either to CNO's technical or operative qualification (INDEC, 2000, p. 15). So although in the CO-EPH semi-qualified positions (digit 3) occupied by small independents can be classified as informal, it would not be congruent with the identification strategy we adopted for the CNO classification to assume all small independents surveyed with the CO-EPH occupying a qualified position were qualified. It is possible to overcome this limit by assuming all small independents whose occupation was considered qualified (P20 ending with 2) following the CO-EPH classification but that did not attain a complete secondary education belonged to the informal sector. Likewise, small independents occupying a qualified position per the CO-EPH classification that did complete their secondary education are considered as belonging to the formal sector. We thus adopt this strategy for all periods and urban areas where the CO-EPH is used, as described in (INDEC, 2000, p. 4), for the BUA, the BT and the BU. This method is also consistent with the aforementioned stylised facts that independent workers with higher levels of education tend to belong to the formal sector (De Paula & Scheinkman, 2011). With this strategy, we get formal independent labour shares that are stable throughout the 1980s and 1990s despite the presence of incompatible occupation classifiers (CNO and CO-EPH) and of different EPH datasets (the EPHc, BUA, BT and BU).

In the end, our methodologies for identifying formal wage-earners and independent workers in the EPH are coherent through all the versions of the EPH survey (1974-2017). This allows for a time consistent characterisation of labour formality, as evidenced in Figures 1.7 to 1.9 where we see there are no jumps in the proportions of formal dependent or independent workers when we shift from one version of the EPH to the other. This consistency is crucial for recreating plausible individual careers and past social security contributions that reflect historical labour-market evolutions.

Appendix I

Definition and computation of the individual id, and examples for computing father's id, mother's id and partner's id.

In this appendix, we will give more technical explanations on some elements concerning family links. First and foremost, we need to explain how ids work in the EPH. The individual id, which once assigned does not change when the household is surveyed again, is made of a combination of three distinct variables: CODUSU, NRO_HOGAR and COMPONENTE. CODUSU is the dwelling's id, NRO_HOGAR distinguishes each independent household within the same dwelling and COMPONENTE is a number assigned to each member of the household. In our study, we define a household identification variable HOGAR as the concatenation of variables CODUSU and NRO_HOGAR, which is equal for all members of a given household, and an individual identification variable ID which is the concatenation of variables HOGAR and COMPONENTE. But the variable COMPONENTE is not set arbitrarily: it is closely linked to variable CH03, which defines each individual's link to the household head. Except for some exceptions¹, it follows the hierarchy established in the variable CH03². Since by construction all households have a head (at least when first interviewed) and the household head position is the first in this hierarchy, all individuals with a COMPONENTE of 1 are household heads. Furthermore, the variable COMPONENTE is incremental, in order for each individual id resulting from

¹COMPONENTE equals 51 for domestic service workers housed within the household and 71 for individuals living in pensioners households.

²This hierarchy is: household head, his spouse, his children, his son-in-laws or daughter-in-laws, his grandchildren, his parents, his father-in-law or mother-in-law, his siblings, other kinsmen and not kinsmen.

the combination of CODUSU, NRO_HOGAR and COMPONENTE to be unique. Finally, the COMPONENTE variable is continuous: if there are for instance 5 members in a household, the COMPONENTE will always go from 1 through 5 the first time the household is interviewed³. However, if when surveyed a second time an individual in the household is missing or there is a new arrival, the id of the individuals previously interviewed in the household will not change. This also permits following individuals through time, if they are interviewed again. Hence, we can say variable COMPONENTE, while permitting the construction of a unique individual id, partially reflects the individual's position within the household.

Our strategy in determining family links will consist in trying to guess, for each person taken individually, what would be the value for the COMPONENTE variable of the remaining members of the household, depending on each configuration possible within the household. Since we know variable COMPONENTE is continuous and incremental, it cannot be larger than the number of dwellers within a household when first surveyed, if we exclude the aforementioned exceptions which concern anyway non-relatives. As long as we take an arbitrarily high maximum number of household residents⁴, for any given value of HOGAR we can determine all possible ids for that household's residents. Each hypothetical id that matches someone's in the base is stored within the individual observation by value of the COMPONENTE, reported kinship to the household head (variable CH03), gender and reported civil status. This avoids overwriting information within each individual record: if there are two male single individuals who report being the household head's children their individual ids will be stored in two different variables. This way, all the other household dwellers' ids are accessible within each individual's observation. From then on, we get the ids of each individual's father, mother and partner following the rules we established in sections 2.3.2. and 2.3.3. Once this is done, it becomes straightforward to count the respondent's number of children. We only need to count the number of individuals that have the respondent's id as their mother or father's id. To get the number of minors under their care we only count children under the age of 18, and for the number of little children we retain children under the age of 5⁵.

Let us take some examples in order to show first how variable COMPONENTE works,

³The exception again being values of 51 for domestic service workers and 71 for pensioners households dwellers.

⁴We have in our case set it at 23.

⁵This is due to the fact that since the age of 5 and onward, virtually all children in Argentina attend school. Childcare needs decrease hence significantly, reducing the negative impact of parenthood on the possibility to work, specially for women. This variable's effect on labour supply is studied in detail in section 2.3.

then how we compute family links. Let us take household 1, a nuclear family consisting on a male household head (with a CH03 of 1), the head's female spouse (CH03=2) and their three children (who all have a CH03 of 3). Their individual ids will be, following the above order, 11, 12, 13, 14 and 15. In this case, the kinship variable CH03 is enough to establish all family ids. Indeed, since 11 has a kinship variable of 1 and 12 a kinship variable of 2, 11's partner id is set to 12 and 12's partner id is set to 11, without the need to ascertain their civil statuses show they are indeed married or in a common-law union. Likewise, since their CH03 is set at 3, we know both 13, 14 and 15's parent's ids are 11 and 12. We then check 11 and 12's gender, and thus set as father's id 11 and as mother's id 12.

It is still possible to get by with only variables CH03 and CH04 (which establishes the individual's gender) for some households lacking secondary conjugal nuclei centred around one of the head's children. Let us take household 2 consisting on a male head (CH03=1), his female spouse (CH03=2), two children (CH03=3), the head's mother-in-law and father-in-law (CH03=7), and the head's mother (CH03=6). The ids will be 21 for the male head, 22 for his spouse, 23 and 24 for their children, 25 for the head's mother and (for instance, since there is no precise hierarchy among individuals with the same value for CH03) 26 for the father-in-law and 27 for the mother-in-law. As with household 1, CH03 is enough to establish the partner's id for the head and his spouse, and to establish the mother and father id for the children 23 and 24. However, since 26 and 27 are both parents in law of 21, then they are each other's partners, and 22's father's id is 26 and mother's id, 27. Also, the head's mother id will be 25. Now, suppose household 2 is interviewed again and this time the couple made by 21 and 22 gave birth to a girl. Although if we strictly followed CH03's hierarchy her id should be 25, since the other household dweller's ids cannot be changed, she gets id 28.

Now let's take household 3 consisting on 6 individuals: a male household head (CH03=1), his female spouse (CH03=2), two male children (CH03=3), a female daughter-in-law (CH03=4) and a grandchild (CH03=5). Their ids will be 31 for the head, 32 for his spouse, 33 and 34 for their two sons, 35 for the daughter-in-law and 36 for the grandchild. Although we can, solely through kinship and gender variables, get family links for the primary conjugal nucleus made by 31, 32, 33 and 34, the family links of 35 and 36 cannot be established with absolute certainty. Indeed, there is no definite evidence that 35 is actually the partner of an absent child of 31 and 32. There is no definite evidence that 36 is 35's child either. Finally, if we suppose as is most likely to be the case that either 33 or 34 are 35's spouse and that 36 is their child, it is impossible to tell with only kinship and gender variables whether 33 or 34 is 35's partner. Variable civil status can however

help discern with a reasonably high likelihood the secondary conjugal nucleus. If 35 is either married or in a common-law union and only one of the head's children, say 33, has 35's civil status, then 33 and 35 are married / in a common-law union between each other and form the household's secondary conjugal nucleus. If 34 is also single, it hence becomes possible to attach 36 to that secondary conjugal nucleus, and 36 gets a mother id of 35 and a father id of 33. However, if 34 is not single but of a different civil status than 33, 33 and 35 still form a conjugal nucleus but we don't consider 36 to be their child, since it may now be 34's with a reasonable probability. Now, let's assume both 34 and 35 report being single and 33 is not single. In that case, following the identification strategy established in section 2.3.3., 33 is identified as 36's father and neither 34 nor 35 get a partner id. Finally, let's assume 33, 34 and 35 all report being married. In that case, it is impossible to distinguish the secondary conjugal nucleus and hence 33, 34 and 35 get no partner's id and 36 gets no parent's id. As has however been said in section 2.3.3., most of the time a son or daughter-in-law is present in the household, there is exactly one non-single head's child, and he is of the opposite gender of the son or daughter-in-law. Hence, identifying the secondary conjugal nucleus becomes possible with the aforementioned rules. Additionally, as has been stated above, most grandchildren are assigned at least one parent, since in the households they are present, there is often exactly one non-single household head's child. Therefore, in households such as 3 where a son or daughter-in-law or a grandchild is present, we can still manage to identify most of the time the secondary conjugal nucleus involving one of the head's children.

Chapter 2

Building a dynamic microsimulation model for Argentina: methodological foundations, individual-level behaviour simulation and model fitness to our data

2.1 Why dynamic microsimulation? Definition, literature review and motivations for choosing it to model social security in Argentina

2.1.1 What is dynamic microsimulation?

A developing simulation method suffering from a fragmented field

To define it briefly, we can say that a microsimulation model simulates unit-level behaviour, accounting for the diversity of characteristics among the population. The microsimulation literature in economics is quite old, as it traces back to Orcutt's seminal paper (Orcutt, 1957) and has a first application in Orcutt *et al.* (1961). In the fields of economics and sociology it is mostly used to analyse social and economic policies, since these are often targeted to specific segments of the population following a set of requirements. Static microsimulation models simulate an immediate response to a shock, without a time dimension. Some examples of static microsimulation models are the EUROMOD (Sutherland, 2007) model and the IZAΨMOD (Peichl *et al.*, 2010) model. Dynamic mi-

crossimulation models, on the other hand, model this behaviour over time. As explained by Li and O'Donoghue, "dynamic models (...) extend the static model by allowing individuals to change their characteristics due to endogenous factors within the model (...) and let individual units to progress over time"(Li & O'Donoghue, 2013, p. 4). These are the most common in the economic field, since they make it possible to generate synthetic micro-level data useful for prospective analysis. As described by Li & O'Donoghue (2013), "[in] order to evaluate certain impacts of public policies (...) it is necessary to utilise a long panel data set. In general, such data sets are not available, either because the analysis relates to the future, as in the case of pension forecasts, or because collected data sets do not cover sufficiently long time periods; therefore, analysts use dynamic microsimulation models to assist in their analysis (...). Essentially, microsimulation is a tool to generate synthetic micro-unit based data, which can then be used to answer many "what-if" questions that, otherwise, cannot be answered." (Li & O'Donoghue, 2013, p. 4). Some existing models that are used for studying pension reform or future income distribution are for example LIAM (O'Donoghue *et al.* , 2009) (used to study for instance the redistributive impact of pension reform in Ireland (O'Donoghue, 2005)), PRISM (Kennell & Sheils, 1990) or MIDAS for Belgium, Germany and Italy [p. 325-357](Dekkers *et al.* , 2010a). Examples for France include DESTINIE 1 (Bonnet & Mahieu, 2000) and DESTINIE 2 (Blanchet *et al.* , 2011), PRISME (Albert *et al.* , 2009) and TRAJECTOIRE (Duc *et al.* , 2013).

However, one of the major problems of the field has been its fragmentation. As Li and O'Donoghue explain, "microsimulation models are mostly developed in governmental or policy institutions, where developing a literature on which a wider group of scientists has built has been a lesser objective. Furthermore, the documents are mainly spread with limited books and conference presentations, which may not be easily available for researchers outside of the network. (...)Thus a significant proportion of the extensive methods used in the field are not formally codified, meaning that to a large extent new models have had to reinvent the wheel and redevelop existing methods over and over again. This has made it very difficult to work in the field"(Li & O'Donoghue, 2013, p. 34). In addition to the intrinsic complexity of microsimulation models and of their high computing power needs and time, these aspects hamper the transfer of knowledge and know-how in the field. It also meant entry costs in the field were for a long time particularly high. Moreover since a microsimulation model cannot be properly explained in a standard paper, most of the available literature are working papers or reports from organisations describing their microsimulation model. All these elements make it very difficult to replicate previous results using the same methodology, an aspect aggravated by the fact these models mostly use administrative data that is not always publicly available.

Some steps have however been taken in recent years to overcome this field's fragmentation. First of all, in 2005 was created the International Microsimulation Association (IMA), whose goal is to "promote the free inter-change of experience and ideas between practitioners of microsimulation worldwide". Sponsored by various public research bodies¹, this association regularly holds international conferences and workshops on microsimulation modelling that gather contributions on various socio-economic topics from all around the world. An example of such conferences' presentations can be found in the book by Dekkers *et al.* (2016) that presents "a selection of chapters based on presentations held during the 2011 IMA conference in Stockholm" (Dekkers *et al.* , 2016, p. 2). The IMA also edits the International Journal of Microsimulation since 2007, a peer-reviewed online publication specialised in the field of microsimulation modelling. These initiatives help structure an open microsimulation field where exchanges between researchers are facilitated. These specialised conferences and journal also offer more visibility for research on microsimulation modelling, be them from individual researchers or undertaken from within public research bodies.

A recent development: freely available software for microsimulation modelling

Another aspect that has helped overcome the fragmentation of the microsimulation field is the development of software that not only is accessible but also offers increasing modelling possibilities at lower computation times. This is a decisive factor, as it becomes possible for economic modellers to use a microsimulation technique without having to code it from scratch and reduces the number of people needed for developing a microsimulation model. If we add to this the continued increase in computing power of standard individual computers, it becomes possible to make a fully functional microsimulation model with a laptop. Most importantly, a number of freely accessible open-source microsimulation toolboxes have been recently made available. The most relevant examples include the LIAM2 model (Bryon *et al.* , 2015; De Menten *et al.* , 2014) developed by the Belgian Federal Planning Bureau and the recent JAS-mine simulation platform (Richiardi & Richardson, 2017a,b). Their objective is "to make microsimulation models much easier to develop" (De Menten *et al.* , 2014, p. 1) by providing a ready to use environment that takes care of most of the procedures needed for developing a microsimulation model. Both packages are good resources to carry out microsimulation modelling and are optimised so as to increase

¹As of the 11th of August 2017, the sponsors listed in IMA's official website are: NATSEM at the University of Canberra, Australia; Teagasc, Ireland; LISER, Luxembourg; INED, France; CEIS, Italy; Australian Projections, Australia; and CANPI, Hungary. This full list can be found in <http://www.microsimulation.org/sponsoring-institutions/>

computation speed with fewer system requirements. As such, they are both capable of making simulations with very large data-sets in a limited time (De Menten *et al.* , 2014) (Richiardi & Richardson, 2017b, p. 129).

We chose LIAM2 to develop our microsimulation model. Indeed, LIAM2 allows to build a microsimulation model from scratch with no particular programming skills. Although it is coded in Python, it uses a simplified programming language that is easy to learn. Its computation times are remarkably low, as we have witnessed with our model. In our retrospective module that reconstitutes individual careers (see section 2.2.2), it only takes us 10 minutes to model the behaviour of an initial dataset of around 50.000 individuals over 243 periods (60 years and three quarters with a quarterly step) using a mainstream personal computer with 16 GB of RAM. This software is however specialised in microsimulation modelling. As stated in their user manual, “the goal of the project is to let modellers concentrate on what is strictly specific to their model without having to worry about the technical details. This is achieved by providing a generic microsimulation toolbox which is not tied to a particular model. By making it available for free, our hope is to greatly reduce the development costs (in term of both time and money) of microsimulation models” (Bryon *et al.* , 2015, p. 1). LIAM2 has thus all the features we needed to individually develop a dynamic microsimulation model for Argentina’s main social security body, the ANSES, without needing to rely on public research bodies or a team of researchers devoted to the model. Developing our model with LIAM2 however lead to two methodological restrictions. First, LIAM2 only supports logistic regressions for simulating individual behaviour, barring the use of probit models. More importantly though, LIAM2 simulates transitions through a Monte-Carlo simulation method called alignment by sorting procedure. This methodology combines micro and macro-level calibration. It ensures the model not only simulates a plausible individual behaviour but also generates a population that presents the wanted aggregate characteristics, be them historical rates or prospective scenarios. Box 2 below gives a more detailed definition of alignment by sorting. As such, this procedure is widely used in our prospective and retrospective modules, as will be seen in the remainder of this Chapter.

Box 2: The alignment by sorting procedure

Most of the transitions in LIAM2 are modelled using an alignment by sorting procedure. Let's assume we have a polytomous state variable x_t that can take n different values ($a_{1,t}$ to $a_{n,t}$) and is defined for all individuals in universe Ω_t . Then, for each individual in Ω_t and possible state $a_{i,t+1}$, $i \in [1;n]$, we compute a propensity score that depicts the likelihood of being in that state. This score can be purely random (see our retrospective civil status module in section 2.4.2, where we select couples in a common-law union in $t - 1$ that married in t). The score can also be computed through a logistic regression when we want to simulate an individual behaviour that is coherent with observed transitions (see our simulation of labour-market transitions in section 2.3). After that, we sort individuals by their scores and align them with the desired aggregate values of $a_{i,t+1}$ in a Monte-Carlo simulation framework. Let us say in period $t + 1$ we need to have $n_{i,t+1}\%$ of individuals in universe Ω_t be in state $a_{i,t+1}$ as per our scenario. We take the $n_{i,t+1}\%$ individuals ranked with the highest scores and make them be in state $a_{i,t+1}$ in period $t + 1$. A random component ensures the same individuals with the highest propensity scores to be in state $a_{i,t+1}$ are not always selected to make that transition. This implies the chosen seed for this random component has a slight impact in simulated behaviour at the individual level, which is called Monte-Carlo variation (Simpson, 2015).

At the time we started developing our model in 2014, LIAM2 was the only microsimulation toolbox we had access to. However, the very recent emergence of JAS-mine represents an interesting alternative for microsimulation modelling. It is thus important as part of our literature review to describe this platform, although it is not used in this thesis. JAS-mine is a "Java-based computational platform that features tools to support the development of large-scale, data-driven, discrete-event simulations. JAS-mine is specifically designed for both agent-based and microsimulation modelling, anticipating a convergence between the two approaches" (Richiardi & Richardson, 2017b, p. 1). This allows for more modelling possibilities than LIAM2 (which does not allow for agent-based modelling) while also including microsimulation capabilities that are on par with those of LIAM2. For instance, JAS-mine is capable of running the demonstration code provided with LIAM2 (Richiardi & Richardson, 2017a). JAS-mine's architecture is moreover more suited for team work, as it "is built around the idea that model development generally involves the task of several people, who should work in parallel(...). [The] real bottleneck in computational modelling comes not from processor power but from the human element of designing and writing code. Hence, parallelisation in development, and not just

parallelisation in execution, becomes crucial" (Richiardi & Richardson, 2017b, p. 107). JAS-mine is not however user-friendly, as it requires mastering the Java programming language before using it. This disadvantage is counterbalanced by JAS-mine's architecture "[that achieves] a complete parallelisation between the tasks of the econometricians and those of the programmers" (Richiardi & Richardson, 2017b, p. 106), so that only the latter actually need to know Java. Despite this shortcoming, the JAS-mine platform is an interesting choice for developing a microsimulation model. It is not within the scope of this thesis to advocate for the use of one model over the other, but the emergence of various free and open source kits for microsimulation modelling is a welcome development in the field.

Therefore, this thesis carries out retirement and social security projections of ANSES by developing a dynamic microsimulation model coded with LIAM2. Our starting population is respondents of the EPHc (see section 1.2) surveyed between 2014 and 2015. Our modelling choices are based mostly on working papers about existing pension-related microsimulation models. The core of this model is based on LIAM2's capabilities and demonstration code (Bryon *et al.* , 2015). In what regards econometric modelling choices, the most direct reference is DREES' TRAJECTOIRE model (Duc *et al.* , 2013) that is our foremost inspiration for our wage equations (see section 2.3.2). We do model labour-market transition with behavioural equations that are similar to the dynamic microsimulation models of the INSEE (Destinie 2, (Blanchet *et al.* , 2011)) and the CNAV (PRISME (Berteau-Rapin *et al.* , 2015)), as can be seen in section 2.3.1. These are the leading models for microsimulation of pension policy in France, although there are many others that currently exist, particularly for other countries². However, since none of these models are open source nor directly implementable to Argentina's pension system, this thesis only follows some of their methodological choices in our study of Argentina's social security system.

2.1.2 Why choose dynamic microsimulation? The pertinence of this methodology for simulating social security in Argentina

After defining microsimulation modelling, making a literature review of the field and inscribing our own model within it, we have shown microsimulation modelling is a common choice when projecting social security systems' sustainability and adequacy. Before

²Li and O'Donoghue (Li & O'Donoghue, 2013, p. 9) provide an exhaustive list of existing dynamic microsimulation models and of their uses.

presenting our model in detail, it is important to justify why we chose a microsimulation framework for projecting Argentina’s social security sustainability and adequacy instead of developing a macro-level model. The main reason is that “microsimulation models (...) differ from (semi-) aggregate budgetary models in that they simulate the impact of policy measures and schemes on real people, and not on averages or representative agents. (...) Where macro simulation considers averages, a micro simulation model attempts to take into account the heterogeneity behind the average.”(Dekkers *et al.* , 2012, p. 4). Since a number of conditions come into play when considering both benefits granted and the amount a given individual must contribute (as seen in section 1.1), it was only by going down to the individual level that we deemed possible to precisely study and project ANSES benefits and contributions. Such intra-cohort precision is also important to extend our work beyond ANSES future deficit or surplus and include the adequacy of social security benefits in the future and their redistributive power. We could hence study the role ANSES plays in tackling inequality in Argentina and how recent developments, as well as future evolutions, may affect this mission. Only then it is possible to study Argentina’s social security sustainability: if we leave these elements out, we would only be able to study its economic sustainability (whether social security revenues will match expenses in the future with current rules). By giving a picture of the system’s future adequacy and redistributive power it becomes possible to study the system’s political sustainability. We can gauge whether future working generations will likely agree to pay these benefits, but also whether their adequacy will be decent enough for elderly in the future so that the system will be acceptable. If we add to this the historically high litigation Argentina’s pension system has experienced and the fact the right to a mobile retirement pension is inscribed in the Constitution (as seen in section 1.1), it is clear this political (and judiciary) sustainability aspect must be included in any projection of Argentina’s pension system sustainability.

Moreover, a macro model would be unable to capture differences in accumulated pension rights between individuals of a same cohort but also between generations. First, as explained in section 1.2, not only do we lack information on individual careers and thus past contributions to social security in the EPHc. There are no publicly available information on rights to a pension as of today in Argentina. Carrying out a macro level simulation of retirement expenses while only assuming the implicit debt Argentina’s social security system has towards today’s workers through their accumulated pension rights would make the model far too hypothetical and would miss this heterogeneity. It is however possible to simulate individual rights to a pension with dynamic microsimulation modelling, as done in the case of Ireland’s LIAM pension model (Li & O’Donoghue, 2012). This is what

we do in this work, as will be explained in section 2.3. Additionally, there are significant differences in accumulated pension rights between generations. This is first and foremost due to Argentina's troubled economic history which resulted in each generation being exposed to a particularly different economic situation, as can be seen in Figures 1.7 and 1.10 and has been studied in section 1.3. Cohorts have moreover been exposed to very different pension rules. As seen in section 1.1, this is due to pension reforms (the 1993, 2008, 2016 and 2017 reforms), temporary pension moratoriums (2006 and 2014) but also to pension litigation. The insufficient adjustment of pensions to inflation, specially between 2002 and 2006, but also the incorrect discounting of income earned between 2002 and 2008 (as seen in section 1.3 and Figure 1.12) affected differently cohorts and also individuals within a same cohort depending on their accumulated pension rights. All these elements make basing a retirement projection of Argentina's pension system on a representative individual dubious at best.

Finally, microsimulation modelling is best suited for evaluating the impact of different policies on Argentina's social security system. It is able to first estimate plausible individual careers, as we do in sections 2.2.2 and 2.3. After that, it allows us to create a "synthetic population" (Li & O'Donoghue, 2013, p. 4) through the ageing of present-day cohorts and the simulated birth of future generations. From this population can hence be drawn detailed consequences of different macro-economic, demographic or social security reform scenarios. We can also simulate how individuals with different characteristics and accumulated social security rights are affected by these scenarios. We do this in Chapter 3, in particular in Section 3.2 where we simulate the future impact of the 2016 and 2017 pension reforms on social security's economic sustainability, adequacy and redistributive impact, and compare them to counter-factual scenarios based on 2015 legislation, with and without permanent pension moratoriums.

To conclude, we must acknowledge that we benefited from particularly good circumstances in the developing of our model. First, we entered an expanding field that is in a process of unification and had access to the free and open source LIAM2 microsimulation toolbox. Second, we propose the first dynamic microsimulation model for social security projection in Latin America capable of policy impact evaluation in a moment where several emerging countries, such as Brazil, Argentina or to a certain extent Chile, are working on reforming their pension system. It is thus the first of such models that is capable of carrying out an *ex ante* impact analysis of these reforms down to the individual level. This opens the way for studying the impact of these reforms not only on the aggregated economic sustainability of social security systems, but also on the benefits' adequacy and

redistributive power. In the remainder of this second Chapter, we will give a detailed account of our model's architecture, its various modules and the micro-level calibration of our model to available data.

2.2 The architecture of our microsimulation model

First of all, we lay out the general architecture of our model. It involves several steps that use different software and various sources. The general architecture can be summarised in three steps. First, building our micro-level dataset and carrying out the micro-level and macro-level calibration of our microsimulation models. Then comes the retrospective module where we back-cast individual careers and get plausible retirement rights for individuals surveyed between 2014 and 2015. Finally, we input these rights together with a set of social, economic and demographic scenarios into our prospective module to simulate Argentina's social security up to 2040. We will in this section give a more precise account of these matters.

2.2.1 The different steps in our model: from individual careers to future rights

Figure 2.1 gives a general overview of our model. We proceed in our simulations as follows. First of all, we extract the information we need for developing our model from various data sources. The most important dataset is the EPH household survey (seen in section 1.2). We treated it using SAS software, Version 9.4 of the SAS System for Windows³, and the full code is available on-line⁴. Respondents of the EPHc survey (2003-2017) are our studied population to begin with, so we modified this dataset so that it can be input in our model. First, we extract from the EPHc (2003-2017) all the variables that are relevant for our microsimulations, including those that are not directly available such as family links (see section 1.2.2). Then, we make our dataset compatible with LIAM2. All variables are coded as either integers, fractional numbers or booleans (where the only options are either "True" or "False"). Moreover, although it is not stated in the user manual, LIAM2 does not work properly if the compulsory id variable (which must be an integer) has too many digits. However, in the EPHc the individual id is derived from the concatenation of variables CODUSU, HOGAR and COMPONENTE that results in an id variable made

³SAS and all other SAS Institute Inc. product or service names are registered trademarks or trademarks of SAS Institute Inc. in the USA and other countries. indicates USA registration.

⁴We use the Zenodo archiving service for long-term preservation of our code. The DOI link is: [10.5281/zenodo.1420273](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1420273)

Figure 2.1: Our model's general architecture: input and output

of 8 digits, which is not something LIAM2 can handle. The EPHc published since 2016 also modified the CODUSU variable, making it alphanumeric. We thus recoded all our id variables (both for individual and family members' ids) into integers with a lower number of digits. Finally, we exported the dataset into CSV, which is a format that LIAM2 can work with.

Furthermore, we calibrated many aspects of our model with micro-level data from the EPH surveys (1974-2017). On the one hand, we micro-calibrated our model by estimating behavioural equations and Mincer wage equations for both our prospective and retrospective module in the EPHc dataset (2003-2015). The estimated coefficients of these equations were then hard-coded in our dynamic microsimulation model. The estimation of our behavioural and Mincer wage equations as well as the full labour-market module are described in detail in section 2.3. On the other hand, we extracted from the EPH (1974-2017) various pieces of historical macro-level information that we (mostly) used in our retrospective module. These are labour-market participation rates (studied in section 1.3.1 and depicted in Figure 1.7) and civil status by age groups and gender. Lastly, we also computed for each period covered by the EPH (1974-2017) structural coefficients that we use to calculate gender-adjusted mean wages as in the TRAJECTOIRE model (Duc *et al.* , 2013), listed in Table M.9. This last element is further covered in section 2.3.

Finally, we used outside sources other than the EPH surveys in the historical macro-level calibration of our retrospective module. We already reviewed in section 1.3.2 our mean wages sources (1970-2017), which we combine with the aforementioned structural coefficients to get gender adjusted mean wages for the 1970-2017 period. We also use a range of socio-demographic sources to back-cast past civil status, although the importance of this module in our retrospective simulations is limited. We compute death probability by age groups and gender (2000-2009) with data published in the Ministry of Health's Vital Statistics reports (DEIS, 2001-2010) for those years. We combine them with projected death probabilities by age from 2014 INDEC population projections (2010-2040) to get death probability by age and gender since 2000. We also compute marriage probability by age using data from the 2010 National Census and from the City of Buenos Aires for 2010. Finally, we compute divorce probability by age between years 2009 and 2016 with data from the City of Buenos Aires. The computation of death probabilities is explained in detail in Appendix K, while the computation of marriage and divorce probabilities for retrospective simulation is laid out in section 2.4.

All these elements are then input in our retrospective module, which back-casts in-

dividual careers. We get from this module individual retirement rights for respondents surveyed between the first quarter of 2014 and the second quarter of 2015. As such, the output of our retrospective module is a dataset enriched with individual retirement rights with which we carry out our social security simulations to the 2040 horizon. A schematic overview of the retrospective module is given in section 2.2.2 and Figure 2.2, and its different elements are reviewed in detail in sections 2.3 to 2.5. In addition to this enriched dataset, we input our prospective module with different hypotheses on the evolution of various social, demographic and economic variables. These are age-dependent probabilities of giving birth and of dying, the civil status composition of the population, student's success and failure probabilities (which are studied in depth in section 2.5), mean labour income, labour-market participation rates (with formal dependent and independent employment, unemployment, inactivity and informal labour rates) and the proportion of workers affiliated in the Autonomous Worker and Small Independent Contributors (or *Monotributo*) regimes. Finally, different reform scenarios are integrated in the prospective module. In the end, we simulate the evolution of the population surveyed in 2014 and 2015 up to 2040, resulting in social security projections that can then be extrapolated to the total Argentinian population (see Section 3.1). The pertinence of such an extrapolation relies on the representativeness of EPHc respondents on Argentina's urban population as seen in section 1.2.

After presenting the general architecture of our model, it is necessary to look into the prospective and retrospective modules, which are where the actual dynamic microsimulation of Argentina's social security takes place. Figures 2.2 and 2.3 respectively depict the functioning of our model's retrospective and prospective modules.

2.2.2 Our retrospective module, step by step

Let us first of all present our model's retrospective module. Its purpose is to reconstitute plausible individual careers for each individual surveyed in the EPHc waves that are relevant for our social security projections (those of years 2014 and 2015). Its architecture is laid out in Figure 2.2.

The retrospective module starts by importing the sample to LIAM2. Then, before beginning to simulate individual careers, it determines some education-related variables. First, it sets an arbitrary age of entry to the labour market for each respondent based on its attained education level. These are 16 for people with incomplete secondary education, 18 for those with complete secondary education and 24 for those with a university

Figure 2.2: Our retrospective module, step by step

degree. I then forces self-reported students that are too old for their level of education out of education and into the labour market. These are all students aged 30 or more and all those aged 21 or more that do not have a complete secondary education level.

After these preliminary measures, the basic idea of the retrospective module is to move back in time one quarter at a time. Let's assume we start at period t and tick back a quarter to period $t - 1$. We first diminish the respondents' age by a quarter and take out of the sample people with negative age (that were not yet born in period $t - 1$). After that, we determine each respondent's situation for period $t - 1$ for a range of variables following the model's micro-calibration and historical macro-calibration. These are education, civil status and family related variables, labour-market state and income. When all this is done we end the simulation for period $t - 1$ and output the modified dataset. We then repeat this process and simulate each period $t - 2, t - 3$ etc. until we reach the first quarter of year 1955, which we will call here $t - n$. The choice of this lower bound is further explained in Appendix J. In the end, we get for periods $t - 1$ to $t - n$ a simulation of the initial period t sample's situation in periods $t - 1, t - 2$ and so on. From these synthetic populations we can then reconstitute individual careers that are plausible at the micro level while also reproducing historical aggregated values (at least until 1974, as explained in Appendix J).

We will now describe how each step of the retrospective module works. Let's assume we go from period $t - i$ to period $t - i - 1$. First, we make respondents one quarter younger and remove people that were not born yet in period $t - i - 1$. Then, for all respondents that were not already students in period $t - i$, we see if they just went below their end of studies age. If they did, they become students for the rest of the simulation and thus inactive. After that, we run a simplified retrospective civil status module, which is laid out in section 2.4.2. We get as a result civil status and family related variables for period $t - i - 1$, including which self-reported housewives in period t remain housewives (and thus inactive) in period $t - i - 1$. From there we enter the labour-market module, the core of the retrospective module, described in detail in section 2.3. We take individuals of active age that are neither students nor housewives. We compute for them individual propensity scores for each of the five (registered employment, registered independent labour, unregistered labour, unemployment and inactivity) labour-market states through behavioural equations. After that, we apply an alignment by sorting procedure (described in Box 2, section 2.1.1) to reconstitute historical labour-market participation rates by age and gender for period $t - i - 1$. As a result, we get for all working-age individuals their labour-market state in period $t - i - 1$. The last part of the simulation is estimating each working individual's position in the income scale through Mincer wage equations.

This gives us each respondent’s labour income level (after inputting the period’s gender-adjusted mean wage) and sectoral quartile (see section 2.3) at time $t - i - 1$. Once this is done, the simulation of period $t - i - 1$ ends and the dataset is output. If the lower bound (year 1955) is not reached, then the model repeats this process for period $t - i - 2$. Why we chose to simulate past careers up to 1955 even though micro-level historical data only goes up to 1974 is explained in Appendix J.

2.2.3 Our prospective module, step by step

In this section we will present our model’s prospective module. Its purpose is to simulate the evolution of the sample population (the EPHc waves of 2014 and 2015) up to 2040, where the demographic projections provided by the INDEC end. It works upon the output given by our retrospective module, as it uses the simulated individual careers to determine not only retirement rights, but also when each individual retires. As is hinted in Figure 2.1, a major difference between our retrospective and prospective modules lies in their macro and micro calibration. Indeed, the former tries to reproduce historical aggregate values for variables such as labour-market state and income or civil status. Part of its micro calibration also reproduces historical data, as is the case of death, divorce and marriage probabilities that we input the module. Finally, when we back-cast careers the legislation is by definition given. We cannot thus propose varying legislative scenarios in our retrospective simulations. The calibration of our prospective module on the other hand relies heavily on economic, demographic, social and reform scenarios, since we are simulating how our population will evolve in the future. It is true that our behavioural and Mincer wage equations, but also our matching procedures and divorce equations are all estimated with the EPHc (2003-2015) and remain the same in all scenarios. Also, that some details or secondary elements of our module, such as the probabilities of validating a given high-school or university year (see section 2.5), do not change either across our scenarios for the sake of simplicity. This said, all of the model’s macro-calibration, its demographic calibration (birth and death probabilities), future social security benefits and conditions to earn them (such as retirement age) rely on flexible scenarios. These scenarios are crucial: registered employment rates, old-age dependency ratios and social security legislation will weigh far more in determining ANSES’ future economic result than the behavioural equations’ estimated coefficients. For the prospective simulations to make any sense, these scenarios must be well defined, even though making long-term economic forecasts represents taking a leap of faith. We thus rely on INDEC’s population projections for the demographic part of our model, while we make our socio-economic scenarios by looking at the historical evolution of Argentina’s labour market (see Section

2.3). The model's strength however is that it can be re-run with very different scenarios (be them social, economic or demographic) and even social security legislation. This is something we do by defining high and low economic scenarios. More importantly, section 3.2 of Chapter 3 carries out an *ex ante* evaluation of the 2016 and 2017 reforms' impact on social security by simulating counter-factual scenarios in the absence of each of these reforms. The prospective module's architecture is laid out in Figure 2.3.

The basic functioning of our prospective module is as follows. We first define a social, economic and demographic scenario up to 2040. We then import one wave of the EPHc (for instance, the second quarter of 2015) with simulated careers. After that, we carry out some preliminary operations that are related to education and pensions. As with the retrospective module, we consider self-reported students aged 30 or more (21 or more if they do not have a full secondary education level) as dropping out during the first simulated period. Contrary to the retrospective module though, we flag them as having just left education, which is an explanatory variable in our prospective behavioural equations (see section 2.3 and Appendix L). We also assume all individuals between ages 5 to 15 are schooled, which is a condition to receive family benefits such as the AUH (universal child benefit) and the yearly schooling aid. The full details of these hypotheses related to education are studied in our prospective education module (section 2.5). Finally, we need to tell apart, among the elderly who receive a retirement benefit or a survivor's pension (measured by variable `v2_m` in the EPH), who receive a retirement benefit (and have thus liquidated their retirement rights) and who receives a survivor's benefit (and may thus still retire). We assume all individuals that are at least 5 years younger than the legal minimum to retire (55 for women, 60 for men) and that receive a pension are retired as long as they are not widowed. If they are widowed, we consider they have retired their own retirement rights if they say so in the survey (through variable `cat_inac` of the EPH). We assume all the other individuals that do not fulfil these conditions receive a survivor's pension and may yet retire on their own.

After these preliminary steps, we age our population by a quarter and start by studying the demographic features of the model (birth and death). Our central scenario uses the INDEC population projections for the 2010-2040 period, that include death probabilities by age and gender as well as the probability of giving birth by age of the mother. We first simulate deaths in period $t+1$. When an individual is randomly selected as having died, we check whether he or she has any living partner or children. If it is the case, a variable tracks the spouse's / parent date of death and the surviving relatives civil status and family links are updated if need be. This allows for the computation of survivor's pen-

Figure 2.3: Our prospective module, step by step

sions when relevant. After that, the deceased individuals are removed from the sample. We then simulate for each woman the probability of giving birth by age. We assume that 51% of the newly born are boys and the remaining 49% girls, which is a standard masculinity rate at birth and corresponds to data published in the Ministry of Health's Vital Statistics reports (DEIS, 2014-2016) for years 2013, 2014 and 2015. We however make some assumptions on which women can give birth. First, we assume women that are married or in a common-law union have a higher probability of having a baby, and thus select them in priority. Moreover, following INDEC's population projections women aged 50 or more can never have children. We finally assume women with eight children or more or that do not have a partner aged 16 to 59 cannot have children. We refrain from taking into account more factors to determine who gives birth (such as income, labour-market situation, whether she is studying or whether she recently had children) because it would mean modelling a module devoted to the decision or likelihood of having a baby. Although giving birth has an important impact on labour careers, as partially shown by our labour-market behavioural equations (see section 2.3), and fertility decisions may be influenced by our simulated social security legislation (see in the case of Argentina's AUH Garganta *et al.* (2017)), this fertility module is left for future work.

We then model students' behaviour in our prospective education module, laid out in section 2.5. It is fairly more complicated than its counterpart in our retrospective module, which was only interested in back-casting individual careers. It thus focused on determining the respondents' end of studies age. If the respondent was relatively young and studying, we simply supposed he had not yet started his professional career and that we ought to simulate him as having always been inactive in the past. We thus barely modelled students' behaviour. Our prospective module does not need to model non-students' end of studies age, as it is taken care of by the retrospective module. It however needs, for all current and future students, to determine what education level they will attain and when they enter the labour market. We get as an output people who exit the education system in period $t+1$ (that either dropped out of it or successfully completed their studies) and people of working age (aged 16 or more) that are studying in $t+1$. After that, we run our civil status and marriage market module. Contrary to its retrospective counterpart, it simulates future unions and marriages through a matching procedure. It also randomly determines a specific number of couples (married or not) that divorce. Finally, it determines when a new household is formed, via a couple's divorce, a head's child getting in a common-law union or growing old enough to leave the household. We review it in full in section 2.4. The output of this module are updated family links and civil status status for $t+1$.

Next comes the prospective labour-market module. Its functioning is very similar to its retrospective counterpart and is explained in section 2.3. It however has its own specificities. First, since it dynamically simulates retirement and survivor's pensions, it uses pension income as an explanatory variable in the behavioural equations of people older than the minimum retirement age (ages 65 to 69 for men, 60 to 69 for women). These equations are simulated separately because people of retiring age are not subject to the same legislation than people below retiring age, as the latter cannot retire. Second, it uses variables such as seniority or having just finished education as explanatory variables in behavioural and Mincer wage equations, as explained more in detail in section 2.3. We then reproduce the aggregate labour-market proportions defined by our scenario through an alignment by sorting procedure analogous to that of our retrospective module (seen in section 2.2.2). After that, as in our retrospective module, we run Mincer wage equations to estimate each working individual's position in the income scale (seen in section 2.3) and real labour income (dependent on the mean wage scenario). We here also compute contributions to social security, following the rules laid out in section 1.1.4. This also means we assign, on the one hand, formal wage-earners to the public or private sector and, within the latter, to the tertiary or non-tertiary economic sectors. And on the other hand, it means we classify independent workers that belong to the formal sector and some informal sector workers to the Autonomous workers and the Small Independent Contributors (*Monotributo*) regimes. We finally calculate the retirement benefits, survivor's pensions and family benefits each individual is entitled to at period $t+1$ and output the dataset. If we reached the fourth quarter of 2040 we stop the prospective simulation there, and if not, we move on to period $t+2$.

In the end, we get a film depicting the evolution of the base dataset quarter by quarter until 2040 that includes in particular the most relevant social security payments (retirement pensions, survivors' benefits and child allowances) and contributions to social security. All that is left is to analyse the results to get a projection of ANSES' long-term sustainability, benefits adequacy and redistributive impact by scenario (section 3.2) given the social, economic, demographic and legislative scenario adopted for the projection. This extrapolation is done in section 3.1.

The remainder of Chapter 2 gives a detailed account of the more complex elements of the retrospective and prospective modules. Section 2.3 studies the labour-market modules (both prospective and retrospective) and shows we reproduce historical data and aggregate labour-market scenarios. Then, section 2.4 studies the civil status and mar-

riage market modules, their micro-calibration, alignment to aggregate scenarios and how well they reproduce past and future aggregate civil status. Finally, section 2.5 gives an in-depth analysis of the education module within both the retrospective and prospective simulations, while showing we produce plausible education levels.

2.3 Labour market modelling: labour-market states and wage levels

In this section, we will show the core of our microsimulation model, that is determining individual contributions and social security rights of individuals in our dataset, the EPHc. To do so, we simulate past and future individual careers through our labour-market module. In both our prospective and retrospective simulations, this module's general design is as follows. First, we simulate each working age individual's new labour-market state. Then, for working individuals, we derive their labour income from individual characteristics. We do not however simulate these elements in a vacuum, but rather calibrate them to ensure our model adequately reproduces the characteristics of Argentina's labour market, both at the aggregate level and at the micro level. We want our model to be consistent with aggregate historical data, presented in section 1.3. We also want it to simulate individual behaviour that is consistent with how respondents in the EPHc (studied in section 1.2) actually behave. Finally, we want our labour-market states and labour income scenarios to be consistent with future data, while also covering a wide range of possible evolutions of Argentina's labour market. We thus study the determinants of labour market participation and income in Argentina, which constitutes a contribution to the labour market literature, and in particular to the determinants and consequences of informal labour. This section is thus divided in three parts. First, we describe our labour-market participation module and calibrate it through behavioural equations that estimate the determinants of transitions between relevant labour-market states. Then, we lay out our labour income module and how we derive it from individual characteristics through Mincer wage equations. Finally, we propose a plausible labour-market participation scenario and prove the macro-level consistency of our simulations by showing our model reproduces both this scenario and historical values.

2.3.1 A study of individual behaviour: studying the determinants of employment in a fragmented labour-market through behavioural equations

Why estimate labour-market transitions through behavioural equations?

Modelling individual labour-market state is the foundation of our model, since it determines rights to both pensions and family benefits (as seen in section 1.1). We consider five relevant states: formal dependent employment, formal independent labour, informal labour, unemployment and inactivity. All individuals in our dataset are assigned to exactly one of these states. We split registered labour between wage-earners and own-account workers for several reasons. First of all, because they are subject to different social security rules. Contributions to social security and retirement rights are computed differently for wage-earners and independent workers, as we have seen in section 1.1. But also because we indirectly identify formal independent labour following Maurizio (2012) while registered wage-earners are directly identifiable in the EPHc (see section 1.2). Informality, unemployment and inactivity are separated even though they all mean no contributions are made to social security because of the inherent differences between them and the different behaviours they entail. Inactive people are the furthest away from formal labour, be it because they are students, retired, stay-at-home spouses or have health issues, so it is logical not to mix them with active respondents. Informal workers and the unemployed are separated because of differing behaviour but also to allow for the study of unemployment benefits. They were long irrelevant, as their maximum level⁵ had been frozen at 400 pesos a month for ten years (2006-2016), bringing them from 130US\$ on March 2006, when this level was set, to 28 US\$ in May 2016. Moreover very few people (there were 65,000 ANSES unemployment benefits beneficiaries in 2015⁶) claimed these benefits. Thus, in 2015 these represented less than 0.1%⁷ of ANSES current expenses. Their level has however been raised since May 2016 to a minimum of 1,875 pesos and a maximum of 3,000 pesos a month⁸, respectively 130 and 210 US\$ at the time. Although these values have not been adjusted by inflation and have thus seen their real levels sharply decrease (the minimum and maximum unemployment benefits represented respectively 110 and 170 US\$ on July 2017), they may represent a sizeable portion of ANSES expenses in the future were they to be regularly adjusted to inflation. So even though our model does not currently simulate unemployment rights, it is a feature that

⁵Established by Decree 267/2006 issued the 9th of March 2006

⁶Source: 2015 Investment account, Tome II Appendix II.3 Social Security Institutions.

⁷Source: Ibid.

⁸As established by Res. 2/2016 of CNEP and SMVM issued the 20/05/16

may be added in future work, and to do so unemployment needs to be modelled separately.

Next, we need to establish how an individual can move between these labour-market states over time. As is standard in dynamic microsimulation modelling, we adopt a markovian framework to model these transitions. We run backwards microsimulations to reconstitute plausible individual careers and forward simulations to make social security projections. As such, we both forecast (as is standard in dynamic microsimulation modelling) and back-cast individual behaviour (as in the LIAM model for studying the Irish pension system (Li & O'Donoghue, 2012)). When we forecast, we model transitions from one labour-market state to the other between times $t-1$ and t thanks to transition probabilities that depend on labour-market state in $t-1$ and individual characteristics estimated in t . When we "back-cast" (Li & O'Donoghue, 2012) careers, we do the same thing only instead of transiting from $t-1$ to t we do so from t to $t-1$. What is left is to establish the determinants of labour-market transitions. To do so some models, such as for France TRAJECTOIRE model (Duc *et al.* , 2013) or old versions of the PRISME model (Poubelle *et al.* , 2006; Albert *et al.* , 2009), input empirically measured transition probabilities between the defined labour-market states. Others, such as Destinie 2 in France (Bachelet *et al.* , 2014, p. 22), MIDAS_BE in Belgium (Dekkers *et al.* , 2010b, p. 22) or LIAM in Ireland (Li & O'Donoghue, 2012), estimate these transition probabilities through behavioural equations. These are standard multinomial logit or probit binary regressions, and are often nested in a decision tree (Bachelet *et al.* , 2014, p. 22). Empirical and estimated transition probabilities are both widespread in the literature and are used in comparable proportions (Li & O'Donoghue, 2013).

We chose to estimate behavioural equations to reproduce transitions between labour-market states over time. We mainly do this because we developed our model with the LIAM2 software, which simulates careers through behavioural equations. Also, we only model transitions into 5 different states, and to do so we have a very extensive dataset with nearly 650.000 individuals of working age that we observe two consecutive quarters. Our behavioural equations are thus estimated in datasets that are big enough for our logistic regressions to be meaningful. The smallest sample we have is for women in registered independent labour and it still represents more than 9,500 observations. As a way of comparison, the TRAJECTOIRE model simulates 98 possible states for each generation of their dataset, the EIC⁹ (the 1974 generation, for instance, is comprised of

⁹The *Échantillon inter-régimes des cotisants* (EIC), or inter-regimes contributors sample, is a dataset that features accumulated rights to a pension of all workers who have contributed to a pension scheme in France. It is developed by the DREES (the *Direction de la Recherche, des Études, de l'Évaluation et des Statistiques*, or Office on Research, Studies, policy Evaluation and Statistics) with the help of France's

almost 27,000 individuals) which means some states don't have enough respondents to study their behaviour through qualitative regressions (Duc *et al.* , 2013, p. 16). We use the in-built alignment by sorting procedure (as defined in section 2.1.1): for each working-age individual, we compute a propensity score that depicts the likelihood of being in a given labour-market state in t depending on simulated characteristics in t and on the labour-market state, and labour-market state related control variables, in $t-1$. We then sort individuals by their scores and align them with aggregate labour-market participation rates by five-year groups and gender in a Monte-Carlo simulation framework. For our back-casting of individual careers we use historical values drawn from the EPH surveys (1974-2017) (see Section 1.2). In our projections of future labour-market states, we determine these alignment values as part of our prospective scenarios.

By following this alignment by sorting procedure, we not only ensure the macro-coherence of our simulations with both labour-market historical values (when back-casting individual careers) and our projection scenarios. We also ensure a plausible microsimulation of individual behaviour in the labour market. To get our model to be as micro-coherent as possible, a special care is taken in the building of behavioural equations, which we describe below.

The design and estimation of our behavioural equations

The propensity score of transiting into a given labour-market state is obtained through behavioural equations. We estimate them using the EPHc (2003-2015) with multinomial logit regressions on people of working age, separately by gender and with a quarterly pace. In order to avoid overfitting¹⁰ our model to the data, we use five-fold stepwise selection for our logistic equations: we randomly select 80% of our dataset as the training base where we estimate our equations, and then validate them in the remaining 20% test base. We get similar c-statistics (the Area Under the Curve) for the training and validation bases and values that are consistently over 0.75, sometimes over 0.9. This shows our regressions not only have a high predictive power but also that they are not very dependent on the dataset they are estimated with. If they were, the AUC of the training and validating datasets would significantly differ, which is not the case as can be seen in Tables L.1 to L.4. It is thus not far-fetched to use behavioural equations estimated in the 2003-2015 period for simulating individual behaviour in other time frames, be it when back-casting

national statistics institute, the INSEE.

¹⁰An overfitted model is one that has a strong explanatory power in a given dataset but fares badly in modelling the predictive variable in a similar, but distinct, dataset.

individual careers or carrying out our prospective simulations. Finally, we set the Significance Level of Entry (SLE) and to Stay (SLS) in the model to 0.1, so that only variables who are significant at the 10% threshold are kept in the model.

In our forward simulations, for each labour-market state $i \in \llbracket 1; 5 \rrbracket$, we estimate equations that have the following form:

$$X_{i,t} = \alpha + \sum_{j=4}^5 \beta_j X_{j,t-1} + \left(\sum_{j=1}^3 \tilde{\beta}_j X_{j,t-1} \right) \times \left(\kappa_k \sum_{k=1}^4 Q_{k,t-1} + \sum_{k=1}^5 \sigma_k S_{k,t-1} \right) + \gamma Y_{t-1} + \theta Z_t + \epsilon_t \quad (2.1)$$

$X_{i,t}$ is a binomial variable that equals 1 when the individual is of the labour-market state $i \in \llbracket 1; 5 \rrbracket$ at the quarter t . X_1 corresponds to formal wage-earners, X_2 to independent labour in the formal sector, X_3 to informal work, X_4 to unemployment and X_5 to inactivity. Z_t is a set of control variables estimated at time t independently from the individual's labour-market situation and ϵ_t an error term. Y_{t-1} represents a set of control variables that are labour-market related and thus have to be estimated in period $t-1$. Moreover, $\forall j \in \llbracket 1; 4 \rrbracket$ $Q_{j,t-1}$ represents the labour income quartile the working individual belonged to. Finally, $\forall j \in \llbracket 1; 5 \rrbracket$, $S_{j,t-1}$ is the working respondent's seniority in its current firm. Both seniority and labour income quartile are studied separately for formal wage-earners, independent workers in the formal sector and informal workers (so for $i \in \llbracket 1; 3 \rrbracket$). They are thus always combined to labour-market states. A possible dependent variable is thus for instance a seniority of more than five years and being a formal wage-earner (with an estimated parameter of $\tilde{\beta}_1 \times \tilde{\sigma}_5$), never separately being a formal wage-earner or having more than five years of seniority. The same applies for sectoral labour-income quartiles: the dependent variable may be being among the 25% richest informal workers (with an estimated parameter of $\tilde{\beta}_3 \times \tilde{\kappa}_4$), never being simply unregistered or among the 25% richest workers. However, since by definition being unemployed or inactive comes with a null labour income and seniority, both these labour-market states may be input separately as dependent variables $X_{4,t-1}$ and $X_{5,t-1}$. The five-fold stepwise selection procedure presented in the previous paragraph determines which particular combinations of labour-market state, seniority and sectoral labour income quartile are kept as explanatory variables in our behavioural equations. It also determines which set of control variables, among Y_{t-1} and Z_t , are kept in our behavioural equations.

We nevertheless only use seniority in our prospective simulations, and not when we back-cast individual careers. This is because the information available in the EPHc (variables PP05H for wage-earners and PP07A for independent workers) is too vague for us

to set a precise date of entry to the current position. Reported seniority in the EPHc are a month or less, one to three months, more than three to six months, more than six to twelve months, more than a year to five years and more than five years. So for instance, when a 50 year-old respondent reports having withheld his current position for more than five years, we have no way of knowing whether we should make him transit into a different labour-market state when he was 44, 40 or 25. Thus, if we wanted our retrospective simulation to respect this self-reported seniority, we would need to force this individual to transition into another labour-market state at a very imprecise date while at the same time force him to stay in the same position until then. This would be problematic and needlessly complicate our labour-market module.

Meanwhile, seniority is easier to handle in our prospective simulations. Firstly, this imprecision in the date of entry is only troublesome for respondents reporting a seniority of more than one to five years. Values for seniority under a year are precise enough, and for seniority longer than five years it is irrelevant whether the respondent has held his position for six, ten or twenty years as those values are not distinguished from one another in the EPHc. As such, when there is an imprecision in the number of quarters during which the current position was held, we simply assign the individual a random number of quarters within the possible values. Therefore, individuals with a seniority of more than six to twelve months are assigned a seniority of three or four quarters and those with a seniority of one to five years get a random number of quarters between five and twenty. Secondly, simulating seniority in our prospective simulations is straightforward. We simply assume that a given individual changes of occupation only when he changes of labour-market state. Every time a worker stays in his current labour-market state we increment his seniority by a quarter. Once he moves to a different labour-market state we assume he changed his position, and if he is still a worker we set his seniority to a quarter.

Therefore, the behavioural equations we estimate for our backwards simulations are of the following form (see Equation (2.1) to see what each term stands for):

$$X_{i,t-1} = \alpha + \sum_{j=4}^5 \beta_j X_{j,t} + \left(\sum_{j=1}^3 \tilde{\beta}_j X_{j,t} \right) \times \left(\sum_{k=1}^4 \kappa_k Q_{k,t} \right) + \gamma Y_t + \theta Z_{t-1} \epsilon_{t-1} \quad (2.2)$$

Finally, we estimate distinct behavioural equations for individuals above the minimum retirement age (which is 60 for women and 65 for men) up to age 69. This allows us to simulate the retirement decision more realistically than simply having all people retire at the legal minimum age. This is necessary because a significant proportion of these indi-

viduals are not retired, even after the implementation of pension moratoriums. Indeed, only 57% of men and 71% of women those ages were inactive, including 52% of men and 57% of women that were retired¹¹. Moreover, 15% of men and 9% of women those ages cumulate labour income and pension revenue (be them retirement benefits or survivor's pensions¹²). These two elements mean it is incorrect to assume all people above the minimum retirement age earn a pension and stopped working. We however assume all people aged 70 or more are inactive, mainly because this is the new compulsory age at retirement as established by Art. 7 of the 2017 pension reform Law 27426¹³. Also, at that age the vast majority of people define themselves as retired (73% of men and 84% of women¹⁴) while formal wage-earners (the main source of retirement contributions) are negligible (5% of men, 2% of women¹⁵). From a social security perspective, it is thus safe to assume all people aged 70 or more are retired and inactive.

The full list of our explanatory variables as well as the estimated coefficients for all our behavioural equations are available in Appendix L. In particular, our backwards behavioural equations do not use seniority nor a dummy indicating exiting the education system due to the simplified simulation of education in our retrospective simulations, as seen in section 2.5. Also, our forward behavioural equations of people past retirement age include pension income (as well as the partner's) as an explanatory variable. We use them as our primary input in simulating individual labour-market related behaviour. They also shed light on the determinants of labour supply in Argentina, and are interesting in their own right. Before moving on to the determinants of labour income, we will thus analyse the results of our behavioural equations below.

The results: the determinants of labour supply in Argentina

Our estimated behavioural equations are fully transcribed in Tables L.1 to L.8 in Appendix L. The results of our forward and backward behavioural equations are similar overall, so we will only analyse here those of our forward logit regressions, listed in Tables L.1 and L.2. Most of our results amount to stylised facts. As expected when studying quarterly labour-market transitions, the previous labour-market state has the greatest predictive power for today's labour-market state. Being in a given labour-market state in $t - 1$ greatly increases the odds ratio of being in that same labour-market state in t , and

¹¹Source: own computation based on the EPHc (2008-2015).

¹²Ibid.

¹³Published the 28th of December 2017.

¹⁴Source: own computation based on the EPHc (2008-2017).

¹⁵Ibid.

conversely greatly diminishes the probability of being in any other state in t . It is however easier to transit between some labour-market states. Most notably, transitions between unemployment and informal labour are frequent: as can be seen in the case of men (Table L.1), having been unemployed in $t - 1$ diminishes the odds ratio of being a formal wage-earner in t by $\exp(0.3721 + 0.5825 - 5.4804) - 1 \approx -99\%$, while it only decreases the odds ratios of being an informal worker in t by $\exp(1.6482 + 0.0765 - 2.6328) - 1 \approx -60\%$ with respect to the reference individual. Conversely, having been an informal worker with a seniority of three months or less and within the lowest income quartile in $t - 1$ decreases the odds ratio of being unemployed in t only by $\exp(1.1118 - 2.3111 + 0.365) - 1 \approx -57\%$. The permeability between unemployment and (short) informal labour spells confirms the latter are akin to disguised unemployment, with short-term precarious jobs replacing a *de facto* non-existent unemployment benefits scheme.

In the case of workers, we cross labour-market state with sectoral income quartile and seniority in $t - 1$. Both seniority and labour income quartile are ways of introducing heterogeneity between workers within the same labour-market state. The former helps to tell apart workers that are in a more stable situation from those that likely are in a more precarious state. The latter helps to proxy both labour productivity and social class, which should help to further polarise between stable and precarious workers. We computed labour income quartiles within labour-market states because doing so over all workers adds little information in what regards labour-market state, as the poorest workers are most of the time informal while the richest are registered workers. We find that seniority and sectoral labour income quartile both have a significant impact on labour-market transitions. Workers with greater labour-market income and seniority in $t - 1$ have a higher probability of staying in the same labour-market state in t . Longer seniority and higher income both mean the worker is in a stable and well paid position and has thus less reasons for moving to another state. It also means he is less exposed to the risk of losing his job and forcibly move to another state.

By studying seniority and labour-market income, we also found a segmented informal sector in Argentina, with the coexistence of voluntary and involuntary informal labour. First of all, the most precarious and less paid informal workers experience frequent transitions in and out of unemployment. In the case of men (Table L.1), if at $t - 1$ he is among the 25% richest unregistered workers and has a seniority of more than five years then the odds ratio of being unemployed in t decreases by $\exp(-0.3209 - 2.3111) - 1 \approx -93\%$ with respect to the reference individual, as compared to the -57% decrease we computed when that man was among the poorest informal workers and had a seniority of at most

three months. This result follows the literature stating that informal labour is mostly a survival sector with high short-term turnover (Gerxhani, 2004; Kaufmann & Kaliberda, 1996) that replaces a negligible unemployment benefits scheme. This survival sector thus amounts to involuntary informal labour (Kucera & Roncolato, 2008; Arias & Escudero, 2007), "a strategy of last resort" where these workers are "rationed out of the formal sector" (Günther & Launov, 2012). Since this result does not hold for informal workers that are not in a precarious position, not all of Argentina's informal sector is a survival sector or disguised unemployment.

Informal workers that are better paid and in a more stable position also tend to formalise by setting up their own business once they accumulated enough capital and experience to do so (Tornarolli & Conconi, 2007). In the case of men (Table L.1), having been among the richest informal workers in $t - 1$ and having a seniority of five years or more decreases the odds ratio of being an independent worker in t by $\exp(0.3585 - 3.8929 + 1.393) - 1 \approx -88\%$ with respect to the reference individual. Being among the poorest unemployed workers and with a seniority of three months at most decreases this odds ratio by $\exp(-3.8929 + 0.375) - 1 \approx -97\%$. This implies these more well-off workers do not necessarily look to immediately enter the formal sector, but rather aim to set up shop. They may hence count as "voluntary" informal workers (Günther & Launov, 2012; Bosch & Maloney, 2010). Our behavioural equations therefore show the coexistence within Argentina's informal sector of a survival sector akin to disguised unemployment with a relatively more well-off voluntary informal sector.

Variables that are not crossed with labour-market state in $t - 1$ also have a significant explanatory power on labour-market state in period t . Some results amount to stylised facts. Education has a positive effect on the probability of being a formal worker, while lower levels of education increase the probability of being an informal worker, unemployed or inactive. Having just finished education (which mixes successfully completing education and simply dropping out of it) has a strongly negative impact on the probability of being inactive but increases the most the probability of entering informal labour, which confirms Tornarolli & Conconi (2007)'s view that "the unqualified young enter the labour market through informal salaried work" (Tornarolli & Conconi, 2007, p. 26). As is standard, we see that there is a non-linear relationship between age and labour-market participation. For both men and women, the probability of being a registered wage-earner or an informal worker are at their maximum between ages 25 and 45. Being a registered independent worker is the most probable past age 40. This is coherent with a framework where the worker accumulates savings and experience when he is young and sets up his

own business once he has accumulated enough capital (both economic and human) to do so. Finally, inactivity is high at younger ages due to students.

Many explanatory variables however have a differential impact on men and women, as can be seen in Tables L.1 and L.2. For instance, being 55 to 60 increases the odds ratio of being inactive by $\exp(1.0300) - 1 \approx 180\%$ in the case of men and by $\exp(0.4972) - 1 \approx 64\%$ in the case of women. Similarly, the propensity to become unemployed increases with age for men but decreases for women. Being between 55 and 60 increases men's odds ratio of being unemployed by $\exp(0.1426) - 1 \approx 15\%$ as compared to the reference middle-aged individual, while it decreases it for women of those ages by $\exp(-0.5201) - 1 \approx -41\%$. These differences between senior men and women's behaviour can be attributed first to the male breadwinner bias, which means women of central ages are more often inactive than men. Second, because senior men are in a worse health than women of the same ages and are thus more often pushed out of labour than women, into unemployment or invalidity.

Family links and civil status have contrasted effects on men and women. These depict a scenario where the more men get closer to a nuclear family with children, the more often they work. Being single for instance decreases the odds ratio a man has of being a registered wage-earner by $\exp(-0.2396 - 0.2723) - 1 \approx -40\%$ with respect to the reference individual, who is married to a formal wage-earner woman. Similarly, the odds ratio a man has of being a formal independent worker decrease by -79% and of being an unregistered worker by -46% when he is single with respect to the reference individual. Also, more stable family situations increase the odds ratio of being a formal worker for men. Being in a common-law union decreases the odds ratio of being a registered wage-earner by -18% , while being married decreases the odds ratio of being an informal worker by -21% . Finally, the more a man has children under the age of 4 the less he is inactive and the more his labour supply is informal.

Meanwhile, we can see a male breadwinner bias in women's labour supply. The more they get closer to a nuclear family with children, the lower their labour supply. Firstly, being single increases the odds ratio of being a registered wage-earner by $\exp(0.3975 - 0.2842) - 1 \approx 12\%$ and of being an informal worker by 52% with respect to the reference woman, who is married. Also, less stable family situations increase women's labour supply: being in a common-law union instead of married increases the odds ratio of being a formal wage-earner by 24% and of being an informal worker by 9% , while it decreases the odds ratio of being inactive by -23% . Moreover, not having a registered

wage-earner husband decreases the odds ratio of being inactive by between -22% in the case of having an inactive husband to -55% when her partner is unemployed. Women are thus encouraged to stay at home and take on domestic labour when the husband has a stable position. Finally, the higher the number of children under the age of 4 she has, the lower her odds ratio of working. Having one children aged 4 or less instead of none decreases her odds ratio of being a formal wage-earner by -15% . Similarly, having no children aged 4 or less instead of 2 or more decreases her odds ratio of being inactive by -35% . Child care is thus taken on by women, as is most domestic work in a framework of labour specialisation, where the opportunity cost of domestic labour is lower for women than for men. The legislation also encourages this division, as women that are formal wage-earners benefit from a 90 days paid maternity leave, while their formal wage-earner partner's paid paternity leave is limited to 2 days.

To summarise, we have explained in this section why we use behavioural equations in our model, how we built them using the EPHc (2003-2015) and exploited the information they give of Argentina's labour market. The following section covers the last element we need to analyse in this first chapter before moving on to our dynamic microsimulation model: the determinants of labour income.

2.3.2 A deterministic element on labour-market simulations: introducing a housewife module for past careers

The above labour-market states simulation accurately reproduces short-term individual behaviour on the labour market. It however has trouble in simulating a behaviour that is longitudinally consistent over time, and in particular on long simulated periods of time. This problem is particularly present in our back-casting of individual careers. Not only because the simulate period is longer, but also because the past states must be coherent with the present state of the individual, which is known. As in Li & O'Donoghue (2012), we thus combine an individual-level behavioural analysis with deterministic rules in what concerns past careers for the sake of longitudinal consistency. For reasons we will lay out below, we have chosen to do so with married women that report being a stay-at-home wife in the EPHc, whom we call "housewives". If a housewife is interviewed while having children aged 4 or less, then we assume she temporarily withdrew from the labour market. We thus make it so that when she had no children aged 4 she may have been working in the past. If however the self-reported housewife does not have children under the age of 4 we assume she has been inactive since she started living together with her husband.

The following section will explain why we added this deterministic housewife module and what its role is within our dynamic microsimulation model.

Why do we introduce housewives in our model?

Our model simulates civil status and family links and uses them to determine, among others, labour-market state (seen in section 2.3) in both our prospective and retrospective modules. We in particular see that, for women, being married increases all other things being equal the odds ratio of being inactive (see Appendix L). This means self-reported housewives have in our behavioural equations higher chances to have been inactive in the past. The problem is that backwards microsimulation cannot by itself ensure that each individual has a career that is consistent from the beginning to its end (Li & O'Donoghue, 2012, p. 56). In particular, behavioural equations in a Markov chains framework have trouble in telling apart individuals that seldom work in the formal sector, such as stay-at-home wives or workers confined to the informal sector, from others who are likely to have very long formal careers. Indeed, the estimated labour-market state in $t-1$ depends on the state in quarter t and on individual characteristics in $t-1$. Characteristics in $t-1$ and t only indirectly effect labour-market state in $t-3$, $t-4$ etc. This methodology is thus unable to simulate careers where some individuals are very likely to have been out of the formal labour-market for their whole life given their characteristics when they were surveyed. Moreover, this Monte-Carlo simulation framework includes a random component that makes sure the same individuals are not systematically selected for transitioning towards a labour-market state. Conversely, this makes it likely that even individuals with characteristics that make them very unlikely to work in the formal sector are nevertheless simulated as having contributed some quarters to social security in the past. However, the alignment by sorting procedure built-in in LIAM2 ensures that each period only a given percentage of individuals of a given gender and age group are simulated as having been contributing on that period. Thus, some individuals with higher probabilities of having long formal careers are simulated as having gaps in their careers. This reduces the amount of people able to reach the compulsory 30 years (or 120 quarters) of contributions for retiring at the minimum age of 60 for women, and 65 for men. This problem is most binding for women, since these have both lower formal labour participation rates than men and an earlier retirement age.

The "housewife" module: polarising between women with long and short careers

As such, in order to discriminate women that are likely to never have worked in the formal labour-market from women that are more likely to having had a longer formal career, we introduce a simple module for identifying stay-at-home wives in our initial dataset, the EPHc. This corresponds to what Li & O'Donoghue (2012) call a "deterministic simulation", that "generates[a] part of the history that is directly determined by retrospective variables and ensures that the generated history is perfectly consistent with the reported values" (Li & O'Donoghue, 2012, p. 56). We apply this deterministic simulation to identify stay-at-home wives that are very likely to not have worked before. If we interview a working-age woman that reports being a housewife (and is thus inactive) and she does not have children under the age of 5, we assume she has always been inactive. This flags a significant female population (16% of women of working age according to the EPHc) that we simulate as having been inactive since they have been of working age.

The reason why we consider housewives with children aged 4 or less as temporarily withdrawn from the labour market is linked to Argentina's education system. In this country, public school is compulsory and free from the age of 5, and since that age school enrolment is nearly universal. Before that age however, school attendance is far lower: 94% of children aged 5 attend school or an educative facility, but only 71% of those aged 4 and 37% of those aged 3¹⁶. Furthermore, there is a lack of public and affordable nursery facilities. Therefore, parents that cannot afford either sending their children to private nurseries nor hiring domestic employees must take care of their children at home. It is thus safe to assume that in our survey, when a woman declares she is a housewife while she is the mother of at least one child under the age of five, she has temporarily withdrawn herself from the labour market in order to take care of that child. A housewife without a young child is on the other hand likely to not have worked in the past, and thus having been a stay-at-home wife since her marriage. We thus simulate for these women a career with only inactivity spells, leaving room for other women of their age group for having contributed to social security in the past. We thus polarise through this module between women that probably never contributed and women who are likely to have had longer careers. This ensures that a higher proportion of women aged 60 have contributed the 30 years required for retiring at that age.

We however only model housewives in our retrospective module mainly because we

¹⁶Source: own computation using the EPHc, 2003-2015.

cannot model the mechanism by which a woman becomes a stay-at-home wife once she married. The aforementioned identification strategy of permanent housewives is indeed most of the time *ex post*: it is because the self-declared housewife does not have today little children that there is a high probability she withdrew from the labour-market at the time of marriage. If however we interviewed the same woman some years ago and she had at the time children under the age of 4, we would not have been able to distinguish her from a temporary housewife. The problem is she probably became a housewife in the beginning of her marriage or when she had her first child. This is precisely an age where most of the time our module cannot tell apart a temporary stay-at-home wife from a permanent one. We thus do not know the characteristics permanent housewives had when they permanently (as we assume) withdrew from the labour market. As such, when we simulate future careers of younger (or minor) women, we cannot tell which of those is more likely to become a permanent housewife once she marries or becomes a mother. On the other hand, the fact we can identify *ex post*, so many years after she became a housewife, permanent housewives in the EPHc still allows us to know with a decent amount of certitude what her past career was. We thus restrict the study of housewives to the retrospective module.

All in all, this deterministic housewife module allowed us to further polarise between women with long formal careers and those who likely never contributed in the past due to the male breadwinner bias prevalent in Argentina. This addition allows for a more realistic simulation of women's rights to a pension. Finally, we end our simulation of the labour market by estimating labour income.

2.3.3 The micro calibration of our wage module: building and estimating Mincer wage equations for Argentina's labour market

Designing wage equations that fit our model's needs

The behavioural equations we estimated earlier ensure the careers we back-cast and forecast are coherent with observed behaviour in Argentina during the 2003-2015 period. We complete here these careers by estimating individual labour income. Earnings are central in our prospective and retrospective simulations. First and foremost because they are necessary for estimating not only pension rights at retirement but also family benefits, as seen in section 1.1.1. Indeed, formal workers may only get access to a family benefit if their and their family-group's labour income does not exceed a given cap. The amount of

said allowance is also income-dependent. Secondly, because we use labour income quartile as an explanatory (and statistically significant) variable in our behavioural equations, as can be seen in section 2.3.1. Finally, because we use labour income as a means to identify formal independent workers in the Autonomous workers and *Monotributo* regimes, as explained in section 1.1.4 and Appendix F. We thus adopt a standard approach in estimating individual income through Mincer wage equations (Mincer & Polachek, 1974). These OLS regressions typically have as a dependent variable labour income and as explanatory variables a wide set of individual characteristics that explain the individual's wage such as gender, level of education (as a proxy for human capital and thus labour productivity) or age.

We are not however interested in estimating past (or future) income levels, but rather the respondent's income relative to the period's mean labour income, as in France's TRAJECTOIRE dynamic microsimulation model (Duc *et al.* , 2013). After that, we use historical wage levels in our backwards simulations and different wage evolution hypotheses in our prospective simulations to deduce real labour income from the estimated position in the income scale. There are two main reasons for choosing labour income as a percentage of the period's mean wage as a dependent variable. On the one hand, when reproducing individual careers, we make our individuals "rejuvenate" through troubled periods with huge swings in real wages, as we have seen in Figure 1.2. This shows in Argentina real labour income has historically been widely determined by macroeconomic factors and not by individual characteristics. Thus, were we to estimate real wage levels, our OLS regressions would be filled with macroeconomic variables such as GDP growth and unemployment figures, but also inflation levels or the peso's over or under-evaluation with the US dollar, and our model would therefore become needlessly complicated. On the other hand, the tampering with official inflation figures undertaken in the 2007-2015 period (see Figure 1.2) makes precisely estimating real wage figures tricky at best. Running Mincer wage equations where the dependent variable is labour income as a percentage of the period's mean wage deals with both these issues. On the one hand, we can do completely without inflation figures and thus do not use a controverted and at times unavailable¹⁷ consumer price index. On the other hand, we can presume that the elements determining a given worker's place in the income scale are both mostly dependent on individual characteristics and relatively stable over time.

¹⁷Concomitantly with the access to power of president Macri in December 2015, the INDEC decided not to publish any nationwide inflation figures between November 2015 and March 2016. The official objective was creating a new reliable consumer price index, but it also helped dissimulate the impact of December 2015's drastic devaluation of the peso on inflation figures just as labour unions were negotiating wage levels for 2016 between February and April 2016.

The design and estimation of our Mincer wage equations

The Mincer wage equations we run are estimated separately by gender and through 10-fold cross validated OLS regressions with a stepwise selection method. This ensures we select a model that has both the most significant explanatory variables while at the same time not being overfitted to the estimation data. As with our behavioural equations (see section 2.3.1), we need our Mincer wage equations not to be overly dependent on the dataset they are estimated on, the EPHc (2003-2015). This is because we apply them to obtain wages in different time frames, either in the past (1974-2015) or in prospective simulations (2015-2040). The stepwise selection method defines what explanatory variables are selected: entry in the model is reserved for variables that pass the 10% significance threshold, while variables that entered the model but afterwards fail to reach the 10% significance threshold are excluded from the model. In our Mincer wage regressions, this process goes on until the Cross-Validated Predicted Residual Error Sum of Squares (PRESS) statistic is minimised. After selecting the variables that enter in the model, we run our 10-fold cross-validation process. K-fold cross-validation (Kohavi *et al.* , 1995) consists in randomly dividing the data in K sets of equal size. The model is estimated in K-1 of those sets, the training datasets, and validated on the remaining dataset, the validation dataset. This is repeated K times until all of the subsets have been used as a validation dataset. We end up having K cross-validation estimates for each variable in our model, and the final value of the estimated coefficient is a simple average of these K cross-validation estimates.

The equations are estimated on cross-sections of the EPHc on working individuals¹⁸. We do not use the panel dimension of the EPHc but rather stick to its cross-sectional nature because we do not want to leave out from our microsimulation model respondents who may not have been interviewed two consecutive years or quarters. Also, the estimated individual i 's error term $\epsilon_{i,t}$ is used in our dynamic microsimulation model, so it is important to have it for each respondent that was working when surveyed. The equations, inspired from TRAJECTOIRE's wage module (Duc *et al.* , 2013), have the following form,

¹⁸The model does not allow for working individuals with no labour income, even though unpaid family workers are counted as informal workers. Nevertheless, we still estimate unpaid domestic worker's careers, and individual residuals of the wage equations are used in back-cast Mincer wage equations. As such, even though unpaid workers are excluded from the estimation of behavioural equations, we include them in our Mincer wage equations although we input them a minimum wage. This one is equal to the bottom 2% percentile of the respondent's labour-market state at time t .

for each individual i , period t and gender $g \in \{m; f\}$ (m for men and f for women) :

$$\begin{aligned}
\ln \left(\frac{ITL_{i,t}}{RIPTE_t \times structure_{g,t}} \right) &= \alpha + \sum_{j=1}^k \sum_{l=1}^3 \beta_{j,l} \times age_{i,j} \times for_{i,l} \\
&+ \sum_{j=1}^k \sum_{l=1}^3 \gamma_{j,l} \times age_{i,j} \times LMS_{i,l,t} \\
&+ \sum_{j=1}^k \sum_{l=1}^3 \gamma_{j,l} \times age_{i,j} \times seniority_{i,l,t} + \hat{\epsilon}_{i,t}
\end{aligned} \tag{2.3}$$

$ITL_{i,t}$ is individual i 's Total Labour Income at time t , $RIPTE_t$ the value of the wage index RIPTE at time t , $age_{i,j}$ a dummy for belonging to 5-years age groups that range from 16 to 60 for women and 65 for men, $for_{i,l}$ a polytomous variable depicting individual i 's education level (Primary, Secondary or complete Tertiary education), $LMS_{i,l,t}$ individual i 's labour-market state at time t (formal dependent employment, formal independent labour and informal employment) and $seniority_{i,l,t}$ as a polytomous variable with values ranging from under three months to more than five years. We estimate also distinct Mincer wage-equations for back-casting careers as we cannot use seniority as an explanatory variable in our retrospective module, as explained in section 2.3.1. Our backwards Mincer wage equations are thus as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\ln \left(\frac{ITL_{i,t}}{RIPTE_t \times structure_{g,t}} \right) &= \alpha + \sum_{j=1}^k \sum_{l=1}^3 \beta_{j,l} \times age_{i,j} \times for_{i,l} \\
&+ \sum_{j=1}^k \sum_{l=1}^3 \gamma_{j,l} \times age_{i,j} \times LMS_{i,l,t} + \hat{\epsilon}_{i,t}
\end{aligned} \tag{2.4}$$

Education is included as a proxy for human capital and the labour-market state variable controls for Argentina's labour-market segmentation. Seniority gives an indication on how much on-the-job experience the worker has accumulated, which translates into higher productivity over time. In the case of formal wage-earners, there are also trade union agreements where wages are automatically adjusted with seniority, so it may play a direct effect in labour income as well. Crossing discretised age groups with all these variables helps see the non-linear impact of age on labour income, but also how seniority, education and labour-market state have a different impact on labour income depending on the respondents' age. We will further discuss this topic when analysing our Mincer wage equations results.

The dependent variable in our Mincer wage equations is the working individual's position in the income scale, that is, his nominal gross income as a percentage of the period's mean wage. We use the RIPTE (see Figure 1.2 for its evolution and section 1.3.2 for its definition) in the 2003-2015 period where we estimate our Mincer wage equations. When we compute individual careers in earlier periods, we use mean wage sources described in section 1.3 and depicted in Figure 1.10. However, these wage indexes do not make distinctions between male and female workers. We thus modify our dependent variable in the way of TRAJECTOIRE's microsimulation model (Duc *et al.* , 2013, p. 29) with a structural coefficient, where for each period t $structure_{f,t} = (ITL_t - (ITL_{m,t} * N_{m,t}/N_t)) * N_t/N_{f,t}$. $N_{m,t}$ and $N_{f,t}$ respectively stand for the number of working men and women at time t and N_t for the number of working individuals at time t . Similarly, $ITL_{m,t}$, $ITL_{f,t}$ and ITL_t respectively stand for men and women's mean labour income and total worker's mean income at time t . The full list of structural coefficients is available in Table M.9. We finally estimate separately the labour income of workers above the legal retirement age (60 for women, 65 for men) up to age 69.

Results

The results can be seen in Appendix M and are transcribed in Tables M.1 to M.8. Table M.10 helps reading the results of our forward Mincer wage equations (Tables M.1 and M.2). As with behavioural equations, the results barely change for our prospective (Tables M.1 and M.2) and retrospective (Tables M.3 and M.4) regressions, so we will stick to analysing the former. Some results amount to stylised facts. For all ages and both genders, the longer the seniority or the higher the level of education the higher the position in the income scale. Likewise, for any given age labour income is the highest for registered wage-earners, followed by own-account workers and unregistered workers. This wage penalty associated with informal labour has been vastly addressed in the literature (El Badaoui *et al.* , 2008; Beccaria & Groisman, 2008; Gasparini & Tornarolli, 2009).

What is more interesting however is how each of these variables reacts to age. Let us start by analysing the sensitivity of the labour-market variable to age. First of all, the wage penalty associated with being an informal worker instead of a formal wage-earner is huge and relatively constant over time. Starting from age 20, all other things being equal a formal wage-earner earns twice (in the case of men) or 140% (for women) as much as an informal worker (Table M.10). Formal sector independent workers seem to be the ones benefiting the most from ageing. The wage bonus associated with being a formal wage-earner instead of a formal independent worker decreases with age until reach-

ing 14% for men and 30% for women at around age 40. from whence it stabilises until retirement. This may come from the fact older own-account workers have accumulated more capital than younger ones, both physical and human, which translates in higher income. It can moreover be argued that a more important share of independent workers' human capital may come from on-the-job experience and connections as compared to wage-earners. This capital helps counterbalance the loss of labour productivity associated with age more effectively than wage-earners. Formal wage-earners benefit from collective bargaining agreements that often adjust wages with seniority to compensate for this, but informal workers don't. It can thus be seen that the wage bonus associated with being a formal independent worker instead of informal greatly increases with age (Table M.10).

Secondly, education levels also have a differing impact on wages at different ages. The wage penalty associated with having a complete secondary education instead of a university degree may be more or less constant over time (Table M.10). Nevertheless, the wage penalty associated with lacking a complete secondary education increases with age. When it is compared to having a complete secondary education, wage decreases from around -8% (-15% for women) at age 20 to -23% (-22% for women) when reaching retirement age. The gap is even larger when we compare it to the income that would be gained when having a University degree: it decreases from -25% (-33% for women) at age 20 to -39% (-41% for women) when approaching retirement. This means unqualified or poorly qualified labour is more affected by ageing than skilled labour in the case of Argentina.

Thirdly, seniority also has an age-dependent impact on wages. As is logical, for both men and women the highest value of seniority (more than five years) has the strongest positive impact on wages, while the shortest one (less than three months) has the most negative impact on labour income. Seniority affects in similar ways men and women's earnings. In the case of men, it is most of the time possible to group seniority in only three categories. First of all, the shortest seniority (three months at most) implies a significant labour income penalty that increases with age. Secondly, the longest seniority recorded in the EPHc (more than five years working in the current firm) has the highest positive impact on labour income all other things being equal. This bonus increases with age until reaching a maximum just before retiring. Finally, it is possible to group intermediate values of seniority together (from more than three months to five years) as they have the same impact on labour income. As expected, they imply a labour income bonus that increases with age when compared to the shortest seniority. Conversely, it also implies a labour income penalty when compared with the longest possible seniority. The impact of seniority on women's labour income differs slightly from that on men. Seniority

between more than a year up to five years has a significantly different impact on labour income than seniority between three to twelve months, specially at more advanced ages. In contrast, the labour income penalty of seniority under three months as compared to seniority between three and twelve months decreases with age until being minimal after age 40. This means senior female workers need longer seniority to avoid the labour income penalty associated with age. This is counterbalanced by the fact very short seniority does not particularly affect female income levels. The interpretation of this result is tricky at best, but this may be evidence that women tend to jump less often than men from one temporary job to the other. Women that are surveyed when they are just starting their job may have less chances of being in the midst of a high turn-over situation. This may be coherent with higher male employment in such sectors as construction (or seasonal agricultural work, although the EPHc does not really capture rural labour) where temporary employment is more common.

2.3.4 Testing the model's fit: back-cast and forecast labour-market participation rates

Before making social security projections, it is important to show our model's labour-market simulations correctly reproduce both historical values and our scenarios at an aggregate level. In practice, we need to show our model reproduces the desired labour-market participation rates (both past and future). On the other hand, labour income is estimated by our wage module as a percentage of the gross mean wage of formal wage-earners (RIPTE), so its level is directly linked to our wage scenario (see section 2.3.3). Our model simulates hence the dispersion of labour income around this target mean wage depending on individual characteristics (the most important being labour-market state). Simulated labour-income levels are thus secondary for determining our labour-market module's accuracy.

We thus need to prove our model can correctly reproduce labour-market participation by gender at an aggregate level. For our retrospective module, we need to show our model reproduces historical labour-market participation rates. Our prospective module on the other hand needs to reproduce the labour-market scenarios we input. We will thus begin by presenting our labour-market scenarios by gender and labour-market state for the 2017-2040 period. After that, starting from the fourth quarter of 2014 EPHc dataset, we show we fittingly reproduce aggregate historical values for the 1974-2014 period as far as labour-market state is concerned. Finally, we show our prospective simulations result

in aggregate labour-market repartition that is coherent with our central labour-market scenario.

Future labour-market participation rates: deriving age specific rates from aggregate scenarios

We will begin by describing how we make our labour-market scenarios for the 2017-2040 period. More specifically, we propose labour-market scenarios by gender and age groups for the 2017-2040 period. Aligning labour-market states by gender-specific ratios is compulsory as long as we estimate behavioural equations separately by gender because the estimated propensity scores for transiting into a given labour-market state for men and women are not directly comparable. Aligning our microsimulations on age-group specific rates is natural for our retrospective simulations or projected periods for which we can measure age-specific labour-market rates. If we know that in 1994 $n\%$ of men aged 30 to 34 were unemployed, we want to have $n\%$ of men surveyed in 2014 that are aged 50 to 54 to have been unemployed in 1994.

This alignment by age group is however questionable for our labour-market projections. First, these are already explanatory variables of our behavioural equations, so we could rely on them to simulate a labour supply that is consistent at the aggregate level with individual's ages. Most importantly though, this bars other modules of the model from having an endogenous impact on aggregate labour supply. In our case, this constrains our hypotheses on university students as a proportion of young adults, since the share of inactive young adults among the total inactive population is unchanged. Neither does it allow for an actual increase in aggregate labour supply of the elderly as a result of decreasing retirement pensions as a proportion of the mean wage, which is a consequence of the new pension mobility formula established by Law 27426 since March 2018 (see Appendix E). Blanchet *et al.* (2011) also pointed out this flaw in the case of DESTINIE 2's career module, since it "does not allow for [pension reform] scenarios to have an impact on demographic or employment trajectories before retirement" (Blanchet *et al.* , 2011, p. 104). We however decided to align labour-market states to exogenous age group specific proportions in order to ensure future labour supply will be consistent as far as age goes with those observed in recent years. Indeed, "even with big samples, we know microsimulation is still exposed to fluctuation risks or even to a stochastic drift. Aligning [the simulations] on some aggregate values (...) makes controlling this risk possible" (Blanchet *et al.* , 2011, p. 104). As such, aligning projected careers on both gender and age groups is common in the literature. In the case of France, even when behavioural equations are

estimated to simulate labour transitions. This is done for instance by the INSEE in their DESTINIE 2 model (Blanchet *et al.* , 2011, p. 108) and by the CNAV in their PRISME model (Berteau-Rapin *et al.* , 2015, p. 104).

However, choosing to align our microsimulations separately by age groups and gender makes designing labour-market scenarios challenging. Indeed, this for instance means when we input an unemployment scenario in our model, we do not simply enter an unemployment rate for period t of $u_t\%$ for men and $u_{w,t}\%$ for women. We instead enter age-group specific unemployment rates for men $u_{16,t}, u_{20,t}, \dots, u_{65,t}$ and for women $u_{w,16,t}, u_{w,20,t}, \dots, u_{w,65,t}$. Since we have 11 five-year age groups, this makes us input 22 different unemployment rates. The same operation is made for formal wage-earners, formal sector independent workers, unregistered workers and the inactive. As such, we needed a methodology to derive age-specific labour-market proportions from the desired aggregate scenarios.

To do so, we first made the hypothesis that, for each gender, the age-specific structure of each labour-market was equal to the mean-value of this repartition between the first quarter of 2010 and the first quarter of 2017, as measured by the EPHc. We thus made the hypothesis of an age structure for each labour-market state that is constant throughout our prospective simulations (2017-2040). This meant for instance that for every 100 unemployed males aged 35 to 39, there were 110 unemployed males aged 40 to 44 and 91 unemployed males aged 45 to 49. We do not transcribe here the full age structures of all our labour-market states, but the tables are available on-line¹⁹. If we take the 35 to 39 age group as reference, this means each age-group specific unemployment rate can be expressed as such: $u_{i,t} = k_i \times u_{35,t}$, $i \in (16, 20, 25, \dots, 65)$, k_i being a known constant.

Let us assume we want in period t an unemployment rate for men equal to u_t . Given the projected male population for period t aged 16 to 69 n_t , this means we have a total population of unemployed males $U_t = u_t \times n_t$. By definition, $U_t = u_{16,t} \times n_{16,t} + u_{20,t} \times n_{20,t} + \dots + u_{65,t} \times n_{65,t}$. Since we assume the age structure of the unemployed population remains constant throughout our simulation, we can express each age-specific unemployment rate as a known function of a numeral (here the age group 35 to 39). That means we have $U_t = k_{16} \times u_{35,t} \times n_{16,t} + k_{20} \times u_{35,t} \times n_{20,t} + \dots + k_{65} \times u_{35,t} \times n_{65,t}$. As such, we have $u_{35,t} = \frac{u_t \times n_t}{k_{16}n_{16,t} + k_{20}n_{20,t} + \dots + k_{65}n_{65,t}}$. Since all population values are given by our known population scenario for the 2010-2040 period (fully available in Table K.2 of Appendix

¹⁹We use the Zenodo archiving service for long-term preservation of our code. The DOI link is: [10.5281/zenodo.1420273](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1420273)

K), this makes $u_{35,t}$ (and thus all age-group specific unemployment rates) depend on the global unemployment hypothesis for males in t u_t . This thus makes all age-group specific unemployment rates a function of the aggregate male unemployment hypothesis for t u_t . As such, for each period and gender we only need to input one labour-market scenario. The full labour-market scenarios (low, central and high) are listed in Appendix N. We will however present the logic behind its conception and illustrate it through various figures below.

Aggregate labour-market participation rates by economic scenario (2017-2040)

In what regards projected labour-market participation by gender, we wanted our scenarios to be coherent with historical evolutions of labour-market participation in Argentina. We also wanted to cover a wide array of possibilities, depicting scenarios of moderate growth, strong economic growth and protracted economic crisis. We thus designed the following labour-market scenarios, which are depicted in Figures 2.4a and 2.4b.

To make these scenarios, we first assumed by the first quarter of 2019 the proportion of each of these five labour-market states was equal to their 2010- first quarter of 2017 average. In the case of men, since the proportion of formal wage-earners exhibits a negative trend since 2012, we subtracted 3 percentage points to this average, and conversely added 1.5 percentage points to both the proportion of informal workers and the unemployed. For women, we took into account the declining trend in informal labour by subtracting from this average one percentage point, which was added to the proportion of formal wage-earners expected by the first quarter of 2019. We then complete the values between the first quarters of 2017 and 2019 by a linear interpolation. After that, for each of our economic scenarios we fix a labour-market participation profile to be reached by the fourth quarter of 2040, separately for men and women. We fill in the values between the first quarter of 2019 and the fourth quarter of 2040 by linear interpolation, making sure the sum of all the possible labour-market states always equals 100%. The main element that changes from one scenario to the other is the share of formal wage-earners: higher levels of this variable equal to more optimistic labour-market scenarios. In return, the informal labour, unemployment and inactivity rates are modified to compensate this formal wage-earners rate modification. We decided to leave untouched across all scenarios the share of independent workers of the formal sector, where we assume no changes after 2019 in all our scenarios. This is because this share has been extremely stable for both genders since the late 1980s despite. Also, it is reasonable to assume the number of qualified

Figure 2.4: Labour-market participation rates for people aged 16 to 69, past and projected rates (1974-2040)

(a) Men

(b) Women

Source: see Figures 1.8 and 1.9 on page 99 for historical values.

own-account workers or owners of small formal businesses owners is mostly impervious to the economic context, as was the case during the 2001 crisis.

This said, our central scenario assumes a virtual stagnation of the labour market participation of men at their 2019 levels. This would mean the decreasing trend in formal wage-earners' rate stops in 2019. This central hypothesis is the most coherent with the historical evolution of male labour-market participation which, barring the 1974 value, is equivalent to a white noise. Also, prolonging the negative trend in male labour formality observed since 2012 is not really compatible with a long-term growth scenario. This last point will be studied more in detail in Chapter 3 section 3.1, where we assume long-term growth is mostly determined by labour productivity gains, reflected in wages that we will assume grow by 0.75% a year. We suppose on the other hand female formal labour participation will slightly increase, nearing 31% by 2040. We offset this mostly by assuming a decreasing inactivity rate. This allows to keep mimicking in our scenarios the gradual convergence between the rate of formal wage earners by gender. Among people aged 16 to 69, in May 1994 the rate of male formal wage earners was 16.5% higher than that of women. In 2017, this difference was only of 10.2%, so it decreased in those 23 years by 38%. In our central economic scenario, we assume this difference in rates between men and women will equal 6.6% in 23 years (the fourth quarter of 2040), which means this difference will decrease by 35%.

For both men and women, we assume our high (resp. low) scenario consists in a share of formal wage-earners that is 7 percentage points higher (resp. lower) than the one we assumed for our central scenario. These higher (resp. lower) rates are compensated by a decrease (resp. increase) of the informal labour, unemployment and inactivity rates by 3.5, 2 and 1.5 percentage points in the case of men; and by 2.5, 1.5 and 3 percentage points in the case of women. If we discount the 2003 discontinuity in inactivity rates, caused by the fact the EPHc considers unpaid domestic workers as informal while previous EPH waves deemed them inactive, men inactivity rates are more stable in the long term than those of women as shown by Figure 2.4. We thus decided in our scenarios to make inactivity rates more variable for women than for men. We chose to make vary formal wage-earners rates by +/-7 percentage points for both men and women because we wanted the variations in the economic scenario to affect in a similar way both genders. This precise figure was chosen because it meant on the optimistic scenario the share of male formal wage earners neared its historical maximum of 45% by 2040, while it also meant that in our pessimistic scenario with stagnating real wages (see the analysis of our real wage scenarios in section 3.1 for more details) we got formal dependent labour rates

among men consistent with those of the mid 1990s.

In the end, these hypotheses allow us to design three clear-cut scenarios that cover most of Argentina's plausible economic future. Our central labour-market scenario assumes a modest economic growth (on average equal to 1.4% every year, as will be analysed more in depth in section 3.1.3) which is not enough to significantly curb labour informality, inactivity or unemployment but which allows for a slow increase in formal dependent labour. Our high economic scenario on the other hand assumes a strong yearly growth (on average equal to 2.6%) that results in a fast increase of formal dependent labour rates for both men and women, although at a slower pace than what was witnessed between the 2001 economic crisis and 2012. Finally, our low scenario assumes a prolonged economic stagnation (yearly growth is on average equal to 0%) that sees formal wages stagnate and formal labour decline to its 1990s levels. Although the differences between these scenarios are quite radical, they are adequate for Argentina's tormented economic history as studied in section 1.3. In particular, although it is harsh to assume in our pessimistic scenario that Argentina's economy will be in a durable recession, it is not an implausible hypothesis to make when we see the recurrent difficulties faced by Argentina's economy, including the latest May-June 2018 currency crisis. Since a mid-to-long term stagnation of real wages and decrease in formal labour is possible, it had to be taken into account in our pessimistic scenario. Since the growth model we adopted is built on the premise that long-term growth is driven by labour productivity, as we explain more in detail in section 3.1.3, this results in a prolonged economic recession.

The model's performance: replicating historical values and reproducing the aggregate scenarios

Now that we have introduced our prospective labour-market scenarios, available in full in Appendix N, we can now prove the ability of our model to reproduce both historical and projected labour-market participation by gender at the aggregate level. We show it through Figures 2.5, 2.6 and 2.7 that depict the back-casting and forecasting of the labour-market situation of people surveyed the fourth quarter of 2014 respectively for both genders, men and women aged 16 to 69. For our backwards simulations, we followed the past labour-market situation of the generation aged 16 to 69 in the fourth quarter of 2014 as we made them rejuvenate until 1974.

Figure 2.5: Comparing simulated and targeted labour-market situation for people aged 16 to 69, 1974-2040

Before the fourth quarter of 2014, the target rates are historically observed in the EPH surveys (1974-2014) and computed for the generation aged 16 to 69 the fourth quarter of 2014. Between the fourth quarter of 2014 and the first quarter of 2017, the target rates are derived from applying five-year age groups specific rates from the EPHc (2014-2017) to the population structure of the prospective simulation starting the fourth quarter of 2014. These are distinct from the actual rates measured in the EPHc during this period, as the population structure by age and gender differs from one EPHc wave to the other. After the first quarter of 2017, the target rates are discretionary scenarios.

Figure 2.6: Comparing simulated and targeted labour-market situation for men aged 16 to 69, 1974-2040

Sources: see Figure 2.5.

Figure 2.7: Comparing simulated and targeted labour-market situation for women aged 16 to 69, 1974-2040

Sources: see Figure 2.5.

Figures 2.5 to 2.7 show our model adequately reaches the targeted aggregate labour-market participation rates it was fed with. This showcases the accuracy with which the alignment by sorting procedure built-in in LIAM2 ensures microsimulated data behaves as intended at the aggregate level. It also shows our retrospective and prospective labour-market modules are able to simulate past and future individual labour careers that are consistent with historical data and our scenarios. Pension rights derived from these simulated careers are thus also consistent with these historical and projected labour-market participation rates.

As a conclusion, we have in this section laid out the calibration of our model’s two core modules, labour-market behaviour and labour income. After explaining our mod-

elling needs, we developed our estimation strategies and analysed our results. This not only allows us to be transparent about our dynamic microsimulation model's calibration, it is also a good excuse for studying labour-market behaviour in Argentina at the individual level. Although most of our results are straightforward, we closely study informal labour in Argentina, its determinants and how it affects earnings using a very thorough household survey, the EPHc. This section thus constitutes a contribution to the informal sector literature, although we did not focus our analysis on it. It also shows how damaging informal labour is for those workers confined in it. This constitutes another argument in favour of finding ways to foster wage formalisation not only in order to increase tax collection and ensure the financing of social security, but also to grant access to decent labour to the highest possible number of Argentinian workers. Finally, we have shown our model is capable of reproducing aggregate labour-market states while still simulating a plausible individual labour supply and income. The latter elements are key in simulating social security's sustainability as well as the adequacy and redistributive power of its benefits. Before moving on to computing social security rights and contributions, we will first show how our model simulates civil status, family links and education-related variables.

2.4 Simulating the marriage market: unions, weddings and divorces

Although the labour-market module is the core of our model, the marriage market module is key to simulating both civil status and the making and unmaking of family links. These are important elements in our microsimulation for various reasons. First, because family links determine who gets benefits such as child allowances and survivors' pensions, as well as their amount. We have moreover seen in section 2.3 and Appendix L that civil status, partner's characteristics and the number of little children are statistically significant explanatory variables for modelling labour-market behaviour. In this section we will thus lay out our simulation of unions and civil statuses. First, we present the micro-level and macro-level calibration of the retrospective and prospective civil status modules, be it individual probabilities of marriage and divorce, historical aggregate rates of people married or in a common-law union and our scenarios on civil statuses evolution. Then, we lay out our simplified take on simulating past civil status. After that, we present our prospective civil status and marriage market module, that includes the estimation of marriage and divorce equations with EPHc (2003-2015) data. Finally, we show how our model on the one hand reproduces past historical civil status proportions while, on the

other hand, it matches our prospective scenarios on civil status up to 2040.

2.4.1 Calibrating the modules: aggregate civil-status values and marriage and divorce probabilities by gender and age

As was hinted when we reviewed our microsimulation model’s general architecture in Figure 2.1, our civil status modules are calibrated on a range of sources. We carry out on the one hand a macro calibration of our modules with aggregate proportions of people that are married or in a common-law union by age and gender. Why we try to reproduce these percentages through various alignment by sorting procedures will be explained when we present our retrospective and prospective civil status modules in sections 2.4.2 and 2.4.3. We also calibrate our modules with individual marriage and divorce probabilities taken from exogenous data sources, which we will lay out in this section. The last micro-level calibration of our civil status modules, our matching and divorce equations, will be studied in our section 2.4.3 on the prospective marriage market module.

The evolution of civil status in Argentina: historical aggregate values taken from the EPH (1974-2017)

The civil status variable (CH07 in the EPHc) has been present since the 1974 wave of the EPH and has not changed since. It can take five distinct values: being in a common-law union, married, separated or divorced, widowed and single. As such, it is relatively straightforward to compute aggregate civil status rates in Argentina since 1974. The following Figure 2.8a gives civil status rates for men and women aged 16 or more as measured by the EPH surveys (1974-2017). Figures 2.8b, 2.8c and 2.8d give civil status rates by broad age groups: respectively 16 to 29 years, 30 to 64 years and 65 or more years. The four dotted vertical lines represent the moments where the EPH surveys underwent major changes (see Section 1.2 for more details) and the 2015 gap the three quarters where the EPHc was not published. Civil status figures by gender can be found on-line²⁰, although there is barely any gender-specific civil status evolution visible at the aggregate level. We remind the reader our model uses in various alignment by sorting procedures aggregate civil status rates by five-year age groups and gender. We have chosen to draw civil status figures on broader age intervals for the sake of legibility, but the full list of rates used in

²⁰We use the Zenodo archiving service for long-term preservation of our code. The DOI link is: [10.5281/zenodo.1420273](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1420273)

our alignment of past civil status is available on-line²¹. This is also true for our aggregate civil status scenarios, which we will study in the next section.

First of all, we can see in Figure 2.8a a steady decrease in married individuals. These went from representing 60% of the 16+ population to a little over 30% since 2014. This halving of the share of married individuals was compensated by an increase in the share of single people (up from 25% to 30% since the early 2000s), the divorced (from 2% to over 7% since the mid 2000s) and most importantly of people in a common-law union (from 4% to over 20% since the mid 2000s). These evolutions were age dependent. Figure 2.8d shows there were hardly any changes in the civil status of the elderly. In what regards young adults, there was a significant increase in the celibacy of people aged 16 to 29 (from 62% to over 70%), a continuous decrease in marriage rates (from 30% to less than 10%) and an explosion of common-law unions (from 5% to 20%). In what concerns middle-aged adults, we see a steady decrease in marriage rates (from 75% to a little over 40% in 2017), mainly compensated by the generalisation of common-law unions (that went from 5% to more than 25%). Finally, the latest civil status data available suggests these evolutions have mostly stabilised since 2014.

These civil status evolutions are part of what Van de Kaa (1987) and Lesthaeghe (1995) called the "second demographic transition". Originally identified in Western Europe families since the 1960's, this transition consists of an "increase in divorce rates [and in](...) the age of marriage, the soaring of common-law unions as well as the increased procreation within these, and the introduction and popularisation of very effective contraceptives" (Sana, 2001, p. 4). Other consequences of this demographic transition are a decrease in fertility rates, which are taken into account in our central demographic scenario (see Appendix K). We are not going to study in this work the social, cultural, economic and technical reasons behind this transition. We however point out the literature considers this transition has started for Argentina and its neighbours more or less since the 1970's and that it is currently ongoing (Lesthaeghe, 2014; Sana, 2001; Quilodran, 2011; Binstock & Cabella, 2011). As we can see then, the results of this second demographic transition are visible in the aggregate civil status rates and will be integrated in our model, as we will see below.

²¹We use the Zenodo archiving service for long-term preservation of our code. The DOI link is: [10.5281/zenodo.1420273](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1420273)

Figure 2.8: Aggregate civil status evolution in Argentina (1974-2040)

(a) 16 or more

(b) Young adults (16-29)

(c) middle ages (30-64)

(d) The Elderly (65+)

Sources: Own calculus from EPH surveys (1974-2017)

Our aggregate civil status scenario (2017-2040)

We input in our prospective module aggregate civil status scenarios (the percentages of people respectively married and in a common-law union) by five-year age groups and

gender. We will however keep to a simple civil status scenario as we assume the second demographic transition ended in Argentina in 2012 as far as marriage rates are concerned. As such, we take EPHc waves for years 2012 to 2017 and compute the proportion of people respectively in a common-law union and married by five-year age group and gender over that whole period. We then make our model reproduce these aggregate ratios until 2040. The alignment values are listed in Table 2.1 below.

There are multiple reasons as to why we adopt a simple civil status scenario. First, because as we have seen in section 1.1, there is little *de jure* difference between married and unmarried couples in what regards family benefits or survivors' pensions. On the one hand, child allowances are given independently from the marital status of the parents. On the other hand, survivor's pensions are given to both married and unmarried surviving concubines. The latter only need to have cohabited with the deceased for at least 5 years, or 2 if they had children together (Art. 53 of Law 24241). This is a very permissive condition, and since moreover the EPHc does not include information on the duration of couples (married or unmarried), we simply assume all surviving spouses (married or unmarried) get access to a survivor's benefit. We will moreover ignore in our model any additional *de jure* difference between common-law and married unions in what regards social security benefits. It is thus more important for our model to reproduce the proportion of people in a couple rather than the percentage of couples that are married or unmarried. And as we have seen in Figure 2.8a, the proportion of people in a married or unmarried couple has remained stable at around 55% of the population aged 16 or more since the late 1990s. We have additionally seen in Figure 2.8a that since 2012 there are little to no changes in aggregate civil status rates. Finally, it is unlikely the proportion of married adults in Argentina will decrease much further, as it is already lower than in some Western European Countries. For instance, in France 8% of people aged 15 or more were divorced, 7% widowed, 45% married and 39% single (be them in a common-law union or not) in 2015 ²². Meanwhile, only 30% of the population aged 16 or more was married in Argentina in 2017.

²²Source: own computation based on Insee population projections, la situation démographique en 2014, Insee résultats volume n° 182, population in 2014, Table 6.

Table 2.1: Civil status scenarios: the percentage of people in a common-law union or married by five-year age group and gender

Age	In a common-law union		Married	
	Men	Women	Men	Women
<i>Age</i> ∈ [16; 20[2.8%	7.4%	0.1%	0.4%
<i>Age</i> ∈ [20; 25[15.3%	23.1%	1.9%	4.0%
<i>Age</i> ∈ [25; 30[32.2%	35.6%	9.4%	14.3%
<i>Age</i> ∈ [30; 35[40.0%	39.2%	23.9%	27.6%
<i>Age</i> ∈ [35; 40[37.2%	31.8%	37.9%	39.9%
<i>Age</i> ∈ [40; 45[29.7%	25.4%	48.3%	46.6%
<i>Age</i> ∈ [45; 50[24.8%	19.1%	54.2%	48.5%
<i>Age</i> ∈ [50; 55[21.0%	14.8%	57.1%	50.3%
<i>Age</i> ∈ [55; 60[18.3%	11.7%	59.9%	50.3%
<i>Age</i> ∈ [60; 65[15.6%	8.9%	62.5%	49.2%
<i>Age</i> ∈ [65; 70[11.7%	6.3%	65.7%	45.8%
<i>Age</i> ∈ [70; 75[10.2%	5.3%	62.8%	38.6%
<i>Age</i> ∈ [75; 80[6.9%	3.4%	65.2%	30.2%
<i>Age</i> ∈ [80; 85[6.8%	2.5%	56.8%	20.3%
<i>Age</i> ∈ [85; 90[4.0%	1.2%	55.5%	11.5%
<i>Age</i> ∈ [90; 95[5.6%	0.5%	36.5%	3.7%
<i>Age</i> ≥ 95	0.4%	0.4%	37.7%	3.2%

Source: Author's calculation based on the EPHc survey (2012- first quarter of 2017)

This scenario, computed with the 2012-2017 EPHc waves, transcribes a typical life-cycle in what regards couple formation and dissolution. First, young adults transit from celibacy to being in a common-law union, as evidenced by the quick increase in common-law union rates as young adults gradually age. Then, a slow transition from common-law unions into marriage takes place, being mostly over by the late thirties for women and early forties for men. Common-law unions however remain prevalent until retirement age. Finally, once retirement age is reached (60 for women, 65 for men), the percentage of married people steadily declines due to the spouse's death. We can also see in Table 2.1 evidence that women get in a couple and marry at earlier ages than men mainly because women undergo this life cycle at younger ages than men. This is shown by the fact the rates of young adult women married or in a common-law union are systematically higher than those of men of the same ages. The fact women tend to go through widowhood as they age goes in the same direction, as evidenced by the drop in married women past age

60. In fact, 38% of women aged 60 or more are widows, while only 12% of men of those ages widowed²³.

With this, we have finished studying the aggregate civil status ratios by age and gender that enter in the calibration of our retrospective and prospective microsimulation modules. We will now study the micro-level calibration of these modules through marriage and divorce probabilities.

Marriage and divorce probabilities by age and gender: sources, computation and extrapolation up to 2040

We may use alignment by sorting procedures to get the desired number of people married or in a common-law union, but this only ensures the macro-consistency of our simulated civil status with historical data or our proposed scenario. Our prospective civil status module also uses matching, divorce and breakup equations estimated in the EPHc (2003-2015), which we will study at the end of this section. However, the micro consistency of our civil status modules is mostly ensured by marriage and divorce probabilities by age and gender. In our retrospective civil status module, marriage and divorce probabilities ensure that a plausible number of individuals get married or divorce at a given period. The same role is given to marriage probabilities in our prospective civil status module. Meanwhile, divorce probabilities are used in conjunction with estimated divorce equations to determine which married couples will divorce in the future. We will thus explain here how we compute these marriage and divorce probabilities.

First, for each gender, we compute the probability an unmarried man or woman in a common-law union has to marry in a given year. To do so, we use two main data sources. We have on the one hand marriage figures by age and gender for the Autonomous City of Buenos Aires (CABA)²⁴. We do not have precise figures of marriage by age for other parts of the country, so we work with the population of the CABA. We take from the 2001²⁵ and 2010 national Census²⁶ population figures for the City of Buenos Aires by age, gender, civil status and cohabiting with a partner. These are however imperfect estimations of the Autonomous City's total population since, as acknowledged by the

²³Source: Own calculus with data from the EPHc (2012-2017).

²⁴Source: General Office of Statistics and Census, Ministry of Finance, Buenos Aires City Government, Vital Statistics.

²⁵More precisely, we use 2001 National Census' Table 6.7 City of Buenos Aires. Population aged 14 or more by legal civil status and living together with their partner by gender and age groups. Year 2001.

²⁶More precisely, we use Table P25-P. "Autonomous City of Buenos Aires. Population aged 14 or more by legal civil status and living in a couple, by gender and age group".

INDEC itself, census omission rates are particularly important for the CABA. In 2001 for instance, 5.5% of the estimated population of the CABA was not interviewed during the Census (INDEC, 2005, p. 16-17). The following marriage probabilities are thus to be taken with a grain of salt, although these are the best we can compute with available data.

To compute marriage probabilities, we divide, for each gender and age group, the number of marriages by the amount of unmarried people in a couple living with their partner. This gives us the marriage probability by age and gender for years 2001 and 2010. Since information on marriages in the CABA is not differentiated by age groups for people over 50. we divided for each gender total marriages in the year (2001 or 2010) by the unmarried population aged 50 to 85 living with their partner that same year in the CABA as per the National Census. For the sake of simplicity we assume an equal marriage probability for people aged 50 to 84. This gives us the conditional probabilities of marrying by gender and age groups listed in Table 2.2.

Table 2.2: Yearly conditional probabilities of marrying for people in an unmarried couple by age and gender

Age groups	Marriage probability (%)			
	Men		Women	
	2001	2010	2001	2010
<i>Age</i> ∈ [15; 19[4.03	2.33	9.29	3.58
<i>Age</i> ∈ [20; 25[16.28	5.42	17.61	6.02
<i>Age</i> ∈ [25; 30[23.84	8.53	23.02	9.35
<i>Age</i> ∈ [30; 35[16.98	9.13	14.66	8.49
<i>Age</i> ∈ [35; 40[10.96	6.28	8.52	5.59
<i>Age</i> ∈ [40; 45[7.28	4.91	5.04	4.05
<i>Age</i> ∈ [45; 50[5.27	4.41	4.38	3.29
<i>Age</i> ≥ 50	4.74	4.2	3.76	3.04

Source: Author's calculation based on data from Argentina's National Census (2001 and 2010) and the Vital Statistics series by the General Office of Statistics and Census, Ministry of Finance, Buenos Aires City Government.

First of all, marriage probabilities are quite classically distributed for both men and women. Marriage rates rapidly spike at ages 25 to 35 before linearly decreasing with time. In more extreme ages, younger women have more significant probabilities of getting married than men. Conversely, the older men have a higher probability of marrying than women of the same ages. Moreover, we see two significant evolutions in only 9 years.

First, marriage probabilities decrease at all ages for both men and women, often being divided by two. This is in line with Figure 2.8a, where we see a sharp decrease in married people of all ages between 2001 and 2017. Second, this decrease in marriage probabilities is concentrated at younger ages. Indeed, the marriage probabilities of people under the age of 25 are roughly divided by three, while those of people aged 40 or more decrease in a lesser proportion. This is in line with age-dependent aggregate civil state rates, where we see that between years 2001 and 2010 the rates of married young adults (Figure 2.8b) were more than halved (going from 14% to 6%) while those of married middle-aged adults (Figure 2.8c) decreased by a fifth (going from 64% to 50%). Both the lower probability of marriage and the fact this decrease is concentrated among younger adults are in line with the second demographic transition we presented earlier.

We use marriage probabilities in both our retrospective and prospective civil status modules, as will be studied in sections 2.4.2 and 2.4.3. We use the marriage probabilities of 2001 for all periods up to 2001, those of 2010 for the 2010-2040 period and an extrapolation of 2001 and 2010 probabilities for years 2002 to 2009. Keeping 2010 probabilities for the 2010-2040 period is not a problem as it is in line with our aggregate civil status scenario pictured in Table 2.1 that depicts a stagnation of marriage rates. Having to keep 2001 probabilities for the whole 1955-2001 period is more of a problem. Nevertheless, civil status plays a lesser role in our retrospective module than in our prospective (as explained in section 2.4.2), so such an approximation is of little incidence in simulated careers.

The second micro-level calibration element of our modules are divorce probabilities by age and gender. We compute these by dividing the number of divorces by the population for each gender and age group. Once again, we compute these probabilities with data from the City of Buenos Aires (CABA) because we do not have divorce figures by age and gender for other parts of the country. We have divorce figures by age groups and gender for years 2009 to 2016²⁷. We work with estimated population at year 2009 from Ministry of Health's Vital Statistics reports (DEIS, 2001-2010) and INDEC population projections for the 2010-2040 period. The resulting divorce probabilities are listed in Table 2.3 below.

²⁷Source: General Office of Statistics and Census, Ministry of Finance, Buenos Aires City Government, Vital Statistics.

Table 2.3: Yearly conditional probabilities of divorce by age and gender

Age groups	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	Mean
	Men								
<i>Age</i> ∈ [20; 25[0.31%	0.45%	0.28%	0.24%	0.34%	0.10%	0.35%	0.55%	0.33%
<i>Age</i> ∈ [25; 30[1.79%	1.76%	1.67%	1.21%	1.10%	1.13%	1.31%	1.29%	1.41%
<i>Age</i> ∈ [30; 35[2.16%	2.60%	2.26%	1.93%	1.71%	1.61%	1.66%	1.64%	1.95%
<i>Age</i> ∈ [35; 40[1.99%	2.40%	2.23%	2.15%	1.84%	1.81%	1.78%	1.97%	2.02%
<i>Age</i> ∈ [40; 45[1.98%	2.45%	2.43%	2.13%	2.00%	1.86%	1.84%	1.87%	2.06%
<i>Age</i> ∈ [45; 50[2.17%	2.41%	2.51%	2.18%	2.19%	1.97%	2.01%	1.93%	2.17%
<i>Age</i> ∈ [50; 55[1.75%	1.86%	2.04%	1.82%	1.78%	1.82%	1.69%	1.70%	1.81%
<i>Age</i> ∈ [55; 60[1.25%	1.45%	1.55%	1.20%	1.32%	1.33%	1.30%	1.37%	1.35%
<i>Age</i> ≥ 60	0.42%	0.49%	0.52%	0.44%	0.50%	0.45%	0.50%	0.51%	0.48%
	Women								
<i>Age</i> ∈ [20; 25[0.62%	0.63%	0.60%	0.74%	0.78%	0.44%	0.52%	0.81%	0.58%
<i>Age</i> ∈ [25; 30[2.04%	2.27%	1.83%	1.56%	1.39%	1.43%	1.54%	1.59%	1.53%
<i>Age</i> ∈ [30; 35[2.11%	2.60%	2.33%	2.05%	1.80%	1.77%	1.73%	1.64%	1.87%
<i>Age</i> ∈ [35; 40[2.16%	2.42%	2.38%	2.24%	1.92%	1.82%	1.83%	1.90%	2.01%
<i>Age</i> ∈ [40; 45[2.13%	2.32%	2.37%	2.09%	2.13%	1.88%	1.91%	2.08%	2.09%
<i>Age</i> ∈ [45; 50[2.06%	2.23%	2.40%	1.98%	2.03%	1.91%	1.91%	1.95%	2.08%
<i>Age</i> ∈ [50; 55[1.53%	1.68%	1.79%	1.55%	1.53%	1.54%	1.51%	1.52%	1.64%

Source: Author's calculation based on DEIS (2010), population projections by INDEC (2010-2040) and the Vital Statistics series by the General Office of Statistics and Census, Ministry of Finance, Buenos Aires City Government.

Age groups	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	Mean
$Age \in [55; 60[$	1.02%	1.07%	1.20%	0.96%	1.03%	1.04%	1.07%	1.00%	1.10%
$Age \geq 60$	0.34%	0.41%	0.45%	0.38%	0.45%	0.41%	0.43%	0.47%	0.41%
Source: Author's calculation based on DEIS (2010), population projections by INDEC (2010-2040) and the Vital Statistics series by the General Office of Statistics and Census, Ministry of Finance, Buenos Aires City Government.									

We can first of all see there are barely no changes in divorce probabilities by age and gender between 2009 and 2016. This result was expected as the proportion of divorced individuals has remained a stable part of the population since the early 2000s as evidenced in Figures 2.8a to 2.8d. We thus compute mean divorce probabilities: for each age group and gender, we take the total number of divorces and divide it by the married population over the whole 2009-2016 period. These mean divorce probabilities are input in our model for both our prospective and retrospective civil status modules. Secondly, there are no significant differences in divorce probabilities by gender. Finally, divorce probabilities are the highest at middle ages (ages 30 to 50) before plummeting at older ages. These are standard results which we will refrain from analysing further in this work.

Finally, we input for our prospective civil status simulations the probability an individual in a common-law union has of breaking-up. These are computed with data from the EPHc (2003-2015) at a quarterly step separately by five-year age groups and gender and are listed in Table 2.4 below. They play the same role as the individual divorce probabilities we presented earlier and ensure we get a plausible level of total break-ups at each quarter, independently of the desired percentage of people in a common-law union as defined in our civil status scenarios listed in Table 2.1. These are not needed in our retrospective civil status module because in the latter break-ups are aligned with the historical aggregate percentage of people in a common-law union, which is made possible by the fact we do not simulate the formation of new unions in our retrospective module, as will be explained in section 2.4.2.

Table 2.4: Quarterly probabilities of leaving an unmarried couple by age and gender

Age groups	Marriage probability (%)	
	Men	Women
$Age \in [16; 19[$	11.73	6.96
$Age \in [20; 25[$	5.21	3.27
Source: Author's calculation based on the EPHc (2003-2015).		

Age groups	Marriage probability (%)	
	Men	Women
<i>Age</i> ∈ [25; 30[2.49	2.29
<i>Age</i> ∈ [30; 35[1.52	1.49
<i>Age</i> ∈ [35; 40[0.91	1.77
<i>Age</i> ∈ [40; 45[0.75	1.83
<i>Age</i> ∈ [45; 50[1.30	1.60
<i>Age</i> ∈ [50; 55[1.43	1.97
<i>Age</i> ∈ [55; 60[1.38	1.49
<i>Age</i> ∈ [60; 65[2.12	1.91
<i>Age</i> ∈ [65; 70[1.54	1.10
<i>Age</i> ∈ [70; 75[1.36	0.63
<i>Age</i> ∈ [75; 80[0.81	0.81
<i>Age</i> ∈ [80; 85[0.44	3.61
<i>Age</i> ∈ [85; 90[5.47	22.39

Source: Author's calculation based on the EPHc (2003-2015).

We can see from these probabilities that there is a downward trend in the probability of breaking up a common-law union with age. This probability stabilises at under 2% for both genders since age 30 and up until age 7, where there is at least 10% of people in a common-law union. This shows common-law unions are unstable under the age of 25 but that after that age the typical outcome of a common-law union is marriage. This is confirmed by the comparison with marriage probabilities by age and gender as listed in Table 2.2. Indeed, for year 2010 the probability a common-law union has of getting married is similar to that of breaking up since year 25, and strictly higher starting from age 30. Unmarried couples of middle-aged adults represent thus a long-term union starting for young adults onward, an element which is portrayed in these break-up probabilities.

With this, we have laid out the main micro and macro calibration elements of our civil status modules and deduced from them our civil status scenarios for our prospective simulations. These elements are input in both our retrospective and prospective civil status and marriage market modules, which we will study in detail below.

2.4.2 Back-casting individual civil status

Our retrospective module back-casts individual careers and outputs accumulated pension rights. It is not interested in simulating past pensions, survivor's benefits or child allow-

ances. As such, it does not include a marriage market module to match single individuals and sticks to a minimal simulation of family links. Civil status has however a significant impact on labour-market state, as shown in section 2.3 and Appendix L. We are thus interested in simulating past civil status, but we can afford to have a simplified take on past civil statuses, which will be explained below.

Back-casting civil status: objectives and methodology

The logic behind simulating past civil statuses is, starting with the initially reported civil status, trying to figure out a plausible date of entry in that civil status. So for a married respondent we will simulate the date of marriage; for a divorced respondent, the date of divorce; and for a widowed respondent, the spouse's date of death. People that are single or in a common-law union in the initial period may have witnessed many spells were they were single or in a common-law union without it showing in their civil status. For that reason transitions between these two civil statuses are allowed. For the sake of simplicity, we make some hypotheses in what concerns possible past civil statuses. First, that all respondents aged 17 or less are single and that respondents aged 18 or 19 can either be in a common-law union or single. This is in line with data from the EPHc, where in 2015 less than 1% of men and women aged 16 to 19 were married but around 8% of women those ages were in a common-law union. Then, we assume there cannot be widowed or divorced respondents under the age of 25. Moreover, a respondent that declares being single in the initial period can only have been either single or in a common-law union in the past. This allows for transitions between being single and in a common-law union. Finally, we assume no respondent can have been widowed or divorced in the past if he was not already widowed or divorced when he or she was surveyed in the EPHc. This means we do not simulate second marriages in our retrospective module.

We want to replicate historically plausible civil statuses by age and gender as depicted in the EPH (1974-2016). We thus apply an alignment by sorting procedure (defined in section 2.1.1). We know for instance from the EPHc that in the first quarter of 2005 21% of women aged 35 to 39 were in a common-law union. We thus want our model to make it so that 21% of women aged 45 to 49 in the first quarter of 2015 were in a common-law union in the first quarter of 2005. We do not however compute a propensity score of transiting from a given civil status to the other between steps t and $t - 1$ as in the case of our labour-market module (see section 2.3). This is because we want to respect the hypotheses mentioned in the previous paragraph. We want for instance respondents that reported being single in the initial period to have never been married, divorced or wid-

owed in the past. This means establishing a selection order at each step of the simulation so that individuals with certain characteristics at step t are selected in priority (and even sometimes always or never selected) to be in a given civil status at step $t - 1$. We chose to more carefully simulate being married or in a common-law union because they determine the date of formation of couples present in the EPHc. Spouse's labour-market state in particular is an important explanatory variable in our behavioural equations (see section 2.3 and Appendix L). The other civil statuses worked more as adjustment variables to reproduce historically plausible values of people married or in a common-law union by age and gender, as will be explained below.

When did the respondent marry? Determining ages of marriage, widowhood and divorce

First, we determine who was married in period $t - 1$. We choose not to simulate same-sex marriages even though they are possible since July 2010²⁸ for the sake of simplicity. We study women and then change if need be the civil status of their (male) partner. This is done for the sake of consistency, so that both members of the couple have the same civil status. We then study men without a partner that may have been married in $t - 1$. This is typically the case of divorced and widowed men in t , but also of some respondents of the EPHc that report being married but whose spouse was not present in the household during the interview. In the model we work with five-year age groups, but for the sake of explaining the module, let's assume $x_{n,t}$ % of women that are n quarters old in period t were married, and that it represents $k_{n,t}$ women. Now in period $t - 1$ as per the macro-level historical calibration we need to have $x_{n-1,t-1}$ % of women $n - 1$ quarters old that are married, which equals $k_{n-1,t-1}$ women. A woman married in t was either married or in a common-law union in $t - 1$. The latter case means the respondent is a woman who just married in t , and it is logical to assume she was in a common-law union with her husband three months earlier. This said, we need to limit the amount of respondents who just married in a given quarter. To do so, we apply marriage probabilities by age and gender (see section 2.4) to randomly select $m_{n,t}$ women aged n who married in t . We then force the model to keep all married women in t who did not just marry in t as having been married in $t - 1$ (this equals $k_{n,t} - m_{n,t}$ women). This may mean we exceed the required $k_{n-1,t-1}$ married women. If this is the case, we stop simulating married women in $t - 1$ and turn to other civil statuses.

If on the other hand we fall short of the required $k_{n-1,t-1}$ women, we try to reach it

²⁸Same-sex marriages were allowed by Law 26618, published the 22d of July 2010.

by taking widows or divorced women in t and consider they were married in $t - 1$. This means their date of divorce or widowhood was t . However, as when we determined the amount of newly-wed women, we want to limit how many women of a given age divorced or widowed in period t . To do so, we apply on the one hand divorce probabilities by age and gender (studied in section 2.4.1) to determine the amount of women aged n that divorced in t $d_{n,t}$. On the other hand, we apply male death probabilities by age (see Appendix K for details on how we compute them) to determine the amount of women who lost their husband in t $w_{n,t}$ ²⁹. If adding all the newly divorced and widowed makes us exceed our target, then we randomly select among the just divorced or widowed enough women to reach the required $k_{n-1,t-1}$ married women aged $n - 1$ in $t - 1$. If on the other hand we do not reach the target, we take some of the women we randomly selected as having married in t and make them stay married in $t - 1$. If all this is not enough to reach $k_{n-1,t-1}$, we stop there and refrain from reaching $x_{n-1,t-1}$ % of married women.

Reproducing historical common-law union rates by age and gender

The other civil status we try to accurately reproduce in our model is being in a common-law union. The architecture is pretty similar to how we simulate married people. First of all, we only study different-sex unions for the sake of simplicity. Then, we study women and then change if need be their (male) partner's civil status. After that, we study men in a common-law union that don't have a known partner and try to reproduce historical values of men in a common-law union. We have each period t a number of women aged n that are in a common-law union $u_{n,t}$ that we want to reach. The difference here is that we first simulate married people and then, among people aged $n - 1$ in $t - 1$ that are not simulated as married, we select enough individuals to reach the desired number of respondents in a common-law union $u_{n-1,t-1}$. Moreover, here we want to reach historical common-law union rates, so we try to get for each period exactly $u_{n,t}$ individuals that are in a common-law union. Let us call $nop_{n,t}$ and $noc_{n,t}$ the amount of people aged n at time t in a common-law union respectively with no known partner and with no known children living with them under the age of 24.

The selection order is as follows. First, we keep people in a common-law union in t with a known partner. These are $u_{n,t} - nop_{n,t}$. Among these, we force the selection of couples who have children living with them under the age of 24. The logic here is that

²⁹By definition, widows in the EPHc do not have a partner, so we do not know what was their spouse's age when he died. As such, we assume he was of the same five-year age group as the widow at the time of death. If for instance a woman lost her husband when she was 53, then we assume her husband was 50 to 54 years old when he died.

the common-law union is likely to have begun at least before the first child was born. If the number of people aged n in a common-law union in t with a known partner and with children living with them is higher than the desired number $u_{n-1,t-1}$, we stop there and exceed the target of $u_{n-1,t-1}$ women in a common-law union. Else, if the number of people in a common-law union with a known partner (but that do not necessarily have children living with them) exceeds the target $u_{n-1,t-1}$, we randomly select among $noc_{n,t}$ enough women to exactly reach $u_{n-1,t-1}$. If on the other hand people in a common-law union with a known partner in t $u_{n,t} - nop_{n,t}$ is below the target, then we take people that were simulated as having married in t $m_{n,t}$. If they are still not enough to reach $u_{n-1,t-1}$ then we take them among people in a common-law union with no partner $nop_{n,t}$. Finally, if the sum of people in a common-law union aged n in t $u_{n,t}$ and of people that married in t aged n $m_{n,t}$ is below the target $u_{n-1,t-1}$ then we make some single women aged n in t be in a common-law union in $t - 1$ in order to reach $u_{n-1,t-1}$. In any case, we never take women that were simulated as being married in $t - 1$ or women that were single or divorced in t . Also, we usually have enough single women of the required ages to at least always reach the desired percentage of women in a common-law union.

In the end, we are able to reproduce past civil status in a relatively accurate way while preserving some logical hypotheses, such as not having people that were single in the initial period that were married, divorced or widowed in the past. As we will see in our results (Section 2.4.4), we get aggregate civil statuses proportions that are not too far away from historical figures as taken from the EPH (1974-2017). In the next section, we will present how we simulate civil status as well as family links in our prospective marriage market module below.

2.4.3 The prospective marriage market module: calibration, simulating new unions, marriages, break-ups and divorce

In our retrospective module civil status was just an explanatory variable in labour-market behavioural equations, which allowed us to model it simply (see Section 2.4.2). Our prospective module on the other hand also simulates family-dependent benefits such as derived pension rights and child allowances. As such, it needs a detailed and plausible simulation of both family links and civil status through time. Hence, our prospective marriage market module reproduces the desired aggregate levels of people married or in a common-law union as per our civil status scenarios depicted in Table 2.1. It does so by simulating who enters, leaves or stays respectively in a married or unmarried union.

We study marital status transitions through alignment by sorting procedures that are analogous to the ones we employed in our study of labour-market transitions (see Section 2.3). The module is micro-calibrated by computing the propensity score of experiencing each transition with logistic models estimated separately by gender on the EPHc (2003-2015). We also use a 5-fold stepwise selection procedure so as to select the model that has the strongest explanatory power while also avoiding to be over-fit to the dataset it was estimated on. Finally, for the sake of robustness, we estimate the models on transitions observed both at a quarterly and a yearly interval, although we only use the former in our microsimulation model since we simulate our population one quarter at a time. The explanatory power of these models is usually low, with the C-statistic often hovering around 0.6, so the micro-level plausibility of most of our marital status transitions is limited. This is not however an issue as the main purpose of this marriage market module is to reproduce the desired aggregate civil status rates by age and gender. To do so, our module is micro-calibrated on the aggregate civil status rates presented in section 2.4.1. Finally, our marriage market module includes a matching procedure to determine the composition of new unmarried couples. The method is inspired on the work by Zinn *et al.* (2012) and the estimated matching equation has a good C-statistic of 0.75. Appendix O lists all these model's equations (O.1 to O.5), their estimated coefficients (listed in Tables O.1 to O.5) and analyses their results.

In this section, we will lay out our prospective marriage market module in the order our model executes it. It first simulates divorces, which together with deaths simulated in earlier stages of the prospective module (see Figure 2.3) represent all exits from marriage. It then simulates marriages, which function as both entry into the married status and exit from a common-law union. After that, it determines which unmarried couples break up, completing exits from a common-law union (other than deaths). Finally, it reproduces aggregate levels of people in a common-law union by simulating new unions. This last step includes the only matching procedure in the model, which determines the composition of future couples.

The entries and exits from married and unmarried unions

Our model starts with a simple alignment by sorting procedure for simulating divorces. It is aligned at the micro level on the individual probabilities of divorcing by age and gender listed in Table 2.3. This ensures we get for each period, age and gender a number of divorces that is independent from the target rate of married people. This also helps to have

plausible aggregate rates of divorced people by age and gender. We do not directly align divorces to an aggregate rate since it would make it more difficult to reproduce aggregate rates of people in a married or unmarried couple, which are our priority since they are central in computing family benefits. The micro-plausibility of divorces is ensured by a logistic divorce equation, studied in Appendix O's Equation O.1 and Table O.1. A quick summary of its findings is that men tend to divorce more often when they are not working and at younger ages in life. Meanwhile, women divorce the most at middle ages, when they work and have higher education levels.

Through divorce, we ended simulating people leaving marriage but did not reproduce the desired rates of married people by age and gender listed in Table 2.1. To partially reach them, this model relies on the marriage of common-law unions. We use an alignment by sorting procedure to select, among non-newly formed common-law unions, which couples get married. The micro calibration of the procedure relies on a logistic model that computes the propensity score men in a common-law union have of marrying their partner. After that, we first align simulated marriages on marriage probabilities by age and gender listed in Table 2.2. Then, we align the total number of married people on our civil status scenario listed in Table 2.1, but keeping in priority all previously married people that did not divorce or become widowed. This means we often exceed or fail to reach the required rates of married people by age and gender for the sake of micro-level consistency. Nevertheless, we will see in section 2.4.3 that we do not stray too far away from the desired aggregate rates of married people in our scenario. The full estimation of marriage equations is available in Appendix O's Equation O.2 and Table O.2. We find couples that have the highest probability of marrying are made up of middle-aged adults with high levels of education and little difference in age. The results also hint women tend to marry men of higher levels of education.

At this point of the marriage market module, we can move on to the simulation of people in a common-law union. Marriage is one of the ways people can leave a common-law union. The other way (discounting death) is breaking up. We model the breaking-up of unmarried couples in an analogous way to that of married unions. We adopt an alignment by sorting procedure, calibrated at the macro level on the quarterly probabilities of breaking-up by age and gender as measured in the EPHc (2003-2015) and listed in Table 2.4 (see section 2.4.1). This ensures we observe a total number of breakups by age and gender that is coherent with observed data. Couples are selected to break up in a plausible micro-level way by estimating break-up equations, which are analysed in full in Appendix O's Equation O.3 and Table O.3. Our main results are that the probability of

breaking up is the lowest for middle-aged adults with minor children where at least one of the members work. Couples where the woman is younger than her male partner also seem to break-up less often, and the opposite is true when the female partner is significantly older than her male counterpart, although these last two results are not verified when the model is estimated on men's probability of breaking up.

The matching procedure: simulating the formation of new couples

The last part of our prospective marriage market module is the simulation of new unions. Their first goal is to act as an adjustment variable for attaining the aggregate rate of people in a union as determined in our civil status scenario listed in Table 2.1. Their second role is to simulate new family links, as this is the only matching procedure in the model where the composition of future couples is determined, as we assume couples only get married after a period of unmarried cohabitation. The formation of new couples in our model is divided in two steps. First, we carry out an alignment by sorting procedure in order to select unmarried individuals without a known partner to transit into a common-law union. The micro-level plausibility of this selection is ensured by the estimation of logistic models that compute the propensity of single, divorced or widowed men and women of entering a common-law union. The macro-level consistency is ensured by aligning the aggregate people in a common-law union with our civil status hypotheses listed in Table 2.1. We then carry out a matching procedure in order to pair each man that is scheduled to enter a common-law union with a candidate woman.

The alignment by sorting procedure that determines who enters a common-law union is as follows. First, we compute for both men and women propensity scores of entering a common-law union through logistic behavioural equations. These are analysed in length in Appendix O's Equation O.4 and Table O.4. Our results show middle-aged adults with low education levels have the highest probability of entering a common-law union. Having minor children however significantly reduces this probability. Also, men that do not work have a lower probability of entering a common-law union, although this is not verified in the case of women. We however select in priority people that declare being married or in a common-law union but do not have a known partner in order to assign them a partner as soon as possible. Indeed, in the EPHc 6% and 3%³⁰ of people in a respectively unmarried and married union have no known partner. This can be due to an incorrect civil status declaration, the partner not being present in the household at the time of the

³⁰Source: own calculation on the EPHc (2003-2015) after identifying secondary family nuclei (see Section 1.2.3).

survey or the couple being part of secondary conjugal nucleus we could not detect through our algorithm described in section 1.2.3. The cost of doing this is we move some married people into a common-law union, but this allows us to avoid simulating a new matching model for creating married couples. Finally, we reproduce the percentages of people in a common-law union by age and gender taken from our civil status scenarios (listed in Table 2.1).

We next run a matching procedure to pair together these men and women transiting into a common-law union. The plausibility of these unions relies on logit equations run on the EPHc (2003-2015) on a population of men that are detected as entering a common-law union. We cannot however directly estimate these equations because we do not have a control group. We indeed can directly see what were the characteristics of couples that did form but by definition we do not know the characteristics of couples that could have been formed but did not form. We adopt the solution by Zinn *et al.* (2012) who also wanted to simulate first cohabitations through a logistic model in the MicMac microsimulation tool for the Netherlands (Zinn *et al.* , 2009)³¹. In order "to add information about controls (...), for each observed couple a synthetic couple was built by randomly assigning to each male spouse a female who was not his observed partner. The response variable was set to one in the case a couple had been observed. Otherwise, the response variable was set to zero" (Zinn *et al.* , 2012, p. 39). This way, we estimate our matching logit model on a dataset that is half observed newly-formed couples and half couples that were random rearrangements of these new unions.

The model is analysed in full in Appendix O's Equation O.5 and Table O.5. Our main result however is that couples are formed between individuals of similar age and education levels. It is a stylised fact that couples are formed between individuals of similar ages, and this result is for instance present in the logit model for first cohabitation estimated by Zinn *et al.* (2012). Also, couples where the man is significantly older than the woman are more common than those where the woman is the oldest, although the most common case is where there are few age differences between both partners. These matching equations also point to the existence of homogamy in Argentina, or the formation of couples within the same social class. This is a standard result in sociology, as shown in the case of France by the seminal work of Girard (1964), or more recently by Bozon & Héran (2006). The strongest evidence of this fact is that differences in education levels consistently diminish the probability of two individuals forming a couple. This result is also partially verified by the fact newly-formed couples where one of the partner does not work are less common

³¹The project can be accessed at www.micmac-projections.org.

than the reference case where both individuals work, although income differences do not seem to penalise the matching of two individuals.

After all these transitions in and out of married and unmarried unions are done, a last step in our model modifies the composition of households accordingly. Newly formed couples move to a new household. Divorces or break-ups lead to the man forming a new household and we assume minor children stay in their mother's household. Incidentally, we assume single individuals who turn 24 but still live with their parents move to a new household. The composition of households is relevant for the computation of family benefits, as their amount and conditions of accessibility are dependent on the household's labour income.

With this, we finish the presentation of our prospective marriage market module. We get as an end result civil status and family links for all future periods. We will now show in the following section that both our retrospective and prospective civil status modules allow us to accurately reproduce over the 1974-2040 period aggregate civil status values, be them historically measured (1974-2017) or part of our civil status scenarios (2017-2040).

2.4.4 Results: fitting our civil status simulations to historical data and to our scenarios

We will show in this section our prospective simulation of civil status follows the scenario listed in Table 2.1 at the aggregate level. We also show that despite not having actual scenarios, simulated percentages of single, divorced or widowed people are consistent with historical values observed between 1974 and 2017 and analysed in Figures 2.9a to 2.9c. We do not study aggregate civil status of our retrospective module since we gave priority there to the individual-level consistency of civil status over macro-level consistency. Figure 2.9, computed on people aged 16 or more, shows our model's performance.

We can see here our model closely reproduces desired aggregate levels of people in a common-law union and slightly overestimates married people. The moderate downward trend of people in a common-law union comes from population ageing, since young adults are those with the highest propensity to be in a common-law union as depicted by Figure 2.8b. The proportion of widows also slowly decreases, as a consequence of the halving in the proportion of married people witnessed between 1974 and 2014. These decreases are offset by a slight increase in the proportion of single people, particularly since 2030.

Figure 2.9: Comparing simulated and targeted civil status for people aged 16 or more, 1974-2040

(a) Both genders

(b) Men

(c) Women

Before the fourth quarter of 2014, the target rates are historically observed in the EPH surveys (1974-2014) and computed for all individuals aged 16 or more. Between the fourth quarter of 2014 and the first quarter of 2017, the target rates are derived from applying five-year age groups specific rates from the EPHc (2014-2017) to the population structure of the prospective simulation starting the fourth quarter of 2014. These are distinct from the actual rates measured in the EPHc during this period, as the population structure by age and gender differs from one EPHc wave to the other. After the first quarter of 2017, the target rates are discretionary scenarios.

In the end, we show our model is capable of simulating future civil status, the marriage market and thus family links in a micro-coherent way. It does so while also outputting aggregate civil status that respect our scenarios and is coherent with historical data. We will hence move on to our last module of our microsimulation model, simulating the education of our individuals.

2.5 Simulating education levels and age of exit from the education system

The last element of our prospective module that we will study in this chapter is the education module. We do not simulate education levels in our retrospective module because

we back-cast careers of working-age individuals, for which we already have an education level. We simply set an age of entry into the labour market that depends on their self-reported level of education, as explained in section 2.2.2. We cannot adopt this solution in our prospective module because we do not know, for surveyed students, minors or people that are not born yet neither their final education level nor their age of entry into the labour market. This education module provides thus a simple simulation of the secondary and tertiary education of our population, which will output both their attained education level and their age of entry into the labour market.

This education module works as follows. We first establish minimum and maximum ages of study for students of the EPHc. Then, starting from age 16, we determine for each student whether they successfully complete their studies. This also gives us their end of studies date, which is the year where they successfully complete their education or, on the contrary, drop out. These questions are answered with the help of an alignment by sorting procedure. First of all, we macro-calibrate our education module with the proportion of students by age and gender as taken from the EPHc (2010-2017) and listed in Table 2.5. We then present our simulation of secondary education, whose micro-coherence relies on exogenous probabilities of validating, repeating or dropping out of a given high school year. Finally, we simulate tertiary education, to which in our model we assume all people graduating from high school enter.

2.5.1 Establishing minimum and maximum ages of study for respondents of the EPHc

Before actually simulating future education, we need to first set an age after which it becomes possible for individuals to enter the labour market. We also force students in the EPHc older than a given age out of education and into the labour market. Finally, we need to determine the current year of education of self-reported students in the EPHc.

First, we made the arbitrary assumption that individuals could only enter the labour market starting from age 16 and that people below 16 are all (inactive) students. We also assume students aged 15 were in the 10th (out of 12) year of school, which ensures students may enter university starting from age 18. This is close enough to actual data, as 8%, 11%, 18%, 29% and 50% of people respectively aged 14, 15, 16, 17 and 18 surveyed in the EPHc (2003-2015) were not students. The *de jure* age of compulsory education has however changed throughout the 2003-2015 period, increasing from 16 to 18 after a

2006 education reform described in Appendix P. The impact of this reform in high school attendance is patent both in official data (seen by the fall in the percentage of people abandoning high school since 2006, listed in Table 2.6) and in the EPHc, as non-students represented respectively 5%, 8%, 16%, 25% and 46% of people aged 14, 15, 16, 17 and 18 in the 2013-2015 period. Still, schooling is *de facto* not universal at ages 16 or more even after the full implementation of the 2006 reform. It is thus reasonable to assume people can enter the labour market since age 16.

We additionally assume high school students can be up to 20 years old, and college students up to 29 years old. We thus force self-reported students aged 30 or more, as well as those aged 21 or more with incomplete secondary education, out of education. This is because we decided not to allow for people in our model to resume studies after having been in the labour market for the sake of simplicity. These restrictions are coherent with data from the EPHc, as only 3% of people aged 21 were high school students between 2014 and 2017, while only 2% of respondents aged 30 were university students³². We also assumed that tertiary education can take a maximum of 6 years. At the end of the sixth year, students enter the labour market with or without a university degree, as we will simulate in section 2.5.4. These age restrictions are however only applied for self-reported students in the EPHc. If simulated students in our prospective simulation model would complete secondary education after age 20 or college after age 30, there is no hard constraint in our model to make them drop out of education.

Finally, we determine the current year of study of self-reported students in the EPHc that fit the aforementioned age restrictions. This lets us know how far they have advanced in their studies and determines both the probable end of studies age and the likelihood they will actually complete their education. In the case of university students, we directly know from the EPHc (variable CH14) what their current university year is. The case of secondary students however is more complicated due to various educative reforms. We show in Appendix P how we identify the school year of secondary students with data from the EPHc for the later waves of the EPHc, some of which we input in our prospective simulation model (2014-2017).

³²Source: own calculation on the EPHc (2003-2017)

2.5.2 The macro calibration of our education module: students by age and gender

Our education module aims to reproduce aggregate rates of students by age and gender. The micro-calibration of the module ensures we get, for each education year, coherent proportions of students that validate, succeed or repeat that year. These ultimately determine the proportion of students that successfully graduate from secondary or tertiary education. The macro alignment on the other hand ensures we get a flow of students that enter the labour market that is coherent in their gender and age characteristics with actual values. To do so, we compute the proportion of students by age and gender in the EPHc for the 2010-2017 period, after the full implementation of the AUH. For the sake of simplicity, we make the hypothesis these rates, listed in Table 2.5 below, remain stable until 2040.

Table 2.5: Proportion of students by age and gender, 2010-2017 average (%)

Age	Men	Women	All
16	82.14	87.45	84.74
17	70.74	78.30	74.45
18	50.69	56.91	53.71
19	36.82	46.46	41.52
20	27.92	37.69	32.75
21	21.55	32.42	26.94
22	17.55	25.20	21.30
23	14.89	21.14	17.96
24	11.37	16.01	13.70
25	8.17	13.08	10.67
26	5.74	9.31	7.56
27	4.08	6.70	5.40
28	3.23	5.85	4.54
29	2.34	5.19	3.78

Source: author's calculations on data from the EPHc (2010 - first quarter of 2017)

As is standard in education literature, we see that education rates linearly decrease with age and that for any given age women are more likely to be students than their male counterparts. These influences of age and gender on the probability of being a student are (for the most part) absent in the secondary and tertiary education probabilities we

will review in Tables 2.6 and 2.7. Therefore, the macro-level alignment helps simulate transitions that are plausible in what concerns gender and age, so that students are more often young and female, as seen in Table 2.5.

2.5.3 Simulating secondary school completion

In order to simulate secondary education in a micro-coherent way, we use yearly probabilities of succeeding, repeating or dropping out of each school year, issued by Argentina's Ministry of Education. These are consigned in Table 2.6 below.

Table 2.6: Yearly probability of dropping out or repeating a high school year(%)

School year	Probability of dropping out					Probability of repeating the year				
	9 th	10 th	11 th	12 th	10 th / 12 th	9 th	10 th	11 th	12 th	10 th / 12 th
2003	13.39	17.51	13.74	27.19	18.89	9.80	10.29	7.44	1.03	6.86
2004	13.11	18.80	13.95	28.35	19.79	10.57	11.35	7.95	1.37	7.58
2005	13.53	19.65	13.43	26.42	19.44	11.64	12.14	8.20	1.37	8.07
2006	12.21	18.51	13.27	25.45	18.63	12.09	11.97	8.21	1.41	8.09
2007	10.67	19.21	12.95	22.54	18.02	10.76	11.34	7.43	1.54	7.62
2008	10.11	17.79	11.46	23.99	17.38	11.67	12.00	7.32	1.39	7.73
2009	11.51	17.05	10.90	18.48	15.48	12.23	11.59	6.84	1.32	7.41
2010	12.78	15.45	10.23	23.32	15.83	11.85	10.57	6.11	1.20	6.70
2011	11.36	15.05	10.43	23.63	15.83	12.72	10.83	6.14	1.21	6.79
2012	11.12	14.78	9.93	20.89	14.85	11.87	9.64	5.72	1.35	6.18
2013	12.23	13.93	9.28	21.71	14.51	12.16	9.90	5.86	1.59	6.35
2014	11.46	12.56	8.59	21.05	13.61	11.50	9.42	5.59	1.46	6.00
(2010-2014)	11.79	14.36	9.69	22.12		12.02	10.07	5.88	1.36	

9th year corresponds to the last year of middle school and 12th year to the last year of high school.
Source: author's calculations on data from DiNIEE (National Direction of Information and Statistics on Education), Ministry of Education (2003-2015). URL: <http://portales.educacion.gov.ar/diniee/indicadores-educativos/>

We can see the probabilities of repeating a year or dropping out tend to decrease over time for students in the 10th to the 12th year. Their evolution is slower or even stops

since year 2010, so we decided to use for our prospective simulations the average of probabilities computed between years 2010 and 2014. 2010 is also the year where the AUH was first implemented. This family benefit, as we have seen in section 1.1, is given to minor children of parents working in the informal sector under the condition of attending compulsory school, so it is a direct incentive for minors to attend school. By taking the average values for years 2010-2014, we thus work with a constant legislative framework. When we analyse these means, we see the probability of validating a high school year is constant at 75%, except for students in the 11th year for which it is ten percentage points higher. The probability of repeating a year however linearly decreases with school year, so the probabilities of dropping out of high school are highly dependent on the year of schooling.

The simulation of high school education is simple. On the one hand, we take every quarter a proportion $_{1/4}d_y$ of high school students that drop out without completing secondary education, with $y \in [1; 3]$ being high school year. This proportion is deduced from the yearly probabilities of dropping out d_y listed in Table 2.6, following the formula $_{1/4}d_y = 1 - (1 - d_y)^{1/4}$ demonstrated in Equation K.1, Appendix K. On the other hand, we carry out a number of transitions once every year. First, for individuals who just turned 16, and for whom we thus assume they were 10th year students, we see whether they enter the 11th year of high school, repeat their year or drop out, using the probabilities listed in Table 2.6 above. On the other hand, for students aged 16 or more that are already in the 10th, 11th or 12th year of study, we apply every four quarters (but not necessarily when they age) annual Table 2.6 probabilities of validating the high school year or repeating it. Students that validate the last (12th) high school year complete high school and move on to tertiary education.

Finally, every quarter, we sort students by the likelihood they leave education. Drop-outs serve as an adjustment variable, as we select only the number that is required to reach the desired aggregate rate of students by age and gender. Finally, those who repeat the year, validate it or graduate but move on to tertiary education are never selected to transit out of education, even if that means we do not respect the desired aggregate rate of students by age and gender for a given period.

2.5.4 Simulating entry to university and tertiary education

The last part of our education module concerns the simulation of tertiary education. We unfortunately lack detailed information on who (and at what age) enters university, after

how many years people graduate or the abandonment rates by year of studies. This simulation is thus essentially dependent on the macro coherence of our alignment by sorting procedure, which is ensured by the reproduction of the proportion of students by age listed in Table 2.5. We however make best of what micro-level information we have to add to the micro-coherence of our simulation of tertiary education.

First, we assume all high school graduates enter university. This is an unrealistic hypothesis, although *de jure* possible since Law 27204³³'s Art. 4 grants a "free and unrestricted" access to university for all those who successfully completed secondary education. Public university is moreover free of charges, which makes entering tertiary education easier. We however lack data on the proportion of high school graduates who choose to continue their education at higher levels, so the actual rate is unknown. The reason we make all high school graduates enter university is that it helps us replicate the number of new inscriptions to university we get from outside sources. Using data from the Ministry of Education's "Anuario de Estadísticas Universitarias" series (Mirás, 2013) and the 2010 National Census, we know these entries into university represented in 2010 58% of the population aged 18³⁴. Assuming all high school graduates enter university makes it so that, every year, new entrants to university represent 52% of people aged 18 as per our microsimulations. Since in our model all entries to tertiary education are made immediately after completing secondary education, and never at later ages, we can thus replicate a flow of entries into university that is consistent with actual data, although our newly enrolled students are most likely younger than reality.

Furthermore, we arbitrarily assumed graduation was possible at the fourth year of university's end. Most university students graduate after validating a bachelor, which usually takes a minimum of four years. This can however take longer as the university system is quite flexible: a student does not validate a year, but rather a number of courses that can be stretched over various years. We thus supposed students could take up to 6 years to validate a bachelor. We lack data on the average years it takes a university student to graduate, so we assumed students starting the fourth, fifth and sixth year of university have a 50% chance of validating the bachelor and entering the labour market. We finally assumed a student that enters the seventh year of university simply validates its bachelor and enters the labour market.

³³Issued the 11th of November 2015.

³⁴According to Mirás (2013), there were exactly 415,070 students that enrolled to either private or public university in 2010. For that year, the 18 year-old population was of 713,609 individuals according to the 2010 National Census. This means in 2010 new enrolments to University represented 58% of the population aged 18.

Finally, the central piece that makes our university simulation hold together is that each quarter, we randomly select university students that drop out and enter the labour market. We select just enough drop-outs to reproduce the proportion of students by age listed in Table 2.5, or measured in the EPHc until the first quarter of 2017. We however set a maximum number of students that drop out by applying probabilities computed with data from Mirás (2013) and listed in Table 2.7 below. This means we may exceed the desired number of students for a given age and gender, as students that are not selected to drop out as per the abandonment probabilities computed below stay in tertiary education.

Table 2.7: Yearly probability of dropping out of university, 2001-2012 (%)

Age	Men	Women	Women
2001-2002	16.63	17.43	16.03
2002-2003	17.82	18.62	17.21
2003-2004	16.20	17.03	15.57
2004-2005	16.77	17.59	16.16
2005-2006	15.52	16.31	14.93
2006-2007	18.51	19.29	17.92
2007-2008	15.22	16.07	14.58
2008-2009	14.99	15.85	14.33
2009-2010	14.99	15.85	14.33
2010-2011	12.43	13.32	11.76
2011-2012	16.43	17.23	15.83
2012-2013	16.55	18.10	15.38
Mean (2001-2012)	15.99	16.79	15.40

Source: author's calculations on data from Mirás (2013) and the "Anuario de Estadísticas Universitarias" series for years 2001 to 2013.

Computation example: in 2012 and 2013, there were $st_{2012} = 1,824,904$ and $st_{2013} = 1,830,743$ students in Argentinian universities. There were moreover $e_{2013} = 425,650$ enrolments and $g_{2013} = 117,719$ graduates in 2013. $st_{2012} - g_{2013}$ gives us the total of 2012 students that did not graduate in 2013, and $st_{2013} - e_{2013}$ the total number of 2013 students that were students in 2012 but did not graduate. As such, the number of 2012 students that dropped out between 2012 and 2013 $ab_{2012} = (st_{2012} - g_{2013}) - (st_{2013} - e_{2013}) = 302,092$. This means $\frac{ab_{2012}}{st_{2012}} = 16.55\%$ of 2012 students abandoned university without a degree between 2012 and 2013.

We can see the probability of dropping out of university did not significantly change over time, hovering around 17% for men and 15% for women. We thus take the 2001-2012 mean yearly probability of abandoning university as our only hypothesis for prospective

simulations. We hence get quarterly probabilities of dropping out for men ${}_{1/4}dr_{men} = 1 - (1 - dr_{men})^{1/4} = 4.49\%$ and for women ${}_{1/4}dr_{women} = 1 - (1 - dr_{women})^{1/4} = 4.09\%$. By applying our graduation hypotheses and ignoring students' deaths, we show in Appendix Q at least 37% of the male and 40% of the female students that entered university successfully graduate in our model, before taking into account the aggregate aspect of our alignment by sorting model.

In the end, this joint alignment by sorting procedure for secondary and tertiary education ensures we reproduce the desired proportions of students by gender and age. The available micro-level data also ensures we simulate these studies in a micro-coherent way. We will finally show how well our model reproduces the desired proportions of students by age and gender as listed in Table 2.5 and computed in the EPHc (2003-2017). We will also see what education levels by age our model outputs for younger or unborn cohorts, whose education is at least partially simulated by our model.

2.5.5 Result: simulated students and education levels up to 2040

As we explained earlier in section 2.2.2, our education module is vastly simplified in our retrospective simulations. As such, it is mostly relevant to ascertain the plausibility of our prospective simulations' education-related variables. We want to know in particular whether our prospective education module simulates proportions of students by age and levels of education that respect our scenarios laid out in Table 2.5. Indeed, an accurate simulation of the proportion of students by age results in coherent ages of entry into the labour market, which are relevant for the accumulation of retirement rights, access to family benefits and the simulation of social security contributions. Also, simulating plausible education levels for generations that enter the labour market after 2014 is important for estimating future careers due to their importance as an explanatory variable of both labour-market state and labour income.

The following figures show our prospective module simulates both of these variables in a satisfactory way. First, in Figures 2.10a and 2.10b we compare our simulated proportion of students by age to our desired age-specific scenarios listed in Table 2.5. We also represent proportions of students by age observed in the EPH (1980-2017) to put these prospective simulations in the context of historical data. We do not however simulate education levels through an alignment by sorting procedure, where we would aim to reproduce aggregate scenarios. Instead, simulated education levels are the end product of our education module, as explained earlier in sections 2.5.3 and 2.5.4. As such, Figure

2.11 compares simulated proportions of people of a given education level (2014-2040) with observed historical values (1974-2017).

Figure 2.10 shows our simulated proportions of students by age fluctuate around our education scenarios and are subjected to seasonality. This comes from the seasonality of our education module, as each new high school or university year starts during the first quarter of the year. It is thus only then where validation of the year, repeating it or graduating from high school / college may happen. This causes a temporary increase in the proportion of students during the fourth quarter followed by a decrease first quarter of the following year. If we take for instance students in the last year of high school, a significant proportion of them will be aged 18 during the fourth quarter, but the first quarter of the following year a low proportion of last year of high school students will be 18. Since not all students enter college, the probability of still being a student during the first quarter of the following year for people aged 18 decreases. Despite this small volatility, our model results in proportions of students by age that are stable, as per our education scenarios listed in Table 2.5.

On the other hand, Figure 2.11 below show our model simulates stables proportions of education levels up to 2040. This is a logical consequence from assuming probabilities to successfully complete high school or tertiary studies remain those respectively of the 2010-2014 and the 2001-2010 period. Also, since we simulate stable proportions of students by age, the end of studies age barely changes when compared to our last simulated periods. This also results in proportions of students that successfully finish secondary and tertiary education that do not stray away very much from those of the most recent years.

Chapter 2 conclusion: the blueprint of the first dynamic microsimulation model for projecting social security in Latin America.

All in all, this second chapter provides a thorough description of our dynamic microsimulation model for projecting social security benefits and contributions in Argentina. We adopted this methodology because it allows to simulate unit-level behaviour over time with vastly heterogeneous agents, here respondents of the EPHc household survey. This makes it possible to simulate separately each social security benefit and source of revenue, which allows for a policy impact evaluation of the various social security and retirement reforms that were undertaken in recent years. These elements also enable us to simulate not only social security's economic sustainability but also the benefits' adequacy

Figure 2.10: Comparing simulated proportions of students with target education rates (1980-2040)

(a) Ages 16 to 21

(b) Ages 22 to 29

Non-simulated student rates up until the first quarter of 2017 are taken from the EPH survey (1980-2017). After that date, we assume constant proportions of students by age taken from Table 2.5.

Figure 2.11: Comparing simulated education levels with historical proportions for people aged 16 or more (1974-2040)

Both genders

Men

Women

Source: EPH survey (1974-2017) (historical proportions).

and redistributive power, which may give an idea of the system’s political sustainability. The rest of the chapter gives a detailed account of our social security model. Made of a retrospective and a prospective module, which are themselves separated into various modules, it simulates all the elements necessary for determining individual social security contributions and access to the most important social security benefits (retirement benefits, survivor’s pensions and family allowances). These are past and future labour careers, family links and civil status and both education level and age of entry in the labour market, for which we respectively develop the labour-market, family and education modules. Finally, our simulation of births and deaths calibrated on INDEC’s 2010-2040 demographic projections ensures our simulated population follows expected demographic trends.

In the end, Chapter 2 gives us all the detailed individual-level information we need for projecting future social security income and benefits, and thus projecting social security

accounts and evaluating the most recent reforms. This will be the purpose of our final Chapter 3. But this chapter also has a relevance of its own. In particular, the calibration of its labour-market module is a contribution to the literature on informality, labour supply, the retirement decision and the determinants of labour income. Perhaps most importantly, it gives a detailed account on how to build a running dynamic microsimulation model for social security from scratch, using only data from a standard household survey and the free LIAM2 software. We hope this chapter, together with our model's code available on-line³⁵, will help future social scientists develop prospective models for social security systems (in particular for countries with incomplete social security data) and contribute to the growing microsimulation field.

³⁵We use the Zenodo archiving service for long-term preservation of our code. The DOI link is: [10.5281/zenodo.1420273](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1420273)

Appendices

Appendix J

The choice of the lower bound of our retrospective microsimulations: why go back up to 1955?

We will in this Appendix explain why we go as far back as the first quarter of 1955 in our retrospective module, even though we only have historical data up to 1974 for labour-market and civil status and 1970 for mean wages (see section 1.3). Before those dates, we simply extend the earliest available alignment values up to 1955. The cost of doing so is that we do not align past careers to historical aggregated values in the 1955-1973 period. We also increase our model's computation time from the initial 8 to 12 minutes.

There are three reasons why we stretch our retrospective simulations up to 1955. First, because if we stuck to historical values we would not be able to simulate a full career for the oldest working-age individuals of our dataset. Let's take for instance a man that was 64 in 2015, and thus was 23 in 1974. If he does not have a full secondary education, we assume in our retrospective model he started working when he was 16 (see section 2.2.2). As such, if we stop the simulation in 1974 we may be missing up to 7 years of contributions to social security. As we saw in section 1.1, earnings that go that far back in time are most of the time irrelevant for determining the pension's level. However, any validated year within these 7 years may be crucial for reaching the minimum 30 years of contribution to get a contributive retirement pension. Also, any additional year past the compulsory 30 increases the pension's replacement ratio by 1.5 percentage points. It is thus important we simulate full careers for all individuals who do not already earn a retirement pension, so at least for working-age individuals.

Moreover, there are two reasons why we stop at 1955 in particular. On the one hand,

because the pension moratoriums (see section 1.1) allow to buy back missing contribution years that may go as far back as January 1955 (see Appendix B). Back-casting careers up to that date therefore allows for a full simulation of moratorium pensions even for the oldest respondents. On the other hand, because 1955 is also the year when the oldest working-age individuals surveyed in 2003 (men aged 64) were 16, the age we assume individuals with low levels of education entered the labour market. Our model can thus also be used for simulating full individual careers for working-age respondents of the full EPHc survey (2003-2016). This is not something we do in our thesis, but we do so in our working paper on pension moratoriums (Calcagno, 2017) and may be done again in future work.

Thus, we need to work with careers up to 1955 to get full individual careers. The variable of interest for the 1955-1973 period is the number of validated years. This is because it has the most impact in determining access to and the level of pension. It also determines the amount of years to buy back in pension moratoriums (as seen in section 1.1). However, why not stop our model in 1974 and just assume a given percentage of validated years before 1974 (that may for instance replicate the percentage of individuals of a given age and gender contributing to social security in 1974)? The answer is that by running the model before 1974 we still discriminate between individuals of the same age and gender those who have the highest probabilities of being formal workers from those more likely to not having contributed to social security at the time. This helps further polarise between individuals that likely have long formal careers and those who barely contributed to social security in the past. Therefore, although we did not use historical values for the 1955-1973 period of our simulations, we can see here that it was necessary for our model to simulate full individual careers for EPHc respondents.

Appendix K

Life tables: conditional probabilities of death (2000-2040) and of giving birth (2010-2040)

Our microsimulation modelling relies on birth and death probabilities for simulating demographic changes in the future. It also uses death probabilities in the retrospective module as seen in Figure 2.2 and Section 2.2.1. In this Appendix we will explain how we compute probabilities of dying or giving birth at age x during a period of n years, which we respectively write down as ${}_nq_x$ and ${}_nb_x$. We will then present our data on deaths by age and gender for the 2000-2009 and the life tables we computed for that period. Finally, we will show the INDEC's population projection for 2040 life tables and age specific fertility and our computation of ${}_nq_x$ and ${}_nb_x$.

Computing the probability of dying or giving birth during the next n years for people of age x

In our prospective microsimulation module, we use conditional probabilities of dying or giving birth by age and gender to simulate birth and deaths each simulated quarter. We want the probability of dying at age x for the next n years ${}_nq_x$. We also want, for each woman of reproductive age, the probability ${}_nb_x$ she will give birth at age x during the next n years. By definition,

$${}_nq_x = \frac{{}_nd_x}{l_x}$$

where ${}_n d_x$ is the number of people that died at age x during the n years period and l_x the number of people aged x at the beginning of the period. Similarly,

$${}_n b_x = \frac{{}_n y_x}{l_x}$$

where ${}_n y_x$ is the number of children born in the n years period from a mother aged x . Typically, ${}_n y_x$ and ${}_n d_x$ are both known. We however do not know l_x , the population aged x at the beginning of the period. It is however standard when projecting and estimating total populations to work with mid-period figures. We thus have the number of individuals aged x ${}_n L_x$. From there, for a n -years period and a given age x , we get the central death rate ${}_n m_x = \frac{{}_n d_x}{{}_n L_x} = \frac{{}_n d_x}{{}_n L_x}$ with d_x the number of people that died at age x in a year. We also have the age-specific fertility rate ${}_n f_x = \frac{{}_n y_x}{{}_n L_x} = \frac{{}_n y_x}{{}_n L_x}$. It is commonly assumed deaths are linearly distributed during the n -years period, so ${}_n L_x = l_x - \frac{{}_n d_x}{2} = l_x - \frac{{}_n d_x}{2}$. As such, we can replace l_x in equation K.1:

$${}_n q_x = \frac{{}_n d_x}{{}_n L_x + \frac{{}_n d_x}{2}} = \frac{{}_n d_x}{{}_n L_x + \frac{1}{2}{}_n d_x} = \frac{2n \frac{{}_n d_x}{{}_n L_x}}{2 + n \frac{{}_n d_x}{{}_n L_x}} = \frac{2{}_n m_x}{2 + {}_n m_x}$$

with m_x the central death rate for age x in a period of one year ($n = 1$).

Finally, we adopt a quarterly step in our microsimulation model, so we look for a quarterly probability of dying ${}_{1/4} q_x$. It can be deduced from the yearly probability of dying q_x , as shown in Equation K.1 below.

$$(1 - {}_{1/4} q_x)^4 = 1 - q_x \leftrightarrow {}_{1/4} q_x = 1 - (1 - q_x)^{1/4} \quad (\text{K.1})$$

Equation K.1 is however computed differently for newborns (that is, when $x = 0$). If we work with $n \leq 1$, l_0 , we know the population aged 0 at the beginning of the period, which is the amount of births that happened in that period ${}_n b$. As such, ${}_n m_0 = \frac{{}_n d_0}{{}_n b}$. In the end, we can express the conditional probability of dying in a quarter for people of age x with data usually available in demographic projections. We can similarly express the conditional probability of giving birth ${}_n b_x$ as a function of available data:

$${}_n b_x = \frac{{}_n y_x}{{}_n L_x + \frac{{}_n d_x}{2}} = \frac{{}_n y_x}{{}_n L_x + \frac{1}{2}{}_n d_x} = \frac{2n \frac{{}_n y_x}{{}_n L_x}}{2 + n \frac{{}_n d_x}{{}_n L_x}} = \frac{2{}_n f_x}{2 + {}_n m_x}$$

where f_x is the age-specific fertility rate for the n quarters period. Again, the quarterly

probability of giving birth ${}_{1/4}b_x$ is:

$${}_{1/4}b_x = 1 - (1 - b_x)^{1/4} \quad (\text{K.2})$$

In the end, we respectively get in equations K.1 and K.2 conditional probabilities of dying and of giving birth in a given quarter. As seen in section 2.2.1 and Figure 2.1, we use death probabilities by age for the 2000-2040 period and probabilities of giving birth by age for the 2010-2040. We will thus lay out in this Appendix's following sections the computation of historical death probabilities (2000-2009) and projected birth and death probabilities (2010-2040).

K.1 Death probabilities for our retrospective module: computing life tables for the 2000-2009 period

We here work with yearly data and population estimations made by the Ministry of Health's Office of Statistics and Information on Health (DEIS) called Vital Statistics: Basic Information (DEIS, 2001-2010). Among a range of health-related information, we use estimations on mid-year population by gender and five-years age groups, live births by gender of the newborn and deaths by gender and age groups. The only limit here is that we have incomplete data for older ages: population projections and deaths by age are respectively lumped together beyond ages 80 and 85. We however allow in our projections a maximum age of 104, in line with INDEC projected deaths by age and gender. We thus want to divide the eldest population in DEIS (2001-2010) data in five-years age groups until the 100-104 age group. We first divide the population aged 80 or more in five-years age groups by respecting the population distribution by age and gender of the 2010 Census. We then take deaths by age and gender for people aged 85 or more in INDEC's population projections and replicate these proportions in DEIS (2001-2010) data. This way, we get population and deaths by gender divided in five-years age groups that cover ages 0 to 104. With this, we compute death probabilities q_x using equation K.1. Table K.1 shows the life tables we computed with DEIS (2001-2010) data for the 2000-2009 period, which give us conditional probabilities of death by age and gender.

Table K.1: Population, death and conditional death probabilities by age and gender, 2000-2009

Age-group x	Men			Women			Men			Women		
	P_x	d_x	q_x	P_x	d_x	q_x	P_x	d_x	q_x	P_x	d_x	q_x
	2000						2001					

Age-group x	Men			Women			Men			Women		
	P_x	d_x	q_x									
	Births: 360346			Births: 341394			Births: 349607			Births: 333677		
0	352571	6606	0.01817	339847	5018	0.01459	343526	6235	0.01768	330990	4838	0.02916
1-4	1425729	1006	0.00071	1380453	878	0.00064	1458174	1000	0.00069	1412010	793	0.00056
5-9	1738300	527	0.00030	1683500	384	0.00023	1760800	528	0.00030	1705400	419	0.00025
10-14	1697800	594	0.00035	1646800	397	0.00024	1719500	608	0.00035	1668000	413	0.00025
15-19	1671400	1789	0.00107	1625600	661	0.00041	1692400	1907	0.00113	1646300	776	0.00047
20-24	1695900	2520	0.00148	1665200	817	0.00049	1716900	2601	0.00151	1686300	819	0.00049
25-29	1417400	2326	0.00164	1399900	908	0.00065	1435000	2287	0.00159	1417400	880	0.00062
30-34	1237100	2259	0.00182	1228300	1083	0.00088	1252400	2329	0.00186	1243500	1094	0.00088
35-39	1154200	2582	0.00223	1164900	1431	0.00123	1168400	2631	0.00225	1179300	1446	0.00123
40-44	1062700	3603	0.00338	1115400	2114	0.00189	1075600	3443	0.00320	1129100	2061	0.00182
45-49	996900	5375	0.00538	1046200	3007	0.00287	1009000	5263	0.00520	1058800	3063	0.00289
50-54	873700	7650	0.00872	929100	4077	0.00438	883900	7681	0.00865	939900	4200	0.00446
55-59	741500	9860	0.01321	804600	5140	0.00637	750300	10176	0.01347	813700	5175	0.00634
60-64	625100	12705	0.02012	718800	6565	0.00909	632200	12921	0.02023	727000	6740	0.00923
65-69	535400	16305	0.03000	662200	9330	0.01399	541400	16420	0.02988	669300	9186	0.01363
70-74	433700	19876	0.04480	585800	13337	0.02251	438400	20383	0.04544	591900	13666	0.02282
75-79	290900	20451	0.06792	446300	17056	0.03750	294100	21026	0.06903	451000	17800	0.03870
80-84	130614	16165	0.11655	231502	19443	0.08060	131902	17248	0.12274	233840	20202	0.08282
85-89	60893	12234	0.18257	131012	18771	0.13370	61494	12816	0.18874	132335	20354	0.14282
90-94	17743	4885	0.24200	49136	10601	0.19474	17917	5117	0.24990	49632	11495	0.20757
95-99	3242	1263	0.32614	12433	4114	0.28393	3274	1323	0.33626	12558	4461	0.30166
100+	508	239	0.38034	1717	717	0.34540	513	250	0.39175	1735	777	0.36614
	2002						2003					
	Births: 356632			Births: 337868			Births: 356948			Births: 339500		
0	348937	6504	0.01807	336193	5159	0.01515	350795	6387	0.01773	337936	5095	0.01490
1-4	1476077	1045	0.00071	1429580	817	0.00057	1360570	974	0.00072	1315415	830	0.00063
5-9	1783444	502	0.00028	1727547	385	0.00022	1754822	516	0.00029	1697521	356	0.00021
10-14	1741445	616	0.00035	1689462	421	0.00025	1745039	558	0.00032	1690031	398	0.00024
15-19	1713522	1887	0.00110	1667017	703	0.00042	1677971	1722	0.00103	1630973	706	0.00043
20-24	1737941	2645	0.00152	1707234	826	0.00048	1648280	2292	0.00139	1618598	818	0.00051
25-29	1452455	2351	0.00162	1434881	900	0.00063	1554031	2219	0.00143	1541084	901	0.00058
30-34	1267631	2391	0.00188	1258804	1104	0.00088	1293434	2232	0.00172	1291119	1129	0.00087
35-39	1182709	2496	0.00211	1193852	1439	0.00120	1165501	2508	0.00215	1175048	1388	0.00118
40-44	1088601	3520	0.00323	1142728	2047	0.00179	1088836	3405	0.00312	1129756	2062	0.00182
45-49	1021048	5254	0.00513	1071295	2869	0.00267	1010099	5201	0.00514	1076282	3040	0.00282
50-54	894319	7993	0.00890	950692	4281	0.00449	923421	7919	0.00854	986033	4440	0.00449
55-59	758939	10540	0.01379	822921	5400	0.00654	788707	10659	0.01342	858216	5669	0.00658
60-64	639448	13398	0.02074	735184	6873	0.00931	654615	13546	0.02048	742370	6856	0.00919
65-69	547451	16545	0.02977	676659	9293	0.01364	539752	16696	0.03046	663580	9426	0.01410
70-74	443248	20794	0.04584	598163	13704	0.02265	436214	21176	0.04739	592511	13953	0.02327
75-79	297249	21578	0.07005	455632	17932	0.03860	307545	22702	0.07119	477498	18995	0.03900
80-84	133295	17815	0.12528	236142	20854	0.08458	151419	19658	0.12191	271405	22298	0.07892
85-89	62143	12885	0.18787	133638	20660	0.14351	70592	13903	0.17929	153594	22676	0.13749
90-94	18107	5144	0.24878	50121	11668	0.20853	20569	5551	0.23779	57605	12807	0.20008
95-99	3308	1330	0.33482	12682	4528	0.30297	3758	1436	0.32073	14576	4970	0.29132
100+	519	251	0.39013	1752	789	0.36768	589	271	0.37424	2013	866	0.35405
	2004						2005					
	Births: 376762			Births: 359239			Births: 365682			Births: 346164		
0	370620	5902	0.01554	356943	4651	0.01286	358818	5402	0.01466	345657	4088	0.01174
1-4	1328518	906	0.00068	1284456	739	0.00058	1334661	808	0.00061	1290062	728	0.00056
5-9	1746348	478	0.00027	1689265	352	0.00021	1738020	536	0.00031	1681084	365	0.00022
10-14	1752043	606	0.00035	1696785	395	0.00023	1755899	624	0.00036	1700418	401	0.00024
15-19	1693201	1599	0.00094	1644187	645	0.00039	1705978	1660	0.00097	1655417	706	0.00043
20-24	1634163	2178	0.00133	1601934	730	0.00046	1629984	2221	0.00136	1595394	766	0.00048
25-29	1606690	2023	0.00126	1592566	893	0.00056	1641925	2169	0.00132	1626318	869	0.00053
30-34	1328527	2084	0.00157	1326100	1068	0.00081	1367895	2062	0.00151	1365079	1027	0.00075
35-39	1177920	2332	0.00198	1185995	1381	0.00116	1195951	2295	0.00192	1202744	1329	0.00110
40-44	1103394	3203	0.00290	1136432	2008	0.00177	1117097	3174	0.00284	1144194	1980	0.00173
45-49	1015946	4959	0.00487	1085528	2926	0.00269	1024468	4963	0.00483	1094554	2953	0.00269
50-54	939933	7653	0.00811	1005001	4323	0.00429	953838	7622	0.00796	1021683	4235	0.00414
55-59	805839	10388	0.01281	879401	5617	0.00637	822699	10327	0.01247	899777	5499	0.00609
60-64	667183	13095	0.01944	754708	7089	0.00935	680458	13412	0.01952	768908	7075	0.00916
65-69	543376	15920	0.02888	666795	9240	0.01376	549019	16049	0.02881	672215	9146	0.01351
70-74	437005	20207	0.04519	594126	13429	0.02235	438837	19790	0.04410	596579	12977	0.02152
75-79	313741	22020	0.06781	486956	18532	0.03735	318893	21795	0.06609	494819	18740	0.03717

Age-group x	Men			Women			Men			Women		
	P_x	d_x	q_x									
80-84	156628	19396	0.11661	282176	22797	0.07765	161908	19598	0.11414	292926	22946	0.07538
85-89	73021	13443	0.16858	159689	22511	0.13168	75482	13597	0.16525	165773	22829	0.12884
90-94	21276	5367	0.22402	59891	12714	0.19191	21993	5429	0.21972	62173	12893	0.18790
95-99	3887	1388	0.30298	15154	4934	0.28000	4018	1404	0.29742	15731	5004	0.27442
100+	609	262	0.35415	2093	860	0.34078	630	265	0.34784	2173	872	0.33423
	2006						2007					
	Births: 360227			Births: 335675			Births: 363681			Births: 336631		
0	351054	5063	0.01396	338104	3911	0.01158	353184	5221	0.01425	340143	4063	0.01200
1-4	1345664	875	0.00065	1300418	715	0.00055	1353346	867	0.00064	1307445	745	0.00057
5-9	1727996	490	0.00028	1671186	402	0.00024	1715351	452	0.00026	1658704	351	0.00021
10-14	1756088	656	0.00037	1700416	427	0.00025	1753350	644	0.00037	1697534	462	0.00027
15-19	1717102	1669	0.00097	1665541	727	0.00044	1728405	1808	0.00105	1676197	742	0.00044
20-24	1637640	2211	0.00135	1600751	774	0.00048	1651069	2282	0.00138	1611770	802	0.00050
25-29	1653784	2220	0.00134	1636257	920	0.00056	1648462	2363	0.00143	1628588	965	0.00059
30-34	1417740	2109	0.00149	1414326	1079	0.00076	1477980	2269	0.00153	1473910	1118	0.00076
35-39	1219550	2501	0.00205	1225422	1417	0.00116	1247052	2582	0.00207	1252522	1420	0.00113
40-44	1128336	3208	0.00284	1151589	1915	0.00166	1137747	3311	0.00291	1158098	2007	0.00173
45-49	1036319	4970	0.00478	1102882	2900	0.00263	1050175	4973	0.00472	1110075	2950	0.00265
50-54	963891	7424	0.00767	1035677	4197	0.00404	970839	7804	0.00801	1047598	4344	0.00414
55-59	840039	10464	0.01238	919978	5620	0.00609	858209	11044	0.01279	940741	5954	0.00631
60-64	694800	13268	0.01892	785707	7433	0.00942	710473	14265	0.01988	805033	7708	0.00953
65-69	556954	15668	0.02774	679811	9122	0.01333	566698	17049	0.02964	688963	9920	0.01430
70-74	441346	19086	0.04233	599344	12589	0.02079	443870	19952	0.04396	601718	13299	0.02186
75-79	322568	21879	0.06560	500554	18405	0.03611	324995	23065	0.06854	504505	20082	0.03903
80-84	167381	19712	0.11122	303823	22801	0.07233	173103	21764	0.11829	314982	24828	0.07583
85-89	78034	13577	0.16006	171940	23139	0.12609	80702	15621	0.17649	178255	26179	0.13682
90-94	22737	5421	0.21302	64486	13068	0.18401	23514	6237	0.23419	66854	14786	0.19914
95-99	4154	1402	0.28873	16317	5071	0.26901	4296	1613	0.31610	16916	5738	0.29002
100+	651	265	0.33797	2254	884	0.32786	674	305	0.36900	2337	1000	0.35253
	2008						2009					
	Births: 383748			Births: 362318			Births: 382490			Births: 362225		
0	376413	5215	0.01350	362435	4111	0.01128	375936	5112	0.01328	362061	3901	0.01071
1-4	1343011	828	0.00062	1297164	685	0.00053	1355970	786	0.00058	1309178	692	0.00053
5-9	1702852	478	0.00028	1646325	368	0.00022	1693267	463	0.00027	1636738	400	0.00024
10-14	1748461	604	0.00035	1692542	424	0.00025	1742200	606	0.00035	1686208	409	0.00024
15-19	1738687	1917	0.00110	1686067	777	0.00046	1746747	1893	0.00108	1693831	806	0.00048
20-24	1667426	2462	0.00148	1625789	834	0.00051	1683868	2482	0.00147	1640145	876	0.00053
25-29	1634889	2512	0.00154	1612438	934	0.00058	1621994	2434	0.00150	1596933	1055	0.00066
30-34	1539324	2425	0.00157	1534430	1103	0.00072	1592477	2422	0.00152	1586480	1315	0.00083
35-39	1278518	2539	0.00198	1283852	1433	0.00112	1314010	2670	0.00203	1319219	1604	0.00122
40-44	1147736	3392	0.00295	1165910	1872	0.00160	1160710	3298	0.00284	1177209	2096	0.00178
45-49	1065054	4853	0.00455	1116842	2944	0.00263	1079970	4808	0.00444	1123897	3018	0.00268
50-54	976553	7722	0.00788	1058043	4291	0.00405	982902	7574	0.00768	1067611	4408	0.00412
55-59	876087	10689	0.01213	961119	5948	0.00617	892548	10825	0.01206	980163	5993	0.00610
60-64	726939	13777	0.01877	825773	7514	0.00906	743658	13824	0.01842	846815	7942	0.00933
65-69	577847	16438	0.02805	699728	9638	0.01368	590001	16465	0.02752	712161	9636	0.01344
70-74	446952	18618	0.04081	604490	12589	0.02061	451135	18421	0.04002	608445	12648	0.02057
75-79	326827	21746	0.06439	507479	18069	0.03498	328715	21242	0.06260	510281	17902	0.03448
80-84	178892	20405	0.10791	326148	23739	0.07023	184564	20675	0.10608	337067	23420	0.06715
85-89	83401	14772	0.16272	184574	24564	0.12478	86045	15302	0.16332	190753	24984	0.12292
90-94	24301	5898	0.21645	69224	13873	0.18215	25071	6110	0.21722	71542	14110	0.17953
95-99	4440	1525	0.29318	17516	5384	0.26643	4581	1580	0.29419	18102	5476	0.26276
100+	696	288	0.34303	2420	938	0.32482	718	299	0.34417	2501	954	0.32049

K.2 Our central scenario's demographic projections: birth and death probabilities by age and gender in INDEC's population projection (2010-2040)

Table K.1 depicts past death probabilities for period 2000-2009. They are used in our retrospective module, together with projected death probabilities for the 2000-2015 period. Their role is thus secondary as they only enter in the simulation of past civil status (see section 2.2.2 and Figure 2.1). Birth and death probabilities are however crucial in our prospective module as they determine the demographic evolution of the population over time. The resulting old-age and young-age dependency ratios show the dependent population's weight on working-age people, and play thus a substantial role in determining the sustainability of both the retirement and child benefits systems. In our central scenario, we use population projections by INDEC (2010-2040) to compute such probabilities. We use the projected mid-year population by age, number of deaths by age, age-specific birth rates and gross birth rate to compute both conditional probabilities of dying q_x and of giving birth b_x . The death by age and gender data was kindly sent to us by the INDEC, to whom we are grateful. Tables K.2 and K.3 respectively consign our computation of q_x and b_x in the 2010-2040 period. Both these variables are divided by 4 in our dynamic microsimulation model to get quarterly conditional probabilities of dying and of giving birth by age and gender.

Table K.2: Projected population, death and conditional death probabilities by age and gender, 2010-2040

Age-group x	Men			Women			Men			Women		
	P_x	d_x	q_x	P_x	d_x	q_x	P_x	d_x	q_x	P_x	d_x	q_x
	2010						2011					
	Births:		389207	Births:		373944	Births:		388713	Births:		373469
0	388555	4920	0.01256	373411	3784	0.01007	384749	4894	0.01251	370404	3784	0.01008
1-4	1450216	805	0.00055	1359358	658	0.00048	1481040	778	0.00053	1386769	633	0.00046
5-9	1794531	439	0.00024	1712604	331	0.00019	1796735	423	0.00024	1710605	315	0.00018
10-14	1801750	575	0.00032	1740204	399	0.00023	1797932	551	0.00031	1732199	369	0.00021
15-19	1797164	1833	0.00102	1762649	736	0.00042	1806648	1799	0.00100	1766990	718	0.00041
20-24	1674870	2444	0.00146	1671613	840	0.00050	1701340	2429	0.00143	1694250	813	0.00048
25-29	1575889	2417	0.00153	1590985	953	0.00060	1585381	2355	0.00148	1598787	919	0.00057
30-34	1540513	2425	0.00157	1571862	1198	0.00076	1556663	2385	0.00153	1586319	1170	0.00074
35-39	1334655	2604	0.00195	1376489	1515	0.00110	1379507	2621	0.00190	1420822	1508	0.00106
40-44	1149610	3267	0.00284	1198199	1955	0.00163	1174136	3257	0.00277	1222566	1948	0.00159
45-49	1076990	4707	0.00436	1135147	2954	0.00260	1084695	4645	0.00427	1142539	2909	0.00254
50-54	997584	7397	0.00739	1064838	4287	0.00402	1008281	7315	0.00723	1076575	4246	0.00394
55-59	898643	10737	0.01188	978428	6012	0.00613	910396	10663	0.01164	991791	5972	0.00600
60-64	765679	13986	0.01810	862890	7843	0.00905	782593	14049	0.01779	882230	7873	0.00888
65-69	594668	16600	0.02753	709898	9791	0.01370	612286	16773	0.02702	730331	9900	0.01346
70-74	444901	18689	0.04114	584129	12764	0.02162	453580	18731	0.04046	594038	12779	0.02128
75-79	324635	21512	0.06414	483396	18084	0.03672	327143	21356	0.06322	486376	17885	0.03611
80-84	202269	21918	0.10279	365167	26051	0.06888	204429	21772	0.10112	367253	25728	0.06768

For each year and gender, P_x is the mid-year population aged x , d_x the number of people that died aged x during that year and q_x the conditional probability of dying aged x in that year.

Age-group x	Men			Women			Men			Women		
	P_x	d_x	q_x	P_x	d_x	q_x	P_x	d_x	q_x	P_x	d_x	q_x
85-89	94299	15070	0.14799	206656	24268	0.11092	97160	15251	0.14554	213207	24530	0.10879
90-94	27476	6017	0.19738	77506	13706	0.16247	30245	6537	0.19506	83589	14534	0.15997
95-99	5020	1556	0.26837	19611	5319	0.23884	4851	1476	0.26409	19415	5129	0.23335
100+	787	294	0.31478	2709	927	0.29220	1001	361	0.30554	3644	1234	0.28960
	2012						2013					
	Births:	388092		Births:	372873		Births:	387337		Births:	372147	
0	384260	4731	0.01212	369910	3657	0.00976	383639	4565	0.01172	369290	3527	0.00943
1-4	1506389	760	0.00050	1410452	613	0.00043	1528142	734	0.00048	1431540	593	0.00041
5-9	1801192	407	0.00023	1710631	303	0.00018	1808975	395	0.00022	1713746	283	0.00017
10-14	1795551	532	0.00030	1725838	341	0.00020	1794434	505	0.00028	1720867	325	0.00019
15-19	1809575	1742	0.00096	1764945	690	0.00039	1807807	1699	0.00094	1758347	659	0.00037
20-24	1728135	2412	0.00139	1716459	803	0.00047	1753346	2388	0.00136	1736590	785	0.00045
25-29	1600602	2311	0.00144	1612356	887	0.00055	1620530	2272	0.00140	1630453	860	0.00053
30-34	1563298	2328	0.00149	1591036	1133	0.00071	1564398	2266	0.00145	1590032	1084	0.00068
35-39	1424979	2632	0.00185	1465595	1502	0.00102	1467827	2643	0.00180	1507564	1509	0.00100
40-44	1204662	3270	0.00271	1253022	1946	0.00155	1240281	3282	0.00264	1288614	1944	0.00151
45-49	1092116	4582	0.00419	1149467	2862	0.00249	1101131	4530	0.00411	1157884	2823	0.00244
50-54	1019205	7241	0.00708	1088298	4205	0.00386	1029958	7162	0.00693	1099614	4162	0.00378
55-59	921679	10583	0.01142	1004551	5929	0.00588	932661	10495	0.01119	1016836	5877	0.00576
60-64	797936	14071	0.01748	899708	7886	0.00873	811960	14067	0.01718	915644	7887	0.00858
65-69	631151	16970	0.02653	752391	10027	0.01324	650505	17178	0.02606	775093	10154	0.01302
70-74	464039	18853	0.03982	605897	12826	0.02095	476136	19031	0.03919	619734	12913	0.02062
75-79	330001	21209	0.06227	490244	17728	0.03552	333682	21099	0.06129	495228	17601	0.03492
80-84	206862	21648	0.09945	368784	25343	0.06644	209555	21559	0.09785	370427	24959	0.06518
85-89	99878	15406	0.14320	219640	24768	0.10675	102449	15537	0.14097	225581	24946	0.10479
90-94	32570	6944	0.19266	89089	15220	0.15740	34570	7253	0.18989	94105	15773	0.15465
95-99	5240	1548	0.25740	20407	5249	0.22791	5970	1729	0.25298	22275	5601	0.22337
100+	1071	385	0.30471	4160	1385	0.28542	1081	381	0.29965	4434	1454	0.28173
	2014						2015					
	Births:	386440		Births:	371285		Births:	385393		Births:	370279	
0	382878	4397	0.01131	368538	3392	0.00909	381964	4233	0.01092	367643	3255	0.00875
1-4	1545047	710	0.00046	1448836	571	0.00039	3188121	685	0.00021	1469961	552	0.00038
5-9	1820695	387	0.00021	1720580	268	0.00016	1837604	368	0.00020	1732481	255	0.00015
10-14	1794189	485	0.00027	1716783	303	0.00018	1794948	470	0.00026	1713583	289	0.00017
15-19	1803726	1648	0.00091	1749599	635	0.00036	1799127	1594	0.00089	1740503	605	0.00035
20-24	1774923	2366	0.00133	1752831	764	0.00044	1791102	2330	0.00130	1763709	741	0.00042
25-29	1643562	2235	0.00136	1651186	837	0.00051	1668640	2212	0.00132	1673206	820	0.00049
30-34	1565008	2203	0.00141	1588553	1045	0.00066	1568993	2144	0.00137	1590602	997	0.00063
35-39	1504230	2645	0.00176	1542857	1491	0.00097	1531313	2625	0.00171	1568522	1471	0.00094
40-44	1279832	3298	0.00257	1328055	1958	0.00147	1322258	3333	0.00252	1370228	1971	0.00144
45-49	1113955	4492	0.00402	1170187	2786	0.00238	1132249	4465	0.00394	1188129	2768	0.00233
50-54	1040062	7080	0.00678	1109938	4119	0.00370	1049173	6997	0.00665	1118932	4063	0.00362
55-59	943466	10406	0.01097	1028808	5824	0.00564	954332	10309	0.01074	1040676	5781	0.00554
60-64	825113	14041	0.01687	930510	7874	0.00843	837634	14008	0.01658	944632	7843	0.00827
65-69	669445	17368	0.02561	797308	10280	0.01281	687330	17520	0.02517	818174	10381	0.01261
70-74	489752	19257	0.03856	635567	13030	0.02029	504795	19532	0.03796	653336	13185	0.01998
75-79	338698	21074	0.06034	501634	17517	0.03432	345283	21130	0.05938	509702	17492	0.03374
80-84	212432	21485	0.09627	372752	24625	0.06395	215439	21422	0.09472	376016	24353	0.06273
85-89	104823	15629	0.13875	230626	25017	0.10289	107103	15698	0.13656	234703	24967	0.10100
90-94	36398	7512	0.18708	98876	16255	0.15191	38173	7748	0.18427	103573	16699	0.14920
95-99	6896	1960	0.24886	24616	6060	0.21920	7867	2203	0.24564	27227	6585	0.21576
100+	1073	371	0.29480	4657	1502	0.27774	1075	371	0.29433	4858	1543	0.27409
	2016						2017					
	Births:	384198		Births:	369131		Births:	382857		Births:	367843	
0	380890	4083	0.01057	366585	3143	0.00848	379663	3943	0.01025	365385	3034	0.00821
1-4	1552471	663	0.00043	1457763	522	0.00036	1549183	629	0.00041	1454615	502	0.00035
5-9	1864612	362	0.00019	1756909	245	0.00014	1889493	359	0.00019	1780082	232	0.00013
10-14	1797146	451	0.00025	1711561	274	0.00016	1801584	433	0.00024	1711583	255	0.00015
15-19	1795390	1545	0.00086	1732539	580	0.00033	1793078	1508	0.00084	1726202	560	0.00032
20-24	1800611	2295	0.00127	1767969	718	0.00041	1803625	2247	0.00125	1765877	696	0.00039
25-29	1695030	2184	0.00129	1695751	799	0.00047	1721706	2164	0.00126	1717836	782	0.00046
30-34	1578587	2104	0.00133	1598421	979	0.00061	1593874	2065	0.00129	1611962	949	0.00059
35-39	1547524	2590	0.00167	1583000	1436	0.00091	1554318	2543	0.00163	1587812	1399	0.00088
40-44	1366919	3372	0.00246	1414469	1989	0.00141	1412178	3407	0.00241	1459104	2012	0.00138
For each year and gender, P_x is the mid-year population aged x , d_x the number of people that died aged x during that year and q_x the conditional probability of dying aged x in that year.												

Age-group x	Men			Women			Men			Women		
	P_x	d_x	q_x	P_x	d_x	q_x	P_x	d_x	q_x	P_x	d_x	q_x
45-49	1156735	4472	0.00386	1212478	2764	0.00228	1187120	4498	0.00378	1242869	2769	0.00223
50-54	1057225	6913	0.00652	1126516	4016	0.00356	1064970	6827	0.00639	1133649	3966	0.00349
55-59	965405	10238	0.01055	1052602	5732	0.00543	976710	10168	0.01036	1064526	5690	0.00533
60-64	849667	13979	0.01632	958161	7828	0.00814	861250	13935	0.01605	971078	7798	0.00800
65-69	703822	17642	0.02476	837218	10469	0.01243	718924	17733	0.02437	854525	10528	0.01224
70-74	521180	19865	0.03740	673033	13381	0.01969	538648	20230	0.03686	694230	13610	0.01941
75-79	353449	21307	0.05852	519497	17544	0.03321	362996	21556	0.05767	530992	17645	0.03269
80-84	218529	21389	0.09331	380061	24168	0.06163	221851	21366	0.09188	384782	24030	0.06056
85-89	109415	15784	0.13455	238001	24880	0.09934	111904	15891	0.13259	240957	24724	0.09760
90-94	39951	7986	0.18173	108322	17137	0.14661	41676	8199	0.17911	113062	17569	0.14419
95-99	8800	2434	0.24299	29891	7125	0.21298	9634	2636	0.24069	32423	7611	0.21008
100+	1112	378	0.29055	5151	1614	0.27090	1238	414	0.28651	5637	1744	0.26794
	2018						2019					
	Births:	381365		Births:	366410		Births:	379718		Births:	364827	
0	378289	3798	0.00991	364043	2922	0.00794	376750	3664	0.00960	362548	2814	0.00768
1-4	1545155	610	0.00039	1450742	481	0.00033	1540533	578	0.00038	1446331	461	0.00032
5-9	1910645	345	0.00018	1800560	221	0.00012	1926816	340	0.00018	1817115	210	0.00012
10-14	1809332	420	0.00023	1714704	239	0.00014	1821015	406	0.00022	1721498	229	0.00013
15-19	1792030	1469	0.00082	1721209	544	0.00032	1791833	1428	0.00080	1717132	521	0.00030
20-24	1801939	2191	0.00122	1759248	667	0.00038	1797945	2136	0.00119	1750444	641	0.00037
25-29	1746826	2137	0.00122	1737845	762	0.00044	1768349	2109	0.00119	1753984	745	0.00042
30-34	1613810	2042	0.00126	1630031	925	0.00057	1636833	2016	0.00123	1650720	901	0.00055
35-39	1555594	2483	0.00159	1586891	1367	0.00086	1556369	2427	0.00156	1585502	1321	0.00083
40-44	1454862	3439	0.00236	1500972	2016	0.00134	1491146	3447	0.00231	1536188	2023	0.00132
45-49	1222518	4546	0.00371	1278344	2790	0.00218	1261819	4605	0.00364	1317642	2818	0.00214
50-54	1074291	6746	0.00626	1142244	3919	0.00343	1087301	6692	0.00614	1154658	3885	0.00336
55-59	987817	10094	0.01017	1076028	5642	0.00523	998296	10017	0.00998	1086568	5596	0.00514
60-64	872557	13886	0.01579	983551	7774	0.00787	883685	13824	0.01552	995724	7730	0.00773
65-69	732831	17781	0.02397	870372	10562	0.01206	745973	17805	0.02359	885197	10586	0.01189
70-74	556566	20606	0.03635	716011	13845	0.01915	574148	20963	0.03586	737347	14063	0.01889
75-79	373831	21874	0.05685	544232	17793	0.03217	385901	22249	0.05604	559228	18000	0.03168
80-84	225783	21390	0.09045	390360	23942	0.05951	230624	21481	0.08900	397084	23902	0.05844
85-89	114506	15996	0.13058	244021	24564	0.09584	117216	16121	0.12868	247512	24446	0.09412
90-94	43354	8403	0.17670	117558	17948	0.14185	44963	8586	0.17431	121598	18237	0.13952
95-99	10408	2807	0.23765	34866	8057	0.20715	11155	2968	0.23483	37285	8484	0.20430
100+	1428	475	0.28520	6298	1918	0.26430	1662	541	0.27995	7075	2127	0.26135
	2020						2021					
	Births:	377911		Births:	363091		Births:	376556		Births:	361789	
0	375052	3530	0.00930	360894	2713	0.00744	373797	3406	0.00900	359667	2620	0.00722
1-4	1535511	554	0.00036	1441532	440	0.00031	1529521	534	0.00035	1435828	413	0.00029
5-9	1935823	329	0.00017	1827582	204	0.00011	1932305	322	0.00017	1824132	195	0.00011
10-14	1837895	392	0.00021	1733376	218	0.00013	1864856	383	0.00021	1757750	211	0.00012
15-19	1792617	1390	0.00078	1713908	495	0.00029	1794858	1358	0.00076	1711879	483	0.00028
20-24	1793445	2084	0.00116	1741317	620	0.00036	1789776	2033	0.00114	1733273	595	0.00034
25-29	1784486	2073	0.00116	1764757	721	0.00041	1794010	2033	0.00113	1768941	697	0.00039
30-34	1661873	1993	0.00120	1672670	882	0.00053	1688207	1983	0.00117	1695145	869	0.00051
35-39	1560497	2378	0.00152	1587623	1281	0.00081	1570184	2336	0.00149	1595472	1253	0.00079
40-44	1518223	3443	0.00227	1561851	2016	0.00129	1534504	3415	0.00222	1576380	1997	0.00127
45-49	1303929	4672	0.00358	1359623	2854	0.00210	1348259	4746	0.00351	1403688	2889	0.00206
50-54	1105664	6659	0.00600	1172654	3861	0.00329	1130091	6679	0.00589	1196946	3874	0.00323
55-59	1007802	9923	0.00980	1095777	5539	0.00504	1016281	9840	0.00964	1103603	5479	0.00495
60-64	894882	13769	0.01527	1007778	7690	0.00760	906232	13736	0.01504	1019890	7665	0.00749
65-69	758547	17810	0.02321	899331	10594	0.01171	770680	17821	0.02286	912903	10611	0.01156
70-74	590824	21271	0.03537	757455	14259	0.01865	606352	21549	0.03492	775868	14430	0.01843
75-79	399139	22679	0.05525	575975	18246	0.03118	413472	23182	0.05454	594442	18557	0.03074
80-84	236567	21667	0.08758	405126	23935	0.05739	243602	21975	0.08632	414554	24079	0.05644
85-89	119991	16244	0.12679	251592	24386	0.09245	122829	16394	0.12512	256161	24411	0.09096
90-94	46560	8757	0.17191	125138	18449	0.13731	48175	8928	0.16961	128302	18609	0.13523
95-99	11906	3127	0.23215	39738	8890	0.20121	12686	3289	0.22951	42270	9323	0.19865
100+	1899	612	0.27755	7934	2348	0.25780	2141	683	0.27513	8835	2580	0.25481
	2022						2023					
	Births:	375060		Births:	360351		Births:	373420		Births:	358777	
0	372391	3295	0.00875	358305	2527	0.00699	370847	3177	0.00847	356798	2443	0.00679
1-4	1523234	510	0.00033	1429849	402	0.00028	1516845	495	0.00033	1423761	384	0.00027

For each year and gender, P_x is the mid-year population aged x , d_x the number of people that died aged x during that year and q_x the conditional probability of dying aged x in that year.

Age-group x	Men			Women			Men			Women		
	P_x	d_x	q_x	P_x	d_x	q_x	P_x	d_x	q_x	P_x	d_x	q_x
5-9	1927829	314	0.00016	1819781	183	0.00010	1922442	297	0.00015	1814579	176	0.00010
10-14	1889665	375	0.00020	1780891	203	0.00011	1910781	367	0.00019	1801321	191	0.00011
15-19	1799318	1329	0.00074	1711871	462	0.00027	1807060	1299	0.00072	1714977	452	0.00026
20-24	1787527	1983	0.00111	1726877	577	0.00033	1786530	1947	0.00109	1721807	551	0.00032
25-29	1797074	1986	0.00110	1766751	675	0.00038	1795440	1937	0.00108	1760050	651	0.00037
30-34	1714814	1969	0.00115	1717162	853	0.00050	1739884	1951	0.00112	1737087	841	0.00048
35-39	1585523	2309	0.00146	1609026	1231	0.00076	1605466	2282	0.00142	1627091	1209	0.00074
40-44	1541466	3363	0.00218	1581282	1963	0.00124	1542954	3306	0.00214	1580461	1921	0.00121
45-49	1393195	4824	0.00346	1448119	2925	0.00202	1435581	4895	0.00340	1489841	2959	0.00198
50-54	1160244	6728	0.00578	1227215	3903	0.00318	1195310	6794	0.00567	1262490	3939	0.00312
55-59	1024448	9747	0.00947	1111001	5424	0.00487	1034140	9678	0.00931	1119802	5375	0.00479
60-64	917812	13702	0.01482	1031977	7634	0.00737	929171	13658	0.01459	1043663	7605	0.00726
65-69	782388	17818	0.02252	925866	10612	0.01140	793873	17804	0.02218	938435	10605	0.01124
70-74	620705	21786	0.03449	792710	14563	0.01820	634027	21963	0.03405	808178	14671	0.01799
75-79	428705	23713	0.05382	614243	18912	0.03032	444303	24279	0.05319	634556	19262	0.02990
80-84	251592	22364	0.08511	425309	24299	0.05555	260490	22801	0.08386	437492	24590	0.05467
85-89	125828	16538	0.12333	261181	24462	0.08947	129213	16726	0.12158	266788	24556	0.08799
90-94	49884	9125	0.16760	131324	18735	0.13316	51661	9318	0.16545	134418	18855	0.13108
95-99	13448	3443	0.22697	44842	9739	0.19591	14216	3590	0.22422	47338	10133	0.19336
100+	2388	751	0.27176	9770	2820	0.25224	2647	828	0.27050	10767	3066	0.24927
	2024						2025					
	Births:		371638	Births:		357064	Births:		369711	Births:		355213
0	369144	3078	0.00825	356798	2362	0.00659	367302	2974	0.00801	353371	2274	0.00638
1-4	1510567	468	0.00031	1423761	365	0.00026	1504609	452	0.00030	1412151	351	0.00025
5-9	1916301	290	0.00015	1814579	163	0.00009	1909590	279	0.00015	1802211	155	0.00009
10-14	1926898	367	0.00019	1801321	192	0.00011	1935874	353	0.00018	1828245	184	0.00010
15-19	1818746	1272	0.00070	1714977	436	0.00025	1835598	1253	0.00068	1733547	424	0.00024
20-24	1786362	1904	0.00107	1721807	533	0.00031	1787171	1865	0.00104	1714352	518	0.00030
25-29	1791510	1882	0.00105	1760050	625	0.00036	1787061	1832	0.00102	1741935	599	0.00034
30-34	1761368	1931	0.00110	1737087	822	0.00047	1777507	1900	0.00107	1763866	802	0.00045
35-39	1628483	2262	0.00139	1627091	1192	0.00073	1653466	2255	0.00136	1669679	1177	0.00070
40-44	1543937	3242	0.00210	1580461	1881	0.00119	1548254	3181	0.00205	1581415	1843	0.00116
45-49	1471659	4939	0.00335	1489841	2979	0.00200	1498635	4954	0.00330	1550541	2981	0.00192
50-54	1234189	6893	0.00557	1262490	3993	0.00316	1275832	6996	0.00547	1343261	4048	0.00301
55-59	1047404	9621	0.00914	1119802	5337	0.00475	1065823	9614	0.00898	1150395	5321	0.00461
60-64	939917	13613	0.01438	1043663	7562	0.00722	949753	13549	0.01416	1063820	7516	0.00704
65-69	805169	17784	0.02185	938435	10593	0.01122	816528	17759	0.02152	962862	10577	0.01092
70-74	646725	22112	0.03362	808178	14749	0.01808	658920	22244	0.03320	836656	14814	0.01755
75-79	459642	24797	0.05253	634556	19615	0.03044	474305	25269	0.05189	673300	19914	0.02915
80-84	270309	23315	0.08269	437492	24927	0.05540	280985	23880	0.08152	466205	25340	0.05292
85-89	133142	16981	0.11989	266788	24714	0.08853	137737	17293	0.11813	280531	24940	0.08512
90-94	53495	9513	0.16331	134418	18997	0.13200	55369	9707	0.16119	141458	19173	0.12694
95-99	14974	3733	0.22167	47338	10478	0.19929	15741	3882	0.21955	51829	10781	0.18841
100+	2905	900	0.26826	10767	3324	0.26744	3182	977	0.26618	12888	3583	0.24408
	2026						2027					
	Births:		368867	Births:		354402	Births:		367910	Births:		353482
0	366536	2878	0.00777	352613	2209	0.00621	365644	2797	0.00757	351747	2142	0.00604
1-4	1497885	433	0.00029	1405756	338	0.00024	1491688	418	0.00028	1399863	324	0.00023
5-9	1902354	268	0.00014	1795276	150	0.00008	1894674	259	0.00014	1787919	145	0.00008
10-14	1932316	346	0.00018	1824753	171	0.00009	1927789	329	0.00017	1820359	159	0.00009
15-19	1862511	1247	0.00067	1757860	419	0.00024	1887280	1240	0.00066	1780938	418	0.00023
20-24	1789425	1828	0.00102	1712227	502	0.00029	1793875	1799	0.00100	1712119	487	0.00028
25-29	1783436	1787	0.00100	1733812	575	0.00033	1781206	1740	0.00098	1727307	555	0.00032
30-34	1787051	1870	0.00105	1767997	784	0.00044	1790168	1833	0.00102	1765768	756	0.00043
35-39	1679754	2241	0.00133	1692096	1165	0.00069	1706312	2235	0.00131	1714068	1160	0.00068
40-44	1558067	3149	0.00202	1589333	1815	0.00114	1573467	3120	0.00198	1602916	1791	0.00112
45-49	1514973	4939	0.00325	1565116	2962	0.00189	1522118	4891	0.00321	1570128	2927	0.00186
50-54	1319652	7122	0.00538	1387040	4114	0.00296	1364066	7241	0.00529	1431166	4178	0.00292
55-59	1090070	9658	0.00882	1174581	5350	0.00454	1119854	9770	0.00869	1204668	5395	0.00447
60-64	958606	13496	0.01398	1071925	7466	0.00694	967154	13425	0.01379	1079571	7417	0.00685
65-69	828028	17754	0.02121	975052	10576	0.01079	839715	17754	0.02092	987228	10574	0.01065
70-74	670755	22381	0.03282	850042	14882	0.01736	682207	22485	0.03242	862874	14934	0.01716
75-79	488032	25710	0.05133	690650	20193	0.02882	500899	26102	0.05079	706619	20415	0.02848
80-84	292507	24527	0.08048	482717	25846	0.05215	304677	25203	0.07943	500325	26400	0.05141
For each year and gender, P_x is the mid-year population aged x , d_x the number of people that died aged x during that year and q_x the conditional probability of dying aged x in that year.												

Age-group x	Men			Women			Men			Women		
	P_x	d_x	q_x									
85-89	142996	17708	0.11662	288835	25275	0.08384	148823	18181	0.11513	298088	25683	0.08260
90-94	57296	9916	0.15928	145427	19409	0.12511	59339	10140	0.15743	149640	19661	0.12329
95-99	16521	4029	0.21737	53860	11057	0.18618	17355	4180	0.21497	55892	11323	0.18395
100+	3480	1054	0.26304	14049	3863	0.24173	3765	1133	0.26157	15246	4146	0.23939
	2028						2029					
	Births: 366839			Births: 352453			Births: 365655			Births: 351316		
0	364643	2711	0.00736	350770	2078	0.00588	363523	2632	0.00717	349677	2023	0.00574
1-4	1486143	404	0.00027	1394583	311	0.00022	1481317	385	0.00026	1390011	293	0.00021
5-9	1886740	250	0.00013	1780309	135	0.00008	1878765	244	0.00013	1772695	131	0.00007
10-14	1922363	324	0.00017	1815110	150	0.00008	1916185	313	0.00016	1809155	147	0.00008
15-19	1908349	1226	0.00064	1801310	413	0.00023	1924412	1211	0.00063	1817736	403	0.00022
20-24	1801565	1770	0.00098	1715106	473	0.00028	1813216	1751	0.00097	1721733	461	0.00027
25-29	1780238	1695	0.00095	1722130	539	0.00031	1780048	1654	0.00093	1717868	518	0.00030
30-34	1788608	1798	0.00100	1759036	735	0.00042	1784758	1755	0.00098	1750111	713	0.00041
35-39	1731330	2225	0.00128	1733951	1139	0.00066	1752786	2210	0.00126	1749976	1119	0.00064
40-44	1593433	3099	0.00194	1620978	1779	0.00110	1616434	3087	0.00191	1641608	1769	0.00108
45-49	1523853	4836	0.00317	1569478	2877	0.00183	1525096	4761	0.00312	1568405	2826	0.00180
50-54	1405982	7339	0.00521	1472618	4237	0.00287	1441718	7417	0.00513	1507520	4281	0.00284
55-59	1154377	9907	0.00855	1239646	5461	0.00440	1192579	10076	0.00841	1278316	5543	0.00433
60-64	977147	13371	0.01359	1088593	7370	0.00675	990550	13354	0.01339	1101286	7345	0.00665
65-69	851196	17745	0.02063	999009	10570	0.01052	862094	17727	0.02035	1009868	10551	0.01039
70-74	693489	22590	0.03205	875337	14973	0.01696	704602	22678	0.03168	887533	15007	0.01677
75-79	512936	26424	0.05022	721390	20595	0.02815	524489	26705	0.04965	735359	20738	0.02781
80-84	317140	25896	0.07845	518351	26959	0.05069	329461	26565	0.07751	536063	27495	0.05001
85-89	155234	18709	0.11367	308368	26158	0.08138	162247	19286	0.11220	319691	26700	0.08017
90-94	61591	10384	0.15549	154229	19962	0.12156	64120	10667	0.15358	159331	20302	0.11979
95-99	18221	4337	0.21271	57971	11580	0.18162	19117	4498	0.21052	60188	11856	0.17932
100+	4067	1213	0.25955	16467	4425	0.23689	4366	1292	0.25778	17665	4693	0.23452
	2030						2031					
	Births: 364359			Births: 350070			Births: 363867			Births: 349598		
0	362291	2553	0.00698	348485	1957	0.00557	361850	2490	0.00682	348054	1906	0.00544
1-4	1477271	371	0.00025	1386148	285	0.00021	1472967	361	0.00025	1382028	278	0.00020
5-9	1870956	242	0.00013	1765235	125	0.00007	1863441	233	0.00013	1758054	120	0.00007
10-14	1909433	299	0.00016	1802640	142	0.00008	1902159	284	0.00015	1795653	127	0.00007
15-19	1933338	1191	0.00062	1828095	390	0.00021	1929768	1167	0.00060	1824532	387	0.00021
20-24	1829977	1732	0.00095	1733433	454	0.00026	1856763	1729	0.00093	1757615	448	0.00025
25-29	1780865	1622	0.00091	1714447	502	0.00029	1783093	1594	0.00089	1712188	479	0.00028
30-34	1780365	1709	0.00096	1740835	686	0.00039	1776796	1670	0.00094	1732666	669	0.00039
35-39	1768927	2192	0.00124	1760660	1109	0.00063	1778502	2162	0.00121	1764785	1084	0.00061
40-44	1641383	3083	0.00188	1663528	1758	0.00106	1667624	3083	0.00185	1685899	1756	0.00104
45-49	1529635	4693	0.00306	1570718	2776	0.00177	1539590	4658	0.00302	1578744	2748	0.00174
50-54	1468530	7444	0.00506	1533063	4291	0.00280	1484917	7436	0.00500	1547665	4277	0.00276
55-59	1233484	10257	0.00828	1319629	5633	0.00426	1276485	10461	0.00816	1362983	5736	0.00420
60-64	1008817	13399	0.01319	1119299	7349	0.00654	1032637	13529	0.01302	1143294	7406	0.00646
65-69	872137	17694	0.02008	1019469	10520	0.01027	881264	17662	0.01984	1027776	10486	0.01015
70-74	715777	22760	0.03130	899613	15036	0.01658	727061	22874	0.03097	911730	15084	0.01641
75-79	535672	26961	0.04910	748774	20860	0.02748	546565	27223	0.04860	761723	20988	0.02718
80-84	341314	27179	0.07658	552880	27972	0.04934	352552	27753	0.07574	568520	28413	0.04876
85-89	169825	19911	0.11075	332159	27309	0.07897	177978	20623	0.10953	345682	28027	0.07792
90-94	67007	11000	0.15171	164994	20690	0.11800	70234	11387	0.14997	171255	21184	0.11649
95-99	20035	4659	0.20832	62578	12167	0.17720	20997	4835	0.20650	65113	12501	0.17517
100+	4690	1371	0.25505	18854	4948	0.23200	5024	1455	0.25298	20050	5207	0.22985
	2032						2033					
	Births: 363281			Births: 349035			Births: 362602			Births: 348383		
0	361323	2418	0.00663	347535	1852	0.00529	360693	2357	0.00648	346921	1804	0.00516
1-4	1469131	355	0.00024	1378385	268	0.00019	1465784	341	0.00023	1375187	261	0.00019
5-9	1856330	221	0.00012	1751251	111	0.00006	1849773	217	0.00012	1744962	108	0.00006
10-14	1894432	280	0.00015	1788232	129	0.00007	1886437	274	0.00015	1780561	125	0.00007
15-19	1925245	1143	0.00059	1820097	375	0.00021	1919806	1113	0.00058	1814790	357	0.00020
20-24	1881401	1724	0.00092	1780524	439	0.00025	1902364	1712	0.00090	1800779	436	0.00024
25-29	1787506	1562	0.00087	1711950	468	0.00027	1795098	1536	0.00086	1714781	461	0.00027
30-34	1774595	1637	0.00092	1726108	641	0.00037	1773682	1604	0.00090	1720853	628	0.00036
35-39	1781679	2125	0.00119	1762558	1065	0.00060	1780194	2091	0.00117	1755835	1033	0.00059
40-44	1694131	3085	0.00182	1707843	1751	0.00102	1719102	3082	0.00179	1727688	1742	0.00101

For each year and gender, P_x is the mid-year population aged x , d_x the number of people that died aged x during that year and q_x the conditional probability of dying aged x in that year.

Age-group x	Men			Women			Men			Women		
	P_x	d_x	q_x	P_x	d_x	q_x	P_x	d_x	q_x	P_x	d_x	q_x
45-49	1555051	4634	0.00298	1592364	2732	0.00171	1575023	4638	0.00294	1610437	2719	0.00169
50-54	1492307	7374	0.00493	1552838	4237	0.00272	1494377	7268	0.00485	1552408	4179	0.00269
55-59	1320078	10673	0.00805	1406665	5841	0.00414	1361266	10868	0.00795	1447712	5931	0.00409
60-64	1061662	13729	0.01285	1173033	7493	0.00637	1095187	13978	0.01268	1207542	7618	0.00629
65-69	890118	17614	0.01959	1035653	10446	0.01004	900323	17587	0.01935	1044857	10408	0.00991
70-74	738515	22985	0.03065	923817	15125	0.01624	749753	23082	0.03032	935515	15163	0.01608
75-79	557152	27462	0.04810	774166	21094	0.02688	567615	27693	0.04763	786294	21186	0.02659
80-84	363197	28271	0.07492	583074	28781	0.04817	373296	28719	0.07408	596676	29078	0.04757
85-89	186585	21357	0.10827	360018	28799	0.07692	195373	22106	0.10709	374665	29575	0.07594
90-94	73758	11821	0.14838	178113	21728	0.11498	77619	12297	0.14680	185627	22332	0.11348
95-99	22009	5016	0.20459	67778	12849	0.17316	23135	5212	0.20248	70642	13231	0.17126
100+	5380	1544	0.25098	21274	5473	0.22794	5745	1634	0.24901	22553	5744	0.22592
	2034						2035					
	Births:		361831	Births:		347641	Births:		360967	Births:		346812
0	359975	2291	0.00631	346218	1757	0.00504	359157	2235	0.00617	345423	1714	0.00493
1-4	1462917	333	0.00023	1372447	248	0.00018	1460523	325	0.00022	1370171	242	0.00018
5-9	1843794	207	0.00011	1739258	111	0.00006	1838495	198	0.00011	1734159	98	0.00006
10-14	1878422	267	0.00014	1772890	116	0.00007	1870555	256	0.00014	1765362	110	0.00006
15-19	1913610	1092	0.00057	1808782	347	0.00019	1906838	1071	0.00056	1802187	340	0.00019
20-24	1918330	1699	0.00089	1817044	430	0.00024	1927175	1679	0.00087	1827285	424	0.00023
25-29	1806656	1512	0.00084	1721268	443	0.00026	1823295	1497	0.00082	1732793	437	0.00025
30-34	1773503	1575	0.00089	1716530	615	0.00036	1774317	1540	0.00087	1713034	587	0.00034
35-39	1776424	2049	0.00115	1746897	1002	0.00057	1772119	2009	0.00113	1737635	983	0.00057
40-44	1740522	3074	0.00176	1743705	1734	0.00099	1756679	3058	0.00174	1754377	1718	0.00098
45-49	1597974	4630	0.00289	1631048	2717	0.00166	1622867	4647	0.00286	1652935	2711	0.00164
50-54	1496011	7182	0.00479	1551564	4112	0.00265	1500839	7084	0.00471	1554073	4060	0.00261
55-59	1396428	11001	0.00785	1482327	6001	0.00404	1422961	11079	0.00776	1507729	6021	0.00399
60-64	1132229	14267	0.01252	1245629	7752	0.00620	1171834	14581	0.01237	1286323	7909	0.00613
65-69	913681	17610	0.01909	1057594	10409	0.00979	931555	17714	0.01884	1075441	10453	0.00967
70-74	760474	23171	0.03001	946350	15179	0.01591	770395	23218	0.02969	955985	15175	0.01575
75-79	577943	27898	0.04713	798187	21264	0.02629	588344	28107	0.04666	809967	21341	0.02601
80-84	383058	29134	0.07327	609631	29343	0.04700	392584	29511	0.07245	622160	29556	0.04640
85-89	204129	22828	0.10591	389111	30310	0.07498	212632	23516	0.10480	402956	30995	0.07407
90-94	81829	12808	0.14516	193830	23006	0.11204	86356	13356	0.14356	202788	23740	0.11059
95-99	24363	5432	0.20060	73776	13644	0.16928	25753	5680	0.19865	77211	14096	0.16729
100+	6129	1733	0.24773	23886	6022	0.22389	6533	1828	0.24547	25287	6311	0.22189
	2036						2037					
	Births:		360643	Births:		346500	Births:		360237	Births:		346110
0	358874	2184	0.00604	345148	1669	0.00481	358508	2135	0.00591	344791	1629	0.00470
1-4	1457857	312	0.00021	1367607	236	0.00017	1455435	301	0.00021	1365284	231	0.00017
5-9	1833711	197	0.00011	1729557	94	0.00005	1829320	197	0.00011	1725348	88	0.00005
10-14	1862987	248	0.00013	1758120	109	0.00006	1855806	241	0.00013	1751250	101	0.00006
15-19	1899569	1047	0.00055	1795155	335	0.00019	1891816	1019	0.00054	1787666	330	0.00018
20-24	1923564	1653	0.00086	1823586	412	0.00023	1919008	1625	0.00085	1819027	397	0.00022
25-29	1849903	1489	0.00080	1756793	430	0.00024	1874386	1489	0.00079	1779529	427	0.00024
30-34	1776532	1518	0.00085	1710697	577	0.00034	1780925	1488	0.00084	1710365	570	0.00033
35-39	1768650	1973	0.00111	1729466	955	0.00055	1766487	1935	0.00109	1722892	931	0.00054
40-44	1766288	3032	0.00172	1758528	1697	0.00096	1769568	3003	0.00170	1756348	1667	0.00095
45-49	1649002	4663	0.00282	1675269	2714	0.00162	1675405	4681	0.00279	1697160	2716	0.00160
50-54	1511005	7033	0.00464	1562209	4029	0.00258	1526561	7016	0.00459	1575889	4013	0.00254
55-59	1439354	11090	0.00768	1522386	6016	0.00394	1447053	11023	0.00759	1527754	5973	0.00390
60-64	1213472	14934	0.01223	1328984	8075	0.00606	1255653	15286	0.01210	1371987	8243	0.00599
65-69	954541	17926	0.01861	1099055	10561	0.00956	982355	18226	0.01838	1128185	10719	0.00946
70-74	779544	23282	0.02943	964417	15173	0.01561	788428	23325	0.02915	972429	15158	0.01547
75-79	598812	28336	0.04623	821778	21442	0.02576	609442	28566	0.04580	833551	21533	0.02550
80-84	401908	29901	0.07173	634279	29797	0.04590	411026	30270	0.07103	645998	30004	0.04539
85-89	220813	24176	0.10380	415995	31630	0.07325	228646	24778	0.10280	428278	32189	0.07244
90-94	91218	13961	0.14217	212445	24565	0.10931	96353	14596	0.14082	222644	25438	0.10808
95-99	27293	5968	0.19711	80956	14624	0.16568	28965	6269	0.19530	85005	15191	0.16405
100+	6957	1927	0.24329	26758	6618	0.22011	7406	2040	0.24211	28313	6941	0.21838
	2038						2039					
	Births:		359750	Births:		345643	Births:		359183	Births:		345097
0	358062	2084	0.00578	344347	1599	0.00462	357530	2041	0.00567	343834	1560	0.00451
1-4	1453226	294	0.00020	1363178	216	0.00016	1451234	285	0.00020	1361265	212	0.00016
For each year and gender, P_x is the mid-year population aged x , d_x the number of people that died aged x during that year and q_x the conditional probability of dying aged x in that year.												

Age-group x	Men			Women			Men			Women		
	P_x	d_x	q_x	P_x	d_x	q_x	P_x	d_x	q_x	P_x	d_x	q_x
5-9	1825307	187	0.00010	1721489	87	0.00005	1821679	184	0.00010	1717982	84	0.00005
10-14	1849190	234	0.00013	1744881	102	0.00006	1843147	229	0.00012	1739110	96	0.00006
15-19	1883797	1005	0.00053	1779935	313	0.00018	1875763	981	0.00052	1772199	308	0.00017
20-24	1913546	1592	0.00083	1813599	395	0.00022	1907312	1559	0.00082	1807463	378	0.00021
25-29	1895204	1482	0.00078	1799615	422	0.00023	1911033	1463	0.00077	1815707	418	0.00023
30-34	1788463	1468	0.00082	1713090	550	0.00032	1799948	1457	0.00081	1719461	537	0.00031
35-39	1765615	1905	0.00108	1717621	910	0.00053	1765479	1873	0.00106	1713287	890	0.00052
40-44	1768197	2957	0.00167	1749668	1639	0.00094	1764564	2912	0.00165	1740794	1611	0.00093
45-49	1700291	4701	0.00276	1716978	2713	0.00158	1721639	4707	0.00273	1732970	2708	0.00156
50-54	1546507	7006	0.00452	1593966	4011	0.00251	1569383	7021	0.00446	1614528	4008	0.00248
55-59	1449599	10915	0.00750	1527602	5891	0.00385	1451754	10790	0.00740	1527082	5823	0.00381
60-64	1295566	15607	0.01197	1412412	8404	0.00593	1329699	15866	0.01186	1446541	8513	0.00587
65-69	1014322	18605	0.01818	1161898	10923	0.00936	1049554	19030	0.01797	1199045	11156	0.00926
70-74	798540	23387	0.02886	981716	15160	0.01532	811488	23520	0.02857	994340	15195	0.01517
75-79	619873	28792	0.04539	844958	21610	0.02525	629869	28989	0.04499	855575	21672	0.02501
80-84	420048	30611	0.07031	657441	30189	0.04489	428989	30938	0.06961	668707	30362	0.04440
85-89	236202	25330	0.10178	439907	32682	0.07163	243561	25848	0.10078	451070	33119	0.07082
90-94	101614	15242	0.13953	233089	26324	0.10690	106891	15877	0.13827	243430	27182	0.10576
95-99	30791	6595	0.19347	89408	15805	0.16242	32781	6961	0.19197	94207	16467	0.16075
100+	7896	2164	0.24103	29956	7275	0.21656	8425	2286	0.23892	31735	7640	0.21488
Year	2040											
	Births:	358535		Births:	344475							
0	356922	1991	0.00554	343236	1529	0.00443						
1-4	1449414	276	0.00019	1359537	206	0.00015						
5-9	1818425	180	0.00010	1714863	80	0.00005						
10-14	1837799	219	0.00012	1733941	92	0.00005						
15-19	1867863	961	0.00051	1764595	302	0.00017						
20-24	1900506	1535	0.00081	1800741	370	0.00021						
25-29	1919765	1440	0.00075	1825760	409	0.00022						
30-34	1816505	1446	0.00080	1730876	527	0.00030						
35-39	1766308	1847	0.00105	1709759	876	0.00051						
40-44	1760389	2864	0.00163	1731602	1572	0.00091						
45-49	1737775	4699	0.00270	1743665	2698	0.00155						
50-54	1594143	7040	0.00441	1636344	4010	0.00245						
55-59	1457021	10685	0.00731	1529841	5755	0.00375						
60-64	1355589	16023	0.01175	1471683	8578	0.00581						
65-69	1087201	19487	0.01776	1238719	11408	0.00917						
70-74	828492	23758	0.02827	1011782	15303	0.01501						
75-79	639156	29151	0.04459	865081	21703	0.02478						
80-84	438018	31267	0.06892	679883	30516	0.04390						
85-89	250801	26342	0.09979	461967	33520	0.07002						
90-94	112071	16479	0.13697	253429	27982	0.10464						
95-99	34909	7347	0.19042	99416	17187	0.15912						
100+	9021	2427	0.23714	33664	8031	0.21314						
Source: Own calculations based on INDEC's 2010-2040 population projections.												
For each year and gender, P_x is the mid-year population aged x , d_x the number of people that died aged x during that year and q_x the conditional probability of dying aged x in that year.												

Finally, the following Table K.3 depicts our computation of a woman’s conditional probability of giving birth at age x b_x . The projections on the age-specific fertility rate f_x are part of INDEC’s 2010-2040 population projection. These are not however given for every year between 2010 and 2040. but only once every five years (for 2010, 2015, 2020 and so on). We thus extrapolate the values for the missing years. For instance, the fertility rate for age 2011 $f_{x,2011} = \frac{4}{5}f_{x,2010} + \frac{1}{5}f_{x,2015}$.

Table K.3: Conditional probabilities of giving birth by age, women, 2010-2040

Age-group x	f_x	m_x	b_x									
	2010			2011			2012			2013		
10-14	0.00260	0.00023	0.00260	0.00254	0.00021	0.00254	0.00248	0.00020	0.00248	0.00242	0.00019	0.00242
15-19	0.06310	0.00042	0.06309	0.06248	0.00041	0.06247	0.06186	0.00039	0.06185	0.06124	0.00037	0.06123
20-24	0.11250	0.00050	0.11247	0.11096	0.00048	0.11093	0.10942	0.00047	0.10939	0.10788	0.00045	0.10786
25-29	0.11320	0.00060	0.11317	0.11202	0.00057	0.11199	0.11084	0.00055	0.11081	0.10966	0.00053	0.10963
30-34	0.10480	0.00076	0.10476	0.10394	0.00074	0.10390	0.10308	0.00071	0.10304	0.10222	0.00068	0.10219
35-39	0.06470	0.00110	0.06466	0.06400	0.00106	0.06397	0.06330	0.00102	0.06327	0.06260	0.00100	0.06257
40-44	0.01930	0.00163	0.01928	0.01906	0.00159	0.01904	0.01882	0.00155	0.01881	0.01858	0.00151	0.01857
45-49	0.00210	0.00260	0.00210	0.00206	0.00255	0.00206	0.00202	0.00249	0.00202	0.00198	0.00244	0.00198
	2014			2015			2016			2017		
10-14	0.00236	0.00018	0.00236	0.00230	0.00017	0.00230	0.00226	0.00016	0.00226	0.00222	0.00015	0.00222
15-19	0.06062	0.00036	0.06061	0.06000	0.00035	0.05999	0.05936	0.00033	0.05935	0.05872	0.00032	0.05871
20-24	0.10634	0.00044	0.10632	0.10480	0.00042	0.10478	0.10360	0.00041	0.10358	0.10240	0.00039	0.10238
25-29	0.10848	0.00051	0.10845	0.10730	0.00049	0.10727	0.10652	0.00047	0.10649	0.10574	0.00046	0.10572
30-34	0.10136	0.00066	0.10133	0.10050	0.00063	0.10047	0.09992	0.00061	0.09989	0.09934	0.00059	0.09931
35-39	0.06190	0.00097	0.06187	0.06120	0.00094	0.06117	0.06072	0.00091	0.06069	0.06024	0.00088	0.06021
40-44	0.01834	0.00147	0.01833	0.01810	0.00144	0.01809	0.01786	0.00141	0.01785	0.01762	0.00138	0.01761
45-49	0.00194	0.00238	0.00194	0.00190	0.00233	0.00190	0.00186	0.00228	0.00186	0.00182	0.00223	0.00182
	2018			2019			2020			2021		
10-14	0.00218	0.00014	0.00218	0.00214	0.00013	0.00214	0.00210	0.00013	0.00210	0.00208	0.00012	0.00208
15-19	0.05808	0.00032	0.05807	0.05744	0.00030	0.05743	0.05680	0.00029	0.05679	0.05638	0.00028	0.05637
20-24	0.10120	0.00038	0.10118	0.10000	0.00037	0.09998	0.09880	0.00036	0.09878	0.09770	0.00034	0.09768
25-29	0.10496	0.00044	0.10494	0.10418	0.00042	0.10416	0.10340	0.00041	0.10338	0.10278	0.00039	0.10276
30-34	0.09876	0.00057	0.09873	0.09818	0.00055	0.09815	0.09760	0.00053	0.09757	0.09714	0.00051	0.09712
35-39	0.05976	0.00086	0.05973	0.05928	0.00083	0.05926	0.05880	0.00081	0.05878	0.05850	0.00079	0.05848
40-44	0.01738	0.00134	0.01737	0.01714	0.00132	0.01713	0.01690	0.00129	0.01689	0.01674	0.00127	0.01673
45-49	0.00178	0.00218	0.00178	0.00174	0.00214	0.00174	0.00170	0.00210	0.00170	0.00166	0.00206	0.00166
	2022			2023			2024			2025		
10-14	0.00206	0.00011	0.00206	0.00204	0.00011	0.00204	0.00202	0.00011	0.00202	0.00200	0.00010	0.00200
15-19	0.05596	0.00027	0.05595	0.05554	0.00026	0.05553	0.05512	0.00025	0.05511	0.05470	0.00024	0.05469
20-24	0.09660	0.00033	0.09658	0.09550	0.00032	0.09548	0.09440	0.00031	0.09439	0.09330	0.00030	0.09329
25-29	0.10216	0.00038	0.10214	0.10154	0.00037	0.10152	0.10092	0.00036	0.10090	0.10030	0.00034	0.10028
30-34	0.09668	0.00050	0.09666	0.09622	0.00048	0.09620	0.09576	0.00047	0.09574	0.09530	0.00045	0.09528
35-39	0.05820	0.00077	0.05818	0.05790	0.00074	0.05788	0.05760	0.00073	0.05758	0.05730	0.00070	0.05728
40-44	0.01658	0.00124	0.01657	0.01642	0.00122	0.01641	0.01626	0.00119	0.01625	0.01610	0.00117	0.01609
45-49	0.00162	0.00202	0.00162	0.00158	0.00199	0.00158	0.00154	0.00200	0.00154	0.00150	0.00192	0.00150
	2026			2027			2028			2029		
10-14	0.00198	0.00009	0.00198	0.00196	0.00009	0.00196	0.00194	0.00008	0.00194	0.00192	0.00008	0.00192
15-19	0.05450	0.00024	0.05449	0.05430	0.00023	0.05429	0.05410	0.00023	0.05409	0.05390	0.00022	0.05389
20-24	0.09262	0.00029	0.09261	0.09194	0.00028	0.09193	0.09126	0.00028	0.09125	0.09058	0.00027	0.09057
25-29	0.09974	0.00033	0.09972	0.09918	0.00032	0.09916	0.09862	0.00031	0.09860	0.09806	0.00030	0.09805
30-34	0.09496	0.00044	0.09494	0.09462	0.00043	0.09460	0.09428	0.00042	0.09426	0.09394	0.00041	0.09392
35-39	0.05704	0.00069	0.05702	0.05678	0.00068	0.05676	0.05652	0.00066	0.05650	0.05626	0.00064	0.05624
40-44	0.01602	0.00114	0.01601	0.01594	0.00112	0.01593	0.01586	0.00110	0.01585	0.01578	0.00108	0.01577
45-49	0.00148	0.00189	0.00148	0.00146	0.00186	0.00146	0.00144	0.00183	0.00144	0.00142	0.00180	0.00142
	2030			2031			2032			2033		
10-14	0.00190	0.00008	0.00190	0.00188	0.00007	0.00188	0.00186	0.00007	0.00186	0.00184	0.00007	0.00184
15-19	0.05370	0.00021	0.05369	0.05352	0.00021	0.05351	0.05334	0.00021	0.05333	0.05316	0.00020	0.05315
20-24	0.08990	0.00026	0.08989	0.08948	0.00025	0.08947	0.08906	0.00025	0.08905	0.08864	0.00024	0.08863
25-29	0.09750	0.00029	0.09749	0.09718	0.00028	0.09717	0.09686	0.00027	0.09685	0.09654	0.00027	0.09653
Among women in a given year, f_x is fertility rate at age x , m_x the central death rate at age x and b_x the conditional probability of giving birth at age x .												
Source: Own calculations based on INDEC’s 2010-2040 population projections.												

Age-group x	f_x	m_x	b_x									
30-34	0.09360	0.00039	0.09358	0.09336	0.00039	0.09334	0.09312	0.00037	0.09310	0.09288	0.00036	0.09286
35-39	0.05600	0.00063	0.05598	0.05580	0.00061	0.05578	0.05560	0.00060	0.05558	0.05540	0.00059	0.05538
40-44	0.01570	0.00106	0.01569	0.01564	0.00104	0.01563	0.01558	0.00103	0.01557	0.01552	0.00101	0.01551
45-49	0.00140	0.00177	0.00140	0.00140	0.00174	0.00140	0.00140	0.00172	0.00140	0.00140	0.00169	0.00140
	2034			2035			2036			2037		
10-14	0.00182	0.00007	0.00182	0.00180	0.00006	0.00180	0.00000	0.00006	0.00000	0.00176	0.00006	0.00176
15-19	0.05298	0.00019	0.05297	0.05280	0.00019	0.05280	0.05264	0.00019	0.05264	0.05248	0.00018	0.05248
20-24	0.08822	0.00024	0.08821	0.08780	0.00023	0.08779	0.08744	0.00023	0.08743	0.08708	0.00022	0.08707
25-29	0.09622	0.00026	0.09621	0.09590	0.00025	0.09589	0.09568	0.00024	0.09567	0.09546	0.00024	0.09545
30-34	0.09264	0.00036	0.09262	0.09240	0.00034	0.09238	0.09226	0.00034	0.09224	0.09212	0.00033	0.09210
35-39	0.05520	0.00057	0.05518	0.05500	0.00057	0.05498	0.05488	0.00055	0.05486	0.05476	0.00054	0.05475
40-44	0.01546	0.00099	0.01545	0.01540	0.00098	0.01539	0.01534	0.00097	0.01533	0.01528	0.00095	0.01527
45-49	0.00140	0.00167	0.00140	0.00140	0.00164	0.00140	0.00140	0.00162	0.00140	0.00140	0.00160	0.00140
	2038			2039			2040					
10-14	0.00174	0.00006	0.00174	0.00172	0.00006	0.00172	0.00170	0.00005	0.00170			
15-19	0.05232	0.00018	0.05232	0.05216	0.00017	0.05216	0.05200	0.00017	0.05200			
20-24	0.08672	0.00022	0.08671	0.08636	0.00021	0.08635	0.08600	0.00021	0.08599			
25-29	0.09524	0.00023	0.09523	0.09502	0.00023	0.09501	0.09480	0.00022	0.09479			
30-34	0.09198	0.00032	0.09197	0.09184	0.00031	0.09183	0.09170	0.00030	0.09169			
35-39	0.05464	0.00053	0.05463	0.05452	0.00052	0.05451	0.05440	0.00051	0.05439			
40-44	0.01522	0.00094	0.01521	0.01516	0.00093	0.01515	0.01510	0.00091	0.01509			
45-49	0.00140	0.00158	0.00140	0.00140	0.00156	0.00140	0.00140	0.00155	0.00140			
Among women in a given year, f_x is fertility rate at age x , m_x the central death rate at age x and b_x the conditional probability of giving birth at age x .												
Source: Own calculations based on INDEC's 2010-2040 population projections.												

Appendix L

A study of individual behaviour: determining labour-market state through logistic behavioural equations

Table L.1: The determinants of next period's labour-market state: men aged 16-64, 2003-2015.

Dependent variable:	<i>Wage – earner_t</i>	<i>Independent_t</i>	<i>Unregistered_t</i>	<i>Unemployed_t</i>	<i>Inactive_t</i>
<i>Intercept</i>	2.4008 ***	2.3587 ***	0.4251 ***	-0.8166 ***	0.0807
<i>Primary education_t</i>	Ref.	-1.4119 ***	1.1038 ***	0.1661 ***	0.2349 ***
<i>Secondary education_t</i>	0.3469 ***	-0.7266 ***	0.6866 ***	0.1777 ***	0.3882 ***
<i>Tertiary education_t</i>	0.5928 ***	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Age_t ∈ [16; 20[</i>	-1.0280 ***	-2.2866 ***	-0.7414 ***	-0.3485 ***	1.6588 ***
<i>Age_t ∈ [20; 25[</i>	-0.0291	-0.8019 ***	-0.1981 ***	0.0633	0.6971 ***
<i>Age_t ∈ [25; 30[</i>	0.1381 ***	-0.3659 ***	-0.0477 *	0.0676	0.2536 ***
<i>Age_t ∈ [30; 35[</i>	0.0891 ***	-0.1233 ***	0.00353	-0.0545	0.1027 *
<i>Age_t ∈ [35; 40[</i>	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Age_t ∈ [40; 45[</i>	-0.0580 *	0.1716 ***	-0.0264	0.0588	0.0213
<i>Age_t ∈ [45; 50[</i>	-0.2322 ***	0.1076 **	0.0956 ***	0.00376	0.3356 ***
<i>Age_t ∈ [50; 55[</i>	-0.2892 ***	0.1982 ***	-0.0331	0.1456 ***	0.7168 ***
<i>Age_t ∈ [55; 60[</i>	-0.4782 ***	0.1180 ***	0.0140	0.1426 ***	1.0300 ***
<i>Age_t ∈ [60; 65[</i>	-0.6158 ***	0.1420 ***	-0.2403 ***	0.1726 ***	1.5651 ***
<i>Single_t</i>	-0.2936 ***	-0.2713 ***	-0.3861 ***	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Married_t</i>	Ref.	Ref.	-0.2368 ***	-0.3399 ***	-0.6532 ***
<i>Divorced_t</i>	-0.0875	-0.00928	-0.2073 ***	-0.2379 ***	-0.8057 ***
<i>Common – law_t</i>	-0.1996 ***	-0.0712 **	Ref.	-0.3228 ***	-0.8046 ***
<i>Widowed_t</i>	0.0179	-0.0519	-0.1713 **	-0.5263 ***	-0.8122 ***
<i>No partner_{t-1}</i>	-0.2723 ***	-1.2938 ***	-0.2321 ***	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Wage – earner partner_{t-1}</i>	Ref.	-1.3206 ***	-0.5818 ***	0.2461 ***	-0.1611 **
<i>Independent partner_{t-1}</i>	-0.7309 ***	Ref.	-1.1216 ***	-0.4125 ***	-0.8748 ***
<i>Unregistered partner_{t-1}</i>	-0.4503 ***	-1.7128 ***	Ref.	0.0753	-0.3768 ***
<i>Unemployed partner_{t-1}</i>	-0.1341 ***	-1.4936 ***	-0.4161 ***	0.5589 ***	-0.8088 ***
<i>Inactive partner_{t-1}</i>	-0.1496 ***	-1.3040 ***	-0.2728 ***	-0.2215 ***	-0.1580 **
<i>Children_t aged ≤ 4 = 0</i>	Ref.	0.0543	-0.1906 ***	0.0609	0.4851 ***

Source: Author's Calculation based on EPHc microdata, 2003-2015. * Significant at 10%. ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Ref. refers to the reference individual.

Dependent variable:	$Wage - earner_t$	$Independent_t$	$Unregistered_t$	$Unemployed_t$	$Inactive_t$
$Children_t \text{ aged } \leq 4 = 1$	0.00851	Ref.	-0.1465 ***	Ref.	Ref.
$Children_t \text{ aged } \leq 4 \geq 2$	-0.1585 ***	-0.0559	Ref.	0.1765 ***	-0.4817 ***
$Just \text{ finished education} = 1$	1.3811 ***	1.5217 ***	2.0071 ***	1.9343 ***	-3.0751 ***
$Just \text{ finished education} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q1_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 1$	Ref.		0.8375 ***	0.3850 ***	
$Q1_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 0$	0.5825 ***	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q2_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 1$	-0.0662 **	-0.5255 ***	0.2858 ***	0.1222 *	-0.5868 ***
$Q2_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q3_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 1$	0.0844 **	-0.3983 ***			-0.5451 ***
$Q3_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q4_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 1$				-0.5530 ***	-0.9322 ***
$Q4_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q1_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 1$		Ref.		0.2539 **	0.6432 ***
$Q1_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.		Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q2_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 1$		Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q2_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q3_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 1$	0.2611 ***	0.2156 ***	-0.2922 ***	-0.4647 ***	-0.6096 ***
$Q3_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q4_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 1$	0.6674 ***	0.2818 ***	-0.8021 ***	-1.4722 ***	-0.4398 ***
$Q4_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q1_{t-1} \times Unregistered_{t-1} = 1$			Ref.	0.3650 ***	0.9236 ***
$Q1_{t-1} \times Unregistered_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	0.0765 ***	Ref.	Ref.
$Q2_{t-1} \times Unregistered_{t-1} = 1$	0.4140 ***		0.1527 ***		0.5980 ***
$Q2_{t-1} \times Unregistered_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q3_{t-1} \times Unregistered_{t-1} = 1$	0.7758 ***		0.2270 ***	-0.1621 ***	0.1529 ***
$Q3_{t-1} \times Unregistered_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q4_{t-1} \times Unregistered_{t-1} = 1$	1.1512 ***	0.3585 ***		-0.3209 ***	
$Q4_{t-1} \times Unregistered_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Unemployed_{t-1} = 1$	0.3721 ***	0.7164 ***	1.6482 ***	Ref.	1.2560 ***

Source: Author's Calculation based on EPHc microdata, 2003-2015. * Significant at 10%. ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Ref. refers to the reference individual.

Dependent variable:	$Wage - earner_t$	$Independent_t$	$Unregistered_t$	$Unemployed_t$	$Inactive_t$
$Unemployed_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	-2.3111 ***	Ref.
$Inactive_{t-1} = 1$	-0.4878 ***				Ref.
$Inactive_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	-4.0391 ***
$S1_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 1$	3.8934 ***		0.2240 ***		
$S1_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$S2_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 1$	4.0887 ***	-0.3025 *			
$S2_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$S3_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 1$	4.2793 ***		-0.1955 ***	-0.3998 ***	
$S3_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$S4_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 1$	4.7647 ***	-0.3032 ***	-0.6825 ***	-1.0389 ***	-0.4066 ***
$S4_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$S5_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 1$	Ref.	-0.5516 ***	-1.4658 ***	-2.2190 ***	-0.6607 ***
$S5_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 0$	-5.4804 ***	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$S1_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 1$		3.2455 ***	1.8515 ***	0.7208 ***	0.6367 ***
$S1_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$S2_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 1$		3.4825 ***	2.0819 ***	-0.7707 *	
$S2_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$S3_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 1$		3.7521 ***	1.6508 ***		
$S3_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$S4_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 1$		3.7334 ***	2.0071 ***		
$S4_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$S5_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 1$		Ref.	1.3822 ***	-0.6056 ***	-0.5654 ***
$S5_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	-3.8929 ***	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$S1_{t-1} \times Unregistered_{t-1} = 1$		0.3750 ***	Ref.	1.1118 ***	0.1055 ***
$S1_{t-1} \times Unregistered_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	-2.6328 ***	Ref.	Ref.
$S2_{t-1} \times Unregistered_{t-1} = 1$		0.5849 ***	2.7622 ***	0.8855 ***	
$S2_{t-1} \times Unregistered_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$S3_{t-1} \times Unregistered_{t-1} = 1$		0.6760 ***	2.7977 ***	0.7088 ***	
$S3_{t-1} \times Unregistered_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.

Source: Author's Calculation based on EPHc microdata, 2003-2015. * Significant at 10%. ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Ref. refers to the reference individual.

Dependent variable:	<i>Wage – earner_t</i>	<i>Independent_t</i>	<i>Unregistered_t</i>	<i>Unemployed_t</i>	<i>Inactive_t</i>
$S4_{t-1} \times$ $Unregistered_{t-1} = 1$	-0.2032 ***	0.8405 ***	3.0238 ***	0.2270 ***	
$S4_{t-1} \times$ $Unregistered_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$S5_{t-1} \times$ $Unregistered_{t-1} = 1$	-0.7931 ***	1.3930 ***	Ref.		-0.2532 ***
$S5_{t-1} \times$ $Unregistered_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	3.0917 ***	Ref.	Ref.
AUC training dataset	0.9499	0.9113	0.8872	0.8184	0.9511
AUC validation dataset	0.9495	0.9089	0.8896	0.8196	0.9514
Observations	250365	250365	250365	250365	250365
<p>$\forall k \in [1; 5], Sk_t$ is time spent working in the current firm at time t. $S1$ corresponds to a quarter, $S2$ to more than 3 to 6 months, $S3$ to more than 6 to 12 months, $S4$ to more than 1 to 5 years and $S5$ to more than 5 years. Qk_t is the kth sectoral labour-income quartile. It is computed separately among wage-earners, independent and unregistered (informal) workers.</p> <p>Reading example: a man who last quarter was among the 25% poorest (formal) wage-earners and had a seniority of 1 to 5 years sees his odds ratio of being a (formal) wage-earner today decrease by $\exp(4.7647 - 5.4804) - 1 = -51\%$ as compared to the reference individual.</p>					
<p>Source: Author's Calculation based on EPHc microdata, 2003-2015. * Significant at 10%. ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Ref. refers to the reference individual.</p>					

Table L.2: The determinants of next period's labour-market state: women aged 16-59, 2003-2015.

Dependent variable:	<i>Wage – earner_t</i>	<i>Independent_t</i>	<i>Unregistered_t</i>	<i>Unemployed_t</i>	<i>Inactive_t</i>
<i>Intercept</i>	2.0542 ***	1.9333 ***	-0.4302 ***	-0.8726 ***	1.6377 ***
<i>Primary education_t</i>	Ref.	-1.7009 ***	0.6567 ***	-0.2067 ***	0.6443 ***
<i>Secondary education_t</i>	0.4384 ***	-0.8914 ***	0.4431 ***	-0.0300	0.5849 ***
<i>Tertiary education_t</i>	1.0134 ***	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Age_t \in [16; 20[$	-1.4007 ***	-1.5498 ***	-1.1731 ***	-0.3478 ***	1.4630 ***
$Age_t \in [20; 25[$	-0.2928 ***	-0.6639 ***	-0.4240 ***	0.1374 ***	0.5174 ***
$Age_t \in [25; 30[$	-0.0195	-0.2559 ***	-0.2011 ***	0.1462 ***	0.1637 ***
$Age_t \in [30; 35[$	-0.0340	0.0447	-0.0777 ***	0.0625	0.0492 *
$Age_t \in [35; 40[$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Age_t \in [40; 45[$	-0.1255 ***	0.1120 ***	0.0869 ***	-0.0358	-0.0319
$Age_t \in [45; 50[$	-0.0810 **	0.2406 ***	-0.0426	-0.0378	0.0665 **
$Age_t \in [50; 55[$	-0.1163 ***	0.3772 ***	-0.0751 ***	-0.1083 **	0.1318 ***
$Age_t \in [55; 60[$	-0.1291 ***	0.2470 ***	-0.2687 ***	-0.5201 ***	0.4972 ***
<i>Single_t</i>	0.3975 ***	-0.0865	0.0982 **	Ref.	-0.4376 ***
<i>Married_t</i>	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	-0.2273 ***	Ref.
<i>Divorced_t</i>	0.2428 ***	0.1521	0.4052 ***	0.0802 **	-0.9170 ***
<i>Common – law_t</i>	0.2116 ***	0.0270	0.0838 ***	-0.0616	-0.2625 ***
<i>Widowed_t</i>	0.0954	-0.0113	0.2628 ***	-0.1282 *	-0.3597 ***
<i>No partner_{t-1}</i>	-0.2842 ***	-1.0210 ***	0.3237 ***	Ref.	-0.2906 ***
<i>Wage – earner partner_{t-1}</i>	Ref.	-1.2083 ***	Ref.	-0.1738 ***	Ref.
<i>Independent partner_{t-1}</i>	-0.5716 ***	Ref.	0.0500	-0.3421 ***	-0.2950 ***
<i>Unregistered partner_{t-1}</i>	-0.4418 ***	-1.4907 ***	0.5361 ***	-0.2173 ***	-0.3439 ***
<i>Unemployed partner_{t-1}</i>	-0.0349	-1.2222 ***	0.5149 ***	0.4655 ***	-0.8082 ***
<i>Inactive partner_{t-1}</i>	-0.0974 *	-1.2685 ***	0.3951 ***	-0.8006 ***	-0.2260 ***
<p>Source and variables: see Table L.1. * Significant at 10%. ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Ref. refers to the reference individual.</p>					

Dependent variable:	$Wage - earner_t$	$Independent_t$	$Unregistered_t$	$Unemployed_t$	$Inactive_t$
$Children_t \text{ aged } \leq 4 = 0$	Ref.	-0.0767 *	0.1731 ***	0.3634 ***	-0.4377 ***
$Children_t \text{ aged } \leq 4 = 1$	-0.1668 ***	Ref.	0.1147 ***	0.2786 ***	-0.2720 ***
$Children_t \text{ aged } \leq 4 \geq 2$	-0.5477 ***	0.1248	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Just \text{ finished education} = 1$	1.7014 ***	1.4915 ***	1.7935 ***	1.7583 ***	-2.4979 ***
$Just \text{ finished education} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q1_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 1$	Ref.	0.2699 ***	0.6596 ***	0.8357 ***	0.7300 ***
$Q1_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 0$	0.5499 ***	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q2_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 1$				0.4695 ***	0.1725 **
$Q2_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q3_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 1$	0.0705 *				
$Q3_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q4_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 1$		0.3744 ***	-0.3723 ***		-0.1745 *
$Q4_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q1_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 1$	-0.5362 ***	Ref.	0.5423 ***	2.0401 ***	1.1933 ***
$Q1_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.		Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q2_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 1$	-0.1949 **		0.7024 ***	0.7836 ***	0.7660 ***
$Q2_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q3_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 1$		0.2491 ***	0.2326 **	0.5553 **	
$Q3_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q4_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 1$	0.2173 ***	0.2093 ***			
$Q4_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q1_{t-1} \times Unregistered_{t-1} = 1$	-0.7448 ***		Ref.	0.4919 ***	1.8913 ***
$Q1_{t-1} \times Unregistered_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	0.3817 ***	Ref.	Ref.
$Q2_{t-1} \times Unregistered_{t-1} = 1$		0.3169 ***		0.2209 ***	1.2656 ***
$Q2_{t-1} \times Unregistered_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q3_{t-1} \times Unregistered_{t-1} = 1$	0.4558 ***	0.5639 ***			1.0310 ***
$Q3_{t-1} \times Unregistered_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q4_{t-1} \times Unregistered_{t-1} = 1$	0.9393 ***	0.9320 ***	-0.2488 ***		0.8520 ***
$Q4_{t-1} \times Unregistered_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.

Source and variables: see Table L.1. * Significant at 10%. ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Ref. refers to the reference individual.

Dependent variable:	$Wage - earner_t$	$Independent_t$	$Unregistered_t$	$Unemployed_t$	$Inactive_t$
$Unemployed_{t-1} = 1$	-0.4429 ***	0.8869 ***	1.1486 ***	Ref.	2.4077 ***
$Unemployed_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	-3.1407 ***	Ref.
$Inactive_{t-1} = 1$	-1.5604 ***	0.3764 ***		0.9620 ***	Ref.
$Inactive_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	-4.4842 ***
$S1_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 1$	3.7352 ***	-0.8587 ***	0.3301 ***		-0.3165 ***
$S1_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$S2_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 1$	3.7941 ***				
$S2_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$S3_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 1$	4.0156 ***		-0.4149 ***		
$S3_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$S4_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 1$	4.3604 ***	-0.1870 *	-0.5213 ***	-0.7793 ***	-0.5316 ***
$S4_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$S5_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 1$	Ref.	-0.5022 ***	-1.5651 ***	-1.9216 ***	-1.1363 ***
$S5_{t-1} \times Wage - earner_{t-1} = 0$	-5.2337 ***	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$S1_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 1$		4.0320 ***	0.7854 ***		0.9349 ***
$S1_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$S2_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 1$	0.6621 ***	3.6150 ***	1.2148 ***		
$S2_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$S3_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 1$		4.2572 ***	0.6672 ***		0.7613 ***
$S3_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$S4_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 1$		4.4915 ***	0.8877 ***	-0.8252 ***	0.2939 ***
$S4_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$S5_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 1$		Ref.	0.3451 ***	-1.6694 ***	
$S5_{t-1} \times Independent_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	-4.7454 ***	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$S1_{t-1} \times Unregistered_{t-1} = 1$	-0.0932 **		Ref.	1.0232 ***	
$S1_{t-1} \times Unregistered_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	-3.0653 ***	Ref.	Ref.
$S2_{t-1} \times Unregistered_{t-1} = 1$		0.6211 ***	2.9703 ***	1.2405 ***	
$S2_{t-1} \times Unregistered_{t-1} = 0$	Ref.		Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$S3_{t-1} \times Unregistered_{t-1} = 1$		0.9690 ***	2.8721 ***	1.1735 ***	0.1970 ***
$S3_{t-1} \times Unregistered_{t-1} = 0$					

Source and variables: see Table L.1. * Significant at 10%. ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Ref. refers to the reference individual.

Dependent variable:	<i>Wage – earner_t</i>	<i>Independent_t</i>	<i>Unregistered_t</i>	<i>Unemployed_t</i>	<i>Inactive_t</i>
<i>S</i> _{3,t-1} × <i>Unregistered</i> _{t-1} = 0	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>S</i> _{4,t-1} × <i>Unregistered</i> _{t-1} = 1	-0.2517 ***	1.2075 ***	3.1183 ***	0.4767 ***	0.0635 **
<i>S</i> _{4,t-1} × <i>Unregistered</i> _{t-1} = 0	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>S</i> _{5,t-1} × <i>Unregistered</i> _{t-1} = 1	-0.7639 ***	1.7089 ***	3.1887 ***		
<i>S</i> _{5,t-1} × <i>Unregistered</i> _{t-1} = 0	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
AUC training dataset	0.9665	0.9228	0.8718	0.8038	0.9224
AUC validation dataset	0.9654	0.9217	0.8739	0.7967	0.9222
Observations	256291	256291	256291	256291	256291
Reading example: a woman who is single today and has no partner sees her odds ratio of being a (formal) wage-earner increase by $\exp(0.3975 - 0.2842) - 1 = 12\%$ as compared to the reference individual, who is married and whose partner is a (formal) wage-earner.					
Source and variables: see Table L.1. * Significant at 10%. ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Ref. refers to the reference individual.					

Table L.3: The determinants of the previous period’s labour-market state: men aged 16-64, 2003-2015.

Dependent variable:	<i>Wage – earner_{t-1}</i>	<i>Independent_{t-1}</i>	<i>Unregistered_{t-1}</i>	<i>Unemployed_{t-1}</i>	<i>Inactive_{t-1}</i>
Intercept	0.5276 ***	0.0808	-0.1323 ***	-0.4743 ***	0.1820 *
<i>F</i> _{1,t-1}	-0.4969 ***	-1.3995 ***	1.0329 ***		0.3768 ***
<i>F</i> _{2,t-1}	-0.1817 ***	-0.7164 ***	0.6523 ***		0.5099 ***
<i>F</i> _{3,t-1}	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Age</i> _{t-1} ∈ [16; 20[Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	-0.4634 ***	Ref.
<i>Age</i> _{t-1} ∈ [20; 25[0.8695 ***	0.8452 ***	0.5993 ***	Ref.	-0.8659 ***
<i>Age</i> _{t-1} ∈ [25; 30[1.2663 ***	1.4622 ***	0.6697 ***	-0.1666 ***	-1.2544 ***
<i>Age</i> _{t-1} ∈ [30; 35[1.2313 ***	1.6923 ***	0.6212 ***	-0.0782 **	-1.4440 ***
<i>Age</i> _{t-1} ∈ [35; 40[1.2148 ***	1.7724 ***	0.6767 ***	-0.3903 ***	-1.4838 ***
<i>Age</i> _{t-1} ∈ [40; 45[1.1876 ***	1.8067 ***	0.6182 ***	-0.3076 ***	-1.1753 ***
<i>Age</i> _{t-1} ∈ [45; 50[1.1196 ***	1.9367 ***	0.6149 ***	-0.3431 ***	-1.0063 ***
<i>Age</i> _{t-1} ∈ [50; 55[0.9908 ***	1.9864 ***	0.6006 ***	-0.2433 ***	-0.7219 ***
<i>Age</i> _{t-1} ∈ [55; 60[0.9660 ***	1.9567 ***	0.5190 ***	-0.2027 ***	-0.3847 ***
<i>Age</i> _{t-1} ∈ [60; 65[0.7417 ***	2.0062 ***	0.4418 ***	-0.2645 ***	0.00269
<i>Single</i> _{t-1}	Ref.	Ref.	-0.3021 ***	Ref.	0.6854 ***
<i>Married</i> _{t-1}	0.5134 ***	0.2867 ***	-0.2188 ***	-0.5379 ***	Ref.
<i>Divorced</i> _{t-1}	0.2683 ***	0.1427 ***	-0.0944 *	-0.2337 ***	-0.1621 **
<i>Common – law</i> _{t-1}	0.3293 ***	0.1921 **	Ref.	-0.4243 ***	-0.1164 ***
<i>Widowed</i> _{t-1}	0.2753 ***	0.2236 **	-0.3042 ***	-0.4704 ***	0.2673 ***
<i>No partner</i> _{t-1}	-0.1909 ***	-1.2421 ***	-0.3272 ***	0.1804 **	Ref.
<i>Wage – earner partner</i> _t	Ref.	-1.2297 ***	-0.6644 ***	0.4587 ***	-0.1837 **
<i>Independent partner</i> _t	-0.7685 ***	Ref.	-0.9978 ***	-0.6602 ***	-0.7414 ***
<i>Unregistered partner</i> _t	-0.4941 ***	-1.6413 ***	Ref.	0.2385 ***	-0.3587 ***
<i>Unemployed partner</i> _t	-0.2299 ***	-1.7739 ***	-0.3055 ***	0.8260 ***	-0.8255 ***
<i>Inactive partner</i> _t	-0.0615 **	-1.2701 ***	-0.3570 ***	Ref.	-0.2548 ***
<i>Children</i> _{t-1} aged ≤ 4 = 0	0.0122		-0.0752 ***	0.0532	0.5987 ***
Source and variables: see Table L.1. * Significant at 10%. ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Ref. refers to the reference individual.					

Dependent variable:	$Wage - earner_{t-1}$	$Independent_{t-1}$	$Unregistered_{t-1}$	$Unemployed_{t-1}$	$Inactive_{t-1}$
$Children_{t-1} \text{ aged } \leq 4 = 1$	Ref.		Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Children_{t-1} \text{ aged } \leq 4 = 2+$	-0.1882 ***		0.1131 ***	-0.0737	0.2228 **
$Q1_t \times Wage - earner_t = 1$	Ref.			0.6436 ***	0.4150 ***
$Q1_t \times Wage - earner_t = 0$	-4.1889 ***				
$Q2_t \times Wage - earner_t = 1$	4.7790 ***	-0.2787 ***	-0.6602 ***		
$Q3_t \times Wage - earner_t = 1$	5.0873 ***	-0.1585 ***	-1.0852 ***	-0.5750 ***	-0.3548 ***
$Q4_t \times Wage - earner_t = 1$	5.1321 ***		-1.3042 ***	-0.9706 ***	-0.8104 ***
$Q1_t \times Independent_t = 1$	-0.2383 ***	Ref.	1.3420 ***	1.5927 ***	1.4897 ***
$Q1_t \times Independent_t = 0$		-4.1203 ***			
$Q2_t \times Independent_t = 1$		4.3689 ***	1.1725 ***	0.7461 ***	0.8264 ***
$Q3_t \times Independent_t = 1$	0.2589 ***	4.5590 ***	0.8598 ***	0.2649 **	
$Q4_t \times Independent_t = 1$	0.4588 ***	4.6130 ***	0.4520 ***		
$Q1_t \times Unregistered_t = 1$	-0.2642 ***	1.2070 ***	Ref.	2.2478 ***	1.8235 ***
$Q1_t \times Unregistered_t = 0$			-2.4969 ***		
$Q2_t \times Unregistered_t = 1$	0.1555 ***	1.4320 ***	2.7553 ***	1.9061 ***	1.4039 ***
$Q3_t \times Unregistered_t = 1$	0.3260 ***	1.6573 ***	2.9079 ***	1.6268 ***	0.9776 ***
$Q4_t \times Unregistered_t = 1$	0.6433 ***	1.9147 ***	2.8454 ***	1.2575 ***	0.6352 ***
$Unemployed_t = 1$	0.6721 ***	1.1013 ***	1.2240 ***	Ref.	2.1579 ***
$Unemployed_t = 0$				-3.4959 ***	
$Inactive_t = 1$		0.5522 ***	0.1422 ***	1.6644 ***	Ref.
$Inactive_t = 0$					-4.3708 ***
AUC training dataset	0.9449	0.9055	0.8734	0.8019	0.9413
AUC validation dataset	0.9444	0.9129	0.8717	0.7918	0.9456
Observations	249750	249750	249750	249750	249750
Reading example: a man who belongs today to the 25% richest (formal) wage-earners sees his odds ratio of having been a (formal) wage-earner in the previous quarter increase by $\exp(-4.1889 + 5.1321) - 1 = 156.82\%$ as compared to the reference individual.					
Source and variables: see Table L.1. * Significant at 10%. ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Ref. refers to the reference individual.					

Table L.4: The determinants of the previous period's labour-market state: women aged 16-59, 2003-2015.

Dependent variable:	$Wage - earner_{t-1}$	$Independent_{t-1}$	$Unregistered_{t-1}$	$Unemployed_{t-1}$	$Inactive_{t-1}$
Intercept	0.9117 ***	0.0710	-0.8740 ***	-0.5057 ***	1.9847 ***
$F_{1,t-1}$	-1.0687 ***	-1.8104 ***	0.7518 ***	-0.4810 ***	0.7347 ***
$F_{2,t-1}$	-0.5266 ***	-0.8234 ***	0.4697 ***	-0.2163 ***	0.6387 ***
$F_{3,t-1}$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.		Ref.
$Age_{t-1} \in [16; 20[$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	-0.4367 ***	Ref.
$Age_{t-1} \in [20; 25[$	0.7446 ***	0.4529 ***	0.6790 ***	Ref.	-0.7280 ***
$Age_{t-1} \in [25; 30[$	1.0748 ***	0.9768 ***	0.9225 ***	0.0465	-1.1279 ***
$Age_{t-1} \in [30; 35[$	1.2476 ***	1.2556 ***	0.9962 ***	-0.1519 ***	-1.2130 ***
$Age_{t-1} \in [35; 40[$	1.3067 ***	1.3232 ***	0.9831 ***	-0.1713 ***	-1.2309 ***
$Age_{t-1} \in [40; 45[$	1.3424 ***	1.4439 ***	0.9416 ***	-0.3789 ***	-1.1517 ***
$Age_{t-1} \in [45; 50[$	1.4295 ***	1.5279 ***	0.8624 ***	-0.3910 ***	-1.1192 ***
Source and variables: see Table L.1. * Significant at 10%. ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Ref. refers to the reference individual.					

Dependent variable:	<i>Wage – earner</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	<i>Independent</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	<i>Unregistered</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	<i>Unemployed</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	<i>Inactive</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}
<i>Age</i> _{<i>t</i>-1} ∈ [50; 55[1.4181 ***	1.4588 ***	0.7539 ***	-0.5601 ***	-0.9028 ***
<i>Age</i> _{<i>t</i>-1} ∈ [55; 60[1.3596 ***	1.6578 ***	0.6860 ***	-0.8796 ***	-0.7452 ***
<i>Single</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	Ref.		0.0184	Ref.	-0.4117 ***
<i>Married</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	-0.1126 *		-0.0865 ***	-0.3948 ***	Ref.
<i>Divorced</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	-0.0928 ***		0.2688 ***	0.1582 ***	-0.8717 ***
<i>Common – law</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	0.0200		Ref.	-0.3482 ***	-0.1798 ***
<i>Widowed</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	-0.1743 ***		0.1413 ***	-0.1309 *	-0.3264 ***
<i>No partner</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	-0.1129 *	-0.9384 ***	-0.1654 ***	0.3312 ***	0.2823 ***
<i>Wage – earner partner</i> _{<i>t</i>}	Ref.	-0.9982 ***	-0.5137 ***	0.2955 ***	Ref.
<i>Independent partner</i> _{<i>t</i>}	-0.4831 ***	Ref.	-0.4775 ***	-0.2036 **	0.1974 ***
<i>Unregistered partner</i> _{<i>t</i>}	-0.4768 ***	-1.3144 ***	Ref.	0.3378 ***	-0.0270
<i>Unemployed partner</i> _{<i>t</i>}	0.0181	-1.4437 ***	-0.1744 ***	1.0351 ***	-0.3470 ***
<i>Inactive partner</i> _{<i>t</i>}	-0.0960 *	-1.1126 ***	-0.2448 ***	Ref.	0.1532 ***
<i>Children</i> _{<i>t</i>-1} aged ≤ 4 = 0	0.0377	0.1532 ***	0.1684 ***	0.1824 ***	-0.2780 ***
<i>Children</i> _{<i>t</i>-1} aged ≤ 4 = 1	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Children</i> _{<i>t</i>-1} aged ≤ 4 = 2+	-0.2016 ***	0.3316 ***	-0.1474 ***	-0.1773 ***	0.1616 ***
<i>Q</i> ₁ _{<i>t</i>} × <i>Wage – earner</i> _{<i>t</i>} = 1	Ref.		-0.1784 **	1.0684 ***	1.4800 ***
<i>Q</i> ₁ _{<i>t</i>} × <i>Wage – earner</i> _{<i>t</i>} = 0	-3.9787 ***				
<i>Q</i> ₂ _{<i>t</i>} × <i>Wage – earner</i> _{<i>t</i>} = 1	4.6610 ***		-1.0235 ***	0.4336 ***	0.8679 ***
<i>Q</i> ₃ _{<i>t</i>} × <i>Wage – earner</i> _{<i>t</i>} = 1	4.9330 ***		-1.4999 ***		0.3653 ***
<i>Q</i> ₄ _{<i>t</i>} × <i>Wage – earner</i> _{<i>t</i>} = 1	4.9772 ***	0.2255 ***	-1.9122 ***		
<i>Q</i> ₁ _{<i>t</i>} × <i>Independent</i> _{<i>t</i>} = 1	-0.7071 ***	Ref.	0.8153 ***	2.1303 ***	2.9344 ***
<i>Q</i> ₁ _{<i>t</i>} × <i>Independent</i> _{<i>t</i>} = 0		-4.5988 ***			
<i>Q</i> ₂ _{<i>t</i>} × <i>Independent</i> _{<i>t</i>} = 1		4.8289 ***	0.6640 ***	0.7832 ***	2.2431 ***
<i>Q</i> ₃ _{<i>t</i>} × <i>Independent</i> _{<i>t</i>} = 1		4.9404 ***	0.4175 ***	1.1695 ***	1.5071 ***
<i>Q</i> ₄ _{<i>t</i>} × <i>Independent</i> _{<i>t</i>} = 1		5.0694 ***			1.6539 ***
<i>Q</i> ₁ _{<i>t</i>} × <i>Unregistered</i> _{<i>t</i>} = 1	-0.7806 ***	1.3261 ***	Ref.	2.6266 ***	3.2023 ***
<i>Q</i> ₁ _{<i>t</i>} × <i>Unregistered</i> _{<i>t</i>} = 0			-2.0774 ***		
<i>Q</i> ₂ _{<i>t</i>} × <i>Unregistered</i> _{<i>t</i>} = 1	-0.0913 **	1.4622 ***	2.4738 ***	2.2341 ***	2.6699 ***
<i>Q</i> ₃ _{<i>t</i>} × <i>Unregistered</i> _{<i>t</i>} = 1	0.2553 ***	1.7198 ***	2.5947 ***	2.0115 ***	2.3591 ***
<i>Q</i> ₄ _{<i>t</i>} × <i>Unregistered</i> _{<i>t</i>} = 1	0.7296 ***	2.2551 ***	2.3995 ***	1.8154 ***	2.1664 ***
<i>Q</i> ₁ _{<i>t</i>} × <i>Unemployed</i> _{<i>t</i>} = 1		1.2488 ***	0.3574 ***	Ref.	3.7807 ***
<i>Q</i> ₁ _{<i>t</i>} × <i>Unemployed</i> _{<i>t</i>} = 0				-4.2678 ***	
<i>Q</i> ₂ _{<i>t</i>} × <i>Inactive</i> _{<i>t</i>} = 1	-0.9808 ***	0.5859 ***	-0.3995 ***	2.4214 ***	Ref.
<i>Q</i> ₂ _{<i>t</i>} × <i>Inactive</i> _{<i>t</i>} = 0					-5.5474 ***
AUC training dataset	0.9611	0.9090	0.8509	0.7839	0.9098

Source and variables: see Table L.1. * Significant at 10%. ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Ref. refers to the reference individual.

Dependent variable:	<i>Wage – earner_{t-1}</i>	<i>Independent_{t-1}</i>	<i>Unregistered_{t-1}</i>	<i>Unemployed_{t-1}</i>	<i>Inactive_{t-1}</i>
AUC validation dataset	0.9631	0.9034	0.8565	0.7747	0.9135
Observations	256158	256158	256158	256158	256158
Reading example: a woman who belongs today to the 25% richest (formal) wage-earners sees her odds ratio of having been a (formal) wage-earner in the previous quarter increase by $\exp(-3.9787 + 4.9772) - 1 = 171.42\%$ as compared to the reference individual.					
Source and variables: see Table L.1. * Significant at 10%. ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Ref. refers to the reference individual.					

Table L.5: The determinants of next period’s labour-market state: men aged 65-69, 2003-2015.

Dependent variable:	<i>Wage – earner_t</i>	<i>Independent_t</i>	<i>Unregistered_t</i>	<i>Unemployed_t</i>	<i>Inactive_t</i>
<i>Intercept</i>	10.2364 ***	-218.2 *	0.8971 ***	-0.6694**	-4.1454 ***
<i>Pension_{t-1}</i>	-0.7958***	-0.4291 ***	-0.6555 ***	-0.9874 ***	1.0898 ***
<i>Spouse's pension_t</i>	-0.8137***	-0.4151 *	-0.4270 **	-1.9978 ***	1.0445 ***
<i>Primary education_t</i>	Ref.	-1.5656 ***	0.3516 ***	0.3715	0.6416 ***
<i>Secondary education_t</i>	0.2398 **	-0.9560 ***	0.2712 **	-0.2248	0.5661 ***
<i>Tertiary education_t</i>	0.2027	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Age</i>	-0.1427 ***	6.6815 *			0.0750 ***
<i>Age²</i>		-0.0505 *			
<i>Single_t</i>	-0.4419	0.3406		Ref.	
<i>Married_t</i>	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	0.000865	Ref.
<i>Divorced_t</i>	-0.5798 *	0.8384 **		-0.2787	
<i>Common – law_t</i>	0.3793 ***	-0.6187 ***		0.0515	
<i>Widowed_t</i>	-0.0472	0.1454		-0.7317 ***	
<i>No partner_{t-1}</i>	0.0212	-2.5092 ***	-0.6644 ***	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Wage – earner partner_{t-1}</i>		-2.2132 ***	-1.1575 ***	-0.2831	0.3267 ***
<i>Independent partner_{t-1}</i>	-0.6144 **	Ref.	-1.6700 ***	-14.2182	-0.7560 ***
<i>Unregistered partner_{t-1}</i>	-0.3811 **	-2.4300 ***	Ref.	-0.4923	-0.5951 ***
<i>Unemployed partner_{t-1}</i>	-0.1284	-1.5843 ***	-1.0010 ***	1.9827 ***	-1.3737 ***
<i>Inactive partner_{t-1}</i>	-0.1588	-1.9269 ***	-0.7557 ***	-0.8780 ***	0.0958
<i>Q1_{t-1} × Wage – earner_{t-1} = 1</i>	Ref.			-2.4483 **	0.4615 ***
<i>Q1_{t-1} × Wage – earner_{t-1} = 0</i>	-3.9742 ***	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q2_{t-1} × Wage – earner_{t-1} = 1</i>	4.6097 ***		-0.9523 ***		
<i>Q2_{t-1} × Wage – earner_{t-1} = 0</i>	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q3_{t-1} × Wage – earner_{t-1} = 1</i>	4.8504 ***	-0.7870 **	-1.4011 ***	-2.2909 **	
<i>Q3_{t-1} × Wage – earner_{t-1} = 0</i>	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q4_{t-1} × Wage – earner_{t-1} = 1</i>	4.8262 ***	-0.8419 ***	-1.1557 ***	-2.7779 **	
<i>Q4_{t-1} × Wage – earner_{t-1} = 0</i>	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q1_{t-1} × Independent_{t-1} = 1</i>		Ref.	0.6315 ***		1.0431 ***
Source: Author’s Calculation based on EPHc microdata, 2003-2015. * Significant at 10%. ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Ref. refers to the reference individual.					

Dependent variable:	<i>Wage – earner_t</i>	<i>Independent_t</i>	<i>Unregistered_t</i>	<i>Unemployed_t</i>	<i>Inactive_t</i>
<i>Q</i> _{1_{t-1}} × <i>Independent</i> _{t-1} = 0	Ref.	-2.9106 ***		Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q</i> _{2_{t-1}} × <i>Independent</i> _{t-1} = 1	-1.2657 *	3.4490 ***			0.7378 ***
<i>Q</i> _{2_{t-1}} × <i>Independent</i> _{t-1} = 0	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q</i> _{3_{t-1}} × <i>Independent</i> _{t-1} = 1	0.9252 ***	3.4316 ***			0.4138 **
<i>Q</i> _{3_{t-1}} × <i>Independent</i> _{t-1} = 0	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q</i> _{4_{t-1}} × <i>Independent</i> _{t-1} = 1	0.7496 ***	3.7060 ***			
<i>Q</i> _{4_{t-1}} × <i>Independent</i> _{t-1} = 0	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q</i> _{1_{t-1}} × <i>Unregistered</i> _{t-1} = 1			Ref.		1.2913 ***
<i>Q</i> _{1_{t-1}} × <i>Unregistered</i> _{t-1} = 0	Ref.	Ref.	-1.7553 ***	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q</i> _{2_{t-1}} × <i>Unregistered</i> _{t-1} = 1			1.6990 ***	0.8367 ***	1.3040 ***
<i>Q</i> _{2_{t-1}} × <i>Unregistered</i> _{t-1} = 0	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q</i> _{3_{t-1}} × <i>Unregistered</i> _{t-1} = 1	0.4201 *	0.7503 ***	1.6106 ***	0.8323 ***	1.2097 ***
<i>Q</i> _{3_{t-1}} × <i>Unregistered</i> _{t-1} = 0	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q</i> _{4_{t-1}} × <i>Unregistered</i> _{t-1} = 1	0.9091 ***	0.9522 ***	1.9879 ***		0.7044 ***
<i>Q</i> _{4_{t-1}} × <i>Unregistered</i> _{t-1} = 0	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Unemployed</i> _{t-1} = 1				Ref.	2.0713 ***
<i>Unemployed</i> _{t-1} = 0	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	-2.5780 ***	Ref.
<i>Inactive</i> _{t-1} = 1	-0.5191 ***	-0.8878 ***	-0.8953 ***		Ref.
<i>Inactive</i> _{t-1} = 0	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	-3.8835 ***
AUC training dataset	0.9418	0.9032	0.8425	0.7948	0.8938
AUC validation dataset	0.9499	0.9057	0.8210	0.7586	0.8950
Observations	15297	15297	15297	15297	15297

*Q*_{*k*_{*t*}} is the *k*th sectoral labour-income quartile. It is computed separately among wage-earners, independent and unregistered (informal) workers. Pension is computed as a percentage of the period's gross mean wage, the RIPTE.

Source: Author's Calculation based on EPHc microdata, 2003-2015. * Significant at 10%. ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Ref. refers to the reference individual.

Table L.6: The determinants of next period's labour-market state: women aged 60-69, 2003-2015.

Dependent variable:	<i>Wage – earner_t</i>	<i>Independent_t</i>	<i>Unregistered_t</i>	<i>Unemployed_t</i>	<i>Inactive_t</i>
<i>Intercept</i>	10.2364 ***	-218.2 *	0.8971 ***	-0.6694**	-4.1454 ***
<i>Pension</i> _{t-1}	-0.7958***	-0.4291 ***	-0.6555 ***	-0.9874 ***	1.0898 ***
<i>Spouse's pension</i> _{<i>t</i>}	-0.8137***	-0.4151 *	-0.4270 **	-1.9978 ***	1.0445 ***
<i>Primary education</i> _{<i>t</i>}	Ref.	-1.5656 ***	0.3516 ***	0.3715	0.6416 ***
<i>Secondary education</i> _{<i>t</i>}	0.2398 **	-0.9560 ***	0.2712 **	-0.2248	0.5661 ***

Source and variables: see Table L.1. * Significant at 10%. ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Ref. refers to the reference individual.

Dependent variable:	<i>Wage – earner_t</i>	<i>Independent_t</i>	<i>Unregistered_t</i>	<i>Unemployed_t</i>	<i>Inactive_t</i>
<i>Tertiary education_t</i>	0.2027	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Age</i>	-0.1427 ***	6.6815 *			0.0750 ***
<i>Age²</i>		-0.0505 *			
<i>Single_t</i>	-0.4419	0.3406		Ref.	
<i>Married_t</i>	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	0.000865	Ref.
<i>Divorced_t</i>	-0.5798 *	0.8384 **		-0.2787	
<i>Common – law_t</i>	0.3793 ***	-0.6187 ***		0.0515	
<i>Widowed_t</i>	-0.0472	0.1454		-0.7317 ***	
<i>No partner_{t-1}</i>	0.0212	-2.5092 ***	-0.6644 ***	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Wage – earner partner_{t-1}</i>		-2.2132 ***	-1.1575 ***	-0.2831	0.3267 ***
<i>Independent partner_{t-1}</i>	-0.6144 **	Ref.	-1.6700 ***	-14.2182	-0.7560 ***
<i>Unregistered partner_{t-1}</i>	-0.3811 **	-2.4300 ***	Ref.	-0.4923	-0.5951 ***
<i>Unemployed partner_{t-1}</i>	-0.1284	-1.5843 ***	-1.0010 ***	1.9827 ***	-1.3737 ***
<i>Inactive partner_{t-1}</i>	-0.1588	-1.9269 ***	-0.7557 ***	-0.8780 ***	0.0958
<i>Q1_{t-1} × Wage – earner_{t-1} = 1</i>	Ref.			-2.4483 **	0.4615 ***
<i>Q1_{t-1} × Wage – earner_{t-1} = 0</i>	-3.9742 ***	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q2_{t-1} × Wage – earner_{t-1} = 1</i>	4.6097 ***		-0.9523 ***		
<i>Q2_{t-1} × Wage – earner_{t-1} = 0</i>	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q3_{t-1} × Wage – earner_{t-1} = 1</i>	4.8504 ***	-0.7870 **	-1.4011 ***	-2.2909 **	
<i>Q3_{t-1} × Wage – earner_{t-1} = 0</i>	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q4_{t-1} × Wage – earner_{t-1} = 1</i>	4.8262 ***	-0.8419 ***	-1.1557 ***	-2.7779 **	
<i>Q4_{t-1} × Wage – earner_{t-1} = 0</i>	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q1_{t-1} × Independent_{t-1} = 1</i>		Ref.	0.6315 ***		1.0431 ***
<i>Q1_{t-1} × Independent_{t-1} = 0</i>	Ref.	-2.9106 ***		Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q2_{t-1} × Independent_{t-1} = 1</i>	-1.2657 *	3.4490 ***			0.7378 ***
<i>Q2_{t-1} × Independent_{t-1} = 0</i>	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q3_{t-1} × Independent_{t-1} = 1</i>	0.9252 ***	3.4316 ***			0.4138 **
<i>Q3_{t-1} × Independent_{t-1} = 0</i>	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q4_{t-1} × Independent_{t-1} = 1</i>	0.7496 ***	3.7060 ***			
<i>Q4_{t-1} × Independent_{t-1} = 0</i>	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q1_{t-1} × Unregistered_{t-1} = 1</i>			Ref.		1.2913 ***
<i>Q1_{t-1} × Unregistered_{t-1} = 0</i>	Ref.	Ref.	-1.7553 ***	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q2_{t-1} × Unregistered_{t-1} = 1</i>			1.6990 ***	0.8367 ***	1.3040 ***
<i>Q2_{t-1} × Unregistered_{t-1} = 0</i>	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.

Source and variables: see Table L.1. * Significant at 10%. ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Ref. refers to the reference individual.

Dependent variable:	<i>Wage – earner_t</i>	<i>Independent_t</i>	<i>Unregistered_t</i>	<i>Unemployed_t</i>	<i>Inactive_t</i>
<i>Q</i> _{3_{t-1}} × <i>Unregistered_{t-1}</i> = 1	0.4201 *	0.7503 ***	1.6106 ***	0.8323 ***	1.2097 ***
<i>Q</i> _{3_{t-1}} × <i>Unregistered_{t-1}</i> = 0	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q</i> _{4_{t-1}} × <i>Unregistered_{t-1}</i> = 1	0.9091 ***	0.9522 ***	1.9879 ***		0.7044 ***
<i>Q</i> _{4_{t-1}} × <i>Unregistered_{t-1}</i> = 0	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Unemployed_{t-1}</i> = 1				Ref.	2.0713 ***
<i>Unemployed_{t-1}</i> = 0	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	-2.5780 ***	Ref.
<i>Inactive_{t-1}</i> = 1	-0.5191 ***	-0.8878 ***	-0.8953 ***		Ref.
<i>Inactive_{t-1}</i> = 0	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	-3.8835 ***
AUC training dataset	0.9650	0.9379	0.8631	0.7896	0.9111
AUC validation dataset	0.9643	0.9204	0.8509	0.7479	0.9018
Observations	43493	43493	43493	43493	43493

Source and variables: see Table L.1. * Significant at 10%. ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Ref. refers to the reference individual.

Table L.7: The determinants of the previous period’s labour-market state: men aged 65-69, 2003-2015.

Dependent variable:	<i>Wage – earner_{t-1}</i>	<i>Independent_{t-1}</i>	<i>Unregistered_{t-1}</i>	<i>Unemployed_{t-1}</i>	<i>Inactive_{t-1}</i>
<i>Intercept</i>	-12.5827***	-1.6894	-6.2676***	-2.1667***	12.7653***
<i>Primary education_{t-1}</i>	-0.4391***	-1.6582***	0.6665***		0.3186***
<i>Secondary education_{t-1}</i>	-0.1212	-0.8147***	0.3575***		0.3081***
<i>Tertiary education_{t-1}</i>	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Age_{t-1}</i>	0.5709***	0.0433***	0.2689***		-0.4720***
<i>Age_{t-1}²</i>	-0.00550***		-0.00252***		0.00449***
<i>Single_{t-1}</i>		Ref.	-0.0147	Ref.	0.3514*
<i>Married_{t-1}</i>	Ref.	0.7580*	-0.2508***	0.7818**	Ref.
<i>Divorced_{t-1}</i>		0.4891	0.2213	0.6036**	-0.1418
<i>Common – law_{t-1}</i>		1.1563***	Ref.	1.1826***	-0.3903***
<i>Widowed_{t-1}</i>		0.7290**	0.1120	-0.1209	0.0987
<i>No partner_t</i>		-1.1592***	-0.9115***	0.9499***	Ref.
<i>Wage – earner partner_t</i>	Ref.	-0.7147***	-0.6033***	-0.0755	-0.1570
<i>Independent partner_t</i>		Ref.	-1.4885***	-13.5277	-0.4581*
<i>Unregistered partner_t</i>		-1.4051***	Ref.	0.7254***	-0.6212***
<i>Unemployed partner_t</i>		-0.8499*	-1.4515***	1.8501***	-0.2835
<i>Inactive partner_t</i>		-1.3501***	-0.7886***	Ref.	0.2956*
<i>Q</i> _{1_t} × <i>Wage – earner_t</i> = 1			-0.5514***		1.3891***
<i>Q</i> _{1_t} × <i>Wage – earner_t</i> = 0	-3.7985***	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q</i> _{2_t} × <i>Wage – earner_t</i> = 1	5.0398***	-1.5398**	-1.3926***		
<i>Q</i> _{2_t} × <i>Wage – earner_t</i> = 0	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q</i> _{3_t} × <i>Wage – earner_t</i> = 1	4.4160***		-0.8188***		0.4991*
<i>Q</i> _{3_t} × <i>Wage – earner_t</i> = 0	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q</i> _{4_t} × <i>Wage – earner_t</i> = 1	4.8955***		-1.5754***		

Source: Author’s Calculation based on EPHc microdata, 2003-2015. * Significant at 10%. ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Ref. refers to the reference individual.

Dependent variable:	<i>Wage – earner</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	<i>Independent</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	<i>Unregistered</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	<i>Unemployed</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	<i>Inactive</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}
<i>Q</i> ₄ × <i>Wage – earner</i> _{<i>t</i> = 0}	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q</i> ₁ × <i>Independent</i> _{<i>t</i> = 1}			0.4760**		1.5646***
<i>Q</i> ₁ × <i>Independent</i> _{<i>t</i> = 0}	Ref.	-3.5062***	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q</i> ₂ × <i>Independent</i> _{<i>t</i> = 1}		4.3237***			1.0778***
<i>Q</i> ₂ × <i>Independent</i> _{<i>t</i> = 0}	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q</i> ₃ × <i>Independent</i> _{<i>t</i> = 1}		4.4411***			1.0669***
<i>Q</i> ₃ × <i>Independent</i> _{<i>t</i> = 0}	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q</i> ₄ × <i>Independent</i> _{<i>t</i> = 1}		4.4841***			
<i>Q</i> ₄ × <i>Independent</i> _{<i>t</i> = 0}	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q</i> ₁ × <i>Unregistered</i> _{<i>t</i> = 1}		1.0635***	Ref.		2.3384***
<i>Q</i> ₁ × <i>Unregistered</i> _{<i>t</i> = 0}	Ref.	Ref.	-1.4448***	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q</i> ₂ × <i>Unregistered</i> _{<i>t</i> = 1}		1.4922***	1.8238***		1.9165***
<i>Q</i> ₂ × <i>Unregistered</i> _{<i>t</i> = 0}	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q</i> ₃ × <i>Unregistered</i> _{<i>t</i> = 1}	0.3584*	1.5454***	1.7426***		1.8383***
<i>Q</i> ₃ × <i>Unregistered</i> _{<i>t</i> = 0}	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Q</i> ₄ × <i>Unregistered</i> _{<i>t</i> = 1}	0.7388***	1.7353***	1.8114***		1.5585***
<i>Q</i> ₄ × <i>Unregistered</i> _{<i>t</i> = 0}	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Unemployed</i> _{<i>t</i> = 1}		0.8191***		Ref.	2.8946***
<i>Unemployed</i> _{<i>t</i> = 0}	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	-2.6441***	Ref.
<i>Inactive</i> _{<i>t</i> = 1}	-0.6258***		-0.8823***		Ref.
<i>Inactive</i> _{<i>t</i> = 0}	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	-4.7552***
AUC training dataset	0.9181	0.8976	0.8135	0.7490	0.8753
AUC validation dataset	0.9002	0.8710	0.8334	0.7115	0.8702
Observations	15116	15116	15116	15116	15116

Source: Author’s Calculation based on EPHc microdata, 2003-2015. * Significant at 10%. ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Ref. refers to the reference individual.

Table L.8: The determinants of the previous period’s labour-market state: women aged 60-69, 2003-2015.

Dependent variable:	<i>Wage – earner</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	<i>Independent</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	<i>Unregistered</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	<i>Unemployed</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	<i>Inactive</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}
<i>Intercept</i>	3.8351***	1.9350***	-1.0664	-8.1499***	2.6856**
<i>Primary education</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	-1.1294***	-1.9071***	0.8336***	0.00148	0.303***
<i>Secondary education</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	-0.9058***	-1.0457***	0.6496***	0.2390	0.3077***
<i>Tertiary education</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
<i>Age</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	-0.0330***		0.0587	0.2589***	-0.0709**
<i>Age</i> _{<i>t</i>-1} ²			-0.00062**	-0.00255***	0.000867***
<i>Single</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	Ref.	Ref.	-0.0210	Ref.	-0.0995
<i>Married</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	0.4986**		-0.2352***	-0.7177**	Ref.
<i>Divorced</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	0.1856		-0.0647	0.1743	-0.2683**
<i>Common – law</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	0.5313**		Ref.	0.3658	-0.3850***
<i>Widowed</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	-0.1511		-0.3727***	-0.3927***	0.2776**
<i>No partner</i> _{<i>t</i>}	0.3128	-1.0525***	-0.2690**	1.0024***	Ref.
<i>Wage – earner partner</i> _{<i>t</i>}	Ref.	-1.2309***	-0.4845***	0.8866***	0.2951**
<i>Independent partner</i> _{<i>t</i>}	-0.7892***	Ref.	-0.4169***	0.8861***	0.0192
<i>Unregistered partner</i> _{<i>t</i>}	-0.4694***	-1.6277***	Ref.	0.2722	0.1318
<i>Unemployed partner</i> _{<i>t</i>}	-0.4214	-1.2958***	-0.0678	1.6624***	-0.0769
<i>Inactive partner</i> _{<i>t</i>}	-0.6725***	-1.4159***	-0.8123***	Ref.	0.8671***
<i>Q</i> ₁ × <i>Wage – earner</i> _{<i>t</i> = 1}	Ref.	Ref.	-0.5647***	2.8025***	0.7313***

Source and variables: see Table L.1. * Significant at 10%. ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Ref. refers to the reference individual.

Dependent variable:	$Wage - earner_{t-1}$	$Independent_t$	$Unregistered_t$	$Unemployed_{t-1}$	$Inactive_{t-1}$
$Q1_t \times Wage - earner_t = 0$	-4.7967***		Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q2_t \times Wage - earner_t = 1$	5.6448***		-1.4566***		
$Q2_t \times Wage - earner_t = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q3_t \times Wage - earner_t = 1$	6.1616***		-2.7458***		
$Q3_t \times Wage - earner_t = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q4_t \times Wage - earner_t = 1$	5.9224***		-2.6077***		
$Q4_t \times Wage - earner_t = 0$	Ref.			Ref.	Ref.
$Q1_t \times Independent_t = 1$		Ref.	Ref.	4.1551***	2.3970***
$Q1_t \times Independent_t = 0$	Ref.	-4.6637***		Ref.	Ref.
$Q2_t \times Independent_t = 1$		4.6978***		3.5763***	1.6788***
		"			
$Q2_t \times Independent_t = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q3_t \times Independent_t = 1$		4.9216***			1.2219***
$Q3_t \times Independent_t = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q4_t \times Independent_t = 1$	1.3508***	4.5218***			0.9482***
$Q4_t \times Independent_t = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q1_t \times Unregistered_t = 1$		0.9785***	Ref.	4.5434***	2.5376***
$Q1_t \times Unregistered_t = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	-1.3898***	Ref.	Ref.
$Q2_t \times Unregistered_t = 1$	0.6839***	1.3565***	1.7797***	4.2286***	2.0019***
$Q2_t \times Unregistered_t = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q3_t \times Unregistered_t = 1$	1.1643***	1.7137***	1.9865***	4.4858***	1.5055***
$Q3_t \times Unregistered_t = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Q4_t \times Unregistered_t = 1$	1.5673***	2.6051***	1.7151***		1.6390***
$Q4_t \times Unregistered_t = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
$Unemployed_t = 1$		1.4994***		Ref.	3.1651***
$Unemployed_t = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	-6.5962***	Ref.
$Inactive_t = 1$	-0.5468***	0.4391**	-1.5997***	3.9308***	Ref.
$Inactive_t = 0$	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	-5.3756***
AUC training dataset	0.9526	0.9143	0.8380	0.7561	0.8889
AUC validation dataset	0.9485	0.9031	0.8331	0.7587	0.8874
Observations	42984	42984	42984	42984	42984

Source and variables: see Table L.1. * Significant at 10%. ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Ref. refers to the reference individual.

Appendix M

Mincer wage equations

Table M.1: Forward Mincer wage equations: men aged 16-64, 2003-2015

Age group	Labour-market state				Formation				Seniority (months)					
	Wage-earner	Own-account worker	Unregistered worker	Incomplete secondary	Complete secondary	University degree	[0; 3]]3; 6]]6; 12]]12; 60]	More than 5 years			
<i>Age</i> ∈ [16; 20[-	0.8476***	0.9491***	-	-	-	0.1686***	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Age</i> ∈ [20; 25[0.1067***	-	0.5823***	0.2820***	-	-	0.1676***	-	0.0473***	0.0380***	0.0818***	-	-	-
<i>Age</i> ∈ [25; 30[-	0.4184***	0.6242***	0.0967***	0.1991***	0.2537***	-	0.1804***	-	-	0.0622***	-	-	-
<i>Age</i> ∈ [30; 35[-	0.2508***	0.6454***	-	0.1543***	0.4071***	-	-	0.0355***	-	0.0773***	-	-	-
<i>Age</i> ∈ [35; 40[-	0.1743***	0.6498***	-	0.1842***	0.4240***	0.1833***	0.0333***	-	0.0120**	0.0983***	-	-	-
<i>Age</i> ∈ [40; 45[-	0.1294***	0.6631***	-	0.1794***	0.4084***	0.1656***	-	0.0378***	0.0214***	0.1221***	-	-	-
<i>Age</i> ∈ [45; 50[-	0.1095***	0.6872***	-	0.2067***	0.4522***	0.1825***	-	-	-	0.1173***	-	-	-
<i>Age</i> ∈ [50; 55[-	0.1093***	0.6901***	-	0.2555***	0.4780***	0.2144***	-	-	-	0.0861***	-	-	-
<i>Age</i> ∈ [55; 60[0.1228***	0.0992***	0.5896***	-	0.2451***	0.4902***	0.2663***	0.0783***	0.1949***	0.0163**	-	-	-	-
<i>Age</i> ∈ [60; 65[0.1302***	-	0.6187***	-	0.2065***	0.4299***	0.4250***	0.2091***	-	-	0.0357***	-	-	-
							0.3943***	0.1883***	0.1798***	0.1805***				
Intercept -0.5709***														

Reading example: a male formal wage-earner aged between 20 and 24, surveyed during the second quarter of 2015, with incomplete secondary education and a seniority of 3 months at most has a net wage equal to $\exp(-0.5709 + 0.1067 - 0.2820 - 0.1676) \times \text{coefficient}_{h,2015-Q2} \approx 43\%$ of the RIPE. If we take the RIPE from February 2015, 12,410.76 pesos, this amounts to a net wage of 5374 pesos, around 619 US\$. The structural coefficient $\text{coefficient}_{h,2015-Q2}$ is taken from Table M.9

Table M.2: Forward Mincer wage equations: women aged 16-59, 2003-2015

Age group	Labour-market state					Formation				Seniority				
	Wage-earner	Own-account worker	Unregistered worker	Incomplete secondary	Complete secondary	University degree	[0; 3]]3; 6]]6; 12]]12; 60]	More than 5 years			
Age ∈ [16; 20[-	0.9327***	-	0.9019***	-	-	0.2215***	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Age ∈ [20; 25[-	0.7681***	-	0.8160***	-	0.0759***	0.2374***	-	0.0270***	-	-	-	-	0.0857***
Age ∈ [25; 30[-	0.4286***	-	0.8146***	-	0.0745***	0.3189***	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.1061***
Age ∈ [30; 35[-	0.3229***	-	0.8753***	-	0.0678***	0.3306***	-	-	-	-	-	0.0614***	0.1724***
Age ∈ [35; 40[-	0.2559***	-	0.8559***	-	0.0886***	0.3073***	-	-	-	-	-	0.0614***	0.1857***
Age ∈ [40; 45[-	0.2205***	-	0.8674***	-	0.1250***	0.2476***	-	-	-	0.0764***	0.0966***	0.1378***	0.2530***
Age ∈ [45; 50[-	0.2040***	-	0.8617***	-	0.2096***	0.2633***	-	-	-	-	-	0.1083***	0.2901***
Age ∈ [50; 55[-	0.2218***	-	0.8481***	-	0.2371***	0.3103***	-	-	-	-	-	0.1188***	0.2792***
Age ∈ [55; 60[-	0.2584***	-	0.8740***	-	0.2524***	0.2837***	-	-	-	-	-	0.0752***	0.2885***
Intercept											-0.5685***			

Table M.3: Backward Mincer wage equations: men aged 16-64, 2003-2015

Agegroup	Labour-market state			Formation		
	Wage-earner	Own-account worker	Unregistered worker	Incomplete secondary	Complete secondary	University degree
<i>Age</i> ∈ [16; 20[- 0.220813***	- 0.922619***	- 1.061647***	- 0.164159***		
<i>Age</i> ∈ [20; 25[0.072100***	- 0.449996***	- 0.650222***	- 0.286429***	- 0.198596***	
<i>Age</i> ∈ [25; 30[- 0.248352***	- 0.659357***	- 0.144183***		0.206708***
<i>Age</i> ∈ [30; 35[- 0.174357***	- 0.686849***	- 0.025079***	0.136250***	0.387723***
<i>Age</i> ∈ [35; 40[- 0.124567***	- 0.692476***		0.196927***	0.434350***
<i>Age</i> ∈ [40; 45[0.031023***	- 0.076763***	- 0.685832***		0.189445***	0.419548***
<i>Age</i> ∈ [45; 50[0.029422***	- 0.080122***	- 0.711298***		0.217063***	0.464767***
<i>Age</i> ∈ [50; 55[- 0.094559***	- 0.738455***		0.267474***	0.493715***
<i>Age</i> ∈ [55; 60[- 0.122326***	- 0.776263***		0.256907***	0.500037***
<i>Age</i> ∈ [60; 65[- 0.122496***	- 0.807726***	-0.016238**	0.257602***	0.480750***
Intercept -0.52115***						

Table M.4: Backward Mincer wage equations: women aged 16-59, 2003-2015

Agegroup	Labour-market state			Formation		
	Wage-earner	Own-account worker	Unregistered worker	Incomplete secondary	Complete secondary	University degree
<i>Age</i> ∈ [16; 20[- 0.927349***	- 0.969731***	- 0.595628***	- 0.348878***	
<i>Age</i> ∈ [20; 25[- 0.762135***	- 0.876890***	- 0.442623***	- 0.260007***	
<i>Age</i> ∈ [25; 30[- 0.148110***	- 0.579787***	- 1.043151***	- 0.267775***		0.247218***
<i>Age</i> ∈ [30; 35[- 0.069209***	- 0.395679***	- 1.042030***	- 0.245070***		0.272622***
<i>Age</i> ∈ [35; 40[- 0.029459***	- 0.287461***	- 0.986964***	- 0.265817***		0.239900***
<i>Age</i> ∈ [40; 45[- 0.029692***	- 0.244427***	- 0.982245***	- 0.255235***		0.265124***
<i>Age</i> ∈ [45; 50[- 0.212609***	- 0.971356***	- 0.258699***		0.279927***
<i>Age</i> ∈ [50; 55[- 0.225404***	- 0.949373***	- 0.286072***		0.330371***
<i>Age</i> ∈ [55; 60[- 0.252723***	- 0.975866***	- 0.295741***		0.308477***
Intercept -0.338495 *						

Table M.5: Forward Mincer wage equations: men aged 65-69, 2003-2015

Age group	Labour-market state				Formation				Seniority (months)			
	Wage-earner	Own-account worker	Unregistered worker	Incomplete secondary	Complete secondary	University degree	[0; 3]]3; 6]]6; 12]]12; 60]	More than 5 years	
Age = 65		-	0.794422***	-	0.201644***		-	0.216970***			0.167858***	
Age = 66		-	0.780616***	-	0.129785***		-	0.371975***			0.110255***	
Age = 67		-	0.819631***	-	0.272661***	0.215360***	-	0.515953***	-	0.624811***	-	
Age = 68	0.156276***		0.737593***	-	0.221867***		-	0.333434***	-	0.286668***		
Age = 69		-	0.949358***	-	0.278123***	0.141709***	-	0.389636***	-	0.289621***		
Intercept -0.265896***												

Reading example: a male unregistered worker aged 65, surveyed during the second quarter of 2015, with incomplete secondary education and a seniority of 3 months at most has a net wage equal to $\exp(-0.794422 - 0.467708 - 0.216970 - 0.265896) \times \text{coefficient}_{h,2015-Q2} \approx 19\%$ of the RIPTÉ. If we take the RIPTÉ from February 2015, 12,410.76 pesos, this amounts to a net wage of 2340.45 pesos or around 270 US\$ at the time. The structural coefficient $\text{coefficient}_{h,2015-Q2}$ is taken from Table M.9

Table M.6: Forward Mincer wage equations: women aged 60-69, 2003-2015

Age group	Labour-market state				Formation			Seniority				
	Wage-earner	Own-account worker	Unregistered worker	Incomplete second-ary	Complete second-ary	University degree	[0; 3]	[3; 6]	[6; 12]]12; 60]	More than 5 years	
Age = 60	0.829753***	0.661561***		0.233786***	0.549006***						0.288840***	
Age = 61	0.843986***	0.726169***		0.289086***	0.617127***						0.206643***	
Age = 62	0.929473***	0.645584***		0.267575***	0.513271***						0.184767***	
Age = 63	0.977416***	0.815583***		0.190516***	0.450580***						0.227803***	
Age = 64	1.014697***	0.571714***	- 0.108634***	- 0.088451***	0.252750***	0.497386***		- 0.647043***			0.209676***	
Age = 65	1.109104***	0.656392***		0.178429***	0.285721***	0.285721***					0.283217***	
Age = 66	0.973606***	0.372690***		0.208127***	0.374314***	0.374314***		- 0.602344***			0.419863***	
Age = 67	1.063070***	0.455823***		0.215103***	0.359348***	0.359348***					0.260992***	
Age = 68	1.156335***	0.935691***		0.160144***							0.227251***	
Age = 69	1.198301***	0.827900***		0.303823***	0.321255***	0.321255***					0.198191***	
Intercept -1.674574***												

Table M.7: Backward Mincer wage equations: men aged 65-69, 2003-2015

Agegroup	Labour-market state			Formation		
	Wage-earner	Own-account worker	Unregistered worker	Incomplete secondary	Complete secondary	University degree
Age = 65			-0.854072 ***	-0.295363 ***		0.172847 ***
Age = 66		-0.107882 ***	-0.832911 ***	-0.347607 ***		0.140001 ***
Age = 67		-0.207766 ***	-0.898882 ***	-0.284293 ***		0.218057 ***
Age = 68	0.136674 ***		-0.827139 ***	-0.491713 ***	-0.223984 ***	
Age = 69		-0.216034 ***	-1.009800 ***	-0.290140 ***		0.153883 ***
Intercept -0.306073***						

Table M.8: Backward Mincer wage equations: women aged 60-69, 2003-2015

Agegroup	Labour-market state			Formation		
	Wage-earner	Own-account worker	Unregistered worker	Incomplete secondary	Complete secondary	University degree
Age = 60	0.943453 ***	0.776734 ***			0.279157 ***	0.606020 ***
Age = 61	0.911161 ***	0.796114 ***			0.310220 ***	0.645368 ***
Age = 62	0.990238 ***	0.704343 ***			0.274457 ***	0.534429 ***
Age = 63	0.970349 ***	0.813016 ***	-0.102817 ***		0.312767 ***	0.575643 ***
Age = 64	1.231571 ***	0.782904 ***		-0.135180 ***	0.142008 ***	0.381300 ***
Age = 65	1.253209 ***	0.790963 ***		-0.192599 ***		0.305086 ***
Age = 66	1.169145 ***	0.574793 ***		-0.174769 ***		0.487652 ***
Age = 67	1.192556 ***	0.585450 ***		-0.217159 ***		0.400284 ***
Age = 68	1.254222 ***	1.038754 ***		-0.152874 ***		
Age = 69	1.278628 ***	0.919121 ***		-0.310087 ***		0.327427 ***
Intercept -1.591622***						

Table M.9: Structural coefficients for Mincer wage equations

Year	Quarter	Structural coefficient, men	Structural coefficient, women
		$structure_{m,t}$	$structure_{f,t}$
2017	1	1.0658189304	0.9011326229
2016	4	1.0774074127	0.8865355153
2016	3	1.0823447811	0.8813969299
2016	2	1.0794219101	0.8831172402
2016	1	1.0795169208	0.8827987176
2015	4	1.0796119316	0.8824801951
2015	3	1.0797069423	0.8821616725
2015	2	1.079801953	0.8818431499
2015	1	1.0739248409	0.8925263734

Source: own computation on EPH (1974-2015).

Year	Quarter	Structural coefficient, men <i>structure_{m,t}</i>	Structural coefficient, women <i>structure_{f,t}</i>
2014	4	1.0811822812	0.8850201169
2014	3	1.0767573114	0.8877953844
2014	2	1.08963022	0.867126843
2014	1	1.070925944	0.894633394
2013	4	1.0837064262	0.8783211344
2013	3	1.0763190249	0.8863654913
2013	2	1.0792243131	0.8827961813
2013	1	1.0692173049	0.8978844637
2012	4	1.0674866046	0.8998874052
2012	3	1.0833637538	0.8766965249
2012	2	1.0763828182	0.8910213593
2012	1	1.0649462744	0.9052240589
2011	4	1.0689029019	0.8972078182
2011	3	1.0828648208	0.8784729895
2011	2	1.0807535862	0.8805376283
2011	1	1.0704188098	0.8926435188
2010	4	1.0842631717	0.8759431843
2010	3	1.1000888431	0.8543110851
2010	2	1.0865212214	0.8741532362
2010	1	1.0714342877	0.8969866866
2009	4	1.0780967728	0.8887008066
2009	3	1.0851263488	0.8786382013
2009	2	1.0803280593	0.8853148718
2009	1	1.085197341	0.8808973225
2008	4	1.0948690758	0.8647644639
2008	3	1.0949014248	0.8602820281
2008	2	1.0924492688	0.8667132083
2008	1	1.1065908561	0.8445580529
2008-2017 average(projections)		1.0805271538	0.8823483750
2007	4	1.1024754622	0.8508521254
2007	3	1.1027355179	0.8498312636
2007	2	1.1029955736	0.8488104017
2007	1	1.1083953501	0.8401877331
2006	4	1.0944374536	0.8643022859
2006	3	1.0909085153	0.8695160845
2006	2	1.1187709784	0.8301017404
2006	1	1.1206122363	0.8267580065
2005	4	1.1038913411	0.8514612228
2005	3	1.0969816175	0.85667666
2005	2	1.1112565012	0.8374662894
2005	1	1.1136472539	0.8310602557
2004	4	1.1096403104	0.8415939012
2004	3	1.1051796808	0.8506528576
2004	2	1.124171275	0.8269748945
2004	1	1.1169741588	0.8325531138
2003	4	1.1051237592	0.8481228824
2003	3	1.1097214814	0.8519405867
2003	2	1.114401889	0.8355841577
2003	1	1.1068797119	0.843061743
2002	4	1.0993575348	0.8505393283
2002	3	1.0880747711	0.8671672042
2002	2	1.0767920074	0.88379508
2002	1	1.0826064854	0.8739792574
2001	4	1.0884209633	0.8641634347
2001	3	1.0891380224	0.8624177746
2001	2	1.0898550814	0.8606721144
2001	1	1.0856922338	0.8647697299
2000	4	1.0815293862	0.8688673453
2000	3	1.0850947795	0.8637071638
2000	2	1.0886601728	0.8585469822
2000	1	1.0938508768	0.850577323
1999	4	1.0990415807	0.8426076638
1999	3	1.0931809663	0.851445636
1999	2	1.0873203518	0.8602836082
1999	1	1.0970204874	0.8421697849
1998	4	1.1067206229	0.8240559615
1998	3	1.1017187512	0.8330773837

Source: own computation on EPH (1974-2015).

Year	Quarter	Structural coefficient, men <i>structure_{m,t}</i>	Structural coefficient, women <i>structure_{f,t}</i>
1998	2	1.0967168795	0.8420988059
1998	1	1.0922732948	0.8449716626
1997	4	1.0878297101	0.8478445193
1997	3	1.0919416867	0.840628736
1997	2	1.0960536633	0.8334129526
1997	1	1.0958249451	0.8330410352
1996	4	1.0955962269	0.8326691177
1996	3	1.0955553896	0.8317536472
1996	2	1.0955145523	0.8308381767
1996	1	1.0985412689	0.828039691
1995	4	1.1015679855	0.8252412052
1995	3	1.0970647735	0.8329285461
1995	2	1.0925615614	0.840615887
1995	1	1.0942273908	0.834832858
1994	4	1.0958932201	0.829049829
1994	3	1.1020882105	0.8184303918
1994	2	1.1082832008	0.8078109546
1994	1	1.1037531813	0.8149304033
1993	4	1.0992231618	0.822049852
1993	3	1.1104206104	0.8070251422
1993	2	1.1216180589	0.7920004324
1993	1	1.1080579249	0.8111746273
1992	4	1.0944977909	0.8303488222
1992	3	1.0944519936	0.8282437824
1992	2	1.0944061962	0.8261387426
1992	1	1.0847919715	0.8440093411
1991	4	1.0751777468	0.8618799396
1991	3	1.0739520846	0.8630588136
1991	2	1.0727264223	0.8642376876
1991	1	1.0791625224	0.8544004596
1990	4	1.0855986224	0.8445632315
1990	3	1.0796163982	0.8519652727
1990	2	1.0736341739	0.8593673138
1990	1	1.0924250567	0.8172550817
1989	4	1.1112159394	0.7751428496
1989	3	1.1234435604	0.7596565559
1989	2	1.1356711814	0.7441702621
1989	1	1.1303125204	0.7513155567
1988	4	1.1249538594	0.7584608512
1988	3	1.1223471468	0.7607772737
1988	2	1.1197404341	0.7630936962
1988	1	1.1173030409	0.7591120749
1987	4	1.1148656476	0.7551304536
1987	3	1.1258929775	0.7362759353
1987	2	1.1369203074	0.717421417
1987	1	1.1288857636	0.7370688823
1986	4	1.1208512198	0.7567163475
1986	3	1.1121794963	0.7729992664
1986	2	1.1035077728	0.7892821854
1986	1	1.0948360492	0.8055651043
1985	4	1.0861643257	0.8218480232
1985	3	1.0878268931	0.8170213835
1985	2	1.0894894606	0.8121947438
1985	1	1.091152028	0.8073681041
1984	4	1.0928145954	0.8025414644
1984	3	1.0978022977	0.7880615452
1984	2	1.0961397303	0.792888185
1984	1	1.0978022977	0.7880615452
1983	4	1.0994648651	0.7832349055
1983	3	1.1011274325	0.7784082658
1983	2	1.10279	0.7735816261
1983	1	1.1048682092	0.7675483265
1982	4	1.1061151348	0.7639283467
1982	3	1.0887888594	0.8017465054
1982	2	1.0714625841	0.8395646641
1982	1	1.0541363087	0.8773828228
1981	4	1.0368100333	0.9152009815

Source: own computation on EPH (1974-2015).

Year	Quarter	Structural coefficient, men <i>structure_{m,t}</i>	Structural coefficient, women <i>structure_{f,t}</i>
1981	3	1.0558234569	0.8688707934
1981	2	1.0748368805	0.8225406053
1981	1	1.093850304	0.7762104172
1980	4	1.1128637276	0.7298802291
1980	3	1.1113762854	0.7338301449
1980	2	1.1098888431	0.7377800606
1980	1	1.1084014009	0.7417299764
1979	4	1.1069139587	0.7456798921
1979	3	1.1054265164	0.7496298079
1979	2	1.1039390742	0.7535797237
1979	1	1.102451632	0.7575296394
1978	4	1.1009641897	0.7614795552
1978	3	1.0994767475	0.7654294709
1978	2	1.0979893053	0.7693793867
1978	1	1.096501863	0.7733293024
1977	4	1.0950144208	0.7772792182
1977	3	1.0935269786	0.781229134
1977	2	1.0920395363	0.7851790497
1977	1	1.0905520941	0.7891289655
1976	4	1.0890646519	0.7930788812
1976	3	1.0875772096	0.797028797
1976	2	1.0860897674	0.8009787128
1976	1	1.0846023252	0.8049286285
1975	4	1.0831148829	0.8088785443
1975	3	1.0816274407	0.81282846
1975	2	1.0801399985	0.8167783758
1975	1	1.0786525562	0.8207282915
1974	4	1.077165114	0.8246782073
1974	3	1.077165114	0.8246782073
1974	2	1.077165114	0.8246782073
1974	1	1.077165114	0.8246782073

The structural coefficient $structure_{f,t} = (ITL_t - (ITL_{m,t} * N_{m,t}/N_t)) * N_t/N_{f,t}$. $N_{m,t}$, $N_{f,t}$ and N_t respectively stand for the number of working men, women and total working individuals at time t . Similarly, $ITL_{m,t}$, $ITL_{f,t}$ and ITL_t respectively stand for men, women and all workers mean labour income at time t . Values for quarters where the EPH is not carried out are extrapolated from the nearest past and future quarters featuring a wave of the EPH. For periods before 1974 (prior to the creation of the EPH), structural coefficients are equal to 1.

Source: own computation on EPH (1974-2015).

Table M.10: Impact of forward Mincer wage equations coefficients on wages

Compared variables	Age ∈ [16; 20[Age ∈ [20; 25[Age ∈ [25; 30[Age ∈ [30; 35[Age ∈ [35; 40[Age ∈ [40; 45[Age ∈ [45; 50[Age ∈ [50; 55[Age ∈ [55; 60[Age ∈ [60; 65[
Men										
LMS(1) VS LMS(2)	105%	69%	29%	19%	14%	12%	12%	10%	13%	14%
LMS(1) VS LMS(3)	127%	99%	87%	91%	92%	94%	99%	99%	104%	111%
LMS(2) VS LMS(3)	11%	18%	45%	60%	68%	74%	78%	81%	80%	86%
EDU(1) VS EDU(2)	-15%	-8%	-13%	-14%	-17%	-16%	-19%	-23%	-22%	-23%
EDU(1) VS EDU(3)	-15%	-25%	-30%	-33%	-35%	-34%	-36%	-38%	-39%	-39%
EDU(2) VS EDU(3)	0%	-18%	-19%	-22%	-21%	-20%	-22%	-20%	-22%	-20%
SEN(1) VS SEN(2)	-16%	-15%	-17%	-14%	-15%	-17%	-19%	-17%	-19%	-19%
SEN(1) VS SEN(3)	-11%	-15%	-13%	-17%	-12%	-17%	-19%	-23%	-21%	-19%
SEN(1) VS SEN(4)	-16%	-19%	-17%	-17%	-16%	-18%	-19%	-22%	-20%	-19%

Source: own calculus using Tables M.1 and M.2.

Compared variables	Age ∈ [16; 20[Age ∈ [20; 25[Age ∈ [25; 30[Age ∈ [30; 35[Age ∈ [35; 40[Age ∈ [40; 45[Age ∈ [45; 50[Age ∈ [50; 55[Age ∈ [55; 60[Age ∈ [60; 65[
SEN(1) VS SEN(5)	-16%	-22%	-22%	-23%	-23%	-26%	-28%	-30%	-32%	-33%
SEN(2) VS SEN(3)	5%	0%	4%	-3%	4%	0%	0%	-8%	-1%	-1%
SEN(2) VS SEN(4)	0%	-4%	0%	-3%	-1%	-2%	0%	-6%	-1%	-1%
SEN(2) VS SEN(5)	0%	-8%	-6%	-10%	-9%	-11%	-11%	-15%	-16%	-17%
SEN(3) VS SEN(4)	-5%	-4%	-3%	0%	-5%	-2%	0%	2%	0%	0%
SEN(3) VS SEN(5)	-5%	-8%	-9%	-7%	-13%	-11%	-11%	-8%	-15%	-16%
SEN(4) VS SEN(5)	0%	-4%	-6%	-7%	-8%	-10%	-11%	-10%	-15%	-17%
Women										
LMS(1) VS LMS(2)	154%	116%	54%	38%	29%	25%	23%	25%	29%	
LMS(1) VS LMS(3)	146%	126%	126%	140%	135%	138%	137%	134%	140%	
LMS(2) VS LMS(3)	-3%	5%	47%	74%	82%	91%	93%	87%	85%	
EDU(1) VS EDU(2)	-20%	-15%	-21%	-19%	-19%	-19%	-19%	-21%	-22%	
EDU(1) VS EDU(3)	-26%	-33%	-38%	-38%	-35%	-37%	-38%	-42%	-41%	
EDU(2) VS EDU(3)	-7%	-21%	-22%	-23%	-20%	-22%	-23%	-27%	-25%	
SEN(1) VS SEN(2)	-20%	-20%	-21%	-14%	-13%	-7%	0%	0%	0%	
SEN(1) VS SEN(3)	-20%	-18%	-21%	-14%	-13%	-9%	0%	0%	0%	
SEN(1) VS SEN(4)	-20%	-20%	-21%	-19%	-19%	-13%	-10%	-11%	-7%	
SEN(1) VS SEN(5)	-20%	-27%	-29%	-28%	-28%	-22%	-25%	-24%	-25%	
SEN(2) VS SEN(3)	0%	3%	0%	0%	0%	-2%	0%	0%	0%	
SEN(2) VS SEN(4)	0%	0%	0%	-6%	-6%	-6%	-10%	-11%	-7%	
SEN(2) VS SEN(5)	0%	-8%	-10%	-16%	-17%	-16%	-25%	-24%	-25%	
SEN(3) VS SEN(4)	0%	-3%	0%	-6%	-6%	-4%	-10%	-11%	-7%	
SEN(3) VS SEN(5)	0%	-11%	-10%	-16%	-17%	-14%	-25%	-24%	-25%	
SEN(4) VS SEN(5)	0%	-8%	-10%	-11%	-12%	-11%	-17%	-15%	-19%	
LMS(1), LMS(2) and LMS(3) respectively stand for dependent labour, independent labour and informal labour. EDU(1), EDU(2) and EDU(3) represent education levels respectively equal to incomplete secondary, complete secondary and university degree levels. SEN(1) to SEN(5) represent different seniority values in the same firm. From 1 to 5, they are respectively equal to at most three months, more than three to six months, more than six to 12 months, more than a year to five years and more than five years.										
Source: own calculus using Tables M.1 and M.2.										

Compared variables	<i>Age</i> ∈ [16; 20[<i>Age</i> ∈ [20; 25[<i>Age</i> ∈ [25; 30[<i>Age</i> ∈ [30; 35[<i>Age</i> ∈ [35; 40[<i>Age</i> ∈ [40; 45[<i>Age</i> ∈ [45; 50[<i>Age</i> ∈ [50; 55[<i>Age</i> ∈ [55; 60[<i>Age</i> ∈ [60; 65[
<p>The percentage changes are computed using the coefficients estimated in Tables M.1 and M.2. Computation example: in the case of men aged 55 to 60. the coefficient associated with being a formal wage-earner is equal to 0.1228, while the one associated with being an unregistered worker is equal to -0.5896. Let's assume the intercept is written i and that the coefficients associated with level of education and seniority respectively equal a and b. We know from section 2.3.1 that the dependent variable of our Mincer wage equations is the logarithm of labour income divided by the RIPTTE index adjusted by a structural coefficient. Thus, the labour income of the formal wage-earner as a percentage of the mean wage corrected by the structural coefficient equals $\exp(0.1228 + i + a + b) = \exp(0.1228) \times \exp(i + a + b)$. All other things being equal, the labour income of the informal wage-earner equals $\exp(-0.5896 + i + a + b) = \exp(-0.5896) \times \exp(i + a + b)$. Thus, being a formal wage-earner instead of an informal wage-earner increases labour income by $100 \times \frac{\exp(0.1228) \times \exp(i+a+b) - \exp(-0.5896) \times \exp(i+a+b)}{\exp(-0.5896) \times \exp(i+a+b)} = 100 \times \left(\frac{\exp(0.1228)}{\exp(-0.5896)} - 1 \right) \approx 104\%$.</p>										
<p>Reading example: for women aged between 45 and 50. being a formal wage-earner instead of an informal worker increases labour income by 137% all other things being equal.</p>										
<p>Source: own calculus using Tables M.1 and M.2.</p>										

Appendix N

Our labour-market scenarios: central, high and low hypotheses

As explained in section 2.3, our labour-market module follows an alignment by sorting procedure. When simulating labour-market state, their micro-level consistency is ensured by behavioural equations (listed in Appendix L). Their macro-level consistency is on the other hand reached by aligning the simulations on aggregate labour-market state rates. For our retrospective labour-market module, as well as for our prospective simulations up to the first quarter of 2017, the alignment values are historically measured from the EPH, or extrapolated from nearby waves in the case of missing periods (1974-2017). Starting from the second quarter of 2017 however, our prospective labour-market module is fed with plausible low, central and high labour-market participation scenarios. As explained in section 2.3.4, we devised a methodology to derive age-specific scenarios from aggregate labour-market participation rates by gender. Our scenarios therefore only consist in these aggregate rates. Tables N.1 to N.9 below list the central, high and low aggregate scenarios by gender.

Table N.1: Central labour-market scenario: men

Year	Quarter	Labour-market participation rates of men ages 16 to 69				
		Formal wage-earners	Formal in-dependent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2017	1	36.86%	6.80%	28.01%	6.85%	21.47%
2017	2	36.59%	6.97%	28.04%	6.71%	21.69%
2017	3	36.55%	6.93%	28.16%	6.72%	21.64%
2017	4	36.51%	6.88%	28.27%	6.72%	21.62%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Labour-market participation rates of men ages 16 to 69						
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal in-dependent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2018	1	36.46%	6.83%	28.38%	6.73%	21.6%
2018	2	36.42%	6.79%	28.49%	6.74%	21.56%
2018	3	36.38%	6.74%	28.61%	6.74%	21.53%
2018	4	36.34%	6.7%	28.72%	6.75%	21.49%
2019	1	36.3%	6.65%	28.83%	6.75%	21.47%
2019	2	36.31%	6.65%	28.83%	6.75%	21.46%
2019	3	36.32%	6.65%	28.82%	6.74%	21.47%
2019	4	36.34%	6.65%	28.82%	6.74%	21.45%
2020	1	36.35%	6.65%	28.81%	6.73%	21.46%
2020	2	36.36%	6.65%	28.8%	6.72%	21.47%
2020	3	36.37%	6.65%	28.8%	6.72%	21.46%
2020	4	36.38%	6.65%	28.79%	6.71%	21.47%
2021	1	36.39%	6.65%	28.79%	6.71%	21.46%
2021	2	36.41%	6.65%	28.78%	6.7%	21.46%
2021	3	36.42%	6.65%	28.77%	6.7%	21.46%
2021	4	36.43%	6.65%	28.77%	6.69%	21.46%
2022	1	36.44%	6.65%	28.76%	6.68%	21.47%
2022	2	36.45%	6.65%	28.76%	6.68%	21.46%
2022	3	36.46%	6.65%	28.75%	6.67%	21.47%
2022	4	36.47%	6.65%	28.75%	6.67%	21.46%
2023	1	36.49%	6.65%	28.74%	6.66%	21.46%
2023	2	36.5%	6.65%	28.73%	6.65%	21.47%
2023	3	36.51%	6.65%	28.73%	6.65%	21.46%
2023	4	36.52%	6.65%	28.72%	6.64%	21.47%
2024	1	36.53%	6.65%	28.72%	6.64%	21.46%
2024	2	36.54%	6.65%	28.71%	6.63%	21.47%
2024	3	36.55%	6.65%	28.71%	6.63%	21.46%
2024	4	36.57%	6.65%	28.7%	6.62%	21.46%
2025	1	36.58%	6.65%	28.69%	6.61%	21.47%
2025	2	36.59%	6.65%	28.69%	6.61%	21.46%
2025	3	36.6%	6.65%	28.68%	6.6%	21.47%
2025	4	36.61%	6.65%	28.68%	6.6%	21.46%
2026	1	36.62%	6.65%	28.67%	6.59%	21.47%
2026	2	36.64%	6.65%	28.67%	6.59%	21.45%
2026	3	36.65%	6.65%	28.66%	6.58%	21.46%
2026	4	36.66%	6.65%	28.65%	6.57%	21.47%
2027	1	36.67%	6.65%	28.65%	6.57%	21.46%
2027	2	36.68%	6.65%	28.64%	6.56%	21.47%
2027	3	36.69%	6.65%	28.64%	6.56%	21.46%
2027	4	36.7%	6.65%	28.63%	6.55%	21.47%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Labour-market participation rates of men ages 16 to 69						
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal in-dependent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2028	1	36.72%	6.65%	28.63%	6.55%	21.45%
2028	2	36.73%	6.65%	28.62%	6.54%	21.46%
2028	3	36.74%	6.65%	28.61%	6.53%	21.47%
2028	4	36.75%	6.65%	28.61%	6.53%	21.46%
2029	1	36.76%	6.65%	28.6%	6.52%	21.47%
2029	2	36.77%	6.65%	28.6%	6.52%	21.46%
2029	3	36.78%	6.65%	28.59%	6.51%	21.47%
2029	4	36.8%	6.65%	28.59%	6.51%	21.45%
2030	1	36.81%	6.65%	28.58%	6.5%	21.46%
2030	2	36.82%	6.65%	28.57%	6.49%	21.47%
2030	3	36.83%	6.65%	28.57%	6.49%	21.46%
2030	4	36.84%	6.65%	28.56%	6.48%	21.47%
2031	1	36.85%	6.65%	28.56%	6.48%	21.46%
2031	2	36.87%	6.65%	28.55%	6.47%	21.46%
2031	3	36.88%	6.65%	28.54%	6.47%	21.46%
2031	4	36.89%	6.65%	28.54%	6.46%	21.46%
2032	1	36.9%	6.65%	28.53%	6.45%	21.47%
2032	2	36.91%	6.65%	28.53%	6.45%	21.46%
2032	3	36.92%	6.65%	28.52%	6.44%	21.47%
2032	4	36.93%	6.65%	28.52%	6.44%	21.46%
2033	1	36.95%	6.65%	28.51%	6.43%	21.46%
2033	2	36.96%	6.65%	28.5%	6.42%	21.47%
2033	3	36.97%	6.65%	28.5%	6.42%	21.46%
2033	4	36.98%	6.65%	28.49%	6.41%	21.47%
2034	1	36.99%	6.65%	28.49%	6.41%	21.46%
2034	2	37%	6.65%	28.48%	6.4%	21.47%
2034	3	37.01%	6.65%	28.48%	6.4%	21.46%
2034	4	37.03%	6.65%	28.47%	6.39%	21.46%
2035	1	37.04%	6.65%	28.46%	6.38%	21.47%
2035	2	37.05%	6.65%	28.46%	6.38%	21.46%
2035	3	37.06%	6.65%	28.45%	6.37%	21.47%
2035	4	37.07%	6.65%	28.45%	6.37%	21.46%
2036	1	37.08%	6.65%	28.44%	6.36%	21.47%
2036	2	37.1%	6.65%	28.44%	6.36%	21.45%
2036	3	37.11%	6.65%	28.43%	6.35%	21.46%
2036	4	37.12%	6.65%	28.42%	6.34%	21.47%
2037	1	37.13%	6.65%	28.42%	6.34%	21.46%
2037	2	37.14%	6.65%	28.41%	6.33%	21.47%
2037	3	37.15%	6.65%	28.41%	6.33%	21.46%
2037	4	37.16%	6.65%	28.4%	6.32%	21.47%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Labour-market participation rates of men ages 16 to 69						
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal in-dependent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2038	1	37.18%	6.65%	28.4%	6.32%	21.45%
2038	2	37.19%	6.65%	28.39%	6.31%	21.46%
2038	3	37.2%	6.65%	28.38%	6.3%	21.47%
2038	4	37.21%	6.65%	28.38%	6.3%	21.46%
2039	1	37.22%	6.65%	28.37%	6.29%	21.47%
2039	2	37.23%	6.65%	28.37%	6.29%	21.46%
2039	3	37.24%	6.65%	28.36%	6.28%	21.47%
2039	4	37.26%	6.65%	28.36%	6.28%	21.45%
2040	1	37.27%	6.65%	28.35%	6.27%	21.46%
2040	2	37.28%	6.65%	28.34%	6.26%	21.47%
2040	3	37.29%	6.65%	28.34%	6.26%	21.46%
2040	4	37.3%	6.65%	28.33%	6.25%	21.47%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Table N.2: Central labour-market scenario: women

Labour-market participation rates of women ages 16 to 69						
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal in-dependent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2017	1	27.05%	4.07%	18.45%	5.67%	44.76%
2017	2	26.38%	4%	18.29%	5.56%	45.77%
2017	3	26.54%	3.94%	18.34%	5.47%	45.71%
2017	4	26.7%	3.87%	18.39%	5.38%	45.66%
2018	1	26.86%	3.8%	18.44%	5.28%	45.62%
2018	2	27.02%	3.74%	18.49%	5.19%	45.56%
2018	3	27.18%	3.67%	18.54%	5.09%	45.52%
2018	4	27.34%	3.6%	18.59%	5%	45.47%
2019	1	27.71%	3.52%	18.58%	4.81%	45.38%
2019	2	27.74%	3.52%	18.57%	4.81%	45.36%
2019	3	27.78%	3.52%	18.56%	4.81%	45.33%
2019	4	27.81%	3.52%	18.55%	4.81%	45.31%
2020	1	27.84%	3.52%	18.54%	4.81%	45.29%
2020	2	27.88%	3.52%	18.53%	4.81%	45.26%
2020	3	27.91%	3.52%	18.51%	4.81%	45.25%
2020	4	27.95%	3.52%	18.5%	4.81%	45.22%
2021	1	27.98%	3.52%	18.49%	4.81%	45.2%
2021	2	28.02%	3.52%	18.48%	4.81%	45.17%
2021	3	28.05%	3.52%	18.47%	4.81%	45.15%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Labour-market participation rates of women ages 16 to 69						
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal in-dependent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2021	4	28.09%	3.52%	18.46%	4.81%	45.12%
2022	1	28.12%	3.52%	18.44%	4.81%	45.11%
2022	2	28.15%	3.52%	18.43%	4.81%	45.09%
2022	3	28.19%	3.52%	18.42%	4.81%	45.06%
2022	4	28.22%	3.52%	18.41%	4.81%	45.04%
2023	1	28.26%	3.52%	18.4%	4.81%	45.01%
2023	2	28.29%	3.52%	18.39%	4.81%	44.99%
2023	3	28.33%	3.52%	18.38%	4.81%	44.96%
2023	4	28.36%	3.52%	18.36%	4.81%	44.95%
2024	1	28.4%	3.52%	18.35%	4.81%	44.92%
2024	2	28.43%	3.52%	18.34%	4.81%	44.9%
2024	3	28.47%	3.52%	18.33%	4.81%	44.87%
2024	4	28.5%	3.52%	18.32%	4.81%	44.85%
2025	1	28.53%	3.52%	18.31%	4.81%	44.83%
2025	2	28.57%	3.52%	18.3%	4.81%	44.8%
2025	3	28.6%	3.52%	18.28%	4.81%	44.79%
2025	4	28.64%	3.52%	18.27%	4.81%	44.76%
2026	1	28.67%	3.52%	18.26%	4.81%	44.74%
2026	2	28.71%	3.52%	18.25%	4.81%	44.71%
2026	3	28.74%	3.52%	18.24%	4.81%	44.69%
2026	4	28.78%	3.52%	18.23%	4.81%	44.66%
2027	1	28.81%	3.52%	18.22%	4.81%	44.64%
2027	2	28.84%	3.52%	18.2%	4.81%	44.63%
2027	3	28.88%	3.52%	18.19%	4.81%	44.6%
2027	4	28.91%	3.52%	18.18%	4.81%	44.58%
2028	1	28.95%	3.52%	18.17%	4.81%	44.55%
2028	2	28.98%	3.52%	18.16%	4.81%	44.53%
2028	3	29.02%	3.52%	18.15%	4.81%	44.5%
2028	4	29.05%	3.52%	18.13%	4.81%	44.49%
2029	1	29.09%	3.52%	18.12%	4.81%	44.46%
2029	2	29.12%	3.52%	18.11%	4.81%	44.44%
2029	3	29.15%	3.52%	18.1%	4.81%	44.42%
2029	4	29.19%	3.52%	18.09%	4.81%	44.39%
2030	1	29.22%	3.52%	18.08%	4.81%	44.37%
2030	2	29.26%	3.52%	18.07%	4.81%	44.34%
2030	3	29.29%	3.52%	18.05%	4.81%	44.33%
2030	4	29.33%	3.52%	18.04%	4.81%	44.3%
2031	1	29.36%	3.52%	18.03%	4.81%	44.28%
2031	2	29.4%	3.52%	18.02%	4.81%	44.25%
2031	3	29.43%	3.52%	18.01%	4.81%	44.23%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Labour-market participation rates of women ages 16 to 69						
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal in-dependent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2031	4	29.47%	3.52%	18%	4.81%	44.2%
2032	1	29.5%	3.52%	17.99%	4.81%	44.18%
2032	2	29.53%	3.52%	17.97%	4.81%	44.17%
2032	3	29.57%	3.52%	17.96%	4.81%	44.14%
2032	4	29.6%	3.52%	17.95%	4.81%	44.12%
2033	1	29.64%	3.52%	17.94%	4.81%	44.09%
2033	2	29.67%	3.52%	17.93%	4.81%	44.07%
2033	3	29.71%	3.52%	17.92%	4.81%	44.04%
2033	4	29.74%	3.52%	17.9%	4.81%	44.03%
2034	1	29.78%	3.52%	17.89%	4.81%	44%
2034	2	29.81%	3.52%	17.88%	4.81%	43.98%
2034	3	29.84%	3.52%	17.87%	4.81%	43.96%
2034	4	29.88%	3.52%	17.86%	4.81%	43.93%
2035	1	29.91%	3.52%	17.85%	4.81%	43.91%
2035	2	29.95%	3.52%	17.84%	4.81%	43.88%
2035	3	29.98%	3.52%	17.82%	4.81%	43.87%
2035	4	30.02%	3.52%	17.81%	4.81%	43.84%
2036	1	30.05%	3.52%	17.8%	4.81%	43.82%
2036	2	30.09%	3.52%	17.79%	4.81%	43.79%
2036	3	30.12%	3.52%	17.78%	4.81%	43.77%
2036	4	30.15%	3.52%	17.77%	4.81%	43.75%
2037	1	30.19%	3.52%	17.76%	4.81%	43.72%
2037	2	30.22%	3.52%	17.74%	4.81%	43.71%
2037	3	30.26%	3.52%	17.73%	4.81%	43.68%
2037	4	30.29%	3.52%	17.72%	4.81%	43.66%
2038	1	30.33%	3.52%	17.71%	4.81%	43.63%
2038	2	30.36%	3.52%	17.7%	4.81%	43.61%
2038	3	30.4%	3.52%	17.69%	4.81%	43.58%
2038	4	30.43%	3.52%	17.67%	4.81%	43.57%
2039	1	30.47%	3.52%	17.66%	4.81%	43.54%
2039	2	30.5%	3.52%	17.65%	4.81%	43.52%
2039	3	30.53%	3.52%	17.64%	4.81%	43.5%
2039	4	30.57%	3.52%	17.63%	4.81%	43.47%
2040	1	30.6%	3.52%	17.62%	4.81%	43.45%
2040	2	30.64%	3.52%	17.61%	4.81%	43.42%
2040	3	30.67%	3.52%	17.59%	4.81%	43.41%
2040	4	30.71%	3.52%	17.58%	4.81%	43.38%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Table N.3: Central labour-market scenario, both genders

		Labour-market participation rates of people aged 16 to 69				
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal independent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2017	1	31.80%	5.39%	23.09%	6.25%	33.47%
2017	2	31.34%	5.44%	23.03%	6.12%	34.07%
2017	3	31.40%	5.39%	23.11%	6.08%	34.01%
2017	4	31.46%	5.33%	23.18%	6.03%	33.99%
2018	1	31.52%	5.27%	23.27%	5.98%	33.95%
2018	2	31.58%	5.22%	23.35%	5.94%	33.91%
2018	3	31.65%	5.16%	23.43%	5.89%	33.86%
2018	4	31.71%	5.11%	23.51%	5.85%	33.83%
2019	1	31.88%	5.04%	23.55%	5.75%	33.78%
2019	2	31.90%	5.04%	23.55%	5.75%	33.75%
2019	3	31.93%	5.04%	23.54%	5.75%	33.75%
2019	4	31.95%	5.04%	23.54%	5.75%	33.73%
2020	1	31.97%	5.04%	23.53%	5.74%	33.72%
2020	2	32.01%	5.04%	23.53%	5.74%	33.68%
2020	3	32.03%	5.04%	23.52%	5.74%	33.67%
2020	4	32.05%	5.04%	23.50%	5.73%	33.67%
2021	1	32.07%	5.04%	23.50%	5.73%	33.66%
2021	2	32.10%	5.04%	23.49%	5.73%	33.64%
2021	3	32.12%	5.04%	23.48%	5.73%	33.62%
2021	4	32.15%	5.04%	23.48%	5.73%	33.60%
2022	1	32.17%	5.04%	23.47%	5.72%	33.60%
2022	2	32.19%	5.04%	23.46%	5.72%	33.58%
2022	3	32.22%	5.05%	23.46%	5.72%	33.56%
2022	4	32.24%	5.05%	23.45%	5.72%	33.54%
2023	1	32.28%	5.05%	23.45%	5.71%	33.52%
2023	2	32.30%	5.05%	23.44%	5.71%	33.50%
2023	3	32.33%	5.05%	23.44%	5.71%	33.46%
2023	4	32.35%	5.05%	23.43%	5.71%	33.45%
2024	1	32.38%	5.05%	23.43%	5.71%	33.43%
2024	2	32.40%	5.05%	23.42%	5.70%	33.42%
2024	3	32.43%	5.05%	23.42%	5.70%	33.39%
2024	4	32.46%	5.06%	23.41%	5.70%	33.38%
2025	1	32.48%	5.05%	23.40%	5.69%	33.37%
2025	2	32.51%	5.06%	23.40%	5.69%	33.35%
2025	3	32.53%	5.06%	23.38%	5.69%	33.35%
2025	4	32.55%	5.06%	23.38%	5.69%	33.32%
2026	1	32.58%	5.06%	23.37%	5.68%	33.31%
2026	2	32.61%	5.06%	23.37%	5.69%	33.28%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Labour-market participation rates of people aged 16 to 69						
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal in-dependent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2026	3	32.63%	5.06%	23.36%	5.68%	33.27%
2026	4	32.65%	5.06%	23.35%	5.67%	33.27%
2027	1	32.67%	5.06%	23.35%	5.68%	33.24%
2027	2	32.70%	5.06%	23.34%	5.67%	33.24%
2027	3	32.72%	5.06%	23.33%	5.67%	33.22%
2027	4	32.75%	5.06%	23.33%	5.67%	33.20%
2028	1	32.78%	5.06%	23.33%	5.67%	33.16%
2028	2	32.80%	5.06%	23.32%	5.66%	33.15%
2028	3	32.83%	5.07%	23.31%	5.66%	33.13%
2028	4	32.85%	5.07%	23.31%	5.66%	33.12%
2029	1	32.88%	5.07%	23.29%	5.65%	33.11%
2029	2	32.90%	5.07%	23.29%	5.65%	33.09%
2029	3	32.92%	5.07%	23.28%	5.65%	33.08%
2029	4	32.95%	5.07%	23.28%	5.65%	33.05%
2030	1	32.97%	5.07%	23.27%	5.65%	33.04%
2030	2	33.00%	5.07%	23.26%	5.64%	33.03%
2030	3	33.02%	5.07%	23.26%	5.64%	33.01%
2030	4	33.05%	5.07%	23.25%	5.64%	33.00%
2031	1	33.06%	5.07%	23.24%	5.64%	32.99%
2031	2	33.10%	5.07%	23.23%	5.63%	32.98%
2031	3	33.12%	5.07%	23.22%	5.63%	32.97%
2031	4	33.14%	5.07%	23.21%	5.63%	32.96%
2032	1	33.16%	5.07%	23.20%	5.62%	32.95%
2032	2	33.18%	5.07%	23.19%	5.62%	32.94%
2032	3	33.21%	5.07%	23.19%	5.62%	32.92%
2032	4	33.23%	5.07%	23.18%	5.62%	32.90%
2033	1	33.26%	5.07%	23.17%	5.61%	32.88%
2033	2	33.28%	5.07%	23.17%	5.61%	32.87%
2033	3	33.31%	5.07%	23.16%	5.61%	32.85%
2033	4	33.33%	5.07%	23.15%	5.60%	32.85%
2034	1	33.36%	5.07%	23.15%	5.60%	32.82%
2034	2	33.38%	5.07%	23.14%	5.60%	32.82%
2034	3	33.40%	5.07%	23.13%	5.60%	32.80%
2034	4	33.43%	5.07%	23.13%	5.59%	32.78%
2035	1	33.45%	5.07%	23.12%	5.59%	32.77%
2035	2	33.48%	5.07%	23.11%	5.59%	32.75%
2035	3	33.49%	5.07%	23.09%	5.58%	32.76%
2035	4	33.52%	5.07%	23.09%	5.58%	32.74%
2036	1	33.54%	5.07%	23.08%	5.58%	32.74%
2036	2	33.57%	5.07%	23.07%	5.58%	32.71%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Labour-market participation rates of people aged 16 to 69						
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal in-dependent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2036	3	33.58%	5.07%	23.06%	5.57%	32.71%
2036	4	33.60%	5.07%	23.05%	5.57%	32.71%
2037	1	33.63%	5.07%	23.04%	5.57%	32.69%
2037	2	33.65%	5.07%	23.03%	5.56%	32.69%
2037	3	33.68%	5.07%	23.03%	5.56%	32.66%
2037	4	33.70%	5.07%	23.02%	5.56%	32.65%
2038	1	33.73%	5.07%	23.02%	5.56%	32.62%
2038	2	33.75%	5.07%	23.01%	5.55%	32.61%
2038	3	33.78%	5.08%	23.00%	5.55%	32.59%
2038	4	33.80%	5.08%	22.99%	5.55%	32.58%
2039	1	33.82%	5.07%	22.98%	5.55%	32.58%
2039	2	33.84%	5.07%	22.98%	5.55%	32.56%
2039	3	33.86%	5.07%	22.96%	5.54%	32.57%
2039	4	33.89%	5.07%	22.95%	5.54%	32.54%
2040	1	33.91%	5.07%	22.94%	5.53%	32.54%
2040	2	33.93%	5.07%	22.93%	5.53%	32.54%
2040	3	33.95%	5.07%	22.92%	5.53%	32.53%
2040	4	33.98%	5.07%	22.91%	5.52%	32.52%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Table N.4: High labour-market scenario: men

Labour-market participation rates of men ages 16 to 69						
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal in-dependent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2017	1	36.86%	6.80%	28.01%	6.85%	21.47%
2017	2	36.59%	6.97%	28.04%	6.71%	21.69%
2017	3	36.55%	6.93%	28.16%	6.72%	21.64%
2017	4	36.51%	6.88%	28.27%	6.72%	21.62%
2018	1	36.46%	6.83%	28.38%	6.73%	21.60%
2018	2	36.42%	6.79%	28.49%	6.74%	21.56%
2018	3	36.38%	6.74%	28.61%	6.74%	21.53%
2018	4	36.34%	6.70%	28.72%	6.75%	21.49%
2019	1	36.30%	6.65%	28.83%	6.75%	21.47%
2019	2	36.39%	6.65%	28.79%	6.72%	21.45%
2019	3	36.49%	6.65%	28.74%	6.70%	21.42%
2019	4	36.58%	6.65%	28.69%	6.67%	21.41%
2020	1	36.67%	6.65%	28.65%	6.64%	21.39%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Labour-market participation rates of men ages 16 to 69						
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal in-dependent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2020	2	36.76%	6.65%	28.60%	6.61%	21.38%
2020	3	36.85%	6.65%	28.56%	6.58%	21.36%
2020	4	36.95%	6.65%	28.51%	6.55%	21.34%
2021	1	37.04%	6.65%	28.46%	6.52%	21.33%
2021	2	37.13%	6.65%	28.42%	6.49%	21.31%
2021	3	37.22%	6.65%	28.37%	6.47%	21.29%
2021	4	37.31%	6.65%	28.33%	6.44%	21.27%
2022	1	37.41%	6.65%	28.28%	6.41%	21.25%
2022	2	37.50%	6.65%	28.23%	6.38%	21.24%
2022	3	37.59%	6.65%	28.19%	6.35%	21.22%
2022	4	37.68%	6.65%	28.14%	6.32%	21.21%
2023	1	37.77%	6.65%	28.10%	6.29%	21.19%
2023	2	37.87%	6.65%	28.05%	6.26%	21.17%
2023	3	37.96%	6.65%	28.00%	6.24%	21.15%
2023	4	38.05%	6.65%	27.96%	6.21%	21.13%
2024	1	38.14%	6.65%	27.91%	6.18%	21.12%
2024	2	38.23%	6.65%	27.87%	6.15%	21.10%
2024	3	38.32%	6.65%	27.82%	6.12%	21.09%
2024	4	38.42%	6.65%	27.77%	6.09%	21.07%
2025	1	38.51%	6.65%	27.73%	6.06%	21.05%
2025	2	38.60%	6.65%	27.68%	6.03%	21.04%
2025	3	38.69%	6.65%	27.64%	6.01%	21.01%
2025	4	38.78%	6.65%	27.59%	5.98%	21.00%
2026	1	38.88%	6.65%	27.54%	5.95%	20.98%
2026	2	38.97%	6.65%	27.50%	5.92%	20.96%
2026	3	39.06%	6.65%	27.45%	5.89%	20.95%
2026	4	39.15%	6.65%	27.41%	5.86%	20.93%
2027	1	39.24%	6.65%	27.36%	5.83%	20.92%
2027	2	39.34%	6.65%	27.32%	5.80%	20.89%
2027	3	39.43%	6.65%	27.27%	5.78%	20.87%
2027	4	39.52%	6.65%	27.22%	5.75%	20.86%
2028	1	39.61%	6.65%	27.18%	5.72%	20.84%
2028	2	39.70%	6.65%	27.13%	5.69%	20.83%
2028	3	39.80%	6.65%	27.09%	5.66%	20.80%
2028	4	39.89%	6.65%	27.04%	5.63%	20.79%
2029	1	39.98%	6.65%	26.99%	5.60%	20.78%
2029	2	40.07%	6.65%	26.95%	5.57%	20.76%
2029	3	40.16%	6.65%	26.90%	5.55%	20.74%
2029	4	40.26%	6.65%	26.86%	5.52%	20.71%
2030	1	40.35%	6.65%	26.81%	5.49%	20.70%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Labour-market participation rates of men ages 16 to 69						
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal in-dependent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2030	2	40.44%	6.65%	26.76%	5.46%	20.69%
2030	3	40.53%	6.65%	26.72%	5.43%	20.67%
2030	4	40.62%	6.65%	26.67%	5.40%	20.66%
2031	1	40.72%	6.65%	26.63%	5.37%	20.63%
2031	2	40.81%	6.65%	26.58%	5.34%	20.62%
2031	3	40.90%	6.65%	26.53%	5.32%	20.60%
2031	4	40.99%	6.65%	26.49%	5.29%	20.58%
2032	1	41.08%	6.65%	26.44%	5.26%	20.57%
2032	2	41.18%	6.65%	26.40%	5.23%	20.54%
2032	3	41.27%	6.65%	26.35%	5.20%	20.53%
2032	4	41.36%	6.65%	26.30%	5.17%	20.52%
2033	1	41.45%	6.65%	26.26%	5.14%	20.50%
2033	2	41.54%	6.65%	26.21%	5.11%	20.49%
2033	3	41.64%	6.65%	26.17%	5.09%	20.45%
2033	4	41.73%	6.65%	26.12%	5.06%	20.44%
2034	1	41.82%	6.65%	26.07%	5.03%	20.43%
2034	2	41.91%	6.65%	26.03%	5.00%	20.41%
2034	3	42.00%	6.65%	25.98%	4.97%	20.40%
2034	4	42.10%	6.65%	25.94%	4.94%	20.37%
2035	1	42.19%	6.65%	25.89%	4.91%	20.36%
2035	2	42.28%	6.65%	25.84%	4.88%	20.35%
2035	3	42.37%	6.65%	25.80%	4.86%	20.32%
2035	4	42.46%	6.65%	25.75%	4.83%	20.31%
2036	1	42.55%	6.65%	25.71%	4.80%	20.29%
2036	2	42.65%	6.65%	25.66%	4.77%	20.27%
2036	3	42.74%	6.65%	25.61%	4.74%	20.26%
2036	4	42.83%	6.65%	25.57%	4.71%	20.24%
2037	1	42.92%	6.65%	25.52%	4.68%	20.23%
2037	2	43.01%	6.65%	25.48%	4.65%	20.21%
2037	3	43.11%	6.65%	25.43%	4.63%	20.18%
2037	4	43.20%	6.65%	25.38%	4.60%	20.17%
2038	1	43.29%	6.65%	25.34%	4.57%	20.15%
2038	2	43.38%	6.65%	25.29%	4.54%	20.14%
2038	3	43.47%	6.65%	25.25%	4.51%	20.12%
2038	4	43.57%	6.65%	25.20%	4.48%	20.10%
2039	1	43.66%	6.65%	25.15%	4.45%	20.09%
2039	2	43.75%	6.65%	25.11%	4.42%	20.07%
2039	3	43.84%	6.65%	25.06%	4.40%	20.05%
2039	4	43.93%	6.65%	25.02%	4.37%	20.03%
2040	1	44.03%	6.65%	24.97%	4.34%	20.01%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Labour-market participation rates of men ages 16 to 69						
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal in-dependent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2040	2	44.12%	6.65%	24.92%	4.31%	20.00%
2040	3	44.21%	6.65%	24.88%	4.28%	19.98%
2040	4	44.30%	6.65%	24.83%	4.25%	19.97%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Table N.5: High labour-market scenario: women

Labour-market participation rates of women ages 16 to 69						
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal in-dependent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2017	1	27.05%	4.07%	18.45%	5.67%	44.76%
2017	2	26.38%	4.00%	18.29%	5.56%	45.77%
2017	3	26.54%	3.94%	18.34%	5.47%	45.71%
2017	4	26.70%	3.87%	18.39%	5.38%	45.66%
2018	1	26.86%	3.80%	18.44%	5.28%	45.62%
2018	2	27.02%	3.74%	18.49%	5.19%	45.56%
2018	3	27.18%	3.67%	18.54%	5.09%	45.52%
2018	4	27.34%	3.60%	18.59%	5.00%	45.47%
2019	1	27.71%	3.52%	18.58%	4.81%	45.38%
2019	2	27.82%	3.52%	18.54%	4.79%	45.33%
2019	3	27.94%	3.52%	18.50%	4.77%	45.27%
2019	4	28.05%	3.52%	18.46%	4.76%	45.21%
2020	1	28.17%	3.52%	18.42%	4.74%	45.15%
2020	2	28.28%	3.52%	18.38%	4.72%	45.10%
2020	3	28.40%	3.52%	18.34%	4.70%	45.04%
2020	4	28.51%	3.52%	18.30%	4.69%	44.98%
2021	1	28.63%	3.52%	18.26%	4.67%	44.92%
2021	2	28.74%	3.52%	18.22%	4.65%	44.87%
2021	3	28.86%	3.52%	18.18%	4.64%	44.80%
2021	4	28.97%	3.52%	18.14%	4.62%	44.75%
2022	1	29.09%	3.52%	18.10%	4.60%	44.69%
2022	2	29.20%	3.52%	18.06%	4.58%	44.64%
2022	3	29.32%	3.52%	18.02%	4.57%	44.57%
2022	4	29.43%	3.52%	17.98%	4.55%	44.52%
2023	1	29.55%	3.52%	17.94%	4.53%	44.46%
2023	2	29.66%	3.52%	17.90%	4.51%	44.41%
2023	3	29.78%	3.52%	17.86%	4.50%	44.34%
2023	4	29.89%	3.52%	17.82%	4.48%	44.29%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Labour-market participation rates of women ages 16 to 69						
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal in-dependent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2024	1	30.01%	3.52%	17.78%	4.46%	44.23%
2024	2	30.12%	3.52%	17.74%	4.45%	44.17%
2024	3	30.24%	3.52%	17.70%	4.43%	44.11%
2024	4	30.35%	3.52%	17.66%	4.41%	44.06%
2025	1	30.47%	3.52%	17.62%	4.39%	44.00%
2025	2	30.58%	3.52%	17.58%	4.38%	43.94%
2025	3	30.69%	3.52%	17.54%	4.36%	43.89%
2025	4	30.81%	3.52%	17.50%	4.34%	43.83%
2026	1	30.92%	3.52%	17.46%	4.32%	43.78%
2026	2	31.04%	3.52%	17.42%	4.31%	43.71%
2026	3	31.15%	3.52%	17.38%	4.29%	43.66%
2026	4	31.27%	3.52%	17.34%	4.27%	43.60%
2027	1	31.38%	3.52%	17.30%	4.26%	43.54%
2027	2	31.50%	3.52%	17.26%	4.24%	43.48%
2027	3	31.61%	3.52%	17.22%	4.22%	43.43%
2027	4	31.73%	3.52%	17.17%	4.20%	43.38%
2028	1	31.84%	3.52%	17.13%	4.19%	43.32%
2028	2	31.96%	3.52%	17.09%	4.17%	43.26%
2028	3	32.07%	3.52%	17.05%	4.15%	43.21%
2028	4	32.19%	3.52%	17.01%	4.14%	43.14%
2029	1	32.30%	3.52%	16.97%	4.12%	43.09%
2029	2	32.42%	3.52%	16.93%	4.10%	43.03%
2029	3	32.53%	3.52%	16.89%	4.08%	42.98%
2029	4	32.65%	3.52%	16.85%	4.07%	42.91%
2030	1	32.76%	3.52%	16.81%	4.05%	42.86%
2030	2	32.88%	3.52%	16.77%	4.03%	42.80%
2030	3	32.99%	3.52%	16.73%	4.01%	42.75%
2030	4	33.11%	3.52%	16.69%	4.00%	42.68%
2031	1	33.22%	3.52%	16.65%	3.98%	42.63%
2031	2	33.34%	3.52%	16.61%	3.96%	42.57%
2031	3	33.45%	3.52%	16.57%	3.95%	42.51%
2031	4	33.57%	3.52%	16.53%	3.93%	42.45%
2032	1	33.68%	3.52%	16.49%	3.91%	42.40%
2032	2	33.80%	3.52%	16.45%	3.89%	42.34%
2032	3	33.91%	3.52%	16.41%	3.88%	42.28%
2032	4	34.03%	3.52%	16.37%	3.86%	42.22%
2033	1	34.14%	3.52%	16.33%	3.84%	42.17%
2033	2	34.26%	3.52%	16.29%	3.82%	42.11%
2033	3	34.37%	3.52%	16.25%	3.81%	42.05%
2033	4	34.49%	3.52%	16.21%	3.79%	41.99%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Labour-market participation rates of women ages 16 to 69						
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal in-dependent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2034	1	34.60%	3.52%	16.17%	3.77%	41.94%
2034	2	34.72%	3.52%	16.13%	3.76%	41.87%
2034	3	34.83%	3.52%	16.09%	3.74%	41.82%
2034	4	34.95%	3.52%	16.05%	3.72%	41.76%
2035	1	35.06%	3.52%	16.01%	3.70%	41.71%
2035	2	35.18%	3.52%	15.97%	3.69%	41.64%
2035	3	35.29%	3.52%	15.93%	3.67%	41.59%
2035	4	35.41%	3.52%	15.89%	3.65%	41.53%
2036	1	35.52%	3.52%	15.85%	3.64%	41.47%
2036	2	35.64%	3.52%	15.81%	3.62%	41.41%
2036	3	35.75%	3.52%	15.77%	3.60%	41.36%
2036	4	35.87%	3.52%	15.73%	3.58%	41.30%
2037	1	35.98%	3.52%	15.69%	3.57%	41.24%
2037	2	36.10%	3.52%	15.65%	3.55%	41.18%
2037	3	36.21%	3.52%	15.61%	3.53%	41.13%
2037	4	36.33%	3.52%	15.57%	3.51%	41.07%
2038	1	36.44%	3.52%	15.53%	3.50%	41.01%
2038	2	36.56%	3.52%	15.49%	3.48%	40.95%
2038	3	36.67%	3.52%	15.44%	3.46%	40.91%
2038	4	36.79%	3.52%	15.40%	3.45%	40.84%
2039	1	36.90%	3.52%	15.36%	3.43%	40.79%
2039	2	37.02%	3.52%	15.32%	3.41%	40.73%
2039	3	37.13%	3.52%	15.28%	3.39%	40.68%
2039	4	37.25%	3.52%	15.24%	3.38%	40.61%
2040	1	37.36%	3.52%	15.20%	3.36%	40.56%
2040	2	37.48%	3.52%	15.16%	3.34%	40.50%
2040	3	37.59%	3.52%	15.12%	3.32%	40.45%
2040	4	37.71%	3.52%	15.08%	3.31%	40.38%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Table N.6: High labour-market scenario, both genders

Labour-market participation rates of people aged 16 to 69						
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal in-dependent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2017	1	31.80%	5.39%	23.09%	6.25%	33.47%
2017	2	31.34%	5.44%	23.03%	6.12%	34.07%
2017	3	31.40%	5.39%	23.11%	6.08%	34.01%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Labour-market participation rates of people aged 16 to 69						
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal in-dependent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2017	4	31.46%	5.33%	23.18%	6.03%	33.99%
2018	1	31.52%	5.27%	23.27%	5.98%	33.95%
2018	2	31.58%	5.22%	23.35%	5.94%	33.91%
2018	3	31.65%	5.16%	23.43%	5.89%	33.86%
2018	4	31.71%	5.11%	23.51%	5.85%	33.83%
2019	1	31.88%	5.04%	23.55%	5.75%	33.78%
2019	2	31.98%	5.04%	23.52%	5.73%	33.73%
2019	3	32.09%	5.04%	23.47%	5.71%	33.69%
2019	4	32.19%	5.04%	23.43%	5.69%	33.66%
2020	1	32.30%	5.04%	23.39%	5.66%	33.61%
2020	2	32.41%	5.04%	23.35%	5.64%	33.56%
2020	3	32.51%	5.04%	23.31%	5.61%	33.52%
2020	4	32.61%	5.04%	23.26%	5.59%	33.49%
2021	1	32.72%	5.04%	23.22%	5.57%	33.45%
2021	2	32.82%	5.04%	23.18%	5.55%	33.41%
2021	3	32.93%	5.04%	23.14%	5.53%	33.36%
2021	4	33.03%	5.04%	23.10%	5.51%	33.32%
2022	1	33.14%	5.04%	23.06%	5.48%	33.28%
2022	2	33.24%	5.04%	23.01%	5.46%	33.24%
2022	3	33.35%	5.05%	22.98%	5.44%	33.19%
2022	4	33.45%	5.05%	22.94%	5.41%	33.15%
2023	1	33.56%	5.05%	22.90%	5.39%	33.10%
2023	2	33.67%	5.05%	22.86%	5.36%	33.06%
2023	3	33.78%	5.05%	22.82%	5.35%	32.99%
2023	4	33.88%	5.05%	22.78%	5.33%	32.95%
2024	1	33.99%	5.05%	22.74%	5.30%	32.92%
2024	2	34.09%	5.05%	22.70%	5.28%	32.87%
2024	3	34.20%	5.05%	22.66%	5.26%	32.83%
2024	4	34.31%	5.06%	22.62%	5.23%	32.79%
2025	1	34.41%	5.05%	22.58%	5.21%	32.75%
2025	2	34.52%	5.06%	22.54%	5.19%	32.70%
2025	3	34.62%	5.06%	22.50%	5.17%	32.66%
2025	4	34.72%	5.06%	22.46%	5.15%	32.62%
2026	1	34.83%	5.06%	22.41%	5.12%	32.58%
2026	2	34.94%	5.06%	22.38%	5.10%	32.53%
2026	3	35.04%	5.06%	22.33%	5.08%	32.50%
2026	4	35.14%	5.06%	22.29%	5.05%	32.46%
2027	1	35.24%	5.06%	22.25%	5.03%	32.42%
2027	2	35.36%	5.06%	22.21%	5.01%	32.37%
2027	3	35.46%	5.06%	22.16%	4.99%	32.34%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Labour-market participation rates of people aged 16 to 69						
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal in-dependent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2027	4	35.57%	5.06%	22.12%	4.96%	32.29%
2028	1	35.67%	5.06%	22.09%	4.94%	32.23%
2028	2	35.78%	5.06%	22.04%	4.92%	32.19%
2028	3	35.89%	5.07%	22.01%	4.90%	32.15%
2028	4	35.99%	5.07%	21.96%	4.88%	32.10%
2029	1	36.09%	5.07%	21.92%	4.85%	32.07%
2029	2	36.20%	5.07%	21.88%	4.83%	32.03%
2029	3	36.30%	5.07%	21.84%	4.81%	31.99%
2029	4	36.41%	5.07%	21.80%	4.79%	31.93%
2030	1	36.51%	5.07%	21.75%	4.76%	31.90%
2030	2	36.62%	5.07%	21.71%	4.74%	31.86%
2030	3	36.72%	5.07%	21.67%	4.71%	31.82%
2030	4	36.83%	5.07%	21.63%	4.69%	31.78%
2031	1	36.93%	5.07%	21.59%	4.67%	31.75%
2031	2	37.04%	5.07%	21.54%	4.64%	31.71%
2031	3	37.14%	5.07%	21.50%	4.63%	31.67%
2031	4	37.24%	5.07%	21.46%	4.60%	31.64%
2032	1	37.34%	5.07%	21.41%	4.58%	31.60%
2032	2	37.45%	5.07%	21.37%	4.55%	31.56%
2032	3	37.55%	5.07%	21.33%	4.53%	31.52%
2032	4	37.66%	5.07%	21.29%	4.51%	31.48%
2033	1	37.76%	5.07%	21.25%	4.48%	31.44%
2033	2	37.87%	5.07%	21.21%	4.46%	31.40%
2033	3	37.97%	5.07%	21.16%	4.44%	31.35%
2033	4	38.08%	5.07%	21.12%	4.42%	31.31%
2034	1	38.18%	5.07%	21.08%	4.40%	31.27%
2034	2	38.29%	5.07%	21.04%	4.38%	31.23%
2034	3	38.39%	5.07%	21.00%	4.35%	31.19%
2034	4	38.50%	5.07%	20.96%	4.33%	31.14%
2035	1	38.60%	5.07%	20.91%	4.30%	31.11%
2035	2	38.71%	5.07%	20.87%	4.28%	31.07%
2035	3	38.80%	5.07%	20.83%	4.26%	31.04%
2035	4	38.91%	5.07%	20.78%	4.24%	31.00%
2036	1	39.01%	5.07%	20.74%	4.22%	30.97%
2036	2	39.12%	5.07%	20.69%	4.19%	30.93%
2036	3	39.21%	5.07%	20.65%	4.16%	30.90%
2036	4	39.32%	5.07%	20.61%	4.14%	30.86%
2037	1	39.42%	5.07%	20.56%	4.12%	30.83%
2037	2	39.52%	5.07%	20.52%	4.10%	30.79%
2037	3	39.63%	5.07%	20.48%	4.08%	30.74%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Labour-market participation rates of people aged 16 to 69						
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal independent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2037	4	39.74%	5.07%	20.44%	4.05%	30.70%
2038	1	39.84%	5.07%	20.40%	4.03%	30.66%
2038	2	39.95%	5.07%	20.36%	4.01%	30.62%
2038	3	40.05%	5.08%	20.32%	3.98%	30.58%
2038	4	40.16%	5.08%	20.27%	3.96%	30.53%
2039	1	40.26%	5.07%	20.22%	3.94%	30.51%
2039	2	40.36%	5.07%	20.18%	3.91%	30.47%
2039	3	40.46%	5.07%	20.13%	3.89%	30.44%
2039	4	40.56%	5.07%	20.09%	3.87%	30.40%
2040	1	40.67%	5.07%	20.05%	3.85%	30.37%
2040	2	40.77%	5.07%	20.00%	3.82%	30.34%
2040	3	40.87%	5.07%	19.96%	3.80%	30.30%
2040	4	40.98%	5.07%	19.91%	3.78%	30.26%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Table N.7: Low labour-market scenario: men

Labour-market participation rates of men ages 16 to 69						
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal independent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2017	1	36.86%	6.80%	28.01%	6.85%	21.47%
2017	2	36.59%	6.97%	28.04%	6.71%	21.69%
2017	3	36.55%	6.93%	28.16%	6.72%	21.64%
2017	4	36.51%	6.88%	28.27%	6.72%	21.62%
2018	1	36.46%	6.83%	28.38%	6.73%	21.60%
2018	2	36.42%	6.79%	28.49%	6.74%	21.56%
2018	3	36.38%	6.74%	28.61%	6.74%	21.53%
2018	4	36.34%	6.70%	28.72%	6.75%	21.49%
2019	1	36.30%	6.65%	28.83%	6.75%	21.47%
2019	2	36.23%	6.65%	28.87%	6.77%	21.48%
2019	3	36.16%	6.65%	28.90%	6.79%	21.50%
2019	4	36.10%	6.65%	28.94%	6.80%	21.51%
2020	1	36.03%	6.65%	28.97%	6.82%	21.53%
2020	2	35.96%	6.65%	29.00%	6.84%	21.55%
2020	3	35.89%	6.65%	29.04%	6.86%	21.56%
2020	4	35.82%	6.65%	29.07%	6.87%	21.59%
2021	1	35.75%	6.65%	29.11%	6.89%	21.60%
2021	2	35.68%	6.65%	29.14%	6.91%	21.62%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Labour-market participation rates of men ages 16 to 69						
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal in-dependent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2021	3	35.61%	6.65%	29.18%	6.92%	21.64%
2021	4	35.54%	6.65%	29.21%	6.94%	21.66%
2022	1	35.47%	6.65%	29.25%	6.96%	21.67%
2022	2	35.41%	6.65%	29.28%	6.98%	21.68%
2022	3	35.34%	6.65%	29.32%	6.99%	21.70%
2022	4	35.27%	6.65%	29.35%	7.01%	21.72%
2023	1	35.20%	6.65%	29.38%	7.03%	21.74%
2023	2	35.13%	6.65%	29.42%	7.05%	21.75%
2023	3	35.06%	6.65%	29.45%	7.06%	21.78%
2023	4	34.99%	6.65%	29.49%	7.08%	21.79%
2024	1	34.92%	6.65%	29.52%	7.10%	21.81%
2024	2	34.85%	6.65%	29.56%	7.11%	21.83%
2024	3	34.78%	6.65%	29.59%	7.13%	21.85%
2024	4	34.72%	6.65%	29.63%	7.15%	21.85%
2025	1	34.65%	6.65%	29.66%	7.17%	21.87%
2025	2	34.58%	6.65%	29.69%	7.18%	21.90%
2025	3	34.51%	6.65%	29.73%	7.20%	21.91%
2025	4	34.44%	6.65%	29.76%	7.22%	21.93%
2026	1	34.37%	6.65%	29.80%	7.24%	21.94%
2026	2	34.30%	6.65%	29.83%	7.25%	21.97%
2026	3	34.23%	6.65%	29.87%	7.27%	21.98%
2026	4	34.16%	6.65%	29.90%	7.29%	22.00%
2027	1	34.10%	6.65%	29.94%	7.30%	22.01%
2027	2	34.03%	6.65%	29.97%	7.32%	22.03%
2027	3	33.96%	6.65%	30.00%	7.34%	22.05%
2027	4	33.89%	6.65%	30.04%	7.36%	22.06%
2028	1	33.82%	6.65%	30.07%	7.37%	22.09%
2028	2	33.75%	6.65%	30.11%	7.39%	22.10%
2028	3	33.68%	6.65%	30.14%	7.41%	22.12%
2028	4	33.61%	6.65%	30.18%	7.42%	22.14%
2029	1	33.54%	6.65%	30.21%	7.44%	22.16%
2029	2	33.47%	6.65%	30.25%	7.46%	22.17%
2029	3	33.41%	6.65%	30.28%	7.48%	22.18%
2029	4	33.34%	6.65%	30.32%	7.49%	22.20%
2030	1	33.27%	6.65%	30.35%	7.51%	22.22%
2030	2	33.20%	6.65%	30.38%	7.53%	22.24%
2030	3	33.13%	6.65%	30.42%	7.55%	22.25%
2030	4	33.06%	6.65%	30.45%	7.56%	22.28%
2031	1	32.99%	6.65%	30.49%	7.58%	22.29%
2031	2	32.92%	6.65%	30.52%	7.60%	22.31%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Labour-market participation rates of men ages 16 to 69						
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal in-dependent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2031	3	32.85%	6.65%	30.56%	7.61%	22.33%
2031	4	32.78%	6.65%	30.59%	7.63%	22.35%
2032	1	32.72%	6.65%	30.63%	7.65%	22.35%
2032	2	32.65%	6.65%	30.66%	7.67%	22.37%
2032	3	32.58%	6.65%	30.69%	7.68%	22.40%
2032	4	32.51%	6.65%	30.73%	7.70%	22.41%
2033	1	32.44%	6.65%	30.76%	7.72%	22.43%
2033	2	32.37%	6.65%	30.80%	7.74%	22.44%
2033	3	32.30%	6.65%	30.83%	7.75%	22.47%
2033	4	32.23%	6.65%	30.87%	7.77%	22.48%
2034	1	32.16%	6.65%	30.90%	7.79%	22.50%
2034	2	32.10%	6.65%	30.94%	7.80%	22.51%
2034	3	32.03%	6.65%	30.97%	7.82%	22.53%
2034	4	31.96%	6.65%	31.00%	7.84%	22.55%
2035	1	31.89%	6.65%	31.04%	7.86%	22.56%
2035	2	31.82%	6.65%	31.07%	7.87%	22.59%
2035	3	31.75%	6.65%	31.11%	7.89%	22.60%
2035	4	31.68%	6.65%	31.14%	7.91%	22.62%
2036	1	31.61%	6.65%	31.18%	7.92%	22.64%
2036	2	31.54%	6.65%	31.21%	7.94%	22.66%
2036	3	31.47%	6.65%	31.25%	7.96%	22.67%
2036	4	31.41%	6.65%	31.28%	7.98%	22.68%
2037	1	31.34%	6.65%	31.32%	7.99%	22.70%
2037	2	31.27%	6.65%	31.35%	8.01%	22.72%
2037	3	31.20%	6.65%	31.38%	8.03%	22.74%
2037	4	31.13%	6.65%	31.42%	8.05%	22.75%
2038	1	31.06%	6.65%	31.45%	8.06%	22.78%
2038	2	30.99%	6.65%	31.49%	8.08%	22.79%
2038	3	30.92%	6.65%	31.52%	8.10%	22.81%
2038	4	30.85%	6.65%	31.56%	8.11%	22.83%
2039	1	30.78%	6.65%	31.59%	8.13%	22.85%
2039	2	30.72%	6.65%	31.63%	8.15%	22.85%
2039	3	30.65%	6.65%	31.66%	8.17%	22.87%
2039	4	30.58%	6.65%	31.69%	8.18%	22.90%
2040	1	30.51%	6.65%	31.73%	8.20%	22.91%
2040	2	30.44%	6.65%	31.76%	8.22%	22.93%
2040	3	30.37%	6.65%	31.80%	8.24%	22.94%
2040	4	30.30%	6.65%	31.83%	8.25%	22.97%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Table N.8: Low labour-market scenario: women

Year	Quarter	Labour-market participation rates of women ages 16 to 69				
		Formal wage-earners	Formal independent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2017	1	27.05%	4.07%	18.45%	5.67%	44.76%
2017	2	26.38%	4.00%	18.29%	5.56%	45.77%
2017	3	26.54%	3.94%	18.34%	5.47%	45.71%
2017	4	26.70%	3.87%	18.39%	5.38%	45.66%
2018	1	26.86%	3.80%	18.44%	5.28%	45.62%
2018	2	27.02%	3.74%	18.49%	5.19%	45.56%
2018	3	27.18%	3.67%	18.54%	5.09%	45.52%
2018	4	27.34%	3.60%	18.59%	5.00%	45.47%
2019	1	27.71%	3.52%	18.58%	4.81%	45.38%
2019	2	27.66%	3.52%	18.60%	4.82%	45.40%
2019	3	27.61%	3.52%	18.62%	4.84%	45.41%
2019	4	27.57%	3.52%	18.63%	4.86%	45.42%
2020	1	27.52%	3.52%	18.65%	4.88%	45.43%
2020	2	27.48%	3.52%	18.67%	4.89%	45.44%
2020	3	27.43%	3.52%	18.69%	4.91%	45.45%
2020	4	27.38%	3.52%	18.70%	4.93%	45.47%
2021	1	27.34%	3.52%	18.72%	4.95%	45.47%
2021	2	27.29%	3.52%	18.74%	4.96%	45.49%
2021	3	27.25%	3.52%	18.76%	4.98%	45.49%
2021	4	27.20%	3.52%	18.77%	5.00%	45.51%
2022	1	27.15%	3.52%	18.79%	5.01%	45.53%
2022	2	27.11%	3.52%	18.81%	5.03%	45.53%
2022	3	27.06%	3.52%	18.82%	5.05%	45.55%
2022	4	27.02%	3.52%	18.84%	5.07%	45.55%
2023	1	26.97%	3.52%	18.86%	5.08%	45.57%
2023	2	26.92%	3.52%	18.88%	5.10%	45.58%
2023	3	26.88%	3.52%	18.89%	5.12%	45.59%
2023	4	26.83%	3.52%	18.91%	5.14%	45.60%
2024	1	26.79%	3.52%	18.93%	5.15%	45.61%
2024	2	26.74%	3.52%	18.94%	5.17%	45.63%
2024	3	26.69%	3.52%	18.96%	5.19%	45.64%
2024	4	26.65%	3.52%	18.98%	5.20%	45.65%
2025	1	26.60%	3.52%	19.00%	5.22%	45.66%
2025	2	26.56%	3.52%	19.01%	5.24%	45.67%
2025	3	26.51%	3.52%	19.03%	5.26%	45.68%
2025	4	26.47%	3.52%	19.05%	5.27%	45.69%
2026	1	26.42%	3.52%	19.07%	5.29%	45.70%
2026	2	26.37%	3.52%	19.08%	5.31%	45.72%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Labour-market participation rates of women ages 16 to 69						
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal in-dependent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2026	3	26.33%	3.52%	19.10%	5.32%	45.73%
2026	4	26.28%	3.52%	19.12%	5.34%	45.74%
2027	1	26.24%	3.52%	19.13%	5.36%	45.75%
2027	2	26.19%	3.52%	19.15%	5.38%	45.76%
2027	3	26.14%	3.52%	19.17%	5.39%	45.78%
2027	4	26.10%	3.52%	19.19%	5.41%	45.78%
2028	1	26.05%	3.52%	19.20%	5.43%	45.80%
2028	2	26.01%	3.52%	19.22%	5.45%	45.80%
2028	3	25.96%	3.52%	19.24%	5.46%	45.82%
2028	4	25.91%	3.52%	19.26%	5.48%	45.83%
2029	1	25.87%	3.52%	19.27%	5.50%	45.84%
2029	2	25.82%	3.52%	19.29%	5.51%	45.86%
2029	3	25.78%	3.52%	19.31%	5.53%	45.86%
2029	4	25.73%	3.52%	19.32%	5.55%	45.88%
2030	1	25.68%	3.52%	19.34%	5.57%	45.89%
2030	2	25.64%	3.52%	19.36%	5.58%	45.90%
2030	3	25.59%	3.52%	19.38%	5.60%	45.91%
2030	4	25.55%	3.52%	19.39%	5.62%	45.92%
2031	1	25.50%	3.52%	19.41%	5.64%	45.93%
2031	2	25.45%	3.52%	19.43%	5.65%	45.95%
2031	3	25.41%	3.52%	19.44%	5.67%	45.96%
2031	4	25.36%	3.52%	19.46%	5.69%	45.97%
2032	1	25.32%	3.52%	19.48%	5.70%	45.98%
2032	2	25.27%	3.52%	19.50%	5.72%	45.99%
2032	3	25.22%	3.52%	19.51%	5.74%	46.01%
2032	4	25.18%	3.52%	19.53%	5.76%	46.01%
2033	1	25.13%	3.52%	19.55%	5.77%	46.03%
2033	2	25.09%	3.52%	19.57%	5.79%	46.03%
2033	3	25.04%	3.52%	19.58%	5.81%	46.05%
2033	4	24.99%	3.52%	19.60%	5.82%	46.07%
2034	1	24.95%	3.52%	19.62%	5.84%	46.07%
2034	2	24.90%	3.52%	19.63%	5.86%	46.09%
2034	3	24.86%	3.52%	19.65%	5.88%	46.09%
2034	4	24.81%	3.52%	19.67%	5.89%	46.11%
2035	1	24.76%	3.52%	19.69%	5.91%	46.12%
2035	2	24.72%	3.52%	19.70%	5.93%	46.13%
2035	3	24.67%	3.52%	19.72%	5.95%	46.14%
2035	4	24.63%	3.52%	19.74%	5.96%	46.15%
2036	1	24.58%	3.52%	19.76%	5.98%	46.16%
2036	2	24.53%	3.52%	19.77%	6.00%	46.18%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Labour-market participation rates of women ages 16 to 69						
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal in-dependent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2036	3	24.49%	3.52%	19.79%	6.01%	46.19%
2036	4	24.44%	3.52%	19.81%	6.03%	46.20%
2037	1	24.40%	3.52%	19.82%	6.05%	46.21%
2037	2	24.35%	3.52%	19.84%	6.07%	46.22%
2037	3	24.30%	3.52%	19.86%	6.08%	46.24%
2037	4	24.26%	3.52%	19.88%	6.10%	46.24%
2038	1	24.21%	3.52%	19.89%	6.12%	46.26%
2038	2	24.17%	3.52%	19.91%	6.14%	46.26%
2038	3	24.12%	3.52%	19.93%	6.15%	46.28%
2038	4	24.07%	3.52%	19.94%	6.17%	46.30%
2039	1	24.03%	3.52%	19.96%	6.19%	46.30%
2039	2	23.98%	3.52%	19.98%	6.20%	46.32%
2039	3	23.94%	3.52%	20.00%	6.22%	46.32%
2039	4	23.89%	3.52%	20.01%	6.24%	46.34%
2040	1	23.84%	3.52%	20.03%	6.26%	46.35%
2040	2	23.80%	3.52%	20.05%	6.27%	46.36%
2040	3	23.75%	3.52%	20.07%	6.29%	46.37%
2040	4	23.71%	3.52%	20.08%	6.31%	46.38%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Table N.9: Low labour-market scenario, both genders

Labour-market participation rates of people aged 16 to 69						
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal in-dependent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2017	1	31.80%	5.39%	23.09%	6.25%	33.47%
2017	2	31.34%	5.44%	23.03%	6.12%	34.07%
2017	3	31.40%	5.39%	23.11%	6.08%	34.01%
2017	4	31.46%	5.33%	23.18%	6.03%	33.99%
2018	1	31.52%	5.27%	23.27%	5.98%	33.95%
2018	2	31.58%	5.22%	23.35%	5.94%	33.91%
2018	3	31.65%	5.16%	23.43%	5.89%	33.86%
2018	4	31.71%	5.11%	23.51%	5.85%	33.83%
2019	1	31.88%	5.04%	23.55%	5.75%	33.78%
2019	2	31.82%	5.04%	23.59%	5.77%	33.78%
2019	3	31.76%	5.04%	23.61%	5.79%	33.80%
2019	4	31.71%	5.04%	23.64%	5.80%	33.81%
2020	1	31.65%	5.04%	23.66%	5.82%	33.82%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Labour-market participation rates of people aged 16 to 69						
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal in-dependent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2020	2	31.61%	5.04%	23.70%	5.84%	33.82%
2020	3	31.55%	5.04%	23.73%	5.86%	33.83%
2020	4	31.48%	5.04%	23.74%	5.87%	33.86%
2021	1	31.43%	5.04%	23.77%	5.89%	33.87%
2021	2	31.37%	5.04%	23.80%	5.91%	33.88%
2021	3	31.32%	5.04%	23.83%	5.92%	33.89%
2021	4	31.26%	5.04%	23.85%	5.94%	33.90%
2022	1	31.20%	5.04%	23.88%	5.96%	33.91%
2022	2	31.15%	5.04%	23.91%	5.98%	33.92%
2022	3	31.10%	5.05%	23.94%	6.00%	33.92%
2022	4	31.04%	5.05%	23.97%	6.02%	33.93%
2023	1	30.99%	5.05%	23.99%	6.03%	33.94%
2023	2	30.93%	5.05%	24.03%	6.05%	33.94%
2023	3	30.88%	5.05%	24.06%	6.07%	33.94%
2023	4	30.82%	5.05%	24.09%	6.09%	33.94%
2024	1	30.77%	5.05%	24.11%	6.10%	33.96%
2024	2	30.71%	5.05%	24.14%	6.12%	33.97%
2024	3	30.66%	5.05%	24.17%	6.14%	33.98%
2024	4	30.61%	5.06%	24.20%	6.16%	33.98%
2025	1	30.55%	5.05%	24.23%	6.18%	33.99%
2025	2	30.50%	5.06%	24.25%	6.19%	34.01%
2025	3	30.44%	5.06%	24.28%	6.21%	34.02%
2025	4	30.38%	5.06%	24.31%	6.23%	34.02%
2026	1	30.33%	5.06%	24.34%	6.25%	34.03%
2026	2	30.27%	5.06%	24.36%	6.26%	34.04%
2026	3	30.21%	5.06%	24.39%	6.28%	34.06%
2026	4	30.15%	5.06%	24.42%	6.30%	34.08%
2027	1	30.10%	5.06%	24.44%	6.31%	34.08%
2027	2	30.05%	5.06%	24.47%	6.33%	34.09%
2027	3	29.99%	5.06%	24.50%	6.35%	34.11%
2027	4	29.94%	5.06%	24.53%	6.37%	34.10%
2028	1	29.88%	5.06%	24.56%	6.39%	34.11%
2028	2	29.83%	5.06%	24.59%	6.41%	34.11%
2028	3	29.77%	5.07%	24.62%	6.42%	34.12%
2028	4	29.71%	5.07%	24.65%	6.44%	34.13%
2029	1	29.66%	5.07%	24.67%	6.46%	34.15%
2029	2	29.60%	5.07%	24.71%	6.47%	34.15%
2029	3	29.55%	5.07%	24.73%	6.49%	34.16%
2029	4	29.49%	5.07%	24.76%	6.51%	34.17%
2030	1	29.43%	5.07%	24.78%	6.53%	34.19%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Labour-market participation rates of people aged 16 to 69						
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal in-dependent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2030	2	29.38%	5.07%	24.81%	6.54%	34.19%
2030	3	29.32%	5.07%	24.84%	6.56%	34.20%
2030	4	29.27%	5.07%	24.86%	6.58%	34.22%
2031	1	29.20%	5.07%	24.89%	6.60%	34.24%
2031	2	29.15%	5.07%	24.92%	6.61%	34.25%
2031	3	29.09%	5.07%	24.94%	6.63%	34.27%
2031	4	29.03%	5.07%	24.96%	6.65%	34.29%
2032	1	28.98%	5.07%	24.99%	6.66%	34.29%
2032	2	28.92%	5.07%	25.02%	6.68%	34.31%
2032	3	28.86%	5.07%	25.04%	6.70%	34.33%
2032	4	28.81%	5.07%	25.07%	6.72%	34.33%
2033	1	28.75%	5.07%	25.10%	6.74%	34.34%
2033	2	28.70%	5.07%	25.13%	6.76%	34.34%
2033	3	28.64%	5.07%	25.15%	6.77%	34.37%
2033	4	28.58%	5.07%	25.19%	6.79%	34.37%
2034	1	28.53%	5.07%	25.22%	6.81%	34.38%
2034	2	28.47%	5.07%	25.24%	6.82%	34.39%
2034	3	28.42%	5.07%	25.27%	6.84%	34.40%
2034	4	28.36%	5.07%	25.29%	6.86%	34.42%
2035	1	28.30%	5.07%	25.32%	6.88%	34.43%
2035	2	28.25%	5.07%	25.35%	6.89%	34.44%
2035	3	28.18%	5.07%	25.37%	6.91%	34.46%
2035	4	28.13%	5.07%	25.39%	6.93%	34.48%
2036	1	28.07%	5.07%	25.42%	6.94%	34.50%
2036	2	28.01%	5.07%	25.44%	6.96%	34.52%
2036	3	27.95%	5.07%	25.47%	6.98%	34.53%
2036	4	27.89%	5.07%	25.49%	7.00%	34.55%
2037	1	27.84%	5.07%	25.52%	7.01%	34.56%
2037	2	27.78%	5.07%	25.54%	7.03%	34.57%
2037	3	27.72%	5.07%	25.57%	7.05%	34.59%
2037	4	27.67%	5.07%	25.61%	7.07%	34.59%
2038	1	27.61%	5.07%	25.63%	7.08%	34.60%
2038	2	27.56%	5.07%	25.66%	7.10%	34.61%
2038	3	27.50%	5.08%	25.69%	7.12%	34.62%
2038	4	27.44%	5.08%	25.72%	7.13%	34.64%
2039	1	27.38%	5.07%	25.74%	7.15%	34.65%
2039	2	27.33%	5.07%	25.77%	7.17%	34.66%
2039	3	27.27%	5.07%	25.79%	7.19%	34.68%
2039	4	27.21%	5.07%	25.81%	7.20%	34.71%
2040	1	27.15%	5.07%	25.83%	7.22%	34.72%

Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)

Labour-market participation rates of people aged 16 to 69						
Year	Quarter	Formal wage-earners	Formal independent	Informal	Unemployed	Inactive
2040	2	27.09%	5.07%	25.85%	7.24%	34.75%
2040	3	27.03%	5.07%	25.89%	7.26%	34.75%
2040	4	26.98%	5.07%	25.90%	7.27%	34.78%
Source: EPHc (2017/Q1)						

Appendix O

The prospective marriage market module: simulating transitions in and out of couples

In this Appendix, we will lay out the various equations we estimated for the micro-calibration of our prospective marriage market module, studied in section 2.4.3. These are presented in the order we run them in our model. We first analyse the divorce equation, which determines (together with deaths) who exits a married union. We then study the marriage equation, that determines which couples marry. After that, we lay out the break-up equation, which completes the exit from common-law unions. We next present the equation that determines who enters a common-law union. Finally, we explain our matching equation that determines the composition of new common-law unions. All these equations are logistic models estimated on the EPHc (2003-2015) separately by gender and both at a quarterly and yearly transition interval. The methodology employed is the same than for our labour-market behavioural equations studied in section 2.3, so we employ a five-fold stepwise selection procedure to select the model with the best explanatory power while avoiding over-fitting it to the estimation data.

O.1 Simulating divorces

Equation O.1 below depicts our logistic divorce model and its results are listed in Table O.1.

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{i,t} = & \alpha + \beta \text{Age}_{i,t-1} + \gamma \text{Age}_{i,t-1}^2 + \sum_{j=1}^3 \delta_j \text{Edu}_{i,j,t-1} + \zeta \text{Child}_{i,t-1} \\
& + \sum_{k=-2}^2 \eta_k \text{Edu}_{\text{Gap}_{i,k,t-1}} + \sum_{l=-2}^2 \psi_l \text{Age}_{\text{Gap}_{i,l,t-1}} + \sum_{m=1}^4 \theta_m \text{CW}_{i,m,t-1} + \epsilon_{i,t}
\end{aligned} \tag{O.1}$$

The universe of studied individuals Ω is people that were married in $t - 1$ with a surveyed partner. The dependent variable $D_{i,t}$ is a dummy that equals 1 when individual i divorced between $t - 1$ and t and 0 otherwise. We chose to keep all explanatory variables lagged at period $t - 1$ because some pertain to the characteristics of the dissolved couple, which can only be observed $\forall i \in \Omega$ in $t - 1$. We include age and the square of age to capture the non-linear relationship between divorce and age. The rest of the explanatory variables are polytomous and include education level ($\text{Edu}_j, j \in [1; 3]$), having minor children (Child), the couple's difference in education levels Edu_{Gap} and in age Age_{Gap} and which members of the couple work CW. The results are listed in Table O.1 below.

Table O.1: Divorce equations by gender and interval

Explanatory variables	Men				Women			
	Quarterly (1)		Yearly (2)		Quarterly (3)		Yearly (4)	
Intercept	-6.1169 ***	(0.1870)	-4.5321 ***	(0.1976)	-7.4967 ***	(0.7048)	-6.3342 ***	(0.4977)
Age					0.0958 ***	(0.0307)	0.1008 ***	(0.0219)
Age^2	-0.00019 ***	(0.000063)	-0.00045 ***	(0.000058)	-0.00120 ***	(0.000332)	-0.00134 ***	(0.000239)
Does not have minor children			Reference					
Has minor children			-0.3159 **	(0.1331)				
Incomplete secondary education					0.6343 ***	(0.1609)	0.3547 ***	(0.1082)
Complete secondary education					0.4167 ***	(0.1513)	0.2184 **	(0.0976)
University degree					Reference		Reference	
Both work	Reference		Reference		Reference		Reference	
Only partner works	0.8963 ***	(0.2352)	0.5738 ***	(0.2181)	-0.2782 **	(0.1090)	-0.3891 ***	(0.0761)
Works but partner does not	-0.00727	(0.1562)	0.0479	(0.1198)	0.3929 **	(0.1823)	-0.0210	(0.1507)
None work	-0.1166	(0.2809)	0.4827 **	(0.2014)	-0.7627 ***	(0.2421)	-0.3424 **	(0.1587)
$\text{Age} - \text{Age}_{\text{Part}} \geq 10$	1.1575 ***	(0.2104)	1.5896 ***	(0.1536)			-0.4615	(0.5247)
$\text{Age} - \text{Age}_{\text{Part}} \in [7; 9]$	0.0145	(0.2771)	0.1119	(0.2082)			0.7072 ***	(0.2343)

Source: Author's calculation on EPHc (2003-2015) data. * Significant at 10% ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Standard errors are in parentheses.

Dependent variables	Men		Women	
	Quarterly (1)	Yearly (2)	Quarterly (3)	Yearly (4)
$Age - Age_{Part} \in [4; 6]$	0.3934 ** (0.1737)	0.1411 (0.1439)		0.4401 *** (0.1474)
$Age - Age_{Part} \in [-3; 3]$	Reference	Reference		Reference
$Age - Age_{Part} \in [-6; -4]$	0.7033 ** (0.2877)	-0.3938 (0.3434)		-0.1394 (0.0871)
$Age - Age_{Part} \in [-9; -7]$	-12.6843 (367.7)	0.4995 (0.3881)		-0.3637 *** (0.1331)
$Age - Age_{Part} \leq -10$	1.1618 ** (0.4531)	0.1799 (0.5121)		-0.0816 (0.1344)
Two levels of education below partner	0.6812 ** (0.3035)	-1.1133 ** (0.5350)	-1.1871 (0.8933)	-0.2997 (0.4530)
One level of education below partner	0.0795 (0.1813)	-0.1272 (0.1429)	-0.1194 (0.1554)	0.1582 (0.1038)
Same education level	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference
One level of education above partner	0.2948 (0.1993)	0.0870 (0.1595)	0.1795 (0.1426)	0.3952 *** (0.0931)
Two levels of education above partner	0.8456 * (0.4892)	0.8320 ** (0.3804)	0.6284 ** (0.2768)	0.8307 *** (0.1723)
Observations	109268	91749	110117	92954
(training dataset) AUC (training dataset)	0.5875	0.6348	0.6327	0.6432
AUC (validation dataset)	0.5337	0.588	0.6282	0.6647
The starting point for reading this logistic regression is determining an individual of reference. Here, it is a person who does not have minor children, has an university degree, is in a couple where both partners work, has no more than three years of difference in age with his or her partner and both have the same education level. The point of the logistic regression is to see the impact on the dependent variable when one of these elements is changed. For instance, a man that has minor children has less chances of divorcing within the next year than a man without minor children, <i>ceteris paribus</i> . Sometimes, a variable is not significant across all divorce equations by gender and interval. We left blank cells in those cases.				
Source: Author's calculation on EPHc (2003-2015) data. * Significant at 10% ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Standard errors are in parentheses.				

We can see the determinants of divorce for men and women differ significantly. For men, divorces decrease with age and increase when only the woman works. For women on the other hand, the relationship between age and divorce is bell-shaped. Also, the probability of divorcing decreases when the woman does not work and with education level. Finally, there is no robust impact of age and education differences between spouses in the probability to divorce for both men and women. We decided to input the quarterly divorce equation estimated for women (model (3)) in our microsimulation model. This is because we only need to simulate the divorce probability of one of the spouses, and that the model has a stronger explanatory power and is less dependent on the training dataset. This is shown by the fact the C-statistics (or Area Under Curve, AUC) we get

when estimating our divorce equation on women are not only higher but also more similar for our training and validation dataset. In the end, although the explanatory power of this divorce equation is low (with an AUC of 0.63), we still get to determine which women will divorce in a given quarter in a more plausible way than if we were to pick them randomly (which corresponds to an AUC of 0.5, that is a 50% probability of rightly predicting which women divorce). We get as an end result a selection of marriages that will dissolve, the exact quantity being determined by women’s divorce probability by age and gender as listed in Table 2.3.

O.2 The marriage equation

First of all, Equation O.2 below represents the estimated marriage equation.

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_{i,t} = & \alpha + \beta \text{Age}_{i,t-1} + \gamma \text{Age}_{i,t-1}^2 + \sum_{j=1}^3 \delta_j \text{Edu}_{i,j,t-1} + \zeta \text{Child}_{i,t-1} \\
 & + \sum_{k=-2}^2 \eta_k \text{Edu}_{\text{Gap}_{i,k,t-1}} + \sum_{l=-2}^2 \psi_l \text{Age}_{\text{Gap}_{i,l,t-1}} + \sum_{m=1}^4 \theta_m \text{CW}_{i,m,t-1} + \sum_{n=1}^4 \lambda_n \text{Stu}_{i,n,t-1} + \epsilon_{i,t}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{O.2}$$

The universe of studied individuals Ω is people in a common-law union in $t - 1$ with a known partner. The dependent variable $M_{i,t}$ equals 1 when $i \in \Omega$ married his or her partner between periods $t - 1$ and t and 0 otherwise. The explanatory variables are the same than in the divorce equation O.1, although we added variable Stu to check whether any, some or all of the couple members were students. Equation O.2 was estimated separately by gender and for both a quarterly and a yearly interval. The results are listed in Table O.2 below.

Table O.2: Marriage equations by gender and interval

Dependent variables	Men				Women			
	Quarterly (1)		Yearly (2)		Quarterly (3)		Yearly (4)	
Intercept	-4.7054 ***	(0.1775)	-3.2622 ***	(0.0674)	-4.8129 ***	(0.1703)	-3.0960 ***	(0.0813)
Age	0.0748 ***	(0.00766)	0.0342 ***	(0.00142)	0.0841 ***	(0.00768)	0.0334 ***	(0.00157)
Source: Author’s calculation on EPHc (2003-2015) data. * Significant at 10% ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Standard errors are in parentheses.								

Dependent variables	Men		Women	
	Quarterly (1)	Yearly (2)	Quarterly (3)	Yearly (4)
Age^2	-0.00029 (0.000081) ***	-0.4802 (0.0416) ***	-0.00045 (0.000086) ***	-0.1186 (0.0400) ***
Does not have minor children	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference
Has minor children	0.1372 (0.0407) ***		0.1222 (0.0417) ***	-0.1186 (0.0400) ***
Incomplete secondary education	-0.3815 (0.0416) ***	-0.4802 (0.0416) ***	-0.3893 (0.0434) ***	-0.4802 (0.0440) ***
Complete secondary education	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference
University degree	0.2491 (0.0580) ***	0.3937 (0.0597) ***	0.2627 (0.0551) ***	0.2284 (0.0553) ***
Both work	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference
Only partner works	-0.2613 (0.0809) ***	-0.0892 (0.0818) ***	0.0616 (0.0393) ***	0.1191 (0.0388) ***
Works but partner does not	0.0170 (0.0383) ***	0.1377 (0.0388) ***	-0.1185 (0.0792) ***	-0.1401 * (0.0826)
None work	0.1125 (0.0718) ***	0.2268 (0.0691) ***	0.2503 (0.0715) ***	0.2215 (0.0690) ***
$Age - Age_{Part} \geq 10$	-0.7037 (0.0562) ***	-0.5774 (0.0575) ***	-0.4278 (0.0964) ***	-0.9623 (0.1238) ***
$Age - Age_{Part} \in [7; 9]$	-0.3500 (0.0605) ***	-0.1712 (0.0596) ***	-0.6891 (0.1148) ***	-0.5709 (0.1134) ***
$Age - Age_{Part} \in [4; 6]$	-0.0749 (0.0457) ***	-0.1004 (0.0473) **	-0.3038 (0.0735) ***	-0.4366 (0.0762) ***
$Age - Age_{Part} \in [-3; 3]$	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference
$Age - Age_{Part} \in [-6; -4]$	-0.1380 * (0.0728)	-0.1816 (0.0745) **	0.1664 (0.0461) ***	0.0136 (0.0474)
$Age - Age_{Part} \in [-9; -7]$	-0.1999 * (0.1058)	-0.2456 (0.1081) **	-0.0104 (0.0608)	0.0471 (0.0583)
$Age - Age_{Part} \leq -10$	0.0117 (0.0962)	-0.3718 (0.1166) ***	0.0334 (0.0518)	-0.0685 (0.0536)
Two levels of education below partner	0.5717 (0.1003) ***	0.1858 (0.1238)	0.6908 (0.1629) ***	0.4636 (0.1690) ***
One level of education below partner	0.0728 (0.0460)	0.3735 (0.0442) ***	0.1800 (0.0529) ***	0.2399 (0.0542) ***
Same education level	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference
One level of education above partner	-0.1972 (0.0579) ***	-0.2525 (0.0602) ***	-0.2766 (0.0519) ***	-0.0524 (0.0503) ***
Two levels of education above partner	-0.3341 * (0.1901)	-0.5522 (0.1828) ***	-0.2374 (0.1158) **	-0.4432 (0.1296) ***
None is a student			Reference	
Studies and partner does not			-0.3135 (0.1477) **	
Only partner studies			-1.7489 (1.1943)	
Both are students			-10.6122 (127.3)	
Observations (training dataset)	47503	36522	46822	36156
AUC (training dataset)	0.6637	0.6345	0.6662	0.6336
AUC (validation dataset)	0.6665	0.6414	0.6604	0.6479

Source: Author's calculation on EPHc (2003-2015) data. * Significant at 10% ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Standard errors are in parentheses.

First of all, the determinants of marriage are similar for both men and women. The probability of marrying increases with education level and is at its maximum at the middle ages of life, as evidenced by the bell-shaped relationship between age and the probability of marrying. Moreover, age differences have a negative impact on the probability of marrying, although the negative impact is the highest for women that are significantly older than their partner. In what regards education, women tend to marry men that have attained a higher education level, although this result is not robustly verified in the case of men. Finally, labour-market situation does not seem to have a robust impact on marriage probabilities. Contrary to our divorce equations, the explanatory power of the

models estimated for men ((1) and (2)) are the same than those estimated for women ((3) and (4)). We thus arbitrarily decided to input the quarterly marriage equation estimated for women (model (3)) in our microsimulation model, in order to keep the same gender than for our divorce equation. The explanatory power of the marriage equations are still low, having a C-statistic of 0.66, but they give some level of micro-level plausibility when selecting which unmarried couples marry.

O.3 Simulating the breaking-up of common-law unions

The propensity score of breaking off a common-law union is given by a logistic model depicted in equation O.3 below.

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_{i,t} = & \alpha + \beta \text{Age}_{i,t-1} + \gamma \text{Age}_{i,t-1}^2 + \sum_{j=1}^3 \delta_j \text{Edu}_{i,j,t-1} + \zeta \text{Child}_{i,t-1} \\
 & + \sum_{k=-2}^2 \eta_k \text{Edu}_{\text{Gap}_{i,k,t-1}} + \sum_{l=-3}^3 \psi_l \text{Age}_{\text{Gap}_{i,l,t-1}} + \sum_{m=1}^4 \theta_m \text{CW}_{i,m,t-1} + \epsilon_{i,t}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{O.3}$$

The universe of studied individuals Ω is people in a common-law union in $t - 1$ with a known partner. The dependent variable $B_{i,t}$ equals 1 when $i \in \Omega$ broke up with his or her partner between periods $t - 1$ and t and 0 otherwise. The explanatory variables are the same than in the divorce equation O.1. Equation O.3 was estimated separately by gender and for both a quarterly and a yearly interval. The results are listed in Table O.2 below.

Table O.3: Break-up equations by gender and interval

Dependent variables	Men				Women			
	Quarterly (1)		Yearly (2)		Quarterly (3)		Yearly (4)	
Intercept	0.4366	(0.2705)	-0.9241	(0.2847)	-1.3212	(0.2916)	-1.8267	(0.1164)
Age	-0.1722	(0.0133)	-0.0831	(0.0136)	-0.0879	(0.0150)	-0.0282	(0.00264)
Age^2	0.00153	(0.000145)	0.000633	(0.000152)	0.000633	(0.000181)		
Does not have minor children	Reference		Reference		Reference		Reference	
Has minor children	-0.9688	(0.0749)	-0.9187	(0.0692)	-0.5116	(0.0716)	-0.4810	(0.0602)
Both work	Reference		Reference		Reference		Reference	
Only partner works			-0.1534	(0.1663)	-0.1993	(0.0753)	-0.0986	(0.0618)

Source: Author's calculation on EPHc (2003-2015) data. * Significant at 10% ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Standard errors are in parentheses.

Dependent variables	Men				Women			
	Quarterly (1)		Yearly (2)		Quarterly (3)		Yearly (4)	
Works but partner does not			0.0462	(0.0717)	0.7106	(0.1208)	0.4391	(0.1137)
None work			0.4845	(0.1280)	***	(0.1375)	***	(0.1025)
$Age - Age_{Part} \geq 10$	0.6010	(0.1212)	***	0.5191	(0.1067)	***	0.6178	(0.1869)
$Age - Age_{Part} \in [7; 9]$	0.1545	(0.1366)	***	0.0129	(0.1284)	***	0.7479	(0.1657)
$Age - Age_{Part} \in [4; 6]$	-0.0341	(0.1033)	***	0.2540	(0.0877)	***	0.2377 *	(0.1373)
$Age - Age_{Part} \in [-3; 3]$	Reference		Reference		Reference		Reference	
$Age - Age_{Part} \in [-6; -4]$	-0.3557	(0.1684)	**	-0.1542	(0.1441)	***	-0.2920	(0.0977)
$Age - Age_{Part} \in [-9; -7]$	0.1114	(0.2005)	**	-0.1035	(0.2010)	***	-0.3079	(0.1275)
$Age - Age_{Part} \leq -10$	0.6012	(0.1527)	***	-0.1470	(0.1947)	**	-0.1820 *	(0.1070)
Two levels of education below partner	0.1558	(0.2325)	**	-0.0430	(0.2493)	***	0.7159	(0.3100)
One level of education below partner	-0.1980	(0.0960)	***	-0.3327	(0.0953)	**	0.0278	(0.1069)
Same education level	Reference		Reference		Reference		Reference	
One level of education above partner	0.3672	(0.1155)	***	0.2054	(0.0924)	***	0.2933	(0.0790)
Two levels of education above partner	0.3331	(0.4649)	**	0.6668	(0.2816)	***	-0.2241	(0.2704)
Incomplete secondary education	0.1845	(0.0865)	**				0.3384 *	(0.1752)
Complete secondary education	Reference							
University degree	-0.2508 *	(0.1423)						
Observations (training dataset)	44835		34043		44438		34244	
AUC (training dataset)	0.6772		0.6574		0.6127		0.5848	
AUC (validation dataset)	0.6709		0.6108		0.5951		0.5938	

Source: Author's calculation on EPHc (2003-2015) data. * Significant at 10% ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Standard errors are in parentheses.

There are some elements that are verified for both men and women. First, age has a non-linear impact on break-up probabilities: these are the highest at low and advanced ages, and the lowest at middle ages. This result is in line with measured break-up probabilities as listed in Table 2.4. Then, having a minor child significantly reduces the probability of leaving a common-law union. Finally, differences in education level tend to increase the probability of breaking a common-law union, although this result is not robust to changing the length of the interval. This said, there are some gender-specific elements. First, women tend to leave common-law unions where their (male) partner does not work. Second, they also tend to leave unions where they are significantly older than their male counterpart and stay in those where they are significantly younger. These gender-specific results are not however robustly verified in the case of men and must thus be taken with caution. Model (1), depicting the probability a man has of leaving a common-law union within a quarter, has the highest C-statistic (an AUC of 0.67) and suffers less from over-fitting the training dataset, so it is the one we input in our dynamic microsimulation model. In the end, we compute the propensity score men have of leaving a common-law union in a mildly realistic way, which adds to the micro-level consistency

of our microsimulation model.

O.4 Determining who enters a common-law union

Equation O.4 computes the propensity score of entering a common-law union between quarters $t - 1$ and t , while Table O.4 lays out the estimated coefficients for both men and women.

$$N_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta \text{Age}_{i,t} + \beta \text{Age}_{i,t}^2 + \sum_{j=1}^n \gamma_j X_{i,j,t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^3 \sum_{l=1}^4 \delta_{j,l} LMS_{i,j,t-1} \times Q_{i,l,t-1} \quad (\text{O.4})$$

$$+ \delta_4 LMS_{i,4,t-1} + \delta_5 LMS_{i,5,t-1} + \epsilon_{i,t}$$

In equation O.4, $N_{i,t}$ equals 1 when individual i enters a common-law union in t and 0 otherwise. As in our Mincer wage Equations 2.3 and 2.4 of Section 2.3.3, $LMS_{i,j,t-1}$, $j \in [1; 5]$ are dummies for lagged labour-market states (in order, from 1 to 5: registered wage-earners, registered independent workers, informal workers, unemployed and inactive) and $Q_{i,l,t-1}$, $l \in [1; 4]$ are sectoral labour-market income quartiles. Finally, $\sum_{j=1}^n \gamma_j X_{i,j,t-1}$ are other lagged control variables and $\epsilon_{i,t}$ and individual error term. The estimated coefficients are listed in Table O.4 below.

Table O.4: Probability of people out of a relationship of entering a common-law union, ages 18 to 90

Dependent variables	Men				Women			
	Quarterly (1)		Yearly (2)		Quarterly (3)		Yearly (4)	
Intercept	-5.5790 ***	(0.2428)	-4.0409 ***	(0.0499)	-6.1245 ***	(0.2748)	-5.1620 ***	(0.2318)
Age	0.0473 ***	(0.0117)			0.0443 ***	(0.0126)	0.0655 ***	(0.0126)
Age ²	-0.00044 ***	(0.000137)			-0.00072 ***	(0.000152)	-0.00115 ***	(0.000157)
Does not have minor children	Reference		Reference		Reference		Reference	
Has minor children	-0.6678 ***	(0.2020)	-0.4864 ***	(0.1786)	-0.5202 ***	(0.1292)	-1.2214 ***	(0.1336)
Incomplete secondary education	0.5785 ***	(0.0701)	0.3212 ***	(0.0566)	0.4334 ***	(0.0748)	0.3248 ***	(0.0630)
Complete secondary education	Reference		Reference		Reference		Reference	
University degree	-0.0894	(0.1261)	0.1289	(0.0928)	0.2590 **	(0.1085)	0.1229	(0.0923)
Is divorced	0.3886 ***	(0.0993)			0.1513	(0.1174)	0.3352 ***	(0.1089)
Is widowed	-0.1898	(0.1815)			-1.1520 ***	(0.2121)	-0.2727	(0.1744)
Is single	Reference				Reference		Reference	

Source: Author's calculation on EPHc (2003-2015) data. * Significant at 10% ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Standard errors are in parentheses.

Table O.4: Probability of people out of a relationship of entering a common-law union, ages 18 to 90

Dependent variables	Men		Women	
	Quarterly (1)	Yearly (2)	Quarterly (3)	Yearly (4)
$Q1_t \times LMS_{1,t} = 1$	Reference	Reference	Reference	
$Q1_t \times LMS_{1,t} = 0$	-0.1850 * (0.1075)		0.4409 *** (0.1500)	
$Q2_t \times LMS_{1,t} = 1$	-0.3303 ** (0.1334)			
$Q2_t \times LMS_{1,t} = 0$	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference
$Q3_t \times LMS_{1,t} = 1$	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference
$Q3_t \times LMS_{1,t} = 0$	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference
$Q4_t \times LMS_{1,t} = 1$	0.3896 *** (0.1214)	0.7299 *** (0.0923)		
$Q4_t \times LMS_{1,t} = 0$	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference
$Q1_t \times LMS_{2,t} = 1$			-1.4574 ** (0.7222)	
$Q1_t \times LMS_{2,t} = 0$	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference
$Q2_t \times LMS_{2,t} = 1$			Reference	Reference
$Q2_t \times LMS_{2,t} = 0$	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference
$Q3_t \times LMS_{2,t} = 1$	0.5644 ** (0.2352)			0.5775 * (0.3134)
$Q3_t \times LMS_{2,t} = 0$	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference
$Q4_t \times LMS_{2,t} = 1$	-3.3763 ** (1.5504)			
$Q4_t \times LMS_{2,t} = 0$	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference
$Q1_t \times LMS_{3,t} = 1$		-0.2316 ** (0.1036)	0.2702 ** (0.1107)	
$Q1_t \times LMS_{3,t} = 0$	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference
$Q2_t \times LMS_{3,t} = 1$			Reference	Reference
$Q2_t \times LMS_{3,t} = 0$	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference
$Q3_t \times LMS_{3,t} = 1$			Reference	Reference
$Q3_t \times LMS_{3,t} = 0$	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference
$Q4_t \times LMS_{3,t} = 1$		0.2826 *** (0.0835)	0.5364 *** (0.1470)	0.3111 ** (0.1374)
$Q4_t \times LMS_{3,t} = 0$	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference
$LMS_{4,t} = 1$	-0.2531 ** (0.1124)	-0.2561 *** (0.0933)		0.3267 *** (0.0924)
$LMS_{4,t} = 0$	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference
$LMS_{5,t} = 1$	-1.0837 *** (0.0979)	-1.1707 *** (0.0766)		-0.1442 * (0.0740)
$LMS_{5,t} = 0$	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference
Observations (training dataset)	123152	97219	161570	129003
AUC (training dataset)	0.6507	0.6487	0.6725	0.6776
AUC (validation dataset)	0.6468	0.6486	0.6607	0.6901

Source: Author's calculation on EPHc (2003-2015) data. * Significant at 10% ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Standard errors are in parentheses.

First of all, our regressions have a low explanatory power for determining who enters a common-law union. This is evidenced by the low level of our C-statistics (between 0.6 and 0.7) but also by the significant difference of C-statistics on regressions run on the training and validation dataset. We can nevertheless see that, first of all, age has a bell-shaped relationship with entering a common-law union for both men and women, which is coherent with the concentration of people in a common-law union at middle ages as seen in Table 2.1. Then, that having minor children has a strongly negative impact on the probability of entering a common-law union, which may indicate it is either more difficult or less desirable for them to get a new partner. We also see an incomplete secondary education has a negative impact in entering a common-law union. Finally, inactive or unemployed men have a lesser probability of entering a common-law union, while these

same variables do not have a robust impact on women’s probabilities. The other explanatory variables fail to have a robust impact on the probability of entering a common-law union. In the end and despite their limitations, these estimated behavioural equations let us select the individuals that transit into a common-law union in a way that beats a purely random selection as evidenced by the fact our AUC are significantly above 0.5. Since we select uncoupled men and women for entry in a relationship, we input in our dynamic microsimulation model equations (1) and (3).

O.5 Determining the composition of new couples

Equation O.5 below is the matching equation and Table O.5 contains the estimated coefficients. We remind the reader it is estimated using the methodology by Zinn *et al.* (2012), which we reviewed in section 2.4.4. The logic behind this method is that we can observe in our household survey the formation of new couples and their members’ characteristics. The problem is we do not observe the couples that may have been formed but never came to be. To be more specific, each period there is a number of men and women that form a couple, which constitute the individuals on the market for entering a relationship. We can see the couples that were effectively formed, but in theory the composition of the couples could have been different. If those specific couples and not others were formed, it is because the members had individual characteristics (such as age, labour situation or education level) that made them start that specific relationship and not another. It is by comparing the characteristics of newly observed couples with those of other possible couples that never happened that we can gauge the impact of each of those characteristics on the composition of new couples. To generate these observations of unformed couples, Zinn *et al.* (2012) splits the dataset of observed new unions as follows. Half of the dataset is left untouched, while in the other half the observed couples are undone and randomly rearranged. Half of the resulting dataset is thus made up of fictitious couples, and the other half of actual new unions. It is then possible to estimation the matching equation O.5 below.

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_{i,t} = & \alpha + \sum_{j=-2}^2 \beta_j \text{Edu}_{\text{Gap}_{i,j,t}} + \sum_{k=-3}^3 \gamma_k \text{Age}_{\text{Gap}_{i,k,t}} \\
 & + \sum_{m=1}^4 \delta_m \text{CW}_{i,m,t} + \frac{ITL_t - ITL_{\text{Part},t}}{RIPT E_t} + \epsilon_{i,t}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{O.5}$$

The dependent variable $M_{i,t}$ equals 1 when the individual belongs to an actually observed couple and 0 when it is part of an artificial couple. In equation O.5, we have chosen to only keep as explanatory variables differences between partners. This is because it is not the individual characteristics of i that determine whether he is in the observed or in the artificial couple group, but the comparison of his characteristics with those of his partner. Moreover, this logistic model of first cohabitation comes after a behavioural equation that helps determine who enters a common-law union, where individual characteristics are already independent variables. Thus unlike Zinn *et al.* (2012), we leave out non-relational variables from the regression. We built a discrete age gap variable Age_{Gap} that can take the same values as in Zinn *et al.* (2012). We also add an education gap variable Edu_{Gap} only here it is polytomous as it is computed on three possible education levels (incomplete secondary, complete secondary and complete tertiary education). As in Zinn *et al.* (2012), we add a polytomous variables on whether couple members work CW . Finally, we put a continuous income revenue (ITL) gap variable between both partners as an explanatory variable. It is expressed as a percentage of the period's RIPTE, a wage indicator that is studied in section 1.3.2. Table O.5 below lists these estimated coefficients.

Table O.5: Couple members characteristics impact on the probability of forming a couple, ages 18 to 90

Dependent variables	Men		Women	
	Quarterly (1)	Yearly (2)	Quarterly (3)	Yearly (4)
Intercept	1.5850 (0.1268) ***	1.6645 (0.1055) ***	1.6221 (0.1359) ***	1.4717 (0.1080) ***
$\frac{ITL-ITL_{Part}}{RIPTE}$		0.1558 (0.0690) **	-0.2296 (0.1285) *	
Both work	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference
Only partner works	-0.1799 (0.2012)	-0.3497 (0.2139)	-0.4886 (0.1367) ***	-0.0982 (0.1058)
In work and partner not in work	-0.5279 (0.1165) ***	-0.8092 (0.0976) ***	-0.7409 (0.2581) ***	-0.5888 (0.2069) ***
None work	-0.2832 (0.1641) *	-0.5394 (0.1399) ***	-0.2271 (0.1867)	-0.1074 (0.1665)
$Age - Age_{Part} \geq 10$	-1.7427 (0.1290) ***	-1.6328 (0.1112) ***	-2.2109 (0.1628) ***	-2.4635 (0.1604) ***
$Age - Age_{Part} \in [7; 9]$	-0.3506 (0.1908) **	-0.7353 (0.1492) ***	-1.5687 (0.2659) ***	-1.3765 (0.2567) ***
$Age - Age_{Part} \in [4; 6]$	-0.3829 (0.1613) **	-0.1049 (0.1281)	-1.0445 (0.2242) ***	-1.4090 (0.1823) ***
$Age - Age_{Part} \in [-3; 3]$	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference

Source: Author's calculation on EPHc (2003-2015) data. * Significant at 10% ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Standard errors are in parentheses.

Dependent variables	Men				Women			
	Quarterly (1)		Yearly (2)		Quarterly (3)		Yearly (4)	
$Age - Age_{Part} \in [-6; -4]$	-1.5761 ***	(0.2143)	-1.2035 ***	(0.1745)	-0.1724 ***	(0.1800)	-0.6469 ***	(0.1398)
$Age - Age_{Part} \in [-9; -7]$	-0.9418 ***	(0.2895)	-1.3122 ***	(0.2340)	-0.6019 ***	(0.2136)	-0.9373 ***	(0.1867)
$Age - Age_{Part} \leq -10$	-2.4186 ***	(0.1719)	-2.7101 ***	(0.1755)	-2.2109 ***	(0.1628)	-2.5513 ***	(0.1531)
Two levels of education below partner	-2.1229 ***	(0.4097)	-1.5843 ***	(0.2773)	-0.9226 *	(0.5267)	-0.0463 ***	(0.3332)
One level of education below partner	-0.7007 ***	(0.1267)	-0.7212 ***	(0.1070)	-1.2213 ***	(0.1552)	-0.5752 ***	(0.1340)
Same education level	Reference		Reference		Reference		Reference	
One level of education above partner	-0.7662 ***	(0.1341)	-0.8008 ***	(0.1077)	-0.7146 ***	(0.1346)	-0.7943 ***	(0.1132)
Two levels of education above partner	-1.9011 ***	(0.4265)	-1.8065 ***	(0.2670)	-1.7279 ***	(0.3026)	-2.0571 ***	(0.2795)
Observations (training dataset)	2177		3119		1778		2469	
AUC (training dataset)	0.7525		0.7628		0.7744		0.7764	
AUC (validation dataset)	0.759		0.7792		0.7551		0.7635	

Source: Author's calculation on EPHc (2003-2015) data. * Significant at 10% ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%. Standard errors are in parentheses.

We are not going to analyse here the results of this matching equation, as this is done in section 2.4.3. We can nevertheless see these matching equations make a decent job at identifying relational variables behind couple formation, as they boast AUCs around 0.75 and keep a significant explanatory power when we move to the validation dataset. We also stress the point these matching equations are evidence of homogamy in Argentina, that is, the formation of couples between people of similar characteristics. We decided to input equation (1) estimated at a quarterly interval on men in our dynamic microsimulation model on the grounds it is the least overfitted to the training dataset, as shown by the minimal differences in its C-statistics.

Once this matching equation has been computed, our model performs the matching between couple members as follows. The goal is to assign a partner to all men and women aged 18 to 90 that were scheduled to enter a common-law union following the aforementioned alignment by sorting procedure. We largely follow the demonstration code provided with the LIAM2 software to simulate new unions, although we use the optional "by value" matching algorithm, which allows for faster computation times than the default "one by

one" matching algorithm. We first rank the selected women by absolute distance to the average age of all candidate men, so that the women the closest to this average are selected first. We then lump women together by distance to the average age of the candidate men. After that, we take the group closest to the average and lump together candidate men by their score relative to this female group as derived from equation 0.5. We then match this female group with the male group with the highest propensity score to get in an union with the female candidates. Finally, we remove selected men and women and move on to the second female group that is a step further from the mean age of candidate men. This process is repeated until we run out of candidate men or women, after which unselected individuals do not move into a common-law union.

Appendix P

Education reforms in Argentina and their impact on our simulation of students

Argentina witnessed two educative reforms (1993 and 2006) that changed the organisation and educational content of secondary education, as well as the length of compulsory education. The first part of this Appendix will be a quick review of the content of these reforms. Then, we explain why these reforms make it difficult to identify the year of schooling of secondary students in the EPHc and show how we overcame this difficulty for the waves of the EPHc we use in our prospective simulations (2014-2017).

P.1 The reform and counter-reform of Education (1993-2006)

We will provide in this section an overview of the recent reforms of Argentina's secondary education system and the consequences it entailed for our microsimulation model. The Federal Education Law 24195, published the 5th of May 1993, was the first major change in the content and organisation of secondary education since its implementation by the Common Education Law 1420 of 1884 (Arias, 2005). The latter established that the Argentinian State had to provide free (Art. 2), secular (Art. 8) and compulsory education for all children aged 6 to 14 (Art. 1 and 2). On the brink of the 1993 reform, this was enforced through 7 years of compulsory Primary Education (including one year of preschool), the EGB (General Basic Education), and 5 years of optional secondary education.

The 1993 reform extended by two years the duration of compulsory education, by making the EGB encompass nine years. It also replaced the last three years of secondary education by an optional, specialised poly-modal ("polimodal") cycle (Art. 10). The main objective of this reform was increasing attendance to secondary school by pushing back compulsory schooling up to age 15, but also encouraging the completion of secondary education. This objective was largely achieved: between 1995 and 2002, attendance of children aged 12 to 14 increased from 93% to 98%, while the one of children aged 15 to 17 jumped from 72% to 88% (Judengloben *et al.* , 2003, p. 12). Another aspect of the reform was that it decentralised education and transferred to the Provinces the "administration, programming and financing of education" (Arias, 2005, p. 3). This reform however was resisted and never fully adopted by some Provinces (such as the City of Buenos Aires). It was also widely criticised by teachers and members of the educative community on the grounds it reduced funds available for education (Dip. Zamora, n.d., p. 6763), deteriorated the educative content of secondary school (Arias, 2005) and did not prepare well enough students to enter the labour market or undergo tertiary education (Musse, 2011)¹.

As a consequence, the National Education Law 26206, published the 28th of December 2006, revoked the 1993 Law and put an end to poly-modal education. It allowed the Provinces to choose whether they preferred to adopt the old seven years of basic education / five years of secondary education split or if they would rather adopt a new system made of six years of basic education and six years of secondary education. The Provinces gradually opted for one or the other of the systems from 2007 until 2012, as shown by Table P.1 below. There are however barely any differences in educational content between these two systems. The reform also established that education is compulsory until the completion of secondary education (Art.16), so until ages 17 to 18.

Table P.1: Educational structure of each of Argentina's jurisdictions

	Adopted Split	Ruling	Year
City of Buenos Aires (1)	7 Primary / 5 Secondary	None	
Source: Ministry of Education's website. Accessed 27/11/2017 at the URL http://portales.educacion.gov.ar/vnt/acerca-de-la-estructura-educativa/			

¹This criticism of the reform was shown by the fact the end of the poly-modal system in the Province of Buenos Aires was cheered both by the Provincial Minister of Education Gvirtz and the teacher unionist Baradell (Musse, 2011)

	Adopted Split	Ruling	Year
Chaco	7 Primary / 5 Secondary	Law N°6748	2010
Jujuy	7 Primary / 5 Secondary	Decreto Acuerdo N° 8509	2007
La Rioja	7 Primary / 5 Secondary	Education Law N°8678	2009
Mendoza (2)	7 Primary / 5 Secondary	None	
Misiones	7 Primary / 5 Secondary	Resolution N°289	2007
Neuquén (2)	7 Primary / 5 Secondary	None	
Río Negro	7 Primary / 5 Secondary	Education Law N°2444	1991
Salta	7 Primary / 5 Secondary	Education Law N°7546	2008
Santa Cruz	7 Primary / 5 Secondary	Acuerdo N°164	2012
Santa Fe	7 Primary / 5 Secondary	Decree N°2885	2007
Santiago del Estero	7 Primary / 5 Secondary	Education Law N°6976	2007
Buenos Aires	6 Primary / 6 Secondary	Education Law N°13688	2007
Catamarca	6 Primary / 6 Secondary	None	
Córdoba	6 Primary / 6 Secondary	Education Law N°9870	2010
Corrientes	6 Primary / 6 Secondary	Decree N° 222	2008
Chubut	6 Primary / 6 Secondary	Education Law N°91	2010
Entre Ríos	6 Primary / 6 Secondary	Education Law N° 9890	2008
Formosa	6 Primary / 6 Secondary	Resolution N°5476	2007
La Pampa	6 Primary / 6 Secondary	Education Law N° 2511	2009
San Juan	6 Primary / 6 Secondary	Resolution N°5641	2007
San Luis	6 Primary / 6 Secondary	Decree N°154	2008
Tierra del Fuego	6 Primary / 6 Secondary	Resolution N°2848	2007
Tucumán	6 Primary / 6 Secondary	Education Law N°8391	2010
(1) Since this jurisdiction did not enforce the Federal Education Law 24195, it kept the previous structure established by the Common Education Law 1420			
(2) These are the proposed education structures in forthcoming Education Law projects.			
Source: Ministry of Education's website. Accessed 27/11/2017 at the URL http://portales.educacion.gov.ar/vnt/acerca-de-la-estructura-educativa/			

The succession of these two reforms, unevenly applied throughout the country, make

reading the education year of students in the EPHc tricky, as we will explain below.

P.2 Consequences of the reforms on the legibility of the EPHc.

The incomplete adoption of the 1993 reform and the unequal implementation of the 2006 National Education Law have consequences in the legibility of the EPHc. In order to know the year of studies of a student in the EPHc, we need to take into account its city of residence and the time of survey to know to which education structure the respondent is referring to. Fortunately, the periods we input in our prospective microsimulation model (2014-2017) come after the elimination of the poly-modal system and the choice of the 6 / 6 or 7 / 5 split by the Provinces (Table P.1). This is shown by the fact since 2014 less than 6% of secondary students report being in a poly-modal level of education. We can thus assume self-reported secondary students refer to one of these two secondary education frameworks depending on their Province of residence.

There are however still cases where we cannot directly assign a student to a school year. Some students tell what their current level of study is (primary or secondary) but do not tell what is their current year of education. Others live in cities that border two Provinces with different nominal secondary education systems. This is the case of the urban centre of Viedma (Río Negro) / Carmen de Patagones (Buenos Aires) and San Nicolás (Buenos Aires) / Villa Constitución (Santa Fe). As a consequence, we cannot know the current year of education of these respondents. Together, these two groups represent 5% of secondary students aged 15 or more (2014-2015), so the problem is minimal. For these students, we arbitrarily decided those aged 15, 16, and 17 or more were respectively in their 10th, 11th and 12th (and last) year of education, which are the last three years of secondary education. The full code for the identification of students since 2014 is available on-line².

²We use the Zenodo archiving service for long-term preservation of our code. The DOI link is: [10.5281/zenodo.1420273](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1420273)

Appendix Q

The graduation rates of university students derived from our model's hypotheses

Following the hypotheses described in section 2.5.4 and the abandonment rates by gender i dr_i listed in Table 2.7, if we ignore the probability of dying, we can compute the probability a student of gender i who just enters college has of graduating gr_i :

$$\begin{aligned}(1 - gr_i) &= (1 - gr_{i,4}) \times (1 - gr_{i,5}) \times (1 - gr_{i,6}) \\ &= (1 - 0.5 \times (1 - dr_i)^4) \times (1 - 0.5^2 \times (1 - dr_i)^5) \times (1 - 0.5^2 \times (1 - dr_i)^6)\end{aligned}$$

Here, $gr_{i,j}$, $j \in [4;6]$ represents the probability of graduating exactly in the j^{th} year of studies. We get from there the probability male students have of graduating gr_m :

$$\begin{aligned}(1 - gr_m) &\approx (1 - 0.2397) \times (1 - 0.0997) \times (1 - 0.0830) \\ &\approx 0.6277 \\ gr_m &\approx 0.3723\end{aligned}$$

We also get gr_f , the probability female students have of graduating:

$$\begin{aligned}(1 - gr_f) &\approx (1 - 0.2562) \times (1 - 0.1084) \times (1 - 0.0917) \\ &\approx 0.6024 \\ gr_f &\approx 0.3976\end{aligned}$$

We therefore get at least 37% of male and 40% of female first year students that end up graduating from university as per our alignment by sorting procedure. The actual figure can be higher, since we only take enough students to transit out of higher education to reproduce the proportions of students by age listed in Table 2.5. These probabilities however show our model allows for high abandonment rates in university education. It is possible to respect the yearly probabilities of dropping out of university derived from Mirás (2013) data while aiming for a higher or lower abandonment rate by changing the graduation hypotheses. It may in particular be interesting to modify the proportion of fourth or fifth year students that graduate, which we arbitrarily set at 50%. This is however left for future work.

Chapter 3

Social security projections and reform evaluation: horizons to 2040

The object of this third and final Chapter is to make projections of Argentina’s social security sustainability, adequacy and redistributive impact up to 2040. In Chapter 1, we made a social security legislation review, including the latest 2016 and 2017 reforms, that covers all the relevant computation rules for both social security benefits and contributions. We also reviewed aggregate historical data for the labour-market calibration of our model and introduced the base dataset of our microsimulation procedure, Argentina’s household survey EPHc (2003-2015). In Chapter 2, we have shown how we built a dynamic microsimulation capable of simulating all the elements necessary for computing social security benefits and contributions for Argentina. We simulate past and future careers, marital status, family links and education levels of EPHc respondents. We have also shown these simulations are consistent with observed individual behaviour as well as with aggregate values, both historical and projected (with central, optimistic and pessimistic economic scenarios). In this final Chapter 3, we combine these two chapters to compute, in our simulated population up to 2040¹, social security benefits and contributions following various economic scenarios. This lets us project in the long term the sustainability of Argentina’s retirement and family benefits system’s accounts run by the National Social Security Administration (ANSES). This is the first time such a projection has ever been made to study Argentina’s social security system, and the second time a dynamic microsimulation model is used to simulate the social security system of a Latin American country after Brazil’s BRALAMMO model (Zylberstajn *et al.* , 2011). In addition to this aggregate analysis, we propose a micro-level projection of social security benefits long-

¹As we have explained in section 2.2.3, we use INDEC’s population projections for the 2010-2040 period to calibrate our model’s birth and death probabilities by age. These are laid out in Appendix K. We thus stop our simulations in 2040.

term adequacy and redistributive impact. Finally, we introduce counter-factual legislative scenarios that show what would have been the evolution of social security's economic sustainability, adequacy and redistributive impact had the two major social security reforms implemented by the incumbent administration never been adopted. This allows for a rigorous *ex ante* impact evaluation of the influence of the 2016 historical reparation Law 27260 and the late 2017 pension reforms (Laws 27426, 27430 and 27432) on ANSES benefits sustainability, adequacy and redistributive impact.

This third Chapter is divided in two broad sections. First, in section 3.1 we collect detailed quarterly administrative data on ANSES income and expenses for the last years (2014-2017). We then measure the retirement benefits and compute both the social security contributions and family benefits of EPHc respondents surveyed during years 2014 and 2015. After that, we compare these aggregate values with the known administrative data for these same years. We can thus establish an equivalence key between aggregate social security expenses and income as measured with a cohort of the EPHc and actual values. After that, we review our economic and demographic scenarios, simulate the evolution of total workers and real wages and deduce from them future GDP by economic scenario through a simplified long-term growth model. Finally, we simulate social security contributions and expenses for people surveyed the fourth quarter of 2014 up to 2040 and apply this equivalence key to get total ANSES social security income and expenses by economic scenario with 2018 legislation. This way we can express ANSES "Bismarckian" economic result (social security contributions minus retirement pensions and family benefits) as a percentage of GDP. We do this same procedure with other periods (second quarters of 2014 and 2015) to ensure our results are not dependent on the choice of a specific EPHc wave.

The second section 3.2 studies ANSES economic result, as well as the adequacy and redistributive impact of its benefits, with varying economic and legislative scenarios. First, we finish the legislative calibration of our microsimulation model. We introduce non-simulated ANSES expenses and revenue, which lets us deduce the agency's economic result from its "Bismarckian" balance, and define our counter-factual legislative scenarios. Second, we compute ANSES economic result across economic and legislative scenarios. This is not only the first long-term projection of Argentina's social security system accounts, we can also evaluate the impact of the 2016 and 2017 reforms on its future economic sustainability. This is the main contribution of our thesis, as it represents a valuable tool for carrying further pension reforms as is *de jure* due by 2019 following the historical reparation Law 27260. Third, we project ANSES benefits redistributive impact

and show the effects of the 2016 and 2017 reforms on income inequality. Finally, we evaluate the impact of the reforms adopted by the current administration on the future adequacy of social security transfers, considering both their level and coverage.

3.1 Aggregate social security contributions and expenses and extrapolation to the national level (2014-2040)

One of the main objectives of this third chapter is to determine ANSES economic sustainability, which is done by projecting its future economic result (the difference between current income and expenses). What we basically want to do is prolong section's 1.1.1 Figure 1.1 up to 2040, with varying legislation and economic scenarios. The data we use is taken from the yearly Investment Account, computed by the Nation's General Account agency (CGN), and reproduces (with some modifications) the Savings Investment Funding Account (AIF, *Cuenta Ahorro Inversión Financiamiento*) current expenses and income. As we will show in section 3.1.3, our model simulates the most important items of ANSES economic result. First, we simulate Social Security Benefits (retirement benefits + survivor's pensions net of PAMI healthcare contributions (see Box 3 below), excluding the universal pension). These represented during the 2009-2017 period 69% of total ANSES payments, including current and figurative expenses (excluding those explicitly funded by the federal budget) as well as the payment of court rulings². Second, we also simulate Current Transfers paid by ANSES (mostly family benefits and pensioners' PAMI contributions), which in turn represent 15% of total ANSES expenses. Third, on the income side, we simulate Social Security Contributions, which represented on average 54% of ANSES income between years 2009 and 2017, including figurative contributions corresponding to the fiscal pacts between the federal government and the Provinces instituted by Laws 24130 and 27260 (which equal 15% of *coparticipable* taxes) but excluding the extraordinary fiscal amnesty revenue of 2016. Therefore, we only need to make assumptions on 16% of ANSES expenses (2% operation costs, 12% figurative expenses to fund non-contributive pensions and police and military personnel pension schemes, 2% for paying court rulings). On the revenues side, we need to make assumptions on a more substantial 46% of total ANSES income. Of these, 23% are taxes granted to ANSES, 15% are *coparticipable* revenues transferred following the Law 24130 and 27260 fiscal pacts

² All the figures of this paragraph are computed using the following sources: CGN's Investment Account (2009-2016) and data from the Federal Taxes Commission (2009-2017). For year 2017, we use the Savings-Investment-Funding Account (AIF) of the public sector and the physical-financial monitoring of the fourth quarter of 2017.

between the federal government and the provinces, and 8% are FGS investments revenue. All these assumptions are done in full in section 3.2.1.

The only major blind spot of our work is that it sets aside the historical reparation program instituted by the 2016 reform (seen in section 1.1.2) as well as the cost of pension litigation in the future. These two elements are highly dependent on the willingness of retired individuals to take their case to court against ANSES and how much time ANSES takes to actually pay them. We lack information on both elements and thus refrain from simulating them *ex ante* in our model. However, subscription to the historical reparation program will be closed in 2018³, and its impact on ANSES accounts is already visible in 2017 as shown in Figure 1.1. As such, the full impact of the reparation program should be apparent on both ANSES accounts and the EPHc by 2018-2019. Re-launching this model with a posterior starting period and comparing the obtained results with those that will be presented in this third Chapter would thus suffice to evaluate *ex post* the impact of the Law 27260 historical reparation program on ANSES economic sustainability, pension adequacy and redistributive impact.

³ANSES Resolution 100/2018, issued the 28th of June 2018, allows subscribing to the historical reparation program until the 31st of August 2018.

Box 3: Healthcare contributions by the elderly to the INSSJP-PAMI

We have introduced in section 1.1.4 the National Institute of Social Services for Retirees and Pensioners, INSSJP (commonly known as PAMI). This body provides healthcare for retirement pensioners, recipients of a survivor's pension and people earning the universal pension for the elderly. We saw in section 1.1.4 that workers make compulsory contributions to the PAMI. Beneficiaries of the PAMI also make their contributions. Following Law 19032^a Art. 8 section a), the contribution is equal to 3% of the benefit up to the minimum pension and 6% of the retirement income exceeding this amount. These payments to the PAMI are automatically deducted from the pension's amount by ANSES and transferred to the INSSJP. As such, they are listed as current transfers in ANSES' Savings-Investment-Funding account. Their exact amount is listed in General Accounts Agency's (CGN) Investment Account Appendix on the composition of Social Security bodies' expenditure by finality-function and economic nature^b, as health transfers. For 2016, these represented 13% of current transfers paid by the ANSES. Beneficiaries of the universal pension for the elderly adult also pay these contributions, as specified in Art. 13 of Law 27260^c. However, the universal pension as well as the contributions to the PAMI it originates are funded by the Federal Budget. None of these elements are therefore taken into account in the computation of ANSES economic result, nor listed under ANSES expenses in the Investment Account.

^aIssued the 28th of May 1971.

^bIn the 2016 edition, this corresponded to Appendix 3.05.

^cIssued the 22d of July 2016

This said, we cannot use directly simulated ANSES income and expenses because they are not representative enough of actual figures even after we take into account individual weights in our starting dataset (variable PONDERA of the EPHc). A first reason is that we disregard in our simulations all the other existing social security schemes. These concern almost exclusively the civil servants of some provinces (including the province of Buenos Aires) but also military and police personnel. Moreover, the EPHc is not fully representative of the Argentinian population, since it does not survey the inhabitants of small urban or rural areas, as we explained in section 1.2.1. Finally, the EPHc does not survey the elderly in nursing homes, so we are missing their pensions when we measure Social Security Benefits (SSB) in the EPHc. We thus want to extrapolate the simulated Social Security Benefits (SSB), Current Transfers (CT) and Social Security Contributions (SSC) so as to put their starting values on par with their known levels for years 2014 and

2015.

The extrapolation is done through a rule of three. If at the starting period a given variable equals x when measured in the EPHc household survey, but we know from administrative data it actually was equal to y during that period, then the constant $k = \frac{y}{x}$ is the conversion key that allows us to extrapolate the simulated variable in later periods. This extrapolation, when done for variables SSB, CT and SSC, will allow for a meaningful computation of ANSES economic result as is done in the AIF Account and was represented in Figure 1.1 of section 1.1.1. Ideally, we would match these aggregate variables directly to official values listed in each year's Investment Account. These are however yearly figures, and we need quarterly matching data in order to correct our aggregate values simulated at the quarterly step. Also, it is tricky to work with nominal pesos at the yearly level knowing the double-digit inflation figures in Argentina during years 2014 and 2015.

Section 3.1.1 is organised as follows. First, we explain how we get the quarterly figures of Social Security Contributions (SSC), Benefits (SSB) and Current Transfers to the private sector (CT) in section 3.1.1. After that, we do not want to match the simulated values of variables SSB, CT and SSC to the quarterly administrative data reviewed in section 3.1.1. That would simply force our microsimulation to have the required aggregate results. We will instead, in section 3.1.2, compute these variables in the latest waves of the EPHc (from the first quarter of 2014 up to the second quarter of 2015) and extrapolate them to match the known values we computed in section 3.1.1. This match will result in a "conversion key" that will put the starting aggregate values of the SSB, SSC and CT variables on par with their known values for years 2014 and 2015. After that, in section 3.1.3 we will complete the economic scenarios we started studying in section 2.3.4, compute future GDP growth and review the expected evolution of Argentina's population derived from the demographic calibration of our model, laid out in particular in Appendix K. Finally, section 3.1.4 simulates ANSES "Bismarckian" balance (the difference between social security revenue and the sum of retirement and family benefits) by economic scenario as a percentage of the future simulated GDP. The full computation of ANSES economic result with all ANSES income and varying economic and legislative scenarios will be undertaken in section 3.2.

3.1.1 External calibration data: quarterly social security contributions and benefits (2014-2017)

First of all, we present the known quarterly values for Social Security Benefits (SSB), Contributions (SSC) and Current Transfers to the private sector (CT) from the first quarter of 2014 to the fourth quarter of 2017. Since we make our microsimulations with people surveyed the fourth quarter of 2014, and repeat them with surveys carried out the second quarters of 2014 and 2015, we will compute the conversion keys only between the first quarter of 2014 and the second quarter of 2015, as we will show in section 3.1.3. We do not take into account EPHc waves published since 2016 because surveyed workers (excluding family workers, who are typically not paid) have a high non-response rate for the labour income variable⁴. The aggregate value of the respondents' total social security contributions or family benefits is thus not comparable to those we compute for earlier waves of the EPHc. We nevertheless present our external calibration data up to the fourth quarter of 2017, as a way to compare our simulations with values measured between years 2014 and 2017.

Social security contributions assigned to the ANSES (2014-2017)

First, we want to collect quarterly data on social security contributions assigned to ANSES. This information is compiled in AFIP's monthly (and yearly, since 2017) social security bulletins, available in the agency's official website⁵. Although not explicit in the dataset, each month's social security contributions allocated to ANSES were computed on the previous month's labour income. This is evidenced by the spikes in contributions that occur on July and January each year, which correspond to the two-times payment of the thirteenth month on June and December. This is a problem for matching our simulated contributions to actual figures. Indeed, in our simulations labour income and contributions are computed during the same period. Thus, in our simulations contributions originating from the thirteenth month happen each second and fourth quarter, while in reality ANSES receives these payments respectively the third and first quarters. For the sake of computing the conversion key for our microsimulation of total contributions, we assigned payments to ANSES to the quarter where the labour income of these contri-

⁴Between the second quarter of 2016 and the first quarter of 2017, 25% of working respondents that were not family workers had a null or missing labour income. This figure was equal to 2.7% for the previous version of the EPHc, between the third quarter of 2003 and the second quarter of 2015.

⁵As of 9 April 2018, monthly social security bulletins were available at <http://www.afip.gob.ar/institucional/estudios/default.asp#bolSegSocAn>, in the fiscal statistics section of AFIP's website. We retrieve data from these bulletins' Table 8.

butions was earned. For instance, the sum of contributions given to ANSES on February, March and April 2014 are considered as social security contributions allocated to ANSES for the first quarter of 2014, because they were computed on labour income earned respectively on January, February and March 2014. Table 3.1 below lists our computation of quarterly social security contributions assigned to ANSES in constant November 2014 pesos.

Table 3.1: Quarterly contributions assigned to ANSES, millions of constant November 2014 pesos

	Quarter			
	1	2	3	4
2014	59,323.985	70,642.775	66,453.030	75,212.989
2015	71,061.517	85,808.756	76,520.057	81,658.874
2016	71,384.639	78,650.764	72,210.474	79,983.678
2017	74,434.596	80,479.757	73,976.782	82,408.988

Source: Author’s calculation based on February 2014 to January 2018 monthly social security bulletins, AFIP. Current values are discounted following official national CPI indexes. For periods where no official inflation figures are available, we use the average of inflation figures as computed in the province of San Luis and the City of Buenos Aires.

It should moreover be noted that the sum of all contributions assigned to ANSES in a given year as measured in AFIP’s monthly social security bulletins are almost equal to Social Security Contributions (SSC) allocated to ANSES as determined by Appendix 3.14. of the Nation’s General Accounting office (CGN) Investment Account. For instance, total contributions for year 2016 as per AFIP’s data were equal to 452.560 billion pesos, while contributions to social security received by ANSES according to the 2016 Investment Account’s Appendix 3.14. were equal to 449.978 billion pesos. AFIP’s figures are thus a good approximation of official ANSES income as set in the CGN’s Investment Account. It is thus correct to match our aggregate simulated contributions to quarterly AFIP’s figures.

Why use physical-financial monitoring data to calibrate ANSES expenditure?

Next, we want to match simulated ANSES expenses to known quarterly figures. In the AIF Account used for computing ANSES economic result⁶, almost all current ANSES

⁶ The Savings-Investment-Funding (AIF) Account for ANSES is issued yearly in the Investment Account made by the General Accounts Agency (CGN). In the 2016 edition of the Investment Account, the AIF account for ANSES is available in Appendix 23.

expenses are divided between Social Security Benefits (SSB) and Current Transfers (CT). These respectively represent 77% and 21% of 2016 current ANSES expenses. The remaining 2% are Consumption Expenses, which combine ANSES personnel remuneration and various operating costs. Instead of matching our simulated ANSES expenses to the AIF values of the SSB and CT, we reconstitute the latter using a more detailed quarterly dataset called the "physical-financial monitoring" of social security institutions expenses. This dataset is available at the yearly level in CGN's Investment Account⁷. We are however interested in the compilation of quarterly releases that track the execution of social security institutions' budget by program⁸. This quarterly dataset gives ANSES current expenses by program, but also the number of its beneficiaries. It is thus the best source for calibrating our quarterly simulation of ANSES expenses with an external dataset.

Although not directly apparent, expenses as measured in ANSES AIF Account can be deduced from expenses by program in the physical-financial monitoring of ANSES accounts. First, SSB in the AIF are the sum of retirement benefits, survivor's pensions and pensions paid to Malvinas war veterans in the physical-financial monitoring. Indeed, according respectively to the 2016 Investment Account's Appendixes II.3 and 3.14. the sum of these three elements equals 603.972 billion pesos, while the SSB in Argentina's Savings-Investment-Funding (AIF) Account amounted to 603.990 billion pesos. War veterans pensions are not simulated by our model. They are nevertheless funded by the Federal budget (as per Art. 4 of Law 23848⁹), so they must not enter in the computation of ANSES economic result. As such, it is thus correct to match our aggregate simulated Social Security Benefits to direct and indirect retirement pensions as measured in the quarterly physical-financial monitoring of ANSES accounts.

On the other hand, the link between Current Transfers in ANSES' AIF account and expenses by program in the quarterly physical-financial monitoring of ANSES accounts is convoluted. This is because ANSES Current Transfers are not limited to ANSES benefits, covered by this latter dataset. According to the 2016 Investment Account, the sum of family benefits, unemployment pensions, complements to retirement pensions, the PROGRESAR benefit for students aged 18 to 25 (all listed in the physical-financial monitoring of ANSES accounts in Appendix II.3), transfers to the public and external sectors (Appendix 3.05) and health transfers (Appendix 3.06) equal ANSES' AIF Account Cur-

⁷In the 2016 edition of the Investment Account, the physical-financial monitoring of social security institutions is included in Appendix II.3.

⁸The releases are available in the National Budget Office's official website, in the budget evaluation section. As of 10 April 2018, data for years 2005 to 2017 is available in the following link: <https://www.minhacienda.gob.ar/onp/evaluacion/2016>

⁹Issued the 19th of October 1990.

rent Transfers (Appendix 23), or 167.994 billion pesos. Health transfers are compulsory contributions to the PAMI by ANSES pensions beneficiaries (see Box 3), which we can compute from retirement benefits paid by ANSES. Almost all family benefits (excluding disabled child benefits) are computed by our model and deduced from EPHc respondents characteristics, as will be seen below. We neither compute nor simulate the PROGRESAR benefit but this is irrelevant for determining ANSES economic result because this program is funded by the Federal Budget. Similarly, following Decree 1668/2012¹⁰, family benefits earned by workers of the national public sector are paid by ANSES since January 2013 (Art. 6 & 9) but are funded by the federal budget (Art. 7). These family benefits are computed separately in the physical-financial monitoring of ANSES accounts since 2014 but enter in the computation of ANSES CT. As such, we take them out of the calibration of simulated current transfers. Finally, we do not simulate unemployment benefits or complements to retirement pensions. However, these represented in years 2014 and 2015 respectively 2% and 3% of ANSES Current Transfers to the private sector (excluding PROGRESAR benefits) and are thus negligible. We will hence include them in the computation of the conversion key for our rule of three extrapolation, for the sake of getting a more coherent aggregate simulated value for Current Transfers. This will be shown in section 3.1.2.

The main problem we have is Current Transfers to the public and external sectors by ANSES. The reason why these transfers are made is unclear, and in particular we do not know why there is a spike in transfers to the public sector in 2016 (going from 2% to 13% of ANSES current transfers from years 2015 to 2016, before going down to 6% of ANSES CT in 2017). We suspect it has to do with the fiscal pact between the federal and provincial governments ratified by Appendix I of Law 27260, issued 22 July 2016. In this pact, explained in section 1.1.2, the Provinces gradually get back the 15% of *coparticipable* taxes that used to fund ANSES, starting with a retroactive 3% for year 2016. This spike may thus originate from ANSES refunding part of the *coparticipable* income earned before Law 27260 passed and would thus be a one-time event. In any case, transfers to the public and private sectors are neither family benefits nor contributions to the PAMI, so we can disregard them in what regards computing the conversion key of family benefits. Finally, PAMI contributions are a function of retirement benefits, so we apply to them the conversion key of Social Security Benefits.

¹⁰Issued the 12th of September 2012.

Social security benefits paid by the ANSES (2014-2017)

Now that we have presented the ANSES quarterly physical-financial monitoring dataset, we present in Tables 3.2 and 3.3 below the quarterly values of ANSES expenses by program in constant November 2014 pesos.

Table 3.2: Quarterly social security benefits paid by ANSES (2014-2017)

	Benefits, millions of November 2014 pesos				
	PAYG pensions	Moratorium benefits	Former Provincial schemes	ANSES retirement benefits, total	Malvinas war veterans
2014, Q1	41,287.350	23,163.534	3,613.782	68,064.666	567.444
2014, Q2	48,748.924	27,362.424	4,359.480	80,470.828	667.782
2014, Q3	42,898.118	24,223.177	3,903.714	71,025.009	581.875
2014, Q4	55,429.295	31,001.134	4,407.721	90,838.151	729.490
2015, Q1	48,528.942	29,587.372	3,780.729	81,897.044	639.502
2015, Q2	60,425.827	39,306.358	4,791.179	104,523.364	833.843
2015, Q3	54,318.950	35,733.788	4,474.639	94,527.377	759.516
2015, Q4	62,638.625	44,100.147	5,136.391	111,875.163	925.167
2016, Q1	52,114.080	35,198.226	4,102.250	91,414.555	748.120
2016, Q2	58,761.524	40,826.381	4,528.738	104,116.643	837.856
2016, Q3	51,325.898	35,182.621	4,256.167	90,764.686	732.892
2016, Q4	63,670.457	43,663.385	4,749.981	112,083.823	883.274
2017, Q1	57,536.879	37,727.218	3,809.238	99,073.335	758.341
2017, Q2	69,084.251	44,726.953	4,500.344	118,311.548	899.281
2017, Q3	60,647.579	38,553.337	4,053.662	103,254.578	774.260
2017, Q4	73,645.310	46,215.067	4,868.049	124,728.426	974.051
Source: Author's calculation based on the first quarter of 2014 to the fourth quarter of 2017 physical-financial monitoring of ANSES accounts by the National Budget Office. Current values are discounted following official national CPI indexes. For periods where no official inflation figures are available, we use the average of inflation figures as computed in the province of San Luis and the City of Buenos Aires.					
Pay-As-You-Go pensions excluding former provincial schemes include an unknown amount of pension increases linked to the historical reparation program since the third quarter of 2016. These are not simulated by our model, were estimated in Appendix A and are not taken into account in our study of ANSES economic sustainability, as will be explained in section 3.2.1. Nevertheless, since only benefits given between the first quarter of 2014 and the second quarter of 2015 are used to compute the conversion keys for extrapolating retirement and survivor's pensions, we do not bother in separating historical reparation payments from PAYG pension benefits in this table.					

Table 3.2 includes the detailed quarterly expenses in Social Security Benefits paid by ANSES since the first quarter of 2014. We calibrate our aggregate simulation of pensions with the column representing the sum of ANSES retirement benefits. This calibration will only be done from the first quarter of 2014 to the second quarter of 2015, to match the EPHc waves that will provide the starting datasets for our simulation of retirement

benefits. We nevertheless list the quarterly values of these expenses up to 2017 to verify the early accuracy of our ANSES sustainability projections.

Transfers to the private sector (family benefits) paid by the ANSES (2014-2017)

Finally, we present quarterly Current Transfers to the private sector made by ANSES. These are presented in Table 3.3 below.

Table 3.3: Quarterly current transfers to the private sector paid by ANSES (2014-2017)

	Transfers, millions of November 2014 pesos				
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
2014 Q1	10,739.081	279.667	2,463.941	13,482.689	13,733.233
2014 Q2	12,776.103	314.025	2,913.044	16,003.172	16,270.046
2014 Q3	12,974.241	329.242	2,571.105	15,874.588	17,670.964
2014 Q4	12,320.022	393.664	3,288.341	16,002.027	17,161.491
2015 Q1	13,755.547	231.139	2,964.673	16,951.359	18,231.627
2015 Q2	14,117.800	222.029	3,783.746	18,123.575	19,687.952
2015 Q3	16,309.018	386.311	3,421.891	20,117.220	22,190.061
2015 Q4	14,897.345	1,439.656	4,049.881	20,386.882	22,729.748
2016 Q1	17,296.900	230.546	3,309.207	20,836.653	22,762.488
2016 Q2	17,416.310	1,397.281	3,769.022	22,582.613	24,440.890
2016 Q3	16,383.677	605.685	3,285.682	20,275.044	22,167.728
2016 Q4	18,836.259	2,576.097	4,057.434	25,469.790	27,652.288
2017 Q1	20,203.712	574.211	3,586.455	24,364.378	25,889.655
2017 Q2	17,930.416	604.937	4,282.878	22,818.231	24,020.928
2017 Q3	17,872.915	643.861	3,737.816	22,254.592	24,278.814
2017 Q4	18,125.645	621.836	4,515.169	23,262.650	24,785.174

Source: see Table 3.2. (1): Simulated family benefits funded by ANSES; (2): Non-simulated benefits funded by ANSES; (3): PAMI contributions deducted from pensions; (4): Total transfers to the private sector funded by ANSES (1 + 2 + 3); (5): Current transfers to the private Sector paid by ANSES.

Although column (4) represents the sum of all Current Transfers to the Private Sector funded by ANSES, the conversion key for family benefits will be computed using the sum of columns (1) and (2), who correspond to family benefits funded by ANSES. Column (3), PAMI contributions, is a function of retirement pensions as seen in Box 3: they represent 3% of gross pension income below and 6% above the minimum. We however only have information on PAMI contributions made by the ANSES on behalf of the elderly at the yearly level. As we have seen earlier, these are current transfers to the private sector for health reasons made by ANSES, listed in CGN’s Investment Account. For the 2009-2017 period, these are on average equal to 3.62% (with values ranging between 3.61% and

3.63%) of social security benefits paid by ANSES in a given year, excluding pensions for Malvinas war veterans. We thus assumed contributions to the PAMI in a given quarter were equal to 3.62% of retirement benefits paid in said quarter. This is how we ended up with the quarterly figures of PAMI contributions listed in column (3). Finally, column (5) corresponds to Current Transfers to the Private Sector as listed in the AIF account of ANSES, only they are here presented in a quarterly step. It includes the PROGRESAR benefit and family allowances for the children of national civil servants, both funded by the Federal budget. As such, this column is not used in the external calibration of simulated ANSES expenses.

3.1.2 Extrapolating social security benefits and contributions as computed in the EPHc (2014-2015)

In section 3.1.1, we have listed aggregate quarterly ANSES Social Security Benefits (SSB), Current Transfers (CT) and Social Security Contributions (SSC). We want to establish an equivalence relationship between these known quarterly aggregate figures and their projected values. To do so, we will first deduce variables SSB, CT and SSC from the latest EPHc waves (2014-2015) in a way that is consistent with how we simulate these variables in our projections. As we have explained before, we refrain from using EPHc waves from 2016 and beyond due to the abnormally high number of missing values for the labour income variable of non-family workers. We will then extrapolate them to their known values listed in section 3.1.1.

Computing ANSES social security contributions, retirement pensions and family benefits in the EPHc (2014-2015)

We will first of all estimate variables SSB, SSC and CT from the EPHc dataset for years 2014 to 2015 in a way that is consistent with how we simulate these variables in our projections. On the one hand, our microsimulation of SSB takes as a given declared retirement and survivor's pensions listed in the EPHc's variable V2_M. It then discounts declared pensions on known or simulated real pension mobility and simulates future new retirement benefits. As such, variable SSB is simply measured in the EPHc, as will be shown below. We also deduce compulsory contributions by pensioners to the PAMI from their declared pension. On the other hand, Social Security Contributions are not measured in the EPHc. They can however be deduced from declared labour income and situation. We thus compute them using the same rules we apply in our dynamic microsimulation model, listed in section 1.1.4. Finally, the remaining simulated Current Transfers, that is, family

benefits, could be measured by EPHc variable V5_M. We however found family benefits declared in the EPHc are substantially lower than those we simulate in our microsimulation model. This is probably related to EPHc respondents under-declaring their income. First, they are likely not to report earned family benefits in full, which directly decreases variable V5_M. Then, since they do not declare their full labour income, we over-estimate their rights to family allowances (since these are means tested) in our microsimulation model. We thus decided to calculate family benefits in the EPHc following the same rules we applied in our microsimulation model and then use this recomputed value to compute family benefits' conversion key.

Total Social Security Benefits, Contributions and Current Transfers as measured (for SSB and PAMI contributions) or estimated (for SSC and family benefits) in the EPHc are listed in Table 3.4 below. Weights as measured in the EPHc by variable PONDERA are factored in. These result in total ANSES expenses and income that are of the same order of magnitude than the known values for these periods, as listed in tables 3.1 to 3.3¹¹.

Table 3.4: Total EPHc respondents social security contributions and income, millions of November 2014 pesos (2014-2015)

	2014, Q1	2014, Q2	2014, Q3	2014, Q4	2015, Q1	2015, Q2
Social Security Contributions	16,188.957	18,889.075	16,666.087	20,600.306	18,139.908	21,552.53
Retirement benefits	13,367.098	13,911.325	14,531.608	15,148.486	15,853.349	17,180.984
PAMI contributions	552.645	571.465	618.358	597.485	654.53	696.491
Family benefits	2,431.521	2,156.056	2,697.106	2,598.761	3,002.195	2,371.185
Current Transfers	2,984.166	2,727.521	3,315.464	3,196.246	3,656.725	3,067.676
Source: Own computation using the EPHc survey (2014-2015). Values are in millions of November 2014 pesos and are discounted following official national CPI indexes. For periods where no official inflation figures are available, we use the average of inflation figures as computed in the province of San Luis and the City of Buenos Aires.						

In the end, we have in Tables 3.1 to 3.4 all the information necessary to extrapolate simulated ANSES Social Security Contributions, Benefits and Current Transfers, which are the most important determinants of ANSES economic result. We can now carry out

¹¹The full SAS code for estimating the aggregate values of these variables is available on-line. We use the Zenodo archiving service for long-term preservation of our code. The DOI link is: 10.5281/zenodo.1420273

the proper extrapolation in the section below.

Extrapolating aggregate ANSES income and expenses EPHc estimates to their known external values

To extrapolate ANSES Social Security Contributions (SSC), Benefits (SSB) and Current Transfers (CT) to their known values for said periods, we compute for each of these a conversion key. For instance, let us assume respondents of the EPHc in period t paid Social Security Contributions (SSC) equal to EPH_t pesos, while the actual value of SSC as measured by Argentina's Federal Agency for Public Income (AFIP), and listed in Table 3.1 was equal to $AFIP_t$ pesos. We thus get a conversion key $k_{1,t}$ such as $EPH_t \times k_{1,t} = AFIP_t$. We then compute $k_{1,t}$ for multiple periods, average it and get a more accurate conversion key k_1 . We finally multiply simulated social security contributions with this key k_1 to put them up to scale with observed figures. We repeat this process to get the conversion key for retirement (k_2) and family (k_3) benefits. This is done in Table 3.5 below.

Table 3.5: Computing the conversion key for ANSES social security contributions, retirement and survivor's pensions and family benefits (2014-2017)

	Aggregate EPHc value	Known quarterly value	Quarterly conversion key
Social security contributions for ANSES			
2014, Q1	16,189	59,324	3.66
2014, Q2	18,889	70,643	3.74
2014, Q3	16,666	66,453	3.99
2014, Q4	20,600	75,213	3.65
2015, Q1	18,140	71,062	3.92
2015, Q2	21,553	85,809	3.98
Average conversion key: $k_1 = 3.8235866717$			
Retirement benefits and survivor's pensions, net of PAMI contributions			
2014, Q1	13,367	68,065	5.09
2014, Q2	13,911	80,471	5.78
2014, Q3	14,532	71,025	4.89
2014, Q4	15,148	90,838	6.00
2015, Q1	15,853	81,897	5.17
2015, Q2	17,181	10,4523	6.08
Average conversion key: $k_2 = 5.5017049523$			
ANSES funded family benefits			
2014, Q1	2,432	11,019	4.53
2014, Q2	2,156	13,090	6.07

Sources: see Tables 3.1 to 3.4. Values are in millions of November 2014 pesos and are discounted following official national CPI indexes. For periods where no official inflation figures are available, we use the average of inflation figures as computed in the province of San Luis and the City of Buenos Aires.

Table 3.5: Computing the conversion key for ANSES social security contributions, retirement and survivor’s pensions and family benefits (2014-2017)

	Aggregate EPHc value	Known quarterly value	Quarterly conversion key
2014, Q3	2,697	13,303	4.93
2014, Q4	2,599	12,714	4.89
2015, Q1	3,002	13,987	4.66
2015, Q2	2,371	14,340	6.05
Average conversion key: $k_3 = 5.1890047538$			
Sources: see Tables 3.1 to 3.4. Values are in millions of November 2014 pesos and are discounted following official national CPI indexes. For periods where no official inflation figures are available, we use the average of inflation figures as computed in the province of San Luis and the City of Buenos Aires.			

We thus get for each of the three variables of interest (SSC, SSB and CT) a distinct conversion key (k_1 , k_2 and k_3). These keys will be used to extrapolate the simulated values of these variables in our social security projections. This will be done in section 3.1.4. Before that however, we need to finish the economic calibration of our microsimulation model and compute GDP growth by economic scenario. This will be done in section 3.1.3 below.

3.1.3 Demographic, labour market and growth projections for Argentina (2014-2040)

In this section, we present our central, pessimistic and optimistic hypotheses on future real wages, which we assimilate to individual labour productivity evolutions. This completes our economic scenarios, since we had only presented our labour-market participation hypotheses in section 2.3.4 and in Appendix N. We then run our prospective microsimulation model on the 2014-2040 period with the current 2018 legislation and varying economic scenarios. These simulations give us the evolution of Argentina’s working population by scenario, as a result of our labour-market participation (Appendix N) and demographic (Appendix K) hypotheses. Together with the projected evolution of real labour income, it becomes possible to compute future GDP growth by economic scenario using a growth model inspired by France’s Treasury Office for French retirement projections (DGT, 2016). Finally, we extract from the aforementioned simulations the projected evolution of Argentina’s population by age group and gender. This lets us make a quick review of the effects of INDEC’s population projections when applied to our starting dataset of the fourth quarter of 2014. We can in particular measure the evolution of young and old-age dependency ratios, which are some of the key determinants of the future social security

"Bismarckian" balance.

Argentina's economic scenarios, simulations and consequent GDP growth rates

First of all, we complete our economic scenarios for Argentina before computing ANSES income and benefits. We have in section 2.3.4 presented our labour-market scenarios and the methodology behind their computation. In particular, Figure 2.4 depicts the expected evolution of the repartition of men and women aged 16 to 69 between five possible labour-market states (formal employment, independent labour in the formal sector, informal labour, unemployment and inactivity) between the first quarters of 2017 and 2040. The exact calibration values are laid out in Appendix N. As is visible in Figure 2.4, we opted to leave untouched the proportion of independent workers of the formal sector on account of its remarkable historical stability. Other labour-market related variables we kept unchanged across scenarios are the proportions of workers in the Autonomous workers and Small Independent Contributors (*Monotributo*) regimes, but also of students (see Table 2.5). Table 3.6 below summarises the hypothesised labour-market states rates by scenario. These are simply a reminder of the main features of our labour-market scenarios, already depicted in Figure 2.4 and available in detail in Appendix N.

Table 3.6: Labour-market participation of people aged 16 to 69 reached in 2040 by scenario and gender

Labour-market state	Low scenario		Central scenario		High scenario		2019, Q1 value	
	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Women
Formal wage-earners	30.3%	23.7%	37.3%	30.7%	44.3%	37.7%	36.3%	27.7%
Informal workers	31.8%	20.1%	28.3%	17.6%	24.8%	15.1%	28.8%	18.6%
Unemployed	8.3%	6.3%	6.3%	4.8%	4.3%	3.3%	6.8%	4.8%
Inactive	23%	46.4%	21.5%	43.4%	20%	40.4%	21.5%	45.4%
Formal sector independent	6.65%	3.52%	6.65%	3.52%	6.65%	3.52%	6.65%	3.52%
Proportions in the first quarter of 2019 are equal to their average value computed in the EPHc on the 2010-2017Q1 waves. Minor adjustments are undertaken and explained in section 2.3.4								

To complete our labour-market scenario, we give here our real wage hypotheses, which consist in the expected evolution of the Mean Taxable Wage of Stable Workers, or RIPTE. As we have seen in section 2.3.3, the Mincer wage equations in our microsimulation model

have as a dependent variable individual labour income expressed as a percentage of the RIPTE (corrected by a coefficient to reflect gender differences), following the methodology adopted in the French TRAJECTOIRE microsimulation model (Duc *et al.* , 2013). Therefore, by setting the future value of the RIPTE we not only determine the wages of formal wage-earners, we also get the labour income of independent and informal workers. We input nominal RIPTE values up until April 2018 (which we use as the second quarter of 2018 RIPTE), so our scenarios start on the third quarter of 2018 onward. These yearly rates of real formal wages growth were chosen in accordance with the historical evolutions of real formal wages in Argentina, which we compiled in section 1.3 and represented in Figure 1.10. The resulting real wage evolution is depicted in Figure 3.1 below:

Figure 3.1: Quarterly real wage evolution, by scenario (1970-2040)

Sources: for historical values and our chosen inflation indexes for the 2007-2016 period, see Figure 1.10. The base period is the fourth quarter of 2006.

We assume that the RIPTE increases each year by respectively 0%, 0.75% and 1.5% in our low, central and high scenarios. We chose these growth rates based on past real values of the RIPTE. The optimistic scenario prolongs the trend of growing wages between 2003 and 2013 and pushes real wages close to their historical maximum reached during the second Perón presidency (1973-1974). The pessimistic scenario on the other hand assumes

stagnating real wages coherent with the stagnation of real wages since 2013. Finally, the central scenario is set in between these two hypotheses. An important hypothesis we make is that this growth is caused by an equivalent yearly increase in labour productivity in the dependent formal sector. We also assume the GDP share of labour compensation is stable. Both of these are standard hypotheses in the field. For instance, the latest French pension simulations made by the COR assumes that "at the 2070 horizon, the mean labour income [grows] at the same pace than labour productivity, under the hypothesis of a stable division of the GDP between capital and labour since 2023" (COR, 2018, p. 29). This has not historically always been the case in Argentina. As shown by Lindenboim *et al.* (2011), real wages have at times increased far below productivity, such as in the 1990-2002 period. Also, the labour compensation share in Argentina has been all but stable since 1935, as shown by Figure 3.2 below.

Figure 3.2: Share of labour compensation in GDP, (1935-2040)

Labour compensation is here the sum of all wages paid in the public and private sectors, including contributions to social security. Hybrid income (that of own-account workers) is not taken into account. Finally, both the imputed value of usage of the owned residency and Indirectly Measured Revenues of Financial Intermediation Services (SIFMI) are included in the computation of the economy's Gross Added Value (Kidyba & Vega, 2015, p. 9-12) (Sánchez *et al.*, 2016, p. 81). The SAE (1955) series was found in Graña (2007). Finally, values for years 2016 and 2017 are an average of quarterly values taken from the National Institute of Statistics and Census' (INDEC) Income Generation Account (CGI). It can be downloaded in the Institute's website:

https://www.indec.gov.ar/nivel4_default.asp?id_tema_1=3&id_tema_2=9&id_tema_3=49.

The 51% share reached in 2017, unadjusted with mixed labour income earned by own-account workers, is slightly below the average of advanced economies, which equals a stable 55% between years 1993 and 2012 (Cho *et al.*, 2017, p. 16-20). It is also on par with the 50% of selected OECD countries as measured by the ILO and the OECD for the 2015 G20 meeting (ILO & OCDE, 2015, p. 5) or near the share reached in 2010 by South Korea (UNCTAD, 2012, p. 48). From there, it is unclear whether this unadjusted labour compensation share will stagnate at those levels, increase to reach shares of 60% or 65% of GDP close to those of France, the US or the UK (Askenazy & Timbeau, 2003) (UNCTAD, 2012, p. 48), or if this share is a peak and should decline in the long term as Figure 3.2 would suggest. We however assume this division stagnates mostly because

we wanted a simple link between our real wages evolutions and modelled GDP growth. Allowing for a long-term evolution of the share of GDP that compensates labour would make it necessary to include capital productivity evolutions in our growth model. An alternative would be to assume an unstable labour income share in the short run, and then assume this share stabilises, as done by COR (2018). Both these options are however left for future work.

We thus chose to base our output growth for both the short and long term on Equation 3.1 below, used in France’s retirement projections by the COR (DGT, 2016):

$$Y^* = A_L N (1 - NAIRU) H \quad (3.1)$$

where Y^* is potential outcome, A_L labour productivity, N active population, $NAIRU$ the Non-Accelerating Inflation Rate Unemployment and H the average number of worked hours by employed active. Let us call $M = N (1 - NAIRU)$ the total working population, be them in the formal or informal sectors. Let us also assume H is constant. The first difference of equation 3.1 then becomes:

$$y^* = a_L + m \quad (3.2)$$

where y^* is potential GDP growth, a_L labour productivity growth and m working population growth. a_L is by definition in our scenarios equal to real labour income growth. It is not however exactly equal to the growth of formal wages, since our working population is also in formal independent labour or unregistered. Instead, it is equal to the growth of labour income of all workers, which we simulate in our wage module (see section 2.3). This makes variable a_L depend on all the explanatory variables of our Mincer wage equations (listed in Appendix M). Therefore, labour productivity will depend on our exogenous formal wages hypothesis but also on the labour-market state of workers (formal dependent, formal independent or informal), their education level, age and seniority. m is also determined by our labour-market microsimulation and depends on both our demographic hypotheses, which are those of INDEC’s population projection (listed in Appendix K), and our labour-market scenarios, summarised in Table 3.6.

In the end, since we take out capital compensation from our growth model and assume the share of labour compensation in GDP is constant, GDP growth in our model is mostly determined by simulated real wage growth, which is in turn driven by our hypothesized evolution of the RIPTE. Figure 3.3 below shows this by picturing the evolution of GDP together with that of real wages by economic scenario. For instance, our pessimistic scen-

ario assumes stagnating formal real wages and an increase of informality among workers, so real wages decrease. Therefore, this scenario results in a significant long-term recession of Argentina’s economy. Historically though, when real wages in the formal sector strongly increase or decrease in Argentina, a similar evolution of the share of labour compensation in GDP happens as can be seen by comparing Figures 3.1 and 3.2¹². This lessens the impact of these real wage variations in GDP growth, as part of these are absorbed by a change in the division of added value between labour and capital. This phenomenon is however left for future work. The full computation of GDP growth by economic scenario, depending on both real wages and the working population is done in full in Appendix R.

Figure 3.3: Simulated real wages and GDP evolution, 2015-2040 (100=2015, Q1)

Mean real wages are simulated among all workers. GDP figures are computed following Equation 3.2 starting from the first quarter of 2018. For years 2015 to 2017, we consider actual quarterly GDP values.

¹²The real wage of formal workers, RIPTE, is particularly stable in the 1990s during the implementation of the currency board that strongly reduced inflation figures. The fall in the GDP share of labour compensation comes here from the explosion of unemployment and informal labour figures in the mid 1990s following the Tequila crisis, as can be seen in Figure 1.7

Argentina's demographic scenarios: the evolution of the age structure of our starting dataset

Before computing ANSES "Bismarckian" balance by scenario (Social Security Contributions minus Social Security Benefits and Current Transfers to the private sector), we will make a quick review of the expected demographic evolutions of our starting dataset (EPHc fourth quarter of 2014 wave) once it is subjected to INDEC's population projections to the 2040 horizon. Demography plays an essential part when determining the sustainability of a social security system. Indeed, it is people of working age that contribute the most to social security (be it through contributions or taxes assigned to the system), while people not of working age receive most of the payments. Therefore, if in the future the proportion of people of working age diminishes then this will put a strain on social security's accounts. The chosen demographic hypothesis is thus crucial for our model's results.

The full life tables by period adopted in these population projections are available in Appendix K, but they are not very telling in what regards the projected demographic evolution of Argentina. Furthermore, it is important to study the actual demographic composition of our simulated population instead of the one provided by the INDEC in its population projections. This is because the actual demographic structure is dependent on the initial dataset, the fourth quarter of 2014 EPHc survey. Although this survey is weighted so as to reproduce the Argentinian population's structure by age and gender as known through population census, its demographic composition is still bound to differ from the one the INDEC predicted for that period in their population projections. Thus, the actual demographic composition of our simulated population will be different than the one computed by the INDEC in its population forecasts. We thus carry out a quick statistical analysis of the demographic evolution of our micro-simulated population throughout the 2014-2040 period. First, we draw age pyramids at various points of our simulation in Figure 3.4. Then, we compute the dependency ratios for each of our simulated periods to illustrate the strain put on the population of working age (in this case, people aged 16 to 64) by the populations too young (15 or less) or too old (65 or more) to work. These young, old and total dependency ratios are depicted in Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.4: Simulated age pyramids based on the fourth quarter of 2014 EPHc wave

(a) 2014, fourth quarter

(b) 2020, fourth quarter

(c) 2030, fourth quarter

(d) 2040, fourth quarter

Figure 3.5: Simulated young-age and old-age dependency ratios, 2015-2040

These dependency ratios are those resulting from our dynamic microsimulation model, with the fourth quarter of 2014 wave of the EPHc survey as the starting dataset. The young (resp. old)-age dependency ratio is the number of people aged 15 or less (resp. 65 or more) divided by the number of working-age people (16 to 64).

First of all, both the age pyramids and the evolution of the old-age dependency ratio show a significant population ageing throughout the simulated period. The old-age dependency ratio linearly increases from 16% in the fourth quarter of 2014 to 26% in 2040. Put differently, the proportion of people aged 65 or more (and thus eligible to the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult PUAM) grows from 10% in the fourth quarter of 2014 to 17% in 2040. This means by 2040 Argentina’s old-age dependency ratio will be almost equal to that of France in the year 2000, which equalled 27%¹³ (COR, 2017, p. 2).

¹³We take the demographic ratio computed where the elderly are those aged 65 or more and the middle-aged those aged 20 to 64. With this definition, Argentina’s old-age dependency ratio equals 25%

A first reason behind this population ageing is the increase in life expectancy assumed by INDEC's population projections. In these, life expectancy at birth for both genders rises from the 75 years computed in 2009 to 81 years by 2040. Another reason for the increased weight of the elderly is the impact of decreasing fecundity rates, both in the recent past and in the projections up to 2040. The global fertility rate by woman has indeed steadily decreased from a stable 3 to 3.4 child per woman between 1960 and 1990 to 2.4 during the 2010 National Census and 2.3 in 2014¹⁴. This is visible in Figure 3.4a, where five-year cohorts aged 15 to 24 are more numerous than those aged 14 or less. INDEC's population projections assume this fertility rate equals 2.28 in 2015, drops to 2.18 in 2020 and then stabilises near 2 children per woman by 2035, so below the demographic replacement level of 2.1 children per woman. This results in an even narrower base for the age pyramid by 2020, as depicted by Figure 3.4b. It however stabilises by the end of the simulation, as seen in Figure 3.4d. Therefore, not only are the numerous cohorts born before the year 2000 going to reach older ages, but the less populous generations born after the year 2000 will progressively become the working-age population. Both these elements result in a linear increase of the old-age dependency ratio, as depicted in Figure 3.5.

However, the Argentinian economy is set to experience a period of demographic dividend, where the total dependency ratio decreases from 57% in 2014 to 48% in 2035, before slightly increasing to 51% by 2040 as shown by Figure 3.5. This is because the increase in the old-age dependency ratio is more than offset by the fall in the young-age dependency ratio, which decreases from 41% in 2014 to 26% in 2040. This diminution comes from the aforementioned decrease in the global fertility rate predicted by the INDEC. Also, Figure 3.5 shows this reduction is concentrated between years 2014 and 2030, which are the years where the global fecundity rates decrease the fastest in INDEC's population projections (decreasing from 2.28 in 2015 to 2.05 in 2030). After that date, the young-age dependency ratio stabilises near 26%. Naturally, since the proportion of the elderly linearly increases and that of the young stops decreasing, by 2040 the demographic dividend ends and total dependency ratios increase.

It is worth mentioning there are two caveats to this analysis. First, the actual dependency ratios should be lower since we do not take into account migrations in our microsimulation model. INDEC's population projections foresee a slightly positive net migration rate equal to 4 ‰ in 2010, although it converges to zero by 2040. Taking mi-

by 2040.

¹⁴Source: World Bank data bank. URL: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.DYN.TFRT.IN?locations=AR>

grations into account should slightly improve the demographic profile of our simulated population as immigrants typically are young adults who emigrate after finishing their education (Beine *et al.* , 2007). Simulating migration is however left for future work. Second, the ANSES spends significantly more on Social Security Benefits (mostly made up of retirement and survivors pensions) than it does on family benefits even though according to INDEC's population projections minors are more than twice as numerous as people of retiring age¹⁵. Therefore, an increase of the old-age dependency ratio has a negative impact on ANSES accounts that cannot be compensated by an equivalent decrease in the young-age dependency ratio. The demographic dividend is still going to be an actual economic phenomenon since the minor population's cost is more reflected on education expenditures or other expenses assumed by the households. This dividend is simply not going to significantly show in ANSES accounts.

After 2040, Argentina's demographic situation should significantly worsen, specially between 2050 and 2060. These are the years where the relatively numerous generations aged 15 to 44 by 2014, born when the global fertility rates were comprised between 2.75 and 3.4, will reach retirement age. At the same time, the less populous generations aged 14 or less in 2014 or born after 2014 will reach working age, further increasing the old-age dependency ratio. This also implies the cohorts of fertile age will be less numerous than by the end of our simulation, which means the age pyramid is expected to get narrower after 2040 even if global fertility rates stagnate. Argentina is thus likely to experience a "senior boom" after 2040, which will be an additional long-term challenge for Argentina's social security system. How it would weather this coming increase in the old-age dependency ratio is left for future work. In any case, even with a reasonably favourable demographic situation for the 2014-2040 period we will see Argentina's social security system with 2018 legislation is not sustainable. This point will be thoroughly studied in section 3.2. Before that, we will review our simulation of ANSES "Bismarckian" balance, which is the basis for studying Argentina's social security economic result.

¹⁵According to INDEC's population projections, between years 2010 and 2017 there were on average 2.4 times more minors than people of retirement age. During that same period, retirement benefits paid by the ANSES were 6.2 higher than family benefits (excluding those for family members of national civil servants). Source: own computation on Argentina's physical-financial follow-up of social security institutions for years 2010 to 2017.

3.1.4 ANSES Bismarckian economic result by scenario, with 2018 legislation

Now that we have reviewed our economic and demographic scenarios, as well as the projected GDP evolution, we carry out our microsimulation of Argentina's social security with 2018 legislation following these scenarios, which result in aggregate values of Social Security Contributions (SSC), Benefits (SSB) and Current Transfers to the private sector (CT) up to 2040. The full projected values of variables SSC, SSB and CT by economic scenario using the fourth quarter of 2014 EPHc survey as the starting dataset are listed in Appendix R. We then apply the conversion keys we computed in Table 3.5 to these projected values and express them as a percentage of projected GDP (see Appendix R). We can finally compute a Bismarckian version of ANSES economic result, equal to $SSC - (SSB + CT)$. The results are pictured by Figure 3.6 below. As a robustness measure, we made equivalent figures with simulations starting the second quarters of 2014 and of 2015. We show changing the starting dataset has little impact on projected ANSES "Bismarckian" economic result. These Figures are available in Appendix S.

Figure 3.6: ANSES Bismarckian balance by economic scenario, 1993-2040 (% of GDP)

The starting dataset is the EPHc carried out during the fourth quarter of 2014. The Bismarckian balance equals Social Security Contributions minus Social Security Benefits (retirement and survivor's pensions) and Current Transfers to the private sector (mostly family benefits and healthcare contributions by the elderly). The Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult (PUAM) is funded by the federal budget as per the 2016 historical reparation Law 27260. Technically speaking, it is not a retirement benefit either, so a strict definition of ANSES Bismarckian deficit would exclude the PUAM. This pension will however replace the retirement benefit of a large proportion of the elderly and has not been assigned any genuine source of revenue. As such, we consider the case where ANSES takes on the costs of the PUAM. Sources: for historical values, see Figure 1.1. Simulated values come from our microsimulation model and are listed in Appendix R.

We complemented simulated values of ANSES Bismarckian balance with their historical counterparts since the creation of ANSES in 1993. First of all, between years 2014 and 2017 ANSES Bismarckian¹⁶ deficit worsened from 2.2% to 3.3% of GDP¹⁷. This is

¹⁶We exclude from the computation of this "Bismarckian" deficit the additional spending due to the historical reparation plan, as estimated for years 2016 and 2017 in our Appendix A. This is because these expenses are funded with penalties linked to the Law 27260 fiscal amnesty for years 2016 and 2017.

¹⁷Source: own computation using data from the Nation's General Accounts Agency's Investment Account for years 2014 to 2016 and ONP (2018) for 2017

because between years 2014 and 2017 the share of ANSES Social Security Contributions stagnated (5.4% to 5.7% of GDP) while retirement pensions (6.4% to 7.4%) and current transfers funded by ANSES (1.2% to 1.6%) increased by a combined 1.4% of GDP. This increase in retirement pensions spending is most likely due to the Law 26970 pension moratorium. Although it ended in September 2016, it should be noted that access to this moratorium was extended for women until the 23d of July 2019¹⁸ by Art.22 of the historical reparation Law 27260. Meanwhile, the increase in family benefits spending during this same period may come from its extension to the children of *monotributistas* since May 2016 by Decree 593/2016¹⁹ and the significant loosening of means conditions to get a family benefit since September 2016 as established by ANSES Resolution 299/2016²⁰. This last phenomenon is simulated in our model, the child benefit coverage spiking in 2016 as will be shown in Figure 3.17b. Finally, compulsory PAMI contributions by pensioners increased on par with retirement benefits, contributing to the increase of current transfers paid by the ANSES in GDP points.

As can be seen in Figure 3.6, ANSES long term Bismarckian balance is highly dependent on the chosen economic scenario. This is first and foremost due to the changing proportion of formal wage-earners from one scenario to the other. Indeed, in order to make labour-market scenarios that significantly differ from one another but also espouse Argentina's labour-market history as explained in section 2.3.4, the central scenario has a proportion of formal wage-earners that is 7 percentage points higher (resp. lower) than the low (resp. high) scenario as we have seen in Table 3.6 or Appendix N. The number of contributors thus significantly changes from one scenario to the other, impacting directly on ANSES revenue. This is however also a consequence of the indexation of ANSES payments (mostly) on inflation. This is a standard economic result (see for France Blanchet *et al.* (2016a)) as pensions increase slower than social security contributions (who are a percentage of gross wage) and GDP growth in the mid to long term. Thus, the faster the economy and real wages grow, the lower the proportion of GDP represented by benefits indexed on inflation. This effect is apparent when we compare real wage growth with mean pension evolution in Figure 3.17c on page 408. Also, as we have seen earlier in this section and in Figure 3.3, our long-term GDP growth is by hypothesis mostly determined by the changes in workers' population and real wages, which reinforced the simulated growth-dependence of ANSES economic result. Finally, we have seen in section 1.1.4 that Law 27430 decreases employers contributions mostly through a non-taxable income of 12,000 constant January 2018 pesos. Thus, the higher the wages, the lower the propor-

¹⁸This date was defined by Decree 894/2016, issued the 28th of July 2016.

¹⁹Issued the 15th of April 2016.

²⁰Issued the 5th of September 2016.

tion of labour income that does not pay employer's contributions, and thus the lower the impact on ANSES accounts.

This said, a closer analysis of our future simulated Bismarckian balance by scenario gives out some trends of ANSES future economic result. First, a worsening of ANSES accounts is expected up until 2022. This is mostly due to the gradual reduction of employers' contributions to social security established by Law 27430 and that will be fully enforced by 2022. In our central scenario, this contributes to the decrease of social security contributions as a percentage of GDP from 5.6% in 2017 to 4.1% in 2022. Meanwhile, the GDP share of retirement benefits, including universal pensions (PUAM), stagnates between 2017 and 2022. This is first of all due to the small difference in our central scenario between yearly GDP growth (on average equal to 1,4%) and the real pension mobility resulting from 2017's Law 27426 (0.22%). Also, between years 2019 and 2024 moratorium pensions granted between 2014 and 2019 through Law 26970 see their levels automatically increase. Indeed, subscribers to this moratorium earn a reduced benefit (usually 80% of the minimum pension) during five years, and then get at least the minimum pension. Since in our model we made most potential beneficiaries enrol in this moratorium as soon as it was accessible, this increase happens for the most part between years 2019 and 2020, as can be seen in Figure 3.17c on page 408. Both these elements prevent a decrease in pension spending as a percentage of GDP. Therefore, in our projections ANSES "Bismarckian" deficit equals -4.4%, -4.8% and -5.3% in our high, central and low economic scenarios by 2022.

After 2022, the evolution of ANSES "Bismarckian" deficit is highly dependent on the economic scenario. If we set aside the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult (PUAM), this deficit decreases (in the high and central economic scenarios) or slightly increases (in the low scenario), going from -5%, -4.6% and -4.1% of GDP in 2022 to -5.5%, -3.4% and -1.7% of GDP in 2040 in our low, central and high scenarios. The economic scenarios are different enough from one another that they have a significant impact on ANSES Bismarckian balance. Social Security Contributions (SSC) allocated to ANSES are the least affected by the chosen scenario: they go from respectively 4%, 4.1% and 4.2% to 3.7%, 4.1% and 4.5% of GDP between 2022 and 2040. This is logical, since our growth model makes long-term GDP depend on real wage and total workers evolution. Formal wage-earners both get the highest revenues and contribute the most to social security, so evolutions in the universe of formal wage-earners affect in a similar manner both SSC and the GDP.

On the other hand, the future evolution of ANSES Social Security Benefits (SSB) is highly dependent on the chosen economic scenario. As we have explained earlier, this is due to the growth dependence induced by Law 27426 pension mobility formula. Indeed, ANSES expenses are only partially (30%) indexed on real wages (as per Law 27426) while long-term GDP is jointly determined in our model by the growth of workers population and labour productivity (as seen in equation 3.1), the latter following the evolution of real wages. Therefore, a strong GDP growth decreases both SSB and CT as a percentage of GDP in the long term. First, the weight of ANSES Social Security Benefits (SSB) including the cost of the universal pension PUAM on the GDP does changes significantly from one scenario to the other, as a result of this indexation of benefits mostly on inflation. In the low, central and high scenarios, they go from 7.9%, 7.6% and 7.3% of GDP in 2022 to 10.3%, 8.5% and 7.1% of GDP in 2040. It takes however an average yearly growth of 2.6% as the one in our high economic scenario to decrease the GDP share of SSB + PUAM. This is despite the gradual death of generations that benefited from the more generous Laws 24476, 25994 and 26970 moratoriums (see Table 1.1.3 on page 66) and their replacement by seniors that earn the less generous PUAM and only since age 65. This is partly caused by the population ageing depicted in Figure 3.4, but also shows the limits of relying on a change in pension indexation to significantly decrease pensions as a percentage of GDP even in the long term.

Moreover, Current Transfers to the private sector (CT, mostly family benefits and healthcare contributions made by the ANSES on behalf of retirement pensioners) always decrease in GDP points, slightly affected by the chosen economic scenarios. They dwindle from respectively 1.4%, 1.3% and 1.2% of GDP in 2022 for the low, central and high scenarios to 1.3%, 0.9% and 0.7% of GDP in 2040. This is partially due to the decrease in the young-age dependency ratio we saw in Figure 3.4. Moreover and perhaps most importantly, child benefits are significantly reduced in the more optimistic economic scenarios because both their levels and income conditions are discounted following the pension mobility Law 27426: 30% on the RIPTE formal wage index and 70% on the Consumer Price Index. This induces a long-term freeze in real terms of family benefits as depicted in Figure 3.17d. The fact family allowances income caps are mostly indexed on inflation, and thus increase slower than real wages, also means an increasing proportion of formal workers earn lower child benefits or stop earning one altogether. This results in a decrease in coverage, as depicted in Figure 3.17b on page 407. Finally, the decrease of informal labour in our central and optimistic economic scenarios reduces the number of AUH beneficiaries, which in turn decreases the mean level of child benefits paid. Indeed, contributory child benefits are means-tested, and their levels decrease with the parents'

labour income. On the other hand, the AUH is equal to the highest contributory child benefit (see Appendix E), and does not depend on the informal workers' revenue. If we take two couples with the same number of children that receive the same income but that respectively work in the formal and informal sectors, the latter will receive the AUH, which will always be greater or equal than the contributory child benefits granted to the former (Garganta & Gasparini, 2015). Thus, the replacement of universal (AUH) by contributory child benefits decreases family allowances expenditure. All this ensures family benefits (and thus CT) as a percentage of GDP significantly decrease in the long run, reducing their overall economic relevance.

Finally, a separate measurement of the cost of the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult (PUAM) shows it linearly increases after 2019, once access to the Law 26970 moratorium will be definitively cut off. By 2040, it will represent 2.5%, 1.9% and 1.5% of GDP in our low, central and high economic scenarios. Thus, we can see taking into account the PUAM increases the growth dependence of social security accounts. First, because a more pessimistic labour-market scenario increases the number of individuals that need a universal pension to retire. Secondly, PUAM benefits (and also moratorium pensions) only increase following the Law 27426 mobility index, which effectively makes them almost freeze in the long run as is apparent in Figure 3.17c. Contributory retirement pensions on the other hand more or less follow real wages both because their initial level is computed on the last ten wages. In the end, taking into account the cost of this measure therefore significantly increases ANSES Bismarckian deficit, making it reach -7.9%, -5.3% and -3.2% of GDP in our low, central and high scenarios.

All in all, we show in our simulations that despite a fall in the adequacy of retirement pensions and family benefits induced by the pension reforms of 2016 and 2017, the lowering of employers contributions to social security and the impact of the Law 26970 pension moratorium should result in a deteriorating ANSES deficit up to 2022. The fact ANSES benefits are now only 30% indexed on real wages helps reduce the "Bismarckian" deficit in the long run despite an ageing population. It however makes ANSES accounts highly dependent on future growth. A 1.3% difference in yearly economic growth, combined with a 7 percentage points variation of the share of registered wage-earners between our economic scenarios (see Table 3.6) will result in significant differences in the simulated ANSES Bismarckian balance. The pessimistic (resp. optimistic) ANSES Bismarckian result is 2.6 (resp. 2.1) GDP points lower (resp. higher) than the central scenario's, as shown by Figure 3.6. With today's legislation, the long-term sustainability of Argentina's retirement and social security system and of its most recent reforms is thus strongly de-

terminated by the economy's long-term growth.

This analysis does not allow us to conclude on ANSES long-term economic sustainability, as we have shown in the beginning of this section that in this "Bismarckian" economic result we cover 84% of the expenses and 54% of the revenues of ANSES. The remaining 16% and 46% are not simulated by our model, and have been largely modified by the 2016 and 2017 reforms. We will thus study these elements in section 3.2 below, giving ANSES long-term economic result, as well as its benefits' adequacy and redistributive impact, across various counter-factual reform scenarios.

3.2 Projection results: social security projections and reform impact evaluation (2014-2040)

In this last section, we present the first projection of Argentina's social security system funding needs, adequacy and redistributive impact. We carry it out on the 2014-2040 period with varying economic scenarios which cover a wide array of possible labour-market participation and wage evolutions (see sections 2.3.4 and 3.1.3). Our simulations however need a last legislative calibration to go beyond the "Bismarckian" deficit we computed in section 3.1.4 and depicted in Figure 3.6. Indeed, we need to first take into account non-simulated ANSES expenses and sources of revenue to compute ANSES economic result and state on the actual sustainability of social security accounts. As we mentioned in section 3.1.1, these respectively represent 16% and 46% of all ANSES expenses and income, so they are far from negligible. Secondly, we have carried out our simulations so far with the legislation in force on May 2018. We however want to evaluate the impact of the various reforms adopted by the incumbent administration on Argentina's social security system. To this end, we calibrate our simulations to the current mid-2018 legislation and compare the results with what would have happened without the late 2017 reforms first, and then excluding all the reforms undertaken by the current government. We will thus on section 3.2.1 complete the legislative calibration of our model by not only studying the non-simulated ANSES income and expenses, but also by defining our counter-factual legislative scenarios.

After that, it will be possible to not only compute ANSES economic result, but to also launch our counter-factual simulation with alternative legislation scenarios. This allows for an *ex ante* evaluation of the impact of these various reforms on Argentina's

social security. In section 3.2.2, we compute ANSES economic result across economic and legislative scenarios and evaluate the impact of the 2016 and late 2017 reforms on the economic sustainability of Argentina's social security system across the 2014-2040 period, with varying economic scenarios. Finally, in sections 3.2.3 and 3.2.4 we compute various statistics on the simulated synthetic population to track the evolution of respectively social security benefits' redistributive impact and adequacy in the 2014-2040 period across our counter-factual legislative scenarios. We can therefore provide a thorough *ex ante* analysis of the long-term consequences of the recent pension reforms on social security's economic sustainability, adequacy and redistributive impact.

3.2.1 Non-simulated expenses and revenue, and the counter-factual legislative scenarios

The last step we need to undertake before studying Argentina's social security long-term economic sustainability, adequacy and redistributive impact is to put the finishing touches on the legislative calibration of our model. First of all, we list and describe non-simulated ANSES taxes and expenses. Taking them into account allows to move from the estimation of ANSES "Bismarckian" deficit (social security contributions minus retirement and survivors benefits, elderly healthcare contributions and family benefits) to the study of ANSES economic result. Secondly, we recapitulate the legislation changes introduced by the 2016 and late 2017 reforms. This lets us specify the adopted legislative scenarios as far as both simulated and non-simulated ANSES expenses and revenue are concerned, which is a pre-requisite to evaluate the policies adopted by the current administration.

ANSES non-simulated expenses and revenue

We have simulated almost all ANSES expenditure and the majority of its sources of revenue in Section 3.1. We have however opted against simulating a number of sources of revenue and expenses that are not related to Argentina's social security system. On the one hand, acknowledging that contributions are insufficient to fund ANSES benefits, a number of tax benefits have been assigned to fund ANSES. These are listed in Table 3.7 below.

Table 3.7: List of taxes that fund ANSES (1993-2018)

Tax that goes to ANSES ¹	Legislation	Since	Until
15% of <i>coparticipable</i> taxes This share decreases by 3% each year starting from 2016. The missing funds are provided by the federal budget	Fiscal Pact ratified by Law 24130 Law 27260 Appendices I and II and Art. 26 of Law 27260	01/09/1992	31/12/2015 01/01/2016 -
20% of the Income Tax ²	Law 20628 (instituted in 1997), Decree 649/97 Art. 104, Law 24621 Art. 1	01/01/1993 ³	31/12/2017
93.73% of 11% of the net Value-Added Tax	Art. 5 of Law 23966; Law 27432	20/08/1991	31/12/2022
21% of taxes on liquid fuel (excluding gas oil, diesel oil and kerosene), 100% of taxes on compressed natural gas, gas oil, diesel oil and kerosene 28.69% of taxes on liquid fuel and carbon dioxide	Law 23966 Title III, Art. 2 of Law 24699, Law 26078 Art. 143 and 148 of Law 27430	27/09/1996	28/02/2018 01/03/2018 -
100% of the additional emergency tax on cigarettes	Law 24625, Law 25239 Art. 9 to 11, Law 27432 ⁴	31/12/1999	31/12/2022
70% of the fiscal and 100% of the provisional component of the <i>Monotributo</i> integrated tax	Law 24977 Art. 59 and Law 27432	06/07/1998	31/12/2022
100% of the Tax on Credits and Debits on banks' current accounts ⁵	Law 25413 and Art. 1 of Law 27432	01/01/2018	-

¹: Some taxes are collected by the federal government and then automatically redistributed (or co-participated) between it and the different provinces. These are the *coparticipable* taxes.

²: 580 million pesos are first subtracted from the Income Tax, of which 120 million go directly to ANSES. 20% of the remaining Income Tax goes to ANSES.

³: Law 24621, issued the 9th of January 1996, states that 20% of the Income Tax funds ANSES. However, this percentage was already given to ANSES at least since 1993. This is evidenced by the Investment Accounts of years 1993 to 1995, where part of the funding to ANSES comes from an income tax. Moreover, this funding is equal to 20% of the Income Tax collected by the State for years 1993 to 1995 (DNIAF, 2013).

⁴: This tax was equal to 21% of the end price of cigarettes between the 1st of January 2000 and the 31st of December 2017. After that date, it is equal to 7% of the price of cigarettes as per Art. 124 of Law 27430.

⁵: By Art. 7 of Law 27432, starting from January 2018, each year an additional 20% of the tax may be considered as payment of the Income Tax. This means by 2022 the full tax may be effectively eliminated. Decree 409/2018 establishes that since 7 May 2018²¹, 33% of the Law 25413 tax may be considered as payment for the Income Tax.

On the other hand, a number of expenses are paid for by ANSES but are not benefits given by the Integrated Argentinian Pension System (SIPA). First, operational costs are funded with the 15% of *coparticipable funds* assigned to ANSES, according to the Appendix of Law 24130²². This point is still valid even though the funding will eventually be provided for by the federal budget according to Art. 26 of Law 27260. Therefore, these costs must be taken into account when determining ANSES economic result. Moreover, most of ANSES figurative²³ expenses are funded by this agency, and are not compensated by equivalent figurative contributions from the national Treasury. As shown by Rosconi *et al.* (2017), these figurative expenses mostly fund non-contributory pensions paid by the Ministry of Social Development, made up mostly of pensions for the disabled. They also balance the budget of the social security schemes of military and police personnel. We lack detailed information on the recipients of ANSES figurative expenses before 2010. However, available data in CGN's Investment Accounts for years 1993 to 2009 show ANSES has been funding both Social Security schemes and central administration bodies since its inception in 1993. It is unclear whether it is *de jure* established that it is ANSES that ought to fund these figurative expenses. In any case, both these elements are *de facto* paid for by ANSES, are not compensated by equivalent figurative contributions by the Treasury, and must therefore be taken into account in this agency's economic result.

Tables T.1 and T.2 in Appendix T list the evolution of non-simulated ANSES resources and expenses as a percentage of GDP for the 1993-2017 period. We assume they kept their 2008-2017 average and abide by the known legislative changes listed in Table 3.7. Factoring in ANSES fiscal revenues as well as its figurative expenses improves ANSES

²¹The Decree is ambiguous as to whether this deduction may actually be applied since the 1st of January 2018. If so, this measure would be in a contradiction with Art. 7 of Law 27432. We will thus assume this deduction starts on May 2018.

²²Issued the 22d of September 1992

²³In Argentina's public accounts system, some agencies make expenses on behalf of other branches of the public sector. These appear in the Savings-Investment-Funding (AIF) Account as figurative expenses. Similarly, this agency may receive transfers from other parts of the public sector. These are called figurative contributions, and appear as such in the AIF account. The content of figurative expenses and contributions is often vague, as it is not fully set *de jure* and may sometimes be used to compensate a temporary deficit in the agency's accounts.

economic result by an average of 2% of GDP in the 2008-2017 period, as depicted in Figure 3.7. Another non-simulated source of revenue for ANSES are FGS investments returns. These represent an additional income of around 0.9% of GDP since 2014, or on average 10.9% of the Fund's assets by December of the previous year. By 2017, they have been fully reinvested in the Fund, making it reach 10.4% of the fourth quarter of 2017 GDP in December 2017 (ANSES, 2018). These returns will however fund in the future part of ANSES expenses. First of all, FGS returns can be used to fund the Universal Child Benefit (AUH)²⁴. It has however never been the case so far, even though it has been possible *de jure* since late 2009. On the other hand, it is certain that FGS returns and assets will fund the cost of the historical reparation program²⁵. This is because these are this policy's only sources of funding together with the penalties associated with the Law 27260 fiscal amnesty. The question is therefore to what extent will the historical reparation program weigh on FGS returns and take a dent on its assets. If this program's cost were to exceed FGS assets and empty the fund out then the unfunded portion of this program would need to be included in our social security sustainability analysis.

To answer this question, we have estimated how much the historical reparation program has so far increased pension expenses by 2017 in Appendix A. We found this program has increased pension spending by 0.62% of GDP in 2017 and represented 7.9% of all pension spending. This proportion is compatible with the one that was foreseen in the 2017 budget, where spending on the historical reparation program was scheduled to represent 7.5% of all pension spending. Moreover, the 2018 budget schedules historical reparation payments will represent 7% of total pensions paid by ANSES, which decreases the weight of this program on ANSES spending²⁶. We then build upon these 2016 and 2017 expenses, as well as on the budgeted expenditure for 2018, to estimate the future cost of the historical reparation program in Appendix U. We find a modest increase in retirement expenses linked to the historical reparation program. In our central economic scenario, the expenses reach 0.6% of GDP in 2018, gradually decrease to 0.39% in 2025 and finally equal 0.09% of GDP in 2040, becoming negligible. The results are very similar for our low and high scenarios, as can be seen in Appendix U. Finally, these withdrawals from the leftover funds of the fiscal amnesty and the FGS will not be enough to completely empty out the FGS. As we have computed in Appendix U, we find that the FGS will

²⁴As established by Article 3 of the Decree 1602/2009 issued the 30th of October 2009.

²⁵As established by Art. 28 of Law 27260, issued the 22d of July 2016.

²⁶The detailed figures of budgeted ANSES expenditure are established by the Administrative Decisions 12/2017 and 6/2018 taken by the Executive Office of the Cabinet of the Ministers on the distribution of the budget among different entities. The exact figures can be found in both of these decisions' appendices on spending allocated to ANSES. These can be downloaded in the National Budget Office's website. For 2018, the link is <https://www.minhacienda.gob.ar/onp/presupuestos/2018> (accessed 22 May 2018).

represent 4.4% of 2040 GDP by December of that year in our central economic scenario. In our low and high economic scenarios, this figure will respectively reach 3.8% and 4.9% of GDP. We also find that the FGS will only start paying these benefits in 2019 in all these scenarios. The details of our calculations, as well as the full set of future values by year and economic scenario, are shown in Appendix U. We can therefore exclude these expenses from the analysis of ANSES long-term sustainability.

The counter-factual legislative scenarios

We have in section 2.2 mentioned we have to calibrate our prospective microsimulation module with various elements, as depicted in Figure 2.1 page 164. One of these elements is the projected legislative scenario. One of this model’s strengths is that it can be re-run with varying economic legislation, but with the remaining calibration left untouched. The end result is we get various synthetic populations that only differ from one another by the adopted legislative scenario. This lets us carry out a public policy evaluation of Argentina’s social security system for all the aspects taken into account in our simulations. Therefore, we not only see how ANSES aggregate economic sustainability is affected by the various reforms. We can also go down to the individual and household level to see the impact of legislative changes on income inequality as well as on social security benefits’ adequacy. The main differences between our counter-factual scenarios are summarised in Table 3.8 below.

Table 3.8: Differences between the counter-factual legislative scenarios

	Month of reference for the counter-factual legislative scenarios			
	May 2018	Nov. 2017	Dec. 2015	Strict Dec. 2015
Permanent non-contributive retirement pension	PUAM	PUAM	2014 moratorium	None
Indexation formula	70% CPI, 30% RIPTE	100% RIPTE	100% RIPTE	
ANSES gets 100% of the shrinking "Check" tax in replacement of 20% of the income tax	Yes	No	No	

	May 2018	Nov. 2017	Dec. 2015	Strict Dec.
15% of all <i>coparticipable</i> taxes are allocated to ANSES	No	No	Yes	
Reduced employer's contributions	Yes	No	No	
Historical reparation program	Yes	Yes	No	
Child benefits for <i>monotributistas'</i> children	Yes	Yes	No	
Past revenues for the reference income are discounted by	Formal wage indexes		Retirement evolutions index	
RIPTE stands for Mean Taxable Income of Stable Workers. CPI is the Consumer Price Index. PUAM is the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult, presented in section 1.1.2.				
Fuel tariffs that fund ANSES as well as the indexation of family benefits income caps on pension mobility are left unchanged across the counter-factual legislative scenarios. Strictly speaking, fuel tariffs were modified in December 2017 by Law 27430, and the indexation of family benefits income caps on pension mobility was implemented on September 2016 through ANSES Resolution 299/2016.				

Let us give a more detailed account of these counter-factual scenarios and explain the logic behind them.

Our first counter-factual scenario: taking out the late 2017 reforms

Our first counter-factual simulation of social security sustainability, adequacy and redistributive impact assumes the late 2017 reforms (Laws 27426, 27430 and 27432, published the 28th and 29th of December 2017) never took place. First and foremost, we reverse the changes in social security benefits indexation introduced by these reforms. Most importantly, this means ANSES benefits²⁷ would have been subjected to the Law 26417 pension mobility index. It indexed benefits by 50% on the RIPTE wage index and by 50% on the evolution of ANSES fiscal sources of income. In our model, long-term growth is driven by labour productivity gains and thus by the evolution of the RIPTE, as we explained

²⁷As we have seen in section 1.1, not only all relevant ANSES benefits (excluding for instance the unemployment benefits, which we do not simulate) are indexed on the pension mobility index. It is also the case of means conditions for access to contributory child benefits and of the *monotributo* and autonomous workers regimes' categories and payments.

in section 3.1.3 and wrote down in equation 3.2. As explained earlier in this section, we assume in our projections ANSES fiscal sources of income are a fixed percentage of the GDP. This means their real projected evolution mostly follows real wages. As such, we decided for the sake of simplicity that in this counter-factual simulation ANSES benefits were indexed by 100% on the real growth of formal wages, and thus of the RIPTE. We leave for further work the task of precisely estimating the counter-factual Law 26417 pension mobility index for the 2018-2040 period. Secondly, we also take out the guaranteed pension benefit equal to at least 82% of the minimum wage introduced by Law 27426. This guarantee only applies to pensioners that had access to the PBU, that is, all Law 24241 contributory retirees, and excludes moratorium and universal pension (PUAM) pensioners.

A second important reform is the changes in employer's contributions to social security introduced by Law 27430. Employers contribution rates are unified for the services and industrial sectors, and wage income under 12,000 constant (January 2018) pesos will not be subject to employer's contributions. Both these measures are gradually implemented and will be fully in force by 2022. In this counter-factual scenario, we assume these two measures were never undertaken, which mechanically increases social security contributions allocated to the ANSES. It can be argued whether this non-taxable income may have an impact on net wages that we should have taken into account in our central simulations. Or at least whether it would be correct to keep the same net real wage and informality rate evolutions in our central and counter-factual simulations. First, because reduced employer's contributions may be an incentive for the formalisation of the least qualified workers, so this reform may modify the age-dependent and total formality rates. Second, because this reduction in the wage-earner's cost for the employer may give way to net wage increases. However, our model in its current version cannot endogenously simulate labour formality changes or modifications of net real wages caused by changing social security contributions. Moreover, Argentina already eliminated employers' contributions between 1980 and 1983 (see section 1.1.1 and Lo Vuolo & Goldberg (2002)), and reduced them since 1999 (through Decree 1520/1998) with in both cases no significantly positive effect on either net wages or labour formality, as can be seen in Figures 1.7 and 1.10. We thus assume that the reduction of employer's contributions introduced by Law 27430 will have no impact on neither net wages nor labour formality rates. This said, our model can also take into account the impact of contribution reductions on labour formality and wages. The problem is these impacts must be estimated exogenously and then replicated on the model's labour-market scenarios. Since this question is secondary for this thesis, we leave this possibility for future work.

Finally, we undo in this scenario some changes in the taxes that fund ANSES introduced by Law 27430. First, this law established that the whole Income Tax was to be redistributed (*coparticipada*) between the provinces and the federal government, and that ANSES would get in return 100% of the (shrinking) Tax on Credits and Debits on banks' Current Accounts²⁸ (commonly known as "Check" tax). We eliminate this change in this counter-factual simulation. Also, Law 27430 introduced changes to various fuel tariffs that funded ANSES. It is complicated to determine whether these changes will have a significant impact on fuel tariffs and on revenues affected to ANSES. At first glance it does not seem to significantly be the case, although we lack for the moment data on tax collection to know for sure. We thus considered these changes did not significantly modify revenues affected to ANSES. Therefore, in our simulations with both 2018 and 2017 legislation fuel tariffs represent a yearly source of revenue equal to 0.27% of GDP, which is their mean value between 2008 and 2017.

Our second and third counter-factual scenario: 2015 legislation with and without permanent pension moratoriums

Our second and third counter-factual legislative scenarios assume none of the major measures taken by the current administration were undertaken. This means we mostly go back in time to the end of 2015. First of all, we eliminate in these scenarios all the late 2017 social security reforms we already took out in the first counter-factual scenario. Secondly, we eliminate all measures included in the historical reparation Law 27260. This means we keep deducting 15% of all *coparticipable* taxes in favour of ANSES, we do not use the FGS to pay for the historical reparation program and we do not introduce the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult (PUAM). Finally, we either make the Law 26970 pension moratorium end in September 2016 for both men and women as set in that law, or assume on the contrary this moratorium becomes permanent. This is the only difference between our second and third counter-factual scenarios with late 2015 legislation.

Those are the main legislation changes we adopt in these counter-factual scenarios. We also eliminate some smaller measures. First, we take out the extension of contributory family benefits to the children of certain categories of small independent workers (*monotributistas*), established by Decree 593/2016 since May 2016. We then keep computing the initial retirement pension with an index depicting the evolution of past nominal retirement benefits, just as it had been done before Res. 6 / 2016 of the Social Security Secretariat

²⁸This tax was instituted through Law 25413, issued the 26th of March 2001.

issued the 3d of August 2016. Since both indexes are identical since March 2009 and the first actualisation of retirement benefits following Law 26417 pension mobility index, the impact on future benefits is negligible.

The only ulterior reforms we chose to keep were the changes made in the means conditions for having access to a contributory family benefit, and in particular their indexation on the pension mobility law as established since the 31st of August 2016. This is because there previously was no legislation that determined how the means conditions for family benefits would be adjusted with respect to inflation. A consequence of this modelling decision is that we still get the spike in contributory child benefits coverage caused by the significant loosening of means conditions to get a family benefit adopted in September 2016 through ANSES Resolution 299/2016²⁹, as will be seen in Figure 3.19d.

All in all, we have laid out the full legislative calibration relevant for our prospective study of Argentina's social security. We first reviewed ANSES non-simulated expenses and sources of revenue, necessary for moving from our simulated "Bismarckian" deficit to the agency's actual economic result. We then designed our three counter-factual legislative scenarios, which will allow to evaluate the impact of policies adopted by the incumbent administration on Argentina's future social security situation. In the remainder of section 3.2, we first study ANSES economic result up to the 2040 horizon with varying economic and legislative scenarios in section 3.2.2 below. Then, we gauge the impact of the 2016 and 2017 reforms on social security benefits' redistributive impact in section 3.2.3. Finally, we see how the 2016 and 2017 reforms will affect future social security transfers adequacy in section 3.2.4.

3.2.2 Social security economic sustainability across economic and legislative scenarios (2014-2040)

We have in section 3.1.4 presented our simulation of ANSES "Bismarckian" balance, which is the difference between social security contributions and the sum of retirement and survivors pensions, healthcare contributions made on behalf of the elderly and family benefits. We then completed in section 3.2.1 the legislative calibration of our model. This lets us both study the full economic sustainability of social security and introduce counter-factual legislative scenarios in our simulations. In this section, we combine both these elements to project ANSES economic result across economic and legislative scen-

²⁹Issued the 5th of September 2016.

arios for the 2014-2040 period. We will end this section by evaluating the impact of the 2016 and late 2017 pension reforms on the economic sustainability of Argentina's social security system.

2018 ANSES sustainability by economic scenario

First of all, Figure 3.7 below gives a long-term estimation of ANSES sustainability by economic scenario. We exclude both the returns of FGS investments and the cost of the historical reparation program. This is because we have shown in Appendix A that the FGS will be enough to fund the historical reparation program's cost. Thus, the program does not add to the current expenses of ANSES. On the other hand, this also means the FGS cannot be used to fund other ANSES expenses. Hence, its returns cannot be counted as ANSES income, so they must be excluded from the computation of the agency's economic result.

Figure 3.7: ANSES economic result with 2018 legislation (1993-2040) (% of GDP)

The 2016 historical reparation Law 27260 institutes a Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult (PUAM) that is funded *de jure* by the federal budget. It also gradually stops funding ANSES with 15% of all taxes shared between the state and the provinces (called *coparticipable* taxes), although it states the federal budget will step in and compensate these missing funds. Since the federal budget is not a perennial source of funding, we also study the case where the ANSES would stop receiving funds from the federal budget to cover the costs of these Law 27260 measures. Sources: for historical values, see Figure 1.1. Simulated values come from our microsimulation model and are listed in Appendix R. Non-simulated expenses and income are listed in Appendix T, directly expressed in GDP points and do not change from one economic scenario to the other. The starting dataset is the EPHc carried out during the fourth quarter of 2014.

Figure 3.7 reproduces the general scheme of ANSES future economic result we showed in Section 3.1 Figure 3.6. First of all, in the 2015-2017 period our model broadly reproduces the ANSES deficit observed for those years, excluding both FGS returns and items linked to the Law 27260 historical reparation plan. After a slight improvement in 2018 due to the transfer of the Tax on Credits and Debits on banks' Current Accounts³⁰ (commonly known as "Check" tax) to ANSES, the deficit should increase rapidly until 2022. This is

³⁰This tax was instituted through Law 25413, issued the 26th of March 2001.

because on top of the simulated phenomena depicted in Figure 3.6 (the decrease in employers contributions combined with the increase of Law 26970 moratorium pensions after the end of the 5-year penalty period), that year marks the expected full elimination of the "Check" tax, which represented 1.7% of GDP in 2017. The panorama looks even bleaker once we factor in the full return of *coparticipable* taxes to the provinces, due by 2020 as established by Law 27260. Although *de jure* funded by the federal budget and not by the ANSES, this measure further decreases ANSES short-term deficit until making it reach -5.5% of GDP in 2022 in our central economic scenario. This means today's social security legislation as well as its recent reforms are bound to provoke an acute social security crisis in Argentina in the short run, basically because social security funding decreases while the expenses stagnate. The full detail of ANSES future sources of revenue and expenses by economic scenario is listed in Appendix R.

After 2022, social security deficit starts to significantly differ from one economic scenario to the other. Also, the difference between ANSES economic result with and without the additional deficit provoked by Law 27260 widens, mostly because of the increasing cost of the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult (PUAM), which can be found in detail in Appendix R. The general movement is that of a decrease (or at least stagnation) in ANSES deficit between 2022 (-3.3%, -3.7% and -4.2%) and 2040 (-0.7%, -2.4% and -4.4%) across all economic scenarios (high, central and low). However, if we take into account the increased expenditure and decreasing revenue caused by Law 27260, social security accounts are clearly not sustainable in the long run. Only in our high scenario the deficit slightly decreases to -3.7% of GDP by 2040. In our central and low scenarios, the social security deficit increases by respectively 0.4% and 2.5% of GDP between 2022 and 2040, and reaches -5.8% and -8.5% of GDP by 2040, and their trends suggest they would worsen after 2040. It is also worth noting that with the current legislation, ANSES economic result is very similar to the "Bismarckian" deficit (the difference between social security contributions and retirement and family benefits) including the cost of the universal pension (PUAM). We have indeed seen in section 3.1.3 the latter reaches -7.9%, -5.3% and -3.2% of GDP in our low, central and high scenarios in 2040, as depicted in Figure 3.6. We will see in our counter-factual analysis this is directly caused by the 2016 and 2017 reforms, which strongly decrease ANSES fiscal sources of revenue.

One immediate fix to make ANSES deficit more manageable in the absence of a more overarching reform would be to simply refrain from further decreasing the "Check" tax. Law 27432 indeed indicates the federal government may decide to reduce this tax by up to 20% yearly until 2022. We furthermore have seen in Table 3.7 that this reduction has

started with Decree 409/2018 issued the 7th of May 2018, which decreases this tax by 33% starting from May 2018. If we assume the "Check" tax would keep its mean 2008-2017 value of 1.66% of GDP if it were to be left untouched, this means if the government sticks to a 33% tax decrease then the equivalent of 1.28% of GDP would be available to fund social security. The resulting ANSES sustainability is depicted in Figure 3.8 below.

Figure 3.8: ANSES economic result with 2018 legislation, keeping the "Check" tax (1993-2040) (% of GDP)

For sources and additional information, see Figure 3.7.

As we can see in this Figure, keeping these 1.3% of GDP worth of funds for social security would indeed help mitigate the negative short-term impact of the return of *coparticipable* funds to the Provinces due by 2020 and of the reduction of employers' contributions to social security to be fully implemented by 2022. These funds would nevertheless be insufficient to curb the total social security deficit or significantly change its long-term trend. Therefore, it is clear the current legislation is not economically sustainable even in the very short term, and must thus be amended by more overarching measures. The fact this lack of sustainability comes after the succession of the 2016 and 2017 reforms means that at the very least they were not enough to ensure the sustainability of social security

accounts, and that they instead probably worsened it. Still, to rigorously determine the impact of the 2016 and 2017 reforms on social security sustainability, it is necessary to re-run our simulations excluding these reforms, using the three counter-factual scenarios presented in section 3.2.1 and summarised in Table 3.8. This is what we do below.

Counter-factual scenario 1: projections with November 2017 legislation

First of all, we take our first counter-factual scenario that consists on the November 2017 legislation, thus excluding the December 2017 reforms. These most notably changed ANSES sources of funding, reduced employers’ contributions to social security and adopted a less generous pension mobility formula. The counter-factual ANSES economic result without these reforms is shown below.

Figure 3.9: ANSES economic result by scenario with 2017 legislation (2014-2040)

(a) "Bismarckian" result (% of GDP)

Figure 3.9 depicts social security’s "Bismarckian" deficit and future economic result by scenario. We still exclude from this analysis the cost of the historical reparation program, since it is funded by the FGS. First of all, the short-term social security deficit is less important with 2017 legislation and the differences between economic scenarios are

(b) Economic result (% of GDP)

The Bismarckian result equals Social Security Contributions minus Social Security Benefits (retirement and survivor's pensions) and Current Transfers to the private sector (mostly family benefits and healthcare contributions by the elderly). To get the economic result, we add non-simulated ANSES income and expenses, as detailed in section 3.2.1. The 2016 historical reparation Law 27260 institutes a Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult (PUAM) that is funded *de jure* by the federal budget. It also gradually stops funding ANSES with 15% of all taxes shared between the state and the provinces (called *coparticipable* taxes), although it states the federal budget will step in and compensate these missing funds. Since the federal budget is not a perennial source of funding, we also study the case where the ANSES would stop receiving funds from the federal budget to cover the costs of these Law 27260 measures. Sources: for historical values, see Figure 1.1. Simulated values come from our microsimulation with November 2017 legislation and are listed in Appendix R. Non-simulated expenses and income are listed in Appendix T, directly expressed in GDP points and do not change from one economic scenario to the other. They are however subject to the legislative changes detailed in section 3.2.1. The starting dataset is the EPHc carried out during the fourth quarter of 2014.

minimal. Indeed, by 2022 the deficit reaches approximately -3% of GDP in all three of our scenarios when we include the cost of Law 27260 measures (the PUAM and the end of the deduction of 15% of *coparticipable* taxes in favour of ANSES). With 2018 legislation, by that date the total social security deficit reached -5%, -5.5% and -6% of GDP for the high, central and low scenarios. This is because 2018 legislation reduces employers' contributions and assigns to ANSES funding the shrinking "Check" tax. Also, keeping the indexation of ANSES benefits (mostly) on wages, following Law 26417, minimises the short-term differences between economic scenarios, particularly when we bear in mind

they differ in labour participation only starting 2019. The long-term sustainability of social security would also have been better had the late 2017 reforms never been adopted. By 2040, 2017 legislation results in deficits equal to -2.9%, -4.3% and -5.8% of GDP in our high, central and low economic scenarios, instead of the -3.7%, -5.8% and -8.4% of GDP reached with 2018 legislation. Finally, the growth dependence of social security sustainability is substantially lower. The above figures show the 2040 difference in ANSES result between the low and high scenarios reaches 2.9% of GDP with November 2017 legislation, instead of 4.7% of GDP with 2018 legislation. It thus appears the late 2017 reform had a fully negative impact on social security's sustainability for the whole simulated period. Nevertheless, with November 2017 legislation the social security deficit tends to increase at a fast pace in all economic scenarios, as can be seen in Figure 3.9b. On the other hand, the indexation of ANSES benefits mostly on the Consumer Price Index slows down this declining trend with 2018 legislation, as visible in Figure 3.7. The very long term deficit (beyond the period we simulate in our model) would thus have probably been higher with 2017 legislation, assuming no reforms would have been undertaken in the meantime. Given that even excluding the December 2017 reforms this deficit would have been consistently higher than 3% of GDP since as early as 2020, this assumption is a bit of a stretch.

In the end, late 2017 reforms highly worsened the short-term social security deficit. Its long term level furthermore became highly growth-dependent. They however contribute to its long-term stabilisation by partially abandoning the indexation of social security benefits on wages. This measure however strongly decreases the adequacy and redistributive impact of those benefits in the long term. This point will be reviewed more in depth in sections 3.2.3 and 3.2.4.

Counter-factual scenarios 2 and 3: late 2015 legislation with and without permanent pension moratoriums

Our second and third counter-factual legislative scenarios exclude all the major social security reforms adopted by the current administration. They both imply we mostly go back in time and apply the legislation in force in December 2015, as we have detailed in section 3.2.1 and summarised in Table 3.8. This mostly means benefits are indexed on real wages, the ANSES keeps receiving 20% of the Income Tax and 15% of all taxes normally shared between the state and the provinces (*coparticipable* taxes), there is neither the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult (PUAM) nor the historical reparation program and there are no changes in employer's contributions. The only difference between these two scenarios based in December 2015 legislation is what happens with the 2014 Law 26970

pension moratorium, which for a limited period of time allowed people with incomplete careers to retire at the legal minimum (see Table 1.1.3 page 66 for more details). We first assume in these counter-factual simulations that subscription to this pension moratorium would have been closed in September 2016, as originally scheduled. We then suppose this pension moratorium would have been permanent and see the impact it would have had on social security accounts. The resulting ANSES "Bismarckian" balances and economic results are displayed in Figure 3.10 below.

Figure 3.10: ANSES economic result by scenario with 2015 legislation (2014-2040)

In this second counter-factual scenario, the evolution of social security’s economic result is fully driven by ANSES "Bismarckian" result. This is because there is no change in ANSES fiscal sources of revenue between 2014 and 2040. We also assume these non-simulated expenses and revenue are equal to an unchanged proportion of GDP across economic scenarios. Therefore, social security sustainability is fully determined by ANSES economic result: there are no major expenses *de jure* funded by the federal budget, as is the case with the universal pension PUAM and the devolution to the provinces of 15% of the *coparticipable* revenue. This said, we can see ANSES accounts are sustainable in the long run, with either a slight deficit or a modestly positive economic result depending

(b) Economic result (% of GDP)

The "Bismarckian" result equals Social Security Contributions minus Social Security Benefits (retirement and survivor's pensions) and Current Transfers to the private sector (mostly family benefits and healthcare contributions by the elderly). Here, the universal pension considered is a permanent version of the temporary 2014 moratorium pension, described in Table 1.1.3 on page 66. Sources: for historical values, see Figure 1.1. Simulated values come from our microsimulations with late 2015 legislation and are listed in Appendix R. Non-simulated expenses and income are listed in Appendix T, directly expressed in GDP points and do not change from one economic scenario to the other. They are however subject to the legislative changes detailed in section 3.2.1. The starting dataset is the EPHc carried out during the fourth quarter of 2014.

on the chosen scenario, as long as we assume the Law 26970 pension moratorium ends in 2016. If we assume this program becomes permanent, then ANSES economic result plummets, reaching -4% of GDP in 2040 in our central scenario, and exhibits a strongly negative trend, significantly higher than those obtained with 2017 and 2018 legislation (depicted in Figures 3.7 and 3.9b). This result is expected, as not only are Law 26970 moratorium pension benefits indexed on wages, they also are equal to at least the minimum retirement pension five years after being granted, are available to women since age 60 and open rights to a survivor's pension to the beneficiary's family. Therefore, moratorium pensions are more expensive for the ANSES than the Universal Pension for the elderly PUAM, implemented in the two other legislative scenarios.

Public policy evaluation: social security sustainability by legislative scenario

We have so far in this section analysed the sustainability of Argentina's social security system across economic scenarios, but separately by legislation. We will in this last part carry out a quick comparison of social security's economic sustainability across legislative scenarios. Figure 3.11 below depicts ANSES economic result with December 2015, November 2017 and May 2018 legislation in our central economic scenario. We split the May 2018 scenario in two, with and without the "Check"³¹ tax suppression. Finally, in all but the December 2015 scenario, we show both ANSES *de jure* economic result and the actual social security deficit. In our December 2015 scenario, we treat as the *de jure* balance the one where we assume the Law 26970 pension moratorium ends in 2016. In the actual balance, we suppose this moratorium becomes permanent. This is because the total social security deficit in the 2017 and 2018 scenarios includes the cost of the Universal Pension for the Elderly (the PUAM), which allows for a universal access to a pension since age 65. It thus made sense to use as a point of comparison a scenario where the cost of universal pension coverage was taken on by the ANSES.

There are a number of lessons to be drawn from Figure 3.11. First, that Argentina's social security system would have been unsustainable across all legislative scenarios that included a universal pension coverage for the elderly. Second, that social security's deficit would have been the lowest had 2015 legislation been maintained, even if the 2014 Law 26970 moratorium pensions had become permanent. All the measures undertaken by the current administration have had a strongly negative short and long term impact on social security's overall sustainability. Of these, the historical reparation program (not taken into account in ANSES economic result) and the end of the deduction of 15% of *coparticipable* taxes in favour of ANSES were taken in reaction to Supreme Court rulings. All the other measures were undertaken by the sole initiative of the current government, and ended up manufacturing a short-term social security crisis. The only saving grace of these reforms is a more sustainable system in the very long run. Still, we expect the current legislation will result in a social security deficit of nearly -5.5% of GDP starting from 2020 and gradually worsen afterwards. The current legislation is thus unsustainable in the short run, so the very long-term benefits of the reforms undertaken by the current administration are somewhat hypothetical.

³¹Instituted in 2001 by Law 25413, the Tax on Credits and Debits on banks' Current Accounts is commonly known as the "Check" tax.

Figure 3.11: ANSES economic result by legislation in our central economic scenario (1993-2040, % of GDP)

Sources: see Figures 3.7 to 3.10. The 2016 historical reparation Law 27260 introduced a Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult (PUAM) funded by the federal budget. It also stops the deduction of 15% of all *coparticipable* taxes in favour of ANSES, but states the Treasury must step in and compensate these missing funds. These are not sustainable sources of funding, so we consider the case where ANSES has to pay for the PUAM and do without this fiscal source of funding.

As a conclusion, we can see the substantial 2016 (the historical reparation Law 27260) and 2017 (Laws 27426, 27430 and 27432) fiscal and pension reforms significantly worsened Argentina's social security economic sustainability, both in the short and the long term. The main problem with these measures is that they strongly decrease the funding of social security without replacing them with new sources of funding. Some of these policies do not actually worsen the total public economic result. This is the case of the reforms that stop the withholding of *coparticipable* taxes in favour of ANSES, and thus fully distributes between the state and the provinces instead. These are the 2016 historical reparation Law 27260, which states 15% of *coparticipable* funds will gradually stop funding ANSES, and the 2017 Law 27430, which ends the partial funding of ANSES through the Income Tax. On the other hand, tax reductions (the gradual suppression of the "Check"³² tax and the reduction of employers contributions established by Laws 27430 and 27432) and new unfunded benefits (the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult, but also the more generous access to contributive family benefits) both worsen the social security economic balance and widen the public deficit. This is shown by the fact ANSES "Bismarckian" deficit with 2018 legislation including the PUAM (depicted in Figure 3.6) is worse than the "Bismarckian" deficit with 2015 legislation including permanent pension moratoriums (see Figure 3.10), and by the significant increase in social security's deficit caused by the suppression of the "Check" tax as depicted in Figure 3.11.

So far, the only answer adopted by the current government to the issue of social security funding has been reducing pension spending. This has been done through the gradual replacement of moratorium pensions with the less generous (although unfunded) Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult (PUAM) and by adopting a less favourable pension mobility index in Law 27426. Both these measures improve social security's sustainability only on the very long term, failing to curb the short-term deficit. These have been recently joined by a toughening of income conditions to get access to a contributive child benefit starting on September 2018³³. This suggests the preferred tool to tackle this social security deficit will be cuts in spending. Before further speculating on the matter, we will complete our projection of Argentina's social security and public policy evaluation by studying future pension adequacy and redistribution by legislative scenario.

³²Instituted in 2001 by Law 25413, the Tax on Credits and Debits on banks' Current Accounts is commonly known as the "Check" tax.

³³Decree 702/2018, issued the 26th of July 2018, makes the maximum individual and family group income caps a function of the maximum income taken into account for the computation of social security contributions, as defined in Art. 9 of Law 24241. It effectively reduces the income cap for family benefits, restricting its access to formal wage-earners. Finally, this decree also eliminates the preferential family benefits schemes for the inhabitants of some remote provinces and localities. These changes will be effective starting from September 2018, and are thus not simulated in our model.

3.2.3 Social security benefits redistributive impact across legislative scenarios (2014-2040)

We have in section 3.2.2 carried out a macro-level evaluation of Argentina's social security system economic sustainability and found it is not sustainable even in the short term. Our choice of a dynamic microsimulation methodology implies that we derived this aggregate result from the simulation of a synthetic population over time. In our case, we projected the evolution of respondents of the fourth quarter of 2014 wave of the EPHc over the whole 2014-2040 period and extrapolated this dataset so as to be representative of Argentina's total population as far as social security is concerned (see section 3.2.1). In this work, it is the simulation of social security transfers and contributions at the individual level, to which are added total non-simulated expenses and revenue, that results in the system's aggregate sustainability. We can thus analyse these transfers at the micro level and give an evaluation of their future adequacy and redistributive impact that is linked to a given economic sustainability analysis, by economic and legislative scenario. It is important to do so because a public policy cannot only be evaluated by its total cost or its impact on the public deficit. Knowing whether these social security transfers are enough to ensure a decent revenue for vulnerable populations (the young and elderly) and how much they contribute to social justice by curbing income inequalities brought on by the labour market is an integral part of public policy evaluation. If adequacy is too low and the income distribution derived from these benefits too unjust, the system becomes politically unsustainable. In that case, the legislation is unlikely to be maintained unchanged in the long run even if it were economically sustainable. We thus review in sections 3.2.3 and 3.2.4 the expected evolution of social security benefits redistributive impact and adequacy with varying legislation.

First of all, the study of the redistributive impact of social security benefits is particularly important in a Latin American country such as Argentina where income inequality is particularly high following international standards. As we have mentioned in our general introduction, Argentina had a Gini index of 0.41 in 2014 according to the World Bank data bank, significantly higher than the 0.318 OECD average³⁴ for that year. It is thus important to monitor social security policies' impact on income inequality. Furthermore, social security represents an important source of income for the children and the elderly,

³⁴Source: OECD income distribution database. Link: <http://www.oecd.org/social/income-distribution-database.htm>.

which are often by definition excluded from the labour market. It is thus an important lever of intergenerational income distribution, so social security reforms may have strong redistributive impacts on total income distribution. Finally, Pay-As-You-Go pension systems may also be a means of intragenerational income distribution among the elderly, as pension differences do not fully reflect past labour income inequalities. Thus, projecting future inter and intra generational income inequality and assessing the impact of policies on these variables is important for the study of Argentina's social security system.

To measure the impact of social security transfers on income distribution, we selected five indicators. These are the Gini index, computed both at the household level and individually among the elderly, the income share of the 10% wealthiest and 10% poorest households, and the decile ratio³⁵. The Gini index sums up income inequality across the whole studied population, while the other three indexes put the focus on the wealthiest and poorest households. The combination of these five indexes gives an accurate enough representation of income inequality in our simulated dataset.

They are however subjected to a number of methodological challenges, which we describe in Appendix V. To summarise, social security transfers cannot be studied separately from the total disposable income of a household, so there is the question of how to combine them with individuals and households' other sources of revenue. Then, there is the problem on how to treat households that are simulated without any revenue, a possibility that is not ruled out by our model. This makes households with no reported sources of revenue abruptly increase from the measured 3% in the fourth quarter of 2014 EPHc survey to 16% the following quarter, as shown by Figure 3.12 below. The question of how to handle these missing values in our microsimulated datasets is thus crucial. Finally, individuals live in households and usually share their income with other dwellers. Thus, the person's disposable revenue depends on the total earnings of the household but also on eventual economies of scale in consumption (heating, electricity, rent...) and on the consumption needs of the other dwellers, which may be lower for young children. There is an ongoing debate in the literature on how to best compute this household's equalised income, or the disposable income of each dweller. We handle these methodological difficulties in Appendix V. We explain there that we adopt a combination of labour income, retirement and survivor's benefits and family allowances to measure income inequality. Also, following CEDLAS and The World Bank (2014) we exclude from the computation of inequality statistics households with no declared income. Finally, we adopt the definition

³⁵The decile ratio is the quotient of the lowest income needed to be part of the wealthiest 10% divided by the maximum income among the poorest 10%.

of a household’s equivalised income proposed by CEDLAS and The World Bank (2014). For reference, income inequality statistics with alternative methodologies for computing an individual’s disposable income are available in Appendix W.

Figure 3.12: Percentage of households with no source of revenue (2014-2040).

The fourth quarter of 2014 value is measured in the EPHc survey, and corresponds to households with no labour, pension or family benefits revenue (variables P21, TOT_P12, V2_M and V5_M of the survey).

Lastly, we present in this section income distribution statistics computed in the central economic scenario only. This is first due to the large number of descriptive statistics we employ to measure social security benefits’ redistributive impact. Taking into account both economic and legislative scenarios would have thus excessively lengthened our analysis. Most importantly though, our simulations result in a difficult to explain decrease of labour income inequality towards the end of our simulated period, as we will see later in this section. We believe this is an undesired artefact of our simulations and not the reflection of an actual economic phenomenon. Therefore, it is more the evolution of these statistics than their actual value that is relevant for our analysis. Hence, it is more interesting to see how they differ from one legislative scenario to the other than between economic evolutions. In any case, the changes in social security benefits adequacy and redistributive impact across economic scenarios are reviewed in Appendix W.

In this section, we will first of all justify why we refrained from simulating the historical reparation program instituted by the 2016 Law 27260 even though it probably has

a relevant impact on income distribution. After that, we will analyse the redistributive impact of social security on household income across the legislative scenarios we defined in section 3.2.1. Finally, we will study more specifically the evolution of inequalities among the elderly across legislative scenarios.

The historical reparation program: a limit to our analysis of social security transfers adequacy and redistributive impact

Before moving on to our income inequality and pension adequacy analysis, we remind the reader we do not include in our microsimulation model the 2016 Law 27260 historical reparation program. This consisted in a compensation plan for pensioners that had been wronged between the end of pension indexation on inflation with the 1991 convertibility law and the implementation of the pension mobility law 26970 on March 2009. Subscription is voluntary, since it requires the subscriber to drop any pending lawsuits against the ANSES. Further details can be found in section 1.1.2. This program affects ANSES benefits adequacy and redistributive impact because it raises the benefits of some generations of pensioners that retired normally with Law 24241. This results in increased inequalities between the elderly, better pension adequacy and an unclear effect on total household income inequality. The impact of this program in the short term is likely to be significant, as the ANSES informs that "there is a total of 1.333.868 retirement and survivor's pensions beneficiaries that get benefits 35% higher thanks to the Historical Reparation"³⁶ the 15th of August 2018, which represents 23% of March 2018 retirement and survivor's pensions beneficiaries (Aisenberg *et al.*, 2018). Access to the program closes the 31st of August 2018, so the importance of the program will only decrease in the future.

As explained in section 3.2.1 and Appendix U, we did not simulate the historical reparation in our microsimulation model for two reasons. First, because we have been able to estimate the past and future cost of this program without using a dynamic microsimulation methodology in Appendices A and U. It is thus not necessary to simulate it at the micro level for studying ANSES economic sustainability. Second, because it is difficult to precisely identify pensioners who have the right to subscribe to this program, following the conditions laid out in section 1.1.2. We can add a last point: to accurately simulate enrolment in the historical reparation program, we have to take into account subscribing to this plan requires dropping all lawsuits against the ANSES. We would thus need to also simulate at the individual level pension litigation (so far, we include it as a non-simulated

³⁶Source: ANSES official news site, accessed the 17th of August 2018 in <http://noticias.anses.gob.ar/noticia/repuracion-historica-hay-tiempo-hasta-el-de-agosto-para-completar-el-tramite-2896>

expense in section 3.2.1) to identify potential beneficiaries that refuse to drop their lawsuit. Also, a microsimulation of pension litigation would allow to meaningfully compare today's legislation including the historical reparation with 2015 counter-factual scenarios, where pensioners that had seen their pensions or initial benefit wrongly paid could only bring their case to court to eventually get a higher benefit. This point is thus left to future work.

ANSES benefits impact on household income distribution with 2018 legislation

Now that we have reviewed the methodological issues behind the computation of income distribution statistics, we present in this subsection the resulting income inequality indicators by legislative scenario, while applying our central economic hypothesis. First of all, we study the evolution over the 2014-2040 period of our four household income inequality indicators: the Gini index, the decile ratio and the shares of total income in the hands of the bottom and top 10% households ranked by income per consumption unit. These indicators are computed using SEDLAC's methodology as far as the handling of households with no revenue and the computation of equivalised income are concerned. We also compute each indicator before and after social security transfers, so as to get an illustration of their redistributive power. Finally, we depict the evolution of their levels with 2018 legislation in Figure 3.13 before studying their difference across legislative scenarios in Figures 3.14 and 3.15.

We start by showing the measured income inequality variables for the fourth quarter of 2014 are close to those measured by the SEDLAC (CEDLAS and The World Bank, 2014) in the EPHc waves of the second quarter of 2014 and first quarter of 2015³⁷. In all cases, we compare the statistics with equivalised household income. First, the Gini we measure equals 0.386, while the SEDLAC measures for the second quarter of 2014 and the first quarter of the 2015 a Gini of respectively 0.383 and 0.375. Second, although we do not use the exact same methodology than the SEDLAC for computing the decile ratio³⁸, we measure a decile ratio of 6.5, while SEDLAC reports ratios of 6.4 and 6.2 for the aforementioned periods. The only significant difference arises when comparing the income shares of the top 10% and bottom 10%. Indeed, the SEDLAC reports a share of equivalised income for the bottom 10% households of 1.9%, and for the top 10% of 29.5%

³⁷The SEDLAC dataset only studies income distribution in Argentina during the first semester of each year. The May 2018 version of the dataset can be found in the following link, accessed the 8th of August 2018: <http://www.cedlas.econo.unlp.edu.ar/wp/en/estadisticas/sedlac/estadisticas/#1496165297107-cedda6d3-6c7d>.

³⁸CEDLAS and The World Bank (2014) divide the mean income of the richest decile by that of the poorest 10%. We on the other hand divide the minimum income among the richest 10% by the maximum revenue of the poorest decile

and 28.9%. We on the other hand measure for the fourth quarter of 2014 income shares of the top and bottom deciles equal to 21% and 3% of all income. This discrepancy may come from the fact we do not consider in our analysis non-labour and non social security revenue, such as capital income. Finally, our simulated household inequality statistics for the first periods of our simulation are very close to those initial values, which shows our model is capable of reproducing the dataset's income inequality values, as will be shown below.

Figure 3.13 depicts this evolution for our central economic scenario. Figures with varying disposable income definitions and economic scenarios are listed in Appendix W and broadly follow the same trends. This said, the low and high economic scenarios end up with respectively lower and higher levels of measured income inequality. Meanwhile, different computation methods of disposable income mostly change the Gini index level, without modifying its evolution over the 2014-2040 period. Keeping *per capita* income increases the Gini by roughly 2 percentage points, while adopting INSEE's methodology for Consumption Units decreases it by 2 percentage points. This is because SEDLAC's calibration assigns an intermediate weight to the children of a household (0.5 to those aged under 6, and 0.75 for ages 6 to 14). The *per capita* method gives them a weight of 1, while INSEE's methodology assigns them a weight of 0.3, instead of 1 for the first adult and 0.5 for each additional dweller aged 14 or more. Hence, households with children are moderately penalised with SEDLAC's methodology, resulting in an intermediate level of income inequality.

Figure 3.13 shows various interesting evolutions of Argentina's income inequality, and a varying role of social security transfers. First of all, the evolution of income inequality throughout the period is roughly divided in two periods. Up until 2030, earnings distribution slowly becomes more equal according to all four indicators, without witnessing major changes in levels. By the end of that period, most of the redistributive impact comes from taking into account pension income, as family benefits' importance gradually fades away. The latter remain however relevant regarding the top and bottom 10% income shares. They strongly increase the revenue of the poorest households, while they slightly decrease the top 10% share. This means the poorest households have on average more dependent children than the wealthier ones. After 2030 however, the Gini index and decile ratio both plummet, and pension income stops playing a meaningful redistribution role for these statistics. Meanwhile, the top 10% income share tends to overall increase, while the bottom 10% share gradually returns to the values it had at the beginning of the simulation. Finally, it is pension income that starts playing a significant redistributive

Figure 3.13: Equivalised household income inequality measures by income definition, with 2018 legislation (2014-2040)

Households with no income are excluded from this analysis. The 2014 value is computed on the starting dataset, the fourth quarter of 2014 EPHc survey. The decile ratio is equal to the minimum *per capita* income a household must have to be part of the 10% wealthiest households divided by the maximum *per capita* income a household may have while still being part of the 10% poorest households. When computing the decile ratio, we re-define deciles when we change the income type. For the share of the top and bottom 10% in the total of a given income type however, the determination of the wealthiest and poorest households is always done with respect to total income (labour, pension and family benefits). Household income is equivalised following OECDLAS and The World Bank (2014), who adopted the calibration established by Deaton & Zaidi (2002).

role in what concerns the top and bottom 10% households, which shows by the end of the period the poorest (resp. richest) households include more (resp. less) often retirement pensioners.

We can see in Figure 3.13 the changes in income distribution are mostly driven by labour earnings. Not only because the main source of revenue for the simulated households usually comes from the labour market, but also because it is when inequality is measured on labour income only that it is the most volatile throughout the 2014-2040 period. Part of these changes in labour income distribution may be a logical consequence of our model's labour-market module design. First, since in our central economic scenario we assume a steady increase of real wages (as depicted in Figure 3.1) while the proportion of workers only slightly increases (as shown in Table 3.6 and Figure 2.5), it is logical that the share of total income at the hands of the top and bottom 10% households respectively increase and decrease by the end of the simulation. A stagnant proportion of households made up of skilled workers get an increasing labour revenue, while a stable ratio of households with informal workers and dependent dwellers fall further behind in income distribution. Second, as shown by Figure 2.5 the proportion of formal wage-earners gradually increases in our central labour-market scenario, mainly among women and at the expense of informal labour, inactivity and unemployment. Therefore, there are more workers and among these fewer of these are informal. We have moreover seen in our behavioural equations in Appendix L there is a significant income penalty associated with informal labour. Since the formality of workers strays further away from a 50 / 50 split that would maximise income inequality, this is a mechanism that tends to decrease labour income inequality. Finally, the Law 27426 pension mobility index in force since March 2018 gradually reduces the relevance of family benefits and pension income earned by moratorium pensioners or beneficiaries of the universal pension for the elderly adult PUAM, who benefit from insufficient adjustments with regards to real wage evolutions. This also increases inequalities among pensioners, as individuals who contributed the required 30 years to get a contributive pension see their pensions follow better formal wages. These two last points will be evidenced in our pension adequacy analysis in section 3.2.4, and depicted by Figure 3.17c. It is thus normal the redistributive impact of social security transfers strongly decreases towards the end of the simulation.

However, the strong decrease in the Gini index and decile ratios, particularly after 2030, is most likely an artefact resulting both from the design of our dynamic microsimulation model and our treatment of households with missing income. First, the share of households simulated with no income is always higher than 15%, while it is only of

3% in our initial dataset as shown in Figure 3.12. This is because our model does not prevent the formation of households where nobody has a source of income. This excludes a significant proportion of inactive and unemployed individuals from the income distribution analysis. Households who tend to have less dwellers with no income are compared between each other, mechanically reducing measured income inequality without reflecting an actual economic phenomenon. The inactive or unemployed family members, instead of weighing on the disposable income of workers and being thus measured in the inequality indicators, are simply left out of the analysis when no worker or pensioner dwells in their household. Since it would not make many sense either to keep in the analysis households simulated with no income, the solution would be to rework the labour-market and family modules of our microsimulation model to limit the creation of households with no sources of income. Still, this only poses a significant problem to our inequality analysis, without substantially affecting the simulation of Argentina's social security's economic sustainability and adequacy. Hence, this point is left for future work. The main problem with this explanation is it does not however explain why labour income inequality only falls towards the end of our simulation, even though the share of households with no income is stable throughout the 2015-2040 period.

Second, when a worker is surveyed in our initial dataset its individual error term related to the Mincer wage equation estimation of labour income is kept in memory by our model and applied throughout its future career, even through temporary inactivity or unemployment spells. As explained in section 2.3.3, this error term captures the portion of the respondent's labour income that cannot be explained by the Mincer wage equation. However, when in our simulations an individual who was not working in the initial dataset enters a labour spell, our model assigns him or her a null individual error term. This mechanically reduces labour income variability. As our simulation stretches further in time, an increasing proportion of workers have a null individual error term, and therefore end up having less unequal labour income. This phenomenon is mostly driven by the ageing of the generations that were working in 2014 and their replacement by cohorts that were younger or not yet born at the time. A solution to this problem would be to assign a random error term to each individual who was not originally surveyed as earning a labour income when he or she works for the first time. The choice of the statistical law behind this random term and its calibration is however far from being trivial, and thus left for future work.

All the above elements make studying the evolution of inequality in our simulations through their levels dubious. Therefore, it is more interesting to study the impact of

pension reforms on the above measures of income distribution, as is done below.

ANSES benefits impact on household income distribution across counter-factual legislative scenarios

For studying the impact of legislation on income distribution, we use the three counter-factual legislative scenarios we used in our study of prospective social security sustainability and defined in section 3.2.1. First, the 2017 legislation scenario takes all rules in force at the eve of the December 2017 pension reforms. Second, the 2015 legislation with pension moratoriums goes mostly back to the rules in force in December 2015, before the current administration's reforms, but supposes the 2014 Law 26970 pension moratoriums becomes permanent. And third, the 2015 legislation without pension moratoriums assumes the latter ended in September 2016 as originally scheduled by Law 26970. The third legislative scenario is mostly depicted in these figures for reference. As we explained earlier in this section, our inequality measures computed at the household level take out of the analysis households with no revenue. Therefore, the negative redistributive impact of the fact some of the elderly get no benefit at all is not properly depicted by inequality statistics computed at the household level. This third legislative scenario will be far more useful in our study of the individual Gini index computed among the elderly, depicted in Figure 3.16 further down this section, since individuals with null income are computed in this statistic.

Our graphical comparison of the impact of legislation on income inequality is done as follows. First, we drew figures analogous to those of Figure 3.13 with varying legislation and put them for reference in Appendix W. Then, to more explicitly gauge the impact of these reforms on income distribution, we depicted for each inequality indicator the difference between its value with 2018 legislation and with our three alternative legislative scenarios. For instance, we subtract in Figure 3.14b the Gini index computed on all income with SEDLAC's methodology and 2018 legislation to the same index computed with alternative legislative scenarios. Thus, variations of labour income inequality caused by imperfections of the model are eliminated from this measurement, provided these errors are unaffected by the chosen legislative scenario. The resulting difference between inequality indexes measured across varying legislative scenarios is consigned in Figure 3.14 for the Gini index and decile ratio, and Figure 3.15 for the share of the top and bottom deciles. Both figures are computed before and after social security transfers. For the sake of exhaustiveness, Appendix W includes similar figures computed on labour income and family benefits, and labour income and pension revenue. The same Appendix makes

the comparison with varying definitions of disposable income (*per capita* or equivalised following INSEE's methodology) and economic scenarios.

Figures 3.14 and 3.15 show the successive reforms adopted by the current administration significantly undermined the redistributive impact of social security transfers. First of all, Figure 3.14a shows there are no significant differences in labour income distribution from one legislative scenario to the other, when measured with the Gini index. However, factoring in social security transfers shows income inequality would have been significantly lower with 2015 legislation including permanent pension moratoriums as shown by Figure 3.14b. By 2040, the Gini index would have been nearly 1.5 percentage points lower with this counter-factual scenario.

Secondly, income inequality barely changes between 2018 and 2017 legislation. This suggests the less generous pension mobility index Law 27426 in force since March 2018 does not play that much of a role on overall income inequality. In theory, the introduction through Art. 5 of Law 27426 of a guarantee for people with 30 years of contributions to earn at least 82% of the minimum wage (see 1.1.3) should increase inequality between contributive and non-contributive pensioners. There is however an ongoing sharp fall of the real minimum wage in 2018. Assuming 30% of inflation for year 2018 and given the already defined levels of the nominal minimum wage for the rest of the year, our simulations expect a fall of the real minimum wage of 18% between the fourth quarters of 2016 and 2018. This causes the minimum pension to always be higher than 82% of the minimum wage up until 2040 in all our economic scenarios, so this guarantee never comes into play. It could be argued the real legal minimum wage is likely to compensate this loss in the middle run and increase faster than all real wages at least temporarily. This would likely lead to a situation where contributory pensioners effectively benefit from this guarantee and see their pensions increase on par with wages. This point is left for future work.

Thirdly, comparing the decile ratio as well as the top and bottom 10% income shares across scenarios is also telling of the increase in inequalities caused by the current administration's reforms. Before making our comparison, it is worth reminding the reader the top and bottom income deciles correspond to the households with the most (resp. least) equivalised labour, pension and family benefits income. We do not re-rank households when we study the top and bottom 10% share on a different income type, such as labour income without social security transfers. For instance, Figure 3.13c shows in 2039 the 10% richest households, all income types considered, captured 24% of all income and of all labour and pension income, but more than 26% of labour income and of all labour

Figure 3.14: Comparing inequality indicators with varying legislative scenarios before and after social security transfers: the Gini index and decile ratio (2014-2040)

(a) Gini index, labour income

(b) Gini index, all income

(c) Decile ratio, labour income

(d) Decile ratio, all income

See Figure 3.13 for details on the computation of inequality indexes. Reading example: when computed on all income, the Gini index with 2018 legislation was greater by 2.5 percentage points than the Gini index computed with 2015 legislation and permanent moratoriums in 2039. The linear trend shows, by the end of the simulation, the Gini index with 2018 legislation is greater than the Gini index computed with 2015 legislation and permanent moratoriums by on average 1.5 percentage points.

Figure 3.15: Comparing inequality indicators with varying legislative scenarios before and after social security transfers: the top and bottom 10% income shares (2014-2040)

(a) Top 10%, labour income share

(b) Top 10%, all income share

(c) Bottom 10%, labour income share

(d) Bottom 10%, all income share

See Figure 3.13 for details on the computation of inequality indexes. Reading example: in 2040, the bottom 10% share of all income with 2018 legislation is lower by 2.5 percentage points than its estimated share with the counter-factual scenario with 2015 legislation and permanent moratoriums. The linear trend shows by the end of the simulation, the bottom 10% share of all income would have been greater with 2015 legislation including pension moratoriums by on average 2 percentage points, when compared to its share with 2018 legislation.

and family benefits revenue. This means the 10% richest households capture a higher percentage of labour income, but a lower proportion of pension benefits. This indicates its members live on average more off labour than pension income. However, we have to redefine the top and bottom deciles when we compute the decile ratio with different income types. If not, we would risk having the maximum income among the lowest decile be equal or close to 0, which would greatly skew the level of our decile ratio.

This said, we can see the reforms undertaken since December 2015 strongly increase (resp. decrease) the labour income share of the top (resp. bottom) 10%. First of all, the distance between these two deciles as measured by the decile ratio slightly increases. As can be seen in Figure 3.14d, by the end of our simulations the decile ratio with 2018 legislation is higher by 0.5 points than with our counter-factual scenario with 2015 rules and permanent pension moratoriums. The negative impact of these reforms on income distribution is however far more telling in Figure 3.15, where are depicted the evolutions across legislative scenarios of the top and bottom 10% income shares. First, Figure 3.15a shows the share of labour income at the hands of the richest decile is higher on average by more than 5 percentage points with 2018 than with 2017 legislation by the end of our simulation. This means the 2018 legislation made it more difficult for households getting social security transfers to make it to the top of the income distribution. Second, we can see in Figure 3.15c that the bottom 10%'s share of labour income is lower by roughly 3 percentage points with 2018 instead of 2017 legislation by the end of the simulation. Thus, the 2018 reform pushed to the bottom of the income distribution households whose revenue come to a large extent from social security transfers. The fact most of the difference is between the 2018 and 2017 scenarios means it is primarily the change in the pension mobility formula through the 2017 Law 27426 that degraded the position in the income scale of households receiving social security transfers.

When pensions and family benefits are factored in the analysis (Figures 3.15b and 3.15d) the differences of top and bottom 10% shares from one legislative scenario to the other are more modest. Nevertheless, these figures show 2018 legislation results in a higher concentration of income in the hands of the richest decile, and in a lower share of total income for the poorest decile. By the end of our simulation, the total revenue of the richest decile would be nearly 1.5 percentage points lower with 2015 legislation (with or without pension moratoriums) than with the current laws. Most of the impact seems to come from the change in the pension mobility law through 2017 Law 27426, as shown by the important difference between 2017 and 2018 legislation and the fact pension moratoriums do not seem to affect the top 10%'s income share. Moreover, the poorest

decile's share would be respectively 2 and 1.5 percentage points higher with 2015 legislation with permanent moratoriums and 2017 rules. In this case, it is both the replacement of pension moratoriums by the PUAM and the unfavourable pension mobility Law 27426 that negatively impacts the bottom 10%'s income share. This is shown by the fact 2015 legislation without moratoriums results in a similar income share for the poorest households (excluding households with no income) than 2018 legislation.

All in all, we have shown both the 2016 historical reparation Law 27260 and the late 2017 reforms have worsened income distribution both on the whole population (as measured by the Gini index) and on the top and bottom of the income scale. These reforms reduce the redistributive impact of social security benefits and worsen in the long term the income distribution of an already significantly unequal Argentinian society. We cannot however settle this issue with inequality statistics computed on household income only. Indeed, as we have explained earlier these are unable to factor in households that are simulated as having no sources of income. Also, they miss the strongly negative redistributive impact of our 2015 legislation scenario with no permanent pension moratoriums, where households made up of elders with no pension income are excluded from the redistribution analysis. We thus finish our study of the 2016 and 2017 reforms redistributive impact with a comparison of the individual Gini index computed among the elderly with varying legislative scenarios.

The impact of social security reforms on income distribution among the elderly

Figure 3.16 below studies the impact of legislation changes on the Gini index computed at the individual level among various universes of the elderly. First, it depicts its evolution with 2018 legislation including (Figure 3.16a) and excluding (Figure 3.16b) individuals with none of the studied income. Then, it shows the differences of this index when computed in our three counter-factual legislative scenarios, defined in section 3.2.1. All these computations are done with our central economic scenario, but the results barely change when the statistic is recomputed with our low and high economic scenarios. For the sake of completeness, graphs equivalent to those of Figure 3.16 but taken from our optimistic and pessimistic simulations are consigned and analysed in Appendix W.

Figure 3.16 shows our projections result in increasing inequality among the elderly over time with 2018 legislation, for all kinds of income and including or excluding individuals with no income (Figures 3.16a and 3.16b). First, we see the rise in individual Gini indexes begins with the implementation in late 2016 of the historical reparation law

Figure 3.16: Individual Gini indexes for the elderly (2014-2040). Level with 2018 legislation and comparison with other scenarios.

(a) 2018 legislation, all seniors

(b) 2018 legislation, seniors with income

(c) Comparing legislations, all seniors

(d) Comparing legislations, seniors with income

Reading example, Figure 3.16c: in 2040, the individual Gini index computed on all types of income among all people of retirement age is 13.5 percentage points greater with 2018 legislation than with 2015 legislation including pension moratoriums.

27260. This trend is temporarily offset between 2020 and 2023 by the automatic increase of moratorium pensions granted between 2014 and 2019, who go up from 80% to 100% of the minimum pension after five years (as explained in Table 1.1.3 of section 1.1.3). After that, the individual Gini for the elderly linearly increases for all ages, but faster when we include in the analysis women aged 60 to 64³⁹. Also, non-labour income plays a decreasing role over time in reducing income inequality, to the point where the individual Gini is even slightly higher when computed on non-labour income as compared to all income when we study all people of retirement age (see Figure 3.16a). This means pension income loses its redistributive power for people of retirement age with 2018 legislation.

These elements suggest the main driver of the increase in inequalities among the elderly is the gradual replacement of the 2014 Law 26970 pension moratoriums with the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult PUAM. To begin with, the lower level of the PUAM (permanently equal to 80% of the minimum pension) when compared to Law 26970 pension moratoriums increases inequality among the elderly. This is shown by the gradual increase of the Gini when computed among people aged 65 or more, both including (Figure 3.16a) and excluding (Figure 3.16b) seniors with no revenue. However, most of the impact comes from the fact the PUAM is only available since age 65, while Law 26970 moratorium pensions are accessible to women aged 60. It is thus women under 65 who get cut off from a non contributive benefit that increase the most income inequality among the elderly. Proof of that is that all inequality measures are substantially higher when the studied elderly are of retirement age, and the only difference with the universe of people aged 65 or more are women aged 60 to 64. Also, differences between individual Gini for the elderly including (Figure 3.16a) and excluding (Figure 3.16b) people with no income are the highest when we include women aged 60 to 64 in the analysis. This confirms most seniors with no pension income in our prospective simulations will be women under 65. Also, they increase the Gini index by roughly 5 percentage points by 2040, as can be seen by comparing the continuous red lines of Figures 3.16a and 3.16b.

When we extend our study to take into account counter-factual legislation scenarios in Figures 3.16c and 3.16d, we find the main driver of income distribution among the elderly is non-contributive retirement benefits (be them pension moratoriums or the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult PUAM). First of all, because the late 2017 reforms do not seem to have a significant impact on income distribution among the elderly, no matter the studied age interval (retirement age or 65+), the type of income or if we kept in

³⁹The retirement age in Argentina is 60 for women and 65 for men. Thus, the only difference between the universe of people of retirement age and that of people aged 65 or more is women aged 60 to 64.

the analysis individuals with none of the studied income (either social security transfers or any kind of earnings). This means the fact initial contributory retirement benefits are computed on the last ten years of wage and thus follow more or less wage evolutions, while benefits computed on the minimum benefit increase slower than wages due to the pension mobility Law 27426 does not significantly increase inequalities among seniors.

Second, because the biggest differences arise when we compare 2018 legislation with the two counter-factual scenarios based on 2015 legislation, which either keep a permanent law 2014 moratorium pension or include no non-contributive benefit for the elderly. With the former counter-factual scenario, inequality among people of retirement age would be much lower, keeping indexes close to their starting 2015 values throughout the simulation. By 2040, the Gini indexes respectively computed on all income and on non-labour income only would have been lower by 11.2 and 13.6 percentage points with 2015 legislation including pension moratoriums for people of retirement age, and of 6.6 percentage points for those aged 65 or more as depicted by Figure 3.16c. The increase in inequality among the elderly also comes from the reduced level of the PUAM when compared to Law 26970 moratorium pensions, as explained in section 1.1.2. This is evidenced by Figure 3.16d, as the Gini computed among the elderly with income (or non-labour income) is greater with 2018 legislation by only 6 percentage points when compared to 2015 rules with permanent moratoriums. In any case, this comparison across legislations shows barring access to non-contributive pensions to women aged 60 to 64 and lowering their level will strongly increase income inequality among the elderly.

On the other hand, income inequality among the elderly would have been far worse with a 2015 legislation scenario without permanent pension moratoriums. As can be seen in Figure 3.16c, the Gini index would have been 25 percentage points higher when computed among people aged 65 and more on non-labour income only, and by 22 points if all income types were considered in the analysis. Granted, our model only allows for labour-market participation up until age 69 and it is unrealistic to assume people aged 70 or more could live with absolutely no individual revenue. This statistic however underlines the importance of keeping a non-contributive pension for the elderly to ensure pensions are at least to some extent equitable, and not a factor that aggravates income inequality among the elderly.

In the end, we have shown through our counter-factual legislative analysis the reforms undertaken so far by the current administration will worsen the income distribution of the Argentinian economy. This result holds if we consider the whole population or focus

on the elderly, with varying income definitions, methodology, economic scenarios and inequality statistics. So far, we have thus shown the 2016 and 2017 pension reforms have worsened both social security's economic sustainability, as seen in Figure 3.11 of section 3.2.2, and the redistributive impact of social security benefits. In the last section of this thesis, we will see that these reforms also significantly reduced the adequacy of social security transfers.

3.2.4 Social security benefits adequacy across legislative scenarios (2014-2040)

Finally, we give a quick estimation of the evolution of social security benefits adequacy across legislative scenarios. As we explained in our general introduction, benefits are adequate when they provide for the beneficiaries' basic needs and when they cover a high percentage of the dependent population. A Bismarckian approach also looks at the proportion of the last earned wages they replace. In the case of Argentina, a direct study of social security adequacy is complicated. First, there is not an official long-term poverty line that would help gauge the actual adequacy of social security benefits, and see how well they provide for the needs of the beneficiaries. Secondly, the existence of widespread non-contributive retirement pensions such as moratorium benefits and the PUAM introduces strong differences in the replacement ratios of the elderly. People with short, mostly informal, careers get a significantly high replacement of their past income with the minimum benefit, and this statistic cannot be computed for people that never worked. Still, it is possible to grasp the evolutions of social security benefits adequacy over time and across legislations, more so than their actual levels. To this end, we kept a range of indicators that measure the mean real level of various social security benefits, access to a pension for the elderly (65+) and to a child benefit for minors (17 or less). First, we follow their evolutions over the 2014-2040 to study the evolution of social security transfers adequacy with the current 2018 legislation. Then, to evaluate the impact of the 2016 and 2017 reforms on the adequacy of social security benefits, we compare these results with those of our counter-factual legislative scenarios.

The evolution of social security benefits adequacy with 2018 legislation (2014-2040)

First of all, we computed various indicators depicting numerous aspects of social security transfers adequacy with our central economic scenario and 2018 legislation. These are

depicted in Figure 3.17 below, but analogous figures with our optimistic and pessimistic economic variants can be found in Appendix W.

First of all, we find in Figure 3.17a access to a retirement pension for people of retiring age will gradually decrease from a simulated 100%⁴⁰ in 2015 to 83% in 2040. This drop in coverage is due to the end of the 2014 pension moratorium in September 2016 for men and July 2019 for women (as seen in Table 1.1.3 of section 1.1). The replacement benefit, the PUAM, is only accessible for people aged 65 or more. For all women with incomplete careers, this *de facto* pushes back their retirement age to 65. This causes a drop in pension coverage for women aged 60 to 64.

The proportion of seniors receiving a given pension benefit also changes following the introduction of the PUAM. First, the non-renewal of the 2014 Law 26970 pension moratorium gradually reduces the proportion of people of retiring age earning a 2014 moratorium pension from 19% in 2015 to 9% in 2040. Second, the share of pensioners earning either a 2006 moratorium pension or a normal Law 24241 retirement benefit falls from 80% in 2015 to 31% in 2040. We have to lump together these two categories of pensioners because it is not possible to tell them apart in the fourth quarter of 2014 EPHc survey. This is because by that date all 2006 moratorium pensioners earn at least the minimum pension, as explained in Table 1.1.3 of section 1.1, and there is no other variable that would allow us to tell them apart. Therefore, this fall is first and foremost caused by the death of 2006 moratorium pensioners. It can however be reasonably assumed by the end of the simulation there is a negligible number of 2006 moratorium pensioners. As we saw in Table 1.1.3, it was only possible to subscribe to this benefit during years 2006 and 2007, so the youngest beneficiaries, women aged 60 in 2007, will be 93 by 2040. This means at the end of our simulations only 31% of people of retirement age will have retired normally. In the end, the current legislation will ensure a high universal access to a pension through the PUAM, which will reach 41% of people of retirement age by 2040. The majority of retirees will thus earn 80% of the legal pension minimum and will not leave a survivors' benefit to their spouse. They will also have to wait until age 65 to retire.

⁴⁰In our model, all individuals claim a retirement benefit or the pension for the elderly adult (PUAM) as soon as they have the right to do so. This means at the start of our simulation, when the Law 26970 moratorium was in force, the coverage is almost equal to 100% even after taking into account the existing household income restrictions to get access to this 2014 pension moratorium. We had seen in Figure 1.3 of section 1.1 that 90% of people of retiring age had access to a retirement pension granted by the ANSES in 2015. Since this figure does not include retirees of other pension schemes (some provincial civil servants, military and police personnel), there probably was a high full access to a retirement benefit at that time.

Figure 3.17: The evolution of pension adequacy: coverage and pension level (2014-2040)

(a) Retirement pension coverage (% of people of retiring age)

(b) Child benefits coverage (% of minor children)

The retirement age in Argentina is 60 for women and 65 for men. Mean values are in November 2014 pesos. Between November 2014 and March 2016, we use a simple average of the Consumer Price Indexes (CPI) of the province of San Luis and the Autonomous City of Buenos Aires (CABA). Between April 2016 and May 2018, we use INDEC's national CPI. After May 2018, we keep a monthly annualised inflation of 30%. This (underestimated, due to the ongoing 2018 currency crisis) inflation level is only useful for computing real family benefits and retirement pension evolution for 2018. Labour income is computed across formal and informal workers, be they wage-earners or independent, net of social security contributions.

(c) Mean retirement benefits

(d) Mean child benefits

Reading examples: Figure 3.17a shows that in 2040, 31% of people of retirement age will earn a contributory retirement benefit or a pension derived from the 2006 moratorium; 9% a 2014 moratorium pension; 41% the Universal Pension PUAM; 3% only a survivor's benefit; and 17% will not receive any retirement or survivor's pension. Figure 3.17b shows in 2040 55% of children aged 17 or less will earn a contributory child benefit; 16% the Universal Child Benefit AUH; and the remaining 29% will not receive a family benefit. Figure 3.17c shows in 2040 the median retirement benefit will be equal to 46% of the median labour income. In Figure 3.17d, our simulations show that by 2040 the mean universal child benefit AUH will be equal to 676 constant November 2014 pesos, while mean and contributive child benefits will respectively equal 436 and 372 constant pesos.

Another downside of this increasing reliance on the PUAM to ensure universal access to a pension is the future expected surge of inequalities between pensioners. We have already shown in section 3.2.3 the individual Gini for the elderly depicted in Figure 3.16 mostly increases with 2018 legislation due to the replacement of pension moratoriums with the PUAM. Figure 3.17c also shows the Law 27426 pension mobility formula strongly limits the real increase of both moratorium pensions and the PUAM, even as real labour income increases by 18% between the second quarter of 2018 and the end of 2040 in our central economic scenario. An exception is the expected raise of moratorium pensions between the fourth quarter of 2019 and 2024, when the five-year penalty on pension levels for Law 26970 moratorium pensioners will start to be lifted. These pensioners will begin to earn the full minimum pension, instead of the previous 80% reduced rate as explained in Table 1.1.3 of section 1.1.3. The legal minimum pension from which are computed both moratorium pensions and the PUAM will more or less stay at its real 2018 level, so in the end non-contributive pensions will practically be frozen in the long run.

On the other hand, contributory retirement benefits will increase faster than non-contributive pensions, even though they are subjected to the same pension mobility formula. A first reason is that in our starting dataset we cannot distinguish contributory retirement benefits from 2006 moratoriums who generally receive the minimum pension (see Table 1.1.3 on page 66) as we explained earlier. Thus, in the first periods of our simulation these moratorium pensioners push down the mean pension value. As the simulation goes further in time they however lose their relevance, and the mean pension mechanically increases since it represents more and more exclusively contributory pensioners. However, if this was the only element in play the mean pension increase should slow down over time as 2006 moratorium pensioners die. Figure 3.17c shows this is not the case and that there must be other factors in play behind this increase of the real contributive pension benefit. We have already shown in section 3.2.3 the guarantee instituted by Art. 5 of Law 27426 that contributive pensions will be equal to at least 82% of the legal minimum wage does not come into play in our simulations due to the real fall of the minimum wage in 2018. Therefore, the only remaining explanation is that future initial benefits will be computed on higher formal wages, and will thus broadly follow the latter's evolution. This will make contributory retirement beneficiaries earn a pension that, by 2040, will be almost three times higher in real terms than the universal pension granted in the PUAM. This explains why by the end of the simulated period retirement pension revenue stops having a redistributive impact and even increases income inequality, as we have seen in Figure 3.13.

There is a last point that needs to be taken into consideration when studying the

adequacy of pension benefits, which is retirees do not actually consume the goods and services basket used to compute the CPI. Instead, a high proportion of their expenses are directly linked to real wage evolutions, such as medical treatment or elderly care, and even more so at higher ages where they are more dependent. The adequacy of retirement pensions means they have to be able to meet the pensioners' needs, so if they fall too much behind wages they see their adequacy fall even if their real value does not decrease. We do not simulate this aspect in our model, so it is difficult to quantify the impact of this phenomenon on pension adequacy. We can however say that when 2014 moratorium pensions and the PUAM stagnate in real terms as shown by Figure 3.17c their adequacy actually decreases. Also, we see a decrease of 19% in the median pension to labour income ratio: the median pension went from representing 58% of the median labour income for years 2015 to 2017 to 47% in 2040. This shows retirement benefits do not keep up with labour income (both formal, informal and independent) and suggests overall pension adequacy falls. However, the level of contributory retirement benefits increases faster than labour income because it partially follows formal wages as we explained above. Therefore, although the adequacy of contributory retirement benefits should increase in the long run, that of all pensions will worsen over time, following the fall in the adequacy of both moratorium and PUAM benefits.

Finally, the adequacy and overall relevance of child benefits will fall over time, despite the increased coverage provoked by the loosening of means conditions to get a benefit and the extension of contributory child benefits to the children of *monotributistas* in 2016, as can be seen in Figure 3.17b⁴¹. We can see the real level of the AUH will only mildly increase over time, following the pension mobility formula established by Law 27426. Contributory child benefits on the other hand will even see their real level decrease. As we explained in section 3.1.4, the means conditions to get access to a contributory child benefit are discounted following the Law 27426 pension mobility formula, and therefore increase slower than wages. This mechanically makes access to the highest contributory child benefit increasingly difficult for the children of formal workers and either reduces the benefit they have or bars them from having any benefit at all⁴². The wealthiest formal workers do get a deduction in the income tax (also called *Impuesto a las Ganancias*) depending on the number of children they have, which acts as a substantial child benefit

⁴¹This measure has been partially reversed by Decree 702/2018, issued the 26th of July 2018, that makes access to a contributive child benefit more difficult for formal wage-earners. The inclusion of this decree in our simulations is left for future work.

⁴²The modest increase of real wages in our central scenario (0.75% each year) helps maintain the share of children that get a contributive child benefit over the 2016-2040 period. Child benefit coverage does decrease in our high economic scenario, where real wages annually increase by 1.5%. This point is studied in Appendix W

(Basualdo *et al.* , 2012). Although we do not simulate this aspect in our model, there will most likely be a growing number of formal workers that earn too much to qualify for a child benefit, but not enough to get an income tax deduction. This aspect is however left for future work

In the end, although the 2016 and 2017 reforms ensure a universal access to a pension since age 65 and a high child benefit coverage, they will strongly decrease the redistributive impact of these social security transfers. Child benefits and pensions indexed on the minimum benefit (the PUAM and moratorium pensions) will stagnate in real terms, decreasing their adequacy and overall relevance as a source of income when compared to increasing wages. Only contributory pension benefits will increase on par with wages, mostly due to the computation of new retirement benefits on the wages earned during the last ten years before retirement. This will drastically increase inequalities among retirees, to the point we even found pension benefits will have a negative impact on income distribution by 2040 in section 3.2.3. We are moreover underestimating this increasing inequality among pensioners. First, because the guarantee that contributive retirement benefits will always be equal to at least 82% of the minimum wage is not effective *de facto* due to the simulated low level of the minimum wage. Second, because we did not simulate the historical reparation program at the micro level, which further increases the contributory retirement benefits of some generations of pensioners. Finally, we have shown with 2018 legislation the median pension falls behind the median labour income. This pushes down pensioners in the income scale as explained in section 3.2.3, and further reduces the adequacy of pensions. This is because a significant proportion of the pensioners' expenses are indexed on wages, such as medical treatment or elderly care.

Nevertheless, to settle the issue of the impact of 2016 and 2017 reforms on social security transfers adequacy, it is necessary to see what would have been the adequacy of pension and family benefits in our three counter-factual legislative scenarios. This is done in the last section below.

Evaluating the impact of 2016 and 2017 reforms on social security benefits adequacy (2014-2040)

Social security transfers adequacy has been mostly affected by three sets of reforms undertaken between years 2015 and 2018. The first one is the increased access to contributory child benefits for the children of formal wage-earners (mostly through ANSES Resolution 299/2016, issued the 5th of September 2016) and of some small independent workers or

monotributistas (since May 2016, following Decree 593/2016). The end result is a strong increase in the coverage of contributory child benefits, which we studied earlier in this section and depicted in Figure 3.17b. We chose to keep these two reforms unchanged throughout our counter-factual legislative scenarios for reasons explained in section 3.2.1. So although this was an important reform, we exclude this measure from the evaluation of the impact of reforms on social security benefits adequacy. The second important reform is the replacement of Law 26970 pension moratoriums with the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult PUAM as part of the 2016 historical reparation Law 27260. The adequacy of this benefit is lower than that of moratorium pensions first because it is of a lower value (80% of the minimum benefit, instead of at least 100% of the minimum pension after five years for moratorium pensions). Most importantly though, because it pushes back retirement age for women with incomplete careers up to age 65, profoundly modifying pension coverage. The third and final important reform is the introduction of the less favourable pension mobility Law 27426 since March 2018, which mostly indexes social security benefits on the Consumer Price Index instead of wages. This freezes the real value of the minimum pension as well as that of family benefits and their means conditions (toughening thus access to a family benefit). In the case of contributory benefits, although the reform left untouched the method to determine the initial benefit, subsequent payments are indexed below real wages and thus lose part of their adequacy as long as real wages increase.

In the end, this means there are two important elements to be studied across legislative scenarios. First, we will study the impact of the implementation of the PUAM on pension coverage. Then, we will review the consequences of the change in the pension mobility formula and of the lower level of the PUAM on real retirement and family benefits as well as on child allowances coverage.

The impact of the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult on pension coverage

First and foremost, we can evaluate the impact of 2016 and 2017 reforms on pension coverage, as depicted in Figure 3.18. First, we can see there is no impact on this variable of the late 2017 reforms, as can be seen by comparing Figures 3.18a and 3.18b. It is thus the 2016 historical reparation Law 27260 that impacted this statistic. By establishing the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult PUAM as the non-contributive benefit, this law should ensure access to a benefit to 83% of people of retirement age by 2040. Of these, 31% will have a contributory benefit, 41% the PUAM, 8% a 2014 moratorium pension and 3% only get a survivor's benefit. This last group is not only made up of women aged 60 to 64. Since pensioners cannot cumulate the PUAM with a survivor's pension, we made

it so PUAM beneficiaries that eventually get a survivor's pension give up on the former, since the latter is always at least equal to the minimum pension⁴³, while the PUAM is only equal to 80% of the minimum pension.

A first comparison can be made with our counter-factual scenario with 2015 legislation and no permanent pension moratoriums, depicted in Figure 3.18d. With this legislation, only 47% of people of retirement age would have access to a pension by 2040. These are values akin to those of the late 1990s and early 2000s as depicted in Figure 1.3 of page 55, before the implementation of the 2006 pension moratorium. First, the proportion of Law 26970 moratorium pensioners drops significantly, representing only 5% of people of retirement age by 2040. This is because in this scenario we close access to moratorium benefits on September 2016 as originally scheduled, while the historical reparation Law 27260 extended it until July 2019 for women. Moreover, survivor's benefits represent the only accessible benefit for 10% of people of retirement age. This scenario thus shows the importance of keeping a universal benefit as a safety net for the elderly, since failing to do so would deprive of a pension a majority of people of retirement age.

Nevertheless, the most surprising result in this scenario is that the proportion of the elderly with a contributory pension only slightly increases to 32%. In our behavioural equations, pension level has a negative impact on labour supply of the elderly under 70 (see section 2.3.1 and Appendix L), so cutting off access to a pension for people aged 65 or more⁴⁴ with incomplete careers results in these seniors concentrating labour supply, more often prolonging their formal career and thus increasing their access to a pension. The fact this phenomenon is here marginal may first come from the fact we assume all seniors aged 70 or more are inactive, so the eventual impact on formal careers is limited to five years at most. A second reason may also be that we leave unchanged across legislative scenarios the percentage of working seniors. It may be argued that without access to a non contributive benefit seniors would increase their labour supply, so we should raise the proportion of working elderly in this counter-factual scenario of 2015 legislation with no permanent pension moratoriums. This should also result in higher access to a contributory pension by 2040, due to more people completing their careers. It is however not evident that this phenomenon would actually happen, as it is not granted that a higher supply of elderly labour would be significantly absorbed by the formal labour market and

⁴³The spouse's share can be lower in our model if there are minor children also eligible for a survivor's benefit. In any case, the total survivor's benefits earned by the family is always at least equal to the minimum pension. See Section 1.1.3 and Appendix D for further details.

⁴⁴We are comparing here a scenario without any non-contributive pensions to 2017 and 2018 legislation, where a universal pension is available since age 65. Thus, in both these scenarios women under 65 are barred from getting a non contributive benefit.

Figure 3.18: The evolution of retirement pension coverage among people of retiring age with varying legislation (2014-2040)

(a) 2018 legislation

(b) 2017 legislation

(c) 2015 legislation with permanent moratoriums

(d) 2015 legislation without moratoriums

result in higher retirement rights. Determining this new proportion of elderly workers is thus far from trivial, so we leave it for future work.

A second comparison can be made with our counter-factual scenario that keeps 2015 legislation but assumes permanent Law 26970 moratoriums, depicted in Figure 3.18c. In this scenario, access to a benefit is nearly universal for all people of retirement age because we assumed in our microsimulation model all individuals claim a pension as soon as they have the right to do so. On the other hand, only 22% of people of retirement age will have a contributory benefit by 2040, instead of 31% with 2018 or 2017 legislation. As we explained earlier, our model simulates the labour market behaviour of people under 70 but above the retirement age and finds a negative impact on labour supply of pension levels (see section 2.3.1 and Appendix L). Since we kept the same proportion of working elderly by age group and genders across our legislative scenarios, with 2018 or 2017 legislation labour supply was concentrated on seniors with no pensions, mostly women aged 60 to 64 with incomplete careers. In this counter-factual scenario labour supply is more evenly distributed among women with complete and incomplete careers since they all get some amount of pension. This means the replacement of pension moratoriums by the PUAM, by *de facto* pushing back the retirement age for most women to 65, encourages women with incomplete careers aged 60 to 64 to increase their labour supply, resulting in a higher proportion of the elderly that end up getting a contributive retirement benefit. In this case, the impact on careers is important because the proportion of formal women aged 60 to 64 is slightly above 15% in our central scenarios, while it is only equal to 7% for women and 10% for men aged 65 to 69. Also, as can be seen in our age pyramids depicted in Figure 3.4 women aged 60 to 64 are the most numerous group among people of retiring age. Any change in the proportion of members of this group that get a contributory benefit is thus bound to have a higher impact on total pension coverage than if it had happened at later ages.

Finally, it should be noted the lower contributory pension access we simulate in our 2015 legislation counter-factual scenario with permanent moratoriums should be taken with a grain of salt. On the one hand, we may be underestimating the difference in contributory pension coverage between this scenario and those with 2017 and 2018 legislation. Indeed, Bosch & Guajardo (2012) find the 2006 pension moratorium "generated a (...) fall in formal employment among women [aged 60 to 64], indicating that the moratorium caused women in formal jobs to retire, when they would have otherwise continued to contribute to the system." (Bosch & Guajardo, 2012, p. 4). Similarly, we should have a lower proportion of formal women aged 60 to 64 in this counter-factual scenario with

universal access to a pension moratorium for women aged 60 or more. Instead, we kept the same labour-market calibration across counter-factual legislative scenarios. Thus, the proportion of people of retirement age with a contributory pension should be even lower. However, we may be on the contrary underestimating in this scenario access to a contributory pension. This is because in our simulations the formal labour supply for the elderly does not take into account individual careers, and in particular the remaining number of contribution years needed to retire normally (see section 2.3.1 and Appendix L). It is reasonable to assume a senior with an incomplete career but having almost reached the required years to retire may have a higher formal labour output to get a contributory (and higher) Law 24241 retirement benefit than another senior who knows it will be impossible for him or her to retire normally. So even in a counter-factual scenario where both of them get a moratorium benefit, it is to be expected moratorium pensioners close to retiring with a contributory (and thus higher) Law 24241 benefit would concentrate formal labour supply. This should in turn result in a higher proportion of normal contributory pensioners than the one depicted in Figure 3.18d. This phenomenon cannot however be calibrated with the EPHc household survey data, where direct information on individual pension rights is unavailable. It is thus left to future work.

In the end, we find it is the *de facto* pushing back of the retirement age for women from 60 to 65 with the PUAM through the historical reparation Law 27260 that has the most interesting impact on pension coverage. This should cause senior women to prolong their formal careers, hence increasing contributions to the system and raising the proportion of contributory pensioners. The universal aspect of the PUAM also acts as an important safety net for the elderly, ensuring they get at least some pension revenue since age 65. The PUAM also includes healthcare coverage for the pensioner, since the beneficiary gets access to the health insurance for the elderly run by the PAMI as we saw in section 1.1.2. The counterpart of this measure is a reduced pension adequacy for the elderly in the long term, since pension coverage decreases as well as the mean earned benefit. We study this aspect below, together with the impact on pension adequacy of the Law 27426 pension mobility formula in force since March 2018.

The impact of the Law 27426 pension mobility formula on social security benefits adequacy

After studying the impact of the PUAM on pension coverage, we study in this last part the effect of the pension mobility formula's change on social security transfers adequacy. Not only does it directly effect the real level of benefits, it also reduces the median pension to labour income ratio and has a negative impact on child benefits coverage. All these

elements are depicted in Figure 3.19 below.

First of all, all of the variables consigned in Figure 3.19 show the 2018 reform worsened all social security transfers adequacy, as well as the coverage of family benefits. By 2040, it is this legislation that ensures the lowest levels of pensions (Figures 3.19a and 3.19b), child benefits (Figure 3.19c) and access to a child benefit (3.19d). This is first and foremost due to the introduction of the less generous pension mobility Law 27426, where social security benefits are mostly indexed on the Consumer Price Index. In the other counter-factual scenarios, it is the old Law 26417 pension mobility formula that is enforced. As we explained in section 3.2.1, we assumed it followed the real growth of formal wages, thus the evolution of the RIPTE. Hence, 2018 legislation results in a stagnating level of overall pensions, while 2017 and 2015 legislations give a significant real increase of retirement and survivors' benefits. Also, the fact income conditions to get access to a contributory child benefit are mostly indexed on the CPI instead of wages gives a lower child benefit coverage with 2018 legislation than with any other counter-factual scenario. Access to the Universal Child Benefit AUH is not means-tested but depends on the proportion of informal workers or of the unemployed, which is by definition the same across legislative scenarios. This is why AUH coverage is not affected by legislative changes. Finally, child benefits mean levels are the lowest with 2018 legislation. This is on the one hand due to their real freeze with the Law 27426 pension mobility formula. On the other hand, the aforementioned toughening of means conditions to get a contributive child benefits pushes an increasing number of formal workers' children into the categories that give the lowest child benefits. This is why with 2018 legislation the real level of contributory child benefits decreases and that of the AUH stagnates, as depicted by Figure 3.19c.

This said, the study of social security adequacy among the other three legislative scenarios that use the old pension mobility Law 26417 sheds light on various interesting aspects. First of all, the mean pension as well as the median pension to income ratio are the highest with 2015 legislation without permanent moratoriums, as can be seen in Figures 3.19a and 3.19b. This is a logical result, since by the end of the simulation almost all pensions are contributory as seen in Figure 3.18d. Also, contributory child benefits coverage and levels are the lowest in this counter-factual scenario. This may come from the fact the children of retirement and survivor's pensions beneficiaries get access to a contributive child benefit, provided the family group's income passes the means test. On the other hand, the children of inactive people with no pension revenue are barred from both contributive and universal child benefits, the latter being reserved *de jure* to the children of informal workers and the unemployed. It may make sense to grant the AUH

Figure 3.19: The evolution of social security benefits adequacy: coverage and level (2014-2040)

(a) Mean retirement benefits

(b) Median pension to labour income ratio

(c) Mean child benefits

(d) Child benefits coverage (% of minor children)

Mean values are in constant November 2014 pesos. Between November 2014 and March 2016, we use a simple average of the Consumer Price Indexes (CPI) of the province of San Luis and the Autonomous City of Buenos Aires (CABA). Between April 2016 and May 2018, we use INDEC's national CPI. After May 2018, we keep a monthly annualised inflation of 30%. This (underestimated, due to the current 2018 currency crisis) inflation level is only useful for computing real family benefits and retirement pension evolution in 2018. Labour income is computed across formal and informal workers, be them wage-earners or independent, net of social security contributions.

in our model to the children of inactive parents with no pension revenue, since the latter only need to declare being unemployed for receiving the universal child benefit AUH. This point is left for future versions of our model. Still, this counter-factual scenario shows drastically reducing retirement pension coverage has a small but significant effect on family benefits. In any case, it is more relevant to study the adequacy of the 2015 legislation without permanent moratoriums counter-factual scenario through the prism of pension coverage as we have done earlier in this section. The real level of retirement pensions in this scenario is thus not particularly telling of social security adequacy due to the exclusion of most of the elderly from the retirement system.

Instead, it is more interesting to compare the counter-factual scenarios of 2017 legislation and 2015 legislation with permanent pension moratoriums through the prism of social security transfers levels and child benefits coverage. First of all, mean contributory pensions are higher with 2015 legislation, but average overall pensions are lower than with 2017 rules. This shows the individuals that subscribed to a contributory retirement benefit with 2017 legislation, but would have instead gotten a moratorium benefit with 2015 rules (see the difference in contributory pension coverage in Figures 3.18b and 3.18c) have lower retirement rights than those who would have retired normally in either of these scenarios. The mean pension is however higher with 2017 legislation both because of the more important number of contributory pensioners and the fact women are barred from having access to a non-contributive benefit until age 65, as shown by the drop in pension coverage depicted in Figure 3.18b which we studied earlier. The other significant difference lies in contributive child benefits. With 2017 legislation, these are slightly higher in their mean value (Figure 3.19c) and their coverage (Figure 3.19d). This slight difference is most likely due to the replacement of pension moratoriums by the less generous PUAM. Since family benefits are granted depending on the family group's total income, higher retirement benefits result in fewer households getting access to these child allowances, or having a right to a lesser benefit. As such, 2017 legislation partially compensates the fall in pension revenue provoked by the introduction of the PUAM through higher and more widely available family benefits.

All in all, the 2016 and 2017 pension reforms both had a negative impact on social security benefits and coverage, decreasing thus their adequacy. The replacement of pension moratoriums by the PUAM, lower and only accessible since age 65, and the implementation of the less generous law 27426 pension mobility formula had a negative impact on all indicators of social security transfers adequacy. This is however only valid when we compare them to a counter-factual scenario that both assumes moratorium pensions become

permanent and that the wider access to child benefits instituted in 2016 remains in place. Pension adequacy is far lower in our counter-factual scenario with the strict application of the legislation in force in December 2015, which only kept Law 26970 moratorium pensions until September 2016. Child benefits coverage would have also plummeted with a strict application of the current legislation, where the maximum family income compatible with a contributory benefit was not indexed and thus decreased in real terms with inflation. Thus, by indexing the means test of family benefits on pension mobility and instituting the permanent Universal Pension for the Elderly (PUAM), the 2016 and 2017 reforms maintain a high pension and child benefits coverage, and thus a decent level of social security benefits adequacy. This would have been an encouraging result had these measures bettered the economic sustainability of Argentina's national social security system, run by the ANSES. We have however shown in section 3.2.2 that 2018 legislation results in an even worse economic sustainability than the one that would have been reached with 2015 legislation and permanent pension moratoriums. We can therefore conclude that the 2016 and 2017 reforms undertaken by the incumbent government had a negative impact on all the aspects of Argentina's social security system: its economic sustainability, redistributive impact and the adequacy of its benefits.

Chapter 3 conclusion: the dire prospects of Argentina's social security

This third and last chapter is divided in two parts. The first section extrapolates the social security benefits and contributions we simulate with the dynamic microsimulation model laid out in Chapter 2 to actual measured values. This allows for an aggregate study of social security's economic sustainability up to the 2040 horizon through the computation of ANSES "Bismarckian" balance, where social security and family benefits are subtracted from contributions to the ANSES. It also finishes the legislative calibration of our model. First, it introduces non-simulated social security expenses and revenues, which lets us go from ANSES "Bismarckian" balance to the study of social security's full economic result. Second, it precisely defines our three counter-factual legislative scenarios. These make it possible to gauge the impact of the reforms undertaken by the incumbent administration between 2016 and 2018 on the social security system's economic sustainability, adequacy and redistributive impact. The second half of Chapter 3 presents the results of our projections, with varying economic and legislative scenarios. By taking advantage of the dynamic microsimulation method we adopted for our prospective analysis, we are able to study future social security evolutions both at the aggregate and individual level. This

lets us analyse future evolutions of social security's aggregate economic sustainability as well as the individual adequacy and redistributive impact of its benefits, which together determine the system's political sustainability.

The main result of our simulations is that Argentina's social security system is not sustainable with the current legislation. In our central economic scenario, ANSES economic result linearly falls from -1.5% of GDP in 2017 to -5.7% in 2022, down to -6.7% of GDP in 2040, as depicted in Figure 3.7. We have moreover shown that far from mitigating this fall, the recent 2016 (the historical reparation Law 27260) and 2017 reforms (Laws 27426, 27430 and 27432) are the direct cause of the brutal increase of social security deficit expected in the short run. In fact, had none of these reforms ever taken place, ANSES economic sustainability would have been better across the 2014-2040 period even if the 2014 Law 26970 pension moratoriums were permanent, as shown by Figure 3.11. This generous counter-factual scenario would have ensured a universal access to a pension for all people of retirement age. It would have also kept the indexation of social security benefits (mostly) on wages, following the 2008 Law 26417 pension mobility index. We have also shown it would have ensured the highest social security benefits adequacy⁴⁵ and redistributive impact of all our counter-factual legislative scenarios. In the end, the main social security reforms undertaken by the current administration had a strongly negative impact on all aspects of Argentina's social security system, decreasing its adequacy, redistributive impact but most importantly its economic sustainability even in the very short term.

At first glance, it would seem absurd for any government to adopt pension reforms that would worsen all the aspects of the social security system at once. A first reason is that the government chose to deviate funds away from social security in order to fund three distinct measures. First, the fiscal pact signed between the federal government and the provinces, included in the 2016 historical reparation Law 27260. This deal gradually stops the direct assignment of 15% of *coparticipable* funds (taxes shared between the federal and provincial governments) to the ANSES between 2016 and 2020. This particular measure was taken to abide by the 24th of November 2015 Supreme Court of Justice's rulings and it does not increase *per se* the total deficit of Argentina's public sector. The

⁴⁵One limitation of our work is we do not simulate at the individual level the positive effect of the 2016 Law 27260 historical reparation program on the contributive pensions of some generations of pensioners. In theory, pension adequacy could have been higher with 2017 legislation at least for the generations of pensioners that subscribed to this program. However, the current legislation has pensions indexed mostly on the Consumer Price Index following Law 27426. Thus, in the middle term it is likely the positive impact on pension adequacy of the historical reparation program is more than offset by the lesser increase of benefits in real terms.

problem is no alternative source of revenue stepped in to replace these 1.5% of GDP⁴⁶ worth of missing ANSES funding, worsening the agency's balance. Second, the late 2017 fiscal reform Law 27430 gradually decreases employers contributions to social security between years 2018 and 2022, reducing ANSES funding by an estimated 1.6% of GDP by 2022 in our central economic scenario. Finally, Laws 27430 and 27432 replace since 2018 fully share (or *coparticipate*) the income tax between the provincial and federal governments, so it stops being a source of revenue for ANSES. It allocates the agency in turn the full "Check"⁴⁷ tax, which will most likely be progressively eliminated between 2018 and 2022, reducing total taxes by 1.7%⁴⁸ of GDP. Thus by 2022, the full *coparticipation* of the Income Tax will reduce ANSES funding by an additional 1% of GDP⁴⁹.

Both the elimination of the "Check" tax and the reduction of employers' contributions aim to foster economic growth, but there is no economically sound reason to make social security fund these measures. It is hard to tell how reducing retirement and family benefits to fund tax exemptions could be a desirable policy outcome, or even succeed in boosting economic growth. All in all, these two tax reductions combined with the return of 15% of *coparticipable* funds to the provinces will reduce social security funding by 4% of GDP between 2015 and 2022. Knowing our simulations find a deterioration of social security's balance of 5% of GDP between 2015 and 2022, this means 80% of this increase in social security's deficit was directly caused by the 2016 and 2017 reforms. Finally, the overall sustainability of social security is reduced by the historical reparation plan, which will spend most of the Sustainability Guarantee Fund (FGS) starting from 2019, as we computed in Appendix U. It will thus not be possible to pay for future temporary ANSES deficits with the Fund. Also, the FGS currently funds economic development through its financing of productive and infrastructure projects. It will no longer be able to do so in the future, resulting in a lower long-term growth of Argentina's economy.

All in all, the 2016 and 2017 reforms jeopardised social security accounts by de-funding ANSES but also opting not to find genuine funding for the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult (PUAM), other than transfers from the federal budget. At this point, it is evident these reforms had the explicit objective to render Argentina's social security sys-

⁴⁶This is the mean GDP share of *coparticipable* taxes transferred to the ANSES between 2008 and 2015, as informed by the Federal Tax Commission. The values of these transfers in nominal pesos can be found in <http://www.cfi.gov.ar>.

⁴⁷Instituted in 2001 by Law 25413, the Tax on Credits and Debits on banks' Current Accounts is commonly known as the "Check" tax.

⁴⁸Source: own computation based on AFIP's total taxation figures (2008-2017).

⁴⁹Source: Own computation based on the Savings-Investment-Funding (AIF) accounts for social security institutions as taken from the Investment Account (2008-2017).

tem blatantly unsustainable in the short term. This may be linked to the major pension reform *de jure* scheduled by the historical reparation Law 27260's Art. 12 by 2019. Indeed, the stronger the social security accounts crisis, the easier it becomes to carry out drastic and unpopular pension reforms. This hypothesis will be further discussed in this thesis' General Conclusion.

Appendices

Appendix R

Detailed simulation results with the fourth quarter of 2014 starting date, by scenario

We have in sections 3.1 and 3.2 set down the outlines of the computation of ANSES future economic result from our simulation results. In particular, Figures 3.6 and 3.7 respectively depict ANSES "Bismarckian" deficit (social security contributions minus social security benefits and current transfers to the private sector) and its economic result in the 1993-2040 period, taking into account all the social security reforms enforced between 2014 and May 2018. The actual figures with which these future deficits were computed will be listed in this Appendix. First, we will show our computation of future GDP by economic scenario, based on real wage evolution and the growth of total workers. We will then show our simulated social security benefits, contributions and current transfers to the private sector for the 2015-2040 period and extrapolate them using the conversion keys we listed in Table 3.5 of section 3.1. Finally, we will compute ANSES "Bismarckian" deficit and economic result by scenario, respectively depicted in Figures 3.6 and 3.7

R.1 Real GDP growth by economic scenario, fourth quarter of 2014 start

First of all, we take the simulated total number of workers and their mean wage in the 2018-2040 period by economic scenario. As established by equation (3.1) of page 349 in section 3.2, we assume the joint evolution of these two terms determines future GDP growth. From the latest GDP figure available, that of the fourth quarter of 2017, we compute future GDP evolution as depicted in Table R.1 below.

Table R.1: Future GDP by economic scenario (2018-2040)

	Total workers	Working population growth	Mean labour income	Labour income growth	Real GDP (millions of pesos)
2017 ,Q4	11,181,611		6,722.13		5,747,025
Low economic scenario					
2018 ,Q1	11,195,427	0.12%	6,643.97	-1.16%	5,687,221
2018 ,Q2	11,278,619	0.74%	6,608.64	-0.53%	5,699,009
2018 ,Q3	11,305,467	0.24%	6,673.71	0.98%	5,768,822
2018 ,Q4	11,298,518	-0.06%	6,682.33	0.13%	5,772,722
2019 ,Q1	11,397,825	0.88%	6,685.04	0.04%	5,825,822
2019 ,Q2	11,388,578	-0.08%	6,694.54	0.14%	5,829,369
2019 ,Q3	11,375,749	-0.11%	6,675.88	-0.28%	5,806,577
2019 ,Q4	11,449,719	0.65%	6,684.35	0.13%	5,851,746
2020 ,Q1	11,461,882	0.11%	6,652.99	-0.47%	5,830,476
2020 ,Q2	11,482,419	0.18%	6,674.51	0.32%	5,859,823
2020 ,Q3	11,515,687	0.29%	6,651.48	-0.35%	5,856,517
2020 ,Q4	11,583,569	0.59%	6,614.73	-0.55%	5,858,498
2021 ,Q1	11,621,462	0.33%	6,604.33	-0.16%	5,868,414
2021 ,Q2	11,595,947	-0.22%	6,621.77	0.26%	5,870,995
2021 ,Q3	11,631,571	0.31%	6,621.21	-0.01%	5,888,538
2021 ,Q4	11,631,260	0.00%	6,614.14	-0.11%	5,882,091
2022 ,Q1	11,629,663	-0.01%	6,561.28	-0.80%	5,834,277
2022 ,Q2	11,627,932	-0.01%	6,587.24	0.40%	5,856,487
2022 ,Q3	11,666,206	0.33%	6,559.43	-0.42%	5,850,957
2022 ,Q4	11,665,397	-0.01%	6,597.92	0.59%	5,884,888
2023 ,Q1	11,618,250	-0.40%	6,607.04	0.14%	5,869,200
2023 ,Q2	11,612,612	-0.05%	6,571.61	-0.54%	5,834,894
2023 ,Q3	11,696,181	0.72%	6,557.10	-0.22%	5,863,915
2023 ,Q4	11,779,991	0.72%	6,545.56	-0.18%	5,895,539
2024 ,Q1	11,815,803	0.30%	6,552.59	0.11%	5,919,811
2024 ,Q2	11,881,764	0.56%	6,529.40	-0.35%	5,931,791
2024 ,Q3	11,881,635	0.00%	6,522.98	-0.10%	5,925,894
2024 ,Q4	11,877,882	-0.03%	6,539.30	0.25%	5,938,846
2025 ,Q1	11,916,429	0.32%	6,538.93	-0.01%	5,957,780
2025 ,Q2	11,925,014	0.07%	6,534.50	-0.07%	5,958,031
2025 ,Q3	11,932,895	0.07%	6,506.54	-0.43%	5,936,463
2025 ,Q4	11,994,521	0.52%	6,495.65	-0.17%	5,957,130
2026 ,Q1	12,018,877	0.20%	6,492.91	-0.04%	5,966,709
2026 ,Q2	11,960,995	-0.48%	6,487.26	-0.09%	5,932,804
<p>Mean labour income and working population growth are both simulated in our model. The fourth quarter of 2017 GDP is official data discounted with official inflation indexes and expressed in November 2014 pesos. Working population and labour income growth are computed at a quarterly step.</p>					

	Total workers	Working population growth	Mean labour income	Labour income growth	Real GDP (millions of pesos)
2017, Q4	11,190,883		6,736		5,747,025
2026 ,Q3	12,005,192	0.37%	6,463.82	-0.36%	5,933,213
2026 ,Q4	11,980,958	-0.20%	6,488.52	0.38%	5,943,860
2027 ,Q1	12,029,196	0.40%	6,485.68	-0.04%	5,965,184
2027 ,Q2	12,017,415	-0.10%	6,472.85	-0.20%	5,947,548
2027 ,Q3	11,995,212	-0.18%	6,490.27	0.27%	5,952,534
2027 ,Q4	12,012,508	0.14%	6,507.76	0.27%	5,977,185
2028 ,Q1	12,149,495	1.14%	6,492.75	-0.23%	6,031,405
2028 ,Q2	12,145,452	-0.03%	6,494.78	0.03%	6,031,279
2028 ,Q3	12,116,689	-0.24%	6,497.57	0.04%	6,019,584
2028 ,Q4	12,149,648	0.27%	6,485.48	-0.19%	6,024,726
2029 ,Q1	12,203,767	0.45%	6,477.15	-0.13%	6,043,788
2029 ,Q2	12,179,290	-0.20%	6,477.56	0.01%	6,032,051
2029 ,Q3	12,186,458	0.06%	6,469.56	-0.12%	6,028,148
2029 ,Q4	12,208,240	0.18%	6,464.36	-0.08%	6,034,069
2030 ,Q1	12,224,550	0.13%	6,463.26	-0.02%	6,041,097
2030 ,Q2	12,212,095	-0.10%	6,454.26	-0.14%	6,026,539
2030 ,Q3	12,176,551	-0.29%	6,452.30	-0.03%	6,007,173
2030 ,Q4	12,211,777	0.29%	6,444.94	-0.11%	6,017,686
2031 ,Q1	12,256,048	0.36%	6,429.67	-0.24%	6,025,192
2031 ,Q2	12,188,008	-0.56%	6,452.55	0.36%	6,013,063
2031 ,Q3	12,229,047	0.34%	6,426.19	-0.41%	6,008,665
2031 ,Q4	12,253,631	0.20%	6,419.12	-0.11%	6,014,115
2032 ,Q1	12,241,316	-0.10%	6,433.96	0.23%	6,021,962
2032 ,Q2	12,246,726	0.04%	6,416.02	-0.28%	6,007,820
2032 ,Q3	12,189,857	-0.46%	6,426.86	0.17%	5,990,027
2032 ,Q4	12,189,296	0.00%	6,411.83	-0.23%	5,975,742
2033 ,Q1	12,296,968	0.88%	6,377.09	-0.54%	5,995,867
2033 ,Q2	12,208,424	-0.72%	6,384.36	0.11%	5,959,485
2033 ,Q3	12,212,985	0.04%	6,369.24	-0.24%	5,947,587
2033 ,Q4	12,272,310	0.49%	6,346.90	-0.35%	5,955,521
2034 ,Q1	12,255,779	-0.13%	6,360.54	0.21%	5,960,281
2034 ,Q2	12,199,168	-0.46%	6,344.84	-0.25%	5,918,105
2034 ,Q3	12,180,048	-0.16%	6,373.87	0.46%	5,935,863
2034 ,Q4	12,182,352	0.02%	6,343.69	-0.47%	5,908,870
2035 ,Q1	12,110,740	-0.59%	6,351.53	0.12%	5,881,394
2035 ,Q2	12,123,092	0.10%	6,356.13	0.07%	5,891,657
2035 ,Q3	12,188,710	0.54%	6,338.65	-0.27%	5,907,259

Mean labour income and working population growth are both simulated in our model. The fourth quarter of 2017 GDP is official data discounted with official inflation indexes and expressed in November 2014 pesos. Working population and labour income growth are computed at a quarterly step.

	Total workers	Working population growth	Mean labour income	Labour income growth	Real GDP (millions of pesos)
2017, Q4	11,190,883		6,736		5,747,025
2035 ,Q4	12,221,913	0.27%	6,301.34	-0.59%	5,888,484
2036 ,Q1	12,238,727	0.14%	6,301.40	0.00%	5,896,645
2036 ,Q2	12,241,791	0.03%	6,300.32	-0.02%	5,897,112
2036 ,Q3	12,270,425	0.23%	6,297.95	-0.04%	5,908,681
2036 ,Q4	12,241,320	-0.24%	6,279.04	-0.30%	5,876,960
2037 ,Q1	12,185,095	-0.46%	6,284.62	0.09%	5,855,169
2037 ,Q2	12,233,921	0.40%	6,274.54	-0.16%	5,869,201
2037 ,Q3	12,263,149	0.24%	6,251.19	-0.37%	5,861,326
2037 ,Q4	12,192,353	-0.58%	6,219.81	-0.50%	5,798,235
2038 ,Q1	12,272,239	0.66%	6,228.29	0.14%	5,844,189
2038 ,Q2	12,266,908	-0.04%	6,226.78	-0.02%	5,840,228
2038 ,Q3	12,248,964	-0.15%	6,235.90	0.15%	5,840,231
2038 ,Q4	12,236,788	-0.10%	6,237.58	0.03%	5,835,993
2039 ,Q1	12,220,467	-0.13%	6,249.84	0.20%	5,839,671
2039 ,Q2	12,181,699	-0.32%	6,234.27	-0.25%	5,806,639
2039 ,Q3	12,229,858	0.40%	6,213.61	-0.33%	5,810,281
2039 ,Q4	12,201,357	-0.23%	6,208.75	-0.08%	5,792,199
2040 ,Q1	12,155,814	-0.37%	6,225.94	0.28%	5,786,559
2040 ,Q2	12,146,628	-0.08%	6,240.59	0.24%	5,795,791
2040 ,Q3	12,187,490	0.34%	6,228.89	-0.19%	5,804,392
2040 ,Q4	12,161,963	-0.21%	6,224.14	-0.08%	5,787,818
Central economic scenario					
2018 ,Q1	11,195,427	0.12%	6,643.97	-1.16%	5,687,221
2018 ,Q2	11,278,619	0.74%	6,608.64	-0.53%	5,699,009
2018 ,Q3	11,305,467	0.24%	6,673.71	0.98%	5,768,822
2018 ,Q4	11,298,518	-0.06%	6,694.82	0.32%	5,783,516
2019 ,Q1	11,397,825	0.88%	6,710.06	0.23%	5,847,628
2019 ,Q2	11,395,972	-0.02%	6,736.84	0.40%	5,870,010
2019 ,Q3	11,393,818	-0.02%	6,738.81	0.03%	5,870,621
2019 ,Q4	11,468,374	0.65%	6,762.95	0.36%	5,930,198
2020 ,Q1	11,491,158	0.20%	6,743.35	-0.29%	5,924,760
2020 ,Q2	11,519,026	0.24%	6,781.02	0.56%	5,972,313
2020 ,Q3	11,594,810	0.66%	6,762.24	-0.28%	5,994,948
2020 ,Q4	11,641,835	0.41%	6,746.12	-0.24%	6,004,919
2021 ,Q1	11,663,401	0.19%	6,757.13	0.16%	6,025,862
2021 ,Q2	11,662,781	-0.01%	6,789.49	0.48%	6,054,395
2021 ,Q3	11,720,545	0.50%	6,809.50	0.29%	6,102,316
Mean labour income and working population growth are both simulated in our model. The fourth quarter of 2017 GDP is official data discounted with official inflation indexes and expressed in November 2014 pesos. Working population and labour income growth are computed at a quarterly step.					

	Total workers	Working population growth	Mean labour income	Labour income growth	Real GDP (millions of pesos)
2017, Q4	11,190,883		6,736		5,747,025
2021 ,Q4	11,725,050	0.04%	6,816.58	0.10%	6,111,008
2022 ,Q1	11,717,986	-0.06%	6,816.64	0.00%	6,107,381
2022 ,Q2	11,695,249	-0.19%	6,851.49	0.51%	6,126,694
2022 ,Q3	11,760,267	0.56%	6,826.05	-0.37%	6,137,874
2022 ,Q4	11,772,049	0.10%	6,850.35	0.36%	6,165,894
2023 ,Q1	11,817,916	0.39%	6,872.22	0.32%	6,209,684
2023 ,Q2	11,808,542	-0.08%	6,895.50	0.34%	6,225,774
2023 ,Q3	11,855,572	0.40%	6,889.84	-0.08%	6,245,437
2023 ,Q4	11,894,602	0.33%	6,898.89	0.13%	6,274,230
2024 ,Q1	11,949,006	0.46%	6,936.37	0.54%	6,337,175
2024 ,Q2	11,958,837	0.08%	6,930.09	-0.09%	6,336,643
2024 ,Q3	11,993,759	0.29%	6,937.41	0.11%	6,361,859
2024 ,Q4	12,035,845	0.35%	6,944.30	0.10%	6,390,529
2025 ,Q1	12,057,642	0.18%	6,963.16	0.27%	6,419,483
2025 ,Q2	12,218,382	1.33%	6,953.94	-0.13%	6,496,453
2025 ,Q3	12,159,137	-0.48%	6,965.38	0.16%	6,475,586
2025 ,Q4	12,122,064	-0.30%	6,985.40	0.29%	6,474,400
2026 ,Q1	12,138,162	0.13%	7,020.87	0.51%	6,515,912
2026 ,Q2	12,202,873	0.53%	7,049.80	0.41%	6,577,642
2026 ,Q3	12,316,523	0.93%	7,044.54	-0.07%	6,633,955
2026 ,Q4	12,340,000	0.19%	7,092.76	0.68%	6,692,097
2027 ,Q1	12,353,010	0.11%	7,100.93	0.12%	6,706,863
2027 ,Q2	12,360,350	0.06%	7,108.70	0.11%	6,718,195
2027 ,Q3	12,465,592	0.85%	7,117.90	0.13%	6,784,159
2027 ,Q4	12,529,157	0.51%	7,117.23	-0.01%	6,818,118
2028 ,Q1	12,519,637	-0.08%	7,161.00	0.61%	6,854,832
2028 ,Q2	12,550,095	0.24%	7,180.59	0.27%	6,890,308
2028 ,Q3	12,542,207	-0.06%	7,186.21	0.08%	6,891,369
2028 ,Q4	12,492,115	-0.40%	7,226.52	0.56%	6,902,350
2029 ,Q1	12,563,995	0.58%	7,229.85	0.05%	6,945,263
2029 ,Q2	12,600,795	0.29%	7,226.92	-0.04%	6,962,785
2029 ,Q3	12,524,539	-0.61%	7,233.46	0.09%	6,926,909
2029 ,Q4	12,518,155	-0.05%	7,251.17	0.24%	6,940,325
2030 ,Q1	12,528,013	0.08%	7,266.96	0.22%	6,960,920
2030 ,Q2	12,589,547	0.49%	7,252.30	-0.20%	6,980,991
2030 ,Q3	12,669,878	0.64%	7,270.60	0.25%	7,043,265
2030 ,Q4	12,712,932	0.34%	7,294.19	0.32%	7,090,134

Mean labour income and working population growth are both simulated in our model. The fourth quarter of 2017 GDP is official data discounted with official inflation indexes and expressed in November 2014 pesos. Working population and labour income growth are computed at a quarterly step.

	Total workers	Working population growth	Mean labour income	Labour income growth	Real GDP (millions of pesos)
2017, Q4	11,190,883		6,736		5,747,025
2031 ,Q1	12,781,006	0.54%	7,286.05	-0.11%	7,120,141
2031 ,Q2	12,779,934	-0.01%	7,317.78	0.44%	7,150,552
2031 ,Q3	12,755,254	-0.19%	7,336.12	0.25%	7,154,630
2031 ,Q4	12,683,930	-0.56%	7,354.28	0.25%	7,132,230
2032 ,Q1	12,761,743	0.61%	7,313.28	-0.56%	7,135,980
2032 ,Q2	12,697,036	-0.51%	7,401.13	1.20%	7,185,083
2032 ,Q3	12,761,685	0.51%	7,389.06	-0.16%	7,209,888
2032 ,Q4	12,832,907	0.56%	7,380.64	-0.11%	7,241,867
2033 ,Q1	12,727,551	-0.82%	7,428.02	0.64%	7,228,520
2033 ,Q2	12,717,402	-0.08%	7,443.16	0.20%	7,237,473
2033 ,Q3	12,766,226	0.38%	7,447.64	0.06%	7,269,633
2033 ,Q4	12,813,300	0.37%	7,459.92	0.16%	7,308,473
2034 ,Q1	12,812,849	0.00%	7,453.91	-0.08%	7,302,332
2034 ,Q2	12,817,337	0.04%	7,480.07	0.35%	7,330,519
2034 ,Q3	12,827,475	0.08%	7,443.41	-0.49%	7,300,365
2034 ,Q4	12,887,794	0.47%	7,479.63	0.49%	7,370,389
2035 ,Q1	12,878,035	-0.08%	7,495.31	0.21%	7,380,247
2035 ,Q2	12,955,192	0.60%	7,498.67	0.04%	7,427,786
2035 ,Q3	12,937,415	-0.14%	7,549.93	0.68%	7,468,308
2035 ,Q4	12,975,513	0.29%	7,572.43	0.30%	7,512,618
2036 ,Q1	13,039,994	0.50%	7,593.98	0.28%	7,571,441
2036 ,Q2	12,983,072	-0.44%	7,628.78	0.46%	7,572,929
2036 ,Q3	12,978,706	-0.03%	7,619.64	-0.12%	7,561,312
2036 ,Q4	13,039,589	0.47%	7,618.70	-0.01%	7,595,845
2037 ,Q1	12,963,326	-0.58%	7,655.03	0.48%	7,587,434
2037 ,Q2	12,982,956	0.15%	7,688.15	0.43%	7,631,797
2037 ,Q3	13,053,998	0.55%	7,646.14	-0.55%	7,631,632
2037 ,Q4	12,980,923	-0.56%	7,675.10	0.38%	7,617,655
2038 ,Q1	12,944,456	-0.28%	7,677.71	0.03%	7,598,837
2038 ,Q2	12,925,521	-0.15%	7,736.41	0.76%	7,645,729
2038 ,Q3	13,002,376	0.59%	7,708.42	-0.36%	7,663,363
2038 ,Q4	13,039,381	0.28%	7,712.96	0.06%	7,689,705
2039 ,Q1	13,073,649	0.26%	7,701.83	-0.14%	7,698,786
2039 ,Q2	13,016,841	-0.43%	7,707.80	0.08%	7,671,275
2039 ,Q3	13,001,161	-0.12%	7,698.52	-0.12%	7,652,812
2039 ,Q4	13,039,899	0.30%	7,712.36	0.18%	7,689,406
2040 ,Q1	12,992,499	-0.36%	7,719.06	0.09%	7,668,113

Mean labour income and working population growth are both simulated in our model. The fourth quarter of 2017 GDP is official data discounted with official inflation indexes and expressed in November 2014 pesos. Working population and labour income growth are computed at a quarterly step.

	Total workers	Working population growth	Mean labour income	Labour income growth	Real GDP (millions of pesos)
2017 ,Q4	11,190,883		6,736		5,747,025
2040 ,Q2	13,059,447	0.52%	7,744.20	0.33%	7,732,734
2040 ,Q3	13,059,232	0.00%	7,767.92	0.31%	7,756,291
2040 ,Q4	13,081,094	0.17%	7,791.44	0.30%	7,792,794
High economic scenario					
2018 ,Q1	11,195,427	0.12%	6,643.97	-1.16%	5,687,221
2018 ,Q2	11,278,619	0.74%	6,608.64	-0.53%	5,699,009
2018 ,Q3	11,305,467	0.24%	6,673.71	0.98%	5,768,822
2018 ,Q4	11,298,518	-0.06%	6,707.25	0.50%	5,794,249
2019 ,Q1	11,397,825	0.88%	6,734.99	0.41%	5,869,353
2019 ,Q2	11,404,929	0.06%	6,777.50	0.63%	5,910,086
2019 ,Q3	11,415,016	0.09%	6,796.63	0.28%	5,932,003
2019 ,Q4	11,496,650	0.72%	6,841.73	0.66%	6,014,072
2020 ,Q1	11,529,198	0.28%	6,833.52	-0.12%	6,023,861
2020 ,Q2	11,571,754	0.37%	6,883.77	0.74%	6,090,554
2020 ,Q3	11,638,399	0.58%	6,890.92	0.10%	6,132,002
2020 ,Q4	11,652,733	0.12%	6,940.57	0.72%	6,183,784
2021 ,Q1	11,693,969	0.35%	6,931.34	-0.13%	6,197,414
2021 ,Q2	11,758,139	0.55%	6,938.81	0.11%	6,238,138
2021 ,Q3	11,749,339	-0.07%	7,006.56	0.98%	6,294,331
2021 ,Q4	11,759,353	0.09%	7,053.91	0.68%	6,342,270
2022 ,Q1	11,857,690	0.84%	7,043.81	-0.14%	6,386,151
2022 ,Q2	11,867,550	0.08%	7,094.74	0.72%	6,437,678
2022 ,Q3	11,906,136	0.33%	7,134.16	0.56%	6,494,490
2022 ,Q4	11,880,720	-0.21%	7,175.06	0.57%	6,517,782
2023 ,Q1	11,914,866	0.29%	7,181.39	0.09%	6,542,279
2023 ,Q2	12,020,203	0.88%	7,186.61	0.07%	6,604,915
2023 ,Q3	12,067,978	0.40%	7,193.39	0.09%	6,637,423
2023 ,Q4	12,049,445	-0.15%	7,265.26	1.00%	6,693,441
2024 ,Q1	12,162,033	0.93%	7,279.33	0.19%	6,769,067
2024 ,Q2	12,217,730	0.46%	7,309.90	0.42%	6,828,627
2024 ,Q3	12,252,663	0.29%	7,326.45	0.23%	6,863,656
2024 ,Q4	12,245,450	-0.06%	7,374.96	0.66%	6,905,032
2025 ,Q1	12,251,579	0.05%	7,422.12	0.64%	6,952,665
2025 ,Q2	12,327,032	0.62%	7,441.53	0.26%	7,013,782
2025 ,Q3	12,417,548	0.73%	7,477.35	0.48%	7,099,291
2025 ,Q4	12,512,543	0.77%	7,521.39	0.59%	7,195,733
2026 ,Q1	12,560,336	0.38%	7,534.05	0.17%	7,235,377
Mean labour income and working population growth are both simulated in our model. The fourth quarter of 2017 GDP is official data discounted with official inflation indexes and expressed in November 2014 pesos. Working population and labour income growth are computed at a quarterly step.					

	Total workers	Working population growth	Mean labour income	Labour income growth	Real GDP (millions of pesos)
2017, Q4	11,190,883		6,736		5,747,025
2026 ,Q2	12,554,154	-0.05%	7,588.11	0.72%	7,283,709
2026 ,Q3	12,653,475	0.79%	7,595.44	0.10%	7,348,425
2026 ,Q4	12,613,364	-0.32%	7,645.96	0.67%	7,373,850
2027 ,Q1	12,620,468	0.06%	7,682.59	0.48%	7,413,350
2027 ,Q2	12,711,581	0.72%	7,701.83	0.25%	7,485,574
2027 ,Q3	12,741,249	0.23%	7,748.86	0.61%	7,548,860
2027 ,Q4	12,762,935	0.17%	7,780.00	0.40%	7,592,097
2028 ,Q1	12,775,739	0.10%	7,835.94	0.72%	7,654,358
2028 ,Q2	12,836,614	0.48%	7,841.05	0.07%	7,695,845
2028 ,Q3	12,902,596	0.51%	7,866.14	0.32%	7,760,154
2028 ,Q4	12,906,477	0.03%	7,910.47	0.56%	7,806,228
2029 ,Q1	12,991,647	0.66%	7,948.24	0.48%	7,895,263
2029 ,Q2	13,003,846	0.09%	7,974.16	0.33%	7,928,451
2029 ,Q3	12,967,558	-0.28%	8,057.79	1.05%	7,989,248
2029 ,Q4	13,042,453	0.58%	8,070.52	0.16%	8,048,076
2030 ,Q1	13,048,276	0.04%	8,135.69	0.81%	8,116,693
2030 ,Q2	13,107,930	0.46%	8,151.96	0.20%	8,170,103
2030 ,Q3	13,202,316	0.72%	8,176.42	0.30%	8,253,631
2030 ,Q4	13,130,352	-0.55%	8,217.95	0.51%	8,250,335
2031 ,Q1	13,127,954	-0.02%	8,255.67	0.46%	8,286,686
2031 ,Q2	13,149,232	0.16%	8,270.75	0.18%	8,315,275
2031 ,Q3	13,158,523	0.07%	8,275.77	0.06%	8,326,205
2031 ,Q4	13,237,452	0.60%	8,328.84	0.64%	8,429,865
2032 ,Q1	13,186,773	-0.38%	8,375.93	0.57%	8,445,070
2032 ,Q2	13,270,448	0.63%	8,385.66	0.12%	8,508,528
2032 ,Q3	13,308,919	0.29%	8,416.14	0.36%	8,564,212
2032 ,Q4	13,375,499	0.50%	8,453.91	0.45%	8,645,677
2033 ,Q1	13,387,490	0.09%	8,477.87	0.28%	8,677,952
2033 ,Q2	13,368,898	-0.14%	8,535.71	0.68%	8,725,032
2033 ,Q3	13,366,061	-0.02%	8,564.04	0.33%	8,752,125
2033 ,Q4	13,351,862	-0.11%	8,619.17	0.64%	8,799,106
2034 ,Q1	13,350,753	-0.01%	8,673.67	0.63%	8,854,009
2034 ,Q2	13,366,652	0.12%	8,674.61	0.01%	8,865,516
2034 ,Q3	13,343,387	-0.17%	8,710.20	0.41%	8,886,401
2034 ,Q4	13,358,980	0.12%	8,750.41	0.46%	8,937,857
2035 ,Q1	13,421,103	0.47%	8,748.15	-0.03%	8,977,100
2035 ,Q2	13,477,014	0.42%	8,779.70	0.36%	9,047,009

Mean labour income and working population growth are both simulated in our model. The fourth quarter of 2017 GDP is official data discounted with official inflation indexes and expressed in November 2014 pesos. Working population and labour income growth are computed at a quarterly step.

	Total workers	Working population growth	Mean labour income	Labour income growth	Real GDP (millions of pesos)
2017, Q4	11,190,883		6,736		5,747,025
2035 ,Q3	13,512,216	0.26%	8,796.30	0.19%	9,087,787
2035 ,Q4	13,581,169	0.51%	8,873.10	0.87%	9,213,914
2036 ,Q1	13,484,461	-0.71%	8,946.85	0.83%	9,224,342
2036 ,Q2	13,465,932	-0.14%	9,004.67	0.65%	9,271,199
2036 ,Q3	13,588,712	0.91%	9,003.62	-0.01%	9,354,637
2036 ,Q4	13,594,562	0.04%	9,034.90	0.35%	9,391,181
2037 ,Q1	13,621,440	0.20%	9,103.14	0.76%	9,480,818
2037 ,Q2	13,610,392	-0.08%	9,111.31	0.09%	9,481,628
2037 ,Q3	13,649,032	0.28%	9,128.22	0.19%	9,526,197
2037 ,Q4	13,645,974	-0.02%	9,180.86	0.58%	9,578,978
2038 ,Q1	13,707,158	0.45%	9,201.22	0.22%	9,643,274
2038 ,Q2	13,748,092	0.30%	9,244.63	0.47%	9,717,697
2038 ,Q3	13,754,669	0.05%	9,349.28	1.13%	9,832,409
2038 ,Q4	13,758,759	0.03%	9,390.18	0.44%	9,878,353
2039 ,Q1	13,766,070	0.05%	9,397.10	0.07%	9,890,884
2039 ,Q2	13,779,309	0.10%	9,404.12	0.07%	9,907,801
2039 ,Q3	13,813,609	0.25%	9,454.19	0.53%	9,985,348
2039 ,Q4	13,874,418	0.44%	9,457.22	0.03%	10,032,515
2040 ,Q1	13,854,659	-0.14%	9,544.50	0.92%	10,110,682
2040 ,Q2	13,848,453	-0.04%	9,573.54	0.30%	10,136,909
2040 ,Q3	13,924,031	0.55%	9,582.25	0.09%	10,201,502
2040 ,Q4	13,940,477	0.12%	9,629.75	0.50%	10,264,182

Mean labour income and working population growth are both simulated in our model. The fourth quarter of 2017 GDP is official data discounted with official inflation indexes and expressed in November 2014 pesos. Working population and labour income growth are computed at a quarterly step.

We use these computed GDP figures in order to express our extrapolated future social security contributions, benefits and current transfers as a percent of GDP. Reasoning with GDP points also allows to add non-simulated sources of income and expenses to our analysis, and compute ANSES economic result. Finally, this future real GDP evolution is also used in our estimation of the future evolution of the FGS, whose detail is given in Appendix W.

R.2 Simulated social security contributions, benefits and current transfers by economic scenario (2015-2040)

Our microsimulation model simulates both social security contributions and (most) benefits granted by ANSES. We then take for each period the total value of these variables, extrapolate them using the conversion keys listed in Table 3.5 and compute ANSES "Bismarckian" deficit. Once we express this deficit in GDP points, we get the values we used for making Figure 3.6.

R.2.1 Simulated social security contributions and benefits

First, we compare our simulations of ANSES Social Security Contributions (SSC) and Benefits (SSB) to actual values as reported in ANSES Savings-Investment-Funding (AIF) Account. As we have seen in section 3.1, social security contributions are made by registered wage-earners and independent workers in the Autonomous and Small Independent Workers (or *Monotributo*) regimes. Social security benefits on the other hand are equal to the sum of survivors and retirement pensions granted by ANSES, excluding the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult (PUAM) but including pensions given to Malvinas war veterans. We have given the quarterly values of both SSC and SSB in Tables 3.1 and 3.2 of section 3.1 for years 2014 to 2017. For the sake of comparing our simulated SSC and SSB up to 2040 however, we are more interested in the yearly values of these variables expressed in GDP points. These are listed, over a longer time frame (1993-2017) on Table R.2 below.

Table R.2: ANSES Social Security Contributions (SSC) and Benefits (SSB), % of GDP (1993-2017)

	SSB	SSC		SSB	SSC
1993	5.26%	4.54%	2006	3.64%	2.53%
1994	5.65%	4.12%	2007	4.85%	3.85%
1995	5.36%	3.67%	2008	4.79%	3.69%
1996	5.32%	3.64%	2009	5.63%	5.08%

Source: ANSES Savings-Investment-Funding (AIF) Account (1993-2017), physical-financial monitoring of ANSES expenditure (2005-2017).
 Social Security Benefits exclude additional payments derived from the historical reparation program (computed in Appendix A) as well as Malvinas war veterans pensions, since the former is funded by the FGS and fiscal amnesty penalties and the latter by the federal budget.

	SSB	SSC		SSB	SSC
1997	5.01%	3.50%	2010	5.27%	5.05%
1998	4.92%	2.65%	2011	5.55%	5.16%
1999	5.17%	2.49%	2012	6.34%	5.58%
2000	5.19%	2.36%	2013	6.60%	5.77%
2001	5.25%	2.39%	2014	6.40%	5.42%
2002	4.43%	2.05%	2015	7.34%	5.74%
2003	4.14%	2.05%	2016	7.23%	5.50%
2004	3.67%	1.99%	2017	7.29%	5.49%
2005	3.42%	2.14%			

Source: ANSES Savings-Investment-Funding (AIF) Account (1993-2017), physical-financial monitoring of ANSES expenditure (2005-2017).
Social Security Benefits exclude additional payments derived from the historical reparation program (computed in Appendix A) as well as Malvinas war veterans pensions, since the former is funded by the FGS and fiscal amnesty penalties and the latter by the federal budget.

Figures 1.2 page 50 and 1.3 page 55 give some clues that explain both the evolution of past ANSES SSB and SSC, and we have already discussed the evolution of both these variables in section 1.1.1. Nevertheless, we will make a quick overview of the past evolution of ANSES Social Security Benefits and Contributions for the sake of legibility of the above data.

First of all, we can see between years 1993 and 2001 SSB stagnate at around 5.2% of GDP, while SSC plummet from 4.5% to 2.4% of GDP. The stagnation of SSB is due both to the freeze of retirement pensions at a time where inflation figures were negligible and to the slight decrease in access to a retirement pension for people of retiring age (see Figure 1.3). On the other hand, the fall of SSC is due to both the implementation of a two-pillar retirement system that steered away contributors from the PAYG pillar run by ANSES to a fully-funded pillar (see in particular the fall of contributors per retiree in Figure 1.3) and to the 1998-2002 economic crisis, who decreased levels of formal employment. SSC decreased even further between 2002 and 2005 due to the slow recovery from the crisis. SSB on the other hand sharply decreased between 2002 and 2006 due to the insufficient adjustment of retirement pensions with respect to the high inflation figures of the time (see Figure 1.2) and to decreased pension coverage, which reached its lowest level at the eve of the 2006 pension moratorium (see Figure 1.3). 2007 on the other hand signals the start of an upward trend in both Social Security Contributions and Benefits. SSC increased first in 2007 and 2008 with the possibility for

contributors to opt out of the fully-funded pillar and contribute instead to the PAYG system run by ANSES. By 2009, with private pension funds fully nationalised, all contributions went to ANSES, pushing up SSC to 5% of GDP. Since 2012, these have stabilised at around 5.5% of GDP due to the stagnation of the share of formal wage-earners (see Figure 1.7 page 97) and of their real wage (see Figure 1.2). Between 2006 and 2017 however, SSB have more than doubled. This is due on the one hand to the attainment of a nearly universal pension coverage through the 2006 and 2014 pension moratoriums (see Figure 1.3). On the other hand, retirement pensions started being more substantially adjusted with respect to inflation since 2007. Also, they were (mostly) indexed on formal workers wage evolution between March 2009 and February 2018 following the pension mobility Law 26417. These two elements made ANSES SSB reach 7.3% of GDP in 2015, following the implementation of the 2014 Law 26970 pension moratorium, and stay around that level since. The stagnating values of variables SSB and SSC between 2015 and 2017 are adequately reproduced by our model, as listed in Table R.3 below.

Table R.3: Social Security Contributions and Benefits by economic scenario, % of GDP (2018-2040)

	Social Security Contributions made by...				Social Security Benefits
	Wage-earners	Autonomous workers	<i>Monotributistas</i>	Total	
Low economic scenario					
2015	5.60%	0.15%	0.04%	5.80%	7.80%
2016	5.51%	0.14%	0.03%	5.69%	7.49%
2017	5.44%	0.14%	0.05%	5.64%	7.65%
2018	5.12%	0.14%	0.05%	5.30%	7.38%
2019	4.78%	0.12%	0.05%	4.95%	7.35%
2020	4.44%	0.13%	0.05%	4.62%	7.52%
2021	4.11%	0.13%	0.05%	4.29%	7.55%
2022	3.85%	0.13%	0.05%	4.03%	7.65%
2023	3.82%	0.14%	0.05%	4.01%	7.71%
2024	3.79%	0.14%	0.05%	3.98%	7.70%
2025	3.80%	0.13%	0.05%	3.98%	7.70%
2026	3.74%	0.14%	0.05%	3.94%	7.73%
2027	3.74%	0.14%	0.05%	3.93%	7.72%
2028	3.73%	0.14%	0.05%	3.92%	7.64%
2029	3.72%	0.14%	0.05%	3.91%	7.64%
2030	3.70%	0.14%	0.05%	3.89%	7.63%
2031	3.67%	0.14%	0.05%	3.87%	7.60%
2032	3.67%	0.14%	0.05%	3.87%	7.63%
2033	3.62%	0.15%	0.06%	3.83%	7.72%
2034	3.61%	0.15%	0.05%	3.81%	7.78%
2035	3.56%	0.15%	0.06%	3.76%	7.85%

	Social Security Contributions made by...				Social Security Benefits
	Wage-earners	Autonomous workers	<i>Monotributistas</i>	Total	
2036	3.52%	0.16%	0.06%	3.74%	7.82%
2037	3.50%	0.15%	0.06%	3.71%	7.87%
2038	3.47%	0.15%	0.06%	3.68%	7.82%
2039	3.49%	0.15%	0.06%	3.70%	7.87%
2040	3.47%	0.16%	0.06%	3.69%	7.85%
Central economic scenario					
2015	5.60%	0.15%	0.04%	5.80%	7.80%
2016	5.51%	0.14%	0.03%	5.69%	7.49%
2017	5.44%	0.14%	0.05%	5.64%	7.65%
2018	5.12%	0.14%	0.05%	5.30%	7.38%
2019	4.79%	0.12%	0.05%	4.96%	7.32%
2020	4.47%	0.13%	0.05%	4.65%	7.42%
2021	4.16%	0.13%	0.05%	4.34%	7.38%
2022	3.92%	0.13%	0.05%	4.10%	7.39%
2023	3.94%	0.12%	0.05%	4.11%	7.37%
2024	3.93%	0.12%	0.05%	4.11%	7.34%
2025	3.92%	0.13%	0.05%	4.10%	7.30%
2026	3.95%	0.13%	0.05%	4.12%	7.25%
2027	3.94%	0.12%	0.05%	4.12%	7.09%
2028	3.97%	0.12%	0.05%	4.14%	6.98%
2029	3.97%	0.12%	0.05%	4.14%	6.93%
2030	3.95%	0.13%	0.05%	4.12%	6.91%
2031	3.95%	0.12%	0.05%	4.12%	6.82%
2032	3.95%	0.12%	0.05%	4.12%	6.83%
2033	3.96%	0.12%	0.05%	4.12%	6.80%
2034	3.95%	0.12%	0.05%	4.12%	6.80%
2035	3.96%	0.12%	0.05%	4.13%	6.70%
2036	3.98%	0.12%	0.05%	4.14%	6.63%
2037	3.97%	0.13%	0.05%	4.14%	6.60%
2038	3.98%	0.12%	0.05%	4.14%	6.60%
2039	3.95%	0.12%	0.05%	4.12%	6.63%
2040	3.94%	0.12%	0.05%	4.11%	6.58%
High economic scenario					
2015	5.60%	0.15%	0.04%	5.80%	7.80%
2016	5.51%	0.14%	0.03%	5.69%	7.49%
2017	5.44%	0.14%	0.05%	5.64%	7.65%
2018	5.12%	0.14%	0.05%	5.30%	7.38%
2019	4.80%	0.12%	0.05%	4.97%	7.27%
2020	4.51%	0.13%	0.05%	4.68%	7.27%
2021	4.22%	0.12%	0.05%	4.38%	7.19%
2022	3.99%	0.12%	0.05%	4.16%	7.09%
2023	4.01%	0.12%	0.05%	4.18%	7.03%
2024	4.03%	0.12%	0.05%	4.19%	6.92%
2025	4.04%	0.12%	0.04%	4.21%	6.82%
2026	4.08%	0.11%	0.04%	4.24%	6.66%

	Social Security Contributions made by...				Social Security Benefits
	Wage-earners	Autonomous workers	<i>Monotributistas</i>	Total	
2027	4.10%	0.11%	0.04%	4.25%	6.50%
2028	4.11%	0.11%	0.04%	4.26%	6.36%
2029	4.15%	0.11%	0.04%	4.30%	6.21%
2030	4.18%	0.12%	0.04%	4.34%	6.11%
2031	4.21%	0.11%	0.04%	4.36%	6.06%
2032	4.22%	0.11%	0.04%	4.37%	6.00%
2033	4.24%	0.11%	0.04%	4.39%	5.93%
2034	4.28%	0.11%	0.04%	4.43%	5.88%
2035	4.28%	0.10%	0.04%	4.42%	5.83%
2036	4.31%	0.11%	0.04%	4.45%	5.77%
2037	4.34%	0.10%	0.04%	4.48%	5.71%
2038	4.38%	0.09%	0.04%	4.51%	5.59%
2039	4.39%	0.10%	0.04%	4.53%	5.59%
2040	4.41%	0.09%	0.04%	4.54%	5.58%

We can see first of all that the gradual reduction of employers contributions will make SSC reach their lowest value in 2022 across all economic scenarios, decreasing between 1.6% and 1.8% of GDP between 2015 and 2022. After that, only the optimistic economic scenario will see a recovery of SSC as a percentage of GDP, following strong increases in real wages and in the share of formal wage-earners. We can thus see this decrease in employers contributions strongly reduces ANSES income, which endangers the agency’s short and long term sustainability. Social Security Benefits as a percentage of GDP on the other hand linearly decrease in all scenarios. This is mostly due to the institution of the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult (PUAM) since 2016 for men and 2019 for (most) women, which is not paid *de jure* by ANSES. The PUAM’s future projected cost by economic scenario is taken into account in Table R.8, at the end of this Appendix. On the other hand, the new Law 27426 pension mobility formula indexes pensions only by 30% on nominal wages. Therefore, the fastest real wages (and thus the economy, following our growth formula) grows, the smaller the share of SSB as a percent of GDP. In our simulations, SSB as a percentage of GDP decrease by 1.2% and 2.2% of GDP in the central and high economic scenarios between 2015 and 2040, while in the low scenario SSB (excluding the universal pension PUAM) increase by 0.1%.

Finally, we list in Table R.4 the simulated cost of the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult (PUAM), introduced by the 2016 historical reparation Law 27260. Although *de jure* funded by the national budget, this institutional arrangement is unlikely to be maintained in the long run. We thus also compute ANSES Bismarckian balance and

economic result assuming it is the agency that will have to pay for the PUAM. Logically, the cost of this universal pension linearly increases over time as it gradually becomes the only non-contributive benefit available for the elderly with incomplete careers. The share of GDP this pension ends up representing is dependent on the chosen economic scenario. First, because it is indexed mostly on the Consumer Price Index (70%) and only by 30% on the formal wage index RIPTE as per the 2017 pension mobility Law 27426. Thus, assuming long-term GDP growth follows labour productivity (and thus wages) as in our long-term GDP growth model, the faster real wages (and the GDP) grow, the smaller the GDP share of the PUAM. Second, because the PUAM is targeted at the elderly with incomplete careers. The better the economic situation witnessed in the 2014-2040 period, the lower the proportion of seniors with incomplete formal careers, and thus the lower the cost of the PUAM. Therefore, by 2040 the PUAM respectively represents 2.5%, 1.9% and 1.5% of GDP in our low, central and high economic scenarios.

Table R.4: Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult (PUAM) as a percentage of GDP, by economic scenario (2016-2040)

	Low scenario	Central scenario	High scenario
2016	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
2017	0.05%	0.05%	0.05%
2018	0.09%	0.09%	0.09%
2019	0.12%	0.12%	0.12%
2020	0.17%	0.16%	0.16%
2021	0.20%	0.20%	0.19%
2022	0.25%	0.24%	0.23%
2023	0.29%	0.27%	0.26%
2024	0.33%	0.32%	0.30%
2025	0.45%	0.42%	0.40%
2026	0.58%	0.52%	0.49%
2027	0.73%	0.63%	0.59%
2028	0.86%	0.75%	0.68%
2029	0.99%	0.87%	0.77%
2030	1.11%	0.96%	0.84%
2031	1.22%	1.04%	0.91%
2032	1.35%	1.15%	0.99%
2033	1.48%	1.24%	1.05%
2034	1.61%	1.33%	1.12%
2035	1.75%	1.40%	1.17%
2036	1.88%	1.48%	1.23%
2037	2.03%	1.58%	1.30%
2038	2.18%	1.70%	1.36%
2039	2.33%	1.81%	1.43%
2040	2.49%	1.93%	1.48%

R.2.2 Family benefits and pensioners healthcare contributions: past and projected figures (2004-2040)

Next, we give here the detail of ANSES family benefits and PAMI transfers. We have said in section 3.1.1 that we extrapolate ANSES family benefits expenditure on data from the physical-financial monitoring of ANSES. This dataset provides the highest level of detail in what regards quarterly expenses on family benefits. We have also shown in the same section that the "current transfers" item on the expenditures side of ANSES Savings-Investment-Funding (AIF) Account was the sum of various elements. First, we take the sum of family benefits (for the active, inactive and the AUH), complements to retirement benefits, unemployment pensions, family benefits for national civil servants and PROGRESAR benefits from the physical-financial monitoring of ANSES accounts. We then take from ANSES Investment Account the sum of current transfers to the public and external sectors as well as health transfers paid by ANSES (healthcare contributions by pensioners to the PAMI). The sum of these two terms equals current transfers to ANSES in the AIF Account. We have explained in section 3.1.1 that our model simulates family benefits and healthcare contributions made by retirement pensioners. Unemployment benefits and complements to retirement pensions are negligible in later dates and thus enter the computation of the conversion key, in order to get a more accurate aggregate value of ANSES current transfers. Finally, other current transfers are treated separately in section 3.2.1. Therefore, we list here the detail of simulated family benefits and PAMI contributions. First, in Table R.5 we present past values of ANSES family benefits and contributions to the PAMI. Then, in Table R.6 we present our simulated family benefits and healthcare contributions as a percentage of future GDP by economic scenario. This means column (7) of Table R.6 is calibrated on column (6) of Table R.5 and should therefore be compared to it in order to gauge the accuracy of our family benefits simulation.

Table R.5: ANSES current transfers to the private sector by type, % of GDP (2004-2017)

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
2004	0.19%	0.00%	0.17%	0.35%	0.15%	0.50%
2005	0.28%	0.00%	0.10%	0.38%	0.14%	0.51%
2006	0.28%	0.00%	0.12%	0.39%	0.14%	0.54%
2007	0.34%	0.00%	0.06%	0.40%	0.18%	0.59%

(1): Contributive family benefits; (2): Universal Child Benefit and Pregnancy Benefit for Social Protection; (3): Unemployment benefit and complements to retirement benefits; (4): Current social security transfers (excluding conectar igualdad, PROGRESAR, family benefits for national civil servants); (5): Pensioners' healthcare contributions; (6): (4)+(5).

Table R.5: ANSES current transfers to the private sector by type, % of GDP (2004-2017)

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
2008	0.41%	0.00%	0.13%	0.55%	0.18%	0.72%
2009	0.60%	0.00%	0.18%	0.78%	0.20%	0.99%
2010	0.61%	0.38%	0.18%	1.17%	0.19%	1.36%
2011	0.57%	0.41%	0.04%	1.03%	0.20%	1.23%
2012	0.50%	0.42%	0.03%	0.96%	0.23%	1.19%
2013	0.52%	0.47%	0.03%	1.02%	0.24%	1.26%
2014	0.52%	0.48%	0.03%	1.03%	0.23%	1.27%
2015	0.52%	0.58%	0.04%	1.14%	0.27%	1.41%
2016	0.66%	0.62%	0.09%	1.37%	0.26%	1.64%
2017	0.74%	0.57%	0.04%	1.35%	0.29%	1.64%

(1): Contributive family benefits; (2): Universal Child Benefit and Pregnancy Benefit for Social Protection; (3): Unemployment benefit and complements to retirement benefits; (4): Current social security transfers (excluding conectar igualdad, PROGRESAR, family benefits for national civil servants); (5): Pensioners' healthcare contributions; (6): (4)+(5).

These historical values show family benefits and healthcare contributions to the PAMI as a percentage of GDP increased sharply since 2004. Contributive child benefits (column (1)) nearly quadrupled their GDP share, the AUH and the Pregnancy Benefit for Social Protection represent around 0.6% of GDP since 2015 and healthcare contributions to the PAMI nearly doubled in the period. On the other hand, the share of unemployment expenses and complementary pensions to the retired plummeted, mostly due to their non indexation with inflation figures. Finally, family benefits jumped an additional 0.2% of GDP in years 2016 and 2017 following mostly the extension of family benefits to the children of small independent workers (*monotributistas*) and the increase of income limits to get contributive child benefits as well as their indexation on the pension mobility formula, as seen in section 1.1. Table R.6 below shows our model broadly reproduces the aggregate value of family benefits and pensioners contributions to the PAMI for years 2015 and 2017.

Table R.6: Family benefits as a percent of GDP, by economic scenario (2018-2040)

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
Low scenario							
2015	0.49%	0.32%	0.05%	0.10%	0.96%	0.32%	1.28%
2016	0.44%	0.45%	0.05%	0.11%	1.06%	0.31%	1.37%

(1): Universal Child Benefit and Pregnancy Benefit for Social Protection; (2): Contributive child and pre-natal benefits; (3): School aid; (4): Spouse and wedding benefits; (5): Total family benefits; (6): Pensioners' healthcare contributions; (7): Current Transfers to the Private Sector.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
2017	0.46%	0.71%	0.07%	0.13%	1.37%	0.32%	1.69%
2018	0.40%	0.59%	0.06%	0.12%	1.17%	0.31%	1.48%
2019	0.36%	0.53%	0.05%	0.11%	1.06%	0.31%	1.36%
2020	0.36%	0.51%	0.05%	0.11%	1.04%	0.32%	1.36%
2021	0.35%	0.51%	0.05%	0.11%	1.01%	0.32%	1.34%
2022	0.34%	0.51%	0.05%	0.10%	1.00%	0.33%	1.33%
2023	0.34%	0.49%	0.05%	0.10%	0.99%	0.34%	1.32%
2024	0.33%	0.48%	0.05%	0.10%	0.96%	0.34%	1.30%
2025	0.34%	0.47%	0.05%	0.10%	0.95%	0.34%	1.30%
2026	0.33%	0.47%	0.05%	0.09%	0.94%	0.35%	1.28%
2027	0.33%	0.46%	0.05%	0.09%	0.93%	0.35%	1.28%
2028	0.32%	0.46%	0.05%	0.09%	0.91%	0.35%	1.26%
2029	0.32%	0.45%	0.05%	0.09%	0.91%	0.35%	1.26%
2030	0.31%	0.45%	0.05%	0.09%	0.89%	0.35%	1.25%
2031	0.32%	0.45%	0.05%	0.09%	0.90%	0.36%	1.26%
2032	0.28%	0.47%	0.04%	0.08%	0.87%	0.36%	1.23%
2033	0.28%	0.46%	0.04%	0.08%	0.87%	0.37%	1.24%
2034	0.28%	0.45%	0.05%	0.08%	0.86%	0.37%	1.23%
2035	0.27%	0.48%	0.05%	0.08%	0.88%	0.38%	1.26%
2036	0.30%	0.45%	0.05%	0.08%	0.87%	0.38%	1.25%
2037	0.28%	0.47%	0.05%	0.08%	0.88%	0.38%	1.26%
2038	0.29%	0.46%	0.05%	0.08%	0.89%	0.38%	1.26%
2039	0.29%	0.46%	0.05%	0.08%	0.87%	0.38%	1.26%
2040	0.29%	0.45%	0.05%	0.08%	0.87%	0.38%	1.25%
Central scenario							
2015	0.49%	0.32%	0.05%	0.10%	0.96%	0.32%	1.28%
2016	0.44%	0.45%	0.05%	0.11%	1.06%	0.31%	1.37%
2017	0.46%	0.71%	0.07%	0.13%	1.37%	0.32%	1.69%
2018	0.40%	0.59%	0.06%	0.12%	1.17%	0.31%	1.48%
2019	0.36%	0.52%	0.05%	0.11%	1.04%	0.31%	1.35%
2020	0.35%	0.50%	0.05%	0.11%	1.01%	0.31%	1.32%
2021	0.33%	0.49%	0.05%	0.10%	0.97%	0.32%	1.29%
2022	0.32%	0.47%	0.05%	0.10%	0.94%	0.32%	1.26%
2023	0.32%	0.45%	0.05%	0.10%	0.91%	0.32%	1.24%
2024	0.31%	0.45%	0.05%	0.09%	0.89%	0.32%	1.22%
2025	0.29%	0.45%	0.05%	0.09%	0.87%	0.33%	1.19%
2026	0.28%	0.43%	0.04%	0.09%	0.84%	0.33%	1.16%
2027	0.25%	0.42%	0.04%	0.08%	0.80%	0.32%	1.12%
2028	0.25%	0.39%	0.04%	0.08%	0.76%	0.32%	1.08%
2029	0.23%	0.40%	0.04%	0.08%	0.75%	0.32%	1.07%
2030	0.24%	0.38%	0.04%	0.08%	0.73%	0.32%	1.05%
2031	0.21%	0.37%	0.04%	0.07%	0.69%	0.32%	1.01%
2032	0.21%	0.36%	0.04%	0.07%	0.69%	0.32%	1.01%
2033	0.22%	0.36%	0.04%	0.07%	0.68%	0.32%	1.01%
(1): Universal Child Benefit and Pregnancy Benefit for Social Protection; (2): Contributive child and pre-natal benefits; (3): School aid; (4): Spouse and wedding benefits; (5): Total family benefits; (6): Pensioners' healthcare contributions; (7): Current Transfers to the Private Sector.							

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
2034	0.22%	0.36%	0.04%	0.07%	0.68%	0.33%	1.01%
2035	0.20%	0.34%	0.04%	0.07%	0.65%	0.32%	0.97%
2036	0.18%	0.34%	0.04%	0.07%	0.62%	0.32%	0.94%
2037	0.18%	0.33%	0.04%	0.07%	0.62%	0.32%	0.94%
2038	0.18%	0.33%	0.03%	0.07%	0.61%	0.32%	0.94%
2039	0.18%	0.33%	0.03%	0.07%	0.61%	0.33%	0.93%
2040	0.18%	0.31%	0.03%	0.07%	0.60%	0.33%	0.92%
High scenario							
2015	0.49%	0.32%	0.05%	0.10%	0.96%	0.32%	1.28%
2016	0.44%	0.45%	0.05%	0.11%	1.06%	0.31%	1.37%
2017	0.46%	0.71%	0.07%	0.13%	1.37%	0.32%	1.69%
2018	0.40%	0.59%	0.06%	0.12%	1.17%	0.31%	1.48%
2019	0.35%	0.52%	0.05%	0.11%	1.03%	0.31%	1.34%
2020	0.33%	0.50%	0.05%	0.10%	0.98%	0.31%	1.29%
2021	0.31%	0.47%	0.05%	0.10%	0.93%	0.31%	1.24%
2022	0.29%	0.45%	0.05%	0.10%	0.88%	0.31%	1.19%
2023	0.29%	0.42%	0.05%	0.09%	0.84%	0.31%	1.15%
2024	0.27%	0.41%	0.04%	0.09%	0.80%	0.31%	1.11%
2025	0.25%	0.39%	0.04%	0.08%	0.76%	0.30%	1.07%
2026	0.24%	0.37%	0.04%	0.08%	0.73%	0.30%	1.03%
2027	0.21%	0.35%	0.04%	0.08%	0.68%	0.30%	0.97%
2028	0.20%	0.35%	0.04%	0.07%	0.65%	0.29%	0.94%
2029	0.19%	0.32%	0.03%	0.07%	0.62%	0.29%	0.91%
2030	0.18%	0.31%	0.03%	0.07%	0.58%	0.28%	0.87%
2031	0.18%	0.29%	0.03%	0.07%	0.56%	0.28%	0.84%
2032	0.16%	0.28%	0.03%	0.06%	0.54%	0.28%	0.82%
2033	0.16%	0.28%	0.03%	0.06%	0.52%	0.28%	0.81%
2034	0.14%	0.27%	0.03%	0.06%	0.50%	0.28%	0.78%
2035	0.14%	0.26%	0.03%	0.06%	0.48%	0.28%	0.76%
2036	0.12%	0.25%	0.03%	0.06%	0.45%	0.28%	0.73%
2037	0.12%	0.23%	0.03%	0.06%	0.43%	0.28%	0.71%
2038	0.11%	0.22%	0.02%	0.06%	0.41%	0.28%	0.69%
2039	0.11%	0.21%	0.02%	0.05%	0.39%	0.28%	0.67%
2040	0.10%	0.21%	0.02%	0.05%	0.38%	0.28%	0.66%
(1): Universal Child Benefit and Pregnancy Benefit for Social Protection; (2): Contributive child and pre-natal benefits; (3): School aid; (4): Spouse and wedding benefits; (5): Total family benefits; (6): Pensioners' healthcare contributions; (7): Current Transfers to the Private Sector.							

Table R.6 however also shows other interesting evolutions. Indeed, not only our simulated family benefits and PAMI contributions are close on aggregate levels to their observed values for years 2015 to 2017. We also see that family benefits as a percentage of GDP sharply diminish over time with May 2018 legislation. This is due first of all to the demographic hypotheses of our model which include the ageing of Argentina's population. Also, our long-term economic hypotheses assume in all scenarios increased real wages and labour formality. This last element causes families to no longer be eligible to

the AUH, which explains its significant fall in all economic scenarios. The increase in real wages however also bars the access to contributive family benefits to an increased number of formal workers children the fastest we assume real wages will grow. This is because means-tested conditions for access to the various contributive child benefits are indexed on the Law 27426 pension mobility formula. Since this formula follows the Consumer Price Index by 70% and the RIPTE (Taxable Income of Stable Workers) by 30%, means conditions to get access to a family benefit become more and more difficult to reach for formal wage-earners. They thus get reduced pensions or stop having access to them even if their position in the income scale did not change. Finally, since all family benefits are indexed on the Law 27426 pension mobility formula their weight on Argentina's GDP decreases the most the fastest real wages (and thus the economy, in the long term) grow. This explains why simulated ANSES family benefits significantly differ from one economic scenario to the other. Between the low, central and high scenarios, their GDP share respectively reach 0.9%, 0.6% and 0.4% of GDP.

R.3 ANSES "Bismarckian" deficit and economic result

Finally, we list in Table R.8 ANSES projected "Bismarckian" deficit and economic result for the 2015-2040 period. In Table R.7, we list these for years 1993 to 2017. We refrain from commenting these values in this Appendix since they are exactly those used in Figures 3.6 page 357 and 3.7 page 373, so their analysis can be found there. The "Bismarckian" deficit is computed using Tables R.3, R.4 and R.6, while the economic result also uses non-simulated income and expenses listed in Tables T.1 and T.2. We also put our simulations of ANSES Bismarckian balance and economic result with our counter-factual legislative scenarios described in Table 3.8 (November 2017 legislation, December 2015 rules with permanent pension moratoriums, strict December 2015 legislation). The detailed computation of these counter-factual legislative scenarios economic results, as well as the excel files we use for computing ANSES economic result, are available on-line¹.

Table R.7: ANSES historical "Bismarckian" deficit and economic result (1993-2017)

	Bismarckian deficit	Economic result		Bismarckian deficit	Economic result
1993	-1.77%	-0.04%	2006	-1.65%	0.92%
1994	-2.66%	-1.31%	2007	-1.59%	1.08%
Values are in GDP points. Sources: see Figure 1.1, and Tables T.1 and T.2.					

¹We use the Zenodo archiving service for long-term preservation of our code. The DOI link is: 10.5281/zenodo.1420273

Table R.7: ANSES historical "Bismarckian" deficit and economic result (1993-2017)

	Bismarckian deficit	Economic result		Bismarckian deficit	Economic result
1995	-2.23%	-0.64%	2008	-1.83%	0.47%
1996	-2.33%	-0.53%	2009	-1.57%	0.35%
1997	-2.08%	-0.32%	2010	-1.58%	0.41%
1998	-2.71%	-0.27%	2011	-1.62%	0.33%
1999	-3.22%	-0.78%	2012	-1.95%	0.11%
2000	-3.38%	-0.67%	2013	-2.11%	-0.10%
2001	-3.43%	-1.02%	2014	-2.17%	-0.13%
2002	-2.97%	-1.14%	2015	-2.88%	-0.76%
2003	-2.78%	-0.49%	2016	-3.23%	-1.61%
2004	-2.19%	0.38%	2017	-3.32%	-1.47%
2005	-1.79%	0.76%			

Values are in GDP points. Sources: see Figure 1.1, and Tables T.1 and T.2.

Table R.8: ANSES simulated "Bismarckian" deficit and economic result with May 2018 legislation (2015-2040)

	Central scenario		Low scenario		High scenario	
	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
ANSES "Bismarckian" balance						
2015	-3.28%					
2016	-3.17%	-3.17%				
2017	-3.70%	-3.75%	-3.70%	-3.74%	-3.70%	-3.75%
2018	-3.56%	-3.65%	-3.62%	-3.70%	-3.55%	-3.64%
2019	-3.72%	-3.84%	-3.89%	-4.01%	-3.64%	-3.76%
2020	-4.09%	-4.26%	-4.36%	-4.52%	-3.88%	-4.04%
2021	-4.33%	-4.53%	-4.69%	-4.89%	-4.05%	-4.24%
2022	-4.55%	-4.79%	-5.04%	-5.29%	-4.12%	-4.35%
2023	-4.50%	-4.77%	-5.11%	-5.40%	-4.00%	-4.26%
2024	-4.46%	-4.77%	-5.10%	-5.43%	-3.84%	-4.14%
2025	-4.40%	-4.82%	-5.09%	-5.54%	-3.67%	-4.07%
2026	-4.29%	-4.81%	-5.15%	-5.74%	-3.45%	-3.94%
2027	-4.10%	-4.73%	-5.14%	-5.87%	-3.23%	-3.81%
2028	-3.92%	-4.67%	-5.08%	-5.93%	-3.04%	-3.72%
2029	-3.87%	-4.73%	-5.05%	-6.04%	-2.82%	-3.59%
2030	-3.84%	-4.80%	-5.08%	-6.18%	-2.65%	-3.49%
2031	-3.72%	-4.76%	-5.06%	-6.28%	-2.54%	-3.46%
2032	-3.72%	-4.87%	-5.07%	-6.42%	-2.45%	-3.44%
2033	-3.69%	-4.92%	-5.20%	-6.68%	-2.35%	-3.40%
2034	-3.69%	-5.02%	-5.30%	-6.91%	-2.24%	-3.36%

Values are in GDP points. The 2016 historical reparation Law 27260 creates the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult (PUAM) and stops detracting 15% of *coparticipable* taxes to fund ANSES. In return, it states the national budget must fund the PUAM, and that it also must compensate ANSES for the missing *coparticipation* income. Transfers from the national budget are usually not a perennial source of income. Thus, in (1) we assume the federal budget funds these Law 27260 measures; and in (2) we assume it is ANSES that has to fund them.

	Central scenario		Low scenario		High scenario	
	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
2035	-3.55%	-4.95%	-5.40%	-7.15%	-2.17%	-3.34%
2036	-3.43%	-4.90%	-5.39%	-7.27%	-2.05%	-3.28%
2037	-3.40%	-4.98%	-5.46%	-7.50%	-1.94%	-3.24%
2038	-3.39%	-5.09%	-5.44%	-7.62%	-1.76%	-3.13%
2039	-3.44%	-5.25%	-5.47%	-7.81%	-1.74%	-3.17%
2040	-3.39%	-5.32%	-5.45%	-7.93%	-1.71%	-3.19%
ANSES full economic result						
2015	-1.15%					
2016	-1.30%	-1.30%				
2017	-1.76%	-2.44%	-1.76%	-2.44%	-1.76%	-2.44%
2018	-1.30%	-2.31%	-1.36%	-2.37%	-1.30%	-2.31%
2019	-1.87%	-3.22%	-2.04%	-3.40%	-1.79%	-3.14%
2020	-2.58%	-4.28%	-2.84%	-4.55%	-2.36%	-4.06%
2021	-3.14%	-4.88%	-3.51%	-5.25%	-2.87%	-4.59%
2022	-3.70%	-5.48%	-4.18%	-5.97%	-3.27%	-5.03%
2023	-3.65%	-5.46%	-4.26%	-6.08%	-3.15%	-4.95%
2024	-3.60%	-5.46%	-4.25%	-6.12%	-2.98%	-4.82%
2025	-3.55%	-5.50%	-4.24%	-6.23%	-2.82%	-4.76%
2026	-3.44%	-5.49%	-4.30%	-6.42%	-2.60%	-4.63%
2027	-3.24%	-5.41%	-4.29%	-6.55%	-2.37%	-4.50%
2028	-2.91%	-5.20%	-4.07%	-6.46%	-2.03%	-4.25%
2029	-2.86%	-5.26%	-4.04%	-6.56%	-1.81%	-4.12%
2030	-2.83%	-5.33%	-4.07%	-6.71%	-1.64%	-4.02%
2031	-2.71%	-5.29%	-4.05%	-6.81%	-1.53%	-3.98%
2032	-2.71%	-5.39%	-4.06%	-6.95%	-1.45%	-3.97%
2033	-2.68%	-5.45%	-4.20%	-7.21%	-1.34%	-3.92%
2034	-2.69%	-5.55%	-4.29%	-7.44%	-1.23%	-3.88%
2035	-2.54%	-5.47%	-4.39%	-7.68%	-1.16%	-3.87%
2036	-2.42%	-5.43%	-4.39%	-7.80%	-1.04%	-3.81%
2037	-2.39%	-5.51%	-4.45%	-8.02%	-0.93%	-3.77%
2038	-2.38%	-5.61%	-4.43%	-8.14%	-0.75%	-3.65%
2039	-2.43%	-5.78%	-4.46%	-8.33%	-0.73%	-3.69%
2040	-2.38%	-5.84%	-4.44%	-8.46%	-0.70%	-3.72%
ANSES full economic result, no further "Check" tax reduction						
2015	-1.15%					
2016	-1.30%					
2017	-1.76%	-2.44%	-1.76%	-2.44%	-1.76%	-2.44%
2018	-1.30%	-2.31%	-1.36%	-2.37%	-1.30%	-2.31%
2019	-1.59%	-2.94%	-1.76%	-3.11%	-1.51%	-2.86%
2020	-1.96%	-3.67%	-2.23%	-3.93%	-1.75%	-3.45%
<p>Values are in GDP points. The 2016 historical reparation Law 27260 creates the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult (PUAM) and stops detracting 15% of <i>coparticipable</i> taxes to fund ANSES. In return, it states the national budget must fund the PUAM, and that it also must compensate ANSES for the missing <i>coparticipation</i> income. Transfers from the national budget are usually not a perennial source of income. Thus, in (1) we assume the federal budget funds these Law 27260 measures; and in (2) we assume it is ANSES that has to fund them.</p>						

	Central scenario		Low scenario		High scenario	
	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
2021	-2.20%	-3.93%	-2.56%	-4.30%	-1.92%	-3.65%
2022	-2.43%	-4.20%	-2.91%	-4.70%	-1.99%	-3.76%
2023	-2.37%	-4.18%	-2.98%	-4.81%	-1.87%	-3.67%
2024	-2.33%	-4.18%	-2.97%	-4.84%	-1.71%	-3.54%
2025	-2.27%	-4.23%	-2.96%	-4.95%	-1.54%	-3.48%
2026	-2.16%	-4.22%	-3.02%	-5.14%	-1.32%	-3.35%
2027	-1.97%	-4.14%	-3.01%	-5.27%	-1.10%	-3.22%
2028	-1.64%	-3.92%	-2.79%	-5.18%	-0.76%	-2.98%
2029	-1.58%	-3.99%	-2.77%	-5.29%	-0.53%	-2.85%
2030	-1.56%	-4.05%	-2.79%	-5.43%	-0.37%	-2.74%
2031	-1.44%	-4.02%	-2.78%	-5.53%	-0.26%	-2.71%
2032	-1.44%	-4.12%	-2.79%	-5.67%	-0.17%	-2.70%
2033	-1.40%	-4.17%	-2.92%	-5.93%	-0.07%	-2.65%
2034	-1.41%	-4.28%	-3.02%	-6.16%	0.05%	-2.61%
2035	-1.27%	-4.20%	-3.12%	-6.40%	0.11%	-2.60%
2036	-1.14%	-4.15%	-3.11%	-6.53%	0.23%	-2.54%
2037	-1.11%	-4.23%	-3.18%	-6.75%	0.35%	-2.49%
2038	-1.11%	-4.34%	-3.16%	-6.87%	0.52%	-2.38%
2039	-1.16%	-4.50%	-3.19%	-7.06%	0.55%	-2.42%
2040	-1.10%	-4.57%	-3.16%	-7.19%	0.58%	-2.44%

Values are in GDP points. The 2016 historical reparation Law 27260 creates the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult (PUAM) and stops detracting 15% of *coparticipable* taxes to fund ANSES. In return, it states the national budget must fund the PUAM, and that it also must compensate ANSES for the missing *coparticipation* income. Transfers from the national budget are usually not a perennial source of income. Thus, in (1) we assume the federal budget funds these Law 27260 measures; and in (2) we assume it is ANSES that has to fund them.

Table R.9: ANSES simulated "Bismarckian" deficit and economic result with November 2017 legislation (2015-2040)

	Central scenario		Low scenario		High scenario	
	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
ANSES "Bismarckian" balance						
2015	-3.28%					
2016	-3.17%	-3.17%				
2017	-3.70%	-3.75%	-3.70%	-3.75%	-3.70%	-3.75%
2018	-3.25%	-3.34%	-3.23%	-3.32%	-3.24%	-3.33%
2019	-3.10%	-3.23%	-3.07%	-3.19%	-3.05%	-3.18%
2020	-3.27%	-3.44%	-3.30%	-3.47%	-3.15%	-3.31%

Values are in GDP points. The 2016 historical reparation Law 27260 creates the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult (PUAM) and stops detracting 15% of *coparticipable* taxes to fund ANSES. In return, it states the national budget must fund the PUAM, and that it also must compensate ANSES for the missing *coparticipation* income. Transfers from the national budget are usually not a perennial source of income. Thus, in (1) we assume the federal budget funds these Law 27260 measures; and in (2) we assume it is ANSES that has to fund them.

	Central scenario		Low scenario		High scenario	
	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
2021	-3.22%	-3.43%	-3.25%	-3.46%	-3.02%	-3.22%
2022	-3.19%	-3.44%	-3.26%	-3.51%	-3.00%	-3.24%
2023	-3.13%	-3.41%	-3.30%	-3.59%	-2.87%	-3.14%
2024	-3.12%	-3.46%	-3.45%	-3.79%	-2.78%	-3.10%
2025	-3.09%	-3.53%	-3.43%	-3.90%	-2.67%	-3.09%
2026	-3.02%	-3.57%	-3.41%	-4.00%	-2.59%	-3.12%
2027	-2.98%	-3.67%	-3.36%	-4.08%	-2.51%	-3.16%
2028	-2.97%	-3.79%	-3.42%	-4.29%	-2.37%	-3.14%
2029	-2.91%	-3.85%	-3.43%	-4.42%	-2.22%	-3.09%
2030	-2.80%	-3.83%	-3.37%	-4.48%	-2.15%	-3.10%
2031	-2.74%	-3.86%	-3.46%	-4.67%	-2.12%	-3.16%
2032	-2.66%	-3.87%	-3.56%	-4.91%	-2.01%	-3.15%
2033	-2.67%	-4.00%	-3.58%	-5.04%	-1.94%	-3.18%
2034	-2.67%	-4.11%	-3.54%	-5.11%	-1.89%	-3.22%
2035	-2.65%	-4.19%	-3.65%	-5.36%	-1.77%	-3.17%
2036	-2.71%	-4.38%	-3.64%	-5.47%	-1.68%	-3.16%
2037	-2.64%	-4.43%	-3.69%	-5.65%	-1.64%	-3.22%
2038	-2.63%	-4.55%	-3.81%	-5.94%	-1.57%	-3.25%
2039	-2.62%	-4.66%	-3.79%	-6.06%	-1.55%	-3.32%
2040	-2.59%	-4.76%	-3.83%	-6.29%	-1.54%	-3.38%

ANSES economic result

2015	-1.15%					
2016	-1.30%	-1.61%				
2017	-1.76%	-2.44%	-1.76%	-2.44%	-1.76%	-2.44%
2018	-1.35%	-2.36%	-1.33%	-2.34%	-1.35%	-2.36%
2019	-1.21%	-2.56%	-1.17%	-2.53%	-1.16%	-2.51%
2020	-1.38%	-3.08%	-1.41%	-3.11%	-1.25%	-2.95%
2021	-1.33%	-3.07%	-1.35%	-3.10%	-1.12%	-2.86%
2022	-1.30%	-3.08%	-1.36%	-3.15%	-1.11%	-2.88%
2023	-1.23%	-3.06%	-1.40%	-3.23%	-0.97%	-2.78%
2024	-1.23%	-3.10%	-1.55%	-3.43%	-0.88%	-2.74%
2025	-1.19%	-3.17%	-1.54%	-3.54%	-0.77%	-2.73%
2026	-1.12%	-3.21%	-1.51%	-3.64%	-0.70%	-2.76%
2027	-1.09%	-3.31%	-1.47%	-3.72%	-0.61%	-2.80%
2028	-0.92%	-3.27%	-1.37%	-3.77%	-0.32%	-2.62%
2029	-0.86%	-3.34%	-1.38%	-3.91%	-0.17%	-2.57%
2030	-0.75%	-3.31%	-1.32%	-3.97%	-0.10%	-2.59%
2031	-0.69%	-3.35%	-1.41%	-4.16%	-0.07%	-2.65%
2032	-0.61%	-3.36%	-1.51%	-4.39%	0.04%	-2.64%
2033	-0.62%	-3.48%	-1.53%	-4.52%	0.11%	-2.66%

Values are in GDP points. The 2016 historical reparation Law 27260 creates the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult (PUAM) and stops detracting 15% of *coparticipable* taxes to fund ANSES. In return, it states the national budget must fund the PUAM, and that it also must compensate ANSES for the missing *coparticipation* income. Transfers from the national budget are usually not a perennial source of income. Thus, in (1) we assume the federal budget funds these Law 27260 measures; and in (2) we assume it is ANSES that has to fund them.

	Central scenario		Low scenario		High scenario	
	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
2034	-0.62%	-3.59%	-1.49%	-4.60%	0.16%	-2.70%
2035	-0.60%	-3.68%	-1.60%	-4.84%	0.28%	-2.65%
2036	-0.66%	-3.87%	-1.59%	-4.96%	0.37%	-2.65%
2037	-0.59%	-3.91%	-1.64%	-5.14%	0.41%	-2.71%
2038	-0.58%	-4.03%	-1.76%	-5.42%	0.48%	-2.73%
2039	-0.57%	-4.15%	-1.74%	-5.55%	0.50%	-2.80%
2040	-0.54%	-4.25%	-1.78%	-5.78%	0.51%	-2.87%

Values are in GDP points. The 2016 historical reparation Law 27260 creates the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult (PUAM) and stops detracting 15% of *coparticipable* taxes to fund ANSES. In return, it states the national budget must fund the PUAM, and that it also must compensate ANSES for the missing *coparticipation* income. Transfers from the national budget are usually not a perennial source of income. Thus, in (1) we assume the federal budget funds these Law 27260 measures; and in (2) we assume it is ANSES that has to fund them.

Table R.10: ANSES simulated "Bismarckian" deficit and economic result with December 2015 legislation (2015-2040)

	Central scenario		Low scenario		High scenario	
	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
ANSES "Bismarckian" balance						
2015	-3.28%					
2016	-3.05%	-3.06%				
2017	-3.44%	-3.58%	-3.44%	-3.58%	-3.44%	-3.58%
2018	-2.82%	-3.19%	-2.89%	-3.17%	-2.90%	-3.18%
2019	-2.65%	-3.10%	-2.62%	-3.07%	-2.63%	-3.05%
2020	-2.82%	-3.36%	-2.88%	-3.43%	-2.76%	-3.25%
2021	-2.79%	-3.35%	-2.93%	-3.57%	-2.68%	-3.16%
2022	-2.73%	-3.52%	-2.95%	-3.71%	-2.59%	-3.24%
2023	-2.66%	-3.54%	-3.05%	-3.88%	-2.55%	-3.28%
2024	-2.69%	-3.75%	-3.12%	-4.01%	-2.44%	-3.30%
2025	-2.76%	-3.92%	-3.13%	-4.28%	-2.34%	-3.40%
2026	-2.55%	-3.96%	-3.11%	-4.49%	-2.23%	-3.38%
2027	-2.51%	-3.98%	-3.08%	-4.58%	-2.02%	-3.39%
2028	-2.41%	-4.14%	-3.07%	-4.66%	-1.80%	-3.39%
2029	-2.39%	-4.28%	-3.04%	-4.88%	-1.70%	-3.39%
2030	-2.40%	-4.30%	-3.08%	-5.18%	-1.65%	-3.48%
2031	-2.43%	-4.36%	-3.14%	-5.45%	-1.62%	-3.57%
2032	-2.34%	-4.63%	-3.24%	-5.77%	-1.52%	-3.59%
2033	-2.23%	-4.67%	-3.31%	-5.98%	-1.50%	-3.71%
2034	-2.24%	-4.84%	-3.36%	-6.39%	-1.46%	-3.86%
2035	-2.27%	-5.01%	-3.42%	-6.72%	-1.36%	-3.97%
2036	-2.25%	-5.12%	-3.43%	-6.89%	-1.28%	-3.97%
2037	-2.20%	-5.30%	-3.49%	-7.11%	-1.28%	-4.13%

Values are in GDP points. (1): a counter-factual scenario where there are no non-contributive pensions after the 2014 Law 26970 pension moratorium. (2): a counter-factual scenario where the 2014 Law 26970 pension moratorium becomes permanent.

	Central scenario		Low scenario		High scenario	
	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
2038	-2.20%	-5.45%	-3.53%	-7.53%	-1.24%	-4.19%
2039	-2.16%	-5.61%	-3.55%	-7.85%	-1.25%	-4.31%
2040	-2.13%	-5.89%	-3.65%	-8.05%	-1.24%	-4.44%
ANSES economic result						
2015	-1.15%					
2016	-1.17%	-1.18%				
2017	-1.50%	-1.64%	-1.50%	-1.64%	-1.50%	-1.64%
2018	-0.92%	-1.29%	-0.99%	-1.27%	-1.01%	-1.29%
2019	-0.75%	-1.20%	-0.72%	-1.17%	-0.73%	-1.15%
2020	-0.93%	-1.47%	-0.98%	-1.54%	-0.86%	-1.35%
2021	-0.90%	-1.45%	-1.03%	-1.67%	-0.78%	-1.26%
2022	-0.83%	-1.62%	-1.06%	-1.82%	-0.70%	-1.34%
2023	-0.76%	-1.64%	-1.16%	-1.98%	-0.65%	-1.39%
2024	-0.80%	-1.86%	-1.22%	-2.12%	-0.54%	-1.41%
2025	-0.86%	-2.02%	-1.24%	-2.39%	-0.44%	-1.51%
2026	-0.65%	-2.06%	-1.21%	-2.59%	-0.33%	-1.48%
2027	-0.61%	-2.08%	-1.18%	-2.68%	-0.13%	-1.49%
2028	-0.36%	-2.09%	-1.02%	-2.61%	0.25%	-1.34%
2029	-0.34%	-2.23%	-0.98%	-2.83%	0.35%	-1.34%
2030	-0.35%	-2.25%	-1.03%	-3.13%	0.40%	-1.43%
2031	-0.38%	-2.31%	-1.09%	-3.40%	0.43%	-1.52%
2032	-0.29%	-2.58%	-1.19%	-3.72%	0.53%	-1.54%
2033	-0.18%	-2.62%	-1.26%	-3.93%	0.55%	-1.66%
2034	-0.19%	-2.79%	-1.31%	-4.34%	0.59%	-1.81%
2035	-0.22%	-2.96%	-1.37%	-4.67%	0.69%	-1.92%
2036	-0.20%	-3.07%	-1.38%	-4.84%	0.77%	-1.91%
2037	-0.15%	-3.25%	-1.44%	-5.06%	0.77%	-2.08%
2038	-0.15%	-3.40%	-1.47%	-5.48%	0.81%	-2.14%
2039	-0.11%	-3.56%	-1.50%	-5.80%	0.80%	-2.26%
2040	-0.08%	-3.84%	-1.59%	-6.00%	0.81%	-2.39%
Values are in GDP points. (1): a counter-factual scenario where there are no non-contributive pensions after the 2014 Law 26970 pension moratorium. (2): a counter-factual scenario where the 2014 Law 26970 pension moratorium becomes permanent.						

Appendix S

Robustness check: computing ANSES Bismarckian deficit with varying starting datasets (second quarters of 2014 and 2015)

Although representative of Argentina's urban population, the EPHc is an imperfect approximation of Argentina's total population. The choice of a given wave as the starting dataset of our simulations is thus bound to alter the end result, since the socio-demographic characteristics of the surveyed population change from one period to the other even after the population has been weighted. We chose as our starting dataset the EPHc wave of the fourth quarter of 2014 because it is one of the latest available periods before the methodological modification undertaken in 2016. Moreover, at that date the pension mobility Law 26417 was in force, so pensions were adjusted twice a year on March and September. It is therefore crucial to take as a starting dataset a survey carried out either during the second or the fourth quarter. If we kept either the first or the third quarter as our starting dataset, recipients of a retirement benefit may have been interviewed before or after the bi-annual pension adjustment took place. On the other hand, we know a respondent surveyed during the second or fourth quarter has not seen his pension modified during that quarter, so we avoid this bias.

Therefore, as a test of the robustness of our sustainability projections regarding the starting dataset, we recomputed ANSES "Bismarckian" deficit starting the second quarters of 2014 and 2015. Figures S.1 and S.2 below give the resulting "Bismarckian" deficits. We also reproduce Figure 3.6 to make the comparison easier. These figures show the end result as well as the expected evolution of ANSES "Bismarckian" deficit do not change

significantly if we take a different starting dataset than the fourth quarter of 2014. The only significant difference is when we compare the Bismarckian balance in 2040 computed with the pessimistic economic scenario: in that case, the low scenario (including or excluding the universal pension PUAM) is 1 % of GDP lower when we pick as a starting dataset the fourth quarter of 2040 (Figure S) than if we had started with the second quarter of 2014 or 2015. On the other hand, the results obtained with as a starting dataset the second quarters of 2014 or 2015 are almost identical throughout the 2014-2040 simulation period (Figures S.1 and S.2). This suggests it is seasonal aspects that may be behind this difference in simulation results. In any case, the resulting economic sustainability of Argentina’s social security system is mostly unaffected by the chosen initial dataset, so our results are robust to this discretionary choice.

Figure S.1: ANSES Bismarckian deficit (1993-2040), simulations starting the second quarter of 2014 (% of GDP)

Sources: for historical values, see Figure 1.1. Simulated values come from our microsimulation model and are listed in Appendix R. The starting dataset is the EPHc carried out during the second quarter of 2014.

Figure S.2: ANSES Bismarckian deficit (1993-2040), simulations starting the second quarter of 2015 by economic scenario, 1993-2040 (% of GDP)

Sources: for historical values, see Figure 1.1. Simulated values come from our microsimulation model and are listed in Appendix R. The starting dataset is the EPHc carried out during the second quarter of 2015.

ANSES Bismarckian deficit by economic scenario, starting the fourth quarter of 2014, 1993-2040 (% of GDP)

Sources: for historical values, see Figure 1.1. Simulated values come from our microsimulation model and are listed in Appendix R. The starting dataset is the EPHc carried out during the fourth quarter of 2014.

Appendix T

ANSES non-simulated income, expenses and evolution of the FGS: historical values

Table T.1: Taxes that fund ANSES, % of GDP

	(1)		(2)		(3)		(4)	(5)		(6)	(7)	(8)
	Total	to	Total	to	Total	to		Total	to			Total
	ANSES		ANSES		ANSES			ANSES				
1993	1.81%	0.36%	6.54%	0.67%	0.87%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	1.28%	0.00%	2.31%
1994	2.26%	0.45%	6.40%	0.66%	0.80%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	1.25%	0.00%	2.37%
1995	2.42%	0.48%	6.40%	0.66%	0.69%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	1.16%	0.00%	2.30%
1996	2.50%	0.54%	6.65%	0.70%	0.86%	0.19%	0.06%	0.00%	0.00%	1.19%	0.00%	2.68%
1997	2.85%	0.57%	6.77%	0.70%	1.34%	0.68%	0.07%	0.00%	0.00%	1.23%	0.00%	3.24%
1998	3.17%	0.64%	6.81%	0.70%	1.24%	0.62%	0.07%	0.03%	0.02%	1.27%	0.00%	3.32%
1999	3.26%	0.65%	6.42%	0.66%	1.27%	0.66%	0.07%	0.14%	0.10%	1.31%	0.00%	3.44%
2000	3.68%	0.74%	6.69%	0.69%	1.22%	0.63%	0.17%	0.12%	0.09%	1.32%	0.00%	3.64%
2001	3.76%	0.74%	5.71%	0.59%	1.27%	0.65%	0.08%	0.11%	0.08%	1.24%	1.09%	3.39%
2002	2.85%	0.55%	4.88%	0.50%	1.43%	0.58%	0.07%	0.07%	0.05%	0.96%	1.55%	2.72%
2003	3.92%	0.78%	5.57%	0.57%	1.32%	0.50%	0.07%	0.08%	0.05%	1.18%	1.57%	3.15%
2004	4.59%	0.92%	6.39%	0.66%	1.11%	0.42%	0.07%	0.10%	0.07%	1.36%	1.58%	3.50%
2005	4.81%	0.96%	6.33%	0.65%	1.03%	0.39%	0.07%	0.13%	0.09%	1.40%	1.62%	3.56%
2006	4.70%	0.94%	6.58%	0.68%	0.92%	0.34%	0.06%	0.12%	0.08%	1.41%	1.63%	3.51%
2007	4.78%	0.95%	6.99%	0.72%	0.83%	0.30%	0.05%	0.12%	0.08%	1.49%	1.68%	3.59%
2008	4.67%	0.93%	6.98%	0.72%	0.84%	0.28%	0.05%	0.12%	0.08%	1.46%	1.70%	3.53%
2009	4.45%	0.89%	7.00%	0.72%	0.93%	0.31%	0.05%	0.12%	0.09%	1.46%	1.65%	3.52%
2010	4.61%	0.92%	7.00%	0.71%	0.92%	0.30%	0.05%	0.13%	0.09%	1.47%	1.62%	3.53%
2011	4.98%	0.99%	7.08%	0.70%	0.83%	0.26%	0.05%	0.14%	0.10%	1.49%	1.66%	3.58%
2012	5.25%	1.05%	7.22%	0.73%	0.98%	0.31%	0.05%	0.15%	0.10%	1.56%	1.67%	3.79%
2013	5.48%	1.09%	7.44%	0.74%	0.93%	0.26%	0.04%	0.13%	0.09%	1.59%	1.69%	3.82%
2014	5.83%	1.16%	7.23%	0.71%	0.97%	0.27%	0.04%	0.09%	0.07%	1.59%	1.68%	3.84%

Source: DNIAF (2013) (1993-1995), AFIP's yearly tax collection data (1996-2017), Federal Tax Commission, ONP (n.d.)

	(1)		(2)		(3)		(4)	(5)		(6)	(7)	(8)
	Total	to	Total	to	Total	to		Total	to			Total
	ANSES		ANSES		ANSES			ANSES				
2015	6.52%	1.29%	7.40%	0.74%	0.96%	0.24%	0.05%	0.10%	0.07%	1.63%	1.67%	4.03%
2016	5.38%	1.07%	7.24%	0.72%	0.94%	0.25%	0.05%	0.09%	0.06%	1.57%	1.64%	3.73%
2017	5.41%	1.06%	7.46%	0.77%	1.00%	0.29%	0.06%	0.10%	0.07%	1.62%	1.69%	3.88%
2008-2017	5.26%	1.05%	7.21%	0.73%	0.93%	0.28%	0.05%	0.12%	0.08%	1.54%	1.66%	3.72%
(1): Income tax; (2): Net VAT; (3): Fuel tariffs Law 23966; (4): Additional emergency tax on Cigarettes Law 24625 (100% goes to ANSES); (5): Fiscal component of the <i>monotributo</i> integrated tax; (6): 15% of <i>coparticipabe</i> taxes (that go to ANSES as figurative contributions); (7): Law 25413 "Check" tax (100% goes to ANSES since 01/01/2018); (8): Total taxes assigned to ANSES												
Source: DNIAF (2013) (1993-1995), AFIP's yearly tax collection data (1996-2017), Federal Tax Commission, ONP (n.d.)												

Table T.2: ANSES non-simulated expenses, % of GDP

	Operative costs	Figurative expenses			Payment of court rulings	Total
		To Social Security Institutions	Central Administration	Total Figurative expenses		
1993	0.15%	0.44%	0.09%	0.53%		0.68%
1994	0.11%	0.50%	0.18%	0.68%		0.79%
1995	0.12%	0.46%	0.20%	0.66%		0.78%
1996	0.12%	0.37%	0.37%	0.75%		0.87%
1997	0.08%	0.38%	0.35%	0.72%		0.81%
1998	0.08%	0.44%	0.38%	0.82%		0.90%
1999	0.08%	0.50%	0.37%	0.87%		0.95%
2000	0.08%	0.46%	0.38%	0.84%		0.92%
2001	0.07%	0.46%	0.39%	0.85%		0.92%
2002	0.07%	0.39%	0.29%	0.68%		0.75%
2003	0.07%	0.39%	0.29%	0.68%		0.75%
2004	0.06%	0.30%	0.32%	0.62%		0.68%
2005	0.08%	0.26%	0.33%	0.60%		0.67%
2006	0.08%	0.24%	0.39%	0.63%		0.71%
2007	0.09%	0.23%	0.46%	0.69%		0.79%
2008	0.11%	0.22%	0.54%	0.76%	0.15%	1.02%
2009	0.18%	0.28%	0.69%	0.96%	0.18%	1.32%
2010	0.19%	0.28%	0.72%	1.00%	0.17%	1.36%
2011	0.22%	0.25%	0.81%	1.05%	0.14%	1.41%
2012	0.24%	0.25%	1.01%	1.26%	0.15%	1.65%
2013	0.21%	0.26%	1.08%	1.34%	0.21%	1.77%
2014	0.21%	0.26%	1.07%	1.33%	0.25%	1.78%
2015	0.21%	0.27%	1.17%	1.44%	0.22%	1.88%
2016	0.18%	0.28%	1.10%	1.38%	0.28%	1.83%
2017	0.17%			1.44%	0.25%	1.86%
Source: CGN's Investment Accounts (1993-2016), public sector's Savings-Investment-Funding Account for 2017.						

Table T.2: ANSES non-simulated expenses, % of GDP

	Operative costs	Figurative expenses			Payment of court rulings	Total
		To Social Security Institutions	Central Administration	Total Figurative expenses		
2008-2017 average	0.19%	0.26%	0.91%	1.20%	0.20%	1.59%

Source: CGN's Investment Accounts (1993-2016), public sector's Savings-Investment-Funding Account for 2017.

Table T.3: FGS fund asset value and yearly investment returns (2008-2017)

	Size, million of pesos	Returns, million of pesos	Size, % of GDP	Returns, % of GDP
2008	98,224	1,117.4	8.54%	0.10%
2009	135,692.7	8,487.1	10.87%	0.68%
2010	178,016	8,714.71	10.71%	0.52%
2011	199,490	11,038.7	9.16%	0.51%
2012	244,799	17,349.3	9.28%	0.66%
2013	329,472	22,873.1	9.84%	0.68%
2014	472,265	38,383.8	10.31%	0.84%
2015	664,029	53,181.0	11.34%	0.91%
2016	875,380	72,470.2	10.87%	0.90%
2017	1,202,579	85,873.4	12.45%	0.89%

Source: FGS reports (2008-2017) for the size of the Fund, CGN's Investment Account (2008-2016) and the public Sector's Savings-Investment-Funding account (2017) for FGS returns.

Appendix U

The historical reparation program's future: simulated cost and funding

We have in Appendix A estimated the cost of the historical reparation program for years 2016 and 2017 and used these estimations in our analysis of ANSES accounts. As discussed in section 1.1.2, we argued that both historical reparation costs and sources of funding should be studied separately from other ANSES expenses and revenue as far as ANSES long-term sustainability is concerned. This is because the funding of this program is ensured by two stocks of revenue: fiscal amnesty penalties and the FGS. It would only be relevant to take this plan's spending into account when studying ANSES economic sustainability if either the plan's expenses were to fully deplete these two stocks by 2040 or if we consider FGS returns or assets ought to fund other ANSES expenses. *De jure*, we have pointed out in section 1.1.2 that the AUH can also be funded with FGS returns¹. However, since the AUH has never been funded with FGS returns so far, we assume it will not be the case in the future either. Therefore, we need to estimate whether the historical reparation program will deplete both the stock of fiscal amnesty penalties available in December 2017 (95,988.816 million pesos or 0.8% of the fourth quarter of 2017 GDP, as we estimated in section 1.1) and the FGS (10.4% of GDP in the fourth quarter of 2017). First, we estimate the future cost of the historical reparation program up to 2040. We then withdraw from both stocks payments made to fund the historical reparation program and see how it affects the future evolution of the FGS. In the end, we show the FGS will be enough to fund the program in all our economic scenarios and with the youngest possible population of the program's beneficiaries. This means it is probably correct to keep historical reparation payments out of the analysis as far as ANSES sustainability is concerned.

¹This is established by Art. 3 of the Decree 1602/2009, issued the 30th of October 2009.

U.1 Estimating the future cost of the historical reparation program by economic scenario (2018-2040)

First of all, we determine the future cost of the historical reparation program. We have shown in Appendix A that the budgeted cost of this program for years 2017 and 2018 is equal to respectively 7% and 7.5% of the ANSES retirement pension budget (including the additional cost for this specific plan). We have also estimated this program represented in 2017 7.9% of all ANSES retirement and survivor's pensions. To be safe, we thus assume the 2018 budget also slightly underestimates the historical reparation program's cost for that year. We therefore presume in 2018 additional spending on the plan will represent 7.5% of all ANSES retirement pension expenses (simulated as social security contributions). This means we add expenses on the historical reparation program equal to 8.1% of these simulated pensions, which equals 0.62% of GDP for 2018 in our central scenario. Since we know the possibility to enter the program ends in 2018, this is the peak value of its cost. After that date, there will not be additional subscribers to the historical reparation program. Its cost will thus gradually decrease as the stock of beneficiaries dies. We can therefore get an approximation of the evolution of this program's cost by computing the life expectancy of the population of beneficiaries, using INDEC's population projections future death probabilities by age and gender listed in Appendix K.

We do not however know the age and gender composition of the population that benefits from this program due to the lack of official information on the subject. Hence, we assume the 2017 expenses on the historical reparation program were equally distributed by gender and age among all the cohorts that were able to enter the program due to their age. Pensions were mostly underpaid in the 2002-2006 period, so the youngest cohort of pensioners that was penalised by this are women aged 60 in 2006, or 74 by 2020. We have also shown with Figure 1.12 page 109 that the initial pension recognised by the historical reparation program is significantly higher than the actual benefit only for registered wage-earners retiring between 2003 and 2012. The youngest cohort that may thus benefit from the program is women aged 60 in 2012 and men aged 65 in 2012. We thus assume the population that benefits from the historical reparation program is all women aged 66 or more and all men aged 71 or more in 2018. Its exact composition by age and gender is taken from INDEC's demographic projections, and can be found in Table K.2 page 249 in Appendix K. In the absence of more detailed information on the population of historical reparation beneficiaries, we willingly take the youngest possible version of the recipients population. This way, our estimates represent the highest possible value of future ex-

penses of the program. It is false all the members of this population will benefit from the historical reparation program. It is however of no consequence for our analysis of this program’s cost, as the program’s *per capita* cost will simply be lower, leaving unaffected the plan’s aggregate cost.

In the end, we have on the one hand expenses made in 2018 for the historical reparation program (deduced from the 2018 budget), which are equal to 0.62% of that year’s GDP in our central scenario. On the other hand, we have the population of beneficiaries, which we assume all receive the same benefit. We thus divide the expenses by the number of beneficiaries and get the individual pension increase for each member of this population. We finally apply the death probabilities by age and gender listed in Table K.2 page 249 to this population, keep the survivors’ mean benefit increase (which is adjusted following the pension mobility formula established by Law 27426) and deduce the future cost of this program in GDP points. There are slight differences from one economic scenario to the other due to the different values of the pension mobility formula and the varying projected GDP. Table U.1 below shows our estimation of the future historical reparation cost by economic scenario, in both constant November 2014 pesos and GDP points. The full computation is available on-line².

Table U.1: Estimated future cost of the historical reparation program (2018-2040)

	Mid-year population	Cost, low scenario		Cost, central scenario		Cost, high scenario	
		Millions of pesos ¹	% of GDP	Millions of pesos ¹	% of GDP	Millions of pesos ¹	% of GDP
2018	3,964,206	34,256	0.60%	34,286	0.60%	34,286	0.60%
2019	3,768,114	32,756	0.56%	32,785	0.56%	32,785	0.55%
2020	3,600,623	31,300	0.53%	31,327	0.52%	31,327	0.51%
2021	3,404,532	29,596	0.50%	29,621	0.49%	29,621	0.47%
2022	3,212,045	27,922	0.48%	27,947	0.46%	27,947	0.43%
2023	3,024,123	26,289	0.45%	26,312	0.42%	26,312	0.40%
2024	2,844,280	24,725	0.42%	24,747	0.39%	24,747	0.36%
2025	2,662,244	23,143	0.39%	23,163	0.36%	23,163	0.33%
2026	2,487,618	21,625	0.36%	21,644	0.33%	21,644	0.30%
2027	2,317,320	20,144	0.34%	20,162	0.30%	20,162	0.27%
2028	2,151,847	18,706	0.31%	18,722	0.27%	18,722	0.24%

1: Values are in millions of constant November 2014 pesos.

²We use the Zenodo archiving service for long-term preservation of our code. The DOI link is: 10.5281/zenodo.1420273

		Cost, low scenario		Cost, central scenario		Cost, high scenario	
	Mid-year population	Millions of pesos ¹	% of GDP	Millions of pesos ¹	% of GDP	Millions of pesos ¹	% of GDP
2029	1,995,218	17,344	0.29%	17,360	0.25%	17,360	0.22%
2030	1,841,863	16,011	0.27%	16,025	0.23%	16,025	0.20%
2031	1,693,833	14,725	0.24%	14,737	0.21%	14,737	0.18%
2032	1,551,132	13,484	0.22%	13,496	0.19%	13,496	0.16%
2033	1,413,842	12,291	0.21%	12,301	0.17%	12,301	0.14%
2034	1,286,293	11,182	0.19%	11,191	0.15%	11,191	0.13%
2035	1,164,096	10,120	0.17%	10,128	0.14%	10,128	0.11%
2036	1,048,551	9,115	0.15%	9,123	0.12%	9,123	0.10%
2037	939,256	8,165	0.14%	8,172	0.11%	8,172	0.09%
2038	835,939	7,267	0.12%	7,273	0.10%	7,273	0.07%
2039	742,109	6,451	0.11%	6,457	0.08%	6,457	0.06%
2040	654,252	5,687	0.10%	5,692	0.07%	5,692	0.06%

1: Values are in millions of constant November 2014 pesos.

Table U.1 shows the yearly cost of the historical reparation program should decrease from its peak value of 0.6% of GDP in 2018 until being almost negligible by 2040, reaching 0.07% at that date. Moreover, the cost of the program in real terms is almost identical from one economic scenario to the other. This is because this increase in benefits is indexed by 70% on the CPI and by only 30% on the mean wage of formal workers (RIPTE), following Law 27426 pension mobility law.

U.2 Estimating the impact of the historical reparation program on the FGS

Now that we have an estimation of future historical reparation payments, we can determine whether the combination of fiscal amnesty penalties left by December 2017 and the FGS future returns and assets will be enough to fund these expenses. First of all, we assume both these stocks are invested and that they increase on par with GDP growth. This simple hypothesis is adopted for the sake of simplicity, but also because it reproduces the observed evolution of the FGS. Indeed, the FGS increased in nominal terms by 786% between November 2009 and December 2017. Between the fourth quarters of 2009 and 2017, the GDP measured in current pesos increased by 750%. Therefore, the FGS grew only 4.8% faster than the GDP between these periods. This shows the FGS grew on

average at the same pace than Argentina's economy, which makes sense since it is fully invested in the country (ANSES, 2018). This means we assume the FGS would keep its December 2017 size as a percentage of the GDP were all his future returns reinvested in the fund. Secondly, we assume the funds necessary to pay for the historical reparation program are withdrawn from these stocks at the end of each month, without any transaction cost or the need to take out these funds in advance (and therefore not investing them for a period of time). We furthermore assume the monthly payments for the historical reparation program are equal to a twelfth of the annual spending. Once we take these two last hypotheses into account, we can prove by mathematical induction that the Fund's value after n months A_n is equal to:

$$A_n = A(1 + y)^{\frac{n}{12}} - W \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (1 + y)^{\frac{i}{12}} \quad (\text{U.1})$$

Where y is the annualised return of the Fund, A the fund's value the starting year and W the amount of withdrawals made in a month to pay for the historical reparation program. This relationship is true for $n = 1$. Indeed, at the end of one month the Fund gives a return of $(1 + y)^{\frac{1}{12}}$ and W is withdrawn from it. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= A(1 + y) - W \\ A_1 &= A(1 + y)^{\frac{1}{12}} - W \sum_{i=0}^0 (1 + y)^{\frac{i}{12}} \end{aligned}$$

Let us now assume the statement (U.1) is true for a given n . We have therefore:

$$\begin{aligned} A_{n+1} &= A_n(1 + y)^{\frac{1}{12}} - W \\ A_{n+1} &= \left[A(1 + y)^{\frac{n}{12}} - W \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (1 + y)^{\frac{i}{12}} \right] (1 + y)^{\frac{1}{12}} - W \\ A_{n+1} &= A(1 + y)^{\frac{n+1}{12}} - W \left(\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (1 + y)^{\frac{i+1}{12}} + 1 \right) \\ A_{n+1} &= A(1 + y)^{\frac{n+1}{12}} - W \left(\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (1 + y)^{\frac{i+1}{12}} + (1 + y)^{\frac{0}{12}} \right) \\ A_{n+1} &= A(1 + y)^{\frac{n+1}{12}} - W \sum_{j=0}^n (1 + y)^{\frac{j}{12}} \end{aligned}$$

Hence, the statement (U.1) is verified for $n+1$. Therefore, this relationship is true for any number of months n as long as y and W are the same for all these months. If we

reason with twelve months of a same year t , it is indeed the case. First, the yearly growth of the Fund is y_t for all the months of year t . Second, we assumed earlier that monthly withdrawals from the fund were simply equal to a twelfth of the yearly total withdrawals needed to pay for the historical reparation program W_t . Therefore, we deduce from equation (U.1) the following formula that gives us the value's fund in December each year F_t , as a function of the fund's value in December of the previous year F_{t-1} :

$$F_t = F_{t-1} (1 + y_t) - \frac{W_t}{12} \sum_{i=0}^{11} (1 + y_t)^{\frac{i}{12}} \quad (\text{U.2})$$

We have in Table U.1 all the yearly withdrawals W_t for years 2018 to 2040. We also have the yearly GDP growth between years 2018 and 2040 y_t for all our economic scenarios. We can thus apply equation (U.2) to the value of the two different stocks available to fund the historical reparation program in December 2017. The resulting evolution of both these funds across economic scenarios is listed in Table U.2 below:

Table U.2: "Historical reparation" expenses impact on the FGS by economic scenario

	GDP growth	Yearly withdrawals	Funds' values. by December		
			Fiscal amnesty penalties	FGS	FGS December value, % of GDP
Low scenario					
2017			46,349,018	580,675,520	10.10%
2018	0.45%	34,256,427	12,229,691	583,272,018	10.10%
2019	1.37%	32,756,268		570,692,304	9.75%
2020	0.12%	31,300,261		540,033,981	9.22%
2021	0.40%	29,595,645		512,558,526	8.71%
2022	0.05%	27,922,350		484,873,897	8.24%
2023	0.18%	26,288,740		459,440,870	7.79%
2024	0.73%	24,725,359		438,007,286	7.38%
2025	0.31%	23,142,925		416,180,253	6.99%
2026	-0.22%	21,624,894		393,650,367	6.62%
2027	0.56%	20,144,491		375,661,228	6.28%
2028	0.80%	18,706,037		359,875,023	5.97%
2029	0.16%	17,344,459		343,076,279	5.69%
2030	-0.27%	16,011,335		326,153,440	5.42%
2031	-0.06%	14,724,508		311,239,374	5.18%
2032	-0.64%	13,484,008		295,808,972	4.95%
2033	-0.34%	12,290,543		282,536,561	4.74%
2034	-0.78%	11,181,760		269,181,805	4.56%
2035	-0.35%	10,119,500		258,149,625	4.38%

GDP growth is measured between the fourth quarters of two consecutive years. Values are in thousands of constant November 2014 pesos. The size of the FGS is given as a percentage of the fourth quarter GDP.

			Funds' values. by December		
	GDP growth	Yearly withdrawals	Fiscal amnesty penalties	FGS	FGS December value, % of GDP
2036	-0.20%	9,115,069		248,537,528	4.23%
2037	-1.34%	8,164,968		237,093,522	4.09%
2038	0.65%	7,266,828		231,348,989	3.96%
2039	-0.75%	6,451,162		223,183,976	3.85%
2040	-0.08%	5,687,418		217,329,687	3.75%

Central scenario

2017			46,349,018	580,675,520	10.10%
2018	0.63%	34,286,154	12,257,496	584,362,590	10.10%
2019	2.54%	32,784,694		578,587,578	9.76%
2020	1.26%	31,327,423		554,369,856	9.23%
2021	1.77%	29,621,327		534,303,502	8.74%
2022	0.90%	27,946,580		511,040,883	8.29%
2023	1.76%	26,311,552		493,497,258	7.87%
2024	1.85%	24,746,815		477,688,307	7.47%
2025	1.31%	23,163,008		460,655,654	7.12%
2026	3.36%	21,643,660		454,169,625	6.79%
2027	1.88%	20,161,972		442,386,821	6.49%
2028	1.24%	18,722,270		429,024,075	6.22%
2029	0.55%	17,359,511		413,981,249	5.96%
2030	2.16%	16,025,230		406,734,001	5.74%
2031	0.59%	14,737,286		394,371,503	5.53%
2032	1.54%	13,495,709		386,843,286	5.34%
2033	0.92%	12,301,209		378,048,214	5.17%
2034	0.85%	11,191,463		370,016,154	5.02%
2035	1.93%	10,128,281		366,938,935	4.88%
2036	1.11%	9,122,979		361,834,762	4.76%
2037	0.29%	8,172,054		354,690,887	4.66%
2038	0.95%	7,273,134		350,741,050	4.56%
2039	0.00%	6,456,760		344,270,761	4.48%
2040	1.34%	5,692,353		343,172,341	4.40%

High scenario

2017			46,349,018	580,675,520	10.10%
2018	0.82%	34,286,231	12,314,710	585,447,091	10.10%
2019	3.79%	32,784,767		587,088,697	9.76%
2020	2.82%	31,327,493		571,925,176	9.25%
2021	2.56%	29,621,394		556,615,512	8.78%
2022	2.77%	27,946,643		543,719,563	8.34%
2023	2.70%	26,311,611		531,738,132	7.94%
2024	3.16%	24,746,871		523,443,884	7.58%
2025	4.21%	23,163,060		521,874,107	7.25%
2026	2.48%	21,643,709		512,903,973	6.96%
2027	2.96%	20,162,017		507,650,555	6.69%

GDP growth is measured between the fourth quarters of two consecutive years. Values are in thousands of constant November 2014 pesos. The size of the FGS is given as a percentage of the fourth quarter GDP.

			Funds' values. by December		
	GDP growth	Yearly withdrawals	Fiscal amnesty penalties	FGS	FGS December value, % of GDP
2028	2.82%	18,722,312		503,005,443	6.44%
2029	3.10%	17,359,550		500,984,563	6.22%
2030	2.51%	16,025,266		497,365,905	6.03%
2031	2.18%	14,737,319		493,305,040	5.85%
2032	2.56%	13,495,739		492,280,718	5.69%
2033	1.77%	12,301,237		488,615,938	5.55%
2034	1.58%	11,191,488		485,048,667	5.43%
2035	3.09%	10,128,304		489,759,114	5.32%
2036	1.92%	9,123,000		489,978,424	5.22%
2037	2.00%	8,172,072		491,529,909	5.13%
2038	3.13%	7,273,150		499,515,075	5.06%
2039	1.56%	6,456,775		500,807,692	4.99%
2040	2.31%	5,692,366		506,619,790	4.94%

GDP growth is measured between the fourth quarters of two consecutive years. Values are in thousands of constant November 2014 pesos. The size of the FGS is given as a percentage of the fourth quarter GDP.

In the end, we can see that in all three scenarios the FGS is enough to pay for the historical reparation program in the long run. This is true even though we took the youngest possible population of historical reparation subscribers, which represents the case where expenses linked to the historical reparation program will decrease the slowest. However, in all scenarios the FGS sees its relevance as an economic actor dwindle in the long run due to these withdrawals. It will indeed represent respectively 3.8%, 4.4% and 4.9% of the fourth quarter of 2040 GDP in our low, central and high economic scenarios. Its real size will also fall by -13%, -41% and -63% in the high, central and low scenarios. These payments for the historical reparation program will therefore significantly weaken its other missions, which are acting as a buffer fund for social security in case of a temporary economic crisis and contributing to fund Argentina's economic actors in order to bolster the country's long-term growth. The first mission is simply incompatible with the long-term funding by the FGS of the historical reparation program. On the other hand, the Fund will still fund various Argentinian economic actors under incises l), m) and n) of Law 24241's Article 74. Its decreased size will however reduce the impact the FGS can have in the short ³ and mid to long-term⁴ funding of Argentina's economy.

³Incise m) of Law 24241's Article 74 allow the FGS to establish credit lines for ANSES survivor's or retirement pensioners. According to ANSES (2018), these (mostly) short-term loans represented 3.6% of FGS assets by December 2017. Incise n) allows the FGS to make similar credits to other individuals that receive a benefit paid by ANSES. These are mostly households that receive family benefits, in particular the AUH. By December 2017, 2.5% of FGS assets were invested in such loans.

⁴Incise l) of Law 24241's Article 74 forces the FGS to use at least 5% of its assets to "fund productive,

real estate or infrastructure projects at the middle and long terms in (...) Argentina". Up to 50% of the fund's assets can be invested in those items. In December 2017, 7.8% of FGS assets were invested accordingly (ANSES, 2018).

Appendix V

Methodological considerations behind the computation of income distribution statistics

First of all, we chose five indicators to measure the impact of social security transfers on income distribution. These are the Gini index, computed both at the household level and individually among the elderly, the income share of the 10% wealthiest and 10% poorest households, and the decile ratio¹. The Gini index sums up income inequality across the whole studied population, while the other three indexes put the focus on the wealthiest and poorest households. The combination of these five indices gives an accurate enough representation of income inequality in our simulated dataset. There are however a number of methodological challenges associated with these income inequality indicators.

V.1 Computing inequality indicators through varying income types

First of all, the redistributive impact of social security benefits cannot be studied *in abstracto*, disregarding other sources of income. Indeed, it would not make any sense to study the unequal distribution among households of pensions or family benefits. It is because they are meant to be redistributive that the richest households get fewer of these transfers. Retirement benefits replace part of the labour income the elderly used to earn, and are seldom cumulated with sizeable labour income as shown by our behavi-

¹The decile ratio is the quotient of the lowest income needed to be part of the wealthiest 10% divided by the maximum income among the poorest 10%.

oural equations for the elderly (under 70) listed in Appendix L. Also, family benefits help households care for dependent children and are even means-tested in Argentina, as seen in section 1.1.3. They are thus targeted at the poorest households, and their distribution is meant to be unequal for them to have a meaningful redistributive impact. Therefore, we compute income distribution before and after social security transfers. This means we successively take into account labour compensation only, labour income and retirement pensions, labour income and family benefits and all simulated revenue. Comparing the evolution over time of our Gini index, decile ratio, top 10% and bottom 10% income shares across these sources of revenue lets us give a first impression of the redistributive impact of pension and family benefits. The exception is the Gini computed among the elderly at the individual level. Since pension income is often the main source of income for the elderly, it is interesting to compute this statistic first without labour income, and then on all simulated sources of income. By doing so, it becomes possible to study the impact of the reforms adopted by the current administration on income inequality among the elderly. Such a methodology has already been adopted by Antón (2012) in its static microsimulation of labour and pension income in Mexico.

V.2 Computing the individual's disposable income

Secondly, all but the individual Gini index for the elderly are computed at the household level. This is because the standard of living is determined by the income available for each member of the household. The most logical assumption to make is that family members who live together share their earnings. An individual's disposable income is thus dependent on the composition of its household and the sources of revenue of all its members. For instance, if we take two workers with the exact same revenue, but one lives alone and the other has to maintain family members with no individual revenue, the former has the most available income and is thus wealthier than the latter. The relevant variable for computing income inequality is thus household members' disposable income.

The problem is there is no consensus in the literature on how to compute disposable income for each household member. One basic solution is to simply divide the total revenue by the number of household members and get a *per capita* income. This is the methodology adopted for instance by the United Nation's Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC) when computing income inequality indexes, be it

the Gini index² or the share of income earned by a given decile³. However, part of the literature considers individually disposable income is not equal to *per capita* revenue. First, because there are economies of scale in consumption. Sharing a dwelling means the cost for each dweller of for instance housing, heating and electricity is lower than if each inhabitant lived separately. This in turn increases each individual's disposable income. Second, because members of a household do not have the same consumption needs, so it is incorrect to assign to each individual the same weight when computing disposable income⁴. In particular, it is a stylised fact that children tend to have lower consumption needs than adults. One typical example of this is their lower daily calorie needs (US Department of Health and Human Services, 2017, p. 77-78). Thus, some statistical bodies "refer to disposable household income *per consumption unit* rather than per capita as an individual living standard. Introducing equivalence scales to account for economies of scale in consumption and the fact that children have less consumption needs than adults increases the standard of living of large poor families relative to the case where household income is divided by family size. This logically leads to lower inequality summary measures." (Bourguignon, 2015, p. 560-561). Bourguignon (2015) gives the examples of three different income distribution datasets that use equivalised income to measure inequality. These are the OECD Income Distribution Database, the Luxembourg Income Study (LIS) and the Socio-Economic Database for Latin America and the Caribbean (SEDLAC) developed by the CEDLAS Laboratory of the National University of La Plata, Argentina, and the World Bank.

However, there is not a consensus in the literature on how to compute an individual's equivalised household income either, and there are varying definitions of individual Consumption Units. Therefore, in addition to *per capita* income, we kept two distinct methodologies to compute a Consumption Unit. The first one is calibrated for Argentina and other Latin-American countries, and is the benchmark case adopted for the SEDLAC database by CEDLAS and The World Bank (2014). As explained in the guide to this dataset, "an individual's equivalized household income [equals] total household income

²The technical note describing the ECLAC's methodology can be found in: http://interwp.cepal.org/sisgen/Sisgen_MuestraFicha_puntual.asp?indicador=250&id_estudio=363&id_aplicacion=1&idioma=e.

³The technical note describing the methodology adopted by the ECLAC can be found in: http://interwp.cepal.org/sisgen/Sisgen_MuestraFicha_puntual.asp?indicador=284&id_estudio=363&id_aplicacion=1&idioma=e.

⁴A third reason pointed out by part of the literature is that there may be an unequal allocation of resources within the household, beyond the varying individual needs of the members. This point is not usually taken into account when computing income inequality statistics (CEDLAS and The World Bank, 2014, p. 23).

divided by $(A + \alpha_1 K_1 + \alpha_2 K_2)^\theta$, where A is the number of adults⁵, K_1 the number of children under 5 years old, and K_2 the number of children between 6 and 14. Parameters α allow for different weights for adults and kids, while θ regulates the degree of household economies of scale. Deaton & Zaidi (2002) suggest intermediate values of the α 's ($\alpha_1 = 0.5$ and $\alpha_2 = 0.75$), and a rather high value of θ (0.9) for countries like those in the region. We take that as the benchmark case, but also experiment with alternative vectors of parameters." (CEDLAS and The World Bank, 2014, p. 24). This statement also shows CEDLAS and The World Bank (2014) acknowledge there is no consensus on how to compute household equivalised income, and thus as a robustness measure re-compute their income distribution statistics with varying calibration. We thus chose to keep a second methodology to compute household equivalised income for the sake of the robustness of our analysis. The chosen methodology is the one from France's INSEE statistical body, which follows OECD guidelines. The INSEE considers that the first adult of the household counts for 1 Consumption Unit (CU), every additional household member aged 14 or more equals 0.5 CU, and people under 14 weigh 0.3 CU. All in all, we decided to keep the SEDLAC database definition of equivalised income as our main methodology for computing individual disposable revenue. *Per capita* income as well as INSEE's methodology are kept as tokens of the robustness of our inequality measures and for the sake of future comparability with datasets that use these methodologies for measuring income inequality.

V.3 Handling missing values: households with no reported income

A last methodological problem is how to treat households with no declared labour, pension or family benefits income, which represent 3% of households in the fourth quarter of 2014 EPHc dataset as shown in Figure 3.12 on page 386. The literature usually considers these as individuals misreporting their income. Another possibility contemplated by the literature is households that lived the surveyed month off other sources of revenue (such as charity, transfers, savings, etc.), for the temporary period where the household's breadwinners were unemployed (CEDLAS and The World Bank, 2014, p. 20). In the case of our synthetic microsimulated prospective database, by construction all workers get a non-zero labour income, and beneficiaries of social security benefits report them in full. Despite that, 15% of our households have no income by 2040. This is mainly because although our behavioural equations reduce the likelihood of being unemployed or

⁵A is actually the number of dwellers aged 15 or more.

inactive in the absence of a working spouse (see Appendix L), there is no hard constraint in our model that forbids the creation of households where nobody gets a labour, pension or family benefits income. This point is left to future work because it only marginally affects aggregate social security sustainability or benefits adequacy. It is however a more significant problem when studying future income distribution. All our inequality statistics would be strongly affected by the presence of a significant portion of households with no income, so it is not possible to simply include households with no simulated revenue in our analysis. Indeed, "some inequality measures collapse when considering zero income. (...) Accepting zero income implies dividing by zero, which generates computational problems." (CEDLAS and The World Bank, 2014, p. 20). This is in particular the case of the decile ratio statistic, which cannot be computed if the maximum income of the 10% poorest households equals 0.

The literature is split on how to handle households with no reported sources of income. A first approach seeks to correct non-declared or under-reported income before computing inequality indicators. For instance, ECLAC's statistical body CEPALSTAT carries out various adjustments to correct non-reported or unreported income in Latin-American household surveys (Bourguignon, 2015, p. 565), while Chile's and Paraguay's household surveys include direct imputations for income non-response (CEDLAS and The World Bank, 2014, p. 19). This approach is not valid for our dynamic microsimulation model, since by construction all individuals correctly report labour, pension and family benefits income. We therefore adopted the same approach than CEDLAS and The World Bank (2014) and excluded households with no revenue from the computation of income inequality measures, "as it is mostly done in academic papers"(CEDLAS and The World Bank, 2014, p. 19) such as Székely & Hilgert (1999). This method is also much easier to apply. The level of confidence of our inequality indicators is nevertheless not very high, as a little more than 15% of households are excluded from the analysis in the 2015-2040 period. This means we take out of the analysis inactive or unemployed individuals who would otherwise weigh on the household budget and reduce the disposable income of the cohabiting workers. This is one of the possible reasons why inequality indicators plummet by the end of our simulation as seen in section 3.2.3. It cannot however be the only one, since the share of households with no revenue is stable throughout our simulations, and despite that this fall only occurs towards its end.

Lastly, it is worth mentioning the fact our individual Gini for the elderly statistic is unaffected by the missing income issue. First, this is because it is computed at the individual level, so household composition has no impact on it. Second, observations with

no declared income are an integral part of the analysis. Indeed, our legislative scenarios include cases where some of the elderly do not have any simulated income, in particular in our 2015 legislation scenario without permanent pension moratoriums. It is thus important to include all the elderly in the computation of this inequality indicator in order to fully gauge the redistributive impact among the elderly of pension reforms.

Appendix W

Social security benefits simulated adequacy and redistributive impact, by economic and reform scenario

In this thesis, the baseline for studying social security benefits' adequacy and redistributive impact is the central economic scenario. Also, to study household income distribution, we need to define the disposable income for each household dweller, or the household's equivalised income. We adopted in our analysis the methodology established by CEDLAS and The World Bank (2014). In this Appendix and for the sake of reference, we show our adequacy and redistributive impact statistics with varying economic scenarios and equivalised household income methodologies reviewed in Appendix V.

W.1 Alternative redistributive impact statistics: changing the methodology for computing household equivalised income

We can see from these figures that the chosen methodology for computing individual disposable income has a significant impact on measured inequality statistics, as we explained in Appendix V. Keeping a *per capita* definition results in the highest income inequality statistics as shown by Figure W.3, because the consumption needs of minors within the household are the same than of other adult dwellers. Also, there is no method for taking into account economies of scale in consumption among household dwellers. Individuals that live in households with many children thus have a lower measured disposable income when it is measured *per capita*, as done for instance by the ECLAC when computing

Figure W.1: Household inequality measures by income definition, with 2018 legislation and SEDLAC's equivalised household income (2014-2040)

Households with no income are excluded from this analysis. The 2014 value is computed on the starting dataset, the fourth quarter of 2014 EPHc survey. The decile ratio is equal to the minimum *per capita* income a household must have to be part of the 10% wealthiest households divided by the maximum *per capita* income a household may have while still being part of the 10% poorest households. When computing the decile ratio, we re-define deciles when we change the income type. For the share of the top and bottom 10% in the total of a given income type however, the determination of the wealthiest and poorest households is always done with respect to total income (labour, pension and family benefits). Household income is equivalised following SEDLAC and The World Bank (2014), who adopted the calibration established by Deaton & Zaidi (2002).

Figure W.2: Household inequality measures by income definition, with 2018 legislation and INSEE’s equivalised household income (2014-2040)

Households with no income are excluded from this analysis. The 2014 value is computed on the starting dataset, the fourth quarter of 2014 EPHc survey. The decile ratio is equal to the minimum *per capita* income a household must have to be part of the 10% wealthiest households divided by the maximum *per capita* income a household may have while still being part of the 10% poorest households. When computing the decile ratio, we re-define deciles when we change the income type. For the share of the top and bottom 10% in the total of a given income type however, the determination of the wealthiest and poorest households is always done with respect to total income (labour, pension and family benefits). Household income is equivalised following INSEE’s and OECD’s methodology, detailed in Appendix V.

Figure W.3: Per capita household income inequality measures by income definition, with 2018 legislation (2014-2040)

Households with no income are excluded from this analysis. The 2014 value is computed on the starting dataset, the fourth quarter of 2014 EPHc survey. The decile ratio is equal to the minimum *per capita* income a household must have to be part of the 10% wealthiest households divided by the maximum *per capita* income a household may have while still being part of the 10% poorest households. When computing the decile ratio, we re-define deciles when we change the income type. For the share of the top and bottom 10% in the total of a given income type however, the determination of the wealthiest and poorest households is always done with respect to total income (labour, pension and family benefits). Individually disposable income is computed *per capita*, following the methodology adopted for instance by ECLAC to compute income inequality statistics. See Appendix V for more details on this subject.

income inequality statistics in Latin America. Since in Argentina households with many children also tend to have adults that are in the lower levels of the income scale, this results in high measured income inequality. On the other hand, INSEE's formula to compute household's equivalised income gives the first adult a weight of 100%, each additional dweller aged 14 or more 50%, and each child aged 13 or less a 30% weight. Our baseline methodology gives a 100% weight for the first adult, but weights of 75% and 50% for children respectively aged 6 to 14 and 5 or less. Thus, the presence of children in the household reduces by a fewer amount individually disposable income with INSEE's methodology than with the one by CEDLAS and The World Bank (2014). It is thus normal that measured household income inequality with our baseline methodology (Figure W.1) is higher than the one measured with INSEE's methodology (Figure W.2). Our baseline methodology for computing the disposable income of an individual thus results in intermediary levels of income inequality.

W.2 The impact of economic scenarios on future income distribution

Next, let us cover the influence of economic scenarios on future income distribution. We can see the central economic scenario is the one that results in the lowest measured household income inequality. This is because the pessimistic scenario results in higher proportions of informal workers, which get closer to that of formal workers. Since their earnings are significantly different (see Appendix M), this results in higher income inequality even though real wages stagnate. Meanwhile, the optimistic scenario results in higher wages, which tend to increase labour income variance and thus income inequality measured with the Gini or Decile ratio indices but do not affect that much the top and bottom 10% income shares. Finally, the low scenario is the one where the redistributive impact of family and retirement benefits is the strongest on the top and bottom 10% income shares. This is because they are discounted mostly on inflation following the 2017 Law 27426, so when real wages stagnate as in our pessimistic scenario, their relevance in total household income does not decrease.

Figure W.4: Equivalised household income inequality measures by income definition, with 2018 legislation (2014-2040), central scenario

Households with no income are excluded from this analysis. The 2014 value is computed on the starting dataset, the fourth quarter of 2014 EPHc survey. The decile ratio is equal to the minimum *per capita* income a household must have to be part of the 10% wealthiest households divided by the maximum *per capita* income a household may have while still being part of the 10% poorest households. When computing the decile ratio, we re-define deciles when we change the income type. For the share of the top and bottom 10% in the total of a given income type however, the determination of the wealthiest and poorest households is always done with respect to total income (labour, pension and family benefits). Household income is equivalised following [OECDLAS](#) and [The World Bank \(2014\)](#), who adopted the calibration established by [Deaton & Zaidi \(2002\)](#).

Figure W.5: Equivalised household income inequality measures by income definition, with 2018 legislation (2014-2040), low scenario

Households with no income are excluded from this analysis. The 2014 value is computed on the starting dataset, the fourth quarter of 2014 EPHc survey. The decile ratio is equal to the minimum *per capita* income a household must have to be part of the 10% wealthiest households divided by the maximum *per capita* income a household may have while still being part of the 10% poorest households. When computing the decile ratio, we re-define deciles when we change the income type. For the share of the top and bottom 10% in the total of a given income type however, the determination of the wealthiest and poorest households is always done with respect to total income (labour, pension and family benefits). Household income is equivalised following OECDLAS and The World Bank (2014), who adopted the calibration established by Deaton & Zaidi (2002).

Figure W.6: Equivalised household income inequality measures by income definition, with 2018 legislation (2014-2040), high scenario

Households with no income are excluded from this analysis. The 2014 value is computed on the starting dataset, the fourth quarter of 2014 EPHc survey. The decile ratio is equal to the minimum *per capita* income a household must have to be part of the 10% wealthiest households divided by the maximum *per capita* income a household may have while still being part of the 10% poorest households. When computing the decile ratio, we re-define deciles when we change the income type. For the share of the top and bottom 10% in the total of a given income type however, the determination of the wealthiest and poorest households is always done with respect to total income (labour, pension and family benefits). Household income is equivalised following OECDLAS and The World Bank (2014), who adopted the calibration established by Deaton & Zaidi (2002).

Figure W.7: Individual Gini indexes for the elderly (2014-2040). Level with 2018 legislation and comparison with other scenarios.

(a) 2018 legislation, all seniors

(b) 2018 legislation, seniors with income

Lastly, we see the optimistic and pessimistic economic scenarios respectively result in

(c) Comparing legislations, all seniors

(d) Comparing legislations, seniors with income

Reading example, Figure W.7c: in 2040, the individual Gini index computed on all types of income among all people of retirement age is 13.5 percentage points greater with 2018 legislation than with 2015 legislation including pension moratoriums.

Figure W.8: Individual Gini indexes for the elderly (2014-2040). Level with 2018 legislation and comparison with other scenarios. Pessimistic scenario.

(a) 2018 legislation, all seniors

(b) 2018 legislation, seniors with income

(c) Comparing legislations, all seniors

(d) Comparing legislations, seniors with income

Reading example, Figure W.8c: in 2040, the individual Gini index computed on all types of income among all people of retirement age is 13.5 percentage points greater with 2018 legislation than with 2015 legislation including pension moratoriums.

Figure W.9: Individual Gini indexes for the elderly (2014-2040). Level with 2018 legislation and comparison with other scenarios. Optimistic scenario.

(a) 2018 legislation, all seniors

(b) 2018 legislation, seniors with income

(c) Comparing legislations, all seniors

(d) Comparing legislations, seniors with income

Reading example, Figure W.9c: in 2040, the individual Gini index computed on all types of income among all people of retirement age is 13.5 percentage points greater with 2018 legislation than with 2015 legislation including pension moratoriums.

higher and lower levels of the individual Gini for the elderly. This is an expected result, since the Gini index increases when income increases in absolute terms all other things being equal, and both pensions and labour income increase faster the more optimistic our economic scenarios are. However, the impact of the 2017 and 2016 pension reforms on income inequality among the elderly is independent from the adopted economic scenario. We can see the same phenomenon for our statistics on household income inequality, which we upload in the digital repository linked to this thesis¹. Thus, although income distribution levels differ from one economic scenario to the other, the simulated impact of reforms on income inequality is independent from the adopted economic scenario.

W.3 The impact of economic scenarios on adequacy statistics

Finally, the impact of the chosen economic scenario on social security benefits adequacy is mostly seen in child benefits coverage and retirement pension levels. With an optimistic economic scenario, real wages increase significantly faster than the income caps for getting a contributive child benefit (which are mostly indexed on inflation), and informal labour and unemployment decreases, so access to a child benefit dwindles as shown by Figure W.12b. Conversely, a pessimistic economic situation sees child benefits coverage increase as shown by Figure W.11b. Retirement benefits on the other hand increase the most in real terms the more optimistic our scenarios are. The initial pension is computed on the last ten wages before retirement, and the pension mobility index instituted by the 2017 Law 27426 follows by 30% formal wages, so both effects result in higher pensions in absolute terms. This is shown by Figure W.12c. However, the median pension to labour income ratio is the highest in the pessimistic economic scenario: if real wages stagnate, they can't grow faster than retirement benefits, so pensions represent a higher proportion of wages than in our central or optimistic scenarios (see Figure W.11c).

We moreover see there is no effect on the access to a retirement benefit of the chosen economic scenario. This is a logical result, as 30 years of contributions are required to get a contributive benefit, and we only carry out a projection on 26 years. The impact of changing proportions of formal and informal labour within those 26 years on access to a pension is thus limited. Finally, the real level of mean child benefits is remarkably stable throughout our economic scenarios. On the one hand, the more optimistic scenarios

¹We use the Zenodo digital repository service for long-term preservation of our code. The DOI link is: [10.5281/zenodo.1420273](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1420273)

result in higher real levels of the AUH, due to their partial indexation on formal wages following the 2017 pension mobility Law 27426. But the lower proportion of informal workers and of the unemployed decreases access to the AUH, and increases the share of contributive child beneficiaries. Also, contributive child benefits decrease in real terms in this optimistic scenario, as the means-tests to get the highest contributive benefits, which follow the 2017 pension mobility index, increase slower than real wages (Figure W.12d). Conversely, our pessimistic economic scenario sees lower levels of the AUH earned by a higher proportion of children, but also higher access to the highest contributive child benefits (Figure W.11d). This is why the real level of mean child benefits is more or less the same (450 November 2014 pesos) in our three economic scenarios.

Figure W.10: The evolution of pension adequacy: coverage and pension level (2014-2040), central scenario

(a) Retirement pension coverage (% of people of retiring age)

(b) Child benefits coverage (% of minor children)

The retirement age in Argentina is 60 for women and 65 for men. Mean values are in November 2014 pesos. Between November 2014 and March 2016, we use a simple average of the Consumer Price Indexes (CPI) of the province of San Luis and the Autonomous City of Buenos Aires (CABA). Between April 2016 and May 2018, we use INDEC’s national CPI. After May 2018, we keep a monthly annualised inflation of 30%. This (underestimated, due to the ongoing 2018 currency crisis) inflation level is only useful for computing real family benefits and retirement pension evolution for 2018. Labour income is computed across formal and informal workers, be them wage-earners or independent, net of social security contributions.

(c) Mean retirement benefits

(d) Mean child benefits

Reading examples: Figure W.10a shows that in 2040, 31% of people of retirement age will earn a contributory retirement benefit or a pension derived from the 2006 moratorium; 9% a 2014 moratorium pension; 41% the Universal Pension PUAM; 3% only a survivor's benefit; and 17% will not receive any retirement or survivor's pension. Figure W.10b shows in 2040 55% of children aged 17 or less will earn a contributory child benefit; 16% the Universal Child Benefit AUH; and the remaining 29% will not receive a family benefit. Figure W.10c shows in 2040 the median retirement benefit will be equal to 46% of the median labour income. In Figure W.10d, our simulations show that by 2040 the mean universal child benefit AUH will be equal to 676 constant November 2014 pesos, while mean and contributive child benefits will respectively equal 436 and 372 constant pesos.

Figure W.11: The evolution of pension adequacy: coverage and pension level (2014-2040), pessimistic scenario

(a) Retirement pension coverage (% of people of retiring age)

(b) Child benefits coverage (% of minor children)

The retirement age in Argentina is 60 for women and 65 for men. Mean values are in November 2014 pesos. Between November 2014 and March 2016, we use a simple average of the Consumer Price Indexes (CPI) of the province of San Luis and the Autonomous City of Buenos Aires (CABA). Between April 2016 and May 2018, we use INDEC’s national CPI. After May 2018, we keep a monthly annualised inflation of 30%. This (underestimated, due to the ongoing 2018 currency crisis) inflation level is only useful for computing real family benefits and retirement pension evolution for 2018. Labour income is computed across formal and informal workers, be them wage-earners or independent, net of social security contributions.

(c) Mean retirement benefits

(d) Mean child benefits

Reading examples: Figure W.11a shows that in 2040, 30% of people of retirement age will earn a contributory retirement benefit or a pension derived from the 2006 moratorium; 8% a 2014 moratorium pension; 42% the Universal Pension PUAM; 2% only a survivor's benefit; and 17% will not receive any retirement or survivor's pension. Figure W.11b shows in 2040 56% of children aged 17 or less will earn a contributory child benefit; 23% the Universal Child Benefit AUH; and the remaining 21% will not receive a family benefit. Figure W.11c shows in 2040 the median retirement benefit will be equal to 58% of the median labour income. In Figure W.11d, our simulations show that by 2040 the mean universal child benefit AUH will be equal to 658 constant November 2014 pesos, while mean and contributive child benefits will respectively equal 448 and 387 constant pesos.

Figure W.12: The evolution of pension adequacy: coverage and pension level (2014-2040), optimistic scenario

(a) Retirement pension coverage (% of people of retiring age)

(b) Child benefits coverage (% of minor children)

The retirement age in Argentina is 60 for women and 65 for men. Mean values are in November 2014 pesos. Between November 2014 and March 2016, we use a simple average of the Consumer Price Indexes (CPI) of the province of San Luis and the Autonomous City of Buenos Aires (CABA). Between April 2016 and May 2018, we use INDEC’s national CPI. After May 2018, we keep a monthly annualised inflation of 30%. This (underestimated, due to the ongoing 2018 currency crisis) inflation level is only useful for computing real family benefits and retirement pension evolution for 2018. Labour income is computed across formal and informal workers, be them wage-earners or independent, net of social security contributions.

(c) Mean retirement benefits

(d) Mean child benefits

Reading examples: Figure W.12a shows that in 2040, 33% of people of retirement age will earn a contributory retirement benefit or a pension derived from the 2006 moratorium; 8% a 2014 moratorium pension; 40% the Universal Pension PUAM; 3% only a survivor's benefit; and 17% will not receive any retirement or survivor's pension. Figure W.12b shows in 2040 47% of children aged 17 or less will earn a contributory child benefit; 13% the Universal Child Benefit AUH; and the remaining 40% will not receive a family benefit. Figure W.12c shows in 2040 the median retirement benefit will be equal to 42% of the median labour income. In Figure W.12d, our simulations show that by 2040 the mean universal child benefit AUH will be equal to 714 constant November 2014 pesos, while mean and contributive child benefits will respectively equal 443 and 383 constant pesos.

General Conclusion

This thesis presents the first dynamic microsimulation model that simulates Argentina's social security system, which is also as far as we know the second of its kind for a developing country. Although structured around the development of this model, the results of this thesis are diverse. Our first chapter provides a thorough account of Argentina's social security legislation evolution and components, as well as a historical analysis of the country's labour market. These are all necessary elements for designing and calibrating our dynamic microsimulation model, but retracing the genesis of today's legislative framework also helps understand its current state. We show the various reforms undertaken since the private pension funds nationalisation in 2008 put Argentina in the conservative-Bismarckian welfare world of Esping-Andersen (1990), although complemented by important universalistic-Beveridgean elements and funded by the Sustainability Guarantee Fund (FGS). Argentina's current institutional arrangement sees most of its social security managed by a public National Social Security Administration (ANSES). The Bismarckian basis of the system is a unified Pay-As-You-Go Defined Benefits pension scheme, with contributive pensions that follow an insurance logic and replace a proportion of the last wages before retirement. This basis is complemented by contributive survivor's pensions and family benefits targeted at formal workers' families. However, more and more Beveridgean and non-contributive elements have been added to the system. These include the 2006 and 2014 temporary pension moratoriums for the elderly with incomplete careers; the 2009 Universal Child Benefit (AUH) for the children of informal workers and the unemployed; and the 2016 Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult (PUAM) for seniors aged 65 or more with no pensions. This system thus covers the vast majority of the population and even reaches out to those excluded from the formal labour market.

We have shown this system currently faces an increasing financial deficit. We first strip down ANSES economic result of sources of funding that are not *de jure* allocated to the payment of social security transfers, disregard transfers from the federal budget as a source of social security funding and include benefits that are *de facto* paid for by ANSES although they are *de jure* granted by other agencies. We also estimate the opaque

cost of the 2016 historical reparation program, funded with the national Sustainability Guarantee Fund (FGS), and exclude from the computation both this program's cost and the returns of FGS investments. We find social security accounts suddenly deteriorate from a balanced budget in 2014 to a -2.5% of GDP deficit in 2017. In fact, the current legislation is not meant to be sustainable, as the 2016 historical reparation Law 27260 explicitly states a more overarching social security reform is due by 2019. This thesis thus projects social security accounts, redistributive impact and adequacy in the long run based on a temporary legislative setting that is bound to change in the short term. It is nevertheless important to show what would be the short and long-term consequences of keeping today's legislation, as it serves as a baseline for future reforms. This thesis also points out the responsibility of the 2016 and 2017 reforms on the coming social security crisis, and carries out an *ex ante* evaluation of their consequences, which should have been estimated and discussed before their actual adoption.

The second chapter of this thesis is mostly methodological. It lays out the development of our dynamic microsimulation model. It details and justifies our most relevant modelling choices, and explains the structure and functioning of our model. Starting with one wave of Argentina's Permanent Household Survey (EPH), this model simulates past plausible individual careers and projects heterogeneous individual behaviour up to 2040 on the labour-market, family and education domains while respecting input socio-demographic, legislative and macroeconomic scenarios. This turns the initial cross-section into a panel that spans the 2014-2040 period, where it becomes possible to follow how individuals develop in the socio-demographic, education and labour-market spheres. The model then simulates future social security rights, transfers and contributions, which represent the basis of social security's economic sustainability, adequacy and redistributive impact. The reiteration of this simulation with varying economic and legislative scenarios spawns various datasets where all things other than the chosen legislation and macroeconomic hypothesis are equal. This makes our projections cover a wide array of possible economic situations, and allows for a comparison of the effects of varying legislation on social security.

This chapter aims to make our social security projections as transparent as possible. Together with the code and instructions uploaded in this thesis' on-line digital repository², we look to make our social security projections reproducible, verifiable and improvable by the scientific community. Apart from its application to Argentina's social security

²We use the Zenodo digital repository service for long-term preservation of our code. The DOI link is: [10.5281/zenodo.1420273](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1420273)

system, this methodological chapter may also be of use for the dynamic microsimulation literature in general, as our modelling choices may help build or refine models for other countries and topics. Finally, the model's calibration on individual behaviour observed in Argentina's Permanent Household Survey (EPH) may be of interest for those studying labour-market transitions, the determinants of labour income and issues related to the formation and dissolution of couples. In particular, our logistic behavioural equations contribute to the question of the determinants of labour informality, and our Mincer wage equations give a measure of the negative impact of unregistered labour on earnings.

Most of this thesis results are concentrated on its third chapter. We first extrapolate our aggregate simulations of retirement, survivors and family benefits as well as of social security contributions to their actual scale as known from various administrative sources. This gives us ANSES "Bismarckian" balance: the difference between social security contributions and retirement, survivors and family benefits. This statistic shows to what extent social security contributions are enough to pay for the scheme's benefits, and thus whether a purely insurance-led social security system would be economically sustainable: the higher the Bismarckian deficit, the more external fiscal funds are needed to fund social security. Finally, we add to this Bismarckian balance non simulated ANSES expenses and revenue to know whether the social security setting in force on May 2018 is enough to fund the promised social security benefits in the future. We find the current legislation is not economically sustainable even in the immediate future. ANSES economic result falls from a balanced budget in 2014 to a measured -1.5% GDP deficit in 2017, -5.5% of GDP in 2022 and -5.8% by 2040. We show most importantly this social security crisis is directly caused by the 2016 and 2017 reforms, as without these and even with a permanent and almost unrestricted access to the generous 2014 moratorium pension, the deficit only reaches -1.6% of GDP in 2022 and -3.8% of GDP by 2040.

We also carried out exploratory projections of social security's future adequacy and redistributive impact as a by-product of our actuarial projections. We kept simple household composition simulations and excluded from the analysis the impact of the 2016 Law 27260 historical reparation plan on individual pensions. Despite that, these results suggest social security benefits would have been more adequate and would have had a higher redistributive impact both in the short and long term with the counter-factual 2015 legislation with permanent 2014 pension moratorium scenario. This decrease is mostly due to two policies. The first one is the introduction on 2016 of the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult (PUAM), only available since age 65 and permanently equal to 80% of the minimum pension. The latest 2019 budget that is currently under discussion even

seeks to bar formal workers aged 65 or more from getting access to the PUAM. It replaces the 2014 moratorium pension, which starts at that same level but after five years reaches at least 100% of the minimum pension. It is also available (although means-tested) for women aged 60 or more with no other benefits. The second one is the replacement of the 2008 Law 26417 pension mobility index, that made benefits mostly follow formal wages, with the 2017 Law 27426 indexation formula, which adjusts them by 30% on formal wages and 70% on inflation. This mostly freezes in the long term the real level of family benefits and pensions that are a function of the legal minimum (the PUAM, moratorium benefits and contributory pensioners that only qualify for the minimum pension).

We thus get the peculiar result of reforms that deteriorate social security accounts while also giving lower and more unequal benefits. As shown in our third chapter, this strong increase in the short term social security deficit comes from the de-funding of ANSES. We have computed that the combination of tax reductions (lower employers contributions and the gradual reduction of the "Check"³ tax) and of the reduced funding of ANSES with taxes usually shared between the federal and provincial governments (*coparticipable* funds) represents 4% of GDP of missing income by 2022. We moreover estimate the funding of the 2016 Law 27260 historical reparation program with the Sustainability Guarantee Fund (FGS) will decrease its value from 11% of GDP in December 2017 to 3.8%, 4.4% or 4.9% of GDP by the end of 2040 in our pessimistic, central and optimistic economic scenarios. This shows the 2016 and 2017 reforms seriously jeopardise social security accounts by mostly reducing both its flow and stock of resources.

We can thus conclude the reforms undertaken by the incumbent administration renders Argentina's social security accounts blatantly unsustainable in the very short term. If we exclude the beneficiaries of the 2016 historical reparation program, these reforms also decrease social security benefits adequacy and redistributive impact, and thus the scheme's political sustainability as well. We believe decreasing the economic and political sustainability of Argentina's social security system is an intended consequence of the 2016 and 2017 reforms. The system would face an economic and political crisis that would reduce public support to its current configuration. When we factor in the major pension reform scheduled by the historical reparation Law 27260's Art. 12 by 2019, it becomes clear these manufactured crises serve the purpose of promoting an unpopular pension reform that would strongly reduce the scope of Argentina's welfare state. This outcome is even more likely now that the government promised in its ongoing re-negotiation of the stand-

³Instituted in 2001 by Law 25413, the Tax on Credits and Debits on banks' Current Accounts is commonly known as the "Check" tax.

by agreement signed in June 2019 with the IMF it would drastically reduce Argentina's primary public deficit from an objective of 2.7% for 2018 to 0% in 2019, and start depleting the FGS. This ongoing re-negotiation may also explain why the 2019 national budget draft opts not to further decrease the "Check" tax on 2019 and seeks to bar access to the Universal Pension PUAM to formal senior workers, as both these measures contribute to reduce the public deficit.

Argentina is thus headed towards a drastic social security reform in a very unfavourable context. The country is cut off from voluntary funding by the international financial markets, it is in the midst of a currency and current-account crisis, and depends on IMF funding in order to avoid a partial or full debt default in the short term. The actual contents of this reform are open to speculation, but the budgetary leeway is dramatically short and its contents are likely to be at least partially dictated by the IMF.

The parametric pension reform recommendations made by the IMF in 2016 (Canales-Kriljenko *et al.* , 2016) all involved cutting social security spending. These included an indexation of benefits on inflation instead of wages, partially established by the 2017 Law 27426 pension mobility index (70% Consumer Price Index, 30% formal wages). If we take the rest of the recommendations in that report at face value, these would include pushing back the retirement age of women from 60 to 65 and lowering the replacement rate of new retirement pensions. They propose to decrease the replacement ratio of one year of contributions from 1.5 to 1.1 percentage points and/or decrease the minimum pension from 75 to 45 percent of the median wage. Now that the economic situation of the country has worsened, the IMF may also push for additional parametric reforms such as making access to non-contributive benefits such as the Universal Child Benefit or the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult more difficult. The latter measure has even been proposed in the draft 2019 budget. A systemic reform may also be on the books, with the reintroduction of a fully-funded pillar dedicated to the wealthier formal workers in order to complement their Pay-As-You-Go pension, whose adequacy has been reduced by the less generous 2017 pension mobility formula. This would partially reverse the 2008 private pension funds nationalisation, which the current government party resisted at the time when it was in the opposition. It even recently considered these funds had been "seized" in its letter of intention sent to the IMF the 12th of June 2018, suggesting it had been an illegal measure. All in all, the measures that are the most likely to be proposed by the current government and supported by the IMF should favour large cuts in pension and family benefits spending over higher social security funding or the reversal of tax cuts adopted on 2017.

The contents of the next structural reform are crucial, as from the current state of social security the new setting can end up in any of the conservative, liberal or social-democratic welfare worlds (Esping-Andersen, 1990). First, the universal pension and family benefits coverage can be kept for the most vulnerable, but at a low level, ensuring a universalistic, Beveridgean but modest first pillar. From there, if public contributory pensions are closely linked to past contributions and can cater to the exigences of the upper-middle classes, through for instance the introduction of complementary pension schemes such as those prevalent in France, then market mechanisms can be crowded out by public social security. In that case, Argentina's pension system would shift to the conservative-Bismarckian welfare state typology, only with the corporatist aspect of social security limited to healthcare as is currently the case since the 1993 social security reform.

If, in a different setting, the public pension system refrains from offering high contributory benefits, then a systemic reform may lead to the re-creation of private pension schemes to supplement the modest public social security benefits for those who can afford it. This would represent a shift back to the liberal welfare state, only this time Argentina's social security would have three pillars. Incidentally, it is the kind of shift that is the most likely to be endorsed by the IMF. First, a Beveridgean, universal, non-contributory but low pillar consisting on the Universal Pension for the Elderly PUAM and the Universal Child Benefit AUH. Second, a public contributory pillar consisting on limited contributive retirement and child benefits. And third, a private pillar made up of private pension funds directed to formal workers with the longest careers and the highest labour income that would like to supplement the modest benefits earned in the second pillar.

Finally, a combination of a high floor of social protection through adequate first-pillar benefits and of high contributory pension benefits granted through a public scheme (either within the second pillar or through the creation of complementary pension benefits) would push Argentina's social security system towards the "social-democratic" welfare state.

Thus, the main contribution of this work to the literature is providing transparent, although perfectible, actuarial projections of future social security funding needs to contribute to the debate on future social security reforms. The previous lack of any official actuarial projection on social security funding needs probably had political motivations, as it allowed to eschew the economic sustainability of social security from the public debate. This also forces reforms to be taken in a hurry and, in this case, amidst a dramatic social security accounts crisis. We hope that this projection tool will allow for a thorough *ex*

ante evaluation of future possible reforms on social security's long-term economic sustainability, adequacy and redistributive impact before they are actually adopted. This would help the society and policy-makers alike take an informed decision on future reforms, not only on their impact on social security accounts, but also on the livelihood of the families that receive these benefits.

This work is but a first contribution to the projection of Argentina's social security, and there is plenty of room for improvement. There are first some simplifications within this model that should be lifted. For instance, a proper fertility module that would model the decision of couples to have a child and link it for instance to their labour situation would give an added credibility to our socio-demographic simulations. Also, it could be possible to rework the education module and make educational success depend for instance on the parents' level of education or the family group's income. Moreover, a more realistic simulation of households would increase the model's individual-level realism. For instance, there should be a provision in the model that forces at least one household member to have some source of income, and thus avoid having 15% of simulated households where no dweller earns social security transfers or labour income, instead of the 3% measured in our starting dataset. Further work also needs to be done to get a better projection of future household income inequality. To this end, a strategy to simulate individual error terms in the Mincer wage equations of respondents that were not working in the initial dataset would help keep a realistic simulated level of labour income inequality. Furthermore, it would be useful to re-run the model with alternative datasets. It would of course gain much from using administrative data from ANSES beneficiaries, which would include accumulated pension rights that would thus not need to be retrospectively simulated. Apart from that, it may be interesting to re-run the simulation using as a starting dataset the Yearly Survey of Urban Households (EAHU), that covers a wider proportion of the Argentinian urban population over the 2010-2014 period. Finally, for the sake of simplicity we assumed the pension mobility Law 26417 in force between March 2009 and March 2018 adjusted benefits on formal wage evolutions, when the actual formula also factors in the evolution of ANSES fiscal sources of income, and even limits the adjustment to a percentage of total ANSES income. Taking the whole formula into account would result in more rigorous counter-factual legislative scenarios, and would gain from being implemented in future versions of this model.

Secondly, there are some features we left out of the model but that would be interesting for future social security projections. For example, an unemployment rights module would allow to simulate the impact of a reform that would reintroduce significant unemployment

benefits (today almost non-existent) on social security. Also, it would be interesting to model the impact of the 2016 historical reparation program on retirement benefits. This would nevertheless need a previous simulation of pension litigation in order to determine which pensioners decide to subscribe to this program and drop their cases against ANSES for the underpayment of their retirement pensions. Next, introducing migrations in the model would both help us reproduce the full population projections at the base of the model's demographic scenario and see how migrants are covered by social security, knowing they did not have their entire career in Argentina. It would also be interesting to adopt alternative demographic scenarios for our projections, with varying fertility and life expectancy, to see how sensible the results are to the evolution of Argentina's population. Finally, a taxation module could be introduced in the model, to see the impact of for instance the income tax or the "Check" tax on inequalities and disposable income.

Thirdly, there are some methodological limitations to our dynamic microsimulation model. It models individual behaviour following a deterministic setting, where it is the characteristics of the individual that make him or her more likely to experience a given transition. There is no maximisation strategy behind observed behaviour, so modelling the impact of policies that try to encourage a given behaviour (for instance, subscribing to the historical reparation program or pushing back the retirement decision) is not possible. Instead, we use an alignment by sorting procedure made available by LIAM2, where we assume there is a given proportion of individuals that will make a determined transition (giving birth, dying, working in the formal sector, entering in a common-law union, graduating from high school...). We pick just enough individuals among the persons that may make this transition to reproduce these exogenous proportions, and we select in priority those who are the most likely to make this transition due to their characteristics. Our model thus cannot have endogenous labour supply, income, retirement decisions that would change the aggregate proportions of, say, formal workers based on individual maximisation programs. The simulated behaviour is thus not robust to the Lucas critique, in that we cannot endogenously model the reaction of individuals to a change in legislation. The economic hypotheses input would thus gain from being estimated by a distinct macro model, which would estimate the impact on aggregate variables of policy changes. For instance, it could estimate the change in labour supply of women aged 60 to 64 if their retirement age was pushed back to 65, the impact on the demand and net remuneration of formal labour of the reduction of employers contributions established by the 2017 Law 27430, or how formal labour supply of seniors aged 65 or more with incomplete careers would change if the Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult (PUAM) becomes incompatible with formal employment as drafted in the 2019 federal budget. Also, adopting

a more complex growth model, with a transition period before reaching the long-term growth regime, varying labour shares of GDP or the introduction of capital productivity would add to the model's robustness.

Despite these limits, we believe we have provided a useful tool for the analysis of Argentina's social security system. We have addressed the vital issue of its sustainability, under different schemes, and also those of its adequacy and redistributive impact. The model we developed can be used to assess how different reform proposals perform in all these important areas. We therefore hope it will help in the design of future policies that are adopted with the short and long term economic sustainability in mind, which has seldom been the case so far. But it may also be used to evaluate the consequences of these reforms in the livelihood of those more directly concerned, which are social security beneficiaries. In the end, we view these projections as a contribution to the political debate on what is the desirable welfare state for Argentina, which is a decision the Argentinian society should take based on neutral and transparent projections, much as those done in France by the Pensions Advisory Council (COR).

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Glossaries: acronyms, terms and legislation

Acronyms

ANSES	Administración Nacional de la Seguridad Social	National Social Security Administration	National social security agency active since 1993. It works under the orbit of the Ministry of Labour, but it enjoys a financial and organisational autonomy. Includes the retirement, family benefits and unemployment branches of social security.
AFJP	Administradora de Fondos de Jubilaciones y Pensiones	Retirement and Survivors' Pension Funds Manager	Private pension funds that managed individual pension accounts in the private fully-funded pension pillar in Argentina. Created by Law 24241, these started operating in 1994. They were dissolved by the 2008 private pension funds nationalisation established by Law 26425, and their assets transferred to the FGS.
AUH	Asignación Universal por Hijo	Universal Child Benefit	Non-contributive child benefit established by Decree 1602/2009, and first paid on November 2009. Equal to the highest contributive child benefit, it is destined to the children of informal workers and the unemployed. The benefit is conditional: the children must attend a public school and follow the compulsory vaccination program.
CGN	Contaduría General de la Nación	Nation's General Accounting Agency	Official agency that tracks the execution of the national budget and the sources of funding of the different ministries and government agencies. Publishes this information each year in the Investment Account.

Acronyms

EPH	Encuesta Permanente de Hogares	Permanent Household Survey	A household survey representative of Argentina's main urban centres, spread throughout the country. It was first carried out in 1974 and witnessed various methodological changes. The last major one happened in 2003, when the survey became a rotating panel, published every quarter and that measures transitions at the quarterly and yearly steps, thus becoming the Continuous EPH (EPHc). Publicly available, it provides thorough self-reported information on the individual's socio-demographic situation, its labour state, income education, household composition and the material characteristics of the dwelling.
FGS	Fondo de Garantía de Sustentabilidad	Sustainability Guarantee Fund	National pension fund managed by ANSES. Its starting assets were the individual pension accounts managed by the AFJPs that were transferred to the public pension system, first voluntarily (in 2007, following Law 26222), then in a compulsory manner with the private pension funds nationalisation of 2008 (Law 26425). Equal to 11% of the GDP in December 2017, it will be gradually depleted to pay for the historical reparation program instituted in 2016 by Law 27260.
INDEC	Instituto Nacional de Estadísticas y Censos	National Statistics and Census Institute	Argentina's main statistical body. Provides economic, sociologic and demographic information on Argentina. It publishes among other things the Permanent Household Survey (EPH) and the National Census.
INSSJP-PAMI	Instituto Nacional de Servicios Sociales para Jubilados y Pensionados – Programa de Asistencia Médica Integral	National Institute of Social Service for Retirement and Survivors' Pensioners – Integral Medical Assistance Plan	National healthcare agency created in 1971 by Law 19032 and destined to beneficiaries of a retirement or survivors benefit. Also covers beneficiaries of the universal pension PUAM.

Acronyms

ISBIC	Índice de Salarios Básicos de la Industria y la Construcción	Base Salary Index for Industry and Construction	Monthly index computed by the Argentinian Ministry of Labour since January 1988. It gives the mean nominal base wage resulting from collective-bargaining agreements for manufacturing and construction workers. The Eliff ruling of the Nations' Supreme Court of Justice uses this index to discount income earned before March 2009 in the computation of the initial retirement benefit.
PAP	Prestación Adicional por Permanencia	Additional Permanence Prestation	Part of the contributive retirement pension. When an individual with access to the PBU claims his retirement benefit, a reference income is computed by combining the last ten years of wages and the lifelong contributions made as an independent worker. The PAP is equal to this reference income multiplied by the sum of all years contributed since July 1994 times 1,5%. The sum of the PBU, the PAP and the PC equals the contributive retirement pension, always at least equal to the minimum pension.
PBU	Prestación Básica Universal	Universal Basic Pension	A fixed sum that is part of the contributive retirement pension. Access to the PBU (and thus to the contributive retirement pension) is unlocked after 30 years of contributions, but each two months above the legal retirement age decreases this requirement by one month. The contributive pension is defined by the sum of the PBU, the PAP and the PC, and is at least equal to the minimum pension.

Acronyms

PC	Prestación Complementaria	Complementary Prestation	Part of the contributive retirement pension. When an individual with access to the PBU claims his retirement benefit, a reference income is computed by combining the last ten years of wages and the lifelong contributions made as an independent worker. The PC is equal to this reference income multiplied by the sum of all years contributed before July 1994 times 1.5%. A maximum of 35 years can be taken into account for the computation of the PC. The sum of the PBU, the PAP and the PC equals the contributive retirement pension, always at least equal to the minimum pension.
PUAM	Pensión Universal para el Adulto Mayor	Universal Pension for the Elderly Adult	Non-contributive benefit established in 2016 by the historical reparation Law 27260 equal to 80% of the minimum pension benefit. It is accessible to all people aged 65 or more that lack any other retirement or survivors' benefit, and does not generate survivors benefits upon the beneficiary's death. The draft 2019 budget law seeks to make this pension incompatible with formal labour.
RIPTE	Remuneración Imponible Promedio de los Trabajadores Estables	Mean Taxable Income of Stable Workers	Monthly gross wage index of stable formal wage-earners computed by the Argentinian Ministry of Labour since July 1994. One of its official uses is the computation of pension mobility since March 2018, following the 2017 Law 27426 pension mobility index.

Acronyms

SIJP	Sistema Integrado de Jubilaciones y Pensiones	Integrated Retirement and Survivors' Pension System	Argentina's two-pillar pension system, that consisted in a public PAYG pillar run by ANSES and a fully-funded system run by private pension funds, the AFJP. Established by the 1993 Law 24241, it was replaced by the SIPA in 2008 when private pension funds were nationalised through Law 26425.
SIPA	Sistema Integrado Previsional Argentino	Integrated Argentinian Pension System	Argentina's current pension system, run by ANSES. Replaced in 2008 the SIJP through Law 26425. It consists on a single-pillar Pay-As-You-Go Defined Benefits pension system.

Legal Glossary

Norm	Publication date	Description
Law 19032	28/05/71	Creates the INSSJP-PAMI healthcare institution for retirement and survivors pensioners. It specifies its funding, in particular contributions made by the elderly.
Law 23548	07/01/88	Defines coparticipable taxes. These are collected by the central government on behalf of the provinces. The federal government then keeps 42.34% of these funds, and distributes the remaining 54.66% between the provinces following a fixed proportion.
Law 23360	20/01/89	A reform to the formal workers health system, the "obras sociales". Establishes the current level of employers contributions destined to these health bodies.
Law 23361	20/01/89	A reform to the formal workers health system, the "obras sociales". Establishes the level of employers contributions destined to the Solidarity Redistribution Fund that helps even out resources between sectoral "obras sociales".
Law 23848	19/10/90	Creates pensions for the 1982 Malvinas war veterans, funded by the federal budget. These are paid by ANSES, and it is unclear whether the federal budget always compensated ANSES for the payment of these benefits.
Law 23928	28/03/91	The convertibility law. It most notably forbids any indexation of taxes, benefits or wages on inflation. This paved the way to the discretionary adjustment of retirement benefits with respect to inflation since April 1995 as determined by Law 24463.
Law 23966	20/08/91	Makes a proportion of fuel tariffs and of the VAT fund ANSES. Fuel tariffs were modified by Law 27430.
Law 24013	17/12/91	Creates the National Employment Fund, to which is destined part of employers contributions, and who used to pay unemployment benefits. During the 1993 reforms, the ANSES absorbed this fund, so the unemployment branch of social security is managed by ANSES.

Legal Glossary

Norm	Publication date	Description
Law 24130	22/09/92	Ratifies the Fiscal Pact between the federal and provincial governments. Among all coparticipable taxes defined by Law 23548 and shared between the state and the provinces, 15% directly fund ANSES for a limited period of time. This pact was only renewed until the 31st of December 2005, but the detraction was prolonged until 2015. After litigation by some Provinces and a Supreme Court of Justice decision in their favour, Law 27260 gradually stops this detraction since 2016, which will fully be eliminated by 2020.
Law 24195	05/05/93	The federal education law. The length of primary education increases from 7 to 9 years, which makes schooling compulsory until ages 15 or 16. This achieved almost full schooling until age 15. The last three years are the poly-modal education, and are optional. Replaced by the 2006 National Education Law 26206. Some Provinces opted to keep the old division of 7 years of basic education and 5 years of secondary education.
Law 24241	18/10/93	Unifies previous sectoral pension systems and creates the SIJP (replaced in 2008 by the SIPA). It determines the functioning of Argentina's pension system, its funding and the computation rules of its benefits.
Law 24463	30/03/95	Starting from the 31st of March 1995, pension mobility is set by the budget law and thus at the discretion of the federal government. The only restriction is that pensions cannot be nominally decreased. The discretionary adjustment of pensions remained until March 2009 and the implementation of the Law 26417 pension mobility law.
Decree 679/1995	22/05/95	Contains the computation formula for contributive retirement benefits granted through Law 24241.
Law 24476	23/11/95	Establishes a permanent pension moratorium that allows to buy back non-contributed years before 1993. Started being in effect only since the 25th of November 2005, through Decree 1454/2005 that implements Law 25865.

Legal Glossary

Norm	Publication date	Description
Law 24714	18/10/96	Unifies previous family benefits regimes and transfers them to ANSES. It is the main legal basis to Argentina's family benefits system.
Decree 649/1997	06/08/97	Implements and modifies some aspects of the Income Tax Law 20628. 20% of the Income Tax funds ANSES, although this had already been the case since 1993. It is no longer the case since January 2018, as Laws 27430 and 27432 fully coparticipate this tax between the state and the provinces.
Decree 833/1997	29/08/97	Makes the adjustment of pensions depend on the MOPRE, an index established in the federal budget law. This also affected compulsory social security contributions made in the Autonomous Workers regime. The discretionary adjustment of pensions with respect to inflation only ended on March 2009 with the pension mobility law 26417.
Law 24977	06/07/98	Creates the Simplified Regime for Small Tax-Payers, or Monotributo. Small independent workers get to pay low taxes and still get access to basic healthcare and pension coverage.
Decree 1520/1998	31/12/98	Institutes a reduction of employers contributions to the retirement system.
Law 25239	31/12/99	Makes personal contributions of Monotributistas to social security optional since April 2000. If these were not made, contributions to the monotributo only gave access to the PBU. The possibility to make these additional optional contributions was eliminated in December 2009 by Law 26565.
Law 25413	26/03/01	The competitiveness law. It introduces the Tax on Credits and Debits on banks' current accounts, commonly known as "Check" tax. It represented on average a stable 1.6% of GDP between 2002 and 2017. It was reduced by 33% since May 2018 by Decree 409/2018

Legal Glossary

Norm	Publication date	Description
Decree 814/2001	22/06/01	Modifies employers contributions: these are higher for firms of the services and trade sectors, and lower for the industrial, primary, construction and public sectors. This Decree was complemented by Laws 25453 and 25565. Law 27430 undoes this measure and gradually unifies employers contributions across economic sectors.
Law 25453	31/07/01	The zero deficit law. It complements changes in employers contributions set by Decree 814/2001.
Decree 1387/2001	02/11/01	This decree reduced to 5% of the wage employee's contributions to the fully funded system for one year and forced private pension funds to increase the share of public debt bonds in their investment portfolio.
Law 25565	21/03/02	The 2002 federal budget law. Complements changes in employers contributions introduced by Decree 814/2001.
Law 25865	19/01/04	Introduces a permanent moratorium system that allows small independent workers to buy back non-contributed years before 1993.
Law 25994	07/01/05	Opens the possibility for a large pension moratorium, where it becomes possible to buy back missing contribution years before the 31st of December 2004. It was effectively implemented by the Joint General Resolution 2091 and 579/2006. All retirement age individuals with no survivors or retirement benefit could subscribe to this benefit between 06/07/2006 and 30/04/2007.
Decree 1454/2005	07/12/05	Re-activates the pension moratorium established by Law 24476, under the repayment conditions of Law 25865. Permanently implements the possibility to buy back missing contribution years before the 30th of September 1993 since the 25th of November 2005.

Legal Glossary

Norm	Publication date	Description
Joint General Resolutions 2091 and 579/2006 Decree 1866/2006	12/07/06 15/12/06	Implemented the Law 25994 pension moratorium, granting a universal access to a pension benefit for people of retirement age between July 2006 and April 2007. Modifies the Autonomous workers regime, introducing three categories for own-account workers and two categories for independent workers that employ salaried workers. The non actualisation of means conditions to enter these categories means there are today <i>de facto</i> only one category for own-account workers and another one for those who employ other workers.
Law 26206	28/12/06	The National Education Law repeals the Federal Education Law 24195. Provinces may opt to keep the old division of 7 years of basic and 5 years of secondary school, or adopt an even 6 years split. Education becomes compulsory until age 18 and the completion of high school.
Law 26222	08/03/07	Opens the possibility for contributors to the fully-funded pension pillar to opt for the public Pay-As-You-Go pillar. The government subsidises private pensions to make them reach at least the legal minimum. Senior workers of the private pillar who have too few contributions to eventually get the minimum pension are automatically transferred to the public pillar.
Decree 897/2007	13/07/07	Creates the FGS, that will receive the private pension accounts of individuals that move from the private to the public pension pillar. States this fund will be managed by ANSES.
Law 26417	16/10/08	Adjusts every six months pensions with a mobility index that combines nominal wage and ANSES fiscal income evolutions. At first limited to retirement and survivor's benefits, this indexation was later extended to family benefits levels (March 2016) and means-tests (March 2017). This mobility index was applied between March 2009 and September 2017. Since March 2018, it is the Law 27426 index that is in force.

Legal Glossary

Norm	Publication date	Description
Law 26425	09/12/08	The private pensions nationalisation law. It eliminates the two-pillar pension system (the SLJP) and replaces it by a single-pillar Pay-As-You-Go pension system run by ANSES (the SIPA). All the contributors and pensioners of the fully-funded pillar are transferred to ANSES. Their individual pension accounts are managed by the FGS national pension fund. The counterpart is ANSES recognises all contributions made to the private pillar as if they had been done to the public PAYG system.
Decree 1602/2009	30/10/09	Creates the non contributive AUH family benefit. Its cost is supported by ANSES, but it is also possible to use the returns of FGS investments to pay for the benefit.
Decree 1668/2012	13/09/12	Family benefits of national civil servants are paid by ANSES. They are still funded by the federal budget.
Decree 84/2014	27/01/14	Creates the PROGRESAR benefit, a scholarship to encourage people aged 18 to 25 to carry on or resume their education in public institutions. It was paid by ANSES but funded by the federal budget. The benefit was not nominally increased throughout 2016 and 2017. Decree 90/2018 of 31/01/2018 transfers the program to the Ministry of Education, and ties access to this benefit to academic results.
Law 26970	10/09/14	This law establishes a temporary pension moratorium accessible to individuals of retirement age that do not have other retirement or survivors benefits. It was open for men from September 2014 to September 2016. Its validity was extended for women until July 2019 by Law 27260. Subscribers may buy back non-contributed years up to the 31st of December 2003 to reach the required minimum contribution years. The payment is done during 5 years through a discount in the benefit, which can reach a minimum of 80% of the minimum pension. After five years, the pensions regain their full value, which means they are at least equal to 100% of the minimum pension.

Legal Glossary

Norm	Publication date	Description
Law 27160	17/07/15	This law establishes family benefits levels are indexed to the pension mobility formula. So are means-test to receive a given contributory family benefit. The first indexation took place on March 2016. The maximum household income above which no child benefits are paid was however linked to the changes in non-taxable income levels in the Income Tax. Decree 702/2018 issued 26/07/2018 changed this and links it to the maximum income that can be taken into account to pay social security contributions, following Law 24241. This indexes family benefits income cap on pension mobility.
Law 27204	11/11/15	Completing high school gives the right to enter a public university, and any degree it proposes.
Decree 593/2016	19/04/16	Extends family benefits to the children of some categories of small independent contributors (<i>monotributistas</i>) starting from May 2016.
Decree 807/2016	28/06/16	For the computation of the reference income that determines the initial contributive retirement benefit, past income is discounted following various wage indices up to March 2009. Benefits earned after that date are discounted following the pension mobility index. In force since August 2016.
Law 27260	22/07/16	The historical reparation law for retirement and survivors pensioners. Creates the PUAM, extends the validity of the 2014 pension moratorium for women, gradually stops the detraction of 15% of coparticipable income in favour of ANSES, fully eliminated by 2020. Introduces the historical reparation program, which consists in a voluntary payment plan that partially compensates pensioners for the under-payment of their pensions, on the condition they drop all lawsuits against ANSES. Funds this program through a fiscal amnesty and FGS funds. States additional overarching social security reforms must be carried out by 2019.
Law 27346	27/12/16	Introduces a reform of the <i>monotributo</i> regime. Social security contributions now differ from one <i>monotributo</i> category to the other.

Legal Glossary

Norm	Publication date	Description
Law 27426	28/12/17	Introduces a new pension mobility law, where ANSES benefits are indexed on 70% of the Consumer Price Index and 30% of the RIPTE index. Also pushed back to 70 the age at which an employer may force his or her employee to retire.
Law 27430	29/12/17	Unifies employers contribution rates throughout economic sectors, and states the first 12,000 constant January 2018 pesos of a given wage are not subject to employers contributions. Changes the fuel tariffs partially destined to ANSES. Adjusts <i>monotributo</i> categories and contributions following the pension mobility index.
Law 27432	29/12/17	Specifies ANSES fiscal sources of income. The Income tax is fully coparticipated, and stops funding ANSES. The full Law 25413 "Check" tax funds ANSES, but the government may decrease it by 20% every year until fully eliminating it as early as 2022. Other taxes that partially fund ANSES are: the net VAT (93.73% of 11%), the emergency tax on cigarettes (100%), the fiscal(70%) and provisional (100%) components of the monotributo, and various fuel tariffs.
Decree 409/2018	07/05/18	33% of the "Check" tax instituted by Law 25413 counts instead for the payment of the Income Tax. This effectively reduces the "Check" tax by 33%.

Adequacy

The adequacy of social security benefits depends on three main variables. First, how well these are enough to meet the beneficiary's needs, so the real level of these benefits as related to the beneficiaries consumption needs. Second, coverage also enters in the equation: the more benefits are accessible to those who need them (the dependent population), the more they are adequate. Third, in the case of Bismarckian social security benefits, the percentage of previous wages these social security benefits represent is also important, separately from the question of their real level: a high replacement ratio means these benefits are more adequate.

Beveridgean

Beveridgean aspects of social security follow a universalistic logic: all citizens get the same rights to social protection, regardless of their past contributions. As a consequence, these benefits are funded through general taxation. They usually complement Bismarckian aspects of social security: individuals with no access to a Bismarckian (contributive) benefit get access to a Beveridgean (non-contributive) benefit, sometimes after passing a means-test.

Bismarckian

Social security benefits are referred to as Bismarckian when they follow an insurance logic. Access to them depends on past contributions and they seek to replace a proportion of missing labour income when the beneficiary is out of the labour market (illness, old-age, unemployment). The levels of these benefits are thus closely linked to past labour income.

Check tax

Tax on Credits and Debits on banks' current accounts, usually referred to as tax on checks. It was established in 2001 by Law 25453. This tax completely funds ANSES following Law 27432, but this same law states its level can be reduced by up to 20% each year until being eliminated as early as 2022. Decree 409/2018 reduced on May 2018 this tax by 33%.

Coparticipable taxes (coparticipate)

Various taxes that are collected by the AFIP on behalf of the provincial and federal governments. Some deductions can be made from coparticipable taxes, the most important example being the 15% of coparticipable taxes that used to fund ANSES before the 2016 historical reparation Law 27260. What remains is then distributed (or coparticipated) between the central and provincial governments following the proportions defined by Law 23548.

Glossary of terms

- Defined Benefits (DB)** A pension system has Defined Benefits when past contributions give way to a future defined level of pensions. This future level becomes an acquired social security right of the pensioner, and changing it may give way to pension litigation. The value of past contributions may change between the time these were made and actual retirement, but once retired, benefits can only be changed following general pension mobility.
- Defined Contributions (DC)** A pension system has Defined Contributions when the future pension level is not guaranteed. Even after claiming retirement rights, the real level of pensions can change depending on the economic and financial conjuncture. Most fully-funded pension systems are Defined Contributions, as pensions are paid from individual accounts that are invested in financial markets by pension managers. Thus, the level of these pensions is subject to financial market risk. PAYG pension systems can however have a DC scheme as well as in Sweden's notional account system.
- Figurative contributions** When a public agency receives transfers that come from other public agencies or from federal or provincial governments, these are considered figurative contributions. These contributions are often not *de jure* established as permanent: they seek to compensate the agency's figurative expenses or an operational deficit.
- Figurative expenses** When a public agency carries out expenditure on behalf of other agencies, these are considered as figurative expenses. This expenditure is not *de jure* pre-established in the agency's legislative framework. As such, it is not this agency that ought to fund this expenditure, so normally it receives figurative contributions as a counterpart.
- Fully-funded pension system** A pension system where individual contributions feed an individual account managed (and reinvested) by private pension funds. Upon retirement, the beneficiary earns a pension that depends on the current value of accumulated funds. Since these are reinvested in financial markets, pension levels are exposed to financial risks.

Glossary of terms

Informal, unregistered work

There are two main definitions of informal or unregistered work. A sectoral definition considers as informal all workers that belong to the informal sector. This sector consists on small firms, own-account workers or small farmers that have low productivity and employ unqualified labour. A second, legalistic definition states informal workers are those that are not registered in social security: they don't pay social security contributions and are thus not covered by Bismarckian social security benefits. In this work, we use the legalistic definition of labour informality for wage-earners and to determine independent workers contributions. We also use the sectoral definition of labour informality to study the behaviour of independent workers of the formal sector.

Microsimulation

A simulation methodology that uses as an initial dataset a cross-section of heterogeneous individual units. Each individual unit's behaviour and characteristics is then modified, usually independently from one another, and following either transition probabilities, behavioural equations or a maximisation program. Static microsimulation models eschew time from the analysis and are mostly used to model the impact of a policy (such as tax changes) on the starting dataset. Dynamic microsimulation models turn the initial cross-section into a panel dataset by simulating the future behaviour, changes and entries or exits of individual units from the starting dataset over a period of time.

Moratorium pensions

Retirement benefits that are accessible after the beneficiary enters a moratorium plan to buy back his or her missing contribution years. These non-contributed years are considered as the individual's debt to social security, that needs to be repaid on various instalments (after substantial cuts on the debt's capital). Subscription begins after paying the first instalment, and future payments are directly deduced from retirement benefits. The 2006 pension moratoriums established constant instalments in nominal terms, that quickly became negligible due to double digit inflation figures. The 2014 Law 26970 pension moratorium indexed these instalments on pension mobility, but these were paid only during five years and could not reduce the benefit below 80% of the minimum pension.

Pay-As-You-Go (PAYG) pension systems

A system where today's contributions are used to pay for today's retirement pensions. In return, the contributor accumulates rights to a pension that are related to past contributions.

Glossary of terms

Sustainability

A social security scheme is sustainable when its current rules can be maintained in the foreseeable future. This includes both social security expenditure and sources of funding. Economic sustainability means the sources of income established today will be enough to pay for the benefits in the future without changing their computation rules. Political sustainability means the current social security scheme enjoys from a broad enough consensus and a sufficient adequacy and redistributive impact that makes it plausible it will be maintained in the long run. A social security setting that would excessively lower the adequacy of social security benefits would thus be economically, but not politically sustainable.

Leonardo CALCAGNO

Le système de sécurité sociale argentin: un modèle de microsimulation dynamique pour projeter sa soutenabilité, son adéquation et son impact redistributif

Résumé :

Le principal organisme argentin de retraites et d'allocations familiales, l'Administration Nationale de Sécurité Sociale (ANSES), ne projette pas ses besoins de financement futurs. Nous proposons ici le premier modèle de microsimulation dynamique qui projette la soutenabilité de ce système, et le deuxième modèle de son genre appliqué à un pays en développement. Il permet aussi d'évaluer l'impact des réformes adoptées en 2016 et 2017 sur le système de sécurité sociale. D'abord, le Chapitre 1 détaille la législation argentine en matière de sécurité sociale, estime le déficit de 2017 à -1.5% du PIB, et étudie les bases de données nécessaires au développement de notre modèle. Ensuite, nous développons notre modèle dans le Chapitre 2. Nous recréons des carrières individuelles plausibles pour les individus de notre base de départ, et simulons leurs comportements futurs ayant trait au travail, à la famille et à l'éducation, ce qui crée un panel qui englobe la période 2014-2040. Nous en déduisons dans le Chapitre 3 nos résultats. Nos projections anticipent un déficit de la sécurité sociale de -5.5% du PIB d'ici 2022, qui devrait se stabiliser ensuite à ce niveau jusqu'en 2040. C'est une conséquence des réformes de 2016 et de 2017, qui réduisent les taxes allouées à ANSES et baissent des impôts et cotisations sociales. Sans ces réformes et en gardant un minimum retraite universel, non seulement l'adéquation et la redistribution induite par la sécurité sociale auraient été plus grandes, mais nous projetons également un déficit moins important entre 2014 et 2040. Ceci suggère que les réformes de 2016 et 2017 cherchaient à réduire la soutenabilité économique et politique du système, afin de favoriser une réforme plus ambitieuse prévue d'ici 2019.

Mots clés : Retraites, Sécurité Sociale, Microsimulation, Travail, Démographie, Argentine, Évaluation de politiques publiques, Finances publiques, Comptes Publics

Argentina's social security system: a dynamic microsimulation model for projecting its sustainability, adequacy and redistributive impact

Abstract :

Argentina's main retirement and family benefits body, the National Social Security Administration (ANSES), lacks actuarial projections on its economic sustainability. This dissertation proposes the first dynamic microsimulation model that projects this system's future financing needs up to the 2040 horizon, and is the second of its kind developed for a developing country. It also evaluates the impact of the reforms adopted in 2016 and 2017 in social security's sustainability, adequacy and redistributive impact. Firstly, we review in Chapter 1 Argentina's social security legislation, estimate social security's deficit at -1.5% of GDP by 2017, and study the datasets relevant for the development of our model. Secondly, we develop our model in Chapter 2. We model past plausible careers and simulate individual behaviour in the labour-market, family and education spheres to turn the initial cross-section into a panel that spans the 2014-2040 period. We draw our results from this panel in Chapter 3. We project a social security deficit of -5.5% of GDP by 2022 that should stabilise at that level until 2040. The 2016 and 2017 will cause this deficit by reducing taxes allocated to ANSES and cutting taxes and social contributions. We show 2015 legislation with a universal access to a minimal retirement pension would have been more adequate and resulted in lower income inequality while also resulting in a lower deficit throughout the 2014-2040 period. This suggests the 2016 and 2017 reforms intentionally reduced the system's economic and political sustainability to pave the way for a more overarching reform scheduled by 2019.

Keywords : Retirement pensions, Social Security, Microsimulation, Labour, Demographics, Argentina, Public Policy Evaluation, Public Finances, National Accounts

Laboratoire d'Économie d'Orléans UMR7322
Rue de Blois - BP 26739
45067 ORLEANS Cedex 2

